

Sequential Pythagorean Triples and Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares

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Abstract

The **Pythagoras theorem** is very famous in the literature of mathematics. It led us to many Pythagorean triples. In this work we have considered all possible Pythagorean triples between 3 to 1000 and generated magic squares, where the sum of entries is a **perfect square**. The Pythagorean triples are considered in sequential form from number 3 onwards. Fortunately, we have Pythagorean triples for all numbers except number 4. In total we have 5803 triples. These triples generate 2172 magic squares. These magic squares are written with possible entries. In the second part of the work these magic squares are analysed according to their orders, and found interesting relations with Pythagorean triples. Also, it is observed that there is always a triple with the first element as an even number generating a magic square. These magic squares are written in last section of the work.

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1 Introduction

The author worked with Pythagorean triples and magic squares in different situations. In this work our aim is to analyse all possible Pythagorean triples between 3 to 1000 and generate magic squares with sum of all entries a **perfect square**. We found in total 5803 triples and out of them 2172 magic squares are generated. This work is done in Section 2. In Section 3, generated magic squares are analysed and found very interesting similarities. For each even number, from 8 onward, there is at least one triple that always generate magic square with perfect square sum of entries. A formula to generate magic square from Pythagorean triples can be seen in author's previous works [3, 11]. As a consequence of study in Section 3 below is a general formula relating Pythagorean triples and magic squares.

Result 1.1. A general formula relating Pythagorean triples and magic squares given by

$$F(n, k) := \left(n(2k + n), 2k(k + n), 2k(k + n) + n^2 \right), k \in \mathbf{N}_+, \quad (1)$$

where n is the order of a magic square and k is the gap between two consecutive triples of first term. The right side of the function $F(n, k)$ is written in terms of a Pythagorean triples, i.e., (a, b, c) .

The entries of magic squares are given by

$$E_1(n, k) := \left\{ 4k(k + n) + 1, 4k(k + n) + 3, \dots, 4k(k + n) + 2n^2 - 3, 4k(k + n) + 2n^2 - 1 \right\};$$

$$E_2(n, k) := \left\{ 4k(k + n) + \frac{n^2 + 1}{2}, 4k(k + n) + \frac{n^2 + 3}{2}, \dots, 4k(k + n) + \frac{3(n^2 - 1)}{2}, 4k(k + n) + \frac{3n^2 - 1}{2} \right\}.$$

The entries $E_1(n, k)$ are for all order magic squares resulting in **consecutive odd numbers**. The entries $E_2(n, k)$ are only for **odd order magic squares** resulting in **consecutive natural numbers**. In this case, the sum of entries is the same in both the situations. In view of this, there is a **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle n, n^2, n^3, n^4 \rangle$, where

$n \rightarrow$ order of magic square;

$n^2 \rightarrow$ total entries;

$n^3 \rightarrow$ sum of magic square;

$n^4 \rightarrow$ sum of total entries.

As a consequence of results studied in Sections 4 and 5, we have following observations:

Remark 1. (i) For the triple with first member. i.e, when a is even number, it generates magic squares of even or odd orders, and when it is of odd number, it always generates magic squares of odd orders.

(ii) *Magic squares of odd orders can be obtained from odd numbers or natural numbers having the same magic sum. While in case of even order magic squares, the entries are always odd numbers.*

(iii) *There is always a triple with a as even number generating a magic square.*

2 Part I: Pythagorean Triples and Magic Squares

This section brings patterns in Pythagorean triples in a sequential way, i.e., from 3 to 1000. In some cases, based on Pythagorean triples, magic squares are generated with perfect square sum of entries. The formula to generate the magic squares is already given in author's another works [3, 11]. We brought, Pythagorean triples for all the numbers from 3 to 1000, except for number 4. In all the case, there is no repetition of Pythagorean triples. The sequential counting refers to first member of the triple, (a, b, c) , where $a < b < c$ and $a \in 3 \leq a \leq 1000 - \{4\}$.

2.1 Pythagorean Triples: 3 to 100

■ Numbers 3, 5, 6 and 7

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$3^2 + 4^2 := 5^2$$

$$5^2 + 12^2 := 13^2$$

$$6^2 + 8^2 := 10^2$$

$$7^2 + 24^2 := 25^2$$

Remark 2. *We don't have any triple with $a = 4$. The triple $(3, 4, 5)$ is with 4 as in the middle. The following numbers give all the triples from 8 to 1000. Moreover, the first magic square generated by the triple $(8, 15, 17)$. See below.*

■ Number 8

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$8^2 + 15^2 := 17^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **$(8, 15, 17)$** $\Rightarrow 17 - 8 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 75$, $T_9 := 15^2$, $E := \{17, 19, \dots, 31, 33\}$
or $E := \{21, 22, \dots, 28, 29\}$

■ Number 9

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$9^2 + 12^2 := 15^2$$

$$9^2 + 40^2 := 41^2$$

■ Number 10

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$10^2 + 24^2 := 26^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(10, 24, 26)** $\Rightarrow 26 - 10 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 144$, $T_{16} := 24^2$, $E := \{21, 23, \dots, 49, 51\}$

■ Number 11

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$11^2 + 60^2 := 61^2$$

■ Number 12

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$12^2 + 16^2 := 20^2$$

$$12^2 + 35^2 := 37^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(12, 35, 37)** $\Rightarrow 37 - 12 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 245$, $T_{25} := 35^2$, $E := \{25, 27, \dots, 71, 73\}$
or $E := \{37, 38, \dots, 60, 61\}$

■ Number 13

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$13^2 + 84^2 := 85^2$$

■ Number 14

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$14^2 + 48^2 := 50^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(14, 48, 50)** $\Rightarrow 50 - 14 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 384$, $T_{36} := 48^2$, $E := \{29, 31, \dots, 97, 99\}$

■ Number 15

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$15^2 + 20^2 := 25^2$$

$$15^2 + 36^2 := 39^2$$

$$15^2 + 112^2 := 113^2$$

■ Number 16

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$16^2 + 30^2 := 34^2$$

$$16^2 + 63^2 := 65^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(16, 63, 65)** $\Rightarrow 65 - 16 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 567$, $T_{49} := 63^2$, $E := \{33, 35, \dots, 127, 129\}$
or $E := \{57, 58, \dots, 104, 105\}$

■ Number 17

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$17^2 + 144^2 := 145^2$$

■ Number 18

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$18^2 + 24^2 := 30^2$$

$$18^2 + 80^2 := 82^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(18, 80, 82)** $\Rightarrow 82 - 18 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 800$, $T_{64} := 80^2$, $E := \{37, 39, \dots, 161, 163\}$

■ Number 19

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$19^2 + 180^2 := 181^2$$

■ Number 20

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$20^2 + 21^2 := 29^2$$

$$20^2 + 48^2 := 52^2$$

$$20^2 + 99^2 := 101^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(20, 21, 29)** $\Rightarrow 29 - 20 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 147$, $T_9 := 21^2$, $E := \{41, 43, \dots, 55, 57\}$
or $E := \{45, 46, \dots, 52, 53\}$
2. **(20, 99, 101)** $\Rightarrow 101 - 20 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 1089$, $T_{81} := 99^2$, $E := \{41, 43, \dots, 199, 201\}$
or $E := \{81, 82, \dots, 160, 161\}$

■ Number 21

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$21^2 + 28^2 := 35^2$$

$$21^2 + 72^2 := 75^2$$

$$21^2 + 220^2 := 221^2$$

■ Number 22

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$22^2 + 120^2 := 122^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(22, 120, 122)** $\Rightarrow 122 - 22 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 1440$, $T_{100} := 120^2$, $E := \{45, 47, \dots, 241, 243\}$

■ Number 23

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$23^2 + 264^2 := 265^2$$

■ Number 24

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$24^2 + 32^2 := 40^2$$

$$24^2 + 45^2 := 51^2$$

$$24^2 + 70^2 := 74^2$$

$$24^2 + 143^2 := 145^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(24, 32, 40)** $\Rightarrow 40 - 24 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 256$, $T_{16} := 32^2$, $E := \{49, 51, \dots, 77, 79\}$
2. **(24, 143, 145)** $\Rightarrow 145 - 24 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 1859$, $T_{121} := 143^2$, $E := \{49, 51, \dots, 287, 289\}$
or $E := \{109, 110, \dots, 228, 229\}$

■ Number 25

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$25^2 + 60^2 := 65^2$$

$$25^2 + 312^2 := 313^2$$

■ Number 26

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$26^2 + 168^2 := 170^2$$

■ Number 27

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$27^2 + 36^2 := 45^2$$

$$27^2 + 120^2 := 123^2$$

$$27^2 + 364^2 := 365^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(27, 36, 45)** $\Rightarrow 45 - 36 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 243$, $T_9 := 27^2$, $E := \{73, 75, \dots, 87, 89\}$
or $E := \{77, 78, \dots, 84, 85\}$

■ Number 28

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$28^2 + 45^2 := 53^2$$

$$28^2 + 96^2 := 100^2$$

$$28^2 + 195^2 := 197^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(28, 45, 53)** $\Rightarrow 53 - 28 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 405$, $T_{25} := 45^2$, $E := \{57, 59, \dots, 103, 105\}$
or $E := \{69, 70, \dots, 92, 93\}$
2. **(28, 195, 197)** $\Rightarrow 197 - 28 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 2925$, $T_{169} := 195^2$, $E := \{57, 59, \dots, 391, 393\}$
or $E := \{141, 142, \dots, 308, 309\}$

■ Number 29

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$29^2 + 420^2 := 421^2$$

■ Number 30

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$30^2 + 40^2 := 50^2$$

$$30^2 + 72^2 := 78^2$$

$$30^2 + 224^2 := 226^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(30, 224, 226)** $\Rightarrow 226 - 30 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 3584$, $T_{196} := 224^2$, $E := \{61, 63, \dots, 449, 451\}$

■ Number 31

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$31^2 + 480^2 := 481^2$$

■ Number 32

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$32^2 + 60^2 := 68^2$$

$$32^2 + 126^2 := 130^2$$

$$32^2 + 255^2 := 257^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(32, 60, 68)** $\Rightarrow 68 - 32 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 600$, $T_{36} := 60^2$, $E := \{65, 67, \dots, 133, 135\}$
2. **(32, 255, 257)** $\Rightarrow 257 - 32 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 4335$, $T_{225} := 255^2$, $E := \{65, 67, \dots, 511, 513\}$
or $E := \{177, 178, \dots, 400, 401\}$

■ Number 33

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$33^2 + 44^2 := 55^2$$

$$33^2 + 56^2 := 65^2$$

$$33^2 + 180^2 := 183^2$$

$$33^2 + 544^2 := 545^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(33, 56, 65)** $\Rightarrow 65 - 56 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 363$, $T_9 := 33^2$, $E := \{113, 115, \dots, 127, 129\}$
or $E := \{117, 118, \dots, 124, 125\}$

■ Number 34

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$34^2 + 288^2 := 290^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(34, 288, 290)** $\Rightarrow 290 - 34 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 5184$, $T_{256} := 288^2$, $E := \{69, 71, \dots, 577, 579\}$

■ Number 35

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$35^2 + 84^2 := 91^2$$

$$35^2 + 120^2 := 125^2$$

$$35^2 + 612^2 := 613^2$$

■ Number 36

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$36^2 + 48^2 := 60^2$$

$$36^2 + 77^2 := 85^2$$

$$36^2 + 105^2 := 111^2$$

$$36^2 + 160^2 := 164^2$$

$$36^2 + 323^2 := 325^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(36, 77, 85)** $\Rightarrow 85 - 36 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 847$, $T_{49} := 77^2$, $E := \{73, 75, \dots, 167, 169\}$
or $E := \{97, 98, \dots, 144, 145\}$
2. **(36, 323, 325)** $\Rightarrow 325 - 36 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 6137$, $T_{289} := 323^2$, $E := \{73, 75, \dots, 647, 649\}$
or $E := \{217, 218, \dots, 504, 505\}$

■ Number 37

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$37^2 + 684^2 := 685^2$$

■ Number 38

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$38^2 + 360^2 := 362^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(38, 360, 362)** $\Rightarrow 362 - 38 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 7200$, $T_{324} := 360^2$, $E := \{77, 79, \dots, 721, 723\}$

■ Number 39

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$39^2 + 52^2 := 65^2$$

$$39^2 + 80^2 := 89^2$$

$$39^2 + 252^2 := 255^2$$

$$39^2 + 760^2 := 761^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(39, 80, 89)** $\Rightarrow 89 - 80 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 507$, $T_9 := 39^2$, $E := \{161, 163, \dots, 175, 177\}$
or $E := \{165, 166, \dots, 172, 173\}$

■ Number 40

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$40^2 + 42^2 := 58^2$$

$$40^2 + 75^2 := 85^2$$

$$40^2 + 96^2 := 104^2$$

$$40^2 + 198^2 := 202^2$$

$$40^2 + 399^2 := 401^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

According to Results 3.1 and ??, below are a generating magic squares with entries sum a **perfect square**. See below:

1. **(40, 42, 58)** $\Rightarrow 58 - 42 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 400$, $T_{16} := 40^2$, $E := \{85, 87, \dots, 113, 115\}$
2. **(40, 96, 104)** $\Rightarrow 104 - 40 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 1152$, $T_{64} := 96^2$, $E := \{81, 83, \dots, 205, 207\}$
3. **(40, 399, 401)** $\Rightarrow 401 - 40 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 8379$, $T_{361} := 399^2$, $E := \{81, 83, \dots, 799, 801\}$
or $E := \{261, 262, \dots, 620, 621\}$

■ Number 41

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$41^2 + 840^2 := 841^2$$

■ Number 42

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$42^2 + 56^2 := 70^2$$

$$42^2 + 144^2 := 150^2$$

$$42^2 + 440^2 := 442^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(42, 440, 442)** $\Rightarrow 442 - 42 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 9680$, $T_{400} := 440^2$, $E := \{85, 87, \dots, 881, 883\}$

■ Number 43

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$43^2 + 924^2 := 925^2$$

■ Number 44

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$44^2 + 117^2 := 125^2$$

$$44^2 + 240^2 := 244^2$$

$$44^2 + 483^2 := 485^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

Some of the above triples generate magic squares with perfect square entries sum. See below:

1. **(44, 117, 125)** $\Rightarrow 125 - 44 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 1521$, $T_{81} := 117^2$, $E := \{89, 91, \dots, 247, 249\}$
or $E := \{129, 130, \dots, 208, 209\}$

2. **(44, 483, 485)** $\Rightarrow 485 - 44 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 11109$, $T_{441} := 483^2$, $E := \{89, 91, \dots, 967, 969\}$
or $E := \{309, 310, \dots, 748, 749\}$

■ Number 45

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$45^2 + 60^2 := 75^2$$

$$45^2 + 108^2 := 117^2$$

$$45^2 + 200^2 := 205^2$$

$$45^2 + 336^2 := 339^2$$

$$45^2 + 1012^2 := 1013^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(45, 108, 117)** $\Rightarrow 117 - 108 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 675$, $T_9 := 45^2$, $E := \{217, 219, \dots, 231, 233\}$
or $E := \{221, 222, \dots, 228, 229\}$

■ Number 46

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$46^2 + 528^2 := 530^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(46, 528, 530)** $\Rightarrow 530 - 46 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 12672$, $T_{484} := 528^2$, $E := \{93, 95, \dots, 1057, 1059\}$

■ Number 47

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$47^2 + 1104^2 := 1105^2$$

■ Number 48

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$48^2 + 55^2 := 73^2$$

$$48^2 + 64^2 := 80^2$$

$$48^2 + 90^2 := 102^2$$

$$48^2 + 140^2 := 148^2$$

$$48^2 + 189^2 := 195^2$$

$$48^2 + 286^2 := 290^2$$

$$48^2 + 575^2 := 577^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

Some of the above triples generate magic squares with perfect square entries sum. See below:

1. **(48, 64, 80)** $\Rightarrow 80 - 64 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 576$, $T_{16} := 48^2$,
 $E := \{129, 131, \dots, 157, 159\}$
2. **(48, 55, 73)** $\Rightarrow 73 - 48 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 605$, $T_{25} := 55^2$,
 $E := \{97, 99, \dots, 143, 145\}$ or $E := \{109, 110, \dots, 132, 133\}$
3. **(48, 140, 148)** $\Rightarrow 148 - 48 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 1960$, $T_{100} := 140^2$,
 $E := \{97, 99, \dots, 293, 295\}$
4. **(48, 575, 577)** $\Rightarrow 577 - 48 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 14375$, $T_{529} := 575^2$,
 $E := \{97, 99, \dots, 1151, 1153\}$ or $E := \{361, 362, \dots, 888, 889\}$

■ Number 49

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$49^2 + 168^2 := 175^2$$

$$49^2 + 1200^2 := 1201^2$$

■ Number 50

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$50^2 + 120^2 := 130^2$$

$$50^2 + 624^2 := 626^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(50, 624, 626)** $\Rightarrow 626 - 50 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 16224$, $T_{576} := 624^2$,
 $E := \{101, 103, \dots, 1249, 1251\}$

■ Number 51

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$51^2 + 68^2 := 85^2$$

$$51^2 + 140^2 := 149^2$$

$$51^2 + 432^2 := 435^2$$

$$51^2 + 1300^2 := 1301^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(51, 140, 149)** $\Rightarrow 149 - 140 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 867$, $T_9 := 51^2$,
 $E := \{281, 283, \dots, 295, 297\}$ or $E := \{285, 286, \dots, 292, 293\}$

■ Number 52

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$52^2 + 165^2 := 173^2$$

$$52^2 + 336^2 := 340^2$$

$$52^2 + 675^2 := 677^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(52, 165, 173)** $\Rightarrow 173 - 52 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 2475$, $T_{121} := 165^2$,
 $E := \{105, 107, \dots, 343, 345\}$ or $E := \{165, 166, \dots, 284, 285\}$
2. **(52, 675, 677)** $\Rightarrow 677 - 52 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 18225$, $T_{625} := 675^2$,
 $E := \{105, 107, \dots, 1351, 1353\}$ or $E := \{417, 418, \dots, 1040, 1041\}$

■ Number 53

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$53^2 + 1404^2 := 1405^2$$

■ Number 54

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$54^2 + 72^2 := 90^2$$

$$54^2 + 728^2 := 730^2$$

$$54^2 + 240^2 := 246^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(54, 72, 90)** $\Rightarrow 90 - 54 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 864$, $T_{36} := 72^2$,
 $E := \{109, 111, \dots, 177, 179\}$
2. **(54, 728, 730)** $\Rightarrow 730 - 54 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 20384$, $T_{676} := 728^2$,
 $E := \{109, 111, \dots, 1457, 1459\}$

■ Number 55

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned}55^2 + 132^2 &:= 143^2 \\55^2 + 300^2 &:= 305^2 \\55^2 + 1512^2 &:= 1513^2\end{aligned}$$

■ Number 56

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned}56^2 + 90^2 &:= 106^2 & 56^2 + 390^2 &:= 394^2 \\56^2 + 105^2 &:= 119^2 & 56^2 + 783^2 &:= 785^2 \\56^2 + 192^2 &:= 200^2\end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(56, 90, 106)** $\Rightarrow 106 - 90 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 784$, $T_{16} := 56^2$,
 $E := \{181, 183, \dots, 209, 211\}$
2. **(56, 192, 200)** $\Rightarrow 200 - 56 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 3072$, $T_{144} := 192^2$,
 $E := \{113, 115, \dots, 397, 399\}$
3. **(56, 783, 785)** $\Rightarrow 785 - 56 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 22707$, $T_{729} := 783^2$,
 $E := \{113, 115, \dots, 1567, 1569\}$ or $E := \{477, 478, \dots, 1204, 1205\}$

■ Number 57

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$57^2 + 76^2 := 95^2$$

$$57^2 + 176^2 := 185^2$$

$$57^2 + 540^2 := 543^2$$

$$57^2 + 1624^2 := 1625^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(57, 176, 185)** $\Rightarrow 185 - 176 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 1083$, $T_9 := 57^2$,
 $E := \{353, 355, \dots, 367, 369\}$ or $E := \{357, 358, \dots, 364, 365\}$

■ Number 58

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$58^2 + 840^2 := 842^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(58, 840, 842)** $\Rightarrow 842 - 58 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 25200$, $T_{784} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{117, 119, \dots, 1681, 1683\}$

■ Number 59

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$59^2 + 1740^2 := 1741^2$$

■ Number 60

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$60^2 + 63^2 := 87^2$$

$$60^2 + 80^2 := 100^2$$

$$60^2 + 91^2 := 109^2$$

$$60^2 + 144^2 := 156^2$$

$$60^2 + 175^2 := 185^2$$

$$60^2 + 221^2 := 229^2$$

$$60^2 + 297^2 := 303^2$$

$$60^2 + 448^2 := 452^2$$

$$60^2 + 899^2 := 901^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

Some of the above triples generate magic squares with perfect square entries sum. See below:

1. **(60, 91, 109)** $\Rightarrow 109 - 60 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 1183$, $T_{49} := 91^2$,
 $E := \{121, 123, \dots, 215, 217\}$ or $E := \{145, 146, \dots, 192, 193\}$

2. **(60, 221, 229)** $\Rightarrow 229 - 60 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 3757$, $T_{169} := 221^2$,
 $E := \{121, 123, \dots, 455, 457\}$ or $E := \{205, 206, \dots, 372, 373\}$
3. **(60, 899, 901)** $\Rightarrow 901 - 60 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 27869$, $T_{841} := 899^2$,
 $E := \{121, 123, \dots, 1799, 1801\}$ or $E := \{541, 542, \dots, 1380, 1381\}$

■ Number 61

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$61^2 + 1860^2 := 1861^2$$

■ Number 62

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$62^2 + 960^2 := 962^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(62, 960, 962)** $\Rightarrow 962 - 62 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 30720$, $T_{900} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{125, 127, \dots, 1921, 1923\}$

■ Number 63

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$63^2 + 84^2 := 105^2$$

$$63^2 + 216^2 := 225^2$$

$$63^2 + 280^2 := 287^2$$

$$63^2 + 660^2 := 663^2$$

$$63^2 + 1984^2 := 1985^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(63, 216, 225)** $\Rightarrow 225 - 216 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 1323$, $T_9 := 63^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 447, 449\}$ or $E := \{437, 438, \dots, 444, 445\}$

■ Number 64

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$64^2 + 120^2 := 136^2$$

$$64^2 + 252^2 := 260^2$$

$$64^2 + 510^2 := 514^2$$

$$64^2 + 1023^2 := 1025^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(64, 120, 136)** $\Rightarrow 136 - 120 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 1024$, $T_{16} := 64^2$,

$$E := \{241, 243, \dots, 269, 271\}$$

2. **(64, 252, 260)** $\Rightarrow 260 - 64 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 4536$, $T_{196} := 252^2$,

$$E := \{129, 131, \dots, 517, 519\}$$

3. **(64, 1023, 1025)** $\Rightarrow 1025 - 64 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 33759$, $T_{961} := 1023^2$,

$$E := \{129, 131, \dots, 2047, 2049\} \text{ or } E := \{609, 610, \dots, 1568, 1569\}$$

■ Number 65

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$65^2 + 72^2 := 97^2$$

$$65^2 + 156^2 := 169^2$$

$$65^2 + 420^2 := 425^2$$

$$65^2 + 2112^2 := 2113^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

• **(65, 72, 97)** $\Rightarrow 97 - 72 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 845$, $T_{25} := 65^2$,

$$E := \{145, 147, \dots, 191, 193\} \text{ or } E := \{157, 158, \dots, 180, 181\}$$

■ Number 66

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$66^2 + 88^2 := 110^2$$

$$66^2 + 112^2 := 130^2$$

$$66^2 + 360^2 := 366^2$$

$$66^2 + 1088^2 := 1090^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

Some of the above triples generate magic squares with perfect square entries sum. See below:

1. **(66, 112, 130)** $\Rightarrow 130 - 66 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 1568$, $T_{64} := 112^2$,

$$E := \{133, 135, \dots, 257, 259\}$$

2. **(66, 1088, 1090)** $\Rightarrow 1090 - 66 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 36992$, $T_{1024} := 1088^2$,

$$E := \{133, 135, \dots, 2177, 2179\}$$

■ Number 67

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$67^2 + 2244^2 := 2245^2$$

■ Number 68

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$68^2 + 285^2 := 293^2$$

$$68^2 + 576^2 := 580^2$$

$$68^2 + 1155^2 := 1157^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(68, 285, 293)** $\Rightarrow 293 - 68 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 5415$, $T_{225} := 285^2$,
 $E := \{137, 139, \dots, 583, 585\}$ or $E := \{249, 250, \dots, 472, 473\}$

2. **(68, 1155, 1157)** $\Rightarrow 1157 - 68 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 40425$, $T_{1089} := 1155^2$,
 $E := \{137, 139, \dots, 2311, 2313\}$ or $E := \{681, 682, \dots, 1768, 1769\}$

■ Number 69

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$69^2 + 92^2 := 115^2$$

$$69^2 + 260^2 := 269^2$$

$$69^2 + 792^2 := 795^2$$

$$69^2 + 2380^2 := 2381^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(69, 260, 269)** $\Rightarrow 269 - 260 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 1587$, $T_9 := 69^2$,
 $E := \{521, 523, \dots, 535, 537\}$ or $E := \{525, 526, \dots, 532, 533\}$

■ Number 70

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$70^2 + 168^2 := 182^2$$

$$70^2 + 240^2 := 250^2$$

$$70^2 + 1224^2 := 1226^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(70, 1224, 1226)** $\Rightarrow 1226 - 70 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 44064$, $T_{1156} := 1224^2$,
 $E := \{141, 143, \dots, 2449, 2451\}$

■ Number 71

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$71^2 + 2520^2 := 2521^2$$

■ Number 72

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$72^2 + 96^2 := 120^2$$

$$72^2 + 135^2 := 153^2$$

$$72^2 + 154^2 := 170^2$$

$$72^2 + 210^2 := 222^2$$

$$72^2 + 320^2 := 328^2$$

$$72^2 + 429^2 := 435^2$$

$$72^2 + 646^2 := 650^2$$

$$72^2 + 1295^2 := 1297^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(72, 154, 170)** $\Rightarrow 170 - 154 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 1296$, $T_{16} := 72^2$,
 $E := \{309, 311, \dots, 337, 339\}$
2. **(72, 135, 153)** $\Rightarrow 153 - 72 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 2025$, $T_{81} := 135^2$,
 $E := \{145, 147, \dots, 303, 305\}$ or $E := \{185, 186, \dots, 264, 265\}$
3. **(72, 320, 328)** $\Rightarrow 328 - 72 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 6400$, $T_{256} := 320^2$,
 $E := \{145, 147, \dots, 653, 655\}$
4. **(72, 1295, 1297)** $\Rightarrow 1297 - 72 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 47915$, $T_{1225} := 1295^2$,
 $E := \{145, 147, \dots, 2591, 2593\}$ or $E := \{757, 758, \dots, 1980, 1981\}$

■ Number 73

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$73^2 + 2664^2 := 2665^2$$

■ Number 74

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$74^2 + 1368^2 := 1370^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(74, 1368, 1370)** $\Rightarrow 1370 - 74 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 51984$, $T_{1296} := 1368^2$,
 $E := \{149, 151, \dots, 2737, 2739\}$

■ Number 75

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$75^2 + 100^2 := 125^2$$

$$75^2 + 180^2 := 195^2$$

$$75^2 + 308^2 := 317^2$$

$$75^2 + 560^2 := 565^2$$

$$75^2 + 936^2 := 939^2$$

$$75^2 + 2812^2 := 2813^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

Some of the above triples generate magic squares with perfect square entries sum. See below:

1. **(75, 308, 317)** $\Rightarrow 317 - 308 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 1875$, $T_9 := 75^2$,
 $E := \{617, 619, \dots, 631, 633\}$ or $E := \{621, 622, \dots, 628, 629\}$
2. **(75, 100, 125)** $\Rightarrow 125 - 100 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 1125$, $T_{25} := 75^2$,
 $E := \{201, 203, \dots, 247, 249\}$ or $E := \{213, 214, \dots, 236, 237\}$

■ Number 76

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$76^2 + 357^2 := 365^2$$

$$76^2 + 720^2 := 724^2$$

$$76^2 + 1443^2 := 1445^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(76, 357, 365)** $\Rightarrow 365 - 76 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 7497$, $T_{289} := 357^2$,
 $E := \{153, 155, \dots, 727, 729\}$ or $E := \{297, 298, \dots, 584, 585\}$

2. **(76, 1443, 1445)** $\Rightarrow 1445 - 76 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 56277$, $T_{1369} := 1443^2$,
 $E := \{153, 155, \dots, 2887, 2889\}$ or $E := \{837, 838, \dots, 2204, 2205\}$

■ Number 77

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$77^2 + 264^2 := 275^2$$

$$77^2 + 420^2 := 427^2$$

$$77^2 + 2964^2 := 2965^2$$

■ Number 78

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$78^2 + 104^2 := 130^2$$

$$78^2 + 160^2 := 178^2$$

$$78^2 + 504^2 := 510^2$$

$$78^2 + 1520^2 := 1522^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(78, 160, 178)** $\Rightarrow 178 - 78 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 2560$, $T_{100} := 160^2$,
 $E := \{157, 159, \dots, 353, 355\}$

2. **(78, 1520, 1522)** $\Rightarrow 1522 - 78 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 60800$, $T_{1444} := 1520^2$,
 $E := \{157, 159, \dots, 3041, 3043\}$

■ Number 79

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$79^2 + 3120^2 := 3121^2$$

■ Number 80

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$80^2 + 84^2 := 116^2$$

$$80^2 + 150^2 := 170^2$$

$$80^2 + 192^2 := 208^2$$

$$80^2 + 315^2 := 325^2$$

$$80^2 + 396^2 := 404^2$$

$$80^2 + 798^2 := 802^2$$

$$80^2 + 1599^2 := 1601^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(80, 192, 208)** $\Rightarrow 208 - 192 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 1600$, $T_{16} := 80^2$,

$$E := \{385, 387, \dots, 413, 415\}$$

2. **(80, 84, 116)** $\Rightarrow 116 - 80 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 1176$, $T_{36} := 84^2$,

$$E := \{161, 163, \dots, 229, 231\}$$

3. **(80, 396, 404)** $\Rightarrow 404 - 80 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 8712$, $T_{324} := 396^2$,

$$E := \{161, 163, \dots, 805, 807\}$$

4. **(80, 1599, 1601)** $\Rightarrow 1601 - 80 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 65559$, $T_{1521} := 1599^2$,

$$E := \{161, 163, \dots, 3199, 3201\} \text{ or } E := \{921, 922, \dots, 2440, 2441\}$$

■ Number 82

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$82^2 + 1680^2 := 1682^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(82, 1680, 1682)** $\Rightarrow 1682 - 82 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 70560$, $T_{1600} := 1680^2$,

$$E := \{165, 167, \dots, 3361, 3363\}$$

■ Number 83

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$83^2 + 3444^2 := 3445^2$$

■ Number 84

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$84^2 + 112^2 := 140^2$$

$$84^2 + 135^2 := 159^2$$

$$84^2 + 187^2 := 205^2$$

$$84^2 + 245^2 := 259^2$$

$$84^2 + 288^2 := 300^2$$

$$84^2 + 437^2 := 445^2$$

$$84^2 + 585^2 := 591^2$$

$$84^2 + 880^2 := 884^2$$

$$84^2 + 1763^2 := 1765^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(84, 187, 205)** $\Rightarrow 205 - 84 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 3179$, $T_{121} := 187^2$,
 $E := \{169, 171, \dots, 407, 409\}$ or $E := \{229, 230, \dots, 348, 349\}$
2. **(84, 437, 445)** $\Rightarrow 445 - 84 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 10051$, $T_{361} := 437^2$,
 $E := \{169, 171, \dots, 887, 889\}$ or $E := \{349, 350, \dots, 708, 709\}$
3. **(84, 1763, 1765)** $\Rightarrow 1765 - 84 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 75809$, $T_{1681} := 1763^2$,
 $E := \{169, 171, \dots, 3527, 3529\}$ or $E := \{1009, 1010, \dots, 2688, 2689\}$

■ Number 85

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$85^2 + 132^2 := 157^2$$

$$85^2 + 204^2 := 221^2$$

$$85^2 + 720^2 := 725^2$$

$$85^2 + 3612^2 := 3613^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(85, 132, 157)** $\Rightarrow 157 - 132 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 1445$, $T_{25} := 85^2$,
 $E := \{265, 267, \dots, 311, 313\}$ or $E := \{277, 278, \dots, 300, 301\}$

■ Number 86

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$86^2 + 1848^2 := 1850^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(86, 1848, 1850)** $\Rightarrow 1850 - 86 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 81312$, $T_{1764} := 1848^2$,
 $E := \{173, 175, \dots, 3697, 3699\}$

■ Number 87

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$87^2 + 116^2 := 145^2$$

$$87^2 + 416^2 := 425^2$$

$$87^2 + 1260^2 := 1263^2$$

$$87^2 + 3784^2 := 3785^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(87, 416, 425)** $\Rightarrow 425 - 416 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 2523$, $T_9 := 87^2$,
 $E := \{833, 835, \dots, 847, 849\}$ or $E := \{837, 838, \dots, 844, 845\}$

■ Number 88

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$88^2 + 105^2 := 137^2$$

$$88^2 + 165^2 := 187^2$$

$$88^2 + 234^2 := 250^2$$

$$88^2 + 480^2 := 488^2$$

$$88^2 + 966^2 := 970^2$$

$$88^2 + 1935^2 := 1937^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

Some of the above triples generate magic squares with perfect square entries sum. See below:

1. **(88, 234, 250)** $\Rightarrow 250 - 234 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 1936$, $T_{16} := 88^2$,
 $E := \{469, 471, \dots, 497, 499\}$
2. **(88, 105, 137)** $\Rightarrow 137 - 88 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 1575$, $T_{49} := 105^2$,
 $E := \{177, 179, \dots, 271, 273\}$ or $E := \{201, 202, \dots, 248, 249\}$
3. **(88, 480, 488)** $\Rightarrow 488 - 88 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 11520$, $T_{400} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{177, 179, \dots, 973, 975\}$
4. **(88, 1935, 1937)** $\Rightarrow 1937 - 88 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 87075$, $T_{1849} := 1935^2$,
 $E := \{177, 179, \dots, 3871, 3873\}$ or $E := \{1101, 1102, \dots, 2948, 2949\}$

■ Number 89

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$89^2 + 3960^2 := 3961^2$$

■ Number 90

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$90^2 + 120^2 := 150^2$$

$$90^2 + 216^2 := 234^2$$

$$90^2 + 400^2 := 410^2$$

$$90^2 + 672^2 := 678^2$$

$$90^2 + 2024^2 := 2026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(90, 216, 234)** $\Rightarrow 234 - 90 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 3888$, $T_{144} := 216^2$,
 $E := \{181, 183, \dots, 465, 467\}$

2. **(90, 2024, 2026)** $\Rightarrow 2026 - 90 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 93104$, $T_{1936} := 2024^2$,
 $E := \{181, 183, \dots, 4049, 4051\}$

■ Number 91

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$91^2 + 312^2 := 325^2$$

$$91^2 + 588^2 := 595^2$$

$$91^2 + 4140^2 := 4141^2$$

■ Number 92

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$92^2 + 525^2 := 533^2$$

$$92^2 + 1056^2 := 1060^2$$

$$92^2 + 2115^2 := 2117^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(92, 525, 533)** $\Rightarrow 533 - 92 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 13125$, $T_{441} := 525^2$,
 $E := \{185, 187, \dots, 1063, 1065\}$ or $E := \{405, 406, \dots, 844, 845\}$

2. **(92, 2115, 2117)** $\Rightarrow 2117 - 92 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 99405$, $T_{2025} := 2115^2$,
 $E := \{185, 187, \dots, 4231, 4233\}$ or $E := \{1197, 1198, \dots, 3220, 3221\}$

■ Number 93

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$93^2 + 124^2 := 155^2$$

$$93^2 + 1440^2 := 1443^2$$

$$93^2 + 476^2 := 485^2$$

$$93^2 + 4324^2 := 4325^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(93, 476, 485)** $\Rightarrow 485 - 476 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 2883$, $T_9 := 93^2$,
 $E := \{953, 955, \dots, 967, 969\}$ or $E := \{957, 958, \dots, 964, 965\}$

■ Number 94

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$94^2 + 2208^2 := 2210^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(94, 2208, 2210)** $\Rightarrow 2210 - 94 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 105984$, $T_{2116} := 2208^2$,
 $E := \{189, 191, \dots, 4417, 4419\}$

■ Number 95

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$95^2 + 168^2 := 193^2$$

$$95^2 + 900^2 := 905^2$$

$$95^2 + 228^2 := 247^2$$

$$95^2 + 4512^2 := 4513^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(95, 168, 193)** $\Rightarrow 193 - 168 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 1805$, $T_{25} := 95^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 383, 385\}$ or $E := \{349, 350, \dots, 372, 373\}$

■ Number 96

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$96^2 + 110^2 := 146^2$$

$$96^2 + 247^2 := 265^2$$

$$96^2 + 572^2 := 580^2$$

$$96^2 + 128^2 := 160^2$$

$$96^2 + 280^2 := 296^2$$

$$96^2 + 765^2 := 771^2$$

$$96^2 + 180^2 := 204^2$$

$$96^2 + 378^2 := 390^2$$

$$96^2 + 1150^2 := 1154^2$$

$$96^2 + 2303^2 := 2305^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(96, 280, 296)** $\Rightarrow 296 - 280 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 2304$, $T_{16} := 96^2$,
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 589, 591\}$
2. **(96, 110, 146)** $\Rightarrow 146 - 110 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 1536$, $T_{36} := 96^2$,
 $E := \{221, 223, \dots, 289, 291\}$
3. **(96, 128, 160)** $\Rightarrow 160 - 96 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 2048$, $T_{64} := 128^2$,
 $E := \{193, 195, \dots, 317, 319\}$
4. **(96, 247, 265)** $\Rightarrow 265 - 96 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 4693$, $T_{169} := 247^2$,
 $E := \{193, 195, \dots, 527, 529\}$ or $E := \{277, 278, \dots, 444, 445\}$
5. **(96, 572, 580)** $\Rightarrow 580 - 96 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 14872$, $T_{484} := 572^2$,
 $E := \{193, 195, \dots, 1157, 1159\}$
6. **(96, 2303, 2305)** $\Rightarrow 2305 - 96 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 112847$, $T_{2209} := 2303^2$,
 $E := \{193, 195, \dots, 4607, 4609\}$ or $E := \{1297, 1298, \dots, 3504, 3505\}$

■ Number 97

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$97^2 + 4704^2 := 4705^2$$

■ Number 98

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$98^2 + 336^2 := 350^2$$

$$98^2 + 2400^2 := 2402^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(98, 2400, 2402)** $\Rightarrow 2402 - 98 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 120000$, $T_{2304} := 2400^2$,
 $E := \{197, 199, \dots, 4801, 4803\}$

■ Number 99

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$99^2 + 132^2 := 165^2$$

$$99^2 + 168^2 := 195^2$$

$$99^2 + 440^2 := 451^2$$

$$99^2 + 540^2 := 549^2$$

$$99^2 + 1632^2 := 1635^2$$

$$99^2 + 4900^2 := 4901^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(99, 540, 549)** $\Rightarrow 549 - 540 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 3267$, $T_9 := 99^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 1095, 1097\}$ or $E := \{1085, 1086, \dots, 1092, 1093\}$

■ Number 100

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$100^2 + 105^2 := 145^2$$

$$100^2 + 240^2 := 260^2$$

$$100^2 + 495^2 := 505^2$$

$$100^2 + 621^2 := 629^2$$

$$100^2 + 1248^2 := 1252^2$$

$$100^2 + 2499^2 := 2501^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(100, 621, 629)** $\Rightarrow 629 - 100 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 16767$, $T_{529} := 621^2$,
 $E := \{201, 203, \dots, 1255, 1257\}$ or $E := \{465, 466, \dots, 992, 993\}$
2. **(100, 2499, 2501)** $\Rightarrow 2501 - 100 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 127449$, $T_{2401} := 2499^2$,
 $E := \{201, 203, \dots, 4999, 5001\}$ or $E := \{1401, 1402, \dots, 3800, 3801\}$

2.2 Pythagorean Triples: 101 to 200

■ Number 101

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$101^2 + 5100^2 := 5101^2$$

■ Number 102

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$102^2 + 136^2 := 170^2$$

$$102^2 + 280^2 := 298^2$$

$$102^2 + 864^2 := 870^2$$

$$102^2 + 2600^2 := 2602^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(102, 280, 298)** $\Rightarrow 298 - 102 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 5600$, $T_{196} := 280^2$,
 $E := \{205, 207, \dots, 593, 595\}$
2. **(102, 2600, 2602)** $\Rightarrow 2602 - 102 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 135200$, $T_{2500} := 2600^2$,
 $E := \{205, 207, \dots, 5201, 5203\}$

■ Number 103

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$103^2 + 5304^2 := 5305^2$$

■ Number 104

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$104^2 + 153^2 := 185^2$$

$$104^2 + 195^2 := 221^2$$

$$104^2 + 330^2 := 346^2$$

$$104^2 + 672^2 := 680^2$$

$$104^2 + 1350^2 := 1354^2$$

$$104^2 + 2703^2 := 2705^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(104, 330, 346)** $\Rightarrow 346 - 330 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 2704$, $T_{16} := 104^2$,
 $E := \{661, 663, \dots, 689, 691\}$
2. **(104, 153, 185)** $\Rightarrow 185 - 104 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 2601$, $T_{81} := 153^2$,
 $E := \{209, 211, \dots, 367, 369\}$ or $E := \{249, 250, \dots, 328, 329\}$
3. **(104, 672, 680)** $\Rightarrow 680 - 104 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 18816$, $T_{576} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{209, 211, \dots, 1357, 1359\}$
4. **(104, 2703, 2705)** $\Rightarrow 2705 - 104 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 143259$, $T_{2601} := 2703^2$,
 $E := \{209, 211, \dots, 5407, 5409\}$ or $E := \{1509, 1510, \dots, 4108, 4109\}$

■ Number 105

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$105^2 + 140^2 := 175^2$$

$$105^2 + 208^2 := 233^2$$

$$105^2 + 252^2 := 273^2$$

$$105^2 + 360^2 := 375^2$$

$$105^2 + 608^2 := 617^2$$

$$105^2 + 784^2 := 791^2$$

$$105^2 + 1100^2 := 1105^2$$

$$105^2 + 1836^2 := 1839^2$$

$$105^2 + 5512^2 := 5513^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(105, 608, 617)** $\Rightarrow 617 - 608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 3675$, $T_9 := 105^2$,
 $E := \{1217, 1219, \dots, 1231, 1233\}$ or $E := \{1221, 1222, \dots, 1228, 1229\}$
2. **(105, 208, 233)** $\Rightarrow 233 - 208 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 2205$, $T_{25} := 105^2$,
 $E := \{417, 419, \dots, 463, 465\}$ or $E := \{429, 430, \dots, 452, 453\}$

■ Number 106

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$106^2 + 2808^2 := 2810^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(106, 2808, 2810)** $\Rightarrow 2810 - 106 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 151632$, $T_{2704} := 2808^2$,
 $E := \{213, 215, \dots, 5617, 5619\}$

■ Number 107

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$107^2 + 5724^2 := 5725^2$$

■ Number 108

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$108^2 + 144^2 := 180^2$$

$$108^2 + 231^2 := 255^2$$

$$108^2 + 315^2 := 333^2$$

$$108^2 + 480^2 := 492^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}108^2 + 725^2 &:= 733^2 \\108^2 + 969^2 &:= 975^2 \\108^2 + 1456^2 &:= 1460^2 \\108^2 + 2915^2 &:= 2917^2\end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(108, 144, 180)** $\Rightarrow 180 - 144 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 1944$, $T_{36} := 108^2$,
 $E := \{289, 291, \dots, 357, 359\}$
2. **(108, 315, 333)** $\Rightarrow 333 - 108 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 6615$, $T_{225} := 315^2$,
 $E := \{217, 219, \dots, 663, 665\}$ or $E := \{329, 330, \dots, 552, 553\}$
3. **(108, 725, 733)** $\Rightarrow 733 - 108 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 21025$, $T_{625} := 725^2$,
 $E := \{217, 219, \dots, 1463, 1465\}$ or $E := \{529, 530, \dots, 1152, 1153\}$
4. **(108, 2915, 2917)** $\Rightarrow 2917 - 108 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 160325$, $T_{2809} := 2915^2$,
 $E := \{217, 219, \dots, 5831, 5833\}$ or $E := \{1621, 1622, \dots, 4428, 4429\}$

■ Number 109

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$109^2 + 5940^2 := 5941^2$$

■ Number 110

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned}110^2 + 264^2 &:= 286^2 \\110^2 + 600^2 &:= 610^2 \\110^2 + 3024^2 &:= 3026^2\end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(110, 3024, 3026)** $\Rightarrow 3026 - 110 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 169344$, $T_{2916} := 3024^2$,
 $E := \{221, 223, \dots, 6049, 6051\}$

■ Number 111

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$111^2 + 148^2 := 185^2$$

$$111^2 + 2052^2 := 2055^2$$

$$111^2 + 680^2 := 689^2$$

$$111^2 + 6160^2 := 6161^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(111, 680, 689)** $\Rightarrow 689 - 680 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 4107$, $T_9 := 111^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 1375, 1377\}$ or $E := \{1365, 1366, \dots, 1372, 1373\}$

■ Number 112

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$112^2 + 180^2 := 212^2$$

$$112^2 + 780^2 := 788^2$$

$$112^2 + 210^2 := 238^2$$

$$112^2 + 1566^2 := 1570^2$$

$$112^2 + 384^2 := 400^2$$

$$112^2 + 3135^2 := 3137^2$$

$$112^2 + 441^2 := 455^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(112, 384, 400)** $\Rightarrow 400 - 384 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 3136$, $T_{16} := 112^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 797, 799\}$
2. **(112, 180, 212)** $\Rightarrow 212 - 112 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 3240$, $T_{100} := 180^2$,
 $E := \{225, 227, \dots, 421, 423\}$
3. **(112, 780, 788)** $\Rightarrow 788 - 112 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 23400$, $T_{676} := 780^2$,
 $E := \{225, 227, \dots, 1573, 1575\}$
4. **(112, 3135, 3137)** $\Rightarrow 3137 - 112 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 178695$, $T_{3025} := 3135^2$,
 $E := \{225, 227, \dots, 6271, 6273\}$ or $E := \{1737, 1738, \dots, 4760, 4761\}$

■ Number 113

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$113^2 + 6384^2 := 6385^2$$

■ Number 114

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$114^2 + 152^2 := 190^2$$

$$114^2 + 352^2 := 370^2$$

$$114^2 + 1080^2 := 1086^2$$

$$114^2 + 3248^2 := 3250^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(114, 352, 370)** $\Rightarrow 370 - 114 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 7744$, $T_{256} := 352^2$,
 $E := \{229, 231, \dots, 737, 739\}$

2. **(114, 3248, 3250)** $\Rightarrow 3250 - 114 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 188384$, $T_{3136} := 3248^2$,
 $E := \{229, 231, \dots, 6497, 6499\}$

■ Number 115

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$115^2 + 252^2 := 277^2$$

$$115^2 + 276^2 := 299^2$$

$$115^2 + 1320^2 := 1325^2$$

$$115^2 + 6612^2 := 6613^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

• **(115, 252, 277)** $\Rightarrow 277 - 252 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 2645$, $T_{25} := 115^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 551, 553\}$ or $E := \{517, 518, \dots, 540, 541\}$

■ Number 116

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$116^2 + 837^2 := 845^2$$

$$116^2 + 1680^2 := 1684^2$$

$$116^2 + 3363^2 := 3365^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(116, 837, 845)** $\Rightarrow 845 - 116 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 25947$, $T_{729} := 837^2$,
 $E := \{233, 235, \dots, 1687, 1689\}$ or $E := \{597, 598, \dots, 1324, 1325\}$

2. **(116, 3363, 3365)** $\Rightarrow 3365 - 116 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 198417$, $T_{3249} := 3363^2$,
 $E := \{233, 235, \dots, 6727, 6729\}$ or $E := \{1857, 1858, \dots, 5104, 5105\}$

■ Number 117

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$117^2 + 156^2 := 195^2$$

$$117^2 + 240^2 := 267^2$$

$$117^2 + 520^2 := 533^2$$

$$117^2 + 756^2 := 765^2$$

$$117^2 + 2280^2 := 2283^2$$

$$117^2 + 6844^2 := 6845^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(117, 756, 765)** $\Rightarrow 765 - 756 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 4563$, $T_9 := 117^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 1527, 1529\}$ or $E := \{1517, 1518, \dots, 1524, 1525\}$

■ Number 118

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$118^2 + 3480^2 := 3482^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(118, 3480, 3482)** $\Rightarrow 3482 - 118 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 208800$, $T_{3364} := 3480^2$,
 $E := \{237, 239, \dots, 6961, 6963\}$

■ Number 119

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$119^2 + 120^2 := 169^2$$

$$119^2 + 408^2 := 425^2$$

$$119^2 + 1008^2 := 1015^2$$

$$119^2 + 7080^2 := 7081^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(119, 120, 169)** $\Rightarrow 169 - 120 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 2023$, $T_{49} := 119^2$,
 $E := \{241, 243, \dots, 335, 337\}$ or $E := \{265, 266, \dots, 312, 313\}$

■ Number 120

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 120^2 + 126^2 &:= 174^2 \\ 120^2 + 160^2 &:= 200^2 \\ 120^2 + 182^2 &:= 218^2 \\ 120^2 + 209^2 &:= 241^2 \\ 120^2 + 225^2 &:= 255^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 120^2 + 288^2 &:= 312^2 \\ 120^2 + 350^2 &:= 370^2 \\ 120^2 + 391^2 &:= 409^2 \\ 120^2 + 442^2 &:= 458^2 \\ 120^2 + 594^2 &:= 606^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 120^2 + 715^2 &:= 725^2 \\ 120^2 + 896^2 &:= 904^2 \\ 120^2 + 1197^2 &:= 1203^2 \\ 120^2 + 1798^2 &:= 1802^2 \\ 120^2 + 3599^2 &:= 3601^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(120, 442, 458)** $\Rightarrow 458 - 442 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 3600$, $T_{16} := 120^2$,
 $E := \{885, 887, \dots, 913, 915\}$
2. **(120, 182, 218)** $\Rightarrow 218 - 182 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 2400$, $T_{36} := 120^2$,
 $E := \{365, 367, \dots, 433, 435\}$
3. **(120, 209, 241)** $\Rightarrow 241 - 120 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 3971$, $T_{121} := 209^2$,
 $E := \{241, 243, \dots, 479, 481\}$ or $E := \{301, 302, \dots, 420, 421\}$
4. **(120, 391, 409)** $\Rightarrow 409 - 120 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 8993$, $T_{289} := 391^2$,
 $E := \{241, 243, \dots, 815, 817\}$ or $E := \{385, 386, \dots, 672, 673\}$
5. **(120, 896, 904)** $\Rightarrow 904 - 120 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 28672$, $T_{784} := 896^2$,
 $E := \{241, 243, \dots, 1805, 1807\}$
6. **(120, 3599, 3601)** $\Rightarrow 3601 - 120 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 219539$, $T_{3481} := 3599^2$,
 $E := \{241, 243, \dots, 7199, 7201\}$ or $E := \{1981, 1982, \dots, 5460, 5461\}$

■ Number 121

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 121^2 + 660^2 &:= 671^2 \\ 121^2 + 7320^2 &:= 7321^2 \end{aligned}$$

■ Number 122

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$122^2 + 3720^2 := 3722^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(122, 3720, 3722)** $\Rightarrow 3722 - 122 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 230640$, $T_{3600} := 3720^2$,
 $E := \{245, 247, \dots, 7441, 7443\}$

■ Number 123

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$123^2 + 164^2 := 205^2$$

$$123^2 + 836^2 := 845^2$$

$$123^2 + 2520^2 := 2523^2$$

$$123^2 + 7564^2 := 7565^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(123, 836, 845)** $\Rightarrow 845 - 836 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 5043$, $T_9 := 123^2$,
 $E := \{1673, 1675, \dots, 1687, 1689\}$ or $E := \{1677, 1678, \dots, 1684, 1685\}$

■ Number 124

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$124^2 + 957^2 := 965^2$$

$$124^2 + 1920^2 := 1924^2$$

$$124^2 + 3843^2 := 3845^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(124, 957, 965)** $\Rightarrow 965 - 124 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 31581$, $T_{841} := 957^2$,
 $E := \{249, 251, \dots, 1927, 1929\}$ or $E := \{669, 670, \dots, 1508, 1509\}$
2. **(124, 3843, 3845)** $\Rightarrow 3845 - 124 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 242109$, $T_{3721} := 3843^2$,
 $E := \{249, 251, \dots, 7687, 7689\}$ or $E := \{2109, 2110, \dots, 5828, 5829\}$

■ Number 125

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$125^2 + 300^2 := 325^2$$

$$125^2 + 1560^2 := 1565^2$$

$$125^2 + 7812^2 := 7813^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(125, 300, 325)** $\Rightarrow 325 - 300 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 3125$, $T_{25} := 125^2$,
 $E := \{601, 603, \dots, 647, 649\}$ or $E := \{613, 614, \dots, 636, 637\}$

■ Number 126

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$126^2 + 168^2 := 210^2$$

$$126^2 + 432^2 := 450^2$$

$$126^2 + 560^2 := 574^2$$

$$126^2 + 1320^2 := 1326^2$$

$$126^2 + 3968^2 := 3970^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(126, 432, 450)** $\Rightarrow 450 - 126 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 10368$, $T_{324} := 432^2$,
 $E := \{253, 255, \dots, 897, 899\}$
2. **(126, 3968, 3970)** $\Rightarrow 3970 - 126 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 253952$, $T_{3844} := 3968^2$,
 $E := \{253, 255, \dots, 7937, 7939\}$

■ Number 127

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$127^2 + 8064^2 := 8065^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

■ Number 128

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$128^2 + 240^2 := 272^2$$

$$128^2 + 504^2 := 520^2$$

$$128^2 + 1020^2 := 1028^2$$

$$128^2 + 2046^2 := 2050^2$$

$$128^2 + 4095^2 := 4097^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(128, 504, 520)** $\Rightarrow 520 - 504 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 4096$, $T_{16} := 128^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 1037, 1039\}$

2. **(128, 240, 272)** $\Rightarrow 272 - 128 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 4800$, $T_{144} := 240^2$,
 $E := \{257, 259, \dots, 541, 543\}$
3. **(128, 1020, 1028)** $\Rightarrow 1028 - 128 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 34680$, $T_{900} := 1020^2$,
 $E := \{257, 259, \dots, 2053, 2055\}$
4. **(128, 4095, 4097)** $\Rightarrow 4097 - 128 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 266175$, $T_{3969} := 4095^2$,
 $E := \{257, 259, \dots, 8191, 8193\}$ or $E := \{2241, 2242, \dots, 6208, 6209\}$

■ Number 129

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 129^2 + 172^2 := 215^2 & 129^2 + 2772^2 := 2775^2 \\ 129^2 + 920^2 := 929^2 & 129^2 + 8320^2 := 8321^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(129, 920, 929)** $\Rightarrow 929 - 920 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 5547$, $T_9 := 129^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 1855, 1857\}$ or $E := \{1845, 1846, \dots, 1852, 1853\}$

■ Number 130

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 130^2 + 144^2 := 194^2 & 130^2 + 840^2 := 850^2 \\ 130^2 + 312^2 := 338^2 & 130^2 + 4224^2 := 4226^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(130, 144, 194)** $\Rightarrow 194 - 130 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 2592$, $T_{64} := 144^2$,
 $E := \{261, 263, \dots, 385, 387\}$
2. **(130, 4224, 4226)** $\Rightarrow 4226 - 130 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 278784$, $T_{4096} := 4224^2$,
 $E := \{261, 263, \dots, 8449, 8451\}$

■ Number 131

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$131^2 + 8580^2 := 8581^2$$

■ Number 132

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$132^2 + 176^2 := 220^2$$

$$132^2 + 224^2 := 260^2$$

$$132^2 + 351^2 := 375^2$$

$$132^2 + 385^2 := 407^2$$

$$132^2 + 475^2 := 493^2$$

$$132^2 + 720^2 := 732^2$$

$$132^2 + 1085^2 := 1093^2$$

$$132^2 + 1449^2 := 1455^2$$

$$132^2 + 2176^2 := 2180^2$$

$$132^2 + 4355^2 := 4357^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

$$1. \text{ (132, 224, 260)} \Rightarrow 260 - 224 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 2904, T_{36} := 132^2,$$

$$E := \{449, 451, \dots, 517, 519\}$$

$$2. \text{ (132, 475, 493)} \Rightarrow 493 - 132 = 19^2, S_{19 \times 19} := 11875, T_{361} := 475^2,$$

$$E := \{265, 267, \dots, 983, 985\} \text{ or } E := \{445, 446, \dots, 804, 805\}$$

$$3. \text{ (132, 1085, 1093)} \Rightarrow 1093 - 132 = 31^2, S_{31 \times 31} := 37975, T_{961} := 1085^2,$$

$$E := \{265, 267, \dots, 2183, 2185\} \text{ or } E := \{745, 746, \dots, 1704, 1705\}$$

$$4. \text{ (132, 4355, 4357)} \Rightarrow 4357 - 132 = 65^2, S_{65 \times 65} := 291785, T_{4225} := 4355^2,$$

$$E := \{265, 267, \dots, 8711, 8713\} \text{ or } E := \{2377, 2378, \dots, 6600, 6601\}$$

■ Number 133

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$133^2 + 156^2 := 205^2$$

$$133^2 + 456^2 := 475^2$$

$$133^2 + 1260^2 := 1267^2$$

$$133^2 + 8844^2 := 8845^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

$$- \text{ (133, 156, 205)} \Rightarrow 205 - 156 = 7^2, S_{7 \times 7} := 2527, T_{49} := 133^2,$$

$$E := \{313, 315, \dots, 407, 409\} \text{ or } E := \{337, 338, \dots, 384, 385\}$$

■ Number 134

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$134^2 + 4488^2 := 4490^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

$$- \text{ (134, 4488, 4490)} \Rightarrow 4490 - 134 = 66^2, S_{66 \times 66} := 305184, T_{4356} := 4488^2,$$

$$E := \{269, 271, \dots, 8977, 8979\}$$

■ Number 135

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$135^2 + 180^2 := 225^2$$

$$135^2 + 324^2 := 351^2$$

$$135^2 + 352^2 := 377^2$$

$$135^2 + 600^2 := 615^2$$

$$135^2 + 1008^2 := 1017^2$$

$$135^2 + 1820^2 := 1825^2$$

$$135^2 + 3036^2 := 3039^2$$

$$135^2 + 9112^2 := 9113^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(135, 1008, 1017)** $\Rightarrow 1017 - 1008 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 6075$, $T_9 := 135^2$,
 $E := \{2017, 2019, \dots, 2031, 2033\}$ or $E := \{2021, 2022, \dots, 2028, 2029\}$
2. **(135, 352, 377)** $\Rightarrow 377 - 352 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 3645$, $T_{25} := 135^2$,
 $E := \{705, 707, \dots, 751, 753\}$ or $E := \{717, 718, \dots, 740, 741\}$

■ Number 136

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$136^2 + 255^2 := 289^2$$

$$136^2 + 273^2 := 305^2$$

$$136^2 + 570^2 := 586^2$$

$$136^2 + 1152^2 := 1160^2$$

$$136^2 + 2310^2 := 2314^2$$

$$136^2 + 4623^2 := 4625^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(136, 570, 586)** $\Rightarrow 586 - 570 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 4624$, $T_{16} := 136^2$,
 $E := \{1141, 1143, \dots, 1169, 1171\}$
2. **(136, 273, 305)** $\Rightarrow 305 - 136 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 5733$, $T_{169} := 273^2$,
 $E := \{273, 275, \dots, 607, 609\}$ or $E := \{357, 358, \dots, 524, 525\}$
3. **(136, 1152, 1160)** $\Rightarrow 1160 - 136 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 41472$, $T_{1024} := 1152^2$,
 $E := \{273, 275, \dots, 2317, 2319\}$
4. **(136, 4623, 4625)** $\Rightarrow 4625 - 136 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 318987$, $T_{4489} := 4623^2$,
 $E := \{273, 275, \dots, 9247, 9249\}$ or $E := \{2517, 2518, \dots, 7004, 7005\}$

■ Number 137

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$137^2 + 9384^2 := 9385^2$$

■ Number 138

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$138^2 + 184^2 := 230^2$$

$$138^2 + 520^2 := 538^2$$

$$138^2 + 1584^2 := 1590^2$$

$$138^2 + 4760^2 := 4762^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(138, 520, 538)** $\Rightarrow 538 - 138 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 13520$, $T_{400} := 520^2$,
 $E := \{277, 279, \dots, 1073, 1075\}$

2. **(138, 4760, 4762)** $\Rightarrow 4762 - 138 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 333200$, $T_{4624} := 4760^2$,
 $E := \{277, 279, \dots, 9521, 9523\}$

■ Number 139

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$139^2 + 9660^2 := 9661^2$$

■ Number 140

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$140^2 + 147^2 := 203^2$$

$$140^2 + 171^2 := 221^2$$

$$140^2 + 225^2 := 265^2$$

$$140^2 + 336^2 := 364^2$$

$$140^2 + 480^2 := 500^2$$

$$140^2 + 693^2 := 707^2$$

$$140^2 + 975^2 := 985^2$$

$$140^2 + 1221^2 := 1229^2$$

$$140^2 + 2448^2 := 2452^2$$

$$140^2 + 4899^2 := 4901^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(140, 171, 221)** $\Rightarrow 221 - 140 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 3249$, $T_{81} := 171^2$,
 $E := \{281, 283, \dots, 439, 441\}$ or $E := \{321, 322, \dots, 400, 401\}$

2. **(140, 1221, 1229)** $\Rightarrow 1229 - 140 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 45177$, $T_{1089} := 1221^2$,
 $E := \{281, 283, \dots, 2455, 2457\}$ or $E := \{825, 826, \dots, 1912, 1913\}$
3. **(140, 4899, 4901)** $\Rightarrow 4901 - 140 = 69^2$, $S_{69 \times 69} := 347829$, $T_{4761} := 4899^2$,
 $E := \{281, 283, \dots, 9799, 9801\}$ or $E := \{2661, 2662, \dots, 7420, 7421\}$

■ Number 141

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 141^2 + 188^2 := 235^2 & 141^2 + 3312^2 := 3315^2 \\ 141^2 + 1100^2 := 1109^2 & 141^2 + 9940^2 := 9941^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(141, 1100, 1109)** $\Rightarrow 1109 - 1100 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 6627$, $T_9 := 141^2$,
 $E := \{2201, 2203, \dots, 2215, 2217\}$ or $E := \{2205, 2206, \dots, 2212, 2213\}$

■ Number 142

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$142^2 + 5040^2 := 5042^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(142, 5040, 5042)** $\Rightarrow 5042 - 142 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 362880$, $T_{4900} := 5040^2$,
 $E := \{285, 287, \dots, 10081, 10083\}$

■ Number 143

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 143^2 + 780^2 := 793^2 \\ 143^2 + 924^2 := 935^2 \\ 143^2 + 10224^2 := 10225^2 \end{array}$$

■ Number 144

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$144^2 + 165^2 := 219^2$$

$$144^2 + 192^2 := 240^2$$

$$144^2 + 270^2 := 306^2$$

$$144^2 + 308^2 := 340^2$$

$$144^2 + 420^2 := 444^2$$

$$144^2 + 567^2 := 585^2$$

$$144^2 + 640^2 := 656^2$$

$$144^2 + 858^2 := 870^2$$

$$144^2 + 1292^2 := 1300^2$$

$$144^2 + 1725^2 := 1731^2$$

$$144^2 + 2590^2 := 2594^2$$

$$144^2 + 5183^2 := 5185^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(144, 640, 656)** $\Rightarrow 656 - 640 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 5184$, $T_{16} := 144^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 1309, 1311\}$
2. **(144, 270, 306)** $\Rightarrow 306 - 270 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3456$, $T_{36} := 144^2$,
 $E := \{541, 543, \dots, 609, 611\}$
3. **(144, 308, 340)** $\Rightarrow 340 - 144 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 6776$, $T_{196} := 308^2$,
 $E := \{289, 291, \dots, 677, 679\}$
4. **(144, 567, 585)** $\Rightarrow 585 - 144 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 15309$, $T_{441} := 567^2$,
 $E := \{289, 291, \dots, 1167, 1169\}$ or $E := \{509, 510, \dots, 948, 949\}$
5. **(144, 1292, 1300)** $\Rightarrow 1300 - 144 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 49096$, $T_{1156} := 1292^2$,
 $E := \{289, 291, \dots, 2597, 2599\}$
6. **(144, 5183, 5185)** $\Rightarrow 5185 - 144 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 378359$, $T_{5041} := 5183^2$,
 $E := \{289, 291, \dots, 10367, 10369\}$ or $E := \{2809, 2810, \dots, 7848, 7849\}$

■ Number 145

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$145^2 + 348^2 := 377^2$$

$$145^2 + 408^2 := 433^2$$

$$145^2 + 2100^2 := 2105^2$$

$$145^2 + 10512^2 := 10513^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(145, 408, 433)** $\Rightarrow 433 - 408 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 4205$, $T_{25} := 145^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 863, 865\}$ or $E := \{829, 830, \dots, 852, 853\}$

■ Number 146

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$146^2 + 5328^2 := 5330^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(146, 5328, 5330)** $\Rightarrow 5330 - 146 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 394272$, $T_{5184} := 5328^2$,
 $E := \{293, 295, \dots, 10657, 10659\}$

■ Number 147

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$147^2 + 196^2 := 245^2$$

$$147^2 + 504^2 := 525^2$$

$$147^2 + 1196^2 := 1205^2$$

$$147^2 + 1540^2 := 1547^2$$

$$147^2 + 3600^2 := 3603^2$$

$$147^2 + 10804^2 := 10805^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(147, 1196, 1205)** $\Rightarrow 1205 - 1196 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 7203$, $T_9 := 147^2$,
 $E := \{2393, 2395, \dots, 2407, 2409\}$ or $E := \{2397, 2398, \dots, 2404, 2405\}$

2. **(147, 196, 245)** $\Rightarrow 245 - 196 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 3087$, $T_{49} := 147^2$,
 $E := \{393, 395, \dots, 487, 489\}$ or $E := \{417, 418, \dots, 464, 465\}$

■ Number 148

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$148^2 + 1365^2 := 1373^2$$

$$148^2 + 2736^2 := 2740^2$$

$$148^2 + 5475^2 := 5477^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(148, 1365, 1373)** $\Rightarrow 1373 - 148 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 53235$, $T_{1225} := 1365^2$,
 $E := \{297, 299, \dots, 2743, 2745\}$ or $E := \{909, 910, \dots, 2132, 2133\}$

2. **(148, 5475, 5477)** $\Rightarrow 5477 - 148 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 410625$, $T_{5329} := 5475^2$,
 $E := \{297, 299, \dots, 10951, 10953\}$ or $E := \{2961, 2962, \dots, 8288, 8289\}$

■ Number 149

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$149^2 + 11100^2 := 11101^2$$

■ Number 150

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$150^2 + 200^2 := 250^2$$

$$150^2 + 360^2 := 390^2$$

$$150^2 + 616^2 := 634^2$$

$$150^2 + 1120^2 := 1130^2$$

$$150^2 + 1872^2 := 1878^2$$

$$150^2 + 5624^2 := 5626^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(150, 200, 250)** $\Rightarrow 250 - 150 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 4000$, $T_{100} := 200^2$,

$$E := \{301, 303, \dots, 497, 499\}$$

2. **(150, 616, 634)** $\Rightarrow 634 - 150 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 17248$, $T_{484} := 616^2$,

$$E := \{301, 303, \dots, 1265, 1267\}$$

3. **(150, 5624, 5626)** $\Rightarrow 5626 - 150 = 74^2$, $S_{74 \times 74} := 427424$, $T_{5476} := 5624^2$,

$$E := \{301, 303, \dots, 11249, 11251\}$$

■ Number 151

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$151^2 + 11400^2 := 11401^2$$

■ Number 152

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$152^2 + 285^2 := 323^2$$

$$152^2 + 345^2 := 377^2$$

$$152^2 + 714^2 := 730^2$$

$$152^2 + 1440^2 := 1448^2$$

$$152^2 + 2886^2 := 2890^2$$

$$152^2 + 5775^2 := 5777^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(152, 714, 730)** $\Rightarrow 730 - 714 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 5776$, $T_{16} := 152^2$,

$$E := \{1429, 1431, \dots, 1457, 1459\}$$

2. **(152, 345, 377)** $\Rightarrow 377 - 152 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 7935$, $T_{225} := 345^2$,
 $E := \{305, 307, \dots, 751, 753\}$ or $E := \{417, 418, \dots, 640, 641\}$
3. **(152, 1440, 1448)** $\Rightarrow 1448 - 152 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 57600$, $T_{1296} := 1440^2$,
 $E := \{305, 307, \dots, 2893, 2895\}$
4. **(152, 5775, 5777)** $\Rightarrow 5777 - 152 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 444675$, $T_{5625} := 5775^2$,
 $E := \{305, 307, \dots, 11551, 11553\}$ or $E := \{3117, 3118, \dots, 8740, 8741\}$

■ Number 153

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$153^2 + 204^2 := 255^2$$

$$153^2 + 420^2 := 447^2$$

$$153^2 + 680^2 := 697^2$$

$$153^2 + 1296^2 := 1305^2$$

$$153^2 + 3900^2 := 3903^2$$

$$153^2 + 11704^2 := 11705^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(153, 1296, 1305)** $\Rightarrow 1305 - 1296 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 7803$, $T_9 := 153^2$,
 $E := \{2593, 2595, \dots, 2607, 2609\}$ or $E := \{2597, 2598, \dots, 2604, 2605\}$

■ Number 154

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$154^2 + 528^2 := 550^2$$

$$154^2 + 840^2 := 854^2$$

$$154^2 + 5928^2 := 5930^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(154, 5928, 5930)** $\Rightarrow 5930 - 154 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 462384$, $T_{5776} := 5928^2$,
 $E := \{309, 311, \dots, 11857, 11859\}$

■ Number 155

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$155^2 + 372^2 := 403^2$$

$$155^2 + 468^2 := 493^2$$

$$155^2 + 2400^2 := 2405^2$$

$$155^2 + 12012^2 := 12013^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(155, 468, 493)** $\Rightarrow 493 - 468 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 4805$, $T_{25} := 155^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 983, 985\}$ or $E := \{949, 950, \dots, 972, 973\}$

■ Number 156

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$156^2 + 208^2 := 260^2$$

$$156^2 + 320^2 := 356^2$$

$$156^2 + 455^2 := 481^2$$

$$156^2 + 495^2 := 519^2$$

$$156^2 + 667^2 := 685^2$$

$$156^2 + 1008^2 := 1020^2$$

$$156^2 + 1517^2 := 1525^2$$

$$156^2 + 2025^2 := 2031^2$$

$$156^2 + 3040^2 := 3044^2$$

$$156^2 + 6083^2 := 6085^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

Below are Pythagorean triples generating magic squares:

1. **(156, 320, 356)** $\Rightarrow 356 - 320 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 4056$, $T_{36} := 156^2$,
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 709, 711\}$
2. **(156, 667, 685)** $\Rightarrow 685 - 156 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 19343$, $T_{529} := 667^2$,
 $E := \{313, 315, \dots, 1367, 1369\}$ or $E := \{577, 578, \dots, 1104, 1105\}$
3. **(156, 1517, 1525)** $\Rightarrow 1525 - 156 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 62197$, $T_{1369} := 1517^2$,
 $E := \{313, 315, \dots, 3047, 3049\}$ or $E := \{997, 998, \dots, 2364, 2365\}$
4. **(156, 6083, 6085)** $\Rightarrow 6085 - 156 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 480557$, $T_{5929} := 6083^2$,
 $E := \{313, 315, \dots, 12167, 12169\}$ or $E := \{3277, 3278, \dots, 9204, 9205\}$

■ Number 157

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$157^2 + 12324^2 := 12325^2$$

■ Number 158

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$158^2 + 6240^2 := 6242^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(158, 6240, 6242)** $\Rightarrow 6242 - 158 = 78^2$, $S_{78 \times 78} := 499200$, $T_{6084} := 6240^2$,
 $E := \{317, 319, \dots, 12481, 12483\}$

■ **Number 159**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll} 159^2 + 212^2 := 265^2 & 159^2 + 4212^2 := 4215^2 \\ 159^2 + 1400^2 := 1409^2 & 159^2 + 12640^2 := 12641^2 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(159, 1400, 1409)** $\Rightarrow 1409 - 1400 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 8427$, $T_9 := 159^2$,
 $E := \{2801, 2803, \dots, 2815, 2817\}$ or $E := \{2805, 2806, \dots, 2812, 2813\}$

■ **Number 160**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{lll} 160^2 + 168^2 := 232^2 & 160^2 + 384^2 := 416^2 & 160^2 + 1275^2 := 1285^2 \\ 160^2 + 231^2 := 281^2 & 160^2 + 630^2 := 650^2 & 160^2 + 1596^2 := 1604^2 \\ 160^2 + 300^2 := 340^2 & 160^2 + 792^2 := 808^2 & 160^2 + 3198^2 := 3202^2 \\ & & 160^2 + 6399^2 := 6401^2 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(160, 792, 808)** $\Rightarrow 808 - 792 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 6400$, $T_{16} := 160^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 1613, 1615\}$
2. **(160, 168, 232)** $\Rightarrow 232 - 168 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 3200$, $T_{64} := 160^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 461, 463\}$
3. **(160, 231, 281)** $\Rightarrow 281 - 160 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 4851$, $T_{121} := 231^2$,
 $E := \{321, 323, \dots, 559, 561\}$ or $E := \{381, 382, \dots, 500, 501\}$
4. **(160, 384, 416)** $\Rightarrow 416 - 160 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 9216$, $T_{256} := 384^2$,
 $E := \{321, 323, \dots, 829, 831\}$
5. **(160, 1596, 1604)** $\Rightarrow 1604 - 160 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 67032$, $T_{1444} := 1596^2$,
 $E := \{321, 323, \dots, 3205, 3207\}$
6. **(160, 6399, 6401)** $\Rightarrow 6401 - 160 = 79^2$, $S_{79 \times 79} := 518319$, $T_{6241} := 6399^2$,
 $E := \{321, 323, \dots, 12799, 12801\}$ or $E := \{3441, 3442, \dots, 9680, 9681\}$

■ Number 161

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$161^2 + 240^2 := 289^2$$

$$161^2 + 552^2 := 575^2$$

$$161^2 + 1848^2 := 1855^2$$

$$161^2 + 12960^2 := 12961^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(161, 240, 289)** $\Rightarrow 289 - 240 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 3703$, $T_{49} := 161^2$,

$$E := \{481, 483, \dots, 575, 577\} \text{ or } E := \{505, 506, \dots, 552, 553\}$$

■ Number 162

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$162^2 + 216^2 := 270^2$$

$$162^2 + 720^2 := 738^2$$

$$162^2 + 2184^2 := 2190^2$$

$$162^2 + 6560^2 := 6562^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(162, 720, 738)** $\Rightarrow 738 - 162 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 21600$, $T_{576} := 720^2$,

$$E := \{325, 327, \dots, 1473, 1475\}$$

2. **(162, 6560, 6562)** $\Rightarrow 6562 - 162 = 80^2$, $S_{80 \times 80} := 537920$, $T_{6400} := 6560^2$,

$$E := \{325, 327, \dots, 13121, 13123\}$$

■ Number 163

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$163^2 + 13284^2 := 13285^2$$

■ Number 164

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$164^2 + 1677^2 := 1685^2$$

$$164^2 + 3360^2 := 3364^2$$

$$164^2 + 6723^2 := 6725^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(164, 1677, 1685)** $\Rightarrow 1685 - 164 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 72111$, $T_{1521} := 1677^2$,
 $E := \{329, 331, \dots, 3367, 3369\}$ or $E := \{1089, 1090, \dots, 2608, 2609\}$
2. **(164, 6723, 6725)** $\Rightarrow 6725 - 164 = 81^2$, $S_{81 \times 81} := 558009$, $T_{6561} := 6723^2$,
 $E := \{329, 331, \dots, 13447, 13449\}$ or $E := \{3609, 3610, \dots, 10168, 10169\}$

■ Number 165

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$165^2 + 220^2 := 275^2$	$165^2 + 532^2 := 557^2$	$165^2 + 1508^2 := 1517^2$
$165^2 + 280^2 := 325^2$	$165^2 + 900^2 := 915^2$	$165^2 + 2720^2 := 2725^2$
$165^2 + 396^2 := 429^2$	$165^2 + 1232^2 := 1243^2$	$165^2 + 4536^2 := 4539^2$
		$165^2 + 13612^2 := 13613^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(165, 1508, 1517)** $\Rightarrow 1517 - 1508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 9075$, $T_9 := 165^2$,
 $E := \{3017, 3019, \dots, 3031, 3033\}$ or $E := \{3021, 3022, \dots, 3028, 3029\}$
2. **(165, 532, 557)** $\Rightarrow 557 - 532 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 5445$, $T_{25} := 165^2$,
 $E := \{1065, 1067, \dots, 1111, 1113\}$ or $E := \{1077, 1078, \dots, 1100, 1101\}$

■ Number 166

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$166^2 + 6888^2 := 6890^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(166, 6888, 6890)** $\Rightarrow 6890 - 166 = 82^2$, $S_{82 \times 82} := 578592$, $T_{6724} := 6888^2$,
 $E := \{333, 335, \dots, 13777, 13779\}$

■ Number 167

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$167^2 + 13944^2 := 13945^2$$

■ Number 168

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$168^2 + 224^2 := 280^2$$

$$168^2 + 270^2 := 318^2$$

$$168^2 + 315^2 := 357^2$$

$$168^2 + 374^2 := 410^2$$

$$168^2 + 425^2 := 457^2$$

$$168^2 + 490^2 := 518^2$$

$$168^2 + 576^2 := 600^2$$

$$168^2 + 775^2 := 793^2$$

$$168^2 + 874^2 := 890^2$$

$$168^2 + 1001^2 := 1015^2$$

$$168^2 + 1170^2 := 1182^2$$

$$168^2 + 1760^2 := 1768^2$$

$$168^2 + 2349^2 := 2355^2$$

$$168^2 + 3526^2 := 3530^2$$

$$168^2 + 7055^2 := 7057^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(168, 874, 890)** $\Rightarrow 890 - 874 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 7056$, $T_{16} := 168^2$,
 $E := \{1749, 1751, \dots, 1777, 1779\}$
2. **(168, 374, 410)** $\Rightarrow 410 - 374 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 4704$, $T_{36} := 168^2$,
 $E := \{749, 751, \dots, 817, 819\}$
3. **(168, 425, 457)** $\Rightarrow 457 - 168 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 10625$, $T_{289} := 425^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 911, 913\}$ or $E := \{481, 482, \dots, 768, 769\}$
4. **(168, 775, 793)** $\Rightarrow 793 - 168 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 24025$, $T_{625} := 775^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 1583, 1585\}$ or $E := \{649, 650, \dots, 1272, 1273\}$
5. **(168, 1760, 1768)** $\Rightarrow 1768 - 168 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 77440$, $T_{1600} := 1760^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 3533, 3535\}$
6. **(168, 7055, 7057)** $\Rightarrow 7057 - 168 = 83^2$, $S_{83 \times 83} := 599675$, $T_{6889} := 7055^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 14111, 14113\}$ or $E := \{3781, 3782, \dots, 10668, 10669\}$

■ Number 169

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$169^2 + 1092^2 := 1105^2$$

$$169^2 + 14280^2 := 14281^2$$

■ Number 170

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$170^2 + 264^2 := 314^2$$

$$170^2 + 408^2 := 442^2$$

$$170^2 + 1440^2 := 1450^2$$

$$170^2 + 7224^2 := 7226^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(170, 264, 314)** $\Rightarrow 314 - 170 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 5808$, $T_{144} := 264^2$,
 $E := \{341, 343, \dots, 625, 627\}$

2. **(170, 7224, 7226)** $\Rightarrow 7226 - 170 = 84^2$, $S_{84 \times 84} := 621264$, $T_{7056} := 7224^2$,
 $E := \{341, 343, \dots, 14449, 14451\}$

■ Number 171

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$171^2 + 228^2 := 285^2$$

$$171^2 + 528^2 := 555^2$$

$$171^2 + 760^2 := 779^2$$

$$171^2 + 1620^2 := 1629^2$$

$$171^2 + 4872^2 := 4875^2$$

$$171^2 + 14620^2 := 14621^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(171, 1620, 1629)** $\Rightarrow 1629 - 1620 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 9747$, $T_9 := 171^2$,
 $E := \{3241, 3243, \dots, 3255, 3257\}$ or $E := \{3245, 3246, \dots, 3252, 3253\}$

■ Number 172

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$172^2 + 1845^2 := 1853^2$$

$$172^2 + 3696^2 := 3700^2$$

$$172^2 + 7395^2 := 7397^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(172, 1845, 1853)** $\Rightarrow 1853 - 172 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 83025$, $T_{1681} := 1845^2$,
 $E := \{345, 347, \dots, 3703, 3705\}$ or $E := \{1185, 1186, \dots, 2864, 2865\}$

2. **(172, 7395, 7397)** $\Rightarrow 7397 - 172 = 85^2$, $S_{85 \times 85} := 643365$, $T_{7225} := 7395^2$,
 $E := \{345, 347, \dots, 14791, 14793\}$ or $E := \{3957, 3958, \dots, 11180, 11181\}$

■ Number 173

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$173^2 + 14964^2 := 14965^2$$

■ Number 174

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$174^2 + 232^2 := 290^2$$

$$174^2 + 832^2 := 850^2$$

$$174^2 + 2520^2 := 2526^2$$

$$174^2 + 7568^2 := 7570^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(174, 832, 850)** $\Rightarrow 850 - 174 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 26624$, $T_{676} := 832^2$,
 $E := \{349, 351, \dots, 1697, 1699\}$

2. **(174, 7568, 7570)** $\Rightarrow 7570 - 174 = 86^2$, $S_{86 \times 86} := 665984$, $T_{7396} := 7568^2$,
 $E := \{349, 351, \dots, 15137, 15139\}$

■ Number 175

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$175^2 + 288^2 := 337^2$$

$$175^2 + 420^2 := 455^2$$

$$175^2 + 600^2 := 625^2$$

$$175^2 + 2184^2 := 2191^2$$

$$175^2 + 3060^2 := 3065^2$$

$$175^2 + 15312^2 := 15313^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(175, 600, 625)** $\Rightarrow 625 - 600 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 6125$, $T_{25} := 175^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 1247, 1249\}$ or $E := \{1213, 1214, \dots, 1236, 1237\}$

2. **(175, 288, 337)** $\Rightarrow 337 - 288 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 4375$, $T_{49} := 175^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 671, 673\}$ or $E := \{601, 602, \dots, 648, 649\}$

■ Number 176

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$176^2 + 210^2 := 274^2$$

$$176^2 + 330^2 := 374^2$$

$$176^2 + 468^2 := 500^2$$

$$176^2 + 693^2 := 715^2$$

$$176^2 + 960^2 := 976^2$$

$$176^2 + 1932^2 := 1940^2$$

$$176^2 + 3870^2 := 3874^2$$

$$176^2 + 7743^2 := 7745^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(176, 960, 976)** $\Rightarrow 976 - 960 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 7744$, $T_{16} := 176^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 1949, 1951\}$
2. **(176, 210, 274)** $\Rightarrow 274 - 210 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 3872$, $T_{64} := 176^2$,
 $E := \{421, 423, \dots, 545, 547\}$
3. **(176, 468, 500)** $\Rightarrow 500 - 176 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 12168$, $T_{324} := 468^2$,
 $E := \{353, 355, \dots, 997, 999\}$
4. **(176, 1932, 1940)** $\Rightarrow 1940 - 176 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 88872$, $T_{1764} := 1932^2$,
 $E := \{353, 355, \dots, 3877, 3879\}$
5. **(176, 7743, 7745)** $\Rightarrow 7745 - 176 = 87^2$, $S_{87 \times 87} := 689127$, $T_{7569} := 7743^2$,
 $E := \{353, 355, \dots, 15487, 15489\}$ or $E := \{4137, 4138, \dots, 11704, 11705\}$

■ Number 177

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$177^2 + 236^2 := 295^2$$

$$177^2 + 1736^2 := 1745^2$$

$$177^2 + 5220^2 := 5223^2$$

$$177^2 + 15664^2 := 15665^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(177, 1736, 1745)** $\Rightarrow 1745 - 1736 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 10443$, $T_9 := 177^2$,
 $E := \{3473, 3475, \dots, 3487, 3489\}$ or $E := \{3477, 3478, \dots, 3484, 3485\}$

■ Number 100

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$178^2 + 7920^2 := 7922^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(178, 7920, 7922)** $\Rightarrow 7922 - 178 = 88^2$, $S_{88 \times 88} := 712800$, $T_{7744} := 7920^2$,
 $E := \{357, 359, \dots, 15841, 15843\}$

■ **Number 179**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$179^2 + 16020^2 := 16021^2$$

■ **Number 180**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$180^2 + 189^2 := 261^2$$

$$180^2 + 240^2 := 300^2$$

$$180^2 + 273^2 := 327^2$$

$$180^2 + 299^2 := 349^2$$

$$180^2 + 385^2 := 425^2$$

$$180^2 + 432^2 := 468^2$$

$$180^2 + 525^2 := 555^2$$

$$180^2 + 663^2 := 687^2$$

$$180^2 + 800^2 := 820^2$$

$$180^2 + 891^2 := 909^2$$

$$180^2 + 1344^2 := 1356^2$$

$$180^2 + 1615^2 := 1625^2$$

$$180^2 + 2021^2 := 2029^2$$

$$180^2 + 2697^2 := 2703^2$$

$$180^2 + 4048^2 := 4052^2$$

$$180^2 + 8099^2 := 8101^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(180, 432, 468)** $\Rightarrow 468 - 432 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 5400$, $T_{36} := 180^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 933, 935\}$

2. **(180, 189, 261)** $\Rightarrow 261 - 180 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 3969$, $T_{81} := 189^2$,
 $E := \{361, 363, \dots, 519, 521\}$ or $E := \{401, 402, \dots, 480, 481\}$

3. **(180, 299, 349)** $\Rightarrow 349 - 180 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 6877$, $T_{169} := 299^2$,
 $E := \{361, 363, \dots, 695, 697\}$ or $E := \{445, 446, \dots, 612, 613\}$

4. **(180, 891, 909)** $\Rightarrow 909 - 180 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 29403$, $T_{729} := 891^2$,
 $E := \{361, 363, \dots, 1815, 1817\}$ or $E := \{725, 726, \dots, 1452, 1453\}$

5. **(180, 2021, 2029)** $\Rightarrow 2029 - 180 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 94987$, $T_{1849} := 2021^2$,
 $E := \{361, 363, \dots, 4055, 4057\}$ or $E := \{1285, 1286, \dots, 3132, 3133\}$

6. **(180, 8099, 8101)** $\Rightarrow 8101 - 180 = 89^2$, $S_{89 \times 89} := 737009$, $T_{7921} := 8099^2$,
 $E := \{361, 363, \dots, 16199, 16201\}$ or $E := \{4321, 4322, \dots, 12240, 12241\}$

■ Number 181

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$181^2 + 16380^2 := 16381^2$$

■ Number 182

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$182^2 + 624^2 := 650^2$$

$$182^2 + 1176^2 := 1190^2$$

$$182^2 + 8280^2 := 8282^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(182, 8280, 8282)** $\Rightarrow 8282 - 182 = 90^2$, $S_{90 \times 90} := 761760$, $T_{8100} := 8280^2$,
 $E := \{365, 367, \dots, 16561, 16563\}$

■ Number 183

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$183^2 + 244^2 := 305^2$$

$$183^2 + 1856^2 := 1865^2$$

$$183^2 + 5580^2 := 5583^2$$

$$183^2 + 16744^2 := 16745^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(183, 1856, 1865)** $\Rightarrow 1865 - 1856 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 11163$, $T_9 := 183^2$,
 $E := \{3713, 3715, \dots, 3727, 3729\}$ or $E := \{3717, 3718, \dots, 3724, 3725\}$

■ Number 184

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$184^2 + 345^2 := 391^2$$

$$184^2 + 513^2 := 545^2$$

$$184^2 + 1050^2 := 1066^2$$

$$184^2 + 2112^2 := 2120^2$$

$$184^2 + 4230^2 := 4234^2$$

$$184^2 + 8463^2 := 8465^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(184, 1050, 1066)** $\Rightarrow 1066 - 1050 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 8464$, $T_{16} := 184^2$,
 $E := \{2101, 2103, \dots, 2129, 2131\}$
2. **(184, 513, 545)** $\Rightarrow 545 - 184 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 13851$, $T_{361} := 513^2$,
 $E := \{369, 371, \dots, 1087, 1089\}$ or $E := \{549, 550, \dots, 908, 909\}$
3. **(184, 2112, 2120)** $\Rightarrow 2120 - 184 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 101376$, $T_{1936} := 2112^2$,
 $E := \{369, 371, \dots, 4237, 4239\}$
4. **(184, 8463, 8465)** $\Rightarrow 8465 - 184 = 91^2$, $S_{91 \times 91} := 787059$, $T_{8281} := 8463^2$,
 $E := \{369, 371, \dots, 16927, 16929\}$ or $E := \{4509, 4510, \dots, 12788, 12789\}$

■ **Number 185**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 185^2 + 444^2 := 481^2 & 185^2 + 3420^2 := 3425^2 \\
 185^2 + 672^2 := 697^2 & 185^2 + 17112^2 := 17113^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(185, 672, 697)** $\Rightarrow 697 - 672 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 6845$, $T_{25} := 185^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 1391, 1393\}$ or $E := \{1357, 1358, \dots, 1380, 1381\}$

■ **Number 186**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 186^2 + 248^2 := 310^2 & 186^2 + 2880^2 := 2886^2 \\
 186^2 + 952^2 := 970^2 & 186^2 + 8648^2 := 8650^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(186, 952, 970)** $\Rightarrow 970 - 186 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 32368$, $T_{784} := 952^2$,
 $E := \{373, 375, \dots, 1937, 1939\}$
2. **(186, 8648, 8650)** $\Rightarrow 8650 - 186 = 92^2$, $S_{92 \times 92} := 812912$, $T_{8464} := 8648^2$,
 $E := \{373, 375, \dots, 17297, 17299\}$

■ Number 187

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$187^2 + 1020^2 := 1037^2$$

$$187^2 + 1584^2 := 1595^2$$

$$187^2 + 17484^2 := 17485^2$$

■ Number 188

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$188^2 + 2205^2 := 2213^2$$

$$188^2 + 4416^2 := 4420^2$$

$$188^2 + 8835^2 := 8837^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(188, 2205, 2213)** $\Rightarrow 2213 - 188 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 108045$, $T_{2025} := 2205^2$,
 $E := \{377, 379, \dots, 4423, 4425\}$ or $E := \{1389, 1390, \dots, 3412, 3413\}$
2. **(188, 8835, 8837)** $\Rightarrow 8837 - 188 = 93^2$, $S_{93 \times 93} := 839325$, $T_{8649} := 8835^2$,
 $E := \{377, 379, \dots, 17671, 17673\}$ or $E := \{4701, 4702, \dots, 13348, 13349\}$

■ Number 189

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$189^2 + 252^2 := 315^2$$

$$189^2 + 340^2 := 389^2$$

$$189^2 + 648^2 := 675^2$$

$$189^2 + 840^2 := 861^2$$

$$189^2 + 5952^2 := 5955^2$$

$$189^2 + 1980^2 := 1989^2$$

$$189^2 + 2548^2 := 2555^2$$

$$189^2 + 17860^2 := 17861^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(189, 1980, 1989)** $\Rightarrow 1989 - 1980 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 11907$, $T_9 := 189^2$,
 $E := \{3961, 3963, \dots, 3975, 3977\}$ or $E := \{3965, 3966, \dots, 3972, 3973\}$
2. **(189, 340, 389)** $\Rightarrow 389 - 340 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 5103$, $T_{49} := 189^2$,
 $E := \{681, 683, \dots, 775, 777\}$ or $E := \{705, 706, \dots, 752, 753\}$

■ Number 190

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$190^2 + 336^2 := 386^2$$

$$190^2 + 456^2 := 494^2$$

$$190^2 + 1800^2 := 1810^2$$

$$190^2 + 9024^2 := 9026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(190, 336, 386)** $\Rightarrow 386 - 190 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 8064$, $T_{196} := 336^2$,
 $E := \{381, 383, \dots, 769, 771\}$

2. **(190, 9024, 9026)** $\Rightarrow 9026 - 190 = 94^2$, $S_{94 \times 94} := 866304$, $T_{8836} := 9024^2$,
 $E := \{381, 383, \dots, 18049, 18051\}$

■ Number 191

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$191^2 + 18240^2 := 18241^2$$

■ Number 192

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$192^2 + 220^2 := 292^2$$

$$192^2 + 256^2 := 320^2$$

$$192^2 + 360^2 := 408^2$$

$$192^2 + 494^2 := 530^2$$

$$192^2 + 560^2 := 592^2$$

$$192^2 + 756^2 := 780^2$$

$$192^2 + 1015^2 := 1033^2$$

$$192^2 + 1144^2 := 1160^2$$

$$192^2 + 1530^2 := 1542^2$$

$$192^2 + 2300^2 := 2308^2$$

$$192^2 + 3069^2 := 3075^2$$

$$192^2 + 4606^2 := 4610^2$$

$$192^2 + 9215^2 := 9217^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(192, 1144, 1160)** $\Rightarrow 1160 - 1144 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 9216$, $T_{16} := 192^2$,
 $E := \{2289, 2291, \dots, 2317, 2319\}$

2. **(192, 494, 530)** $\Rightarrow 530 - 494 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 6144$, $T_{36} := 192^2$,
 $E := \{989, 991, \dots, 1057, 1059\}$

3. **(192, 256, 320)** $\Rightarrow 320 - 256 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4608$, $T_{64} := 192^2$,
 $E := \{513, 515, \dots, 637, 639\}$

4. **(192, 220, 292)** $\Rightarrow 292 - 192 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 4840$, $T_{100} := 220^2$,
 $E := \{385, 387, \dots, 581, 583\}$
5. **(192, 560, 592)** $\Rightarrow 592 - 192 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 15680$, $T_{400} := 560^2$,
 $E := \{385, 387, \dots, 1181, 1183\}$
6. **(192, 1015, 1033)** $\Rightarrow 1033 - 192 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 35525$, $T_{841} := 1015^2$,
 $E := \{385, 387, \dots, 2063, 2065\}$ or $E := \{805, 806, \dots, 1644, 1645\}$
7. **(192, 2300, 2308)** $\Rightarrow 2308 - 192 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 115000$, $T_{2116} := 2300^2$,
 $E := \{385, 387, \dots, 4613, 4615\}$
8. **(192, 9215, 9217)** $\Rightarrow 9217 - 192 = 95^2$, $S_{95 \times 95} := 893855$, $T_{9025} := 9215^2$,
 $E := \{385, 387, \dots, 18431, 18433\}$ or $E := \{4897, 4898, \dots, 13920, 13921\}$

■ Number 193

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$193^2 + 18624^2 := 18625^2$$

■ Number 194

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$194^2 + 9408^2 := 9410^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(194, 9408, 9410)** $\Rightarrow 9410 - 194 = 96^2$, $S_{96 \times 96} := 921984$, $T_{9216} := 9408^2$,
 $E := \{389, 391, \dots, 18817, 18819\}$

■ Number 195

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$195^2 + 216^2 := 291^2$$

$$195^2 + 260^2 := 325^2$$

$$195^2 + 400^2 := 445^2$$

$$195^2 + 468^2 := 507^2$$

$$195^2 + 748^2 := 773^2$$

$$195^2 + 1260^2 := 1275^2$$

$$195^2 + 1456^2 := 1469^2$$

$$195^2 + 2108^2 := 2117^2$$

$$195^2 + 6336^2 := 6339^2$$

$$195^2 + 3800^2 := 3805^2$$

$$195^2 + 19012^2 := 19013^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(195, 2108, 2117)** $\Rightarrow 2117 - 2108 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 12675$, $T_9 := 195^2$,
 $E := \{4217, 4219, \dots, 4231, 4233\}$ or $E := \{4221, 4222, \dots, 4228, 4229\}$
2. **(195, 748, 773)** $\Rightarrow 773 - 748 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 7605$, $T_{25} := 195^2$,
 $E := \{1497, 1499, \dots, 1543, 1545\}$ or $E := \{1509, 1510, \dots, 1532, 1533\}$

■ Number 196

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll} 196^2 + 315^2 := 371^2 & 196^2 + 2397^2 := 2405^2 \\ 196^2 + 672^2 := 700^2 & 196^2 + 4800^2 := 4804^2 \\ 196^2 + 1365^2 := 1379^2 & 196^2 + 9603^2 := 9605^2 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(196, 2397, 2405)** $\Rightarrow 2405 - 196 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 122247$, $T_{2209} := 2397^2$,
 $E := \{393, 395, \dots, 4807, 4809\}$ or $E := \{1497, 1498, \dots, 3704, 3705\}$
2. **(196, 9603, 9605)** $\Rightarrow 9605 - 196 = 97^2$, $S_{97 \times 97} := 950697$, $T_{9409} := 9603^2$,
 $E := \{393, 395, \dots, 19207, 19209\}$ or $E := \{5097, 5098, \dots, 14504, 14505\}$

■ Number 197

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$197^2 + 19404^2 := 19405^2$$

■ Number 198

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll} 198^2 + 336^2 := 390^2 & 198^2 + 1080^2 := 1098^2 \\ 198^2 + 880^2 := 902^2 & 198^2 + 3264^2 := 3270^2 \\ 198^2 + 264^2 := 330^2 & 198^2 + 9800^2 := 9802^2 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(198, 1080, 1098)** $\Rightarrow 1098 - 198 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 38880$, $T_{900} := 1080^2$,
 $E := \{397, 399, \dots, 2193, 2195\}$
2. **(198, 9800, 9802)** $\Rightarrow 9802 - 198 = 98^2$, $S_{98 \times 98} := 980000$, $T_{9604} := 9800^2$,
 $E := \{397, 399, \dots, 19601, 19603\}$

■ **Number 199**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$199^2 + 19800^2 := 19801^2$$

■ **Number 200**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$200^2 + 210^2 := 290^2$	$200^2 + 609^2 := 641^2$	$200^2 + 2496^2 := 2504^2$
$200^2 + 375^2 := 425^2$	$200^2 + 1242^2 := 1258^2$	$200^2 + 4998^2 := 5002^2$
$200^2 + 480^2 := 520^2$	$200^2 + 1995^2 := 2005^2$	$200^2 + 990^2 := 1010^2$
		$200^2 + 9999^2 := 10001^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(200, 1242, 1258)** $\Rightarrow 1258 - 1242 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 10000$, $T_{16} := 200^2$,
 $E := \{2485, 2487, \dots, 2513, 2515\}$
2. **(200, 375, 425)** $\Rightarrow 425 - 200 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 9375$, $T_{225} := 375^2$,
 $E := \{401, 403, \dots, 847, 849\}$ or $E := \{513, 514, \dots, 736, 737\}$
3. **(200, 609, 641)** $\Rightarrow 641 - 200 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 17661$, $T_{441} := 609^2$,
 $E := \{401, 403, \dots, 1279, 1281\}$ or $E := \{621, 622, \dots, 1060, 1061\}$
4. **(200, 2496, 2504)** $\Rightarrow 2504 - 200 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 129792$, $T_{2304} := 2496^2$,
 $E := \{401, 403, \dots, 5005, 5007\}$
5. **(200, 9999, 10001)** $\Rightarrow 10001 - 200 = 99^2$, $S_{99 \times 99} := 1009899$, $T_{9801} := 9999^2$,
 $E := \{401, 403, \dots, 19999, 20001\}$ or $E := \{5301, 5302, \dots, 15100, 15101\}$

2.3 Pythagorean Triples: 201 to 300

■ Number 201

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$201^2 + 268^2 := 335^2$$

$$201^2 + 2240^2 := 2249^2$$

$$201^2 + 6732^2 := 6735^2$$

$$201^2 + 20200^2 := 20201^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(201, 2240, 2249)** $\Rightarrow 2249 - 2240 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 13467$, $T_9 := 201^2$,
 $E := \{4481, 4483, \dots, 4495, 4497\}$ or $E := \{4485, 4486, \dots, 4492, 4493\}$

■ Number 202

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$202^2 + 10200^2 := 10202^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(202, 10200, 10202)** $\Rightarrow 10202 - 202 = 100^2$, $S_{100 \times 100} := 1040400$, $T_{10000} := 10200^2$,
 $E := \{405, 407, \dots, 20401, 20403\}$

■ Number 203

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$203^2 + 396^2 := 445^2$$

$$203^2 + 696^2 := 725^2$$

$$203^2 + 2940^2 := 2947^2$$

$$203^2 + 20604^2 := 20605^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(203, 396, 445)** $\Rightarrow 445 - 396 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 5887$, $T_{49} := 203^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 887, 889\}$ or $E := \{817, 818, \dots, 864, 865\}$

■ Number 204

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$204^2 + 253^2 := 325^2$$

$$204^2 + 272^2 := 340^2$$

$$204^2 + 560^2 := 596^2$$

$$204^2 + 595^2 := 629^2$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 204^2 + 855^2 := 879^2 & \\
 204^2 + 1147^2 := 1165^2 & 204^2 + 3465^2 := 3471^2 \\
 204^2 + 1728^2 := 1740^2 & 204^2 + 5200^2 := 5204^2 \\
 204^2 + 2597^2 := 2605^2 & 204^2 + 10403^2 := 10405^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(204, 560, 596)** $\Rightarrow 596 - 560 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 6936$, $T_{36} := 204^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 1189, 1191\}$
2. **(204, 253, 325)** $\Rightarrow 325 - 204 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 5819$, $T_{121} := 253^2$,
 $E := \{409, 411, \dots, 647, 649\}$ or $E := \{469, 470, \dots, 588, 589\}$
3. **(204, 1147, 1165)** $\Rightarrow 1165 - 204 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 42439$, $T_{961} := 1147^2$,
 $E := \{409, 411, \dots, 2327, 2329\}$ or $E := \{889, 890, \dots, 1848, 1849\}$
4. **(204, 2597, 2605)** $\Rightarrow 2605 - 204 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 137641$, $T_{2401} := 2597^2$,
 $E := \{409, 411, \dots, 5207, 5209\}$ or $E := \{1609, 1610, \dots, 4008, 4009\}$
5. **(204, 10403, 10405)** $\Rightarrow 10405 - 204 = 101^2$, $S_{101 \times 101} := 1071509$, $T_{10201} := 10403^2$,
 $E := \{409, 411, \dots, 20807, 20809\}$ or $E := \{5509, 5510, \dots, 15708, 15709\}$

■ Number 205

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 205^2 + 492^2 := 533^2 & 205^2 + 4200^2 := 4205^2 \\
 205^2 + 828^2 := 853^2 & 205^2 + 21012^2 := 21013^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(205, 828, 853)** $\Rightarrow 853 - 828 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 8405$, $T_{25} := 205^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 1703, 1705\}$ or $E := \{1669, 1670, \dots, 1692, 1693\}$

■ Number 206

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$206^2 + 10608^2 := 10610^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(206, 10608, 10610)** $\Rightarrow 10610 - 206 = 102^2$, $S_{102 \times 102} := 1103232$, $T_{10404} := 10608^2$,
 $E := \{413, 415, \dots, 21217, 21219\}$

■ Number 207

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$207^2 + 224^2 := 305^2$$

$$207^2 + 276^2 := 345^2$$

$$207^2 + 780^2 := 807^2$$

$$207^2 + 920^2 := 943^2$$

$$207^2 + 2376^2 := 2385^2$$

$$207^2 + 7140^2 := 7143^2$$

$$207^2 + 21424^2 := 21425^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(207, 2376, 2385)** $\Rightarrow 2385 - 2376 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 14283$, $T_9 := 207^2$,
 $E := \{4753, 4755, \dots, 4767, 4769\}$ or $E := \{4757, 4758, \dots, 4764, 4765\}$
2. **(207, 224, 305)** $\Rightarrow 305 - 224 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 4761$, $T_{81} := 207^2$,
 $E := \{449, 451, \dots, 607, 609\}$ or $E := \{489, 490, \dots, 568, 569\}$

■ Number 208

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$208^2 + 306^2 := 370^2$$

$$208^2 + 390^2 := 442^2$$

$$208^2 + 660^2 := 692^2$$

$$208^2 + 819^2 := 845^2$$

$$208^2 + 1344^2 := 1360^2$$

$$208^2 + 2700^2 := 2708^2$$

$$208^2 + 5406^2 := 5410^2$$

$$208^2 + 10815^2 := 10817^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(208, 1344, 1360)** $\Rightarrow 1360 - 1344 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 10816$, $T_{16} := 208^2$,
 $E := \{2689, 2691, \dots, 2717, 2719\}$
2. **(208, 306, 370)** $\Rightarrow 370 - 306 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 5408$, $T_{64} := 208^2$,
 $E := \{613, 615, \dots, 737, 739\}$
3. **(208, 660, 692)** $\Rightarrow 692 - 208 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 19800$, $T_{484} := 660^2$,
 $E := \{417, 419, \dots, 1381, 1383\}$
4. **(208, 2700, 2708)** $\Rightarrow 2708 - 208 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 145800$, $T_{2500} := 2700^2$,
 $E := \{417, 419, \dots, 5413, 5415\}$
5. **(208, 10815, 10817)** $\Rightarrow 10817 - 208 = 103^2$, $S_{103 \times 103} := 1135575$, $T_{10609} := 10815^2$,
 $E := \{417, 419, \dots, 21631, 21633\}$ or $E := \{5721, 5722, \dots, 16328, 16329\}$

■ Number 209

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$209^2 + 1140^2 := 1159^2$$

$$209^2 + 1980^2 := 1991^2$$

$$209^2 + 21840^2 := 21841^2$$

■ Number 210

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$210^2 + 280^2 := 350^2$$

$$210^2 + 416^2 := 466^2$$

$$210^2 + 504^2 := 546^2$$

$$210^2 + 720^2 := 750^2$$

$$210^2 + 1216^2 := 1234^2$$

$$210^2 + 1568^2 := 1582^2$$

$$210^2 + 2200^2 := 2210^2$$

$$210^2 + 3672^2 := 3678^2$$

$$210^2 + 11024^2 := 11026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(210, 416, 466)** $\Rightarrow 466 - 210 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 10816$, $T_{256} := 416^2$,
 $E := \{421, 423, \dots, 929, 931\}$

2. **(210, 1216, 1234)** $\Rightarrow 1234 - 210 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 46208$, $T_{1024} := 1216^2$,
 $E := \{421, 423, \dots, 2465, 2467\}$

3. **(210, 11024, 11026)** $\Rightarrow 11026 - 210 = 104^2$, $S_{104 \times 104} := 1168544$, $T_{10816} := 11024^2$,
 $E := \{421, 423, \dots, 22049, 22051\}$

■ Number 211

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$211^2 + 22260^2 := 22261^2$$

■ Number 212

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$212^2 + 2805^2 := 2813^2$$

$$212^2 + 5616^2 := 5620^2$$

$$212^2 + 11235^2 := 11237^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(212, 2805, 2813)** $\Rightarrow 2813 - 212 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 154275$, $T_{2601} := 2805^2$,
 $E := \{425, 427, \dots, 5623, 5625\}$ or $E := \{1725, 1726, \dots, 4324, 4325\}$
2. **(212, 11235, 11237)** $\Rightarrow 11237 - 212 = 105^2$, $S_{105 \times 105} := 1202145$, $T_{11025} := 11235^2$,
 $E := \{425, 427, \dots, 22471, 22473\}$ or $E := \{5937, 5938, \dots, 16960, 16961\}$

■ Number 213

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll} 213^2 + 284^2 := 355^2 & 213^2 + 7560^2 := 7563^2 \\ 213^2 + 2516^2 := 2525^2 & 213^2 + 22684^2 := 22685^2 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(213, 2516, 2525)** $\Rightarrow 2525 - 2516 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 15123$, $T_9 := 213^2$,
 $E := \{5033, 5035, \dots, 5047, 5049\}$ or $E := \{5037, 5038, \dots, 5044, 5045\}$

■ Number 214

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$214^2 + 11448^2 := 11450^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(214, 11448, 11450)** $\Rightarrow 11450 - 214 = 106^2$, $S_{106 \times 106} := 1236384$, $T_{11236} := 11448^2$,
 $E := \{429, 431, \dots, 22897, 22899\}$

■ Number 215

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll} 215^2 + 516^2 := 559^2 & 215^2 + 4620^2 := 4625^2 \\ 215^2 + 912^2 := 937^2 & 215^2 + 23112^2 := 23113^2 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(215, 912, 937)** $\Rightarrow 937 - 912 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 9245$, $T_{25} := 215^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 1871, 1873\}$ or $E := \{1837, 1838, \dots, 1860, 1861\}$

■ Number 216

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$216^2 + 288^2 := 360^2$$

$$216^2 + 405^2 := 459^2$$

$$216^2 + 462^2 := 510^2$$

$$216^2 + 630^2 := 666^2$$

$$216^2 + 713^2 := 745^2$$

$$216^2 + 960^2 := 984^2$$

$$216^2 + 1287^2 := 1305^2$$

$$216^2 + 1450^2 := 1466^2$$

$$216^2 + 1938^2 := 1950^2$$

$$216^2 + 2912^2 := 2920^2$$

$$216^2 + 3885^2 := 3891^2$$

$$216^2 + 5830^2 := 5834^2$$

$$216^2 + 11663^2 := 11665^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(216, 1450, 1466)** $\Rightarrow 1466 - 1450 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 11664$, $T_{16} := 216^2$,
 $E := \{2901, 2903, \dots, 2929, 2931\}$
2. **(216, 630, 666)** $\Rightarrow 666 - 630 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 7776$, $T_{36} := 216^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 1329, 1331\}$
3. **(216, 288, 360)** $\Rightarrow 360 - 216 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6912$, $T_{144} := 288^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 717, 719\}$
4. **(216, 713, 745)** $\Rightarrow 745 - 216 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 22103$, $T_{529} := 713^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 1487, 1489\}$ or $E := \{697, 698, \dots, 1224, 1225\}$
5. **(216, 1287, 1305)** $\Rightarrow 1305 - 216 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 50193$, $T_{1089} := 1287^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 2607, 2609\}$ or $E := \{977, 978, \dots, 2064, 2065\}$
6. **(216, 2912, 2920)** $\Rightarrow 2920 - 216 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 163072$, $T_{2704} := 2912^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 5837, 5839\}$
7. **(216, 11663, 11665)** $\Rightarrow 11665 - 216 = 107^2$, $S_{107 \times 107} := 1271267$, $T_{11449} := 11663^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 23327, 23329\}$ or $E := \{6157, 6158, \dots, 17604, 17605\}$

■ Number 217

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$217^2 + 456^2 := 505^2$$

$$217^2 + 744^2 := 775^2$$

$$217^2 + 3360^2 := 3367^2$$

$$217^2 + 23544^2 := 23545^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(217, 456, 505)** $\Rightarrow 505 - 456 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 6727$, $T_{49} := 217^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 1007, 1009\}$ or $E := \{937, 938, \dots, 984, 985\}$

■ Number 218

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$218^2 + 11880^2 := 11882^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(218, 11880, 11882)** $\Rightarrow 11882 - 218 = 108^2$, $S_{108 \times 108} := 1306800$, $T_{11664} := 11880^2$,
 $E := \{437, 439, \dots, 23761, 23763\}$

■ Number 219

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$219^2 + 292^2 := 365^2$$

$$219^2 + 2660^2 := 2669^2$$

$$219^2 + 7992^2 := 7995^2$$

$$219^2 + 23980^2 := 23981^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(219, 2660, 2669)** $\Rightarrow 2669 - 2660 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 15987$, $T_9 := 219^2$,
 $E := \{5321, 5323, \dots, 5335, 5337\}$ or $E := \{5325, 5326, \dots, 5332, 5333\}$

■ Number 220

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$220^2 + 231^2 := 319^2$$

$$220^2 + 459^2 := 509^2$$

$$220^2 + 528^2 := 572^2$$

$$220^2 + 585^2 := 625^2$$

$$220^2 + 1089^2 := 1111^2$$

$$220^2 + 1200^2 := 1220^2$$

$$220^2 + 2415^2 := 2425^2$$

$$220^2 + 3021^2 := 3029^2$$

$$220^2 + 6048^2 := 6052^2$$

$$220^2 + 12099^2 := 12101^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- (220, 459, 509)** $\Rightarrow 509 - 220 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 12393$, $T_{289} := 459^2$,
 $E := \{441, 443, \dots, 1015, 1017\}$ or $E := \{585, 586, \dots, 872, 873\}$
- (220, 3021, 3029)** $\Rightarrow 3029 - 220 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 172197$, $T_{2809} := 3021^2$,
 $E := \{441, 443, \dots, 6055, 6057\}$ or $E := \{1845, 1846, \dots, 4652, 4653\}$
- (220, 12099, 12101)** $\Rightarrow 12101 - 220 = 109^2$, $S_{109 \times 109} := 1342989$, $T_{11881} := 12099^2$,
 $E := \{441, 443, \dots, 24199, 24201\}$ or $E := \{6381, 6382, \dots, 18260, 18261\}$

■ Number 221

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$221^2 + 1428^2 := 1445^2$$

$$221^2 + 1872^2 := 1885^2$$

$$221^2 + 24420^2 := 24421^2$$

■ Number 222

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$222^2 + 296^2 := 370^2$$

$$222^2 + 1360^2 := 1378^2$$

$$222^2 + 4104^2 := 4110^2$$

$$222^2 + 12320^2 := 12322^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(222, 1360, 1378)** $\Rightarrow 1378 - 222 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 54400$, $T_{1156} := 1360^2$,
 $E := \{445, 447, \dots, 2753, 2755\}$

2. **(222, 12320, 12322)** $\Rightarrow 12322 - 222 = 110^2$, $S_{110 \times 110} := 1379840$, $T_{12100} := 12320^2$,
 $E := \{445, 447, \dots, 24641, 24643\}$

■ Number 223

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$223^2 + 24864^2 := 24865^2$$

■ Number 224

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$224^2 + 360^2 := 424^2$$

$$224^2 + 420^2 := 476^2$$

$$224^2 + 768^2 := 800^2$$

$$224^2 + 882^2 := 910^2$$

$$224^2 + 1560^2 := 1576^2$$

$$224^2 + 1785^2 := 1799^2$$

$$224^2 + 3132^2 := 3140^2$$

$$224^2 + 6270^2 := 6274^2$$

$$224^2 + 12543^2 := 12545^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(224, 1560, 1576)** $\Rightarrow 1576 - 1560 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 12544$, $T_{16} := 224^2$,
 $E := \{3121, 3123, \dots, 3149, 3151\}$
2. **(224, 360, 424)** $\Rightarrow 424 - 360 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 6272$, $T_{64} := 224^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 845, 847\}$
3. **(224, 768, 800)** $\Rightarrow 800 - 224 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 24576$, $T_{576} := 768^2$,
 $E := \{449, 451, \dots, 1597, 1599\}$
4. **(224, 3132, 3140)** $\Rightarrow 3140 - 224 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 181656$, $T_{2916} := 3132^2$,
 $E := \{449, 451, \dots, 6277, 6279\}$
5. **(224, 12543, 12545)** $\Rightarrow 12545 - 224 = 111^2$, $S_{111 \times 111} := 1417359$, $T_{12321} := 12543^2$,
 $E := \{449, 451, \dots, 25087, 25089\}$ or $E := \{6609, 6610, \dots, 18928, 18929\}$

■ Number 225

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$225^2 + 272^2 := 353^2$	$225^2 + 924^2 := 951^2$	$225^2 + 2808^2 := 2817^2$
$225^2 + 300^2 := 375^2$	$225^2 + 1000^2 := 1025^2$	$225^2 + 5060^2 := 5065^2$
$225^2 + 540^2 := 585^2$	$225^2 + 1680^2 := 1695^2$	$225^2 + 8436^2 := 8439^2$
		$225^2 + 25312^2 := 25313^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(225, 2808, 2817)** $\Rightarrow 2817 - 2808 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 16875$, $T_9 := 225^2$,
 $E := \{5617, 5619, \dots, 5631, 5633\}$ or $E := \{5621, 5622, \dots, 5628, 5629\}$
2. **(225, 1000, 1025)** $\Rightarrow 1025 - 1000 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 10125$, $T_{25} := 225^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 2047, 2049\}$ or $E := \{2013, 2014, \dots, 2036, 2037\}$
3. **(225, 272, 353)** $\Rightarrow 353 - 272 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 5625$, $T_{81} := 225^2$,
 $E := \{545, 547, \dots, 703, 705\}$ or $E := \{585, 586, \dots, 664, 665\}$

■ Number 226

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$226^2 + 12768^2 := 12770^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(226, 12768, 12770)** $\Rightarrow 12770 - 226 = 112^2$, $S_{112 \times 112} := 1455552$, $T_{12544} := 12768^2$,
 $E := \{453, 455, \dots, 25537, 25539\}$

■ Number 227

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$227^2 + 25764^2 := 25765^2$$

■ Number 228

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$228^2 + 304^2 := 380^2$$

$$228^2 + 325^2 := 397^2$$

$$228^2 + 665^2 := 703^2$$

$$228^2 + 704^2 := 740^2$$

$$228^2 + 1071^2 := 1095^2$$

$$228^2 + 1435^2 := 1453^2$$

$$228^2 + 2160^2 := 2172^2$$

$$228^2 + 3245^2 := 3253^2$$

$$228^2 + 4329^2 := 4335^2$$

$$228^2 + 6496^2 := 6500^2$$

$$228^2 + 12995^2 := 12997^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(228, 704, 740)** $\Rightarrow 740 - 704 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 8664$, $T_{36} := 228^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 1477, 1479\}$

2. **(228, 325, 397)** $\Rightarrow 397 - 228 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 8125$, $T_{169} := 325^2$,
 $E := \{457, 459, \dots, 791, 793\}$ or $E := \{541, 542, \dots, 708, 709\}$

3. **(228, 1435, 1453)** $\Rightarrow 1453 - 228 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 58835$, $T_{1225} := 1435^2$,
 $E := \{457, 459, \dots, 2903, 2905\}$ or $E := \{1069, 1070, \dots, 2292, 2293\}$

4. **(228, 3245, 3253)** $\Rightarrow 3253 - 228 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 191455$, $T_{3025} := 3245^2$,
 $E := \{457, 459, \dots, 6503, 6505\}$ or $E := \{1969, 1970, \dots, 4992, 4993\}$

5. **(228, 12995, 12997)** $\Rightarrow 12997 - 228 = 113^2$, $S_{113 \times 113} := 1494425$, $T_{12769} := 12995^2$,
 $E := \{457, 459, \dots, 25991, 25993\}$ or $E := \{6841, 6842, \dots, 19608, 19609\}$

■ Number 229

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$229^2 + 26220^2 := 26221^2$$

■ Number 230

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$230^2 + 504^2 := 554^2$$

$$230^2 + 552^2 := 598^2$$

$$230^2 + 2640^2 := 2650^2$$

$$230^2 + 13224^2 := 13226^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

$$1. \text{ (230, 504, 554)} \Rightarrow 554 - 230 = 18^2, S_{18 \times 18} := 14112, T_{324} := 504^2,$$

$$E := \{461, 463, \dots, 1105, 1107\}$$

$$2. \text{ (230, 13224, 13226)} \Rightarrow 13226 - 230 = 114^2, S_{114 \times 114} := 1533984, T_{12996} := 13224^2,$$

$$E := \{461, 463, \dots, 26449, 26451\}$$

■ Number 231

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$231^2 + 308^2 := 385^2$$

$$231^2 + 392^2 := 455^2$$

$$231^2 + 520^2 := 569^2$$

$$231^2 + 792^2 := 825^2$$

$$231^2 + 2960^2 := 2969^2$$

$$231^2 + 1260^2 := 1281^2$$

$$231^2 + 2420^2 := 2431^2$$

$$231^2 + 3808^2 := 3815^2$$

$$231^2 + 8892^2 := 8895^2$$

$$231^2 + 26680^2 := 26681^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

$$1. \text{ (231, 2960, 2969)} \Rightarrow 2969 - 2960 = 3^2, S_{3 \times 3} := 17787, T_9 := 231^2,$$

$$E := \{5921, 5923, \dots, 5935, 5937\} \text{ or } E := \{5925, 5926, \dots, 5932, 5933\}$$

$$2. \text{ (231, 520, 569)} \Rightarrow 569 - 520 = 7^2, S_{7 \times 7} := 7623, T_{49} := 231^2,$$

$$E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 1135, 1137\} \text{ or } E := \{1065, 1066, \dots, 1112, 1113\}$$

■ Number 232

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$232^2 + 435^2 := 493^2$$

$$232^2 + 825^2 := 857^2$$

$$232^2 + 1674^2 := 1690^2$$

$$232^2 + 3360^2 := 3368^2$$

$$232^2 + 6726^2 := 6730^2$$

$$232^2 + 13455^2 := 13457^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(232, 1674, 1690)** $\Rightarrow 1690 - 1674 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 13456$, $T_{16} := 232^2$,
 $E := \{3349, 3351, \dots, 3377, 3379\}$
2. **(232, 825, 857)** $\Rightarrow 857 - 232 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 27225$, $T_{625} := 825^2$,
 $E := \{465, 467, \dots, 1711, 1713\}$ or $E := \{777, 778, \dots, 1400, 1401\}$
3. **(232, 3360, 3368)** $\Rightarrow 3368 - 232 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 201600$, $T_{3136} := 3360^2$,
 $E := \{465, 467, \dots, 6733, 6735\}$
4. **(232, 13455, 13457)** $\Rightarrow 13457 - 232 = 115^2$, $S_{115 \times 115} := 1574235$, $T_{13225} := 13455^2$,
 $E := \{465, 467, \dots, 26911, 26913\}$ or $E := \{7077, 7078, \dots, 20300, 20301\}$

■ Number 233

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$233^2 + 27144^2 := 27145^2$$

■ Number 234

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$234^2 + 312^2 := 390^2$$

$$234^2 + 480^2 := 534^2$$

$$234^2 + 1040^2 := 1066^2$$

$$234^2 + 1512^2 := 1530^2$$

$$234^2 + 4560^2 := 4566^2$$

$$234^2 + 13688^2 := 13690^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(234, 1512, 1530)** $\Rightarrow 1530 - 234 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 63504$, $T_{1296} := 1512^2$,
 $E := \{469, 471, \dots, 3057, 3059\}$
2. **(234, 13688, 13690)** $\Rightarrow 13690 - 234 = 116^2$, $S_{116 \times 116} := 1615184$, $T_{13456} := 13688^2$,
 $E := \{469, 471, \dots, 27377, 27379\}$

■ Number 235

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$235^2 + 564^2 := 611^2$$

$$235^2 + 1092^2 := 1117^2$$

$$235^2 + 5520^2 := 5525^2$$

$$235^2 + 27612^2 := 27613^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(235, 1092, 1117)** $\Rightarrow 1117 - 1092 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 11045$, $T_{25} := 235^2$,
 $E := \{2185, 2187, \dots, 2231, 2233\}$ or $E := \{2197, 2198, \dots, 2220, 2221\}$

■ Number 236

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$236^2 + 3477^2 := 3485^2$$

$$236^2 + 6960^2 := 6964^2$$

$$236^2 + 13923^2 := 13925^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(236, 3477, 3485)** $\Rightarrow 3485 - 236 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 212097$, $T_{3249} := 3477^2$,
 $E := \{473, 475, \dots, 6967, 6969\}$ or $E := \{2097, 2098, \dots, 5344, 5345\}$
2. **(236, 13923, 13925)** $\Rightarrow 13925 - 236 = 117^2$, $S_{117 \times 117} := 1656837$, $T_{13689} := 13923^2$,
 $E := \{473, 475, \dots, 27847, 27849\}$ or $E := \{7317, 7318, \dots, 21004, 21005\}$

■ Number 237

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$237^2 + 316^2 := 395^2$$

$$237^2 + 3116^2 := 3125^2$$

$$237^2 + 9360^2 := 9363^2$$

$$237^2 + 28084^2 := 28085^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(237, 3116, 3125)** $\Rightarrow 3125 - 3116 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 18723$, $T_9 := 237^2$,
 $E := \{6233, 6235, \dots, 6247, 6249\}$ or $E := \{6237, 6238, \dots, 6244, 6245\}$

■ Number 238

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$238^2 + 240^2 := 338^2$$

$$238^2 + 816^2 := 850^2$$

$$238^2 + 2016^2 := 2030^2$$

$$238^2 + 14160^2 := 14162^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(238, 240, 338)** $\Rightarrow 338 - 238 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5760$, $T_{100} := 240^2$,
 $E := \{477, 479, \dots, 673, 675\}$

2. **(238, 14160, 14162)** $\Rightarrow 14162 - 238 = 118^2$, $S_{118 \times 118} := 1699200$, $T_{13924} := 14160^2$,
 $E := \{477, 479, \dots, 28321, 28323\}$

■ Number 239

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$239^2 + 28560^2 := 28561^2$$

■ Number 240

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$240^2 + 252^2 := 348^2$$

$$240^2 + 275^2 := 365^2$$

$$240^2 + 320^2 := 400^2$$

$$240^2 + 364^2 := 436^2$$

$$240^2 + 418^2 := 482^2$$

$$240^2 + 450^2 := 510^2$$

$$240^2 + 551^2 := 601^2$$

$$240^2 + 576^2 := 624^2$$

$$240^2 + 700^2 := 740^2$$

$$240^2 + 782^2 := 818^2$$

$$240^2 + 884^2 := 916^2$$

$$240^2 + 945^2 := 975^2$$

$$240^2 + 1188^2 := 1212^2$$

$$240^2 + 1430^2 := 1450^2$$

$$240^2 + 1591^2 := 1609^2$$

$$240^2 + 1792^2 := 1808^2$$

$$240^2 + 2394^2 := 2406^2$$

$$240^2 + 2875^2 := 2885^2$$

$$240^2 + 3596^2 := 3604^2$$

$$240^2 + 4797^2 := 4803^2$$

$$240^2 + 7198^2 := 7202^2$$

$$240^2 + 14399^2 := 14401^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(240, 1792, 1808)** $\Rightarrow 1808 - 1792 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 14400$, $T_{16} := 240^2$,
 $E := \{3585, 3587, \dots, 3613, 3615\}$

2. **(240, 782, 818)** $\Rightarrow 818 - 782 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 9600$, $T_{36} := 240^2$,
 $E := \{1565, 1567, \dots, 1633, 1635\}$

3. **(240, 418, 482)** $\Rightarrow 482 - 418 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 7200$, $T_{64} := 240^2$,
 $E := \{837, 839, \dots, 961, 963\}$

4. **(240, 364, 436)** $\Rightarrow 436 - 240 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 9464$, $T_{196} := 364^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 869, 871\}$
5. **(240, 551, 601)** $\Rightarrow 601 - 240 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 15979$, $T_{361} := 551^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 1199, 1201\}$ or $E := \{661, 662, \dots, 1020, 1021\}$
6. **(240, 884, 916)** $\Rightarrow 916 - 240 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 30056$, $T_{676} := 884^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 1829, 1831\}$
7. **(240, 1591, 1609)** $\Rightarrow 1609 - 240 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 68413$, $T_{1369} := 1591^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 3215, 3217\}$ or $E := \{1165, 1166, \dots, 2532, 2533\}$
8. **(240, 3596, 3604)** $\Rightarrow 3604 - 240 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 222952$, $T_{3364} := 3596^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 7205, 7207\}$
9. **(240, 14399, 14401)** $\Rightarrow 14401 - 240 = 119^2$, $S_{119 \times 119} := 1742279$, $T_{14161} := 14399^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 28799, 28801\}$ or $E := \{7561, 7562, \dots, 21720, 21721\}$

■ Number 241

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$241^2 + 29040^2 := 29041^2$$

■ Number 242

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$242^2 + 1320^2 := 1342^2$$

$$242^2 + 14640^2 := 14642^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(242, 14640, 14642)** $\Rightarrow 14642 - 242 = 120^2$, $S_{120 \times 120} := 1786080$, $T_{14400} := 14640^2$,
 $E := \{485, 487, \dots, 29281, 29283\}$

■ Number 243

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$243^2 + 324^2 := 405^2$$

$$243^2 + 1080^2 := 1107^2$$

$$243^2 + 3276^2 := 3285^2$$

$$243^2 + 9840^2 := 9843^2$$

$$243^2 + 29524^2 := 29525^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(243, 3276, 3285)** $\Rightarrow 3285 - 3276 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 19683$, $T_9 := 243^2$,
 $E := \{6553, 6555, \dots, 6567, 6569\}$ or $E := \{6557, 6558, \dots, 6564, 6565\}$
2. **(243, 324, 405)** $\Rightarrow 405 - 324 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 6561$, $T_{81} := 243^2$,
 $E := \{649, 651, \dots, 807, 809\}$ or $E := \{689, 690, \dots, 768, 769\}$

■ **Number 244**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$244^2 + 3717^2 := 3725^2$$

$$244^2 + 7440^2 := 7444^2$$

$$244^2 + 14883^2 := 14885^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(244, 3717, 3725)** $\Rightarrow 3725 - 244 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 234171$, $T_{3481} := 3717^2$,
 $E := \{489, 491, \dots, 7447, 7449\}$ or $E := \{2229, 2230, \dots, 5708, 5709\}$
2. **(244, 14883, 14885)** $\Rightarrow 14885 - 244 = 121^2$, $S_{121 \times 121} := 1830609$, $T_{14641} := 14883^2$,
 $E := \{489, 491, \dots, 29767, 29769\}$ or $E := \{7809, 7810, \dots, 22448, 22449\}$

■ **Number 245**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$245^2 + 588^2 := 637^2$$

$$245^2 + 840^2 := 875^2$$

$$245^2 + 1188^2 := 1213^2$$

$$245^2 + 4284^2 := 4291^2$$

$$245^2 + 6000^2 := 6005^2$$

$$245^2 + 30012^2 := 30013^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(245, 1188, 1213)** $\Rightarrow 1213 - 1188 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 12005$, $T_{25} := 245^2$,
 $E := \{2377, 2379, \dots, 2423, 2425\}$ or $E := \{2389, 2390, \dots, 2412, 2413\}$
2. **(245, 588, 637)** $\Rightarrow 637 - 588 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 8575$, $T_{49} := 245^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 1271, 1273\}$ or $E := \{1201, 1202, \dots, 1248, 1249\}$

■ Number 246

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$246^2 + 328^2 := 410^2$$

$$246^2 + 1672^2 := 1690^2$$

$$246^2 + 5040^2 := 5046^2$$

$$246^2 + 15128^2 := 15130^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(246, 1672, 1690)** $\Rightarrow 1690 - 246 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 73568$, $T_{1444} := 1672^2$,
 $E := \{493, 495, \dots, 3377, 3379\}$

2. **(246, 15128, 15130)** $\Rightarrow 15130 - 246 = 122^2$, $S_{122 \times 122} := 1875872$, $T_{14884} := 15128^2$,
 $E := \{493, 495, \dots, 30257, 30259\}$

■ Number 247

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$247^2 + 1596^2 := 1615^2$$

$$247^2 + 2340^2 := 2353^2$$

$$247^2 + 30504^2 := 30505^2$$

■ Number 248

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$248^2 + 465^2 := 527^2$$

$$248^2 + 945^2 := 977^2$$

$$248^2 + 1914^2 := 1930^2$$

$$248^2 + 3840^2 := 3848^2$$

$$248^2 + 7686^2 := 7690^2$$

$$248^2 + 15375^2 := 15377^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(248, 1914, 1930)** $\Rightarrow 1930 - 1914 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 15376$, $T_{16} := 248^2$,
 $E := \{3829, 3831, \dots, 3857, 3859\}$

2. **(248, 945, 977)** $\Rightarrow 977 - 248 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 33075$, $T_{729} := 945^2$,
 $E := \{497, 499, \dots, 1951, 1953\}$ or $E := \{861, 862, \dots, 1588, 1589\}$

3. **(248, 3840, 3848)** $\Rightarrow 3848 - 248 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 245760$, $T_{3600} := 3840^2$,
 $E := \{497, 499, \dots, 7693, 7695\}$

4. **(248, 15375, 15377)** $\Rightarrow 15377 - 248 = 123^2$, $S_{123 \times 123} := 1921875$, $T_{15129} := 15375^2$,
 $E := \{497, 499, \dots, 30751, 30753\}$ or $E := \{8061, 8062, \dots, 23188, 23189\}$

■ Number 249

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 249^2 + 332^2 := 415^2 & 249^2 + 10332^2 := 10335^2 \\ 249^2 + 3440^2 := 3449^2 & 249^2 + 31000^2 := 31001^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(249, 3440, 3449)** $\Rightarrow 3449 - 3440 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 20667$, $T_9 := 249^2$,
 $E := \{6881, 6883, \dots, 6895, 6897\}$ or $E := \{6885, 6886, \dots, 6892, 6893\}$

■ Number 250

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{l} 250^2 + 600^2 := 650^2 \\ 250^2 + 3120^2 := 3130^2 \\ 250^2 + 15624^2 := 15626^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(250, 600, 650)** $\Rightarrow 650 - 250 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 18000$, $T_{400} := 600^2$,
 $E := \{501, 503, \dots, 1297, 1299\}$

2. **(250, 15624, 15626)** $\Rightarrow 15626 - 250 = 124^2$, $S_{124 \times 124} := 1968624$, $T_{15376} := 15624^2$,
 $E := \{501, 503, \dots, 31249, 31251\}$

■ Number 251

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$251^2 + 31500^2 := 31501^2$$

■ Number 252

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$252^2 + 275^2 := 373^2$$

$$252^2 + 336^2 := 420^2$$

$$252^2 + 405^2 := 477^2$$

$$252^2 + 539^2 := 595^2$$

$$252^2 + 561^2 := 615^2$$

$$252^2 + 735^2 := 777^2$$

$$252^2 + 864^2 := 900^2$$

$$252^2 + 1120^2 := 1148^2$$

$$252^2 + 1311^2 := 1335^2$$

$$252^2 + 1755^2 := 1773^2$$

$$252^2 + 2261^2 := 2275^2$$

$$252^2 + 2640^2 := 2652^2$$

$$252^2 + 3965^2 := 3973^2$$

$$252^2 + 5289^2 := 5295^2$$

$$252^2 + 7936^2 := 7940^2$$

$$252^2 + 15875^2 := 15877^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(252, 864, 900)** $\Rightarrow 900 - 864 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 10584$, $T_{36} := 252^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 1797, 1799\}$
2. **(252, 275, 373)** $\Rightarrow 373 - 252 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 6875$, $T_{121} := 275^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 743, 745\}$ or $E := \{565, 566, \dots, 684, 685\}$
3. **(252, 405, 477)** $\Rightarrow 477 - 252 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 10935$, $T_{225} := 405^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 951, 953\}$ or $E := \{617, 618, \dots, 840, 841\}$
4. **(252, 1755, 1773)** $\Rightarrow 1773 - 252 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 78975$, $T_{1521} := 1755^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 3543, 3545\}$ or $E := \{1265, 1266, \dots, 2784, 2785\}$
5. **(252, 3965, 3973)** $\Rightarrow 3973 - 252 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 257725$, $T_{3721} := 3965^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 7943, 7945\}$ or $E := \{2365, 2366, \dots, 6084, 6085\}$
6. **(252, 15875, 15877)** $\Rightarrow 15877 - 252 = 125^2$, $S_{125 \times 125} := 2016125$, $T_{15625} := 15875^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 31751, 31753\}$ or $E := \{8317, 8318, \dots, 23940, 23941\}$

■ Number 253

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$253^2 + 1380^2 := 1403^2$$

$$253^2 + 2904^2 := 2915^2$$

$$253^2 + 32004^2 := 32005^2$$

■ Number 254

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$254^2 + 16128^2 := 16130^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(254, 16128, 16130)** $\Rightarrow 16130 - 254 = 126^2$, $S_{126 \times 126} := 2064384$, $T_{15876} := 16128^2$,
 $E := \{509, 511, \dots, 32257, 32259\}$

■ Number 255

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$255^2 + 340^2 := 425^2$$

$$255^2 + 396^2 := 471^2$$

$$255^2 + 612^2 := 663^2$$

$$255^2 + 700^2 := 745^2$$

$$255^2 + 1288^2 := 1313^2$$

$$255^2 + 1904^2 := 1921^2$$

$$255^2 + 2160^2 := 2175^2$$

$$255^2 + 3608^2 := 3617^2$$

$$255^2 + 6500^2 := 6505^2$$

$$255^2 + 10836^2 := 10839^2$$

$$255^2 + 32512^2 := 32513^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(255, 3608, 3617)** $\Rightarrow 3617 - 3608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 21675$, $T_9 := 255^2$,
 $E := \{7217, 7219, \dots, 7231, 7233\}$ or $E := \{7221, 7222, \dots, 7228, 7229\}$
2. **(255, 1288, 1313)** $\Rightarrow 1313 - 1288 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 13005$, $T_{25} := 255^2$,
 $E := \{2577, 2579, \dots, 2623, 2625\}$ or $E := \{2589, 2590, \dots, 2612, 2613\}$

■ Number 256

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$256^2 + 480^2 := 544^2$$

$$256^2 + 1008^2 := 1040^2$$

$$256^2 + 2040^2 := 2056^2$$

$$256^2 + 4092^2 := 4100^2$$

$$256^2 + 8190^2 := 8194^2$$

$$256^2 + 16383^2 := 16385^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(256, 2040, 2056)** $\Rightarrow 2056 - 2040 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 16384$, $T_{16} := 256^2$,
 $E := \{4081, 4083, \dots, 4109, 4111\}$
2. **(256, 480, 544)** $\Rightarrow 544 - 480 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 8192$, $T_{64} := 256^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 1085, 1087\}$
3. **(256, 1008, 1040)** $\Rightarrow 1040 - 256 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 36288$, $T_{784} := 1008^2$,
 $E := \{513, 515, \dots, 2077, 2079\}$
4. **(256, 4092, 4100)** $\Rightarrow 4100 - 256 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 270072$, $T_{3844} := 4092^2$,
 $E := \{513, 515, \dots, 8197, 8199\}$
5. **(256, 16383, 16385)** $\Rightarrow 16385 - 256 = 127^2$, $S_{127 \times 127} := 2113407$, $T_{16129} := 16383^2$,
 $E := \{513, 515, \dots, 32767, 32769\}$ or $E := \{8577, 8578, \dots, 24704, 24705\}$

■ Number 257

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$257^2 + 33024^2 := 33025^2$$

■ Number 258

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$258^2 + 344^2 := 430^2$$

$$258^2 + 1840^2 := 1858^2$$

$$258^2 + 5544^2 := 5550^2$$

$$258^2 + 16640^2 := 16642^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(258, 1840, 1858)** $\Rightarrow 1858 - 258 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 84640$, $T_{1600} := 1840^2$,

$$E := \{517, 519, \dots, 3713, 3715\}$$

2. **(258, 16640, 16642)** $\Rightarrow 16642 - 258 = 128^2$, $S_{128 \times 128} := 2163200$, $T_{16384} := 16640^2$,

$$E := \{517, 519, \dots, 33281, 33283\}$$

■ Number 259

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$259^2 + 660^2 := 709^2$$

$$259^2 + 888^2 := 925^2$$

$$259^2 + 4788^2 := 4795^2$$

$$259^2 + 33540^2 := 33541^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(259, 660, 709)** $\Rightarrow 709 - 660 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 9583$, $T_{49} := 259^2$,

$$E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 1415, 1417\} \text{ or } E := \{1345, 1346, \dots, 1392, 1393\}$$

■ Number 260

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$260^2 + 273^2 := 377^2$$

$$260^2 + 288^2 := 388^2$$

$$260^2 + 624^2 := 676^2$$

$$260^2 + 651^2 := 701^2$$

$$260^2 + 825^2 := 865^2$$

$$260^2 + 1287^2 := 1313^2$$

$$260^2 + 1680^2 := 1700^2$$

$$260^2 + 3375^2 := 3385^2$$

$$260^2 + 4221^2 := 4229^2$$

$$260^2 + 8448^2 := 8452^2$$

$$260^2 + 16899^2 := 16901^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(260, 288, 388)** $\Rightarrow 388 - 288 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 6760$, $T_{100} := 260^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 773, 775\}$
2. **(260, 651, 701)** $\Rightarrow 701 - 260 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 20181$, $T_{441} := 651^2$,
 $E := \{521, 523, \dots, 1399, 1401\}$ or $E := \{741, 742, \dots, 1180, 1181\}$
3. **(260, 4221, 4229)** $\Rightarrow 4229 - 260 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 282807$, $T_{3969} := 4221^2$,
 $E := \{521, 523, \dots, 8455, 8457\}$ or $E := \{2505, 2506, \dots, 6472, 6473\}$
4. **(260, 16899, 16901)** $\Rightarrow 16901 - 260 = 129^2$, $S_{129 \times 129} := 2213769$, $T_{16641} := 16899^2$,
 $E := \{521, 523, \dots, 33799, 33801\}$ or $E := \{8841, 8842, \dots, 25480, 25481\}$

■ Number 261

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$261^2 + 348^2 := 435^2$$

$$261^2 + 380^2 := 461^2$$

$$261^2 + 1160^2 := 1189^2$$

$$261^2 + 1248^2 := 1275^2$$

$$261^2 + 3780^2 := 3789^2$$

$$261^2 + 11352^2 := 11355^2$$

$$261^2 + 34060^2 := 34061^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(261, 3780, 3789)** $\Rightarrow 3789 - 3780 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 22707$, $T_9 := 261^2$,
 $E := \{7561, 7563, \dots, 7575, 7577\}$ or $E := \{7565, 7566, \dots, 7572, 7573\}$
2. **(261, 380, 461)** $\Rightarrow 461 - 380 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 7569$, $T_{81} := 261^2$,
 $E := \{761, 763, \dots, 919, 921\}$ or $E := \{801, 802, \dots, 880, 881\}$

■ Number 262

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$262^2 + 17160^2 := 17162^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(262, 17160, 17162)** $\Rightarrow 17162 - 262 = 130^2$, $S_{130 \times 130} := 2265120$, $T_{16900} := 17160^2$,
 $E := \{525, 527, \dots, 34321, 34323\}$

■ **Number 263**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$263^2 + 34584^2 := 34585^2$$

■ **Number 264**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$264^2 + 315^2 := 411^2$$

$$264^2 + 352^2 := 440^2$$

$$264^2 + 448^2 := 520^2$$

$$264^2 + 495^2 := 561^2$$

$$264^2 + 702^2 := 750^2$$

$$264^2 + 770^2 := 814^2$$

$$264^2 + 950^2 := 986^2$$

$$264^2 + 1073^2 := 1105^2$$

$$264^2 + 1440^2 := 1464^2$$

$$264^2 + 1573^2 := 1595^2$$

$$264^2 + 1927^2 := 1945^2$$

$$264^2 + 2170^2 := 2186^2$$

$$264^2 + 2898^2 := 2910^2$$

$$264^2 + 4352^2 := 4360^2$$

$$264^2 + 5805^2 := 5811^2$$

$$264^2 + 8710^2 := 8714^2$$

$$264^2 + 17423^2 := 17425^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(264, 2170, 2186)** $\Rightarrow 2186 - 2170 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 17424$, $T_{16} := 264^2$,
 $E := \{4341, 4343, \dots, 4369, 4371\}$

2. **(264, 950, 986)** $\Rightarrow 986 - 950 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 11616$, $T_{36} := 264^2$,
 $E := \{1901, 1903, \dots, 1969, 1971\}$

3. **(264, 448, 520)** $\Rightarrow 520 - 264 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 12544$, $T_{256} := 448^2$,
 $E := \{529, 531, \dots, 1037, 1039\}$

4. **(264, 1073, 1105)** $\Rightarrow 1105 - 264 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 39701$, $T_{841} := 1073^2$,
 $E := \{529, 531, \dots, 2207, 2209\}$ or $E := \{949, 950, \dots, 1788, 1789\}$

5. **(264, 1927, 1945)** $\Rightarrow 1945 - 264 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 90569$, $T_{1681} := 1927^2$,
 $E := \{529, 531, \dots, 3887, 3889\}$ or $E := \{1369, 1370, \dots, 3048, 3049\}$

6. **(264, 4352, 4360)** $\Rightarrow 4360 - 264 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 295936$, $T_{4096} := 4352^2$,
 $E := \{529, 531, \dots, 8717, 8719\}$

7. **(264, 17423, 17425)** $\Rightarrow 17425 - 264 = 131^2$, $S_{131 \times 131} := 2317259$, $T_{17161} := 17423^2$,
 $E := \{529, 531, \dots, 34847, 34849\}$ or $E := \{9109, 9110, \dots, 26268, 26269\}$

■ Number 265

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$265^2 + 636^2 := 689^2$$

$$265^2 + 1392^2 := 1417^2$$

$$265^2 + 7020^2 := 7025^2$$

$$265^2 + 35112^2 := 35113^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(265, 1392, 1417)** $\Rightarrow 1417 - 1392 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 14045$, $T_{25} := 265^2$,
 $E := \{2785, 2787, \dots, 2831, 2833\}$ or $E := \{2797, 2798, \dots, 2820, 2821\}$

■ Number 266

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$266^2 + 312^2 := 410^2$$

$$266^2 + 912^2 := 950^2$$

$$266^2 + 2520^2 := 2534^2$$

$$266^2 + 17688^2 := 17690^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(266, 312, 410)** $\Rightarrow 410 - 266 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 8112$, $T_{144} := 312^2$,
 $E := \{533, 535, \dots, 817, 819\}$
2. **(266, 17688, 17690)** $\Rightarrow 17690 - 266 = 132^2$, $S_{132 \times 132} := 2370192$, $T_{17424} := 17688^2$,
 $E := \{533, 535, \dots, 35377, 35379\}$

■ Number 267

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$267^2 + 356^2 := 445^2$$

$$267^2 + 3956^2 := 3965^2$$

$$267^2 + 11880^2 := 11883^2$$

$$267^2 + 35644^2 := 35645^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(267, 3956, 3965)** $\Rightarrow 3965 - 3956 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 23763$, $T_9 := 267^2$,
 $E := \{7913, 7915, \dots, 7927, 7929\}$ or $E := \{7917, 7918, \dots, 7924, 7925\}$

■ Number 268

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$268^2 + 4485^2 := 4493^2$$

$$268^2 + 8976^2 := 8980^2$$

$$268^2 + 17955^2 := 17957^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(268, 4485, 4493)** $\Rightarrow 4493 - 268 = 65^2$, $S_{65 \times 65} := 309465$, $T_{4225} := 4485^2$,
 $E := \{537, 539, \dots, 8983, 8985\}$ or $E := \{2649, 2650, \dots, 6872, 6873\}$
2. **(268, 17955, 17957)** $\Rightarrow 17957 - 268 = 133^2$, $S_{133 \times 133} := 2423925$, $T_{17689} := 17955^2$,
 $E := \{537, 539, \dots, 35911, 35913\}$ or $E := \{9381, 9382, \dots, 27068, 27069\}$

■ Number 269

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$269^2 + 36180^2 := 36181^2$$

■ Number 270

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$270^2 + 360^2 := 450^2$$

$$270^2 + 648^2 := 702^2$$

$$270^2 + 704^2 := 754^2$$

$$270^2 + 1200^2 := 1230^2$$

$$270^2 + 2016^2 := 2034^2$$

$$270^2 + 3640^2 := 3650^2$$

$$270^2 + 6072^2 := 6078^2$$

$$270^2 + 18224^2 := 18226^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(270, 2016, 2034)** $\Rightarrow 2034 - 270 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 96768$, $T_{1764} := 2016^2$,
 $E := \{541, 543, \dots, 4065, 4067\}$
2. **(270, 704, 754)** $\Rightarrow 754 - 270 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 22528$, $T_{484} := 704^2$,
 $E := \{541, 543, \dots, 1505, 1507\}$
3. **(270, 18224, 18226)** $\Rightarrow 18226 - 270 = 134^2$, $S_{134 \times 134} := 2478464$, $T_{17956} := 18224^2$,
 $E := \{541, 543, \dots, 36449, 36451\}$

■ Number 271

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$271^2 + 36720^2 := 36721^2$$

■ Number 272

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$272^2 + 510^2 := 578^2$$

$$272^2 + 546^2 := 610^2$$

$$272^2 + 1071^2 := 1105^2$$

$$272^2 + 1140^2 := 1172^2$$

$$272^2 + 2304^2 := 2320^2$$

$$272^2 + 4620^2 := 4628^2$$

$$272^2 + 9246^2 := 9250^2$$

$$272^2 + 18495^2 := 18497^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(272, 2304, 2320)** $\Rightarrow 2320 - 2304 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 18496$, $T_{16} := 272^2$,
 $E := \{4609, 4611, \dots, 4637, 4639\}$
2. **(272, 546, 610)** $\Rightarrow 610 - 546 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 9248$, $T_{64} := 272^2$,
 $E := \{1093, 1095, \dots, 1217, 1219\}$
3. **(272, 1140, 1172)** $\Rightarrow 1172 - 272 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 43320$, $T_{900} := 1140^2$,
 $E := \{545, 547, \dots, 2341, 2343\}$
4. **(272, 4620, 4628)** $\Rightarrow 4628 - 272 = 66^2$, $S_{66 \times 66} := 323400$, $T_{4356} := 4620^2$,
 $E := \{545, 547, \dots, 9253, 9255\}$
5. **(272, 18495, 18497)** $\Rightarrow 18497 - 272 = 135^2$, $S_{135 \times 135} := 2533815$, $T_{18225} := 18495^2$,
 $E := \{545, 547, \dots, 36991, 36993\}$ or $E := \{9657, 9658, \dots, 27880, 27881\}$

■ Number 273

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$273^2 + 364^2 := 455^2$$

$$273^2 + 560^2 := 623^2$$

$$273^2 + 736^2 := 785^2$$

$$273^2 + 936^2 := 975^2$$

$$273^2 + 1764^2 := 1785^2$$

$$273^2 + 2860^2 := 2873^2$$

$$273^2 + 4136^2 := 4145^2$$

$$273^2 + 5320^2 := 5327^2$$

$$273^2 + 12420^2 := 12423^2$$

$$273^2 + 37264^2 := 37265^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(273, 4136, 4145)** $\Rightarrow 4145 - 4136 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 24843$, $T_9 := 273^2$,
 $E := \{8273, 8275, \dots, 8287, 8289\}$ or $E := \{8277, 8278, \dots, 8284, 8285\}$
2. **(273, 736, 785)** $\Rightarrow 785 - 736 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 10647$, $T_{49} := 273^2$,
 $E := \{1473, 1475, \dots, 1567, 1569\}$ or $E := \{1497, 1498, \dots, 1544, 1545\}$

■ **Number 274**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$274^2 + 18768^2 := 18770^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(274, 18768, 18770)** $\Rightarrow 18770 - 274 = 136^2$, $S_{136 \times 136} := 2589984$, $T_{18496} := 18768^2$,
 $E := \{549, 551, \dots, 37537, 37539\}$

■ **Number 275**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$275^2 + 660^2 := 715^2$	$275^2 + 3432^2 := 3443^2$
$275^2 + 1500^2 := 1525^2$	$275^2 + 7560^2 := 7565^2$
	$275^2 + 37812^2 := 37813^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(275, 1500, 1525)** $\Rightarrow 1525 - 1500 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 15125$, $T_{25} := 275^2$,
 $E := \{3001, 3003, \dots, 3047, 3049\}$ or $E := \{3013, 3014, \dots, 3036, 3037\}$

■ **Number 276**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$276^2 + 368^2 := 460^2$	$276^2 + 1575^2 := 1599^2$	$276^2 + 6345^2 := 6351^2$
$276^2 + 493^2 := 565^2$	$276^2 + 2107^2 := 2125^2$	$276^2 + 9520^2 := 9524^2$
$276^2 + 805^2 := 851^2$	$276^2 + 3168^2 := 3180^2$	$276^2 + 19043^2 := 19045^2$
$276^2 + 1040^2 := 1076^2$	$276^2 + 4757^2 := 4765^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(276, 1040, 1076)** $\Rightarrow 1076 - 1040 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 12696$, $T_{36} := 276^2$,
 $E := \{2081, 2083, \dots, 2149, 2151\}$
2. **(276, 493, 565)** $\Rightarrow 565 - 276 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 14297$, $T_{289} := 493^2$,
 $E := \{553, 555, \dots, 1127, 1129\}$ or $E := \{697, 698, \dots, 984, 985\}$
3. **(276, 2107, 2125)** $\Rightarrow 2125 - 276 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 103243$, $T_{1849} := 2107^2$,
 $E := \{553, 555, \dots, 4247, 4249\}$ or $E := \{1477, 1478, \dots, 3324, 3325\}$
4. **(276, 4757, 4765)** $\Rightarrow 4765 - 276 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 337747$, $T_{4489} := 4757^2$,
 $E := \{553, 555, \dots, 9527, 9529\}$ or $E := \{2797, 2798, \dots, 7284, 7285\}$
5. **(276, 19043, 19045)** $\Rightarrow 19045 - 276 = 137^2$, $S_{137 \times 137} := 2646977$, $T_{18769} := 19043^2$,
 $E := \{553, 555, \dots, 38087, 38089\}$ or $E := \{9937, 9938, \dots, 28704, 28705\}$

■ **Number 277**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$277^2 + 38364^2 := 38365^2$$

■ **Number 278**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$278^2 + 19320^2 := 19322^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(278, 19320, 19322)** $\Rightarrow 19322 - 278 = 138^2$, $S_{138 \times 138} := 2704800$, $T_{19044} := 19320^2$,
 $E := \{557, 559, \dots, 38641, 38643\}$

■ **Number 279**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$279^2 + 372^2 := 465^2$	$279^2 + 4320^2 := 4329^2$
$279^2 + 440^2 := 521^2$	$279^2 + 12972^2 := 12975^2$
$279^2 + 1240^2 := 1271^2$	$279^2 + 38920^2 := 38921^2$
$279^2 + 1428^2 := 1455^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(279, 4320, 4329)** $\Rightarrow 4329 - 4320 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 25947$, $T_9 := 279^2$,
 $E := \{8641, 8643, \dots, 8655, 8657\}$ or $E := \{8645, 8646, \dots, 8652, 8653\}$
2. **(279, 440, 521)** $\Rightarrow 521 - 440 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 8649$, $T_{81} := 279^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 1039, 1041\}$ or $E := \{921, 922, \dots, 1000, 1001\}$

■ **Number 280**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$280^2 + 294^2 := 406^2$	$280^2 + 759^2 := 809^2$	$280^2 + 2793^2 := 2807^2$
$280^2 + 342^2 := 442^2$	$280^2 + 960^2 := 1000^2$	$280^2 + 3915^2 := 3925^2$
$280^2 + 351^2 := 449^2$	$280^2 + 1209^2 := 1241^2$	$280^2 + 4896^2 := 4904^2$
$280^2 + 450^2 := 530^2$	$280^2 + 1386^2 := 1414^2$	$280^2 + 9798^2 := 9802^2$
$280^2 + 525^2 := 595^2$	$280^2 + 1950^2 := 1970^2$	$280^2 + 19599^2 := 19601^2$
$280^2 + 672^2 := 728^2$	$280^2 + 2442^2 := 2458^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(280, 2442, 2458)** $\Rightarrow 2458 - 2442 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 19600$, $T_{16} := 280^2$,
 $E := \{4885, 4887, \dots, 4913, 4915\}$
2. **(280, 342, 442)** $\Rightarrow 442 - 342 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 7840$, $T_{100} := 280^2$,
 $E := \{685, 687, \dots, 881, 883\}$
3. **(280, 351, 449)** $\Rightarrow 449 - 280 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 9477$, $T_{169} := 351^2$,
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 895, 897\}$ or $E := \{645, 646, \dots, 812, 813\}$
4. **(280, 759, 809)** $\Rightarrow 809 - 280 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 25047$, $T_{529} := 759^2$,
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 1615, 1617\}$ or $E := \{825, 826, \dots, 1352, 1353\}$
5. **(280, 1209, 1241)** $\Rightarrow 1241 - 280 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 47151$, $T_{961} := 1209^2$,
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 2479, 2481\}$ or $E := \{1041, 1042, \dots, 2000, 2001\}$
6. **(280, 4896, 4904)** $\Rightarrow 4904 - 280 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 352512$, $T_{4624} := 4896^2$,
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 9805, 9807\}$
7. **(280, 19599, 19601)** $\Rightarrow 19601 - 280 = 139^2$, $S_{139 \times 139} := 2763459$, $T_{19321} := 19599^2$,
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 39199, 39201\}$ or $E := \{10221, 10222, \dots, 29540, 29541\}$

■ **Number 281**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$281^2 + 39480^2 := 39481^2$$

■ Number 282

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$282^2 + 376^2 := 470^2$$

$$282^2 + 2200^2 := 2218^2$$

$$282^2 + 6624^2 := 6630^2$$

$$282^2 + 19880^2 := 19882^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(282, 2200, 2218)** $\Rightarrow 2218 - 282 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 110000$, $T_{1936} := 2200^2$,
 $E := \{565, 567, \dots, 4433, 4435\}$

2. **(282, 19880, 19882)** $\Rightarrow 19882 - 282 = 140^2$, $S_{140 \times 140} := 2822960$, $T_{19600} := 19880^2$,
 $E := \{565, 567, \dots, 39761, 39763\}$

■ Number 283

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$283^2 + 40044^2 := 40045^2$$

■ Number 284

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$284^2 + 5037^2 := 5045^2$$

$$284^2 + 10080^2 := 10084^2$$

$$284^2 + 20163^2 := 20165^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(284, 5037, 5045)** $\Rightarrow 5045 - 284 = 69^2$, $S_{69 \times 69} := 367701$, $T_{4761} := 5037^2$,
 $E := \{569, 571, \dots, 10087, 10089\}$ or $E := \{2949, 2950, \dots, 7708, 7709\}$

2. **(284, 20163, 20165)** $\Rightarrow 20165 - 284 = 141^2$, $S_{141 \times 141} := 2883309$, $T_{19881} := 20163^2$,
 $E := \{569, 571, \dots, 40327, 40329\}$ or $E := \{10509, 10510, \dots, 30388, 30389\}$

■ Number 285

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$285^2 + 380^2 := 475^2$$

$$285^2 + 504^2 := 579^2$$

$$285^2 + 684^2 := 741^2$$

$$285^2 + 880^2 := 925^2$$

$$285^2 + 1612^2 := 1637^2$$

$$285^2 + 2128^2 := 2147^2$$

$$285^2 + 2700^2 := 2715^2$$

$$285^2 + 4508^2 := 4517^2$$

$$285^2 + 8120^2 := 8125^2$$

$$285^2 + 13536^2 := 13539^2$$

$$285^2 + 40612^2 := 40613^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(285, 4508, 4517)** $\Rightarrow 4517 - 4508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 27075$, $T_9 := 285^2$,
 $E := \{9017, 9019, \dots, 9031, 9033\}$ or $E := \{9021, 9022, \dots, 9028, 9029\}$

2. **(285, 1612, 1637)** $\Rightarrow 1637 - 1612 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 16245$, $T_{25} := 285^2$,
 $E := \{3225, 3227, \dots, 3271, 3273\}$ or $E := \{3237, 3238, \dots, 3260, 3261\}$

■ Number 286

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$286^2 + 1560^2 := 1586^2$$

$$286^2 + 1848^2 := 1870^2$$

$$286^2 + 20448^2 := 20450^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(286, 20448, 20450)** $\Rightarrow 20450 - 286 = 142^2$, $S_{142 \times 142} := 2944512$, $T_{20164} := 20448^2$,
 $E := \{573, 575, \dots, 40897, 40899\}$

■ Number 287

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$287^2 + 816^2 := 865^2$$

$$287^2 + 984^2 := 1025^2$$

$$287^2 + 5880^2 := 5887^2$$

$$287^2 + 41184^2 := 41185^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(287, 816, 865)** $\Rightarrow 865 - 816 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 11767$, $T_{49} := 287^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 1727, 1729\}$ or $E := \{1657, 1658, \dots, 1704, 1705\}$

■ Number 288

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$288^2 + 330^2 := 438^2$$

$$288^2 + 384^2 := 480^2$$

$$288^2 + 540^2 := 612^2$$

$$288^2 + 616^2 := 680^2$$

$$288^2 + 741^2 := 795^2$$

$$288^2 + 840^2 := 888^2$$

$$288^2 + 1134^2 := 1170^2$$

$$288^2 + 1280^2 := 1312^2$$

$$288^2 + 1716^2 := 1740^2$$

$$288^2 + 2295^2 := 2313^2$$

$$288^2 + 2584^2 := 2600^2$$

$$288^2 + 3450^2 := 3462^2$$

$$288^2 + 5180^2 := 5188^2$$

$$288^2 + 6909^2 := 6915^2$$

$$288^2 + 10366^2 := 10370^2$$

$$288^2 + 20735^2 := 20737^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(288, 2584, 2600)** $\Rightarrow 2600 - 2584 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 20736$, $T_{16} := 288^2$,
 $E := \{5169, 5171, \dots, 5197, 5199\}$

2. **(288, 1134, 1170)** $\Rightarrow 1170 - 1134 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 13824$, $T_{36} := 288^2$,
 $E := \{2269, 2271, \dots, 2337, 2339\}$

3. **(288, 616, 680)** $\Rightarrow 680 - 616 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 10368$, $T_{64} := 288^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 1357, 1359\}$

4. **(288, 540, 612)** $\Rightarrow 612 - 288 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 16200$, $T_{324} := 540^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 1221, 1223\}$

5. **(288, 1280, 1312)** $\Rightarrow 1312 - 288 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 51200$, $T_{1024} := 1280^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 2621, 2623\}$

6. **(288, 2295, 2313)** $\Rightarrow 2313 - 288 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 117045$, $T_{2025} := 2295^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 4623, 4625\}$ or $E := \{1589, 1590, \dots, 3612, 3613\}$

7. **(288, 5180, 5188)** $\Rightarrow 5188 - 288 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 383320$, $T_{4900} := 5180^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 10373, 10375\}$

8. **(288, 20735, 20737)** $\Rightarrow 20737 - 288 = 143^2$, $S_{143 \times 143} := 3006575$, $T_{20449} := 20735^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 41471, 41473\}$ or $E := \{10801, 10802, \dots, 31248, 31249\}$

■ Number 289

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$289^2 + 2448^2 := 2465^2$$

$$289^2 + 41760^2 := 41761^2$$

■ Number 290

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$290^2 + 696^2 := 754^2$$

$$290^2 + 816^2 := 866^2$$

$$290^2 + 4200^2 := 4210^2$$

$$290^2 + 21024^2 := 21026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(290, 816, 866)** $\Rightarrow 866 - 290 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 27744$, $T_{576} := 816^2$,
 $E := \{581, 583, \dots, 1729, 1731\}$

2. **(290, 21024, 21026)** $\Rightarrow 21026 - 290 = 144^2$, $S_{144 \times 144} := 3069504$, $T_{20736} := 21024^2$,
 $E := \{581, 583, \dots, 42049, 42051\}$

■ Number 291

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$291^2 + 388^2 := 485^2$$

$$291^2 + 4700^2 := 4709^2$$

$$291^2 + 14112^2 := 14115^2$$

$$291^2 + 42340^2 := 42341^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(291, 4700, 4709)** $\Rightarrow 4709 - 4700 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 28227$, $T_9 := 291^2$,
 $E := \{9401, 9403, \dots, 9415, 9417\}$ or $E := \{9405, 9406, \dots, 9412, 9413\}$

■ Number 292

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$292^2 + 5325^2 := 5333^2$$

$$292^2 + 10656^2 := 10660^2$$

$$292^2 + 21315^2 := 21317^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(292, 5325, 5333)** $\Rightarrow 5333 - 292 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 399375$, $T_{5041} := 5325^2$,
 $E := \{585, 587, \dots, 10663, 10665\}$ or $E := \{3105, 3106, \dots, 8144, 8145\}$

2. **(292, 21315, 21317)** $\Rightarrow 21317 - 292 = 145^2$, $S_{145 \times 145} := 3133305$, $T_{21025} := 21315^2$,
 $E := \{585, 587, \dots, 42631, 42633\}$ or $E := \{11097, 11098, \dots, 32120, 32121\}$

■ Number 293

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$293^2 + 42924^2 := 42925^2$$

■ Number 294

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$294^2 + 392^2 := 490^2$$

$$294^2 + 1008^2 := 1050^2$$

$$294^2 + 2392^2 := 2410^2$$

$$294^2 + 3080^2 := 3094^2$$

$$294^2 + 7200^2 := 7206^2$$

$$294^2 + 21608^2 := 21610^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(294, 392, 490)** $\Rightarrow 490 - 294 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 10976$, $T_{196} := 392^2$,

$$E := \{589, 591, \dots, 977, 979\}$$

2. **(294, 2392, 2410)** $\Rightarrow 2410 - 294 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 124384$, $T_{2116} := 2392^2$,

$$E := \{589, 591, \dots, 4817, 4819\}$$

3. **(294, 21608, 21610)** $\Rightarrow 21610 - 294 = 146^2$, $S_{146 \times 146} := 3197984$, $T_{21316} := 21608^2$,

$$E := \{589, 591, \dots, 43217, 43219\}$$

■ Number 295

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$295^2 + 708^2 := 767^2$$

$$295^2 + 8700^2 := 8705^2$$

$$295^2 + 1728^2 := 1753^2$$

$$295^2 + 43512^2 := 43513^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(295, 1728, 1753)** $\Rightarrow 1753 - 1728 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 17405$, $T_{25} := 295^2$,

$$E := \{3457, 3459, \dots, 3503, 3505\} \text{ or } E := \{3469, 3470, \dots, 3492, 3493\}$$

■ Number 296

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 296^2 + 555^2 := 629^2 & 296^2 + 5472^2 := 5480^2 \\
 296^2 + 1353^2 := 1385^2 & 296^2 + 10950^2 := 10954^2 \\
 296^2 + 2730^2 := 2746^2 & 296^2 + 21903^2 := 21905^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(296, 2730, 2746)** $\Rightarrow 2746 - 2730 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 21904$, $T_{16} := 296^2$,
 $E := \{5461, 5463, \dots, 5489, 5491\}$
2. **(296, 1353, 1385)** $\Rightarrow 1385 - 296 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 55473$, $T_{1089} := 1353^2$,
 $E := \{593, 595, \dots, 2767, 2769\}$ or $E := \{1137, 1138, \dots, 2224, 2225\}$
3. **(296, 5472, 5480)** $\Rightarrow 5480 - 296 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 415872$, $T_{5184} := 5472^2$,
 $E := \{593, 595, \dots, 10957, 10959\}$
4. **(296, 21903, 21905)** $\Rightarrow 21905 - 296 = 147^2$, $S_{147 \times 147} := 3263547$, $T_{21609} := 21903^2$,
 $E := \{593, 595, \dots, 43807, 43809\}$ or $E := \{11397, 11398, \dots, 33004, 33005\}$

■ Number 297

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 297^2 + 304^2 := 425^2 & 297^2 + 1320^2 := 1353^2 & 297^2 + 4896^2 := 4905^2 \\
 297^2 + 396^2 := 495^2 & 297^2 + 1620^2 := 1647^2 & 297^2 + 4410^2 := 44105^2 \\
 297^2 + 504^2 := 585^2 & 297^2 + 4004^2 := 4015^2 & 297^2 + 14700^2 := 14703^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(297, 4896, 4905)** $\Rightarrow 4905 - 4896 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 29403$, $T_9 := 297^2$,
 $E := \{9793, 9795, \dots, 9807, 9809\}$ or $E := \{9797, 9798, \dots, 9804, 9805\}$
2. **(297, 504, 585)** $\Rightarrow 585 - 504 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 9801$, $T_{81} := 297^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 1167, 1169\}$ or $E := \{1049, 1050, \dots, 1128, 1129\}$
3. **(297, 304, 425)** $\Rightarrow 425 - 304 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 8019$, $T_{121} := 297^2$,
 $E := \{609, 611, \dots, 847, 849\}$ or $E := \{669, 670, \dots, 788, 789\}$

■ Number 298

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$298^2 + 22200^2 := 22202^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(298, 22200, 22202)** $\Rightarrow 22202 - 298 = 148^2$, $S_{148 \times 148} := 3330000$, $T_{21904} := 22200^2$,
 $E := \{597, 599, \dots, 44401, 44403\}$

■ **Number 299**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$299^2 + 1932^2 := 1955^2$$

$$299^2 + 3432^2 := 3445^2$$

$$299^2 + 44700^2 := 44701^2$$

■ **Number 300**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$300^2 + 315^2 := 435^2$$

$$300^2 + 400^2 := 500^2$$

$$300^2 + 455^2 := 545^2$$

$$300^2 + 589^2 := 661^2$$

$$300^2 + 720^2 := 780^2$$

$$300^2 + 875^2 := 925^2$$

$$300^2 + 1105^2 := 1145^2$$

$$300^2 + 1232^2 := 1268^2$$

$$300^2 + 1485^2 := 1515^2$$

$$300^2 + 1863^2 := 1887^2$$

$$300^2 + 2240^2 := 2260^2$$

$$300^2 + 2491^2 := 2509^2$$

$$300^2 + 3744^2 := 3756^2$$

$$300^2 + 4495^2 := 4505^2$$

$$300^2 + 5621^2 := 5629^2$$

$$300^2 + 7497^2 := 7503^2$$

$$300^2 + 11248^2 := 11252^2$$

$$300^2 + 22499^2 := 22501^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(300, 1232, 1268)** $\Rightarrow 1268 - 1232 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 15000$, $T_{36} := 300^2$,
 $E := \{2465, 2467, \dots, 2533, 2535\}$

2. **(300, 400, 500)** $\Rightarrow 500 - 400 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 9000$, $T_{100} := 300^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 997, 999\}$

3. **(300, 589, 661)** $\Rightarrow 661 - 300 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 18259$, $T_{361} := 589^2$,
 $E := \{601, 603, \dots, 1319, 1321\}$ or $E := \{781, 782, \dots, 1140, 1141\}$

4. **(300, 875, 925)** $\Rightarrow 925 - 300 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 30625$, $T_{625} := 875^2$,
 $E := \{601, 603, \dots, 1847, 1849\}$ or $E := \{913, 914, \dots, 1536, 1537\}$

5. **(300, 2491, 2509)** $\Rightarrow 2509 - 300 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 132023$, $T_{2209} := 2491^2$,
 $E := \{601, 603, \dots, 5015, 5017\}$ or $E := \{1705, 1706, \dots, 3912, 3913\}$

6. **(300, 5621, 5629)** $\Rightarrow 5629 - 300 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 432817$, $T_{5329} := 5621^2$,
 $E := \{601, 603, \dots, 11255, 11257\}$ or $E := \{3265, 3266, \dots, 8592, 8593\}$

$$7. \text{ (300, 22499, 22501) } \Rightarrow 22501 - 300 = 149^2, S_{149 \times 149} := 3397349, T_{22201} := 22499^2, \\ E := \{601, 603, \dots, 44999, 45001\} \text{ or } E := \{11701, 11702, \dots, 33900, 33901\}$$

2.4 Pythagorean Triples: 301 to 400

■ Number 301

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 301^2 + 900^2 := 949^2 & 301^2 + 6468^2 := 6475^2 \\ 301^2 + 1032^2 := 1075^2 & 301^2 + 45300^2 := 45301^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(301, 900, 949)** $\Rightarrow 949 - 900 = 7^2, S_{7 \times 7} := 12943, T_{49} := 301^2,$
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 1895, 1897\}$ or $E := \{1825, 1826, \dots, 1872, 1873\}$

■ Number 302

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$302^2 + 22800^2 := 22802^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(302, 22800, 22802)** $\Rightarrow 22802 - 302 = 150^2, S_{150 \times 150} := 3465600, T_{22500} := 22800^2,$
 $E := \{605, 607, \dots, 45601, 45603\}$

■ Number 303

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 303^2 + 404^2 := 505^2 & 303^2 + 15300^2 := 15303^2 \\ 303^2 + 5096^2 := 5105^2 & 303^2 + 45904^2 := 45905^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(303, 5096, 5105)** $\Rightarrow 5105 - 5096 = 3^2, S_{3 \times 3} := 30603, T_9 := 303^2,$
 $E := \{10193, 10195, \dots, 10207, 10209\}$ or $E := \{10197, 10198, \dots, 10204, 10205\}$

■ Number 304

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$304^2 + 570^2 := 646^2$$

$$304^2 + 690^2 := 754^2$$

$$304^2 + 1197^2 := 1235^2$$

$$304^2 + 1428^2 := 1460^2$$

$$304^2 + 2880^2 := 2896^2$$

$$304^2 + 5772^2 := 5780^2$$

$$304^2 + 11550^2 := 11554^2$$

$$304^2 + 23103^2 := 23105^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

$$1. \text{ (304, 2880, 2896)} \Rightarrow 2896 - 2880 = 4^2, S_{4 \times 4} := 23104, T_{16} := 304^2, \\ E := \{5761, 5763, \dots, 5789, 5791\}$$

$$2. \text{ (304, 690, 754)} \Rightarrow 754 - 690 = 8^2, S_{8 \times 8} := 11552, T_{64} := 304^2, \\ E := \{1381, 1383, \dots, 1505, 1507\}$$

$$3. \text{ (304, 1428, 1460)} \Rightarrow 1460 - 304 = 34^2, S_{34 \times 34} := 59976, T_{1156} := 1428^2, \\ E := \{609, 611, \dots, 2917, 2919\}$$

$$4. \text{ (304, 5772, 5780)} \Rightarrow 5780 - 304 = 74^2, S_{74 \times 74} := 450216, T_{5476} := 5772^2, \\ E := \{609, 611, \dots, 11557, 11559\}$$

$$5. \text{ (304, 23103, 23105)} \Rightarrow 23105 - 304 = 151^2, S_{151 \times 151} := 3534759, T_{22801} := 23103^2, \\ E := \{609, 611, \dots, 46207, 46209\} \text{ or } E := \{12009, 12010, \dots, 34808, 34809\}$$

■ Number 305

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$305^2 + 732^2 := 793^2$$

$$305^2 + 1848^2 := 1873^2$$

$$305^2 + 9300^2 := 9305^2$$

$$305^2 + 46512^2 := 46513^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

$$- \text{ (305, 1848, 1873)} \Rightarrow 1873 - 1848 = 5^2, S_{5 \times 5} := 18605, T_{25} := 305^2, \\ E := \{3697, 3699, \dots, 3743, 3745\} \text{ or } E := \{3709, 3710, \dots, 3732, 3733\}$$

■ Number 306

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$306^2 + 408^2 := 510^2$$

$$306^2 + 840^2 := 894^2$$

$$306^2 + 1360^2 := 1394^2$$

$$306^2 + 2592^2 := 2610^2$$

$$306^2 + 7800^2 := 7806^2$$

$$306^2 + 23408^2 := 23410^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(306, 2592, 2610)** $\Rightarrow 2610 - 306 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 139968$, $T_{2304} := 2592^2$,
 $E := \{613, 615, \dots, 5217, 5219\}$

2. **(306, 23408, 23410)** $\Rightarrow 23410 - 306 = 152^2$, $S_{152 \times 152} := 3604832$, $T_{23104} := 23408^2$,
 $E := \{613, 615, \dots, 46817, 46819\}$

■ Number 307

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$307^2 + 47124^2 := 47125^2$$

■ Number 308

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$308^2 + 435^2 := 533^2$$

$$308^2 + 495^2 := 583^2$$

$$308^2 + 819^2 := 875^2$$

$$308^2 + 1056^2 := 1100^2$$

$$308^2 + 1680^2 := 1708^2$$

$$308^2 + 2145^2 := 2167^2$$

$$308^2 + 3381^2 := 3395^2$$

$$308^2 + 5925^2 := 5933^2$$

$$308^2 + 11856^2 := 11860^2$$

$$308^2 + 23715^2 := 23717^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(308, 435, 533)** $\Rightarrow 533 - 308 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 12615$, $T_{225} := 435^2$,
 $E := \{617, 619, \dots, 1063, 1065\}$ or $E := \{729, 730, \dots, 952, 953\}$

2. **(308, 5925, 5933)** $\Rightarrow 5933 - 308 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 468075$, $T_{5625} := 5925^2$,
 $E := \{617, 619, \dots, 11863, 11865\}$ or $E := \{3429, 3430, \dots, 9052, 9053\}$

3. **(308, 23715, 23717)** $\Rightarrow 23717 - 308 = 153^2$, $S_{153 \times 153} := 3675825$, $T_{23409} := 23715^2$,
 $E := \{617, 619, \dots, 47431, 47433\}$ or $E := \{12321, 12322, \dots, 35728, 35729\}$

■ Number 309

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$309^2 + 412^2 := 515^2$$

$$309^2 + 5300^2 := 5309^2$$

$$309^2 + 15912^2 := 15915^2$$

$$309^2 + 47740^2 := 47741^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(309, 5300, 5309)** $\Rightarrow 5309 - 5300 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 31827$, $T_9 := 309^2$,
 $E := \{10601, 10603, \dots, 10615, 10617\}$ or $E := \{10605, 10606, \dots, 10612, 10613\}$

■ Number 310

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$310^2 + 744^2 := 806^2$$

$$310^2 + 936^2 := 986^2$$

$$310^2 + 4800^2 := 4810^2$$

$$310^2 + 24024^2 := 24026^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(310, 936, 986)** $\Rightarrow 986 - 310 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 33696$, $T_{676} := 936^2$,
 $E := \{621, 623, \dots, 1969, 1971\}$
2. **(310, 24024, 24026)** $\Rightarrow 24026 - 310 = 154^2$, $S_{154 \times 154} := 3747744$, $T_{23716} := 24024^2$,
 $E := \{621, 623, \dots, 48049, 48051\}$

■ Number 311

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$311^2 + 48360^2 := 48361^2$$

■ Number 312

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$312^2 + 416^2 := 520^2$$

$$312^2 + 459^2 := 555^2$$

$$312^2 + 585^2 := 663^2$$

$$312^2 + 640^2 := 712^2$$

$$312^2 + 910^2 := 962^2$$

$$312^2 + 990^2 := 1038^2$$

$$312^2 + 1334^2 := 1370^2$$

$$312^2 + 1505^2 := 1537^2$$

$$312^2 + 1859^2 := 1885^2$$

$$312^2 + 2016^2 := 2040^2$$

$$312^2 + 2695^2 := 2713^2$$

$$312^2 + 3034^2 := 3050^2$$

$$312^2 + 4050^2 := 4062^2$$

$$312^2 + 6080^2 := 6088^2$$

$$312^2 + 8109^2 := 8115^2$$

$$312^2 + 12166^2 := 12170^2$$

$$312^2 + 24335^2 := 24337^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(312, 3034, 3050)** $\Rightarrow 3050 - 3034 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 24336$, $T_{16} := 312^2$,
 $E := \{6069, 6071, \dots, 6097, 6099\}$
2. **(312, 1334, 1370)** $\Rightarrow 1370 - 1334 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 16224$, $T_{36} := 312^2$,
 $E := \{2669, 2671, \dots, 2737, 2739\}$
3. **(312, 640, 712)** $\Rightarrow 712 - 312 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 20480$, $T_{400} := 640^2$,
 $E := \{625, 627, \dots, 1421, 1423\}$
4. **(312, 1505, 1537)** $\Rightarrow 1537 - 312 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 64715$, $T_{1225} := 1505^2$,
 $E := \{625, 627, \dots, 3071, 3073\}$ or $E := \{1237, 1238, \dots, 2460, 2461\}$
5. **(312, 2695, 2713)** $\Rightarrow 2713 - 312 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 148225$, $T_{2401} := 2695^2$,
 $E := \{625, 627, \dots, 5423, 5425\}$ or $E := \{1825, 1826, \dots, 4224, 4225\}$
6. **(312, 6080, 6088)** $\Rightarrow 6088 - 312 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 486400$, $T_{5776} := 6080^2$,
 $E := \{625, 627, \dots, 12173, 12175\}$
7. **(312, 24335, 24337)** $\Rightarrow 24337 - 312 = 155^2$, $S_{155 \times 155} := 3820595$, $T_{24025} := 24335^2$,
 $E := \{625, 627, \dots, 48671, 48673\}$ or $E := \{12637, 12638, \dots, 36660, 36661\}$

■ Number 313

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$313^2 + 48984^2 := 48985^2$$

■ Number 314

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$314^2 + 24648^2 := 24650^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(314, 24648, 24650)** $\Rightarrow 24650 - 314 = 156^2$, $S_{156 \times 156} := 3894384$, $T_{24336} := 24648^2$,
 $E := \{629, 631, \dots, 49297, 49299\}$

■ Number 315

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$315^2 + 420^2 := 525^2$$

$$315^2 + 572^2 := 653^2$$

$$315^2 + 624^2 := 699^2$$

$$315^2 + 756^2 := 819^2$$

$$315^2 + 988^2 := 1037^2$$

$$315^2 + 1080^2 := 1125^2$$

$$315^2 + 1400^2 := 1435^2$$

$$315^2 + 1824^2 := 1851^2$$

$$315^2 + 1972^2 := 1997^2$$

$$315^2 + 2352^2 := 2373^2$$

$$315^2 + 3300^2 := 3315^2$$

$$315^2 + 5508^2 := 5517^2$$

$$315^2 + 7084^2 := 7091^2$$

$$315^2 + 9920^2 := 9925^2$$

$$315^2 + 16536^2 := 16539^2$$

$$315^2 + 49612^2 := 49613^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(315, 5508, 5517)** $\Rightarrow 5517 - 5508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 33075$, $T_9 := 315^2$,
 $E := \{11017, 11019, \dots, 11031, 11033\}$ or $E := \{11021, 11022, \dots, 11028, 11029\}$
2. **(315, 1972, 1997)** $\Rightarrow 1997 - 1972 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 19845$, $T_{25} := 315^2$,
 $E := \{3945, 3947, \dots, 3991, 3993\}$ or $E := \{3957, 3958, \dots, 3980, 3981\}$
3. **(315, 988, 1037)** $\Rightarrow 1037 - 988 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 14175$, $T_{49} := 315^2$,
 $E := \{1977, 1979, \dots, 2071, 2073\}$ or $E := \{2001, 2002, \dots, 2048, 2049\}$
4. **(315, 572, 653)** $\Rightarrow 653 - 572 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 11025$, $T_{81} := 315^2$,
 $E := \{1145, 1147, \dots, 1303, 1305\}$ or $E := \{1185, 1186, \dots, 1264, 1265\}$

■ Number 316

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$316^2 + 6237^2 := 6245^2$$

$$316^2 + 12480^2 := 12484^2$$

$$316^2 + 24963^2 := 24965^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(316, 6237, 6245)** $\Rightarrow 6245 - 316 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 505197$, $T_{5929} := 6237^2$,
 $E := \{633, 635, \dots, 12487, 12489\}$ or $E := \{3597, 3598, \dots, 9524, 9525\}$
2. **(316, 24963, 24965)** $\Rightarrow 24965 - 316 = 157^2$, $S_{157 \times 157} := 3969117$, $T_{24649} := 24963^2$,
 $E := \{633, 635, \dots, 49927, 49929\}$ or $E := \{12957, 12958, \dots, 37604, 37605\}$

■ Number 317

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$317^2 + 50244^2 := 50245^2$$

■ Number 318

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$318^2 + 424^2 := 530^2$$

$$318^2 + 8424^2 := 8430^2$$

$$318^2 + 2800^2 := 2818^2$$

$$318^2 + 25280^2 := 25282^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(318, 2800, 2818)** $\Rightarrow 2818 - 318 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 156800$, $T_{2500} := 2800^2$,
 $E := \{637, 639, \dots, 5633, 5635\}$

2. **(318, 25280, 25282)** $\Rightarrow 25282 - 318 = 158^2$, $S_{158 \times 158} := 4044800$, $T_{24964} := 25280^2$,
 $E := \{637, 639, \dots, 50561, 50563\}$

■ Number 319

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$319^2 + 360^2 := 481^2$$

$$319^2 + 4620^2 := 4631^2$$

$$319^2 + 1740^2 := 1769^2$$

$$319^2 + 50880^2 := 50881^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(319, 360, 481)** $\Rightarrow 481 - 360 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 9251$, $T_{121} := 319^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 959, 961\}$ or $E := \{781, 782, \dots, 900, 901\}$

■ Number 320

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$320^2 + 336^2 := 464^2$$

$$320^2 + 462^2 := 562^2$$

$$320^2 + 600^2 := 680^2$$

$$320^2 + 768^2 := 832^2$$

$$320^2 + 999^2 := 1049^2$$

$$320^2 + 1260^2 := 1300^2$$

$$320^2 + 1584^2 := 1616^2$$

$$320^2 + 2550^2 := 2570^2$$

$$320^2 + 3192^2 := 3208^2$$

$$320^2 + 5115^2 := 5125^2$$

$$320^2 + 6396^2 := 6404^2$$

$$320^2 + 12798^2 := 12802^2$$

$$320^2 + 25599^2 := 25601^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(320, 3192, 3208)** $\Rightarrow 3208 - 3192 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 25600$, $T_{16} := 320^2$,
 $E := \{6385, 6387, \dots, 6413, 6415\}$
2. **(320, 768, 832)** $\Rightarrow 832 - 768 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 12800$, $T_{64} := 320^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 1661, 1663\}$
3. **(320, 462, 562)** $\Rightarrow 562 - 462 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 10240$, $T_{100} := 320^2$,
 $E := \{925, 927, \dots, 1121, 1123\}$
4. **(320, 336, 464)** $\Rightarrow 464 - 320 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 9408$, $T_{144} := 336^2$,
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 925, 927\}$
5. **(320, 999, 1049)** $\Rightarrow 1049 - 320 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 36963$, $T_{729} := 999^2$,
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 2095, 2097\}$ or $E := \{1005, 1006, \dots, 1732, 1733\}$
6. **(320, 1584, 1616)** $\Rightarrow 1616 - 320 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 69696$, $T_{1296} := 1584^2$,
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 3229, 3231\}$
7. **(320, 6396, 6404)** $\Rightarrow 6404 - 320 = 78^2$, $S_{78 \times 78} := 524472$, $T_{6084} := 6396^2$,
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 12805, 12807\}$
8. **(320, 25599, 25601)** $\Rightarrow 25601 - 320 = 159^2$, $S_{159 \times 159} := 4121439$, $T_{25281} := 25599^2$,
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 51199, 51201\}$ or $E := \{13281, 13282, \dots, 38560, 38561\}$

■ Number 321

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$321^2 + 428^2 := 535^2$$

$$321^2 + 5720^2 := 5729^2$$

$$321^2 + 17172^2 := 17175^2$$

$$321^2 + 51520^2 := 51521^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(321, 5720, 5729)** $\Rightarrow 5729 - 5720 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 34347$, $T_9 := 321^2$,
 $E := \{11441, 11443, \dots, 11455, 11457\}$ or $E := \{11445, 11446, \dots, 11452, 11453\}$

■ Number 322

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$322^2 + 480^2 := 578^2$$

$$322^2 + 1104^2 := 1150^2$$

$$322^2 + 3696^2 := 3710^2$$

$$322^2 + 25920^2 := 25922^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

$$1. \text{ (322, 480, 578)} \Rightarrow 578 - 322 = 16^2, S_{16 \times 16} := 14400, T_{256} := 480^2, \\ E := \{645, 647, \dots, 1153, 1155\}$$

$$2. \text{ (322, 25920, 25922)} \Rightarrow 25922 - 322 = 160^2, S_{160 \times 160} := 4199040, T_{25600} := 25920^2, \\ E := \{645, 647, \dots, 51841, 51843\}$$

■ Number 323

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$323^2 + 2736^2 := 2755^2$$

$$323^2 + 3060^2 := 3077^2$$

$$323^2 + 52164^2 := 52165^2$$

■ Number 324

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$324^2 + 432^2 := 540^2$$

$$324^2 + 693^2 := 765^2$$

$$324^2 + 945^2 := 999^2$$

$$324^2 + 1440^2 := 1476^2$$

$$324^2 + 2175^2 := 2199^2$$

$$324^2 + 2907^2 := 2925^2$$

$$324^2 + 4368^2 := 4380^2$$

$$324^2 + 6557^2 := 6565^2$$

$$324^2 + 8745^2 := 8751^2$$

$$324^2 + 13120^2 := 13124^2$$

$$324^2 + 26243^2 := 26245^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

$$1. \text{ (324, 1440, 1476)} \Rightarrow 1476 - 1440 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 17496, T_{36} := 324^2, \\ E := \{2881, 2883, \dots, 2949, 2951\}$$

$$2. \text{ (324, 693, 765)} \Rightarrow 765 - 324 = 21^2, S_{21 \times 21} := 22869, T_{441} := 693^2, \\ E := \{649, 651, \dots, 1527, 1529\} \text{ or } E := \{869, 870, \dots, 1308, 1309\}$$

$$3. \text{ (324, 2907, 2925)} \Rightarrow 2925 - 324 = 51^2, S_{51 \times 51} := 165699, T_{2601} := 2907^2, \\ E := \{649, 651, \dots, 5847, 5849\} \text{ or } E := \{1949, 1950, \dots, 4548, 4549\}$$

4. **(324, 6557, 6565)** $\Rightarrow 6565 - 324 = 79^2$, $S_{79 \times 79} := 544231$, $T_{6241} := 6557^2$,
 $E := \{649, 651, \dots, 13127, 13129\}$ or $E := \{3769, 3770, \dots, 10008, 10009\}$
5. **(324, 26243, 26245)** $\Rightarrow 26245 - 324 = 161^2$, $S_{161 \times 161} := 4277609$, $T_{25921} := 26243^2$,
 $E := \{649, 651, \dots, 52487, 52489\}$ or $E := \{13609, 13610, \dots, 39528, 39529\}$

■ Number 325

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 325^2 + 360^2 := 485^2 & 325^2 + 4056^2 := 4069^2 \\ 325^2 + 780^2 := 845^2 & 325^2 + 10560^2 := 10565^2 \\ 325^2 + 2100^2 := 2125^2 & 325^2 + 52812^2 := 52813^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(325, 2100, 2125)** $\Rightarrow 2125 - 2100 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 21125$, $T_{25} := 325^2$,
 $E := \{4201, 4203, \dots, 4247, 4249\}$ or $E := \{4213, 4214, \dots, 4236, 4237\}$

■ Number 326

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$326^2 + 26568^2 := 26570^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(326, 26568, 26570)** $\Rightarrow 26570 - 326 = 162^2$, $S_{162 \times 162} := 4357152$, $T_{26244} := 26568^2$,
 $E := \{653, 655, \dots, 53137, 53139\}$

■ Number 327

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 327^2 + 436^2 := 545^2 & 327^2 + 17820^2 := 17823^2 \\ 327^2 + 5936^2 := 5945^2 & 327^2 + 53464^2 := 53465^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(327, 5936, 5945)** $\Rightarrow 5945 - 5936 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 35643$, $T_9 := 327^2$,
 $E := \{11873, 11875, \dots, 11887, 11889\}$ or $E := \{11877, 11878, \dots, 11884, 11885\}$

■ Number 328

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$328^2 + 615^2 := 697^2$$

$$328^2 + 1665^2 := 1697^2$$

$$328^2 + 3354^2 := 3370^2$$

$$328^2 + 6720^2 := 6728^2$$

$$328^2 + 13446^2 := 13450^2$$

$$328^2 + 26895^2 := 26897^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(328, 3354, 3370)** $\Rightarrow 3370 - 3354 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 26896$, $T_{16} := 328^2$,

$$E := \{6709, 6711, \dots, 6737, 6739\}$$

2. **(328, 1665, 1697)** $\Rightarrow 1697 - 328 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 74925$, $T_{1369} := 1665^2$,

$$E := \{657, 659, \dots, 3391, 3393\} \text{ or } E := \{1341, 1342, \dots, 2708, 2709\}$$

3. **(328, 6720, 6728)** $\Rightarrow 6728 - 328 = 80^2$, $S_{80 \times 80} := 564480$, $T_{6400} := 6720^2$,

$$E := \{657, 659, \dots, 13453, 13455\}$$

4. **(328, 26895, 26897)** $\Rightarrow 26897 - 328 = 163^2$, $S_{163 \times 163} := 4437675$, $T_{26569} := 26895^2$,

$$E := \{657, 659, \dots, 53791, 53793\} \text{ or } E := \{13941, 13942, \dots, 40508, 40509\}$$

■ Number 329

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$329^2 + 1080^2 := 1129^2$$

$$329^2 + 1128^2 := 1175^2$$

$$329^2 + 7728^2 := 7735^2$$

$$329^2 + 54120^2 := 54121^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(329, 1080, 1129)** $\Rightarrow 1129 - 1080 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 15463$, $T_{49} := 329^2$,

$$E := \{2161, 2163, \dots, 2255, 2257\} \text{ or } E := \{2185, 2186, \dots, 2232, 2233\}$$

■ Number 330

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$330^2 + 440^2 := 550^2$$

$$330^2 + 560^2 := 650^2$$

$$330^2 + 792^2 := 858^2$$

$$330^2 + 1064^2 := 1114^2$$

$$330^2 + 1800^2 := 1830^2$$

$$330^2 + 2464^2 := 2486^2$$

$$330^2 + 3016^2 := 3034^2$$

$$330^2 + 5440^2 := 5450^2$$

$$330^2 + 9072^2 := 9078^2$$

$$330^2 + 27224^2 := 27226^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(330, 1064, 1114)** $\Rightarrow 1114 - 330 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 40432$, $T_{784} := 1064^2$,
 $E := \{661, 663, \dots, 2225, 2227\}$
2. **(330, 3016, 3034)** $\Rightarrow 3034 - 330 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 174928$, $T_{2704} := 3016^2$,
 $E := \{661, 663, \dots, 6065, 6067\}$
3. **(330, 27224, 27226)** $\Rightarrow 27226 - 330 = 164^2$, $S_{164 \times 164} := 4519184$, $T_{26896} := 27224^2$,
 $E := \{661, 663, \dots, 54449, 54451\}$

■ Number 331

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$331^2 + 54780^2 := 54781^2$$

■ Number 332

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$332^2 + 6885^2 := 6893^2$$

$$332^2 + 13776^2 := 13780^2$$

$$332^2 + 27555^2 := 27557^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(332, 6885, 6893)** $\Rightarrow 6893 - 332 = 81^2$, $S_{81 \times 81} := 585225$, $T_{6561} := 6885^2$,
 $E := \{665, 667, \dots, 13783, 13785\}$ or $E := \{3945, 3946, \dots, 10504, 10505\}$
2. **(332, 27555, 27557)** $\Rightarrow 27557 - 332 = 165^2$, $S_{165 \times 165} := 4601685$, $T_{27225} := 27555^2$,
 $E := \{665, 667, \dots, 55111, 55113\}$ or $E := \{14277, 14278, \dots, 41500, 41501\}$

■ Number 333

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned} 333^2 + 444^2 &:= 555^2 \\ 333^2 + 644^2 &:= 725^2 \\ 333^2 + 1480^2 &:= 1517^2 \\ 333^2 + 2040^2 &:= 2067^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 333^2 + 6156^2 &:= 6165^2 \\ 333^2 + 18480^2 &:= 18483^2 \\ 333^2 + 55444^2 &:= 55445^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(333, 6156, 6165)** $\Rightarrow 6165 - 6156 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 36963$, $T_9 := 333^2$,
 $E := \{12313, 12315, \dots, 12327, 12329\}$ or $E := \{12317, 12318, \dots, 12324, 12325\}$
2. **(333, 644, 725)** $\Rightarrow 725 - 644 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 12321$, $T_{81} := 333^2$,
 $E := \{1289, 1291, \dots, 1447, 1449\}$ or $E := \{1329, 1330, \dots, 1408, 1409\}$

■ Number 334

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$334^2 + 27888^2 := 27890^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(334, 27888, 27890)** $\Rightarrow 27890 - 334 = 166^2$, $S_{166 \times 166} := 4685184$, $T_{27556} := 27888^2$,
 $E := \{669, 671, \dots, 55777, 55779\}$

■ Number 335

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned} 335^2 + 804^2 &:= 871^2 & 335^2 + 11220^2 &:= 11225^2 \\ 335^2 + 2232^2 &:= 2257^2 & 335^2 + 56112^2 &:= 56113^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(335, 2232, 2257)** $\Rightarrow 2257 - 2232 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 22445$, $T_{25} := 335^2$,
 $E := \{4465, 4467, \dots, 4511, 4513\}$ or $E := \{4477, 4478, \dots, 4500, 4501\}$

■ Number 336

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$336^2 + 377^2 := 505^2$	$336^2 + 980^2 := 1036^2$	$336^2 + 3520^2 := 3536^2$
$336^2 + 385^2 := 511^2$	$336^2 + 1152^2 := 1200^2$	$336^2 + 4025^2 := 4039^2$
$336^2 + 448^2 := 560^2$	$336^2 + 1323^2 := 1365^2$	$336^2 + 4698^2 := 4710^2$
$336^2 + 527^2 := 625^2$	$336^2 + 1550^2 := 1586^2$	$336^2 + 7052^2 := 7060^2$
$336^2 + 540^2 := 636^2$	$336^2 + 1748^2 := 1780^2$	$336^2 + 9405^2 := 9411^2$
$336^2 + 630^2 := 714^2$	$336^2 + 2002^2 := 2030^2$	$336^2 + 14110^2 := 14114^2$
$336^2 + 748^2 := 820^2$	$336^2 + 2340^2 := 2364^2$	$336^2 + 28223^2 := 28225^2$
$336^2 + 850^2 := 914^2$	$336^2 + 3127^2 := 3145^2$	

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(336, 3520, 3536)** $\Rightarrow 3536 - 3520 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 28224$, $T_{16} := 336^2$,
 $E := \{7041, 7043, \dots, 7069, 7071\}$
2. **(336, 1550, 1586)** $\Rightarrow 1586 - 1550 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 18816$, $T_{36} := 336^2$,
 $E := \{3101, 3103, \dots, 3169, 3171\}$
3. **(336, 850, 914)** $\Rightarrow 914 - 850 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 14112$, $T_{64} := 336^2$,
 $E := \{1701, 1703, \dots, 1825, 1827\}$
4. **(336, 377, 505)** $\Rightarrow 505 - 336 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 10933$, $T_{169} := 377^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 1007, 1009\}$ or $E := \{757, 758, \dots, 924, 925\}$
5. **(336, 527, 625)** $\Rightarrow 625 - 336 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 16337$, $T_{289} := 527^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 1247, 1249\}$ or $E := \{817, 818, \dots, 1104, 1105\}$
6. **(336, 748, 820)** $\Rightarrow 820 - 336 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 25432$, $T_{484} := 748^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 1637, 1639\}$
7. **(336, 1748, 1780)** $\Rightarrow 1780 - 336 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 80408$, $T_{1444} := 1748^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 3557, 3559\}$
8. **(336, 3127, 3145)** $\Rightarrow 3145 - 336 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 184493$, $T_{2809} := 3127^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 6287, 6289\}$ or $E := \{2077, 2078, \dots, 4884, 4885\}$
9. **(336, 7052, 7060)** $\Rightarrow 7060 - 336 = 82^2$, $S_{82 \times 82} := 606472$, $T_{6724} := 7052^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 14117, 14119\}$
10. **(336, 28223, 28225)** $\Rightarrow 28225 - 336 = 167^2$, $S_{167 \times 167} := 4769687$, $T_{27889} := 28223^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 56447, 56449\}$ or $E := \{14617, 14618, \dots, 42504, 42505\}$

■ Number 337

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$337^2 + 56784^2 := 56785^2$$

■ Number 338

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$338^2 + 2184^2 := 2210^2$$

$$338^2 + 28560^2 := 28562^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(338, 28560, 28562)** $\Rightarrow 28562 - 338 = 168^2$, $S_{168 \times 168} := 4855200$, $T_{28224} := 28560^2$,
 $E := \{677, 679, \dots, 57121, 57123\}$

■ Number 339

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$339^2 + 452^2 := 565^2$$

$$339^2 + 6380^2 := 6389^2$$

$$339^2 + 19152^2 := 19155^2$$

$$339^2 + 57460^2 := 57461^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(339, 6380, 6389)** $\Rightarrow 6389 - 6380 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 38307$, $T_9 := 339^2$,
 $E := \{12761, 12763, \dots, 12775, 12777\}$ or $E := \{12765, 12766, \dots, 12772, 12773\}$

■ Number 340

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$340^2 + 357^2 := 493^2$$

$$340^2 + 528^2 := 628^2$$

$$340^2 + 816^2 := 884^2$$

$$340^2 + 1131^2 := 1181^2$$

$$340^2 + 1425^2 := 1465^2$$

$$340^2 + 1683^2 := 1717^2$$

$$340^2 + 2880^2 := 2900^2$$

$$340^2 + 5775^2 := 5785^2$$

$$340^2 + 7221^2 := 7229^2$$

$$340^2 + 14448^2 := 14452^2$$

$$340^2 + 28899^2 := 28901^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(340, 528, 628)** $\Rightarrow 628 - 528 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 11560$, $T_{100} := 340^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 1253, 1255\}$

2. **(340, 1131, 1181)** $\Rightarrow 1181 - 340 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 44109$, $T_{841} := 1131^2$,
 $E := \{681, 683, \dots, 2359, 2361\}$ or $E := \{1101, 1102, \dots, 1940, 1941\}$

3. **(340, 7221, 7229)** $\Rightarrow 7229 - 340 = 83^2$, $S_{83 \times 83} := 628227$, $T_{6889} := 7221^2$,
 $E := \{681, 683, \dots, 14455, 14457\}$ or $E := \{4125, 4126, \dots, 11012, 11013\}$
4. **(340, 28899, 28901)** $\Rightarrow 28901 - 340 = 169^2$, $S_{169 \times 169} := 4941729$, $T_{28561} := 28899^2$,
 $E := \{681, 683, \dots, 57799, 57801\}$ or $E := \{14961, 14962, \dots, 43520, 43521\}$

■ Number 341

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 341^2 + 420^2 := 541^2 & 341^2 + 5280^2 := 5291^2 \\ 341^2 + 1860^2 := 1891^2 & 341^2 + 58140^2 := 58141^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(341, 420, 541)** $\Rightarrow 541 - 420 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 10571$, $T_{121} := 341^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 1079, 1081\}$ or $E := \{901, 902, \dots, 1020, 1021\}$

■ Number 342

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 342^2 + 456^2 := 570^2 & 342^2 + 3240^2 := 3258^2 \\ 342^2 + 1056^2 := 1110^2 & 342^2 + 9744^2 := 9750^2 \\ 342^2 + 1520^2 := 1558^2 & 342^2 + 29240^2 := 29242^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(342, 3240, 3258)** $\Rightarrow 3258 - 342 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 194400$, $T_{2916} := 3240^2$,
 $E := \{685, 687, \dots, 6513, 6515\}$
2. **(342, 29240, 29242)** $\Rightarrow 29242 - 342 = 170^2$, $S_{170 \times 170} := 5029280$, $T_{28900} := 29240^2$,
 $E := \{685, 687, \dots, 58481, 58483\}$

■ Number 343

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{l} 343^2 + 1176^2 := 1225^2 \\ 343^2 + 8400^2 := 8407^2 \\ 343^2 + 58824^2 := 58825^2 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(343, 1176, 1225)** $\Rightarrow 1225 - 1176 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 16807$, $T_{49} := 343^2$,
 $E := \{2353, 2355, \dots, 2447, 2449\}$ or $E := \{2377, 2378, \dots, 2424, 2425\}$

■ Number 344

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$344^2 + 645^2 := 731^2$	$344^2 + 7392^2 := 7400^2$
$344^2 + 1833^2 := 1865^2$	$344^2 + 14790^2 := 14794^2$
$344^2 + 3690^2 := 3706^2$	$344^2 + 29583^2 := 29585^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(344, 3690, 3706)** $\Rightarrow 3706 - 3690 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 29584$, $T_{16} := 344^2$,
 $E := \{7381, 7383, \dots, 7409, 7411\}$
2. **(344, 1833, 1865)** $\Rightarrow 1865 - 344 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 86151$, $T_{1521} := 1833^2$,
 $E := \{689, 691, \dots, 3727, 3729\}$ or $E := \{1449, 1450, \dots, 2968, 2969\}$
3. **(344, 7392, 7400)** $\Rightarrow 7400 - 344 = 84^2$, $S_{84 \times 84} := 650496$, $T_{7056} := 7392^2$,
 $E := \{689, 691, \dots, 14797, 14799\}$
4. **(344, 29583, 29585)** $\Rightarrow 29585 - 344 = 171^2$, $S_{171 \times 171} := 5117859$, $T_{29241} := 29583^2$,
 $E := \{689, 691, \dots, 59167, 59169\}$ or $E := \{15309, 15310, \dots, 44548, 44549\}$

■ Number 345

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$345^2 + 460^2 := 575^2$	$345^2 + 2368^2 := 2393^2$	$345^2 + 11900^2 := 11905^2$
$345^2 + 756^2 := 831^2$	$345^2 + 2576^2 := 2599^2$	$345^2 + 19836^2 := 19839^2$
$345^2 + 828^2 := 897^2$	$345^2 + 3960^2 := 3975^2$	$345^2 + 59512^2 := 59513^2$
$345^2 + 1300^2 := 1345^2$	$345^2 + 6608^2 := 6617^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(345, 6608, 6617)** $\Rightarrow 6617 - 6608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 39675$, $T_9 := 345^2$,
 $E := \{13217, 13219, \dots, 13231, 13233\}$ or $E := \{13221, 13222, \dots, 13228, 13229\}$

2. **(345, 2368, 2393)** $\Rightarrow 2393 - 2368 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 23805$, $T_{25} := 345^2$,
 $E := \{4737, 4739, \dots, 4783, 4785\}$ or $E := \{4749, 4750, \dots, 4772, 4773\}$

■ Number 346

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$346^2 + 29928^2 := 29930^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(346, 29928, 29930)** $\Rightarrow 29930 - 346 = 172^2$, $S_{172 \times 172} := 5207472$, $T_{29584} := 29928^2$,
 $E := \{693, 695, \dots, 59857, 59859\}$

■ Number 347

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$347^2 + 60204^2 := 60205^2$$

■ Number 348

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$348^2 + 464^2 := 580^2$$

$$348^2 + 805^2 := 877^2$$

$$348^2 + 1015^2 := 1073^2$$

$$348^2 + 1664^2 := 1700^2$$

$$348^2 + 2511^2 := 2535^2$$

$$348^2 + 3355^2 := 3373^2$$

$$348^2 + 5040^2 := 5052^2$$

$$348^2 + 7565^2 := 7573^2$$

$$348^2 + 10089^2 := 10095^2$$

$$348^2 + 15136^2 := 15140^2$$

$$348^2 + 30275^2 := 30277^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(348, 1664, 1700)** $\Rightarrow 1700 - 1664 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 20184$, $T_{36} := 348^2$,
 $E := \{3329, 3331, \dots, 3397, 3399\}$

2. **(348, 805, 877)** $\Rightarrow 877 - 348 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 28175$, $T_{529} := 805^2$,
 $E := \{697, 699, \dots, 1751, 1753\}$ or $E := \{961, 962, \dots, 1488, 1489\}$

3. **(348, 3355, 3373)** $\Rightarrow 3373 - 348 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 204655$, $T_{3025} := 3355^2$,
 $E := \{697, 699, \dots, 6743, 6745\}$ or $E := \{2209, 2210, \dots, 5232, 5233\}$

4. **(348, 7565, 7573)** $\Rightarrow 7573 - 348 = 85^2$, $S_{85 \times 85} := 673285$, $T_{7225} := 7565^2$,
 $E := \{697, 699, \dots, 15143, 15145\}$ or $E := \{4309, 4310, \dots, 11532, 11533\}$
5. **(348, 30275, 30277)** $\Rightarrow 30277 - 348 = 173^2$, $S_{173 \times 173} := 5298125$, $T_{29929} := 30275^2$,
 $E := \{697, 699, \dots, 60551, 60553\}$ or $E := \{15661, 15662, \dots, 45588, 45589\}$

■ Number 349

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$349^2 + 60900^2 := 60901^2$$

■ Number 350

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$350^2 + 576^2 := 674^2$$

$$350^2 + 840^2 := 910^2$$

$$350^2 + 1200^2 := 1250^2$$

$$350^2 + 4368^2 := 4382^2$$

$$350^2 + 6120^2 := 6130^2$$

$$350^2 + 30624^2 := 30626^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(350, 576, 674)** $\Rightarrow 674 - 350 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 18432$, $T_{324} := 576^2$,
 $E := \{701, 703, \dots, 1345, 1347\}$
2. **(350, 1200, 1250)** $\Rightarrow 1250 - 350 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 48000$, $T_{900} := 1200^2$,
 $E := \{701, 703, \dots, 2497, 2499\}$
3. **(350, 30624, 30626)** $\Rightarrow 30626 - 350 = 174^2$, $S_{174 \times 174} := 5389824$, $T_{30276} := 30624^2$,
 $E := \{701, 703, \dots, 61249, 61251\}$

■ Number 351

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$351^2 + 468^2 := 585^2$$

$$351^2 + 720^2 := 801^2$$

$$351^2 + 1560^2 := 1599^2$$

$$351^2 + 2268^2 := 2295^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 351^2 + 4732^2 &:= 4745^2 \\
 351^2 + 6840^2 &:= 6849^2 \\
 351^2 + 20532^2 &:= 20535^2 \\
 351^2 + 61600^2 &:= 61601^2
 \end{aligned}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(351, 6840, 6849)** $\Rightarrow 6849 - 6840 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 41067$, $T_9 := 351^2$,
 $E := \{13681, 13683, \dots, 13695, 13697\}$ or $E := \{13685, 13686, \dots, 13692, 13693\}$
2. **(351, 720, 801)** $\Rightarrow 801 - 720 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 13689$, $T_{81} := 351^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 1599, 1601\}$ or $E := \{1481, 1482, \dots, 1560, 1561\}$

■ Number 352

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$352^2 + 420^2 := 548^2$	$352^2 + 1386^2 := 1430^2$	$352^2 + 3864^2 := 3880^2$
$352^2 + 660^2 := 748^2$	$352^2 + 1920^2 := 1952^2$	$352^2 + 7740^2 := 7748^2$
$352^2 + 936^2 := 1000^2$	$352^2 + 2805^2 := 2827^2$	$352^2 + 15486^2 := 15490^2$
		$352^2 + 30975^2 := 30977^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(352, 3864, 3880)** $\Rightarrow 3880 - 3864 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 30976$, $T_{16} := 352^2$,
 $E := \{7729, 7731, \dots, 7757, 7759\}$
2. **(352, 936, 1000)** $\Rightarrow 1000 - 936 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 15488$, $T_{64} := 352^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 1997, 1999\}$
3. **(352, 420, 548)** $\Rightarrow 548 - 352 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 12600$, $T_{196} := 420^2$,
 $E := \{705, 707, \dots, 1093, 1095\}$
4. **(352, 1920, 1952)** $\Rightarrow 1952 - 352 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 92160$, $T_{1600} := 1920^2$,
 $E := \{705, 707, \dots, 3901, 3903\}$
5. **(352, 7740, 7748)** $\Rightarrow 7748 - 352 = 86^2$, $S_{86 \times 86} := 696600$, $T_{7396} := 7740^2$,
 $E := \{705, 707, \dots, 15493, 15495\}$
6. **(352, 30975, 30977)** $\Rightarrow 30977 - 352 = 175^2$, $S_{175 \times 175} := 5482575$, $T_{30625} := 30975^2$,
 $E := \{705, 707, \dots, 61951, 61953\}$ or $E := \{16017, 16018, \dots, 46640, 46641\}$

■ Number 353

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$353^2 + 62304^2 := 62305^2$$

■ Number 354

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$354^2 + 472^2 := 590^2$$

$$354^2 + 3472^2 := 3490^2$$

$$354^2 + 10440^2 := 10446^2$$

$$354^2 + 31328^2 := 31330^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(354, 3472, 3490)** $\Rightarrow 3490 - 354 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 215264$, $T_{3136} := 3472^2$,
 $E := \{709, 711, \dots, 6977, 6979\}$

2. **(354, 31328, 31330)** $\Rightarrow 31330 - 354 = 176^2$, $S_{176 \times 176} := 5576384$, $T_{30976} := 31328^2$,
 $E := \{709, 711, \dots, 62657, 62659\}$

■ Number 355

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$355^2 + 852^2 := 923^2$$

$$355^2 + 2508^2 := 2533^2$$

$$355^2 + 12600^2 := 12605^2$$

$$355^2 + 63012^2 := 63013^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(355, 2508, 2533)** $\Rightarrow 2533 - 2508 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 25205$, $T_{25} := 355^2$,
 $E := \{5017, 5019, \dots, 5063, 5065\}$ or $E := \{5029, 5030, \dots, 5052, 5053\}$

■ Number 356

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$356^2 + 7917^2 := 7925^2$$

$$356^2 + 15840^2 := 15844^2$$

$$356^2 + 31683^2 := 31685^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(356, 7917, 7925)** $\Rightarrow 7925 - 356 = 87^2$, $S_{87 \times 87} := 720447$, $T_{7569} := 7917^2$,
 $E := \{713, 715, \dots, 15847, 15849\}$ or $E := \{4497, 4498, \dots, 12064, 12065\}$
2. **(356, 31683, 31685)** $\Rightarrow 31685 - 356 = 177^2$, $S_{177 \times 177} := 5671257$, $T_{31329} := 31683^2$,
 $E := \{713, 715, \dots, 63367, 63369\}$ or $E := \{16377, 16378, \dots, 47704, 47705\}$

■ Number 357

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$357^2 + 360^2 := 507^2$	$357^2 + 1276^2 := 1325^2$	$357^2 + 9100^2 := 9107^2$
$357^2 + 476^2 := 595^2$	$357^2 + 3024^2 := 3045^2$	$357^2 + 21240^2 := 21243^2$
$357^2 + 980^2 := 1043^2$	$357^2 + 3740^2 := 3757^2$	$357^2 + 63724^2 := 63725^2$
$357^2 + 1224^2 := 1275^2$	$357^2 + 7076^2 := 7085^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(357, 7076, 7085)** $\Rightarrow 7085 - 7076 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 42483$, $T_9 := 357^2$,
 $E := \{14153, 14155, \dots, 14167, 14169\}$ or $E := \{14157, 14158, \dots, 14164, 14165\}$
2. **(357, 1276, 1325)** $\Rightarrow 1325 - 1276 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 18207$, $T_{49} := 357^2$,
 $E := \{2553, 2555, \dots, 2647, 2649\}$ or $E := \{2577, 2578, \dots, 2624, 2625\}$

■ Number 358

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$358^2 + 32040^2 := 32042^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(358, 32040, 32042)** $\Rightarrow 32042 - 358 = 178^2$, $S_{178 \times 178} := 5767200$, $T_{31684} := 32040^2$,
 $E := \{717, 719, \dots, 64081, 64083\}$

■ Number 359

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$359^2 + 64440^2 := 64441^2$$

■ Number 360

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$360^2 + 378^2 := 522^2$$

$$360^2 + 480^2 := 600^2$$

$$360^2 + 546^2 := 654^2$$

$$360^2 + 598^2 := 698^2$$

$$360^2 + 627^2 := 723^2$$

$$360^2 + 675^2 := 765^2$$

$$360^2 + 770^2 := 850^2$$

$$360^2 + 864^2 := 936^2$$

$$360^2 + 1050^2 := 1110^2$$

$$360^2 + 1173^2 := 1227^2$$

$$360^2 + 1271^2 := 1321^2$$

$$360^2 + 1326^2 := 1374^2$$

$$360^2 + 1600^2 := 1640^2$$

$$360^2 + 1782^2 := 1818^2$$

$$360^2 + 2009^2 := 2041^2$$

$$360^2 + 2145^2 := 2175^2$$

$$360^2 + 2688^2 := 2712^2$$

$$360^2 + 3230^2 := 3250^2$$

$$360^2 + 3591^2 := 3609^2$$

$$360^2 + 4042^2 := 4058^2$$

$$360^2 + 5394^2 := 5406^2$$

$$360^2 + 6475^2 := 6485^2$$

$$360^2 + 8096^2 := 8104^2$$

$$360^2 + 10797^2 := 10803^2$$

$$360^2 + 16198^2 := 16202^2$$

$$360^2 + 32399^2 := 32401^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(360, 4042, 4058)** $\Rightarrow 4058 - 4042 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 32400$, $T_{16} := 360^2$,
 $E := \{8085, 8087, \dots, 8113, 8115\}$
2. **(360, 1782, 1818)** $\Rightarrow 1818 - 1782 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 21600$, $T_{36} := 360^2$,
 $E := \{3565, 3567, \dots, 3633, 3635\}$
3. **(360, 598, 698)** $\Rightarrow 698 - 598 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 12960$, $T_{100} := 360^2$,
 $E := \{1197, 1199, \dots, 1393, 1395\}$
4. **(360, 378, 522)** $\Rightarrow 522 - 378 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 10800$, $T_{144} := 360^2$,
 $E := \{757, 759, \dots, 1041, 1043\}$
5. **(360, 864, 936)** $\Rightarrow 936 - 360 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 31104$, $T_{576} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 1869, 1871\}$
6. **(360, 1271, 1321)** $\Rightarrow 1321 - 360 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 52111$, $T_{961} := 1271^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 2639, 2641\}$ or $E := \{1201, 1202, \dots, 2160, 2161\}$
7. **(360, 2009, 2041)** $\Rightarrow 2041 - 360 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 98441$, $T_{1681} := 2009^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 4079, 4081\}$ or $E := \{1561, 1562, \dots, 3240, 3241\}$

8. **(360, 3591, 3609)** $\Rightarrow 3609 - 360 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 226233$, $T_{3249} := 3591^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 7215, 7217\}$ or $E := \{2345, 2346, \dots, 5592, 5593\}$
9. **(360, 8096, 8104)** $\Rightarrow 8104 - 360 = 88^2$, $S_{88 \times 88} := 744832$, $T_{7744} := 8096^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 16205, 16207\}$
10. **(360, 32399, 32401)** $\Rightarrow 32401 - 360 = 179^2$, $S_{179 \times 179} := 5864219$, $T_{32041} := 32399^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 64799, 64801\}$ or $E := \{16741, 16742, \dots, 48780, 48781\}$

■ Number 361

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$361^2 + 3420^2 := 3439^2$$

$$361^2 + 65160^2 := 65161^2$$

■ Number 362

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$362^2 + 32760^2 := 32762^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(362, 32760, 32762)** $\Rightarrow 32762 - 362 = 180^2$, $S_{180 \times 180} := 5962320$, $T_{32400} := 32760^2$,
 $E := \{725, 727, \dots, 65521, 65523\}$

■ Number 363

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$363^2 + 484^2 := 605^2$$

$$363^2 + 616^2 := 715^2$$

$$363^2 + 1980^2 := 2013^2$$

$$363^2 + 5984^2 := 5995^2$$

$$363^2 + 7316^2 := 7325^2$$

$$363^2 + 21960^2 := 21963^2$$

$$363^2 + 65884^2 := 65885^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(363, 7316, 7325)** $\Rightarrow 7325 - 7316 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 43923$, $T_9 := 363^2$,
 $E := \{14633, 14635, \dots, 14647, 14649\}$ or $E := \{14637, 14638, \dots, 14644, 14645\}$

2. **(363, 484, 605)** $\Rightarrow 605 - 484 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 11979$, $T_{121} := 363^2$,
 $E := \{969, 971, \dots, 1207, 1209\}$ or $E := \{1029, 1030, \dots, 1148, 1149\}$

■ Number 364

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$364^2 + 585^2 := 689^2$$

$$364^2 + 627^2 := 725^2$$

$$364^2 + 1155^2 := 1211^2$$

$$364^2 + 1248^2 := 1300^2$$

$$364^2 + 2352^2 := 2380^2$$

$$364^2 + 2535^2 := 2561^2$$

$$364^2 + 4725^2 := 4739^2$$

$$364^2 + 8277^2 := 8285^2$$

$$364^2 + 16560^2 := 16564^2$$

$$364^2 + 33123^2 := 33125^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(364, 627, 725)** $\Rightarrow 725 - 364 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 20691$, $T_{361} := 627^2$,
 $E := \{729, 731, \dots, 1447, 1449\}$ or $E := \{909, 910, \dots, 1268, 1269\}$
2. **(364, 8277, 8285)** $\Rightarrow 8285 - 364 = 89^2$, $S_{89 \times 89} := 769761$, $T_{7921} := 8277^2$,
 $E := \{729, 731, \dots, 16567, 16569\}$ or $E := \{4689, 4690, \dots, 12608, 12609\}$
3. **(364, 33123, 33125)** $\Rightarrow 33125 - 364 = 181^2$, $S_{181 \times 181} := 6061509$, $T_{32761} := 33123^2$,
 $E := \{729, 731, \dots, 66247, 66249\}$ or $E := \{17109, 17110, \dots, 49868, 49869\}$

■ Number 365

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$365^2 + 876^2 := 949^2$$

$$365^2 + 2652^2 := 2677^2$$

$$365^2 + 13320^2 := 13325^2$$

$$365^2 + 66612^2 := 66613^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(365, 2652, 2677)** $\Rightarrow 2677 - 2652 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 26645$, $T_{25} := 365^2$,
 $E := \{5305, 5307, \dots, 5351, 5353\}$ or $E := \{5317, 5318, \dots, 5340, 5341\}$

■ Number 366

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$366^2 + 488^2 := 610^2$$

$$366^2 + 3712^2 := 3730^2$$

$$366^2 + 11160^2 := 11166^2$$

$$366^2 + 33488^2 := 33490^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(366, 3712, 3730)** $\Rightarrow 3730 - 366 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 237568$, $T_{3364} := 3712^2$,
 $E := \{733, 735, \dots, 7457, 7459\}$

2. **(366, 33488, 33490)** $\Rightarrow 33490 - 366 = 182^2$, $S_{182 \times 182} := 6161792$, $T_{33124} := 33488^2$,
 $E := \{733, 735, \dots, 66977, 66979\}$

■ Number 367

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$367^2 + 67344^2 := 67345^2$$

■ Number 368

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$368^2 + 465^2 := 593^2$$

$$368^2 + 690^2 := 782^2$$

$$368^2 + 1026^2 := 1090^2$$

$$368^2 + 1449^2 := 1495^2$$

$$368^2 + 2100^2 := 2132^2$$

$$368^2 + 4224^2 := 4240^2$$

$$368^2 + 8460^2 := 8468^2$$

$$368^2 + 16926^2 := 16930^2$$

$$368^2 + 33855^2 := 33857^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(368, 4224, 4240)** $\Rightarrow 4240 - 4224 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 33856$, $T_{16} := 368^2$,
 $E := \{8449, 8451, \dots, 8477, 8479\}$

2. **(368, 1026, 1090)** $\Rightarrow 1090 - 1026 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 16928$, $T_{64} := 368^2$,
 $E := \{2053, 2055, \dots, 2177, 2179\}$

3. **(368, 465, 593)** $\Rightarrow 593 - 368 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 14415$, $T_{225} := 465^2$,
 $E := \{737, 739, \dots, 1183, 1185\}$ or $E := \{849, 850, \dots, 1072, 1073\}$

4. **(368, 2100, 2132)** $\Rightarrow 2132 - 368 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 105000$, $T_{1764} := 2100^2$,
 $E := \{737, 739, \dots, 4261, 4263\}$

5. **(368, 8460, 8468)** $\Rightarrow 8468 - 368 = 90^2$, $S_{90 \times 90} := 795240$, $T_{8100} := 8460^2$,
 $E := \{737, 739, \dots, 16933, 16935\}$

6. **(368, 33855, 33857)** $\Rightarrow 33857 - 368 = 183^2$, $S_{183 \times 183} := 6263175$, $T_{33489} := 33855^2$,
 $E := \{737, 739, \dots, 67711, 67713\}$ or $E := \{17481, 17482, \dots, 50968, 50969\}$

■ Number 369

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$369^2 + 492^2 := 615^2$	$369^2 + 7560^2 := 7569^2$
$369^2 + 800^2 := 881^2$	$369^2 + 22692^2 := 22695^2$
$369^2 + 1640^2 := 1681^2$	$369^2 + 68080^2 := 68081^2$
$369^2 + 2508^2 := 2535^2$	

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(369, 7560, 7569)** $\Rightarrow 7569 - 7560 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 45387$, $T_9 := 369^2$,
 $E := \{15121, 15123, \dots, 15135, 15137\}$ or $E := \{15125, 15126, \dots, 15132, 15133\}$

2. **(369, 800, 881)** $\Rightarrow 881 - 800 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 15129$, $T_{81} := 369^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 1759, 1761\}$ or $E := \{1641, 1642, \dots, 1720, 1721\}$

■ Number 370

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$370^2 + 888^2 := 962^2$	$370^2 + 6840^2 := 6850^2$
$370^2 + 1344^2 := 1394^2$	$370^2 + 34224^2 := 34226^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(370, 1344, 1394)** $\Rightarrow 1394 - 370 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 56448$, $T_{1024} := 1344^2$,
 $E := \{741, 743, \dots, 2785, 2787\}$

2. **(370, 34224, 34226)** $\Rightarrow 34226 - 370 = 184^2$, $S_{184 \times 184} := 6365664$, $T_{33856} := 34224^2$,
 $E := \{741, 743, \dots, 68449, 68451\}$

■ Number 371

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$371^2 + 1272^2 := 1325^2$$

$$371^2 + 1380^2 := 1429^2$$

$$371^2 + 9828^2 := 9835^2$$

$$371^2 + 68820^2 := 68821^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(371, 1380, 1429)** $\Rightarrow 1429 - 1380 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 19663$, $T_{49} := 371^2$,
 $E := \{2761, 2763, \dots, 2855, 2857\}$ or $E := \{2785, 2786, \dots, 2832, 2833\}$

■ Number 372

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$372^2 + 496^2 := 620^2$$

$$372^2 + 925^2 := 997^2$$

$$372^2 + 5760^2 := 5772^2$$

$$372^2 + 8645^2 := 8653^2$$

$$372^2 + 1085^2 := 1147^2$$

$$372^2 + 1904^2 := 1940^2$$

$$372^2 + 2871^2 := 2895^2$$

$$372^2 + 3835^2 := 3853^2$$

$$372^2 + 11529^2 := 11535^2$$

$$372^2 + 17296^2 := 17300^2$$

$$372^2 + 34595^2 := 34597^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(372, 1904, 1940)** $\Rightarrow 1940 - 1904 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 23064$, $T_{36} := 372^2$,
 $E := \{3809, 3811, \dots, 3877, 3879\}$
2. **(372, 925, 997)** $\Rightarrow 997 - 372 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 34225$, $T_{625} := 925^2$,
 $E := \{745, 747, \dots, 1991, 1993\}$ or $E := \{1057, 1058, \dots, 1680, 1681\}$
3. **(372, 3835, 3853)** $\Rightarrow 3853 - 372 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 249275$, $T_{3481} := 3835^2$,
 $E := \{745, 747, \dots, 7703, 7705\}$ or $E := \{2485, 2486, \dots, 5964, 5965\}$
4. **(372, 8645, 8653)** $\Rightarrow 8653 - 372 = 91^2$, $S_{91 \times 91} := 821275$, $T_{8281} := 8645^2$,
 $E := \{745, 747, \dots, 17303, 17305\}$ or $E := \{4885, 4886, \dots, 13164, 13165\}$
5. **(372, 34595, 34597)** $\Rightarrow 34597 - 372 = 185^2$, $S_{185 \times 185} := 6469265$, $T_{34225} := 34595^2$,
 $E := \{745, 747, \dots, 69191, 69193\}$ or $E := \{17857, 17858, \dots, 52080, 52081\}$

■ Number 373

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$373^2 + 69564^2 := 69565^2$$

■ Number 374

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$374^2 + 2040^2 := 2074^2$$

$$374^2 + 3168^2 := 3190^2$$

$$374^2 + 34968^2 := 34970^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(374, 34968, 34970)** $\Rightarrow 34970 - 374 = 186^2$, $S_{186 \times 186} := 6573984$, $T_{34596} := 34968^2$,
 $E := \{749, 751, \dots, 69937, 69939\}$

■ Number 375

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$375^2 + 500^2 := 625^2$$

$$375^2 + 900^2 := 975^2$$

$$375^2 + 1540^2 := 1585^2$$

$$375^2 + 2800^2 := 2825^2$$

$$375^2 + 4680^2 := 4695^2$$

$$375^2 + 7808^2 := 7817^2$$

$$375^2 + 14060^2 := 14065^2$$

$$375^2 + 23436^2 := 23439^2$$

$$375^2 + 70312^2 := 70313^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(375, 7808, 7817)** $\Rightarrow 7817 - 7808 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 46875$, $T_9 := 375^2$,
 $E := \{15617, 15619, \dots, 15631, 15633\}$ or $E := \{15621, 15622, \dots, 15628, 15629\}$
2. **(375, 2800, 2825)** $\Rightarrow 2825 - 2800 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 28125$, $T_{25} := 375^2$,
 $E := \{5601, 5603, \dots, 5647, 5649\}$ or $E := \{5613, 5614, \dots, 5636, 5637\}$

■ Number 376

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$376^2 + 705^2 := 799^2$$

$$376^2 + 2193^2 := 2225^2$$

$$376^2 + 4410^2 := 4426^2$$

$$376^2 + 8832^2 := 8840^2$$

$$376^2 + 17670^2 := 17674^2$$

$$376^2 + 35343^2 := 35345^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(376, 4410, 4426)** $\Rightarrow 4426 - 4410 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 35344$, $T_{16} := 376^2$,
 $E := \{8821, 8823, \dots, 8849, 8851\}$

2. **(376, 2193, 2225)** $\Rightarrow 2225 - 376 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 111843$, $T_{1849} := 2193^2$,
 $E := \{753, 755, \dots, 4447, 4449\}$ or $E := \{1677, 1678, \dots, 3524, 3525\}$
3. **(376, 8832, 8840)** $\Rightarrow 8840 - 376 = 92^2$, $S_{92 \times 92} := 847872$, $T_{8464} := 8832^2$,
 $E := \{753, 755, \dots, 17677, 17679\}$
4. **(376, 35343, 35345)** $\Rightarrow 35345 - 376 = 187^2$, $S_{187 \times 187} := 6679827$, $T_{34969} := 35343^2$,
 $E := \{753, 755, \dots, 70687, 70689\}$ or $E := \{18237, 18238, \dots, 53204, 53205\}$

■ Number 377

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$377^2 + 2436^2 := 2465^2$$

$$377^2 + 5460^2 := 5473^2$$

$$377^2 + 71064^2 := 71065^2$$

■ Number 378

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$378^2 + 504^2 := 630^2$	$378^2 + 3960^2 := 3978^2$
$378^2 + 680^2 := 778^2$	$378^2 + 5096^2 := 5110^2$
$378^2 + 1296^2 := 1350^2$	$378^2 + 35720^2 := 35722^2$
$378^2 + 1680^2 := 1722^2$	$378^2 + 11904^2 := 11910^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(378, 680, 778)** $\Rightarrow 778 - 378 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 23120$, $T_{400} := 680^2$,
 $E := \{757, 759, \dots, 1553, 1555\}$
2. **(378, 3960, 3978)** $\Rightarrow 3978 - 378 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 261360$, $T_{3600} := 3960^2$,
 $E := \{757, 759, \dots, 7953, 7955\}$
3. **(378, 35720, 35722)** $\Rightarrow 35722 - 378 = 188^2$, $S_{188 \times 188} := 6786800$, $T_{35344} := 35720^2$,
 $E := \{757, 759, \dots, 71441, 71443\}$

■ Number 379

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$379^2 + 71820^2 := 71821^2$$

■ Number 380

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$380^2 + 399^2 := 551^2$$

$$380^2 + 672^2 := 772^2$$

$$380^2 + 912^2 := 988^2$$

$$380^2 + 1419^2 := 1469^2$$

$$380^2 + 1785^2 := 1825^2$$

$$380^2 + 1881^2 := 1919^2$$

$$380^2 + 3600^2 := 3620^2$$

$$380^2 + 7215^2 := 7225^2$$

$$380^2 + 9021^2 := 9029^2$$

$$380^2 + 18048^2 := 18052^2$$

$$380^2 + 36099^2 := 36101^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(380, 672, 772)** $\Rightarrow 772 - 672 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 14440$, $T_{100} := 380^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 1541, 1543\}$
2. **(380, 1419, 1469)** $\Rightarrow 1469 - 380 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 61017$, $T_{1089} := 1419^2$,
 $E := \{761, 763, \dots, 2935, 2937\}$ or $E := \{1305, 1306, \dots, 2392, 2393\}$
3. **(380, 9021, 9029)** $\Rightarrow 9029 - 380 = 93^2$, $S_{93 \times 93} := 875037$, $T_{8649} := 9021^2$,
 $E := \{761, 763, \dots, 18055, 18057\}$ or $E := \{5085, 5086, \dots, 13732, 13733\}$
4. **(380, 36099, 36101)** $\Rightarrow 36101 - 380 = 189^2$, $S_{189 \times 189} := 6894909$, $T_{35721} := 36099^2$,
 $E := \{761, 763, \dots, 72199, 72201\}$ or $E := \{18621, 18622, \dots, 54340, 54341\}$

■ Number 381

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$381^2 + 508^2 := 635^2$$

$$381^2 + 8060^2 := 8069^2$$

$$381^2 + 24192^2 := 24195^2$$

$$381^2 + 72580^2 := 72581^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(381, 8060, 8069)** $\Rightarrow 8069 - 8060 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 48387$, $T_9 := 381^2$,
 $E := \{16121, 16123, \dots, 16135, 16137\}$ or $E := \{16125, 16126, \dots, 16132, 16133\}$

■ Number 382

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$382^2 + 36480^2 := 36482^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(382, 36480, 36482)** $\Rightarrow 36482 - 382 = 190^2$, $S_{190 \times 190} := 7004160$, $T_{36100} := 36480^2$,
 $E := \{765, 767, \dots, 72961, 72963\}$

■ Number 383

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$383^2 + 73344^2 := 73345^2$$

■ Number 384

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$384^2 + 440^2 := 584^2$$

$$384^2 + 512^2 := 640^2$$

$$384^2 + 720^2 := 816^2$$

$$384^2 + 988^2 := 1060^2$$

$$384^2 + 1120^2 := 1184^2$$

$$384^2 + 1512^2 := 1560^2$$

$$384^2 + 2030^2 := 2066^2$$

$$384^2 + 2288^2 := 2320^2$$

$$384^2 + 3060^2 := 3084^2$$

$$384^2 + 4087^2 := 4105^2$$

$$384^2 + 4600^2 := 4616^2$$

$$384^2 + 6138^2 := 6150^2$$

$$384^2 + 9212^2 := 9220^2$$

$$384^2 + 12285^2 := 12291^2$$

$$384^2 + 18430^2 := 18434^2$$

$$384^2 + 36863^2 := 36865^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(384, 4600, 4616)** $\Rightarrow 4616 - 4600 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 36864$, $T_{16} := 384^2$,
 $E := \{9201, 9203, \dots, 9229, 9231\}$
2. **(384, 2030, 2066)** $\Rightarrow 2066 - 2030 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 24576$, $T_{36} := 384^2$,
 $E := \{4061, 4063, \dots, 4129, 4131\}$
3. **(384, 1120, 1184)** $\Rightarrow 1184 - 1120 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 18432$, $T_{64} := 384^2$,
 $E := \{2241, 2243, \dots, 2365, 2367\}$
4. **(384, 440, 584)** $\Rightarrow 584 - 440 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 12288$, $T_{144} := 384^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 1165, 1167\}$

5. **(384, 512, 640)** $\Rightarrow 640 - 384 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 16384$, $T_{256} := 512^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 1277, 1279\}$
6. **(384, 988, 1060)** $\Rightarrow 1060 - 384 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 37544$, $T_{676} := 988^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 2117, 2119\}$
7. **(384, 2288, 2320)** $\Rightarrow 2320 - 384 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 118976$, $T_{1936} := 2288^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 4637, 4639\}$
8. **(384, 4087, 4105)** $\Rightarrow 4105 - 384 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 273829$, $T_{3721} := 4087^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 8207, 8209\}$ or $E := \{2629, 2630, \dots, 6348, 6349\}$
9. **(384, 9212, 9220)** $\Rightarrow 9220 - 384 = 94^2$, $S_{94 \times 94} := 902776$, $T_{8836} := 9212^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 18437, 18439\}$
10. **(384, 36863, 36865)** $\Rightarrow 36865 - 384 = 191^2$, $S_{191 \times 191} := 7114559$, $T_{36481} := 36863^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 73727, 73729\}$ or $E := \{19009, 19010, \dots, 55488, 55489\}$

■ Number 385

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$385^2 + 552^2 := 673^2$$

$$385^2 + 924^2 := 1001^2$$

$$385^2 + 1320^2 := 1375^2$$

$$385^2 + 1488^2 := 1537^2$$

$$385^2 + 2100^2 := 2135^2$$

$$385^2 + 2952^2 := 2977^2$$

$$385^2 + 6732^2 := 6743^2$$

$$385^2 + 10584^2 := 10591^2$$

$$385^2 + 14820^2 := 14825^2$$

$$385^2 + 74112^2 := 74113^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(385, 2952, 2977)** $\Rightarrow 2977 - 2952 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 29645$, $T_{25} := 385^2$,
 $E := \{5905, 5907, \dots, 5951, 5953\}$ or $E := \{5917, 5918, \dots, 5940, 5941\}$
2. **(385, 1488, 1537)** $\Rightarrow 1537 - 1488 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 21175$, $T_{49} := 385^2$,
 $E := \{2977, 2979, \dots, 3071, 3073\}$ or $E := \{3001, 3002, \dots, 3048, 3049\}$
3. **(385, 552, 673)** $\Rightarrow 673 - 552 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 13475$, $T_{121} := 385^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 1343, 1345\}$ or $E := \{1165, 1166, \dots, 1284, 1285\}$

■ Number 386

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$386^2 + 37248^2 := 37250^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(386, 37248, 37250)** $\Rightarrow 37250 - 386 = 192^2$, $S_{192 \times 192} := 7226112$, $T_{36864} := 37248^2$,
 $E := \{773, 775, \dots, 74497, 74499\}$

■ Number 387

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll} 387^2 + 516^2 := 645^2 & 387^2 + 8316^2 := 8325^2 \\ 387^2 + 884^2 := 965^2 & 387^2 + 24960^2 := 24963^2 \\ 387^2 + 1720^2 := 1763^2 & 387^2 + 74884^2 := 74885^2 \\ 387^2 + 2760^2 := 2787^2 & \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(387, 8316, 8325)** $\Rightarrow 8325 - 8316 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 49923$, $T_9 := 387^2$,
 $E := \{16633, 16635, \dots, 16647, 16649\}$ or $E := \{16637, 16638, \dots, 16644, 16645\}$
2. **(387, 884, 965)** $\Rightarrow 965 - 884 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 16641$, $T_{81} := 387^2$,
 $E := \{1769, 1771, \dots, 1927, 1929\}$ or $E := \{1809, 1810, \dots, 1888, 1889\}$

■ Number 388

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{l} 388^2 + 9405^2 := 9413^2 \\ 388^2 + 18816^2 := 18820^2 \\ 388^2 + 37635^2 := 37637^2 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(388, 9405, 9413)** $\Rightarrow 9413 - 388 = 95^2$, $S_{95 \times 95} := 931095$, $T_{9025} := 9405^2$,
 $E := \{777, 779, \dots, 18823, 18825\}$ or $E := \{5289, 5290, \dots, 14312, 14313\}$
2. **(388, 37635, 37637)** $\Rightarrow 37637 - 388 = 193^2$, $S_{193 \times 193} := 7338825$, $T_{37249} := 37635^2$,
 $E := \{777, 779, \dots, 75271, 75273\}$ or $E := \{19401, 19402, \dots, 56648, 56649\}$

■ Number 389

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$389^2 + 75660^2 := 75661^2$$

■ Number 390

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$390^2 + 432^2 := 582^2$$

$$390^2 + 520^2 := 650^2$$

$$390^2 + 800^2 := 890^2$$

$$390^2 + 936^2 := 1014^2$$

$$390^2 + 1496^2 := 1546^2$$

$$390^2 + 2520^2 := 2550^2$$

$$390^2 + 2912^2 := 2938^2$$

$$390^2 + 4216^2 := 4234^2$$

$$390^2 + 7600^2 := 7610^2$$

$$390^2 + 12672^2 := 12678^2$$

$$390^2 + 38024^2 := 38026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(390, 1496, 1546)** $\Rightarrow 1546 - 390 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 65824$, $T_{1156} := 1496^2$,
 $E := \{781, 783, \dots, 3089, 3091\}$

2. **(390, 4216, 4234)** $\Rightarrow 4234 - 390 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 286688$, $T_{3844} := 4216^2$,
 $E := \{781, 783, \dots, 8465, 8467\}$

3. **(390, 38024, 38026)** $\Rightarrow 38026 - 390 = 194^2$, $S_{194 \times 194} := 7452704$, $T_{37636} := 38024^2$,
 $E := \{781, 783, \dots, 76049, 76051\}$

■ Number 391

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$391^2 + 3312^2 := 3335^2$$

$$391^2 + 4488^2 := 4505^2$$

$$391^2 + 76440^2 := 76441^2$$

■ Number 392

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$392^2 + 630^2 := 742^2$$

$$392^2 + 735^2 := 833^2$$

$$392^2 + 1344^2 := 1400^2$$

$$392^2 + 2385^2 := 2417^2$$

$$392^2 + 2730^2 := 2758^2$$

$$392^2 + 4794^2 := 4810^2$$

$$392^2 + 5481^2 := 5495^2$$

$$392^2 + 9600^2 := 9608^2$$

$$392^2 + 19206^2 := 19210^2$$

$$392^2 + 38415^2 := 38417^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(392, 4794, 4810)** $\Rightarrow 4810 - 4794 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 38416$, $T_{16} := 392^2$,
 $E := \{9589, 9591, \dots, 9617, 9619\}$
2. **(392, 735, 833)** $\Rightarrow 833 - 392 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 25725$, $T_{441} := 735^2$,
 $E := \{785, 787, \dots, 1663, 1665\}$ or $E := \{1005, 1006, \dots, 1444, 1445\}$
3. **(392, 2385, 2417)** $\Rightarrow 2417 - 392 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 126405$, $T_{2025} := 2385^2$,
 $E := \{785, 787, \dots, 4831, 4833\}$ or $E := \{1797, 1798, \dots, 3820, 3821\}$
4. **(392, 9600, 9608)** $\Rightarrow 9608 - 392 = 96^2$, $S_{96 \times 96} := 960000$, $T_{9216} := 9600^2$,
 $E := \{785, 787, \dots, 19213, 19215\}$
5. **(392, 38415, 38417)** $\Rightarrow 38417 - 392 = 195^2$, $S_{195 \times 195} := 7567755$, $T_{38025} := 38415^2$,
 $E := \{785, 787, \dots, 76831, 76833\}$ or $E := \{19797, 19798, \dots, 57820, 57821\}$

■ Number 393

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$393^2 + 524^2 := 655^2$$

$$393^2 + 8576^2 := 8585^2$$

$$393^2 + 25740^2 := 25743^2$$

$$393^2 + 77224^2 := 77225^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(393, 8576, 8585)** $\Rightarrow 8585 - 8576 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 51483$, $T_9 := 393^2$,
 $E := \{17153, 17155, \dots, 17167, 17169\}$ or $E := \{17157, 17158, \dots, 17164, 17165\}$

■ Number 394

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$394^2 + 38808^2 := 38810^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(394, 38808, 38810)** $\Rightarrow 38810 - 394 = 196^2$, $S_{196 \times 196} := 7683984$, $T_{38416} := 38808^2$,
 $E := \{789, 791, \dots, 77617, 77619\}$

■ Number 395

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$395^2 + 948^2 := 1027^2$$

$$395^2 + 3108^2 := 3133^2$$

$$395^2 + 15600^2 := 15605^2$$

$$395^2 + 78012^2 := 78013^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(395, 3108, 3133)** $\Rightarrow 3133 - 3108 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 31205$, $T_{25} := 395^2$,
 $E := \{6217, 6219, \dots, 6263, 6265\}$ or $E := \{6229, 6230, \dots, 6252, 6253\}$

■ Number 396

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$396^2 + 403^2 := 565^2$$

$$396^2 + 528^2 := 660^2$$

$$396^2 + 672^2 := 780^2$$

$$396^2 + 847^2 := 935^2$$

$$396^2 + 1053^2 := 1125^2$$

$$396^2 + 1155^2 := 1221^2$$

$$396^2 + 1425^2 := 1479^2$$

$$396^2 + 1760^2 := 1804^2$$

$$396^2 + 2160^2 := 2196^2$$

$$396^2 + 3255^2 := 3279^2$$

$$396^2 + 3553^2 := 3575^2$$

$$396^2 + 4347^2 := 4365^2$$

$$396^2 + 6528^2 := 6540^2$$

$$396^2 + 9797^2 := 9805^2$$

$$396^2 + 13065^2 := 13071^2$$

$$396^2 + 19600^2 := 19604^2$$

$$396^2 + 39203^2 := 39205^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(396, 2160, 2196)** $\Rightarrow 2196 - 2160 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 26136$, $T_{36} := 396^2$,
 $E := \{4321, 4323, \dots, 4389, 4391\}$
2. **(396, 403, 565)** $\Rightarrow 565 - 396 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 12493$, $T_{169} := 403^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 1127, 1129\}$ or $E := \{877, 878, \dots, 1044, 1045\}$
3. **(396, 1053, 1125)** $\Rightarrow 1125 - 396 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 41067$, $T_{729} := 1053^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 2247, 2249\}$ or $E := \{1157, 1158, \dots, 1884, 1885\}$
4. **(396, 4347, 4365)** $\Rightarrow 4365 - 396 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 299943$, $T_{3969} := 4347^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 8727, 8729\}$ or $E := \{2777, 2778, \dots, 6744, 6745\}$
5. **(396, 9797, 9805)** $\Rightarrow 9805 - 396 = 97^2$, $S_{97 \times 97} := 989497$, $T_{9409} := 9797^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 19607, 19609\}$ or $E := \{5497, 5498, \dots, 14904, 14905\}$
6. **(396, 39203, 39205)** $\Rightarrow 39205 - 396 = 197^2$, $S_{197 \times 197} := 7801397$, $T_{38809} := 39203^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 78407, 78409\}$ or $E := \{20197, 20198, \dots, 59004, 59005\}$

■ Number 397

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$397^2 + 78804^2 := 78805^2$$

■ Number 398

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$398^2 + 39600^2 := 39602^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(398, 39600, 39602)** $\Rightarrow 39602 - 398 = 198^2$, $S_{198 \times 198} := 7920000$, $T_{39204} := 39600^2$,
 $E := \{797, 799, \dots, 79201, 79203\}$

■ Number 399

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$399^2 + 468^2 := 615^2$$

$$399^2 + 532^2 := 665^2$$

$$399^2 + 1232^2 := 1295^2$$

$$399^2 + 1368^2 := 1425^2$$

$$399^2 + 1600^2 := 1649^2$$

$$399^2 + 3780^2 := 3801^2$$

$$399^2 + 4180^2 := 4199^2$$

$$399^2 + 8840^2 := 8849^2$$

$$399^2 + 11368^2 := 11375^2$$

$$399^2 + 26532^2 := 26535^2$$

$$399^2 + 79600^2 := 79601^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(399, 8840, 8849)** $\Rightarrow 8849 - 8840 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 53067$, $T_9 := 399^2$,
 $E := \{17681, 17683, \dots, 17695, 17697\}$ or $E := \{17685, 17686, \dots, 17692, 17693\}$
2. **(399, 1600, 1649)** $\Rightarrow 1649 - 1600 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 22743$, $T_{49} := 399^2$,
 $E := \{3201, 3203, \dots, 3295, 3297\}$ or $E := \{3225, 3226, \dots, 3272, 3273\}$

■ Number 400

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$400^2 + 420^2 := 580^2$$

$$400^2 + 561^2 := 689^2$$

$$400^2 + 750^2 := 850^2$$

$$400^2 + 960^2 := 1040^2$$

$$400^2 + 1218^2 := 1282^2$$

$$400^2 + 1575^2 := 1625^2$$

$$400^2 + 1980^2 := 2020^2$$

$$400^2 + 2484^2 := 2516^2$$

$$400^2 + 3990^2 := 4010^2$$

$$400^2 + 4992^2 := 5008^2$$

$$400^2 + 7995^2 := 8005^2$$

$$400^2 + 9996^2 := 10004^2$$

$$400^2 + 19998^2 := 20002^2$$

$$400^2 + 39999^2 := 40001^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(400, 4992, 5008)** $\Rightarrow 5008 - 4992 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 40000$, $T_{16} := 400^2$,
 $E := \{9985, 9987, \dots, 10013, 10015\}$
2. **(400, 1218, 1282)** $\Rightarrow 1282 - 1218 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 20000$, $T_{64} := 400^2$,
 $E := \{2437, 2439, \dots, 2561, 2563\}$
3. **(400, 750, 850)** $\Rightarrow 850 - 750 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 16000$, $T_{100} := 400^2$,
 $E := \{1501, 1503, \dots, 1697, 1699\}$
4. **(400, 561, 689)** $\Rightarrow 689 - 400 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 18513$, $T_{289} := 561^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 1375, 1377\}$ or $E := \{945, 946, \dots, 1232, 1233\}$
5. **(400, 1575, 1625)** $\Rightarrow 1625 - 400 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 70875$, $T_{1225} := 1575^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 3247, 3249\}$ or $E := \{1413, 1414, \dots, 2636, 2637\}$
6. **(400, 2484, 2516)** $\Rightarrow 2516 - 400 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 134136$, $T_{2116} := 2484^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 5029, 5031\}$
7. **(400, 9996, 10004)** $\Rightarrow 10004 - 400 = 98^2$, $S_{98 \times 98} := 1019592$, $T_{9604} := 9996^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 20005, 20007\}$
8. **(400, 39999, 40001)** $\Rightarrow 40001 - 400 = 199^2$, $S_{199 \times 199} := 8039799$, $T_{39601} := 39999^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 79999, 80001\}$ or $E := \{20601, 20602, \dots, 60200, 60201\}$

2.5 Pythagorean Triples: 401 to 500

■ Number 401

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$401^2 + 80400^2 := 80401^2$$

■ Number 402

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$402^2 + 536^2 := 670^2$$

$$402^2 + 4480^2 := 4498^2$$

$$402^2 + 13464^2 := 13470^2$$

$$402^2 + 40400^2 := 40402^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(402, 4480, 4498)** $\Rightarrow 4498 - 402 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 313600$, $T_{4096} := 4480^2$,
 $E := \{805, 807, \dots, 8993, 8995\}$

2. **(402, 40400, 40402)** $\Rightarrow 40402 - 402 = 200^2$, $S_{200 \times 200} := 8160800$, $T_{40000} := 40400^2$,
 $E := \{805, 807, \dots, 80801, 80803\}$

■ Number 403

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$403^2 + 2604^2 := 2635^2$$

$$403^2 + 6240^2 := 6253^2$$

$$403^2 + 81204^2 := 81205^2$$

■ Number 404

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$404^2 + 10197^2 := 10205^2$$

$$404^2 + 20400^2 := 20404^2$$

$$404^2 + 40803^2 := 40805^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(404, 10197, 10205)** $\Rightarrow 10205 - 404 = 99^2$, $S_{99 \times 99} := 1050291$, $T_{9801} := 10197^2$,
 $E := \{809, 811, \dots, 20407, 20409\}$ or $E := \{5709, 5710, \dots, 15508, 15509\}$

2. **(404, 40803, 40805)** $\Rightarrow 40805 - 404 = 201^2$, $S_{201 \times 201} := 8283009$, $T_{40401} := 40803^2$,
 $E := \{809, 811, \dots, 81607, 81609\}$ or $E := \{21009, 21010, \dots, 61408, 61409\}$

■ Number 405

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$405^2 + 540^2 := 675^2$$

$$405^2 + 972^2 := 1053^2$$

$$405^2 + 1056^2 := 1131^2$$

$$405^2 + 1800^2 := 1845^2$$

$$405^2 + 3024^2 := 3051^2$$

$$405^2 + 3268^2 := 3293^2$$

$$405^2 + 5460^2 := 5475^2$$

$$405^2 + 9108^2 := 9117^2$$

$$405^2 + 16400^2 := 16405^2$$

$$405^2 + 27336^2 := 27339^2$$

$$405^2 + 82012^2 := 82013^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(405, 9108, 9117)** $\Rightarrow 9117 - 9108 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 54675$, $T_9 := 405^2$,
 $E := \{18217, 18219, \dots, 18231, 18233\}$ or $E := \{18221, 18222, \dots, 18228, 18229\}$
2. **(405, 3268, 3293)** $\Rightarrow 3293 - 3268 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 32805$, $T_{25} := 405^2$,
 $E := \{6537, 6539, \dots, 6583, 6585\}$ or $E := \{6549, 6550, \dots, 6572, 6573\}$
3. **(405, 972, 1053)** $\Rightarrow 1053 - 972 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 18225$, $T_{81} := 405^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 2103, 2105\}$ or $E := \{1985, 1986, \dots, 2064, 2065\}$

■ Number 406

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$406^2 + 792^2 := 890^2$$

$$406^2 + 1392^2 := 1450^2$$

$$406^2 + 5880^2 := 5894^2$$

$$406^2 + 41208^2 := 41210^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(406, 792, 890)** $\Rightarrow 890 - 406 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 28512$, $T_{484} := 792^2$,
 $E := \{813, 815, \dots, 1777, 1779\}$
2. **(406, 41208, 41210)** $\Rightarrow 41210 - 406 = 202^2$, $S_{202 \times 202} := 8406432$, $T_{40804} := 41208^2$,
 $E := \{813, 815, \dots, 82417, 82419\}$

■ Number 407

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$407^2 + 624^2 := 745^2$$

$$407^2 + 2220^2 := 2257^2$$

$$407^2 + 7524^2 := 7535^2$$

$$407^2 + 82824^2 := 82825^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(407, 624, 745)** $\Rightarrow 745 - 624 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 15059$, $T_{121} := 407^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 1487, 1489\}$ or $E := \{1309, 1310, \dots, 1428, 1429\}$

■ **Number 408**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$408^2 + 506^2 := 650^2$	$408^2 + 1710^2 := 1758^2$	$408^2 + 5194^2 := 5210^2$
$408^2 + 544^2 := 680^2$	$408^2 + 2294^2 := 2330^2$	$408^2 + 6930^2 := 6942^2$
$408^2 + 765^2 := 867^2$	$408^2 + 2431^2 := 2465^2$	$408^2 + 10400^2 := 10408^2$
$408^2 + 819^2 := 915^2$	$408^2 + 2585^2 := 2617^2$	$408^2 + 13869^2 := 13875^2$
$408^2 + 1120^2 := 1192^2$	$408^2 + 3456^2 := 3480^2$	$408^2 + 20806^2 := 20810^2$
$408^2 + 1190^2 := 1258^2$	$408^2 + 4615^2 := 4633^2$	$408^2 + 41615^2 := 41617^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(408, 5194, 5210)** $\Rightarrow 5210 - 5194 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 41616$, $T_{16} := 408^2$,
 $E := \{10389, 10391, \dots, 10417, 10419\}$
2. **(408, 2294, 2330)** $\Rightarrow 2330 - 2294 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 27744$, $T_{36} := 408^2$,
 $E := \{4589, 4591, \dots, 4657, 4659\}$
3. **(408, 506, 650)** $\Rightarrow 650 - 506 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 13872$, $T_{144} := 408^2$,
 $E := \{1013, 1015, \dots, 1297, 1299\}$
4. **(408, 1120, 1192)** $\Rightarrow 1192 - 408 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 44800$, $T_{784} := 1120^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 2381, 2383\}$
5. **(408, 2585, 2617)** $\Rightarrow 2617 - 408 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 142175$, $T_{2209} := 2585^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 5231, 5233\}$ or $E := \{1921, 1922, \dots, 4128, 4129\}$
6. **(408, 4615, 4633)** $\Rightarrow 4633 - 408 = 65^2$, $S_{65 \times 65} := 327665$, $T_{4225} := 4615^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 9263, 9265\}$ or $E := \{2929, 2930, \dots, 7152, 7153\}$
7. **(408, 10400, 10408)** $\Rightarrow 10408 - 408 = 100^2$, $S_{100 \times 100} := 1081600$, $T_{10000} := 10400^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 20813, 20815\}$
8. **(408, 41615, 41617)** $\Rightarrow 41617 - 408 = 203^2$, $S_{203 \times 203} := 8531075$, $T_{41209} := 41615^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 83231, 83233\}$ or $E := \{21421, 21422, \dots, 62628, 62629\}$

■ Number 409

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$409^2 + 83640^2 := 83641^2$$

■ Number 410

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$410^2 + 984^2 := 1066^2$$

$$410^2 + 1656^2 := 1706^2$$

$$410^2 + 8400^2 := 8410^2$$

$$410^2 + 42024^2 := 42026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(410, 1656, 1706)** $\Rightarrow 1706 - 410 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 76176$, $T_{1296} := 1656^2$,

$$E := \{821, 823, \dots, 3409, 3411\}$$

2. **(410, 42024, 42026)** $\Rightarrow 42026 - 410 = 204^2$, $S_{204 \times 204} := 8656944$, $T_{41616} := 42024^2$,

$$E := \{821, 823, \dots, 84049, 84051\}$$

■ Number 411

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$411^2 + 548^2 := 685^2$$

$$411^2 + 9380^2 := 9389^2$$

$$411^2 + 28152^2 := 28155^2$$

$$411^2 + 84460^2 := 84461^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(411, 9380, 9389)** $\Rightarrow 9389 - 9380 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 56307$, $T_9 := 411^2$,

$$E := \{18761, 18763, \dots, 18775, 18777\} \text{ or } E := \{18765, 18766, \dots, 18772, 18773\}$$

■ Number 412

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$412^2 + 10605^2 := 10613^2$$

$$412^2 + 21216^2 := 21220^2$$

$$412^2 + 42435^2 := 42437^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(412, 10605, 10613)** $\Rightarrow 10613 - 412 = 101^2$, $S_{101 \times 101} := 1113525$, $T_{10201} := 10605^2$,
 $E := \{825, 827, \dots, 21223, 21225\}$ or $E := \{5925, 5926, \dots, 16124, 16125\}$
2. **(412, 42435, 42437)** $\Rightarrow 42437 - 412 = 205^2$, $S_{205 \times 205} := 8784045$, $T_{42025} := 42435^2$,
 $E := \{825, 827, \dots, 84871, 84873\}$ or $E := \{21837, 21838, \dots, 63860, 63861\}$

■ Number 413

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$413^2 + 1416^2 := 1475^2 \qquad 413^2 + 12180^2 := 12187^2$$

$$413^2 + 1716^2 := 1765^2 \qquad 413^2 + 85284^2 := 85285^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(413, 1716, 1765)** $\Rightarrow 1765 - 1716 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 24367$, $T_{49} := 413^2$,
 $E := \{3433, 3435, \dots, 3527, 3529\}$ or $E := \{3457, 3458, \dots, 3504, 3505\}$

■ Number 414

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$414^2 + 448^2 := 610^2 \qquad 414^2 + 4752^2 := 4770^2$$

$$414^2 + 552^2 := 690^2 \qquad 414^2 + 14280^2 := 14286^2$$

$$414^2 + 1560^2 := 1614^2 \qquad 414^2 + 42848^2 := 42850^2$$

$$414^2 + 1840^2 := 1886^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(414, 448, 610)** $\Rightarrow 610 - 414 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 14336$, $T_{196} := 448^2$,
 $E := \{829, 831, \dots, 1217, 1219\}$
2. **(414, 4752, 4770)** $\Rightarrow 4770 - 414 = 66^2$, $S_{66 \times 66} := 342144$, $T_{4356} := 4752^2$,
 $E := \{829, 831, \dots, 9537, 9539\}$
3. **(414, 42848, 42850)** $\Rightarrow 42850 - 414 = 206^2$, $S_{206 \times 206} := 8912384$, $T_{42436} := 42848^2$,
 $E := \{829, 831, \dots, 85697, 85699\}$

■ Number 415

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$415^2 + 996^2 := 1079^2$$

$$415^2 + 3432^2 := 3457^2$$

$$415^2 + 17220^2 := 17225^2$$

$$415^2 + 86112^2 := 86113^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(415, 3432, 3457)** $\Rightarrow 3457 - 3432 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 34445$, $T_{25} := 415^2$,
 $E := \{6865, 6867, \dots, 6911, 6913\}$ or $E := \{6877, 6878, \dots, 6900, 6901\}$

■ Number 416

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$416^2 + 612^2 := 740^2$$

$$416^2 + 780^2 := 884^2$$

$$416^2 + 1320^2 := 1384^2$$

$$416^2 + 1638^2 := 1690^2$$

$$416^2 + 2688^2 := 2720^2$$

$$416^2 + 3315^2 := 3341^2$$

$$416^2 + 5400^2 := 5416^2$$

$$416^2 + 10812^2 := 10820^2$$

$$416^2 + 21630^2 := 21634^2$$

$$416^2 + 43263^2 := 43265^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(416, 5400, 5416)** $\Rightarrow 5416 - 5400 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 43264$, $T_{16} := 416^2$,
 $E := \{10801, 10803, \dots, 10829, 10831\}$
2. **(416, 1320, 1384)** $\Rightarrow 1384 - 1320 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 21632$, $T_{64} := 416^2$,
 $E := \{2641, 2643, \dots, 2765, 2767\}$
3. **(416, 612, 740)** $\Rightarrow 740 - 416 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 20808$, $T_{324} := 612^2$,
 $E := \{833, 835, \dots, 1477, 1479\}$
4. **(416, 2688, 2720)** $\Rightarrow 2720 - 416 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 150528$, $T_{2304} := 2688^2$,
 $E := \{833, 835, \dots, 5437, 5439\}$
5. **(416, 10812, 10820)** $\Rightarrow 10820 - 416 = 102^2$, $S_{102 \times 102} := 1146072$, $T_{10404} := 10812^2$,
 $E := \{833, 835, \dots, 21637, 21639\}$
6. **(416, 43263, 43265)** $\Rightarrow 43265 - 416 = 207^2$, $S_{207 \times 207} := 9041967$, $T_{42849} := 43263^2$,
 $E := \{833, 835, \dots, 86527, 86529\}$ or $E := \{22257, 22258, \dots, 65104, 65105\}$

■ Number 417

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$417^2 + 556^2 := 695^2$$

$$417^2 + 9656^2 := 9665^2$$

$$417^2 + 28980^2 := 28983^2$$

$$417^2 + 86944^2 := 86945^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(417, 9656, 9665)** $\Rightarrow 9665 - 9656 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 57963$, $T_9 := 417^2$,
 $E := \{19313, 19315, \dots, 19327, 19329\}$ or $E := \{19317, 19318, \dots, 19324, 19325\}$

■ Number 418

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$418^2 + 2280^2 := 2318^2$$

$$418^2 + 3960^2 := 3982^2$$

$$418^2 + 43680^2 := 43682^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(418, 43680, 43682)** $\Rightarrow 43682 - 418 = 208^2$, $S_{208 \times 208} := 9172800$, $T_{43264} := 43680^2$,
 $E := \{837, 839, \dots, 87361, 87363\}$

■ Number 419

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$419^2 + 87780^2 := 87781^2$$

■ Number 420

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$420^2 + 441^2 := 609^2$$

$$420^2 + 513^2 := 663^2$$

$$420^2 + 560^2 := 700^2$$

$$420^2 + 637^2 := 763^2$$

$$420^2 + 675^2 := 795^2$$

$$420^2 + 832^2 := 932^2$$

$$420^2 + 851^2 := 949^2$$

$$420^2 + 935^2 := 1025^2$$

$$420^2 + 1008^2 := 1092^2$$

$$420^2 + 1189^2 := 1261^2$$

$$420^2 + 1225^2 := 1295^2$$

$$420^2 + 1440^2 := 1500^2$$

$$420^2 + 1547^2 := 1603^2$$

$$420^2 + 1739^2 := 1789^2$$

$$420^2 + 2079^2 := 2121^2$$

$$420^2 + 2185^2 := 2225^2$$

$$420^2 + 2432^2 := 2468^2$$

$$420^2 + 2925^2 := 2955^2$$

$$420^2 + 3136^2 := 3164^2$$

$$420^2 + 3663^2 := 3687^2$$

$$420^2 + 4400^2 := 4420^2$$

$$420^2 + 4891^2 := 4909^2$$

$$420^2 + 6293^2 := 6307^2$$

$$420^2 + 7344^2 := 7356^2$$

$$420^2 + 8815^2 := 8825^2$$

$$420^2 + 11021^2 := 11029^2$$

$$420^2 + 14697^2 := 14703^2$$

$$420^2 + 22048^2 := 22052^2$$

$$420^2 + 44099^2 := 44101^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(420, 2432, 2468)** $\Rightarrow 2468 - 2432 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 29400$, $T_{36} := 420^2$,
 $E := \{4865, 4867, \dots, 4933, 4935\}$
2. **(420, 832, 932)** $\Rightarrow 932 - 832 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 17640$, $T_{100} := 420^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 1861, 1863\}$
3. **(420, 851, 949)** $\Rightarrow 949 - 420 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 31487$, $T_{529} := 851^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 1895, 1897\}$ or $E := \{1105, 1106, \dots, 1632, 1633\}$
4. **(420, 1189, 1261)** $\Rightarrow 1261 - 420 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 48749$, $T_{841} := 1189^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 2519, 2521\}$ or $E := \{1261, 1262, \dots, 2100, 2101\}$
5. **(420, 1739, 1789)** $\Rightarrow 1789 - 420 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 81733$, $T_{1369} := 1739^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 3575, 3577\}$ or $E := \{1525, 1526, \dots, 2892, 2893\}$
6. **(420, 4891, 4909)** $\Rightarrow 4909 - 420 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 357043$, $T_{4489} := 4891^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 9815, 9817\}$ or $E := \{3085, 3086, \dots, 7572, 7573\}$
7. **(420, 11021, 11029)** $\Rightarrow 11029 - 420 = 103^2$, $S_{103 \times 103} := 1179247$, $T_{10609} := 11021^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 22055, 22057\}$ or $E := \{6145, 6146, \dots, 16752, 16753\}$
8. **(420, 44099, 44101)** $\Rightarrow 44101 - 420 = 209^2$, $S_{209 \times 209} := 9304889$, $T_{43681} := 44099^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 88199, 88201\}$ or $E := \{22681, 22682, \dots, 66360, 66361\}$

■ Number 421

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$421^2 + 88620^2 := 88621^2$$

■ Number 422

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$422^2 + 44520^2 := 44522^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(422, 44520, 44522)** $\Rightarrow 44522 - 422 = 210^2$, $S_{210 \times 210} := 9438240$, $T_{44100} := 44520^2$,
 $E := \{845, 847, \dots, 89041, 89043\}$

■ Number 423

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$423^2 + 564^2 := 705^2$$

$$423^2 + 1064^2 := 1145^2$$

$$423^2 + 1880^2 := 1927^2$$

$$423^2 + 3300^2 := 3327^2$$

$$423^2 + 9936^2 := 9945^2$$

$$423^2 + 29820^2 := 29823^2$$

$$423^2 + 89464^2 := 89465^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(423, 9936, 9945)** $\Rightarrow 9945 - 9936 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 59643$, $T_9 := 423^2$,
 $E := \{19873, 19875, \dots, 19887, 19889\}$ or $E := \{19877, 19878, \dots, 19884, 19885\}$
2. **(423, 1064, 1145)** $\Rightarrow 1145 - 1064 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 19881$, $T_{81} := 423^2$,
 $E := \{2129, 2131, \dots, 2287, 2289\}$ or $E := \{2169, 2170, \dots, 2248, 2249\}$

■ Number 424

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$424^2 + 795^2 := 901^2$$

$$424^2 + 2793^2 := 2825^2$$

$$424^2 + 5610^2 := 5626^2$$

$$424^2 + 11232^2 := 11240^2$$

$$424^2 + 22470^2 := 22474^2$$

$$424^2 + 44943^2 := 44945^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(424, 5610, 5626)** $\Rightarrow 5626 - 5610 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 44944$, $T_{16} := 424^2$,
 $E := \{11221, 11223, \dots, 11249, 11251\}$

2. **(424, 2793, 2825)** $\Rightarrow 2825 - 424 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 159201$, $T_{2401} := 2793^2$,
 $E := \{849, 851, \dots, 5647, 5649\}$ or $E := \{2049, 2050, \dots, 4448, 4449\}$
3. **(424, 11232, 11240)** $\Rightarrow 11240 - 424 = 104^2$, $S_{104 \times 104} := 1213056$, $T_{10816} := 11232^2$,
 $E := \{849, 851, \dots, 22477, 22479\}$
4. **(424, 44943, 44945)** $\Rightarrow 44945 - 424 = 211^2$, $S_{211 \times 211} := 9572859$, $T_{44521} := 44943^2$,
 $E := \{849, 851, \dots, 89887, 89889\}$ or $E := \{23109, 23110, \dots, 67628, 67629\}$

■ Number 425

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 425^2 + 660^2 := 785^2 & 425^2 + 5304^2 := 5321^2 \\
 425^2 + 1020^2 := 1105^2 & 425^2 + 18060^2 := 18065^2 \\
 425^2 + 3600^2 := 3625^2 & 425^2 + 90312^2 := 90313^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(425, 3600, 3625)** $\Rightarrow 3625 - 3600 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 36125$, $T_{25} := 425^2$,
 $E := \{7201, 7203, \dots, 7247, 7249\}$ or $E := \{7213, 7214, \dots, 7236, 7237\}$

■ Number 426

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 426^2 + 568^2 := 710^2 & 426^2 + 15120^2 := 15126^2 \\
 426^2 + 5032^2 := 5050^2 & 426^2 + 45368^2 := 45370^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(426, 5032, 5050)** $\Rightarrow 5050 - 426 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 372368$, $T_{4624} := 5032^2$,
 $E := \{853, 855, \dots, 10097, 10099\}$
2. **(426, 45368, 45370)** $\Rightarrow 45370 - 426 = 212^2$, $S_{212 \times 212} := 9708752$, $T_{44944} := 45368^2$,
 $E := \{853, 855, \dots, 90737, 90739\}$

■ Number 427

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$427^2 + 1464^2 := 1525^2$$

$$427^2 + 13020^2 := 13027^2$$

$$427^2 + 1836^2 := 1885^2$$

$$427^2 + 91164^2 := 91165^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(427, 1836, 1885)** $\Rightarrow 1885 - 1836 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 26047$, $T_{49} := 427^2$,
 $E := \{3673, 3675, \dots, 3767, 3769\}$ or $E := \{3697, 3698, \dots, 3744, 3745\}$

■ Number 428

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$428^2 + 11445^2 := 11453^2$$

$$428^2 + 22896^2 := 22900^2$$

$$428^2 + 45795^2 := 45797^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(428, 11445, 11453)** $\Rightarrow 11453 - 428 = 105^2$, $S_{105 \times 105} := 1247505$, $T_{11025} := 11445^2$,
 $E := \{857, 859, \dots, 22903, 22905\}$ or $E := \{6369, 6370, \dots, 17392, 17393\}$
2. **(428, 45795, 45797)** $\Rightarrow 45797 - 428 = 213^2$, $S_{213 \times 213} := 9845925$, $T_{45369} := 45795^2$,
 $E := \{857, 859, \dots, 91591, 91593\}$ or $E := \{23541, 23542, \dots, 68908, 68909\}$

■ Number 429

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$429^2 + 460^2 := 629^2$$

$$429^2 + 880^2 := 979^2$$

$$429^2 + 8360^2 := 8371^2$$

$$429^2 + 572^2 := 715^2$$

$$429^2 + 2340^2 := 2379^2$$

$$429^2 + 10220^2 := 10229^2$$

$$429^2 + 700^2 := 821^2$$

$$429^2 + 2772^2 := 2805^2$$

$$429^2 + 30672^2 := 30675^2$$

$$429^2 + 728^2 := 845^2$$

$$429^2 + 7072^2 := 7085^2$$

$$429^2 + 92020^2 := 92021^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(429, 10220, 10229)** $\Rightarrow 10229 - 10220 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 61347$, $T_9 := 429^2$,
 $E := \{20441, 20443, \dots, 20455, 20457\}$ or $E := \{20445, 20446, \dots, 20452, 20453\}$
2. **(429, 700, 821)** $\Rightarrow 821 - 700 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 16731$, $T_{121} := 429^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 1639, 1641\}$ or $E := \{1461, 1462, \dots, 1580, 1581\}$

3. **(429, 460, 629)** $\Rightarrow 629 - 460 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 14157$, $T_{169} := 429^2$,
 $E := \{921, 923, \dots, 1255, 1257\}$ or $E := \{1005, 1006, \dots, 1172, 1173\}$

■ Number 430

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 430^2 + 1032^2 := 1118^2 & 430^2 + 9240^2 := 9250^2 \\ 430^2 + 1824^2 := 1874^2 & 430^2 + 46224^2 := 46226^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(430, 1824, 1874)** $\Rightarrow 1874 - 430 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 87552$, $T_{1444} := 1824^2$,
 $E := \{861, 863, \dots, 3745, 3747\}$
2. **(430, 46224, 46226)** $\Rightarrow 46226 - 430 = 214^2$, $S_{214 \times 214} := 9984384$, $T_{45796} := 46224^2$,
 $E := \{861, 863, \dots, 92449, 92451\}$

■ Number 431

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$431^2 + 92880^2 := 92881^2$$

■ Number 432

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll} 432^2 + 495^2 := 657^2 & 432^2 + 1426^2 := 1490^2 & 432^2 + 5175^2 := 5193^2 \\ 432^2 + 576^2 := 720^2 & 432^2 + 1701^2 := 1755^2 & 432^2 + 5824^2 := 5840^2 \\ 432^2 + 665^2 := 793^2 & 432^2 + 1920^2 := 1968^2 & 432^2 + 7770^2 := 7782^2 \\ 432^2 + 810^2 := 918^2 & 432^2 + 2574^2 := 2610^2 & 432^2 + 11660^2 := 11668^2 \\ 432^2 + 924^2 := 1020^2 & 432^2 + 2900^2 := 2932^2 & 432^2 + 15549^2 := 15555^2 \\ 432^2 + 1260^2 := 1332^2 & 432^2 + 3876^2 := 3900^2 & 432^2 + 23326^2 := 23330^2 \\ & & 432^2 + 46655^2 := 46657^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(432, 5824, 5840)** $\Rightarrow 5840 - 5824 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 46656$, $T_{16} := 432^2$,
 $E := \{11649, 11651, \dots, 11677, 11679\}$
2. **(432, 2574, 2610)** $\Rightarrow 2610 - 2574 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 31104$, $T_{36} := 432^2$,
 $E := \{5149, 5151, \dots, 5217, 5219\}$
3. **(432, 1426, 1490)** $\Rightarrow 1490 - 1426 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 23328$, $T_{64} := 432^2$,
 $E := \{2853, 2855, \dots, 2977, 2979\}$
4. **(432, 576, 720)** $\Rightarrow 720 - 576 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 15552$, $T_{144} := 432^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 1437, 1439\}$
5. **(432, 495, 657)** $\Rightarrow 657 - 432 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 16335$, $T_{225} := 495^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 1311, 1313\}$ or $E := \{977, 978, \dots, 1200, 1201\}$
6. **(432, 665, 793)** $\Rightarrow 793 - 432 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 23275$, $T_{361} := 665^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 1583, 1585\}$ or $E := \{1045, 1046, \dots, 1404, 1405\}$
7. **(432, 1260, 1332)** $\Rightarrow 1332 - 432 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 52920$, $T_{900} := 1260^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 2661, 2663\}$
8. **(432, 2900, 2932)** $\Rightarrow 2932 - 432 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 168200$, $T_{2500} := 2900^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 5861, 5863\}$
9. **(432, 5175, 5193)** $\Rightarrow 5193 - 432 = 69^2$, $S_{69 \times 69} := 388125$, $T_{4761} := 5175^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 10383, 10385\}$ or $E := \{3245, 3246, \dots, 8004, 8005\}$
10. **(432, 11660, 11668)** $\Rightarrow 11668 - 432 = 106^2$, $S_{106 \times 106} := 1282600$, $T_{11236} := 11660^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 23333, 23335\}$
11. **(432, 46655, 46657)** $\Rightarrow 46657 - 432 = 215^2$, $S_{215 \times 215} := 10124135$, $T_{46225} := 46655^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 93311, 93313\}$ or $E := \{23977, 23978, \dots, 70200, 70201\}$

■ Number 433

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$433^2 + 93744^2 := 93745^2$$

■ Number 434

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$434^2 + 912^2 := 1010^2$$

$$434^2 + 1488^2 := 1550^2$$

$$434^2 + 6720^2 := 6734^2$$

$$434^2 + 47088^2 := 47090^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(434, 912, 1010)** $\Rightarrow 1010 - 434 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 34656$, $T_{576} := 912^2$,
 $E := \{869, 871, \dots, 2017, 2019\}$

2. **(434, 47088, 47090)** $\Rightarrow 47090 - 434 = 216^2$, $S_{216 \times 216} := 10265184$, $T_{46656} := 47088^2$,
 $E := \{869, 871, \dots, 94177, 94179\}$

■ Number 435

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$435^2 + 580^2 := 725^2$$

$$435^2 + 1044^2 := 1131^2$$

$$435^2 + 1224^2 := 1299^2$$

$$435^2 + 2080^2 := 2125^2$$

$$435^2 + 3248^2 := 3277^2$$

$$435^2 + 3772^2 := 3797^2$$

$$435^2 + 6300^2 := 6315^2$$

$$435^2 + 10508^2 := 10517^2$$

$$435^2 + 18920^2 := 18925^2$$

$$435^2 + 31536^2 := 31539^2$$

$$435^2 + 94612^2 := 94613^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(435, 10508, 10517)** $\Rightarrow 10517 - 10508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 63075$, $T_9 := 435^2$,
 $E := \{21017, 21019, \dots, 21031, 21033\}$ or $E := \{21021, 21022, \dots, 21028, 21029\}$

2. **(435, 3772, 3797)** $\Rightarrow 3797 - 3772 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 37845$, $T_{25} := 435^2$,
 $E := \{7545, 7547, \dots, 7591, 7593\}$ or $E := \{7557, 7558, \dots, 7580, 7581\}$

■ Number 436

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$436^2 + 11877^2 := 11885^2$$

$$436^2 + 23760^2 := 23764^2$$

$$436^2 + 47523^2 := 47525^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(436, 11877, 11885)** $\Rightarrow 11885 - 436 = 107^2$, $S_{107 \times 107} := 1318347$, $T_{11449} := 11877^2$,
 $E := \{873, 875, \dots, 23767, 23769\}$ or $E := \{6597, 6598, \dots, 18044, 18045\}$

2. **(436, 47523, 47525)** $\Rightarrow 47525 - 436 = 217^2$, $S_{217 \times 217} := 10407537$, $T_{47089} := 47523^2$,
 $E := \{873, 875, \dots, 95047, 95049\}$ or $E := \{24417, 24418, \dots, 71504, 71505\}$

■ Number 437

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$437^2 + 4140^2 := 4163^2$$

$$437^2 + 5016^2 := 5035^2$$

$$437^2 + 95484^2 := 95485^2$$

■ Number 438

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$438^2 + 584^2 := 730^2$$

$$438^2 + 5320^2 := 5338^2$$

$$438^2 + 15984^2 := 15990^2$$

$$438^2 + 47960^2 := 47962^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(438, 5320, 5338)** $\Rightarrow 5338 - 438 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 404320$, $T_{4900} := 5320^2$,
 $E := \{877, 879, \dots, 10673, 10675\}$
2. **(438, 47960, 47962)** $\Rightarrow 47962 - 438 = 218^2$, $S_{218 \times 218} := 10551200$, $T_{47524} := 47960^2$,
 $E := \{877, 879, \dots, 95921, 95923\}$

■ Number 439

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$439^2 + 96360^2 := 96361^2$$

■ Number 440

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$440^2 + 462^2 := 638^2$	$440^2 + 1911^2 := 1961^2$	$440^2 + 6042^2 := 6058^2$
$440^2 + 525^2 := 685^2$	$440^2 + 2178^2 := 2222^2$	$440^2 + 9675^2 := 9685^2$
$440^2 + 825^2 := 935^2$	$440^2 + 2400^2 := 2440^2$	$440^2 + 12096^2 := 12104^2$
$440^2 + 918^2 := 1018^2$	$440^2 + 3009^2 := 3041^2$	$440^2 + 24198^2 := 24202^2$
$440^2 + 1056^2 := 1144^2$	$440^2 + 4389^2 := 4411^2$	$440^2 + 48399^2 := 48401^2$
$440^2 + 1170^2 := 1250^2$	$440^2 + 4830^2 := 4850^2$	

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(440, 6042, 6058)** $\Rightarrow 6058 - 6042 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 48400$, $T_{16} := 440^2$,
 $E := \{12085, 12087, \dots, 12113, 12115\}$
2. **(440, 918, 1018)** $\Rightarrow 1018 - 918 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 19360$, $T_{100} := 440^2$,
 $E := \{1837, 1839, \dots, 2033, 2035\}$
3. **(440, 1911, 1961)** $\Rightarrow 1961 - 440 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 93639$, $T_{1521} := 1911^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 3919, 3921\}$ or $E := \{1641, 1642, \dots, 3160, 3161\}$
4. **(440, 3009, 3041)** $\Rightarrow 3041 - 440 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 177531$, $T_{2601} := 3009^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 6079, 6081\}$ or $E := \{2181, 2182, \dots, 4780, 4781\}$
5. **(440, 12096, 12104)** $\Rightarrow 12104 - 440 = 108^2$, $S_{108 \times 108} := 1354752$, $T_{11664} := 12096^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 24205, 24207\}$
6. **(440, 48399, 48401)** $\Rightarrow 48401 - 440 = 219^2$, $S_{219 \times 219} := 10696179$, $T_{47961} := 48399^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 96799, 96801\}$ or $E := \{24861, 24862, \dots, 72820, 72821\}$

■ Number 441

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$441^2 + 588^2 := 735^2$	$441^2 + 1960^2 := 2009^2$	$441^2 + 10800^2 := 10809^2$
$441^2 + 1160^2 := 1241^2$	$441^2 + 3588^2 := 3615^2$	$441^2 + 13888^2 := 13895^2$
$441^2 + 1512^2 := 1575^2$	$441^2 + 4620^2 := 4641^2$	$441^2 + 32412^2 := 32415^2$
		$441^2 + 97240^2 := 97241^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(441, 10800, 10809)** $\Rightarrow 10809 - 10800 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 64827$, $T_9 := 441^2$,
 $E := \{21601, 21603, \dots, 21615, 21617\}$ or $E := \{21605, 21606, \dots, 21612, 21613\}$

2. **(441, 1960, 2009)** $\Rightarrow 2009 - 1960 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 27783$, $T_{49} := 441^2$,
 $E := \{3921, 3923, \dots, 4015, 4017\}$ or $E := \{3945, 3946, \dots, 3992, 3993\}$
3. **(441, 1160, 1241)** $\Rightarrow 1241 - 1160 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 21609$, $T_{81} := 441^2$,
 $E := \{2321, 2323, \dots, 2479, 2481\}$ or $E := \{2361, 2362, \dots, 2440, 2441\}$

■ Number 442

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned}442^2 + 2856^2 &:= 2890^2 \\442^2 + 3744^2 &:= 3770^2 \\442^2 + 48840^2 &:= 48842^2\end{aligned}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(442, 48840, 48842)** $\Rightarrow 48842 - 442 = 220^2$, $S_{220 \times 220} := 10842480$, $T_{48400} := 48840^2$,
 $E := \{885, 887, \dots, 97681, 97683\}$

■ Number 443

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$443^2 + 98124^2 := 98125^2$$

■ Number 444

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll}444^2 + 592^2 &:= 740^2 &444^2 + 4095^2 := 4119^2 &444^2 + 16425^2 := 16431^2 \\444^2 + 1295^2 &:= 1369^2 &444^2 + 5467^2 := 5485^2 &444^2 + 24640^2 := 24644^2 \\444^2 + 1333^2 &:= 1405^2 &444^2 + 8208^2 := 8220^2 &444^2 + 49283^2 := 49285^2 \\444^2 + 2720^2 &:= 2756^2 &444^2 + 12317^2 := 12325^2 &\end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(444, 2720, 2756)** $\Rightarrow 2756 - 2720 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 32856$, $T_{36} := 444^2$,
 $E := \{5441, 5443, \dots, 5509, 5511\}$

2. **(444, 1333, 1405)** $\Rightarrow 1405 - 444 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 57319$, $T_{961} := 1333^2$,
 $E := \{889, 891, \dots, 2807, 2809\}$ or $E := \{1369, 1370, \dots, 2328, 2329\}$
3. **(444, 5467, 5485)** $\Rightarrow 5485 - 444 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 420959$, $T_{5041} := 5467^2$,
 $E := \{889, 891, \dots, 10967, 10969\}$ or $E := \{3409, 3410, \dots, 8448, 8449\}$
4. **(444, 12317, 12325)** $\Rightarrow 12325 - 444 = 109^2$, $S_{109 \times 109} := 1391821$, $T_{11881} := 12317^2$,
 $E := \{889, 891, \dots, 24647, 24649\}$ or $E := \{6829, 6830, \dots, 18708, 18709\}$
5. **(444, 49283, 49285)** $\Rightarrow 49285 - 444 = 221^2$, $S_{221 \times 221} := 10990109$, $T_{48841} := 49283^2$,
 $E := \{889, 891, \dots, 98567, 98569\}$ or $E := \{25309, 25310, \dots, 74148, 74149\}$

■ Number 445

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$445^2 + 1068^2 := 1157^2$$

$$445^2 + 3948^2 := 3973^2$$

$$445^2 + 19800^2 := 19805^2$$

$$445^2 + 99012^2 := 99013^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(445, 3948, 3973)** $\Rightarrow 3973 - 3948 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 39605$, $T_{25} := 445^2$,
 $E := \{7897, 7899, \dots, 7943, 7945\}$ or $E := \{7909, 7910, \dots, 7932, 7933\}$

■ Number 446

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$446^2 + 49728^2 := 49730^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(446, 49728, 49730)** $\Rightarrow 49730 - 446 = 222^2$, $S_{222 \times 222} := 11139072$, $T_{49284} := 49728^2$,
 $E := \{893, 895, \dots, 99457, 99459\}$

■ Number 447

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$447^2 + 596^2 := 745^2$$

$$447^2 + 11096^2 := 11105^2$$

$$447^2 + 33300^2 := 33303^2$$

$$447^2 + 99904^2 := 99905^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(447, 11096, 11105)** $\Rightarrow 11105 - 11096 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 66603$, $T_9 := 447^2$,
 $E := \{22193, 22195, \dots, 22207, 22209\}$ or $E := \{22197, 22198, \dots, 22204, 22205\}$

■ **Number 448**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$448^2 + 720^2 := 848^2$	$448^2 + 1764^2 := 1820^2$	$448^2 + 7161^2 := 7175^2$
$448^2 + 840^2 := 952^2$	$448^2 + 3120^2 := 3152^2$	$448^2 + 12540^2 := 12548^2$
$448^2 + 975^2 := 1073^2$	$448^2 + 3570^2 := 3598^2$	$448^2 + 25086^2 := 25090^2$
$448^2 + 1536^2 := 1600^2$	$448^2 + 6264^2 := 6280^2$	$448^2 + 50175^2 := 50177^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(448, 6264, 6280)** $\Rightarrow 6280 - 6264 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 50176$, $T_{16} := 448^2$,
 $E := \{12529, 12531, \dots, 12557, 12559\}$
2. **(448, 1536, 1600)** $\Rightarrow 1600 - 1536 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 25088$, $T_{64} := 448^2$,
 $E := \{3073, 3075, \dots, 3197, 3199\}$
3. **(448, 720, 848)** $\Rightarrow 848 - 448 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 25920$, $T_{400} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{897, 899, \dots, 1693, 1695\}$
4. **(448, 975, 1073)** $\Rightarrow 1073 - 448 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 38025$, $T_{625} := 975^2$,
 $E := \{897, 899, \dots, 2143, 2145\}$ or $E := \{1209, 1210, \dots, 1832, 1833\}$
5. **(448, 3120, 3152)** $\Rightarrow 3152 - 448 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 187200$, $T_{2704} := 3120^2$,
 $E := \{897, 899, \dots, 6301, 6303\}$
6. **(448, 12540, 12548)** $\Rightarrow 12548 - 448 = 110^2$, $S_{110 \times 110} := 1429560$, $T_{12100} := 12540^2$,
 $E := \{897, 899, \dots, 25093, 25095\}$
7. **(448, 50175, 50177)** $\Rightarrow 50177 - 448 = 223^2$, $S_{223 \times 223} := 11289375$, $T_{49729} := 50175^2$,
 $E := \{897, 899, \dots, 100351, 100353\}$ or $E := \{25761, 25762, \dots, 75488, 75489\}$

■ **Number 449**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$449^2 + 100800^2 := 100801^2$$

■ Number 450

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$450^2 + 544^2 := 706^2$$

$$450^2 + 600^2 := 750^2$$

$$450^2 + 1080^2 := 1170^2$$

$$450^2 + 1848^2 := 1902^2$$

$$450^2 + 2000^2 := 2050^2$$

$$450^2 + 3360^2 := 3390^2$$

$$450^2 + 5616^2 := 5634^2$$

$$450^2 + 10120^2 := 10130^2$$

$$450^2 + 16872^2 := 16878^2$$

$$450^2 + 50624^2 := 50626^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(450, 544, 706)** $\Rightarrow 706 - 450 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 18496$, $T_{256} := 544^2$,
 $E := \{901, 903, \dots, 1409, 1411\}$
2. **(450, 2000, 2050)** $\Rightarrow 2050 - 450 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 100000$, $T_{1600} := 2000^2$,
 $E := \{901, 903, \dots, 4097, 4099\}$
3. **(450, 5616, 5634)** $\Rightarrow 5634 - 450 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 438048$, $T_{5184} := 5616^2$,
 $E := \{901, 903, \dots, 11265, 11267\}$
4. **(450, 50624, 50626)** $\Rightarrow 50626 - 450 = 224^2$, $S_{224 \times 224} := 11441024$, $T_{50176} := 50624^2$,
 $E := \{901, 903, \dots, 101249, 101251\}$

■ Number 451

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$451^2 + 780^2 := 901^2$$

$$451^2 + 2460^2 := 2501^2$$

$$451^2 + 9240^2 := 9251^2$$

$$451^2 + 101700^2 := 101701^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(451, 780, 901)** $\Rightarrow 901 - 780 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 18491$, $T_{121} := 451^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 1799, 1801\}$ or $E := \{1621, 1622, \dots, 1740, 1741\}$

■ Number 452

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$452^2 + 12765^2 := 12773^2$$

$$452^2 + 25536^2 := 25540^2$$

$$452^2 + 51075^2 := 51077^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(452, 12765, 12773)** $\Rightarrow 12773 - 452 = 111^2$, $S_{111 \times 111} := 1467975$, $T_{12321} := 12765^2$,
 $E := \{905, 907, \dots, 25543, 25545\}$ or $E := \{7065, 7066, \dots, 19384, 19385\}$
2. **(452, 51075, 51077)** $\Rightarrow 51077 - 452 = 225^2$, $S_{225 \times 225} := 11594025$, $T_{50625} := 51075^2$,
 $E := \{905, 907, \dots, 102151, 102153\}$ or $E := \{26217, 26218, \dots, 76840, 76841\}$

■ Number 453

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 453^2 + 604^2 & := 755^2 \\
 453^2 + 11396^2 & := 11405^2 \\
 453^2 + 34200^2 & := 34203^2 \\
 453^2 + 102604^2 & := 102605^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(453, 11396, 11405)** $\Rightarrow 11405 - 11396 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 68403$, $T_9 := 453^2$,
 $E := \{22793, 22795, \dots, 22807, 22809\}$ or $E := \{22797, 22798, \dots, 22804, 22805\}$

■ Number 454

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$454^2 + 51528^2 := 51530^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(454, 51528, 51530)** $\Rightarrow 51530 - 454 = 226^2$, $S_{226 \times 226} := 11748384$, $T_{51076} := 51528^2$,
 $E := \{909, 911, \dots, 103057, 103059\}$

■ Number 455

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 455^2 + 504^2 & := 679^2 & 455^2 + 2088^2 := 2137^2 & 455^2 + 14784^2 := 14791^2 \\
 455^2 + 528^2 & := 697^2 & 455^2 + 2940^2 := 2975^2 & 455^2 + 20700^2 := 20705^2 \\
 455^2 + 1092^2 & := 1183^2 & 455^2 + 4128^2 := 4153^2 & 455^2 + 103512^2 := 103513^2 \\
 455^2 + 1560^2 & := 1625^2 & 455^2 + 7956^2 := 7969^2 &
 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(455, 4128, 4153)** $\Rightarrow 4153 - 4128 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 41405$, $T_{25} := 455^2$,
 $E := \{8257, 8259, \dots, 8303, 8305\}$ or $E := \{8269, 8270, \dots, 8292, 8293\}$
2. **(455, 2088, 2137)** $\Rightarrow 2137 - 2088 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 29575$, $T_{49} := 455^2$,
 $E := \{4177, 4179, \dots, 4271, 4273\}$ or $E := \{4201, 4202, \dots, 4248, 4249\}$
3. **(455, 528, 697)** $\Rightarrow 697 - 528 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 15925$, $T_{169} := 455^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 1391, 1393\}$ or $E := \{1141, 1142, \dots, 1308, 1309\}$

■ **Number 456**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$456^2 + 608^2 := 760^2$	$456^2 + 2142^2 := 2190^2$	$456^2 + 6490^2 := 6506^2$
$456^2 + 650^2 := 794^2$	$456^2 + 2717^2 := 2755^2$	$456^2 + 8658^2 := 8670^2$
$456^2 + 855^2 := 969^2$	$456^2 + 2870^2 := 2906^2$	$456^2 + 12992^2 := 13000^2$
$456^2 + 1035^2 := 1131^2$	$456^2 + 3233^2 := 3265^2$	$456^2 + 17325^2 := 17331^2$
$456^2 + 1330^2 := 1406^2$	$456^2 + 4320^2 := 4344^2$	$456^2 + 25990^2 := 25994^2$
$456^2 + 1408^2 := 1480^2$	$456^2 + 5767^2 := 5785^2$	$456^2 + 51983^2 := 51985^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(456, 6490, 6506)** $\Rightarrow 6506 - 6490 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 51984$, $T_{16} := 456^2$,
 $E := \{12981, 12983, \dots, 13009, 13011\}$
2. **(456, 2870, 2906)** $\Rightarrow 2906 - 2870 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 34656$, $T_{36} := 456^2$,
 $E := \{5741, 5743, \dots, 5809, 5811\}$
3. **(456, 650, 794)** $\Rightarrow 794 - 650 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 17328$, $T_{144} := 456^2$,
 $E := \{1301, 1303, \dots, 1585, 1587\}$
4. **(456, 1408, 1480)** $\Rightarrow 1480 - 456 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 61952$, $T_{1024} := 1408^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 2957, 2959\}$
5. **(456, 3233, 3265)** $\Rightarrow 3265 - 456 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 197213$, $T_{2809} := 3233^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 6527, 6529\}$ or $E := \{2317, 2318, \dots, 5124, 5125\}$
6. **(456, 5767, 5785)** $\Rightarrow 5785 - 456 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 455593$, $T_{5329} := 5767^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 11567, 11569\}$ or $E := \{3577, 3578, \dots, 8904, 8905\}$
7. **(456, 12992, 13000)** $\Rightarrow 13000 - 456 = 112^2$, $S_{112 \times 112} := 1507072$, $T_{12544} := 12992^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 25997, 25999\}$

8. **(456, 51983, 51985)** $\Rightarrow 51985 - 456 = 227^2$, $S_{227 \times 227} := 11904107$, $T_{51529} := 51983^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 103967, 103969\}$ or $E := \{26677, 26678, \dots, 78204, 78205\}$

■ Number 457

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$457^2 + 104424^2 := 104425^2$$

■ Number 458

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$458^2 + 52440^2 := 52442^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(458, 52440, 52442)** $\Rightarrow 52442 - 458 = 228^2$, $S_{228 \times 228} := 12061200$, $T_{51984} := 52440^2$,
 $E := \{917, 919, \dots, 104881, 104883\}$

■ Number 459

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$459^2 + 612^2 := 765^2$	$459^2 + 6188^2 := 6205^2$
$459^2 + 1260^2 := 1341^2$	$459^2 + 11700^2 := 11709^2$
$459^2 + 2040^2 := 2091^2$	$459^2 + 35112^2 := 35115^2$
$459^2 + 3888^2 := 3915^2$	$459^2 + 105340^2 := 105341^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(459, 11700, 11709)** $\Rightarrow 11709 - 11700 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 70227$, $T_9 := 459^2$,
 $E := \{23401, 23403, \dots, 23415, 23417\}$ or $E := \{23405, 23406, \dots, 23412, 23413\}$
2. **(459, 1260, 1341)** $\Rightarrow 1341 - 1260 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 23409$, $T_{81} := 459^2$,
 $E := \{2521, 2523, \dots, 2679, 2681\}$ or $E := \{2561, 2562, \dots, 2640, 2641\}$

■ Number 460

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$460^2 + 483^2 := 667^2$$

$$460^2 + 1008^2 := 1108^2$$

$$460^2 + 1104^2 := 1196^2$$

$$460^2 + 2091^2 := 2141^2$$

$$460^2 + 2277^2 := 2323^2$$

$$460^2 + 2625^2 := 2665^2$$

$$460^2 + 5280^2 := 5300^2$$

$$460^2 + 52899^2 := 52901^2$$

$$460^2 + 10575^2 := 10585^2$$

$$460^2 + 13221^2 := 13229^2$$

$$460^2 + 26448^2 := 26452^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(460, 1008, 1108)** $\Rightarrow 1108 - 1008 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 21160$, $T_{100} := 460^2$,
 $E := \{2017, 2019, \dots, 2213, 2215\}$
2. **(460, 2091, 2141)** $\Rightarrow 2141 - 460 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 106641$, $T_{1681} := 2091^2$,
 $E := \{921, 923, \dots, 4279, 4281\}$ or $E := \{1761, 1762, \dots, 3440, 3441\}$
3. **(460, 13221, 13229)** $\Rightarrow 13229 - 460 = 113^2$, $S_{113 \times 113} := 1546857$, $T_{12769} := 13221^2$,
 $E := \{921, 923, \dots, 26455, 26457\}$ or $E := \{7305, 7306, \dots, 20072, 20073\}$
4. **(460, 52899, 52901)** $\Rightarrow 52901 - 460 = 229^2$, $S_{229 \times 229} := 12219669$, $T_{52441} := 52899^2$,
 $E := \{921, 923, \dots, 105799, 105801\}$ or $E := \{27141, 27142, \dots, 79580, 79581\}$

■ Number 461

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$461^2 + 106260^2 := 106261^2$$

■ Number 462

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$462^2 + 616^2 := 770^2$$

$$462^2 + 784^2 := 910^2$$

$$462^2 + 1040^2 := 1138^2$$

$$462^2 + 1584^2 := 1650^2$$

$$462^2 + 2520^2 := 2562^2$$

$$462^2 + 4840^2 := 4862^2$$

$$462^2 + 5920^2 := 5938^2$$

$$462^2 + 7616^2 := 7630^2$$

$$462^2 + 17784^2 := 17790^2$$

$$462^2 + 53360^2 := 53362^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(462, 1040, 1138)** $\Rightarrow 1138 - 462 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 41600$, $T_{676} := 1040^2$,
 $E := \{925, 927, \dots, 2273, 2275\}$
2. **(462, 5920, 5938)** $\Rightarrow 5938 - 462 = 74^2$, $S_{74 \times 74} := 473600$, $T_{5476} := 5920^2$,
 $E := \{925, 927, \dots, 11873, 11875\}$

3. **(462, 53360, 53362)** $\Rightarrow 53362 - 462 = 230^2$, $S_{230 \times 230} := 12379520$, $T_{52900} := 53360^2$,
 $E := \{925, 927, \dots, 106721, 106723\}$

■ Number 463

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$463^2 + 107184^2 := 107185^2$$

■ Number 464

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$464^2 + 777^2 := 905^2$$

$$464^2 + 1827^2 := 1885^2$$

$$464^2 + 13452^2 := 13460^2$$

$$464^2 + 870^2 := 986^2$$

$$464^2 + 3348^2 := 3380^2$$

$$464^2 + 26910^2 := 26914^2$$

$$464^2 + 1650^2 := 1714^2$$

$$464^2 + 6720^2 := 6736^2$$

$$464^2 + 53823^2 := 53825^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(464, 6720, 6736)** $\Rightarrow 6736 - 6720 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 53824$, $T_{16} := 464^2$,
 $E := \{13441, 13443, \dots, 13469, 13471\}$

2. **(464, 1650, 1714)** $\Rightarrow 1714 - 1650 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 26912$, $T_{64} := 464^2$,
 $E := \{3301, 3303, \dots, 3425, 3427\}$

3. **(464, 777, 905)** $\Rightarrow 905 - 464 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 28749$, $T_{441} := 777^2$,
 $E := \{929, 931, \dots, 1807, 1809\}$ or $E := \{1149, 1150, \dots, 1588, 1589\}$

4. **(464, 3348, 3380)** $\Rightarrow 3380 - 464 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 207576$, $T_{2916} := 3348^2$,
 $E := \{929, 931, \dots, 6757, 6759\}$

5. **(464, 13452, 13460)** $\Rightarrow 13460 - 464 = 114^2$, $S_{114 \times 114} := 1587336$, $T_{12996} := 13452^2$,
 $E := \{929, 931, \dots, 26917, 26919\}$

6. **(464, 53823, 53825)** $\Rightarrow 53825 - 464 = 231^2$, $S_{231 \times 231} := 12540759$, $T_{53361} := 53823^2$,
 $E := \{929, 931, \dots, 107647, 107649\}$ or $E := \{27609, 27610, \dots, 80968, 80969\}$

■ Number 465

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$465^2 + 620^2 := 775^2$$

$$465^2 + 1116^2 := 1209^2$$

$$465^2 + 1404^2 := 1479^2$$

$$465^2 + 2380^2 := 2425^2$$

$$465^2 + 3472^2 := 3503^2$$

$$465^2 + 4312^2 := 4337^2$$

$$465^2 + 7200^2 := 7215^2$$

$$465^2 + 12008^2 := 12017^2$$

$$465^2 + 21620^2 := 21625^2$$

$$465^2 + 36036^2 := 36039^2$$

$$465^2 + 108112^2 := 108113^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(465, 12008, 12017)** $\Rightarrow 12017 - 12008 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 72075$, $T_9 := 465^2$,
 $E := \{24017, 24019, \dots, 24031, 24033\}$ or $E := \{24021, 24022, \dots, 24028, 24029\}$
2. **(465, 4312, 4337)** $\Rightarrow 4337 - 4312 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 43245$, $T_{25} := 465^2$,
 $E := \{8625, 8627, \dots, 8671, 8673\}$ or $E := \{8637, 8638, \dots, 8660, 8661\}$

■ Number 466

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$466^2 + 54288^2 := 54290^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(466, 54288, 54290)** $\Rightarrow 54290 - 466 = 232^2$, $S_{232 \times 232} := 12703392$, $T_{53824} := 54288^2$,
 $E := \{933, 935, \dots, 108577, 108579\}$

■ Number 467

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$467^2 + 109044^2 := 109045^2$$

■ Number 468

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$468^2 + 595^2 := 757^2$$

$$468^2 + 624^2 := 780^2$$

$$468^2 + 960^2 := 1068^2$$

$$468^2 + 1001^2 := 1105^2$$

$$468^2 + 1365^2 := 1443^2$$

$$468^2 + 1485^2 := 1557^2$$

$$468^2 + 2001^2 := 2055^2$$

$$468^2 + 2080^2 := 2132^2$$

$$468^2 + 3024^2 := 3060^2$$

$$468^2 + 4199^2 := 4225^2$$

$$468^2 + 4551^2 := 4575^2$$

$$468^2 + 6075^2 := 6093^2$$

$$468^2 + 9120^2 := 9132^2$$

$$468^2 + 13685^2 := 13693^2$$

$$468^2 + 18249^2 := 18255^2$$

$$468^2 + 27376^2 := 27380^2$$

$$468^2 + 54755^2 := 54757^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(468, 3024, 3060)** $\Rightarrow 3060 - 3024 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 36504$, $T_{36} := 468^2$,
 $E := \{6049, 6051, \dots, 6117, 6119\}$ item **(468, 595, 757)** $\Rightarrow 757 - 468 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 20825$, $T_{289} := 595^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 1511, 1513\}$ or $E := \{1081, 1082, \dots, 1368, 1369\}$
2. **(468, 1485, 1557)** $\Rightarrow 1557 - 468 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 66825$, $T_{1089} := 1485^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 3111, 3113\}$ or $E := \{1481, 1482, \dots, 2568, 2569\}$
3. **(468, 6075, 6093)** $\Rightarrow 6093 - 468 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 492075$, $T_{5625} := 6075^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 12183, 12185\}$ or $E := \{3749, 3750, \dots, 9372, 9373\}$
4. **(468, 13685, 13693)** $\Rightarrow 13693 - 468 = 115^2$, $S_{115 \times 115} := 1628515$, $T_{13225} := 13685^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 27383, 27385\}$ or $E := \{7549, 7550, \dots, 20772, 20773\}$
5. **(468, 54755, 54757)** $\Rightarrow 54757 - 468 = 233^2$, $S_{233 \times 233} := 12867425$, $T_{54289} := 54755^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 109511, 109513\}$ or $E := \{28081, 28082, \dots, 82368, 82369\}$

■ Number 469

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$469^2 + 1608^2 := 1675^2$$

$$469^2 + 2220^2 := 2269^2$$

$$469^2 + 15708^2 := 15715^2$$

$$469^2 + 109980^2 := 109981^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(469, 2220, 2269)** $\Rightarrow 2269 - 2220 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 31423$, $T_{49} := 469^2$,
 $E := \{4441, 4443, \dots, 4535, 4537\}$ or $E := \{4465, 4466, \dots, 4512, 4513\}$

■ Number 470

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$470^2 + 1128^2 := 1222^2$$

$$470^2 + 2184^2 := 2234^2$$

$$470^2 + 11040^2 := 11050^2$$

$$470^2 + 55224^2 := 55226^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(470, 2184, 2234)** $\Rightarrow 2234 - 470 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 113568$, $T_{1764} := 2184^2$,
 $E := \{941, 943, \dots, 4465, 4467\}$

2. **(470, 55224, 55226)** $\Rightarrow 55226 - 470 = 234^2$, $S_{234 \times 234} := 13032864$, $T_{54756} := 55224^2$,
 $E := \{941, 943, \dots, 110449, 110451\}$

■ Number 471

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$471^2 + 628^2 := 785^2$$

$$471^2 + 12320^2 := 12329^2$$

$$471^2 + 36972^2 := 36975^2$$

$$471^2 + 110920^2 := 110921^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

• **(471, 12320, 12329)** $\Rightarrow 12329 - 12320 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 73947$, $T_9 := 471^2$,
 $E := \{24641, 24643, \dots, 24655, 24657\}$ or $E := \{24645, 24646, \dots, 24652, 24653\}$

■ Number 472

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$472^2 + 885^2 := 1003^2$$

$$472^2 + 6954^2 := 6970^2$$

$$472^2 + 3465^2 := 3497^2$$

$$472^2 + 13920^2 := 13928^2$$

$$472^2 + 27846^2 := 27850^2$$

$$472^2 + 55695^2 := 55697^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

• **(473, 864, 985)** $\Rightarrow 985 - 864 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 20339$, $T_{121} := 473^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 1967, 1969\}$ or $E := \{1789, 1790, \dots, 1908, 1909\}$

■ Number 473

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$473^2 + 864^2 := 985^2$$

$$473^2 + 2580^2 := 2623^2$$

$$473^2 + 10164^2 := 10175^2$$

$$473^2 + 111864^2 := 111865^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(472, 6954, 6970)** $\Rightarrow 6970 - 6954 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 55696$, $T_{16} := 472^2$,
 $E := \{13909, 13911, \dots, 13937, 13939\}$
2. **(472, 3465, 3497)** $\Rightarrow 3497 - 472 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 218295$, $T_{3025} := 3465^2$,
 $E := \{945, 947, \dots, 6991, 6993\}$ or $E := \{2457, 2458, \dots, 5480, 5481\}$
3. **(472, 13920, 13928)** $\Rightarrow 13928 - 472 = 116^2$, $S_{116 \times 116} := 1670400$, $T_{13456} := 13920^2$,
 $E := \{945, 947, \dots, 27853, 27855\}$
4. **(472, 55695, 55697)** $\Rightarrow 55697 - 472 = 235^2$, $S_{235 \times 235} := 13199715$, $T_{55225} := 55695^2$,
 $E := \{945, 947, \dots, 111391, 111393\}$ or $E := \{28557, 28558, \dots, 83780, 83781\}$

■ Number 474

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$474^2 + 632^2 := 790^2$$

$$474^2 + 6232^2 := 6250^2$$

$$474^2 + 18720^2 := 18726^2$$

$$474^2 + 56168^2 := 56170^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(474, 6232, 6250)** $\Rightarrow 6250 - 474 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 511024$, $T_{5776} := 6232^2$,
 $E := \{949, 951, \dots, 12497, 12499\}$
2. **(474, 56168, 56170)** $\Rightarrow 56170 - 474 = 236^2$, $S_{236 \times 236} := 13367984$, $T_{55696} := 56168^2$,
 $E := \{949, 951, \dots, 112337, 112339\}$

■ Number 475

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$475^2 + 840^2 := 965^2$$

$$475^2 + 1140^2 := 1235^2$$

$$475^2 + 4500^2 := 4525^2$$

$$475^2 + 5928^2 := 5947^2$$

$$475^2 + 22560^2 := 22565^2$$

$$475^2 + 112812^2 := 112813^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(475, 4500, 4525)** $\Rightarrow 4525 - 4500 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 45125$, $T_{25} := 475^2$,
 $E := \{9001, 9003, \dots, 9047, 9049\}$ or $E := \{9013, 9014, \dots, 9036, 9037\}$

■ Number 476

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$476^2 + 480^2 := 676^2$	$476^2 + 1995^2 := 2051^2$	$476^2 + 14157^2 := 14165^2$
$476^2 + 765^2 := 901^2$	$476^2 + 3315^2 := 3349^2$	$476^2 + 28320^2 := 28324^2$
$476^2 + 1107^2 := 1205^2$	$476^2 + 4032^2 := 4060^2$	$476^2 + 56643^2 := 56645^2$
$476^2 + 1632^2 := 1700^2$	$476^2 + 8085^2 := 8099^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(476, 480, 676)** $\Rightarrow 676 - 480 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 16184$, $T_{196} := 476^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 1349, 1351\}$
2. **(476, 1107, 1205)** $\Rightarrow 1205 - 476 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 45387$, $T_{729} := 1107^2$,
 $E := \{953, 955, \dots, 2407, 2409\}$ or $E := \{1317, 1318, \dots, 2044, 2045\}$
3. **(476, 14157, 14165)** $\Rightarrow 14165 - 476 = 117^2$, $S_{117 \times 117} := 1712997$, $T_{13689} := 14157^2$,
 $E := \{953, 955, \dots, 28327, 28329\}$ or $E := \{7797, 7798, \dots, 21484, 21485\}$
4. **(476, 56643, 56645)** $\Rightarrow 56645 - 476 = 237^2$, $S_{237 \times 237} := 13537677$, $T_{56169} := 56643^2$,
 $E := \{953, 955, \dots, 113287, 113289\}$ or $E := \{29037, 29038, \dots, 85204, 85205\}$

■ Number 477

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$477^2 + 636^2 := 795^2$	$477^2 + 12636^2 := 12645^2$
$477^2 + 1364^2 := 1445^2$	$477^2 + 37920^2 := 37923^2$
$477^2 + 2120^2 := 2173^2$	$477^2 + 113764^2 := 113765^2$
$477^2 + 4200^2 := 4227^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(477, 12636, 12645)** $\Rightarrow 12645 - 12636 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 75843$, $T_9 := 477^2$,
 $E := \{25273, 25275, \dots, 25287, 25289\}$ or $E := \{25277, 25278, \dots, 25284, 25285\}$

2. **(477, 1364, 1445)** $\Rightarrow 1445 - 1364 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 25281$, $T_{81} := 477^2$,
 $E := \{2729, 2731, \dots, 2887, 2889\}$ or $E := \{2769, 2770, \dots, 2848, 2849\}$

■ Number 478

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$478^2 + 57120^2 := 57122^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(478, 57120, 57122)** $\Rightarrow 57122 - 478 = 238^2$, $S_{238 \times 238} := 13708800$, $T_{56644} := 57120^2$,
 $E := \{957, 959, \dots, 114241, 114243\}$

■ Number 479

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$479^2 + 114720^2 := 114721^2$$

■ Number 480

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$480^2 + 504^2 := 696^2$$

$$480^2 + 550^2 := 730^2$$

$$480^2 + 640^2 := 800^2$$

$$480^2 + 693^2 := 843^2$$

$$480^2 + 728^2 := 872^2$$

$$480^2 + 836^2 := 964^2$$

$$480^2 + 1102^2 := 1202^2$$

$$480^2 + 1152^2 := 1248^2$$

$$480^2 + 1235^2 := 1325^2$$

$$480^2 + 1400^2 := 1480^2$$

$$480^2 + 1564^2 := 1636^2$$

$$480^2 + 1768^2 := 1832^2$$

$$480^2 + 1890^2 := 1950^2$$

$$480^2 + 2279^2 := 2329^2$$

$$480^2 + 2376^2 := 2424^2$$

$$480^2 + 2860^2 := 2900^2$$

$$480^2 + 3182^2 := 3218^2$$

$$480^2 + 3584^2 := 3616^2$$

$$480^2 + 3825^2 := 3855^2$$

$$480^2 + 4788^2 := 4812^2$$

$$480^2 + 5750^2 := 5770^2$$

$$480^2 + 6391^2 := 6409^2$$

$$480^2 + 7192^2 := 7208^2$$

$$480^2 + 11515^2 := 11525^2$$

$$480^2 + 14396^2 := 14404^2$$

$$480^2 + 19197^2 := 19203^2$$

$$480^2 + 28798^2 := 28802^2$$

$$480^2 + 57599^2 := 57601^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(480, 7192, 7208)** $\Rightarrow 7208 - 7192 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 57600$, $T_{16} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{14385, 14387, \dots, 14413, 14415\}$
2. **(480, 3182, 3218)** $\Rightarrow 3218 - 3182 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 38400$, $T_{36} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{6365, 6367, \dots, 6433, 6435\}$
3. **(480, 1768, 1832)** $\Rightarrow 1832 - 1768 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 28800$, $T_{64} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{3537, 3539, \dots, 3661, 3663\}$
4. **(480, 1102, 1202)** $\Rightarrow 1202 - 1102 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 23040$, $T_{100} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{2205, 2207, \dots, 2401, 2403\}$
5. **(480, 728, 872)** $\Rightarrow 872 - 728 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 19200$, $T_{144} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 1741, 1743\}$
6. **(480, 836, 964)** $\Rightarrow 964 - 480 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 31768$, $T_{484} := 836^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 1925, 1927\}$
7. **(480, 1564, 1636)** $\Rightarrow 1636 - 480 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 71944$, $T_{1156} := 1564^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 3269, 3271\}$
8. **(480, 2279, 2329)** $\Rightarrow 2329 - 480 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 120787$, $T_{1849} := 2279^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 4655, 4657\}$ or $E := \{1885, 1886, \dots, 3732, 3733\}$
9. **(480, 3584, 3616)** $\Rightarrow 3616 - 480 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 229376$, $T_{3136} := 3584^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 7229, 7231\}$
10. **(480, 6391, 6409)** $\Rightarrow 6409 - 480 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 530453$, $T_{5929} := 6391^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 12815, 12817\}$ or $E := \{3925, 3926, \dots, 9852, 9853\}$
11. **(480, 14396, 14404)** $\Rightarrow 14404 - 480 = 118^2$, $S_{118 \times 118} := 1756312$, $T_{13924} := 14396^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 28805, 28807\}$
12. **(480, 57599, 57601)** $\Rightarrow 57601 - 480 = 239^2$, $S_{239 \times 239} := 13881359$, $T_{57121} := 57599^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 115199, 115201\}$ or $E := \{29521, 29522, \dots, 86640, 86641\}$

■ Number 481

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$481^2 + 600^2 := 769^2$$

$$481^2 + 3108^2 := 3145^2$$

$$481^2 + 8892^2 := 8905^2$$

$$481^2 + 115680^2 := 115681^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(481, 600, 769)** $\Rightarrow 769 - 600 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 17797$, $T_{169} := 481^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 1535, 1537\}$ or $E := \{1285, 1286, \dots, 1452, 1453\}$

■ Number 482

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$482^2 + 58080^2 := 58082^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(482, 58080, 58082)** $\Rightarrow 58082 - 482 = 240^2$, $S_{240 \times 240} := 14055360$, $T_{57600} := 58080^2$,
 $E := \{965, 967, \dots, 116161, 116163\}$

■ Number 483

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$483^2 + 644^2 := 805^2$$

$$483^2 + 720^2 := 867^2$$

$$483^2 + 1656^2 := 1725^2$$

$$483^2 + 1820^2 := 1883^2$$

$$483^2 + 2356^2 := 2405^2$$

$$483^2 + 5060^2 := 5083^2$$

$$483^2 + 5544^2 := 5565^2$$

$$483^2 + 12956^2 := 12965^2$$

$$483^2 + 16660^2 := 16667^2$$

$$483^2 + 38880^2 := 38883^2$$

$$483^2 + 116644^2 := 116645^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(483, 12956, 12965)** $\Rightarrow 12965 - 12956 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 77763$, $T_9 := 483^2$,
 $E := \{25913, 25915, \dots, 25927, 25929\}$ or $E := \{25917, 25918, \dots, 25924, 25925\}$
2. **(483, 2356, 2405)** $\Rightarrow 2405 - 2356 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 33327$, $T_{49} := 483^2$,
 $E := \{4713, 4715, \dots, 4807, 4809\}$ or $E := \{4737, 4738, \dots, 4784, 4785\}$

■ Number 484

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$484^2 + 1287^2 := 1375^2$$

$$484^2 + 2640^2 := 2684^2$$

$$484^2 + 5313^2 := 5335^2$$

$$484^2 + 14637^2 := 14645^2$$

$$484^2 + 29280^2 := 29284^2$$

$$484^2 + 58563^2 := 58565^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(484, 14637, 14645)** $\Rightarrow 14645 - 484 = 119^2$, $S_{119 \times 119} := 1800351$, $T_{14161} := 14637^2$,
 $E := \{969, 971, \dots, 29287, 29289\}$ or $E := \{8049, 8050, \dots, 22208, 22209\}$

2. **(484, 58563, 58565)** $\Rightarrow 58565 - 484 = 241^2$, $S_{241 \times 241} := 14230809$, $T_{58081} := 58563^2$,
 $E := \{969, 971, \dots, 117127, 117129\}$ or $E := \{30009, 30010, \dots, 88088, 88089\}$

■ Number 485

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$485^2 + 1164^2 := 1261^2$$

$$485^2 + 4692^2 := 4717^2$$

$$485^2 + 23520^2 := 23525^2$$

$$485^2 + 117612^2 := 117613^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(485, 4692, 4717)** $\Rightarrow 4717 - 4692 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 47045$, $T_{25} := 485^2$,
 $E := \{9385, 9387, \dots, 9431, 9433\}$ or $E := \{9397, 9398, \dots, 9420, 9421\}$

■ Number 486

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$486^2 + 648^2 := 810^2$$

$$486^2 + 2160^2 := 2214^2$$

$$486^2 + 6552^2 := 6570^2$$

$$486^2 + 19680^2 := 19686^2$$

$$486^2 + 59048^2 := 59050^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(486, 648, 810)** $\Rightarrow 810 - 486 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 23328$, $T_{324} := 648^2$,
 $E := \{973, 975, \dots, 1617, 1619\}$
2. **(486, 6552, 6570)** $\Rightarrow 6570 - 486 = 78^2$, $S_{78 \times 78} := 550368$, $T_{6084} := 6552^2$,
 $E := \{973, 975, \dots, 13137, 13139\}$
3. **(486, 59048, 59050)** $\Rightarrow 59050 - 486 = 242^2$, $S_{242 \times 242} := 14407712$, $T_{58564} := 59048^2$,
 $E := \{973, 975, \dots, 118097, 118099\}$

■ Number 487

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$487^2 + 118584^2 := 118585^2$$

■ Number 488

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$488^2 + 915^2 := 1037^2$$

$$488^2 + 3705^2 := 3737^2$$

$$488^2 + 7434^2 := 7450^2$$

$$488^2 + 14880^2 := 14888^2$$

$$488^2 + 29766^2 := 29770^2$$

$$488^2 + 59535^2 := 59537^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(488, 7434, 7450)** $\Rightarrow 7450 - 7434 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 59536$, $T_{16} := 488^2$,
 $E := \{14869, 14871, \dots, 14897, 14899\}$
2. **(488, 3705, 3737)** $\Rightarrow 3737 - 488 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 240825$, $T_{3249} := 3705^2$,
 $E := \{977, 979, \dots, 7471, 7473\}$ or $E := \{2601, 2602, \dots, 5848, 5849\}$
3. **(488, 14880, 14888)** $\Rightarrow 14888 - 488 = 120^2$, $S_{120 \times 120} := 1845120$, $T_{14400} := 14880^2$,
 $E := \{977, 979, \dots, 29773, 29775\}$
4. **(488, 59535, 59537)** $\Rightarrow 59537 - 488 = 243^2$, $S_{243 \times 243} := 14586075$, $T_{59049} := 59535^2$,
 $E := \{977, 979, \dots, 119071, 119073\}$ or $E := \{30501, 30502, \dots, 89548, 89549\}$

■ Number 489

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$489^2 + 652^2 := 815^2$$

$$489^2 + 13280^2 := 13289^2$$

$$489^2 + 39852^2 := 39855^2$$

$$489^2 + 119560^2 := 119561^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(489, 13280, 13289)** $\Rightarrow 13289 - 13280 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 79707$, $T_9 := 489^2$,
 $E := \{26561, 26563, \dots, 26575, 26577\}$ or $E := \{26565, 26566, \dots, 26572, 26573\}$

■ Number 490

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$490^2 + 1176^2 := 1274^2$$

$$490^2 + 1680^2 := 1750^2$$

$$490^2 + 2376^2 := 2426^2$$

$$490^2 + 8568^2 := 8582^2$$

$$490^2 + 12000^2 := 12010^2$$

$$490^2 + 60024^2 := 60026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(490, 1176, 1274)** $\Rightarrow 1274 - 490 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 49392$, $T_{784} := 1176^2$,
 $E := \{981, 983, \dots, 2545, 2547\}$
2. **(490, 2376, 2426)** $\Rightarrow 2426 - 490 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 128304$, $T_{1936} := 2376^2$,
 $E := \{981, 983, \dots, 4849, 4851\}$
3. **(490, 60024, 60026)** $\Rightarrow 60026 - 490 = 244^2$, $S_{244 \times 244} := 14765904$, $T_{59536} := 60024^2$,
 $E := \{981, 983, \dots, 120049, 120051\}$

■ Number 491

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$491^2 + 120540^2 := 120541^2$$

■ Number 492

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$492^2 + 656^2 := 820^2$$

$$492^2 + 1435^2 := 1517^2$$

$$492^2 + 1645^2 := 1717^2$$

$$492^2 + 3344^2 := 3380^2$$

$$492^2 + 5031^2 := 5055^2$$

$$492^2 + 6715^2 := 6733^2$$

$$492^2 + 10080^2 := 10092^2$$

$$492^2 + 15125^2 := 15133^2$$

$$492^2 + 20169^2 := 20175^2$$

$$492^2 + 30256^2 := 30260^2$$

$$492^2 + 60515^2 := 60517^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(492, 3344, 3380)** $\Rightarrow 3380 - 3344 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 40344$, $T_{36} := 492^2$,
 $E := \{6689, 6691, \dots, 6757, 6759\}$
2. **(492, 1645, 1717)** $\Rightarrow 1717 - 492 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 77315$, $T_{1225} := 1645^2$,
 $E := \{985, 987, \dots, 3431, 3433\}$ or $E := \{1597, 1598, \dots, 2820, 2821\}$
3. **(492, 6715, 6733)** $\Rightarrow 6733 - 492 = 79^2$, $S_{79 \times 79} := 570775$, $T_{6241} := 6715^2$,
 $E := \{985, 987, \dots, 13463, 13465\}$ or $E := \{4105, 4106, \dots, 10344, 10345\}$
4. **(492, 15125, 15133)** $\Rightarrow 15133 - 492 = 121^2$, $S_{121 \times 121} := 1890625$, $T_{14641} := 15125^2$,
 $E := \{985, 987, \dots, 30263, 30265\}$ or $E := \{8305, 8306, \dots, 22944, 22945\}$

5. **(492, 60515, 60517)** $\Rightarrow 60517 - 492 = 245^2$, $S_{245 \times 245} := 14947205$, $T_{60025} := 60515^2$,
 $E := \{985, 987, \dots, 121031, 121033\}$ or $E := \{30997, 30998, \dots, 91020, 91021\}$

■ Number 493

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned}493^2 + 4176^2 &:= 4205^2 \\493^2 + 7140^2 &:= 7157^2 \\493^2 + 121524^2 &:= 121525^2\end{aligned}$$

■ Number 494

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned}494^2 + 3192^2 &:= 3230^2 \\494^2 + 4680^2 &:= 4706^2 \\494^2 + 61008^2 &:= 61010^2\end{aligned}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(494, 61008, 61010)** $\Rightarrow 61010 - 494 = 246^2$, $S_{246 \times 246} := 15129984$, $T_{60516} := 61008^2$,
 $E := \{989, 991, \dots, 122017, 122019\}$

■ Number 495

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll}495^2 + 660^2 &:= 825^2 &495^2 + 2200^2 := 2255^2 &495^2 + 11132^2 := 11143^2 \\495^2 + 840^2 &:= 975^2 &495^2 + 2700^2 := 2745^2 &495^2 + 13608^2 := 13617^2 \\495^2 + 952^2 &:= 1073^2 &495^2 + 3696^2 := 3729^2 &495^2 + 24500^2 := 24505^2 \\495^2 + 1188^2 &:= 1287^2 &495^2 + 4524^2 := 4551^2 &495^2 + 40836^2 := 40839^2 \\495^2 + 1472^2 &:= 1553^2 &495^2 + 4888^2 := 4913^2 &495^2 + 122512^2 := 122513^2 \\495^2 + 1596^2 &:= 1671^2 &495^2 + 8160^2 := 8175^2 &\end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(495, 13608, 13617)** $\Rightarrow 13617 - 13608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 81675$, $T_9 := 495^2$,
 $E := \{27217, 27219, \dots, 27231, 27233\}$ or $E := \{27221, 27222, \dots, 27228, 27229\}$
2. **(495, 4888, 4913)** $\Rightarrow 4913 - 4888 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 49005$, $T_{25} := 495^2$,
 $E := \{9777, 9779, \dots, 9823, 9825\}$ or $E := \{9789, 9790, \dots, 9812, 9813\}$
3. **(495, 1472, 1553)** $\Rightarrow 1553 - 1472 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 27225$, $T_{81} := 495^2$,
 $E := \{2945, 2947, \dots, 3103, 3105\}$ or $E := \{2985, 2986, \dots, 3064, 3065\}$
4. **(495, 952, 1073)** $\Rightarrow 1073 - 952 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 22275$, $T_{121} := 495^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 2143, 2145\}$ or $E := \{1965, 1966, \dots, 2084, 2085\}$

■ Number 496

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$496^2 + 897^2 := 1025^2$	$496^2 + 1953^2 := 2015^2$	$496^2 + 15372^2 := 15380^2$
$496^2 + 930^2 := 1054^2$	$496^2 + 3828^2 := 3860^2$	$496^2 + 30750^2 := 30754^2$
$496^2 + 1890^2 := 1954^2$	$496^2 + 7680^2 := 7696^2$	$496^2 + 61503^2 := 61505^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(496, 7680, 7696)** $\Rightarrow 7696 - 7680 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 61504$, $T_{16} := 496^2$,
 $E := \{15361, 15363, \dots, 15389, 15391\}$
2. **(497, 2496, 2545)** $\Rightarrow 2545 - 2496 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 35287$, $T_{49} := 497^2$,
 $E := \{4993, 4995, \dots, 5087, 5089\}$ or $E := \{5017, 5018, \dots, 5064, 5065\}$
3. **(496, 1890, 1954)** $\Rightarrow 1954 - 1890 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 30752$, $T_{64} := 496^2$,
 $E := \{3781, 3783, \dots, 3905, 3907\}$
4. **(496, 897, 1025)** $\Rightarrow 1025 - 496 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 34983$, $T_{529} := 897^2$,
 $E := \{993, 995, \dots, 2047, 2049\}$ or $E := \{1257, 1258, \dots, 1784, 1785\}$
5. **(496, 3828, 3860)** $\Rightarrow 3860 - 496 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 252648$, $T_{3364} := 3828^2$,
 $E := \{993, 995, \dots, 7717, 7719\}$
6. **(496, 15372, 15380)** $\Rightarrow 15380 - 496 = 122^2$, $S_{122 \times 122} := 1936872$, $T_{14884} := 15372^2$,
 $E := \{993, 995, \dots, 30757, 30759\}$
7. **(496, 61503, 61505)** $\Rightarrow 61505 - 496 = 247^2$, $S_{247 \times 247} := 15314247$, $T_{61009} := 61503^2$,
 $E := \{993, 995, \dots, 123007, 123009\}$ or $E := \{31497, 31498, \dots, 92504, 92505\}$

■ Number 497

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$497^2 + 1704^2 := 1775^2$$

$$497^2 + 2496^2 := 2545^2$$

$$497^2 + 17640^2 := 17647^2$$

$$497^2 + 123504^2 := 123505^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(497, 2496, 2545)** $\Rightarrow 2545 - 2496 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 35287$, $T_{49} := 497^2$,
 $E := \{4993, 4995, \dots, 5087, 5089\}$ or $E := \{5017, 5018, \dots, 5064, 5065\}$

■ Number 498

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$498^2 + 664^2 := 830^2$$

$$498^2 + 6880^2 := 6898^2$$

$$498^2 + 20664^2 := 20670^2$$

$$498^2 + 62000^2 := 62002^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(498, 6880, 6898)** $\Rightarrow 6898 - 498 = 80^2$, $S_{80 \times 80} := 591680$, $T_{6400} := 6880^2$,
 $E := \{997, 999, \dots, 13793, 13795\}$
2. **(498, 62000, 62002)** $\Rightarrow 62002 - 498 = 248^2$, $S_{248 \times 248} := 15500000$, $T_{61504} := 62000^2$,
 $E := \{997, 999, \dots, 124001, 124003\}$

■ Number 499

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$499^2 + 124500^2 := 124501^2$$

■ Number 500

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$500^2 + 525^2 := 725^2$$

$$500^2 + 1200^2 := 1300^2$$

$$500^2 + 2475^2 := 2525^2$$

$$500^2 + 3105^2 := 3145^2$$

$$500^2 + 6240^2 := 6260^2$$

$$500^2 + 12495^2 := 12505^2$$

$$500^2 + 15621^2 := 15629^2$$

$$500^2 + 31248^2 := 31252^2$$

$$500^2 + 62499^2 := 62501^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(500, 1200, 1300)** $\Rightarrow 1300 - 1200 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 25000$, $T_{100} := 500^2$,
 $E := \{2401, 2403, \dots, 2597, 2599\}$
2. **(500, 525, 725)** $\Rightarrow 725 - 500 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 18375$, $T_{225} := 525^2$,
 $E := \{1001, 1003, \dots, 1447, 1449\}$ or $E := \{1113, 1114, \dots, 1336, 1337\}$
3. **(500, 2475, 2525)** $\Rightarrow 2525 - 500 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 136125$, $T_{2025} := 2475^2$,
 $E := \{1001, 1003, \dots, 5047, 5049\}$ or $E := \{2013, 2014, \dots, 4036, 4037\}$
4. **(500, 15621, 15629)** $\Rightarrow 15629 - 500 = 123^2$, $S_{123 \times 123} := 1983867$, $T_{15129} := 15621^2$,
 $E := \{1001, 1003, \dots, 31255, 31257\}$ or $E := \{8565, 8566, \dots, 23692, 23693\}$
5. **(500, 62499, 62501)** $\Rightarrow 62501 - 500 = 249^2$, $S_{249 \times 249} := 15687249$, $T_{62001} := 62499^2$,
 $E := \{1001, 1003, \dots, 124999, 125001\}$ or $E := \{32001, 32002, \dots, 94000, 94001\}$

2.6 Pythagorean Triples: 501 to 600

■ Number 501

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$501^2 + 668^2 := 835^2$$

$$501^2 + 13940^2 := 13949^2$$

$$501^2 + 41832^2 := 41835^2$$

$$501^2 + 125500^2 := 125501^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(501, 13940, 13949)** $\Rightarrow 13949 - 13940 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 83667$, $T_9 := 501^2$,
 $E := \{27881, 27883, \dots, 27895, 27897\}$ or $E := \{27885, 27886, \dots, 27892, 27893\}$

■ Number 502

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$502^2 + 63000^2 := 63002^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(502, 63000, 63002)** $\Rightarrow 63002 - 502 = 250^2$, $S_{250 \times 250} := 15876000$, $T_{62500} := 63000^2$,
 $E := \{1005, 1007, \dots, 126001, 126003\}$

■ Number 503

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$503^2 + 126504^2 := 126505^2$$

■ Number 504

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$504^2 + 550^2 := 746^2$$

$$504^2 + 672^2 := 840^2$$

$$504^2 + 703^2 := 865^2$$

$$504^2 + 810^2 := 954^2$$

$$504^2 + 945^2 := 1071^2$$

$$504^2 + 1078^2 := 1190^2$$

$$504^2 + 1122^2 := 1230^2$$

$$504^2 + 1247^2 := 1345^2$$

$$504^2 + 1275^2 := 1371^2$$

$$504^2 + 1470^2 := 1554^2$$

$$504^2 + 1728^2 := 1800^2$$

$$504^2 + 2240^2 := 2296^2$$

$$504^2 + 2325^2 := 2379^2$$

$$504^2 + 2622^2 := 2670^2$$

$$504^2 + 3003^2 := 3045^2$$

$$504^2 + 3510^2 := 3546^2$$

$$504^2 + 3953^2 := 3985^2$$

$$504^2 + 4522^2 := 4550^2$$

$$504^2 + 5280^2 := 5304^2$$

$$504^2 + 7047^2 := 7065^2$$

$$504^2 + 7930^2 := 7946^2$$

$$504^2 + 9065^2 := 9079^2$$

$$504^2 + 10578^2 := 10590^2$$

$$504^2 + 15872^2 := 15880^2$$

$$504^2 + 21165^2 := 21171^2$$

$$504^2 + 31750^2 := 31754^2$$

$$504^2 + 63503^2 := 63505^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(504, 7930, 7946)** $\Rightarrow 7946 - 7930 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 63504$, $T_{16} := 504^2$,
 $E := \{15861, 15863, \dots, 15889, 15891\}$
2. **(504, 3510, 3546)** $\Rightarrow 3546 - 3510 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 42336$, $T_{36} := 504^2$,
 $E := \{7021, 7023, \dots, 7089, 7091\}$
3. **(504, 810, 954)** $\Rightarrow 954 - 810 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 21168$, $T_{144} := 504^2$,
 $E := \{1621, 1623, \dots, 1905, 1907\}$
4. **(504, 550, 746)** $\Rightarrow 746 - 550 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 18144$, $T_{196} := 504^2$,
 $E := \{1101, 1103, \dots, 1489, 1491\}$
5. **(504, 703, 865)** $\Rightarrow 865 - 504 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 26011$, $T_{361} := 703^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 1727, 1729\}$ or $E := \{1189, 1190, \dots, 1548, 1549\}$
6. **(504, 1247, 1345)** $\Rightarrow 1345 - 504 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 53621$, $T_{841} := 1247^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 2687, 2689\}$ or $E := \{1429, 1430, \dots, 2268, 2269\}$
7. **(504, 1728, 1800)** $\Rightarrow 1800 - 504 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 82944$, $T_{1296} := 1728^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 3597, 3599\}$

8. **(504, 3953, 3985)** $\Rightarrow 3985 - 504 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 264851$, $T_{3481} := 3953^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 7967, 7969\}$ or $E := \{2749, 2750, \dots, 6228, 6229\}$
9. **(504, 7047, 7065)** $\Rightarrow 7065 - 504 = 81^2$, $S_{81 \times 81} := 613089$, $T_{6561} := 7047^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 14127, 14129\}$ or $E := \{4289, 4290, \dots, 10848, 10849\}$
10. **(504, 15872, 15880)** $\Rightarrow 15880 - 504 = 124^2$, $S_{124 \times 124} := 2031616$, $T_{15376} := 15872^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 31757, 31759\}$
11. **(504, 63503, 63505)** $\Rightarrow 63505 - 504 = 251^2$, $S_{251 \times 251} := 16066259$, $T_{63001} := 63503^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 127007, 127009\}$ or $E := \{32509, 32510, \dots, 95508, 95509\}$

■ Number 505

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$505^2 + 1212^2 := 1313^2$$

$$505^2 + 5088^2 := 5113^2$$

$$505^2 + 25500^2 := 25505^2$$

$$505^2 + 127512^2 := 127513^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(505, 5088, 5113)** $\Rightarrow 5113 - 5088 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 51005$, $T_{25} := 505^2$,
 $E := \{10177, 10179, \dots, 10223, 10225\}$ or $E := \{10189, 10190, \dots, 10212, 10213\}$

■ Number 506

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$506^2 + 2760^2 := 2806^2$$

$$506^2 + 5808^2 := 5830^2$$

$$506^2 + 64008^2 := 64010^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(506, 64008, 64010)** $\Rightarrow 64010 - 506 = 252^2$, $S_{252 \times 252} := 16258032$, $T_{63504} := 64008^2$,
 $E := \{1013, 1015, \dots, 128017, 128019\}$

■ Number 507

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$507^2 + 676^2 := 845^2$$

$$507^2 + 1040^2 := 1157^2$$

$$507^2 + 3276^2 := 3315^2$$

$$507^2 + 9880^2 := 9893^2$$

$$507^2 + 14276^2 := 14285^2$$

$$507^2 + 42840^2 := 42843^2$$

$$507^2 + 128524^2 := 128525^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(507, 14276, 14285)** $\Rightarrow 14285 - 14276 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 85683$, $T_9 := 507^2$,
 $E := \{28553, 28555, \dots, 28567, 28569\}$ or $E := \{28557, 28558, \dots, 28564, 28565\}$
2. **(507, 676, 845)** $\Rightarrow 845 - 676 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 19773$, $T_{169} := 507^2$,
 $E := \{1353, 1355, \dots, 1687, 1689\}$ or $E := \{1437, 1438, \dots, 1604, 1605\}$

■ Number 508

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$508^2 + 16125^2 := 16133^2$$

$$508^2 + 32256^2 := 32260^2$$

$$508^2 + 64515^2 := 64517^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(508, 16125, 16133)** $\Rightarrow 16133 - 508 = 125^2$, $S_{125 \times 125} := 2080125$, $T_{15625} := 16125^2$,
 $E := \{1017, 1019, \dots, 32263, 32265\}$ or $E := \{8829, 8830, \dots, 24452, 24453\}$
2. **(508, 64515, 64517)** $\Rightarrow 64517 - 508 = 253^2$, $S_{253 \times 253} := 16451325$, $T_{64009} := 64515^2$,
 $E := \{1017, 1019, \dots, 129031, 129033\}$ or $E := \{33021, 33022, \dots, 97028, 97029\}$

■ Number 509

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$509^2 + 129540^2 := 129541^2$$

■ Number 510

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$510^2 + 680^2 := 850^2$$

$$510^2 + 792^2 := 942^2$$

$$510^2 + 1224^2 := 1326^2$$

$$510^2 + 1400^2 := 1490^2$$

$$510^2 + 2576^2 := 2626^2$$

$$510^2 + 3808^2 := 3842^2$$

$$510^2 + 4320^2 := 4350^2$$

$$510^2 + 7216^2 := 7234^2$$

$$510^2 + 13000^2 := 13010^2$$

$$510^2 + 21672^2 := 21678^2$$

$$510^2 + 65024^2 := 65026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(510, 2576, 2626)** $\Rightarrow 2626 - 510 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 144256$, $T_{2116} := 2576^2$,
 $E := \{1021, 1023, \dots, 5249, 5251\}$

2. **(510, 7216, 7234)** $\Rightarrow 7234 - 510 = 82^2$, $S_{82 \times 82} := 635008$, $T_{6724} := 7216^2$,
 $E := \{1021, 1023, \dots, 14465, 14467\}$

3. **(510, 65024, 65026)** $\Rightarrow 65026 - 510 = 254^2$, $S_{254 \times 254} := 16646144$, $T_{64516} := 65024^2$,
 $E := \{1021, 1023, \dots, 130049, 130051\}$

■ Number 511

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$511^2 + 1752^2 := 1825^2$$

$$511^2 + 2640^2 := 2689^2$$

$$511^2 + 18648^2 := 18655^2$$

$$511^2 + 130560^2 := 130561^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(511, 2640, 2689)** $\Rightarrow 2689 - 2640 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 37303$, $T_{49} := 511^2$,
 $E := \{5281, 5283, \dots, 5375, 5377\}$ or $E := \{5305, 5306, \dots, 5352, 5353\}$

■ Number 512

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$512^2 + 960^2 := 1088^2$$

$$512^2 + 2016^2 := 2080^2$$

$$512^2 + 4080^2 := 4112^2$$

$$512^2 + 8184^2 := 8200^2$$

$$512^2 + 16380^2 := 16388^2$$

$$512^2 + 32766^2 := 32770^2$$

$$512^2 + 65535^2 := 65537^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(512, 8184, 8200)** $\Rightarrow 8200 - 8184 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 65536$, $T_{16} := 512^2$,
 $E := \{16369, 16371, \dots, 16397, 16399\}$
2. **(512, 2016, 2080)** $\Rightarrow 2080 - 2016 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 32768$, $T_{64} := 512^2$,
 $E := \{4033, 4035, \dots, 4157, 4159\}$
3. **(512, 960, 1088)** $\Rightarrow 1088 - 512 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 38400$, $T_{576} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{1025, 1027, \dots, 2173, 2175\}$
4. **(512, 4080, 4112)** $\Rightarrow 4112 - 512 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 277440$, $T_{3600} := 4080^2$,
 $E := \{1025, 1027, \dots, 8221, 8223\}$
5. **(512, 16380, 16388)** $\Rightarrow 16388 - 512 = 126^2$, $S_{126 \times 126} := 2129400$, $T_{15876} := 16380^2$,
 $E := \{1025, 1027, \dots, 32773, 32775\}$
6. **(512, 65535, 65537)** $\Rightarrow 65537 - 512 = 255^2$, $S_{255 \times 255} := 16842495$, $T_{65025} := 65535^2$,
 $E := \{1025, 1027, \dots, 131071, 131073\}$ or $E := \{33537, 33538, \dots, 98560, 98561\}$

■ Number 513

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$513^2 + 684^2 := 855^2$	$513^2 + 6916^2 := 6935^2$
$513^2 + 1584^2 := 1665^2$	$513^2 + 14616^2 := 14625^2$
$513^2 + 2280^2 := 2337^2$	$513^2 + 43860^2 := 43863^2$
$513^2 + 4860^2 := 4887^2$	$513^2 + 131584^2 := 131585^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(513, 14616, 14625)** $\Rightarrow 14625 - 14616 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 87723$, $T_9 := 513^2$,
 $E := \{29233, 29235, \dots, 29247, 29249\}$ or $E := \{29237, 29238, \dots, 29244, 29245\}$
2. **(513, 1584, 1665)** $\Rightarrow 1665 - 1584 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 29241$, $T_{81} := 513^2$,
 $E := \{3169, 3171, \dots, 3327, 3329\}$ or $E := \{3209, 3210, \dots, 3288, 3289\}$

■ Number 514

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$514^2 + 66048^2 := 66050^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(514, 66048, 66050)** $\Rightarrow 66050 - 514 = 256^2$, $S_{256 \times 256} := 17040384$, $T_{65536} := 66048^2$,
 $E := \{1029, 1031, \dots, 132097, 132099\}$

■ Number 515

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 515^2 + 1236^2 := 1339^2 & 515^2 + 26520^2 := 26525^2 \\ 515^2 + 5292^2 := 5317^2 & 515^2 + 132612^2 := 132613^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(515, 5292, 5317)** $\Rightarrow 5317 - 5292 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 53045$, $T_{25} := 515^2$,
 $E := \{10585, 10587, \dots, 10631, 10633\}$ or $E := \{10597, 10598, \dots, 10620, 10621\}$

■ Number 516

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll} 516^2 + 688^2 := 860^2 & 516^2 + 5535^2 := 5559^2 & 516^2 + 22185^2 := 22191^2 \\ 516^2 + 1505^2 := 1591^2 & 516^2 + 7387^2 := 7405^2 & 516^2 + 33280^2 := 33284^2 \\ 516^2 + 1813^2 := 1885^2 & 516^2 + 11088^2 := 11100^2 & 516^2 + 66563^2 := 66565^2 \\ 516^2 + 3680^2 := 3716^2 & 516^2 + 16637^2 := 16645^2 & \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(516, 3680, 3716)** $\Rightarrow 3716 - 3680 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 44376$, $T_{36} := 516^2$,
 $E := \{7361, 7363, \dots, 7429, 7431\}$
2. **(516, 1813, 1885)** $\Rightarrow 1885 - 516 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 88837$, $T_{1369} := 1813^2$,
 $E := \{1033, 1035, \dots, 3767, 3769\}$ or $E := \{1717, 1718, \dots, 3084, 3085\}$
3. **(516, 7387, 7405)** $\Rightarrow 7405 - 516 = 83^2$, $S_{83 \times 83} := 657443$, $T_{6889} := 7387^2$,
 $E := \{1033, 1035, \dots, 14807, 14809\}$ or $E := \{4477, 4478, \dots, 11364, 11365\}$
4. **(516, 16637, 16645)** $\Rightarrow 16645 - 516 = 127^2$, $S_{127 \times 127} := 2179447$, $T_{16129} := 16637^2$,
 $E := \{1033, 1035, \dots, 33287, 33289\}$ or $E := \{9097, 9098, \dots, 25224, 25225\}$
5. **(516, 66563, 66565)** $\Rightarrow 66565 - 516 = 257^2$, $S_{257 \times 257} := 17239817$, $T_{66049} := 66563^2$,
 $E := \{1033, 1035, \dots, 133127, 133129\}$ or $E := \{34057, 34058, \dots, 100104, 100105\}$

■ Number 517

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$517^2 + 1044^2 := 1165^2$$

$$517^2 + 2820^2 := 2867^2$$

$$517^2 + 12144^2 := 12155^2$$

$$517^2 + 133644^2 := 133645^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(517, 1044, 1165)** $\Rightarrow 1165 - 1044 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 24299$, $T_{121} := 517^2$,
 $E := \{2089, 2091, \dots, 2327, 2329\}$ or $E := \{2149, 2150, \dots, 2268, 2269\}$

■ Number 518

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$518^2 + 1320^2 := 1418^2$$

$$518^2 + 1776^2 := 1850^2$$

$$518^2 + 9576^2 := 9590^2$$

$$518^2 + 67080^2 := 67082^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(518, 1320, 1418)** $\Rightarrow 1418 - 518 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 58080$, $T_{900} := 1320^2$,
 $E := \{1037, 1039, \dots, 2833, 2835\}$
2. **(518, 67080, 67082)** $\Rightarrow 67082 - 518 = 258^2$, $S_{258 \times 258} := 17440800$, $T_{66564} := 67080^2$,
 $E := \{1037, 1039, \dots, 134161, 134163\}$

■ Number 519

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$519^2 + 692^2 := 865^2$$

$$519^2 + 14960^2 := 14969^2$$

$$519^2 + 44892^2 := 44895^2$$

$$519^2 + 134680^2 := 134681^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(519, 14960, 14969)** $\Rightarrow 14969 - 14960 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 89787$, $T_9 := 519^2$,
 $E := \{29921, 29923, \dots, 29935, 29937\}$ or $E := \{29925, 29926, \dots, 29932, 29933\}$

■ Number 52

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$520^2 + 546^2 := 754^2$	$520^2 + 1650^2 := 1730^2$	$520^2 + 6750^2 := 6770^2$
$520^2 + 576^2 := 776^2$	$520^2 + 2574^2 := 2626^2$	$520^2 + 8442^2 := 8458^2$
$520^2 + 765^2 := 925^2$	$520^2 + 2679^2 := 2729^2$	$520^2 + 13515^2 := 13525^2$
$520^2 + 975^2 := 1105^2$	$520^2 + 3360^2 := 3400^2$	$520^2 + 16896^2 := 16904^2$
$520^2 + 1248^2 := 1352^2$	$520^2 + 4209^2 := 4241^2$	$520^2 + 33798^2 := 33802^2$
$520^2 + 1302^2 := 1402^2$	$520^2 + 5187^2 := 5213^2$	$520^2 + 67599^2 := 67601^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(520, 8442, 8458)** $\Rightarrow 8458 - 8442 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 67600$, $T_{16} := 520^2$,
 $E := \{16885, 16887, \dots, 16913, 16915\}$
2. **(520, 1302, 1402)** $\Rightarrow 1402 - 1302 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 27040$, $T_{100} := 520^2$,
 $E := \{2605, 2607, \dots, 2801, 2803\}$
3. **(520, 576, 776)** $\Rightarrow 776 - 520 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 20736$, $T_{256} := 576^2$,
 $E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 1549, 1551\}$
4. **(520, 2679, 2729)** $\Rightarrow 2729 - 520 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 152703$, $T_{2209} := 2679^2$,
 $E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 5455, 5457\}$ or $E := \{2145, 2146, \dots, 4352, 4353\}$
5. **(520, 4209, 4241)** $\Rightarrow 4241 - 520 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 290421$, $T_{3721} := 4209^2$,
 $E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 8479, 8481\}$ or $E := \{2901, 2902, \dots, 6620, 6621\}$
6. **(520, 16896, 16904)** $\Rightarrow 16904 - 520 = 128^2$, $S_{128 \times 128} := 2230272$, $T_{16384} := 16896^2$,
 $E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 33805, 33807\}$
7. **(520, 67599, 67601)** $\Rightarrow 67601 - 520 = 259^2$, $S_{259 \times 259} := 17643339$, $T_{67081} := 67599^2$,
 $E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 135199, 135201\}$ or $E := \{34581, 34582, \dots, 101660, 101661\}$

■ Number 521

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$521^2 + 135720^2 := 135721^2$$

■ Number 522

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$522^2 + 696^2 := 870^2$$

$$522^2 + 760^2 := 922^2$$

$$522^2 + 2320^2 := 2378^2$$

$$522^2 + 2496^2 := 2550^2$$

$$522^2 + 7560^2 := 7578^2$$

$$522^2 + 22704^2 := 22710^2$$

$$522^2 + 68120^2 := 68122^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(522, 760, 922)** $\Rightarrow 922 - 522 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 28880$, $T_{400} := 760^2$,
 $E := \{1045, 1047, \dots, 1841, 1843\}$
2. **(522, 7560, 7578)** $\Rightarrow 7578 - 522 = 84^2$, $S_{84 \times 84} := 680400$, $T_{7056} := 7560^2$,
 $E := \{1045, 1047, \dots, 15153, 15155\}$
3. **(522, 68120, 68122)** $\Rightarrow 68122 - 522 = 260^2$, $S_{260 \times 260} := 17847440$, $T_{67600} := 68120^2$,
 $E := \{1045, 1047, \dots, 136241, 136243\}$

■ Number 523

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$523^2 + 136764^2 := 136765^2$$

■ Number 524

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$524^2 + 17157^2 := 17165^2$$

$$524^2 + 34320^2 := 34324^2$$

$$524^2 + 68643^2 := 68645^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(524, 17157, 17165)** $\Rightarrow 17165 - 524 = 129^2$, $S_{129 \times 129} := 2281881$, $T_{16641} := 17157^2$,
 $E := \{1049, 1051, \dots, 34327, 34329\}$ or $E := \{9369, 9370, \dots, 26008, 26009\}$
2. **(524, 68643, 68645)** $\Rightarrow 68645 - 524 = 261^2$, $S_{261 \times 261} := 18053109$, $T_{68121} := 68643^2$,
 $E := \{1049, 1051, \dots, 137287, 137289\}$ or $E := \{35109, 35110, \dots, 103228, 103229\}$

■ Number 525

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$525^2 + 700^2 := 875^2$$

$$525^2 + 864^2 := 1011^2$$

$$525^2 + 1040^2 := 1165^2$$

$$525^2 + 1260^2 := 1365^2$$

$$525^2 + 1800^2 := 1875^2$$

$$525^2 + 2156^2 := 2219^2$$

$$525^2 + 2788^2 := 2837^2$$

$$525^2 + 3040^2 := 3085^2$$

$$525^2 + 3920^2 := 3955^2$$

$$525^2 + 5500^2 := 5525^2$$

$$525^2 + 6552^2 := 6573^2$$

$$525^2 + 9180^2 := 9195^2$$

$$525^2 + 15308^2 := 15317^2$$

$$525^2 + 19684^2 := 19691^2$$

$$525^2 + 27560^2 := 27565^2$$

$$525^2 + 45936^2 := 45939^2$$

$$525^2 + 137812^2 := 137813^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(525, 15308, 15317)** $\Rightarrow 15317 - 15308 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 91875$, $T_9 := 525^2$,
 $E := \{30617, 30619, \dots, 30631, 30633\}$ or $E := \{30621, 30622, \dots, 30628, 30629\}$
2. **(525, 5500, 5525)** $\Rightarrow 5525 - 5500 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 55125$, $T_{25} := 525^2$,
 $E := \{11001, 11003, \dots, 11047, 11049\}$ or $E := \{11013, 11014, \dots, 11036, 11037\}$
3. **(525, 2788, 2837)** $\Rightarrow 2837 - 2788 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 39375$, $T_{49} := 525^2$,
 $E := \{5577, 5579, \dots, 5671, 5673\}$ or $E := \{5601, 5602, \dots, 5648, 5649\}$

■ Number 526

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$526^2 + 69168^2 := 69170^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(526, 69168, 69170)** $\Rightarrow 69170 - 526 = 262^2$, $S_{262 \times 262} := 18260352$, $T_{68644} := 69168^2$,
 $E := \{1053, 1055, \dots, 138337, 138339\}$

■ Number 527

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$527^2 + 4464^2 := 4495^2$$

$$527^2 + 8160^2 := 8177^2$$

$$527^2 + 138864^2 := 138865^2$$

■ Number 528

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$528^2 + 605^2 := 803^2$	$528^2 + 1900^2 := 1972^2$	$528^2 + 6325^2 := 6347^2$
$528^2 + 630^2 := 822^2$	$528^2 + 2079^2 := 2145^2$	$528^2 + 7735^2 := 7753^2$
$528^2 + 704^2 := 880^2$	$528^2 + 2146^2 := 2210^2$	$528^2 + 8704^2 := 8720^2$
$528^2 + 896^2 := 1040^2$	$528^2 + 2880^2 := 2928^2$	$528^2 + 11610^2 := 11622^2$
$528^2 + 990^2 := 1122^2$	$528^2 + 3146^2 := 3190^2$	$528^2 + 17420^2 := 17428^2$
$528^2 + 1025^2 := 1153^2$	$528^2 + 3854^2 := 3890^2$	$528^2 + 23229^2 := 23235^2$
$528^2 + 1404^2 := 1500^2$	$528^2 + 4340^2 := 4372^2$	$528^2 + 34846^2 := 34850^2$
$528^2 + 1540^2 := 1628^2$	$528^2 + 5796^2 := 5820^2$	$528^2 + 69695^2 := 69697^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(528, 8704, 8720)** $\Rightarrow 8720 - 8704 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 69696$, $T_{16} := 528^2$,
 $E := \{17409, 17411, \dots, 17437, 17439\}$
2. **(528, 3854, 3890)** $\Rightarrow 3890 - 3854 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 46464$, $T_{36} := 528^2$,
 $E := \{7709, 7711, \dots, 7777, 7779\}$
3. **(528, 2146, 2210)** $\Rightarrow 2210 - 2146 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 34848$, $T_{64} := 528^2$,
 $E := \{4293, 4295, \dots, 4417, 4419\}$
4. **(528, 896, 1040)** $\Rightarrow 1040 - 896 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 23232$, $T_{144} := 528^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 2077, 2079\}$
5. **(528, 1025, 1153)** $\Rightarrow 1153 - 528 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 42025$, $T_{625} := 1025^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 2303, 2305\}$ or $E := \{1369, 1370, \dots, 1992, 1993\}$
6. **(528, 1900, 1972)** $\Rightarrow 1972 - 528 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 95000$, $T_{1444} := 1900^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 3941, 3943\}$
7. **(528, 4340, 4372)** $\Rightarrow 4372 - 528 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 303800$, $T_{3844} := 4340^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 8741, 8743\}$
8. **(528, 7735, 7753)** $\Rightarrow 7753 - 528 = 85^2$, $S_{85 \times 85} := 703885$, $T_{7225} := 7735^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 15503, 15505\}$ or $E := \{4669, 4670, \dots, 11892, 11893\}$
9. **(528, 17420, 17428)** $\Rightarrow 17428 - 528 = 130^2$, $S_{130 \times 130} := 2334280$, $T_{16900} := 17420^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 34853, 34855\}$
10. **(528, 69695, 69697)** $\Rightarrow 69697 - 528 = 263^2$, $S_{263 \times 263} := 18469175$, $T_{69169} := 69695^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 139391, 139393\}$ or $E := \{35641, 35642, \dots, 104808, 104809\}$

■ Number 529

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$529^2 + 6072^2 := 6095^2$$

$$529^2 + 139920^2 := 139921^2$$

■ Number 530

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$530^2 + 1272^2 := 1378^2$$

$$530^2 + 2784^2 := 2834^2$$

$$530^2 + 14040^2 := 14050^2$$

$$530^2 + 70224^2 := 70226^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(530, 2784, 2834)** $\Rightarrow 2834 - 530 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 161472$, $T_{2304} := 2784^2$,
 $E := \{1061, 1063, \dots, 5665, 5667\}$

2. **(530, 70224, 70226)** $\Rightarrow 70226 - 530 = 264^2$, $S_{264 \times 264} := 18679584$, $T_{69696} := 70224^2$,
 $E := \{1061, 1063, \dots, 140449, 140451\}$

■ Number 531

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$531^2 + 708^2 := 885^2$$

$$531^2 + 1700^2 := 1781^2$$

$$531^2 + 2360^2 := 2419^2$$

$$531^2 + 5208^2 := 5235^2$$

$$531^2 + 15660^2 := 15669^2$$

$$531^2 + 46992^2 := 46995^2$$

$$531^2 + 140980^2 := 140981^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(531, 15660, 15669)** $\Rightarrow 15669 - 15660 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 93987$, $T_9 := 531^2$,
 $E := \{31321, 31323, \dots, 31335, 31337\}$ or $E := \{31325, 31326, \dots, 31332, 31333\}$

2. **(531, 1700, 1781)** $\Rightarrow 1781 - 1700 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 31329$, $T_{81} := 531^2$,
 $E := \{3401, 3403, \dots, 3559, 3561\}$ or $E := \{3441, 3442, \dots, 3520, 3521\}$

■ Number 532

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$532^2 + 624^2 := 820^2$$

$$532^2 + 855^2 := 1007^2$$

$$532^2 + 1395^2 := 1493^2$$

$$532^2 + 1824^2 := 1900^2$$

$$532^2 + 2499^2 := 2555^2$$

$$532^2 + 3705^2 := 3743^2$$

$$532^2 + 5040^2 := 5068^2$$

$$532^2 + 10101^2 := 10115^2$$

$$532^2 + 17685^2 := 17693^2$$

$$532^2 + 35376^2 := 35380^2$$

$$532^2 + 70755^2 := 70757^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(532, 1395, 1493)** $\Rightarrow 1493 - 532 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 62775$, $T_{961} := 1395^2$,
 $E := \{1065, 1067, \dots, 2983, 2985\}$ or $E := \{1545, 1546, \dots, 2504, 2505\}$
2. **(532, 17685, 17693)** $\Rightarrow 17693 - 532 = 131^2$, $S_{131 \times 131} := 2387475$, $T_{17161} := 17685^2$,
 $E := \{1065, 1067, \dots, 35383, 35385\}$ or $E := \{9645, 9646, \dots, 26804, 26805\}$
3. **(532, 624, 820)** $\Rightarrow 820 - 624 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 20216$, $T_{196} := 532^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 1637, 1639\}$
4. **(532, 70755, 70757)** $\Rightarrow 70757 - 532 = 265^2$, $S_{265 \times 265} := 18891585$, $T_{70225} := 70755^2$,
 $E := \{1065, 1067, \dots, 141511, 141513\}$ or $E := \{36177, 36178, \dots, 106400, 106401\}$

■ Number 533

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$533^2 + 756^2 := 925^2$$

$$533^2 + 3444^2 := 3485^2$$

$$533^2 + 10920^2 := 10933^2$$

$$533^2 + 142044^2 := 142045^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(533, 756, 925)** $\Rightarrow 925 - 756 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 21853$, $T_{169} := 533^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 1847, 1849\}$ or $E := \{1597, 1598, \dots, 1764, 1765\}$

■ Number 534

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$534^2 + 712^2 := 890^2$$

$$534^2 + 7912^2 := 7930^2$$

$$534^2 + 23760^2 := 23766^2$$

$$534^2 + 71288^2 := 71290^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(534, 7912, 7930)** $\Rightarrow 7930 - 534 = 86^2$, $S_{86 \times 86} := 727904$, $T_{7396} := 7912^2$,
 $E := \{1069, 1071, \dots, 15857, 15859\}$
2. **(534, 71288, 71290)** $\Rightarrow 71290 - 534 = 266^2$, $S_{266 \times 266} := 19105184$, $T_{70756} := 71288^2$,
 $E := \{1069, 1071, \dots, 142577, 142579\}$

■ Number 535

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 535^2 + 1284^2 := 1391^2 & 535^2 + 28620^2 := 28625^2 \\ 535^2 + 5712^2 := 5737^2 & 535^2 + 143112^2 := 143113^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(535, 5712, 5737)** $\Rightarrow 5737 - 5712 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 57245$, $T_{25} := 535^2$,
 $E := \{11425, 11427, \dots, 11471, 11473\}$ or $E := \{11437, 11438, \dots, 11460, 11461\}$

■ Number 536

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 536^2 + 1005^2 := 1139^2 & 536^2 + 17952^2 := 17960^2 \\ 536^2 + 4473^2 := 4505^2 & 536^2 + 35910^2 := 35914^2 \\ 536^2 + 8970^2 := 8986^2 & 536^2 + 71823^2 := 71825^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(536, 8970, 8986)** $\Rightarrow 8986 - 8970 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 71824$, $T_{16} := 536^2$,
 $E := \{17941, 17943, \dots, 17969, 17971\}$
2. **(536, 4473, 4505)** $\Rightarrow 4505 - 536 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 317583$, $T_{3969} := 4473^2$,
 $E := \{1073, 1075, \dots, 9007, 9009\}$ or $E := \{3057, 3058, \dots, 7024, 7025\}$
3. **(536, 17952, 17960)** $\Rightarrow 17960 - 536 = 132^2$, $S_{132 \times 132} := 2441472$, $T_{17424} := 17952^2$,
 $E := \{1073, 1075, \dots, 35917, 35919\}$
4. **(536, 71823, 71825)** $\Rightarrow 71825 - 536 = 267^2$, $S_{267 \times 267} := 19320387$, $T_{71289} := 71823^2$,
 $E := \{1073, 1075, \dots, 143647, 143649\}$ or $E := \{36717, 36718, \dots, 108004, 108005\}$

■ Number 537

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 537^2 + 716^2 := 895^2 & 537^2 + 48060^2 := 48063^2 \\ 537^2 + 16016^2 := 16025^2 & 537^2 + 144184^2 := 144185^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(537, 16016, 16025)** $\Rightarrow 16025 - 16016 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 96123$, $T_9 := 537^2$,
 $E := \{32033, 32035, \dots, 32047, 32049\}$ or $E := \{32037, 32038, \dots, 32044, 32045\}$

■ Number 538

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$538^2 + 72360^2 := 72362^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(538, 72360, 72362)** $\Rightarrow 72362 - 538 = 268^2$, $S_{268 \times 268} := 19537200$, $T_{71824} := 72360^2$,
 $E := \{1077, 1079, \dots, 144721, 144723\}$

■ Number 539

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 539^2 + 1140^2 := 1261^2 & 539^2 + 13200^2 := 13211^2 \\ 539^2 + 1848^2 := 1925^2 & 539^2 + 20748^2 := 20755^2 \\ 539^2 + 2940^2 := 2989^2 & 539^2 + 145260^2 := 145261^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(539, 2940, 2989)** $\Rightarrow 2989 - 2940 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 41503$, $T_{49} := 539^2$,
 $E := \{5881, 5883, \dots, 5975, 5977\}$ or $E := \{5905, 5906, \dots, 5952, 5953\}$
2. **(539, 1140, 1261)** $\Rightarrow 1261 - 1140 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 26411$, $T_{121} := 539^2$,
 $E := \{2281, 2283, \dots, 2519, 2521\}$ or $E := \{2341, 2342, \dots, 2460, 2461\}$

■ Number 540

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$540^2 + 567^2 := 783^2$	$540^2 + 1575^2 := 1665^2$	$540^2 + 6063^2 := 6087^2$
$540^2 + 629^2 := 829^2$	$540^2 + 1989^2 := 2061^2$	$540^2 + 7280^2 := 7300^2$
$540^2 + 720^2 := 900^2$	$540^2 + 2400^2 := 2460^2$	$540^2 + 8091^2 := 8109^2$
$540^2 + 819^2 := 981^2$	$540^2 + 2673^2 := 2727^2$	$540^2 + 12144^2 := 12156^2$
$540^2 + 897^2 := 1047^2$	$540^2 + 2891^2 := 2941^2$	$540^2 + 14575^2 := 14585^2$
$540^2 + 1155^2 := 1275^2$	$540^2 + 3625^2 := 3665^2$	$540^2 + 18221^2 := 18229^2$
$540^2 + 1296^2 := 1404^2$	$540^2 + 4032^2 := 4068^2$	$540^2 + 24297^2 := 24303^2$
$540^2 + 1408^2 := 1508^2$	$540^2 + 4845^2 := 4875^2$	$540^2 + 36448^2 := 36452^2$
		$540^2 + 72899^2 := 72901^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(540, 4032, 4068)** $\Rightarrow 4068 - 4032 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 48600$, $T_{36} := 540^2$,
 $E := \{8065, 8067, \dots, 8133, 8135\}$
2. **(540, 1408, 1508)** $\Rightarrow 1508 - 1408 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 29160$, $T_{100} := 540^2$,
 $E := \{2817, 2819, \dots, 3013, 3015\}$
3. **(540, 629, 829)** $\Rightarrow 829 - 540 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 23273$, $T_{289} := 629^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 1655, 1657\}$ or $E := \{1225, 1226, \dots, 1512, 1513\}$
4. **(540, 819, 981)** $\Rightarrow 981 - 540 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 31941$, $T_{441} := 819^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 1959, 1961\}$ or $E := \{1301, 1302, \dots, 1740, 1741\}$
5. **(540, 1989, 2061)** $\Rightarrow 2061 - 540 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 101439$, $T_{1521} := 1989^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 4119, 4121\}$ or $E := \{1841, 1842, \dots, 3360, 3361\}$
6. **(540, 2891, 2941)** $\Rightarrow 2941 - 540 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 170569$, $T_{2401} := 2891^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 5879, 5881\}$ or $E := \{2281, 2282, \dots, 4680, 4681\}$
7. **(540, 8091, 8109)** $\Rightarrow 8109 - 540 = 87^2$, $S_{87 \times 87} := 752463$, $T_{7569} := 8091^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 16215, 16217\}$ or $E := \{4865, 4866, \dots, 12432, 12433\}$
8. **(540, 18221, 18229)** $\Rightarrow 18229 - 540 = 133^2$, $S_{133 \times 133} := 2496277$, $T_{17689} := 18221^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 36455, 36457\}$ or $E := \{9925, 9926, \dots, 27612, 27613\}$
9. **(540, 72899, 72901)** $\Rightarrow 72901 - 540 = 269^2$, $S_{269 \times 269} := 19755629$, $T_{72361} := 72899^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 145799, 145801\}$ or $E := \{37261, 37262, \dots, 109620, 109621\}$

■ Number 541

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$541^2 + 146340^2 := 146341^2$$

■ Number 542

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$542^2 + 73440^2 := 73442^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(542, 73440, 73442)** $\Rightarrow 73442 - 542 = 270^2$, $S_{270 \times 270} := 19975680$, $T_{72900} := 73440^2$,
 $E := \{1085, 1087, \dots, 146881, 146883\}$

■ Number 543

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$543^2 + 724^2 := 905^2$$

$$543^2 + 16376^2 := 16385^2$$

$$543^2 + 49140^2 := 49143^2$$

$$543^2 + 147424^2 := 147425^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(543, 16376, 16385)** $\Rightarrow 16385 - 16376 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 98283$, $T_9 := 543^2$,
 $E := \{32753, 32755, \dots, 32767, 32769\}$ or $E := \{32757, 32758, \dots, 32764, 32765\}$

■ Number 544

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$544^2 + 1020^2 := 1156^2$$

$$544^2 + 1092^2 := 1220^2$$

$$544^2 + 2142^2 := 2210^2$$

$$544^2 + 2280^2 := 2344^2$$

$$544^2 + 4335^2 := 4369^2$$

$$544^2 + 4608^2 := 4640^2$$

$$544^2 + 9240^2 := 9256^2$$

$$544^2 + 18492^2 := 18500^2$$

$$544^2 + 36990^2 := 36994^2$$

$$544^2 + 73983^2 := 73985^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(544, 9240, 9256)** $\Rightarrow 9256 - 9240 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 73984$, $T_{16} := 544^2$,
 $E := \{18481, 18483, \dots, 18509, 18511\}$
2. **(544, 2280, 2344)** $\Rightarrow 2344 - 2280 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 36992$, $T_{64} := 544^2$,
 $E := \{4561, 4563, \dots, 4685, 4687\}$

3. **(544, 1092, 1220)** $\Rightarrow 1220 - 544 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 45864$, $T_{676} := 1092^2$,
 $E := \{1089, 1091, \dots, 2437, 2439\}$
4. **(544, 4608, 4640)** $\Rightarrow 4640 - 544 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 331776$, $T_{4096} := 4608^2$,
 $E := \{1089, 1091, \dots, 9277, 9279\}$
5. **(544, 18492, 18500)** $\Rightarrow 18500 - 544 = 134^2$, $S_{134 \times 134} := 2551896$, $T_{17956} := 18492^2$,
 $E := \{1089, 1091, \dots, 36997, 36999\}$
6. **(544, 73983, 73985)** $\Rightarrow 73985 - 544 = 271^2$, $S_{271 \times 271} := 20197359$, $T_{73441} := 73983^2$,
 $E := \{1089, 1091, \dots, 147967, 147969\}$ or $E := \{37809, 37810, \dots, 111248, 111249\}$

■ Number 545

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 545^2 + 1308^2 := 1417^2 & 545^2 + 29700^2 := 29705^2 \\ 545^2 + 5928^2 := 5953^2 & 545^2 + 148512^2 := 148513^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(545, 5928, 5953)** $\Rightarrow 5953 - 5928 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 59405$, $T_{25} := 545^2$,
 $E := \{11857, 11859, \dots, 11903, 11905\}$ or $E := \{11869, 11870, \dots, 11892, 11893\}$

■ Number 546

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll} 546^2 + 728^2 := 910^2 & 546^2 + 1872^2 := 1950^2 & 546^2 + 8272^2 := 8290^2 \\ 546^2 + 1120^2 := 1246^2 & 546^2 + 3528^2 := 3570^2 & 546^2 + 10640^2 := 10654^2 \\ 546^2 + 1472^2 := 1570^2 & 546^2 + 5720^2 := 5746^2 & 546^2 + 24840^2 := 24846^2 \\ & & 546^2 + 74528^2 := 74530^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(546, 1472, 1570)** $\Rightarrow 1570 - 546 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 67712$, $T_{1024} := 1472^2$,
 $E := \{1093, 1095, \dots, 3137, 3139\}$
2. **(546, 8272, 8290)** $\Rightarrow 8290 - 546 = 88^2$, $S_{88 \times 88} := 777568$, $T_{7744} := 8272^2$,
 $E := \{1093, 1095, \dots, 16577, 16579\}$
3. **(546, 74528, 74530)** $\Rightarrow 74530 - 546 = 272^2$, $S_{272 \times 272} := 20420672$, $T_{73984} := 74528^2$,
 $E := \{1093, 1095, \dots, 149057, 149059\}$

■ Number 547

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$547^2 + 149604^2 := 149605^2$$

■ Number 548

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$548^2 + 18765^2 := 18773^2$$

$$548^2 + 37536^2 := 37540^2$$

$$548^2 + 75075^2 := 75077^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(548, 18765, 18773)** $\Rightarrow 18773 - 548 = 135^2$, $S_{135 \times 135} := 2608335$, $T_{18225} := 18765^2$,
 $E := \{1097, 1099, \dots, 37543, 37545\}$ or $E := \{10209, 10210, \dots, 28432, 28433\}$
2. **(548, 75075, 75077)** $\Rightarrow 75077 - 548 = 273^2$, $S_{273 \times 273} := 20645625$, $T_{74529} := 75075^2$,
 $E := \{1097, 1099, \dots, 150151, 150153\}$ or $E := \{38361, 38362, \dots, 112888, 112889\}$

■ Number 549

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$549^2 + 732^2 := 915^2$$

$$549^2 + 1820^2 := 1901^2$$

$$549^2 + 2440^2 := 2501^2$$

$$549^2 + 5568^2 := 5595^2$$

$$549^2 + 16740^2 := 16749^2$$

$$549^2 + 50232^2 := 50235^2$$

$$549^2 + 150700^2 := 150701^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(549, 16740, 16749)** $\Rightarrow 16749 - 16740 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 100467$, $T_9 := 549^2$,
 $E := \{33481, 33483, \dots, 33495, 33497\}$ or $E := \{33485, 33486, \dots, 33492, 33493\}$
2. **(549, 1820, 1901)** $\Rightarrow 1901 - 1820 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 33489$, $T_{81} := 549^2$,
 $E := \{3641, 3643, \dots, 3799, 3801\}$ or $E := \{3681, 3682, \dots, 3760, 3761\}$

■ Number 550

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$550^2 + 1320^2 := 1430^2$$

$$550^2 + 3000^2 := 3050^2$$

$$550^2 + 6864^2 := 6886^2$$

$$550^2 + 15120^2 := 15130^2$$

$$550^2 + 75624^2 := 75626^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(550, 3000, 3050)** $\Rightarrow 3050 - 550 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 180000$, $T_{2500} := 3000^2$,
 $E := \{1101, 1103, \dots, 6097, 6099\}$

2. **(550, 75624, 75626)** $\Rightarrow 75626 - 550 = 274^2$, $S_{274 \times 274} := 20872224$, $T_{75076} := 75624^2$,
 $E := \{1101, 1103, \dots, 151249, 151251\}$

■ Number 551

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$551^2 + 5220^2 := 5249^2$$

$$551^2 + 7980^2 := 7999^2$$

$$551^2 + 151800^2 := 151801^2$$

■ Number 552

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$552^2 + 736^2 := 920^2$$

$$552^2 + 986^2 := 1130^2$$

$$552^2 + 1035^2 := 1173^2$$

$$552^2 + 1539^2 := 1635^2$$

$$552^2 + 1610^2 := 1702^2$$

$$552^2 + 2080^2 := 2152^2$$

$$552^2 + 3150^2 := 3198^2$$

$$552^2 + 3289^2 := 3335^2$$

$$552^2 + 4214^2 := 4250^2$$

$$552^2 + 4745^2 := 4777^2$$

$$552^2 + 6336^2 := 6360^2$$

$$552^2 + 8455^2 := 8473^2$$

$$552^2 + 9514^2 := 9530^2$$

$$552^2 + 12690^2 := 12702^2$$

$$552^2 + 19040^2 := 19048^2$$

$$552^2 + 25389^2 := 25395^2$$

$$552^2 + 38086^2 := 38090^2$$

$$552^2 + 76175^2 := 76177^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(552, 9514, 9530)** $\Rightarrow 9530 - 9514 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 76176$, $T_{16} := 552^2$,
 $E := \{19029, 19031, \dots, 19057, 19059\}$

2. **(552, 4214, 4250)** $\Rightarrow 4250 - 4214 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 50784$, $T_{36} := 552^2$,
 $E := \{8429, 8431, \dots, 8497, 8499\}$
3. **(552, 986, 1130)** $\Rightarrow 1130 - 986 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 25392$, $T_{144} := 552^2$,
 $E := \{1973, 1975, \dots, 2257, 2259\}$
4. **(552, 2080, 2152)** $\Rightarrow 2152 - 552 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 108160$, $T_{1600} := 2080^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 4301, 4303\}$
5. **(552, 4745, 4777)** $\Rightarrow 4777 - 552 = 65^2$, $S_{65 \times 65} := 346385$, $T_{4225} := 4745^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 9551, 9553\}$ or $E := \{3217, 3218, \dots, 7440, 7441\}$
6. **(552, 8455, 8473)** $\Rightarrow 8473 - 552 = 89^2$, $S_{89 \times 89} := 803225$, $T_{7921} := 8455^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 16943, 16945\}$ or $E := \{5065, 5066, \dots, 12984, 12985\}$
7. **(552, 19040, 19048)** $\Rightarrow 19048 - 552 = 136^2$, $S_{136 \times 136} := 2665600$, $T_{18496} := 19040^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 38093, 38095\}$
8. **(552, 76175, 76177)** $\Rightarrow 76177 - 552 = 275^2$, $S_{275 \times 275} := 21100475$, $T_{75625} := 76175^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 152351, 152353\}$ or $E := \{38917, 38918, \dots, 114540, 114541\}$

■ Number 553

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$553^2 + 1896^2 := 1975^2$$

$$553^2 + 3096^2 := 3145^2$$

$$553^2 + 21840^2 := 21847^2$$

$$553^2 + 152904^2 := 152905^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(553, 3096, 3145)** $\Rightarrow 3145 - 3096 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 43687$, $T_{49} := 553^2$,
 $E := \{6193, 6195, \dots, 6287, 6289\}$ or $E := \{6217, 6218, \dots, 6264, 6265\}$

■ Number 554

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$554^2 + 76728^2 := 76730^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(554, 76728, 76730)** $\Rightarrow 76730 - 554 = 276^2$, $S_{276 \times 276} := 21330384$, $T_{76176} := 76728^2$,
 $E := \{1109, 1111, \dots, 153457, 153459\}$

■ Number 555

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$555^2 + 572^2 := 797^2$$

$$555^2 + 740^2 := 925^2$$

$$555^2 + 1332^2 := 1443^2$$

$$555^2 + 2016^2 := 2091^2$$

$$555^2 + 3400^2 := 3445^2$$

$$555^2 + 4144^2 := 4181^2$$

$$555^2 + 6148^2 := 6173^2$$

$$555^2 + 10260^2 := 10275^2$$

$$555^2 + 17108^2 := 17117^2$$

$$555^2 + 30800^2 := 30805^2$$

$$555^2 + 51336^2 := 51339^2$$

$$555^2 + 154012^2 := 154013^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(555, 6148, 6173)** $\Rightarrow 6173 - 6148 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 61605$, $T_{25} := 555^2$,
 $E := \{12297, 12299, \dots, 12343, 12345\}$ or $E := \{12309, 12310, \dots, 12332, 12333\}$
2. **(555, 17108, 17117)** $\Rightarrow 17117 - 17108 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 102675$, $T_9 := 555^2$,
 $E := \{34217, 34219, \dots, 34231, 34233\}$ or $E := \{34221, 34222, \dots, 34228, 34229\}$
3. **(555, 572, 797)** $\Rightarrow 797 - 572 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 20535$, $T_{225} := 555^2$,
 $E := \{1145, 1147, \dots, 1591, 1593\}$ or $E := \{1257, 1258, \dots, 1480, 1481\}$

■ Number 556

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$556^2 + 19317^2 := 19325^2$$

$$556^2 + 38640^2 := 38644^2$$

$$556^2 + 77283^2 := 77285^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(556, 19317, 19325)** $\Rightarrow 19325 - 556 = 137^2$, $S_{137 \times 137} := 2723697$, $T_{18769} := 19317^2$,
 $E := \{1113, 1115, \dots, 38647, 38649\}$ or $E := \{10497, 10498, \dots, 29264, 29265\}$
2. **(556, 77283, 77285)** $\Rightarrow 77285 - 556 = 277^2$, $S_{277 \times 277} := 21561957$, $T_{76729} := 77283^2$,
 $E := \{1113, 1115, \dots, 154567, 154569\}$ or $E := \{39477, 39478, \dots, 116204, 116205\}$

■ Number 557

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$557^2 + 155124^2 := 155125^2$$

■ Number 558

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$558^2 + 744^2 := 930^2$$

$$558^2 + 880^2 := 1042^2$$

$$558^2 + 2480^2 := 2542^2$$

$$558^2 + 2856^2 := 2910^2$$

$$558^2 + 8640^2 := 8658^2$$

$$558^2 + 25944^2 := 25950^2$$

$$558^2 + 77840^2 := 77842^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(558, 880, 1042)** $\Rightarrow 1042 - 558 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 35200$, $T_{484} := 880^2$,
 $E := \{1117, 1119, \dots, 2081, 2083\}$

2. **(558, 8640, 8658)** $\Rightarrow 8658 - 558 = 90^2$, $S_{90 \times 90} := 829440$, $T_{8100} := 8640^2$,
 $E := \{1117, 1119, \dots, 17313, 17315\}$

3. **(558, 77840, 77842)** $\Rightarrow 77842 - 558 = 278^2$, $S_{278 \times 278} := 21795200$, $T_{77284} := 77840^2$,
 $E := \{1117, 1119, \dots, 155681, 155683\}$

■ Number 559

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$559^2 + 840^2 := 1009^2$$

$$559^2 + 3612^2 := 3655^2$$

$$559^2 + 12012^2 := 12025^2$$

$$559^2 + 156240^2 := 156241^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(559, 840, 1009)** $\Rightarrow 1009 - 840 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 24037$, $T_{169} := 559^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 2015, 2017\}$ or $E := \{1765, 1766, \dots, 1932, 1933\}$

■ Number 560

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$560^2 + 588^2 := 812^2$$

$$560^2 + 684^2 := 884^2$$

$$560^2 + 702^2 := 898^2$$

$$560^2 + 900^2 := 1060^2$$

$$560^2 + 1050^2 := 1190^2$$

$$560^2 + 1161^2 := 1289^2$$

$$560^2 + 1344^2 := 1456^2$$

$$560^2 + 1518^2 := 1618^2$$

$$560^2 + 1551^2 := 1649^2$$

$$560^2 + 1920^2 := 2000^2$$

$$560^2 + 2205^2 := 2275^2$$

$$560^2 + 2418^2 := 2482^2$$

$$560^2 + 2772^2 := 2828^2$$

$$560^2 + 3111^2 := 3161^2$$

$$560^2 + 3900^2 := 3940^2$$

$$560^2 + 4884^2 := 4916^2$$

$$560^2 + 5586^2 := 5614^2$$

$$560^2 + 7830^2 := 7850^2$$

$$560^2 + 9792^2 := 9808^2$$

$$560^2 + 11193^2 := 11207^2$$

$$560^2 + 15675^2 := 15685^2$$

$$560^2 + 19596^2 := 19604^2$$

$$560^2 + 39198^2 := 39202^2$$

$$560^2 + 78399^2 := 78401^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(560, 9792, 9808)** $\Rightarrow 9808 - 9792 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 78400$, $T_{16} := 560^2$,
 $E := \{19585, 19587, \dots, 19613, 19615\}$
2. **(560, 2418, 2482)** $\Rightarrow 2482 - 2418 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 39200$, $T_{64} := 560^2$,
 $E := \{4837, 4839, \dots, 4961, 4963\}$
3. **(560, 1518, 1618)** $\Rightarrow 1618 - 1518 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 31360$, $T_{100} := 560^2$,
 $E := \{3037, 3039, \dots, 3233, 3235\}$
4. **(560, 702, 898)** $\Rightarrow 898 - 702 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 22400$, $T_{196} := 560^2$,
 $E := \{1405, 1407, \dots, 1793, 1795\}$
5. **(560, 684, 884)** $\Rightarrow 884 - 560 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 25992$, $T_{324} := 684^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 1765, 1767\}$
6. **(560, 1161, 1289)** $\Rightarrow 1289 - 560 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 49923$, $T_{729} := 1161^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 2575, 2577\}$ or $E := \{1485, 1486, \dots, 2212, 2213\}$
7. **(560, 1551, 1649)** $\Rightarrow 1649 - 560 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 72897$, $T_{1089} := 1551^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 3295, 3297\}$ or $E := \{1665, 1666, \dots, 2752, 2753\}$
8. **(560, 19596, 19604)** $\Rightarrow 19604 - 560 = 138^2$, $S_{138 \times 138} := 2782632$, $T_{19044} := 19596^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 39205, 39207\}$
9. **(560, 3111, 3161)** $\Rightarrow 3161 - 560 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 189771$, $T_{2601} := 3111^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 6319, 6321\}$ or $E := \{2421, 2422, \dots, 5020, 5021\}$
10. **(560, 4884, 4916)** $\Rightarrow 4916 - 560 = 66^2$, $S_{66 \times 66} := 361416$, $T_{4356} := 4884^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 9829, 9831\}$
11. **(560, 78399, 78401)** $\Rightarrow 78401 - 560 = 279^2$, $S_{279 \times 279} := 22030119$, $T_{77841} := 78399^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 156799, 156801\}$ or $E := \{40041, 40042, \dots, 117880, 117881\}$

■ Number 561

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$561^2 + 748^2 := 935^2$$

$$561^2 + 952^2 := 1105^2$$

$$561^2 + 1240^2 := 1361^2$$

$$561^2 + 1540^2 := 1639^2$$

$$561^2 + 3060^2 := 3111^2$$

$$561^2 + 4752^2 := 4785^2$$

$$561^2 + 9248^2 := 9265^2$$

$$561^2 + 14300^2 := 14311^2$$

$$561^2 + 17480^2 := 17489^2$$

$$561^2 + 52452^2 := 52455^2$$

$$561^2 + 157360^2 := 157361^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(561, 17480, 17489)** $\Rightarrow 17489 - 17480 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 104907$, $T_9 := 561^2$,
 $E := \{34961, 34963, \dots, 34975, 34977\}$ or $E := \{34965, 34966, \dots, 34972, 34973\}$
2. **(561, 1240, 1361)** $\Rightarrow 1361 - 1240 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 28611$, $T_{121} := 561^2$,
 $E := \{2481, 2483, \dots, 2719, 2721\}$ or $E := \{2541, 2542, \dots, 2660, 2661\}$

■ Number 562

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$562^2 + 78960^2 := 78962^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(562, 78960, 78962)** $\Rightarrow 78962 - 562 = 280^2$, $S_{280 \times 280} := 22266720$, $T_{78400} := 78960^2$,
 $E := \{1125, 1127, \dots, 157921, 157923\}$

■ Number 563

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$563^2 + 158484^2 := 158485^2$$

■ Number 564

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$564^2 + 752^2 := 940^2$$

$$564^2 + 1645^2 := 1739^2$$

$$564^2 + 2173^2 := 2245^2$$

$$564^2 + 4400^2 := 4436^2$$

$$564^2 + 6615^2 := 6639^2$$

$$564^2 + 8827^2 := 8845^2$$

$$564^2 + 13248^2 := 13260^2$$

$$564^2 + 19877^2 := 19885^2$$

$$564^2 + 26505^2 := 26511^2$$

$$564^2 + 39760^2 := 39764^2$$

$$564^2 + 79523^2 := 79525^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(564, 4400, 4436)** $\Rightarrow 4436 - 4400 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 53016$, $T_{36} := 564^2$,
 $E := \{8801, 8803, \dots, 8869, 8871\}$
2. **(564, 2173, 2245)** $\Rightarrow 2245 - 564 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 115169$, $T_{1681} := 2173^2$,
 $E := \{1129, 1131, \dots, 4487, 4489\}$ or $E := \{1969, 1970, \dots, 3648, 3649\}$
3. **(564, 8827, 8845)** $\Rightarrow 8845 - 564 = 91^2$, $S_{91 \times 91} := 856219$, $T_{8281} := 8827^2$,
 $E := \{1129, 1131, \dots, 17687, 17689\}$ or $E := \{5269, 5270, \dots, 13548, 13549\}$
4. **(564, 19877, 19885)** $\Rightarrow 19885 - 564 = 139^2$, $S_{139 \times 139} := 2842411$, $T_{19321} := 19877^2$,
 $E := \{1129, 1131, \dots, 39767, 39769\}$ or $E := \{10789, 10790, \dots, 30108, 30109\}$
5. **(564, 79523, 79525)** $\Rightarrow 79525 - 564 = 281^2$, $S_{281 \times 281} := 22505009$, $T_{78961} := 79523^2$,
 $E := \{1129, 1131, \dots, 159047, 159049\}$ or $E := \{40609, 40610, \dots, 119568, 119569\}$

■ Number 565

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$565^2 + 1356^2 := 1469^2$$

$$565^2 + 6372^2 := 6397^2$$

$$565^2 + 31920^2 := 31925^2$$

$$565^2 + 159612^2 := 159613^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(565, 6372, 6397)** $\Rightarrow 6397 - 6372 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 63845$, $T_{25} := 565^2$,
 $E := \{12745, 12747, \dots, 12791, 12793\}$ or $E := \{12757, 12758, \dots, 12780, 12781\}$

■ Number 566

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$566^2 + 80088^2 := 80090^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(566, 80088, 80090)** $\Rightarrow 80090 - 566 = 282^2$, $S_{282 \times 282} := 22744992$, $T_{79524} := 80088^2$,
 $E := \{1133, 1135, \dots, 160177, 160179\}$

■ Number 567

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$567^2 + 756^2 := 945^2$$

$$567^2 + 1020^2 := 1167^2$$

$$567^2 + 1944^2 := 2025^2$$

$$567^2 + 2520^2 := 2583^2$$

$$567^2 + 3256^2 := 3305^2$$

$$567^2 + 5940^2 := 5967^2$$

$$567^2 + 7644^2 := 7665^2$$

$$567^2 + 17856^2 := 17865^2$$

$$567^2 + 22960^2 := 22967^2$$

$$567^2 + 53580^2 := 53583^2$$

$$567^2 + 160744^2 := 160745^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(567, 17856, 17865)** $\Rightarrow 17865 - 17856 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 107163$, $T_9 := 567^2$,
 $E := \{35713, 35715, \dots, 35727, 35729\}$ or $E := \{35717, 35718, \dots, 35724, 35725\}$
2. **(567, 3256, 3305)** $\Rightarrow 3305 - 3256 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 45927$, $T_{49} := 567^2$,
 $E := \{6513, 6515, \dots, 6607, 6609\}$ or $E := \{6537, 6538, \dots, 6584, 6585\}$
3. **(567, 1944, 2025)** $\Rightarrow 2025 - 1944 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 35721$, $T_{81} := 567^2$,
 $E := \{3889, 3891, \dots, 4047, 4049\}$ or $E := \{3929, 3930, \dots, 4008, 4009\}$

■ Number 568

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$568^2 + 1065^2 := 1207^2$$

$$568^2 + 5025^2 := 5057^2$$

$$568^2 + 10074^2 := 10090^2$$

$$568^2 + 20160^2 := 20168^2$$

$$568^2 + 40326^2 := 40330^2$$

$$568^2 + 80655^2 := 80657^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(568, 10074, 10090)** $\Rightarrow 10090 - 10074 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 80656$, $T_{16} := 568^2$,
 $E := \{20149, 20151, \dots, 20177, 20179\}$
2. **(568, 5025, 5057)** $\Rightarrow 5057 - 568 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 376875$, $T_{4489} := 5025^2$,
 $E := \{1137, 1139, \dots, 10111, 10113\}$ or $E := \{3381, 3382, \dots, 7868, 7869\}$
3. **(568, 20160, 20168)** $\Rightarrow 20168 - 568 = 140^2$, $S_{140 \times 140} := 2903040$, $T_{19600} := 20160^2$,
 $E := \{1137, 1139, \dots, 40333, 40335\}$
4. **(568, 80655, 80657)** $\Rightarrow 80657 - 568 = 283^2$, $S_{283 \times 283} := 22986675$, $T_{80089} := 80655^2$,
 $E := \{1137, 1139, \dots, 161311, 161313\}$ or $E := \{41181, 41182, \dots, 121268, 121269\}$

■ Number 569

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$569^2 + 161880^2 := 161881^2$$

■ Number 570

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$570^2 + 760^2 := 950^2$$

$$570^2 + 1008^2 := 1158^2$$

$$570^2 + 1368^2 := 1482^2$$

$$570^2 + 1760^2 := 1850^2$$

$$570^2 + 3224^2 := 3274^2$$

$$570^2 + 4256^2 := 4294^2$$

$$570^2 + 5400^2 := 5430^2$$

$$570^2 + 9016^2 := 9034^2$$

$$570^2 + 16240^2 := 16250^2$$

$$570^2 + 27072^2 := 27078^2$$

$$570^2 + 81224^2 := 81226^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(570, 3224, 3274)** $\Rightarrow 3274 - 570 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 199888$, $T_{2704} := 3224^2$,
 $E := \{1141, 1143, \dots, 6545, 6547\}$

2. **(570, 9016, 9034)** $\Rightarrow 9034 - 570 = 92^2$, $S_{92 \times 92} := 883568$, $T_{8464} := 9016^2$,
 $E := \{1141, 1143, \dots, 18065, 18067\}$

3. **(570, 81224, 81226)** $\Rightarrow 81226 - 570 = 284^2$, $S_{284 \times 284} := 23230064$, $T_{80656} := 81224^2$,
 $E := \{1141, 1143, \dots, 162449, 162451\}$

■ Number 571

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$571^2 + 163020^2 := 163021^2$$

■ Number 572

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$572^2 + 1521^2 := 1625^2$$

$$572^2 + 1815^2 := 1903^2$$

$$572^2 + 3120^2 := 3172^2$$

$$572^2 + 3696^2 := 3740^2$$

$$572^2 + 6279^2 := 6305^2$$

$$572^2 + 7425^2 := 7447^2$$

$$572^2 + 20445^2 := 20453^2$$

$$572^2 + 40896^2 := 40900^2$$

$$572^2 + 81795^2 := 81797^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(572, 20445, 20453)** $\Rightarrow 20453 - 572 = 141^2$, $S_{141 \times 141} := 2964525$, $T_{19881} := 20445^2$,
 $E := \{1145, 1147, \dots, 40903, 40905\}$ or $E := \{11085, 11086, \dots, 30964, 30965\}$

2. **(572, 81795, 81797)** $\Rightarrow 81797 - 572 = 285^2$, $S_{285 \times 285} := 23475165$, $T_{81225} := 81795^2$,
 $E := \{1145, 1147, \dots, 163591, 163593\}$ or $E := \{41757, 41758, \dots, 122980, 122981\}$

■ Number 573

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$573^2 + 764^2 := 955^2$$

$$573^2 + 18236^2 := 18245^2$$

$$573^2 + 54720^2 := 54723^2$$

$$573^2 + 164164^2 := 164165^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

• **(573, 18236, 18245)** $\Rightarrow 18245 - 18236 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 109443$, $T_9 := 573^2$,
 $E := \{36473, 36475, \dots, 36487, 36489\}$ or $E := \{36477, 36478, \dots, 36484, 36485\}$

■ Number 574

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$574^2 + 1632^2 := 1730^2$$

$$574^2 + 1968^2 := 2050^2$$

$$574^2 + 11760^2 := 11774^2$$

$$574^2 + 82368^2 := 82370^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(574, 1632, 1730)** $\Rightarrow 1730 - 574 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 78336$, $T_{1156} := 1632^2$,
 $E := \{1149, 1151, \dots, 3457, 3459\}$

2. **(574, 82368, 82370)** $\Rightarrow 82370 - 574 = 286^2$, $S_{286 \times 286} := 23721984$, $T_{81796} := 82368^2$,
 $E := \{1149, 1151, \dots, 164737, 164739\}$

■ Number 575

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned} 575^2 + 1260^2 &:= 1385^2 \\ 575^2 + 1380^2 &:= 1495^2 \\ 575^2 + 6600^2 &:= 6625^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 575^2 + 7176^2 &:= 7199^2 \\ 575^2 + 33060^2 &:= 33065^2 \\ 575^2 + 165312^2 &:= 165313^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(575, 6600, 6625)** $\Rightarrow 6625 - 6600 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 66125$, $T_{25} := 575^2$,
 $E := \{13201, 13203, \dots, 13247, 13249\}$ or $E := \{13213, 13214, \dots, 13236, 13237\}$

■ Number 576

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$576^2 + 660^2 := 876^2$	$576^2 + 2268^2 := 2340^2$	$576^2 + 9207^2 := 9225^2$
$576^2 + 768^2 := 960^2$	$576^2 + 2560^2 := 2624^2$	$576^2 + 10360^2 := 10376^2$
$576^2 + 943^2 := 1105^2$	$576^2 + 3045^2 := 3099^2$	$576^2 + 13818^2 := 13830^2$
$576^2 + 1080^2 := 1224^2$	$576^2 + 3432^2 := 3480^2$	$576^2 + 20732^2 := 20740^2$
$576^2 + 1232^2 := 1360^2$	$576^2 + 4590^2 := 4626^2$	$576^2 + 27645^2 := 27651^2$
$576^2 + 1482^2 := 1590^2$	$576^2 + 5168^2 := 5200^2$	$576^2 + 41470^2 := 41474^2$
$576^2 + 1680^2 := 1776^2$	$576^2 + 6900^2 := 6924^2$	$576^2 + 82943^2 := 82945^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(576, 10360, 10376)** $\Rightarrow 10376 - 10360 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 82944$, $T_{16} := 576^2$,
 $E := \{20721, 20723, \dots, 20749, 20751\}$
2. **(576, 4590, 4626)** $\Rightarrow 4626 - 4590 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 55296$, $T_{36} := 576^2$,
 $E := \{9181, 9183, \dots, 9249, 9251\}$
3. **(576, 2560, 2624)** $\Rightarrow 2624 - 2560 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 41472$, $T_{64} := 576^2$,
 $E := \{5121, 5123, \dots, 5245, 5247\}$
4. **(576, 1080, 1224)** $\Rightarrow 1224 - 1080 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 27648$, $T_{144} := 576^2$,
 $E := \{2161, 2163, \dots, 2445, 2447\}$
5. **(576, 943, 1105)** $\Rightarrow 1105 - 576 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 38663$, $T_{529} := 943^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 2207, 2209\}$ or $E := \{1417, 1418, \dots, 1944, 1945\}$
6. **(576, 1232, 1360)** $\Rightarrow 1360 - 576 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 54208$, $T_{784} := 1232^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 2717, 2719\}$
7. **(576, 2268, 2340)** $\Rightarrow 2340 - 576 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 122472$, $T_{1764} := 2268^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 4677, 4679\}$

8. **(576, 5168, 5200)** $\Rightarrow 5200 - 576 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 392768$, $T_{4624} := 5168^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 10397, 10399\}$
9. **(576, 9207, 9225)** $\Rightarrow 9225 - 576 = 93^2$, $S_{93 \times 93} := 911493$, $T_{8649} := 9207^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 18447, 18449\}$ or $E := \{5477, 5478, \dots, 14124, 14125\}$
10. **(576, 20732, 20740)** $\Rightarrow 20740 - 576 = 142^2$, $S_{142 \times 142} := 3026872$, $T_{20164} := 20732^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 41477, 41479\}$
11. **(576, 82943, 82945)** $\Rightarrow 82945 - 576 = 287^2$, $S_{287 \times 287} := 23970527$, $T_{82369} := 82943^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 165887, 165889\}$ or $E := \{42337, 42338, \dots, 124704, 124705\}$

■ Number 577

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$577^2 + 166464^2 := 166465^2$$

■ Number 578

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$578^2 + 4896^2 := 4930^2$$

$$578^2 + 83520^2 := 83522^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(578, 83520, 83522)** $\Rightarrow 83522 - 578 = 288^2$, $S_{288 \times 288} := 24220800$, $T_{82944} := 83520^2$,
 $E := \{1157, 1159, \dots, 167041, 167043\}$

■ Number 579

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$579^2 + 772^2 := 965^2$$

$$579^2 + 18620^2 := 18629^2$$

$$579^2 + 55872^2 := 55875^2$$

$$579^2 + 167620^2 := 167621^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(579, 18620, 18629)** $\Rightarrow 18629 - 18620 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 111747$, $T_9 := 579^2$,
 $E := \{37241, 37243, \dots, 37255, 37257\}$ or $E := \{37245, 37246, \dots, 37252, 37253\}$

■ Number 580

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$580^2 + 609^2 := 841^2$	$580^2 + 2871^2 := 2929^2$	$580^2 + 16815^2 := 16825^2$
$580^2 + 741^2 := 941^2$	$580^2 + 3339^2 := 3389^2$	$580^2 + 21021^2 := 21029^2$
$580^2 + 1392^2 := 1508^2$	$580^2 + 4185^2 := 4225^2$	$580^2 + 42048^2 := 42052^2$
$580^2 + 1632^2 := 1732^2$	$580^2 + 8400^2 := 8420^2$	$580^2 + 84099^2 := 84101^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(580, 1632, 1732)** $\Rightarrow 1732 - 1632 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 33640$, $T_{100} := 580^2$,
 $E := \{3265, 3267, \dots, 3461, 3463\}$
2. **(580, 741, 941)** $\Rightarrow 941 - 580 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 28899$, $T_{361} := 741^2$,
 $E := \{1161, 1163, \dots, 1879, 1881\}$ or $E := \{1341, 1342, \dots, 1700, 1701\}$
3. **(580, 3339, 3389)** $\Rightarrow 3389 - 580 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 210357$, $T_{2809} := 3339^2$,
 $E := \{1161, 1163, \dots, 6775, 6777\}$ or $E := \{2565, 2566, \dots, 5372, 5373\}$
4. **(580, 21021, 21029)** $\Rightarrow 21029 - 580 = 143^2$, $S_{143 \times 143} := 3090087$, $T_{20449} := 21021^2$,
 $E := \{1161, 1163, \dots, 42055, 42057\}$ or $E := \{11385, 11386, \dots, 31832, 31833\}$
5. **(580, 84099, 84101)** $\Rightarrow 84101 - 580 = 289^2$, $S_{289 \times 289} := 24472809$, $T_{83521} := 84099^2$,
 $E := \{1161, 1163, \dots, 168199, 168201\}$ or $E := \{42921, 42922, \dots, 126440, 126441\}$

■ Number 581

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$581^2 + 1992^2 := 2075^2$	$581^2 + 24108^2 := 24115^2$
$581^2 + 3420^2 := 3469^2$	$581^2 + 168780^2 := 168781^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(581, 3420, 3469)** $\Rightarrow 3469 - 3420 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 48223$, $T_{49} := 581^2$,
 $E := \{6841, 6843, \dots, 6935, 6937\}$ or $E := \{6865, 6866, \dots, 6912, 6913\}$

■ Number 582

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$582^2 + 776^2 := 970^2$$

$$582^2 + 9400^2 := 9418^2$$

$$582^2 + 28224^2 := 28230^2$$

$$582^2 + 84680^2 := 84682^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(582, 9400, 9418)** $\Rightarrow 9418 - 582 = 94^2$, $S_{94 \times 94} := 940000$, $T_{8836} := 9400^2$,
 $E := \{1165, 1167, \dots, 18833, 18835\}$

2. **(582, 84680, 84682)** $\Rightarrow 84682 - 582 = 290^2$, $S_{290 \times 290} := 24726560$, $T_{84100} := 84680^2$,
 $E := \{1165, 1167, \dots, 169361, 169363\}$

■ Number 583

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$583^2 + 1344^2 := 1465^2$$

$$583^2 + 3180^2 := 3233^2$$

$$583^2 + 15444^2 := 15455^2$$

$$583^2 + 169944^2 := 169945^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(583, 1344, 1465)** $\Rightarrow 1465 - 1344 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 30899$, $T_{121} := 583^2$,
 $E := \{2689, 2691, \dots, 2927, 2929\}$ or $E := \{2749, 2750, \dots, 2868, 2869\}$

■ Number 584

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$584^2 + 1095^2 := 1241^2$$

$$584^2 + 5313^2 := 5345^2$$

$$584^2 + 10650^2 := 10666^2$$

$$584^2 + 21312^2 := 21320^2$$

$$584^2 + 42630^2 := 42634^2$$

$$584^2 + 85263^2 := 85265^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(584, 10650, 10666)** $\Rightarrow 10666 - 10650 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 85264$, $T_{16} := 584^2$,
 $E := \{21301, 21303, \dots, 21329, 21331\}$

2. **(584, 5313, 5345)** $\Rightarrow 5345 - 584 = 69^2$, $S_{69 \times 69} := 409101$, $T_{4761} := 5313^2$,
 $E := \{1169, 1171, \dots, 10687, 10689\}$ or $E := \{3549, 3550, \dots, 8308, 8309\}$
3. **(584, 21312, 21320)** $\Rightarrow 21320 - 584 = 144^2$, $S_{144 \times 144} := 3154176$, $T_{20736} := 21312^2$,
 $E := \{1169, 1171, \dots, 42637, 42639\}$
4. **(584, 85263, 85265)** $\Rightarrow 85265 - 584 = 291^2$, $S_{291 \times 291} := 24982059$, $T_{84681} := 85263^2$,
 $E := \{1169, 1171, \dots, 170527, 170529\}$ or $E := \{43509, 43510, \dots, 128188, 128189\}$

■ Number 585

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$585^2 + 648^2 := 873^2$$

$$585^2 + 780^2 := 975^2$$

$$585^2 + 928^2 := 1097^2$$

$$585^2 + 1200^2 := 1335^2$$

$$585^2 + 1404^2 := 1521^2$$

$$585^2 + 2072^2 := 2153^2$$

$$585^2 + 2244^2 := 2319^2$$

$$585^2 + 2600^2 := 2665^2$$

$$585^2 + 3780^2 := 3825^2$$

$$585^2 + 4368^2 := 4407^2$$

$$585^2 + 6324^2 := 6351^2$$

$$585^2 + 6832^2 := 6857^2$$

$$585^2 + 11400^2 := 11415^2$$

$$585^2 + 13156^2 := 13169^2$$

$$585^2 + 19008^2 := 19017^2$$

$$585^2 + 34220^2 := 34225^2$$

$$585^2 + 57036^2 := 57039^2$$

$$585^2 + 171112^2 := 171113^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(585, 19008, 19017)** $\Rightarrow 19017 - 19008 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 114075$, $T_9 := 585^2$,
 $E := \{38017, 38019, \dots, 38031, 38033\}$ or $E := \{38021, 38022, \dots, 38028, 38029\}$
2. **(585, 6832, 6857)** $\Rightarrow 6857 - 6832 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 68445$, $T_{25} := 585^2$,
 $E := \{13665, 13667, \dots, 13711, 13713\}$ or $E := \{13677, 13678, \dots, 13700, 13701\}$
3. **(585, 2072, 2153)** $\Rightarrow 2153 - 2072 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 38025$, $T_{81} := 585^2$,
 $E := \{4145, 4147, \dots, 4303, 4305\}$ or $E := \{4185, 4186, \dots, 4264, 4265\}$
4. **(585, 928, 1097)** $\Rightarrow 1097 - 928 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 26325$, $T_{169} := 585^2$,
 $E := \{1857, 1859, \dots, 2191, 2193\}$ or $E := \{1941, 1942, \dots, 2108, 2109\}$
5. **(585, 648, 873)** $\Rightarrow 873 - 648 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 22815$, $T_{225} := 585^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 1743, 1745\}$ or $E := \{1409, 1410, \dots, 1632, 1633\}$

■ Number 586

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$586^2 + 85848^2 := 85850^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(586, 85848, 85850)** $\Rightarrow 85850 - 586 = 292^2$, $S_{292 \times 292} := 25239312$, $T_{85264} := 85848^2$,
 $E := \{1173, 1175, \dots, 171697, 171699\}$

■ Number 587

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$587^2 + 172284^2 := 172285^2$$

■ Number 588

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$588^2 + 784^2 := 980^2$$

$$588^2 + 945^2 := 1113^2$$

$$588^2 + 1309^2 := 1435^2$$

$$588^2 + 1715^2 := 1813^2$$

$$588^2 + 2016^2 := 2100^2$$

$$588^2 + 2365^2 := 2437^2$$

$$588^2 + 3059^2 := 3115^2$$

$$588^2 + 4095^2 := 4137^2$$

$$588^2 + 4784^2 := 4820^2$$

$$588^2 + 6160^2 := 6188^2$$

$$588^2 + 7191^2 := 7215^2$$

$$588^2 + 9595^2 := 9613^2$$

$$588^2 + 12341^2 := 12355^2$$

$$588^2 + 14400^2 := 14412^2$$

$$588^2 + 21605^2 := 21613^2$$

$$588^2 + 28809^2 := 28815^2$$

$$588^2 + 43216^2 := 43220^2$$

$$588^2 + 86435^2 := 86437^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(588, 4784, 4820)** $\Rightarrow 4820 - 4784 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 57624$, $T_{36} := 588^2$,
 $E := \{9569, 9571, \dots, 9637, 9639\}$
2. **(588, 784, 980)** $\Rightarrow 980 - 784 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 24696$, $T_{196} := 588^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 1957, 1959\}$
3. **(588, 1715, 1813)** $\Rightarrow 1813 - 588 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 84035$, $T_{1225} := 1715^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 3623, 3625\}$ or $E := \{1789, 1790, \dots, 3012, 3013\}$
4. **(588, 2365, 2437)** $\Rightarrow 2437 - 588 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 130075$, $T_{1849} := 2365^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 4871, 4873\}$ or $E := \{2101, 2102, \dots, 3948, 3949\}$
5. **(588, 9595, 9613)** $\Rightarrow 9613 - 588 = 95^2$, $S_{95 \times 95} := 969095$, $T_{9025} := 9595^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 19223, 19225\}$ or $E := \{5689, 5690, \dots, 14712, 14713\}$
6. **(588, 21605, 21613)** $\Rightarrow 21613 - 588 = 145^2$, $S_{145 \times 145} := 3219145$, $T_{21025} := 21605^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 43223, 43225\}$ or $E := \{11689, 11690, \dots, 32712, 32713\}$
7. **(588, 86435, 86437)** $\Rightarrow 86437 - 588 = 293^2$, $S_{293 \times 293} := 25498325$, $T_{85849} := 86435^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 172871, 172873\}$ or $E := \{44101, 44102, \dots, 129948, 129949\}$

■ Number 589

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$589^2 + 5580^2 := 5611^2$$

$$589^2 + 9120^2 := 9139^2$$

$$589^2 + 173460^2 := 173461^2$$

■ Number 590

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$590^2 + 1416^2 := 1534^2$$

$$590^2 + 3456^2 := 3506^2$$

$$590^2 + 17400^2 := 17410^2$$

$$590^2 + 87024^2 := 87026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(590, 3456, 3506)** $\Rightarrow 3506 - 590 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 221184$, $T_{2916} := 3456^2$,
 $E := \{1181, 1183, \dots, 7009, 7011\}$

2. **(590, 87024, 87026)** $\Rightarrow 87026 - 590 = 294^2$, $S_{294 \times 294} := 25759104$, $T_{86436} := 87024^2$,
 $E := \{1181, 1183, \dots, 174049, 174051\}$

■ Number 591

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$591^2 + 788^2 := 985^2$$

$$591^2 + 19400^2 := 19409^2$$

$$591^2 + 58212^2 := 58215^2$$

$$591^2 + 174640^2 := 174641^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(591, 19400, 19409)** $\Rightarrow 19409 - 19400 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 116427$, $T_9 := 591^2$,
 $E := \{38801, 38803, \dots, 38815, 38817\}$ or $E := \{38805, 38806, \dots, 38812, 38813\}$

■ Number 592

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 592^2 + 1110^2 := 1258^2 & 592^2 + 2706^2 := 2770^2 & 592^2 + 21900^2 := 21908^2 \\
 592^2 + 1305^2 := 1433^2 & 592^2 + 5460^2 := 5492^2 & 592^2 + 43806^2 := 43810^2 \\
 592^2 + 2331^2 := 2405^2 & 592^2 + 10944^2 := 10960^2 & 592^2 + 87615^2 := 87617^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(592, 10944, 10960)** $\Rightarrow 10960 - 10944 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 87616$, $T_{16} := 592^2$,
 $E := \{21889, 21891, \dots, 21917, 21919\}$
2. **(592, 2706, 2770)** $\Rightarrow 2770 - 2706 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 43808$, $T_{64} := 592^2$,
 $E := \{5413, 5415, \dots, 5537, 5539\}$
3. **(592, 1305, 1433)** $\Rightarrow 1433 - 592 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 58725$, $T_{841} := 1305^2$,
 $E := \{1185, 1187, \dots, 2863, 2865\}$ or $E := \{1605, 1606, \dots, 2444, 2445\}$
4. **(592, 5460, 5492)** $\Rightarrow 5492 - 592 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 425880$, $T_{4900} := 5460^2$,
 $E := \{1185, 1187, \dots, 10981, 10983\}$
5. **(592, 21900, 21908)** $\Rightarrow 21908 - 592 = 146^2$, $S_{146 \times 146} := 3285000$, $T_{21316} := 21900^2$,
 $E := \{1185, 1187, \dots, 43813, 43815\}$
6. **(592, 87615, 87617)** $\Rightarrow 87617 - 592 = 295^2$, $S_{295 \times 295} := 26021655$, $T_{87025} := 87615^2$,
 $E := \{1185, 1187, \dots, 175231, 175233\}$ or $E := \{44697, 44698, \dots, 131720, 131721\}$

■ **Number 593**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$593^2 + 175824^2 := 175825^2$$

■ **Number 594**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 594^2 + 608^2 := 850^2 & 594^2 + 2640^2 := 2706^2 & 594^2 + 9792^2 := 9810^2 \\
 594^2 + 792^2 := 990^2 & 594^2 + 3240^2 := 3294^2 & 594^2 + 29400^2 := 29406^2 \\
 594^2 + 1008^2 := 1170^2 & 594^2 + 8008^2 := 8030^2 & 594^2 + 88208^2 := 88210^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(594, 608, 850)** $\Rightarrow 850 - 594 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 23104$, $T_{256} := 608^2$,
 $E := \{1189, 1191, \dots, 1697, 1699\}$

2. **(594, 1008, 1170)** $\Rightarrow 1170 - 594 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 42336$, $T_{576} := 1008^2$,
 $E := \{1189, 1191, \dots, 2337, 2339\}$
3. **(594, 9792, 9810)** $\Rightarrow 9810 - 594 = 96^2$, $S_{96 \times 96} := 998784$, $T_{9216} := 9792^2$,
 $E := \{1189, 1191, \dots, 19617, 19619\}$
4. **(594, 88208, 88210)** $\Rightarrow 88210 - 594 = 296^2$, $S_{296 \times 296} := 26285984$, $T_{87616} := 88208^2$,
 $E := \{1189, 1191, \dots, 176417, 176419\}$

■ Number 595

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$595^2 + 600^2 := 845^2$	$595^2 + 3588^2 := 3637^2$	$595^2 + 35400^2 := 35405^2$
$595^2 + 924^2 := 1099^2$	$595^2 + 5040^2 := 5075^2$	$595^2 + 10404^2 := 10421^2$
$595^2 + 1428^2 := 1547^2$	$595^2 + 7068^2 := 7093^2$	$595^2 + 177012^2 := 177013^2$
$595^2 + 2040^2 := 2125^2$	$595^2 + 25284^2 := 25291^2$	

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(595, 7068, 7093)** $\Rightarrow 7093 - 7068 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 70805$, $T_{25} := 595^2$,
 $E := \{14137, 14139, \dots, 14183, 14185\}$ or $E := \{14149, 14150, \dots, 14172, 14173\}$
2. **(595, 3588, 3637)** $\Rightarrow 3637 - 3588 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 50575$, $T_{49} := 595^2$,
 $E := \{7177, 7179, \dots, 7271, 7273\}$ or $E := \{7201, 7202, \dots, 7248, 7249\}$

■ Number 596

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$596^2 + 22197^2 := 22205^2$
$596^2 + 44400^2 := 44404^2$
$596^2 + 88803^2 := 88805^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(596, 22197, 22205)** $\Rightarrow 22205 - 596 = 147^2$, $S_{147 \times 147} := 3351747$, $T_{21609} := 22197^2$,
 $E := \{1193, 1195, \dots, 44407, 44409\}$ or $E := \{11997, 11998, \dots, 33604, 33605\}$
2. **(596, 88803, 88805)** $\Rightarrow 88805 - 596 = 297^2$, $S_{297 \times 297} := 26552097$, $T_{88209} := 88803^2$,
 $E := \{1193, 1195, \dots, 177607, 177609\}$ or $E := \{45297, 45298, \dots, 133504, 133505\}$

■ Number 597

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$597^2 + 796^2 := 995^2$$

$$597^2 + 19796^2 := 19805^2$$

$$597^2 + 59400^2 := 59403^2$$

$$597^2 + 178204^2 := 178205^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(597, 19796, 19805)** $\Rightarrow 19805 - 19796 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 118803$, $T_9 := 597^2$,
 $E := \{39593, 39595, \dots, 39607, 39609\}$ or $E := \{39597, 39598, \dots, 39604, 39605\}$

■ Number 598

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$598^2 + 3864^2 := 3910^2$$

$$598^2 + 6864^2 := 6890^2$$

$$598^2 + 89400^2 := 89402^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(598, 89400, 89402)** $\Rightarrow 89402 - 598 = 298^2$, $S_{298 \times 298} := 26820000$, $T_{88804} := 89400^2$,
 $E := \{1197, 1199, \dots, 178801, 178803\}$

■ Number 599

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$599^2 + 179400^2 := 179401^2$$

■ Number 600

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$600^2 + 630^2 := 870^2$$

$$600^2 + 800^2 := 1000^2$$

$$600^2 + 910^2 := 1090^2$$

$$600^2 + 1045^2 := 1205^2$$

$$600^2 + 1125^2 := 1275^2$$

$$600^2 + 1178^2 := 1322^2$$

$$600^2 + 1490^2 := 1560^2$$

$$600^2 + 1750^2 := 1850^2$$

$$600^2 + 1827^2 := 1923^2$$

$$600^2 + 2210^2 := 2290^2$$

$$600^2 + 2464^2 := 2536^2$$

$$600^2 + 2970^2 := 3030^2$$

$$600^2 + 3575^2 := 3625^2$$

$$600^2 + 3726^2 := 3774^2$$

$$600^2 + 4480^2 := 4520^2$$

$$600^2 + 4982^2 := 5018^2$$

$$600^2 + 5609^2 := 5641^2$$

$$600^2 + 5985^2 := 6015^2$$

$$600^2 + 7488^2 := 7512^2$$

$$600^2 + 8990^2 := 9010^2$$

$$600^2 + 9991^2 := 10009^2$$

$$600^2 + 11242^2 := 11258^2$$

$$600^2 + 14994^2 := 15006^2$$

$$600^2 + 17995^2 := 18005^2$$

$$600^2 + 22496^2 := 22504^2$$

$$600^2 + 29997^2 := 30003^2$$

$$600^2 + 44998^2 := 45002^2$$

$$600^2 + 89999^2 := 90001^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(600, 11242, 11258)** $\Rightarrow 11258 - 11242 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 90000$, $T_{16} := 600^2$,
 $E := \{22485, 22487, \dots, 22513, 22515\}$
2. **(600, 4982, 5018)** $\Rightarrow 5018 - 4982 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 60000$, $T_{36} := 600^2$,
 $E := \{9965, 9967, \dots, 10033, 10035\}$
3. **(600, 1750, 1850)** $\Rightarrow 1850 - 1750 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 36000$, $T_{100} := 600^2$,
 $E := \{3501, 3503, \dots, 3697, 3699\}$
4. **(600, 1178, 1322)** $\Rightarrow 1322 - 1178 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 30000$, $T_{144} := 600^2$,
 $E := \{2357, 2359, \dots, 2641, 2643\}$
5. **(600, 800, 1000)** $\Rightarrow 1000 - 600 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 32000$, $T_{400} := 800^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 1997, 1999\}$
6. **(600, 2464, 2536)** $\Rightarrow 2536 - 600 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 137984$, $T_{1936} := 2464^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 5069, 5071\}$
7. **(600, 3575, 3625)** $\Rightarrow 3625 - 600 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 232375$, $T_{3025} := 3575^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 7247, 7249\}$ or $E := \{2713, 2714, \dots, 5736, 5737\}$
8. **(600, 5609, 5641)** $\Rightarrow 5641 - 600 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 443111$, $T_{5041} := 5609^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 11279, 11281\}$ or $E := \{3721, 3722, \dots, 8760, 8761\}$
9. **(600, 9991, 10009)** $\Rightarrow 10009 - 600 = 97^2$, $S_{97 \times 97} := 1029073$, $T_{9409} := 9991^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 20015, 20017\}$ or $E := \{5905, 5906, \dots, 15312, 15313\}$
10. **(600, 22496, 22504)** $\Rightarrow 22504 - 600 = 148^2$, $S_{148 \times 148} := 3419392$, $T_{21904} := 22496^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 45005, 45007\}$
11. **(600, 89999, 90001)** $\Rightarrow 90001 - 600 = 299^2$, $S_{299 \times 299} := 27089699$, $T_{89401} := 89999^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 179999, 180001\}$ or $E := \{45901, 45902, \dots, 135300, 135301\}$

2.7 Pythagorean Triples: 601 to 700

■ Number 601

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$601^2 + 180600^2 := 180601^2$$

■ Number 602

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$602^2 + 1800^2 := 1898^2$$

$$602^2 + 12936^2 := 12950^2$$

$$602^2 + 2064^2 := 2150^2$$

$$602^2 + 90600^2 := 90602^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(602, 1800, 1898)** $\Rightarrow 1898 - 602 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 90000$, $T_{1296} := 1800^2$,
 $E := \{1205, 1207, \dots, 3793, 3795\}$
2. **(602, 90600, 90602)** $\Rightarrow 90602 - 602 = 300^2$, $S_{300 \times 300} := 27361200$, $T_{90000} := 90600^2$,
 $E := \{1205, 1207, \dots, 181201, 181203\}$

■ Number 603

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$603^2 + 804^2 := 1005^2$$

$$603^2 + 20196^2 := 20205^2$$

$$603^2 + 2204^2 := 2285^2$$

$$603^2 + 60600^2 := 60603^2$$

$$603^2 + 2680^2 := 2747^2$$

$$603^2 + 181804^2 := 181805^2$$

$$603^2 + 6720^2 := 6747^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(603, 20196, 20205)** $\Rightarrow 20205 - 20196 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 121203$, $T_9 := 603^2$,
 $E := \{40393, 40395, \dots, 40407, 40409\}$ or $E := \{40397, 40398, \dots, 40404, 40405\}$
2. **(603, 2204, 2285)** $\Rightarrow 2285 - 2204 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 40401$, $T_{81} := 603^2$,
 $E := \{4409, 4411, \dots, 4567, 4569\}$ or $E := \{4449, 4450, \dots, 4528, 4529\}$

■ Number 604

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$604^2 + 22797^2 := 22805^2$$

$$604^2 + 45600^2 := 45604^2$$

$$604^2 + 91203^2 := 91205^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(604, 22797, 22805)** $\Rightarrow 22805 - 604 = 149^2$, $S_{149 \times 149} := 3487941$, $T_{22201} := 22797^2$,
 $E := \{1209, 1211, \dots, 45607, 45609\}$ or $E := \{12309, 12310, \dots, 34508, 34509\}$

2. **(604, 91203, 91205)** $\Rightarrow 91205 - 604 = 301^2$, $S_{301 \times 301} := 27634509$, $T_{90601} := 91203^2$,
 $E := \{1209, 1211, \dots, 182407, 182409\}$ or $E := \{46509, 46510, \dots, 137108, 137109\}$

■ Number 605

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$605^2 + 1452^2 := 1573^2$$

$$605^2 + 3300^2 := 3355^2$$

$$605^2 + 7308^2 := 7333^2$$

$$605^2 + 16632^2 := 16643^2$$

$$605^2 + 36600^2 := 36605^2$$

$$605^2 + 183012^2 := 183013^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(605, 7308, 7333)** $\Rightarrow 7333 - 7308 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 73205$, $T_{25} := 605^2$,
 $E := \{14617, 14619, \dots, 14663, 14665\}$ or $E := \{14629, 14630, \dots, 14652, 14653\}$

2. **(605, 1452, 1573)** $\Rightarrow 1573 - 1452 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 33275$, $T_{121} := 605^2$,
 $E := \{2905, 2907, \dots, 3143, 3145\}$ or $E := \{2965, 2966, \dots, 3084, 3085\}$

■ Number 606

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$606^2 + 808^2 := 1010^2$$

$$606^2 + 10192^2 := 10210^2$$

$$606^2 + 30600^2 := 30606^2$$

$$606^2 + 91808^2 := 91810^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(606, 10192, 10210)** $\Rightarrow 10210 - 606 = 98^2$, $S_{98 \times 98} := 1059968$, $T_{9604} := 10192^2$,
 $E := \{1213, 1215, \dots, 20417, 20419\}$
2. **(606, 91808, 91810)** $\Rightarrow 91810 - 606 = 302^2$, $S_{302 \times 302} := 27909632$, $T_{91204} := 91808^2$,
 $E := \{1213, 1215, \dots, 183617, 183619\}$

■ **Number 607**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$607^2 + 184224^2 := 184225^2$$

■ **Number 608**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$608^2 + 1140^2 := 1292^2$$

$$608^2 + 2856^2 := 2920^2$$

$$608^2 + 11544^2 := 11560^2$$

$$608^2 + 1380^2 := 1508^2$$

$$608^2 + 4845^2 := 4883^2$$

$$608^2 + 23100^2 := 23108^2$$

$$608^2 + 2394^2 := 2470^2$$

$$608^2 + 5760^2 := 5792^2$$

$$608^2 + 46206^2 := 46210^2$$

$$608^2 + 92415^2 := 92417^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(608, 11544, 11560)** $\Rightarrow 11560 - 11544 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 92416$, $T_{16} := 608^2$,
 $E := \{23089, 23091, \dots, 23117, 23119\}$
2. **(608, 2856, 2920)** $\Rightarrow 2920 - 2856 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 46208$, $T_{64} := 608^2$,
 $E := \{5713, 5715, \dots, 5837, 5839\}$
3. **(608, 1380, 1508)** $\Rightarrow 1508 - 608 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 63480$, $T_{900} := 1380^2$,
 $E := \{1217, 1219, \dots, 3013, 3015\}$
4. **(608, 5760, 5792)** $\Rightarrow 5792 - 608 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 460800$, $T_{5184} := 5760^2$,
 $E := \{1217, 1219, \dots, 11581, 11583\}$
5. **(608, 23100, 23108)** $\Rightarrow 23108 - 608 = 150^2$, $S_{150 \times 150} := 3557400$, $T_{22500} := 23100^2$,
 $E := \{1217, 1219, \dots, 46213, 46215\}$
6. **(608, 92415, 92417)** $\Rightarrow 92417 - 608 = 303^2$, $S_{303 \times 303} := 28186575$, $T_{91809} := 92415^2$,
 $E := \{1217, 1219, \dots, 184831, 184833\}$ or $E := \{47121, 47122, \dots, 138928, 138929\}$

■ Number 609

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$609^2 + 812^2 := 1015^2$$

$$609^2 + 1188^2 := 1335^2$$

$$609^2 + 2088^2 := 2175^2$$

$$609^2 + 2912^2 := 2975^2$$

$$609^2 + 3760^2 := 3809^2$$

$$609^2 + 6380^2 := 6409^2$$

$$609^2 + 8820^2 := 8841^2$$

$$609^2 + 20600^2 := 20609^2$$

$$609^2 + 26488^2 := 26495^2$$

$$609^2 + 61812^2 := 61815^2$$

$$609^2 + 185440^2 := 185441^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(609, 20600, 20609)** $\Rightarrow 20609 - 20600 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 123627$, $T_9 := 609^2$,
 $E := \{41201, 41203, \dots, 41215, 41217\}$ or $E := \{41205, 41206, \dots, 41212, 41213\}$
2. **(609, 3760, 3809)** $\Rightarrow 3809 - 3760 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 52983$, $T_{49} := 609^2$,
 $E := \{7521, 7523, \dots, 7615, 7617\}$ or $E := \{7545, 7546, \dots, 7592, 7593\}$

■ Number 610

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$610^2 + 1464^2 := 1586^2$$

$$610^2 + 3696^2 := 3746^2$$

$$610^2 + 18600^2 := 18610^2$$

$$610^2 + 93024^2 := 93026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(610, 3696, 3746)** $\Rightarrow 3746 - 610 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 243936$, $T_{3136} := 3696^2$,
 $E := \{1221, 1223, \dots, 7489, 7491\}$
2. **(610, 93024, 93026)** $\Rightarrow 93026 - 610 = 304^2$, $S_{304 \times 304} := 28465344$, $T_{92416} := 93024^2$,
 $E := \{1221, 1223, \dots, 186049, 186051\}$

■ Number 611

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$611^2 + 1020^2 := 1189^2$$

$$611^2 + 3948^2 := 3995^2$$

$$611^2 + 14352^2 := 14365^2$$

$$611^2 + 186660^2 := 186661^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(611, 1020, 1189)** $\Rightarrow 1189 - 1020 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 28717$, $T_{169} := 611^2$,
 $E := \{2041, 2043, \dots, 2375, 2377\}$ or $E := \{2125, 2126, \dots, 2292, 2293\}$

■ **Number 612**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$612^2 + 759^2 := 975^2$	$612^2 + 2565^2 := 2637^2$	$612^2 + 10395^2 := 10413^2$
$612^2 + 816^2 := 1020^2$	$612^2 + 2720^2 := 2788^2$	$612^2 + 15600^2 := 15612^2$
$612^2 + 1075^2 := 1237^2$	$612^2 + 3441^2 := 3495^2$	$612^2 + 23405^2 := 23413^2$
$612^2 + 1309^2 := 1445^2$	$612^2 + 5184^2 := 5220^2$	$612^2 + 31209^2 := 31215^2$
$612^2 + 1680^2 := 1788^2$	$612^2 + 5491^2 := 5525^2$	$612^2 + 46816^2 := 46820^2$
$612^2 + 1785^2 := 1887^2$	$612^2 + 7791^2 := 7815^2$	$612^2 + 93635^2 := 93637^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(612, 5184, 5220)** $\Rightarrow 5220 - 5184 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 62424$, $T_{36} := 612^2$,
 $E := \{10369, 10371, \dots, 10437, 10439\}$
2. **(612, 1075, 1237)** $\Rightarrow 1237 - 612 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 46225$, $T_{625} := 1075^2$,
 $E := \{1225, 1227, \dots, 2471, 2473\}$ or $E := \{1537, 1538, \dots, 2160, 2161\}$
3. **(612, 2565, 2637)** $\Rightarrow 2637 - 612 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 146205$, $T_{2025} := 2565^2$,
 $E := \{1225, 1227, \dots, 5271, 5273\}$ or $E := \{2237, 2238, \dots, 4260, 4261\}$
4. **(612, 10395, 10413)** $\Rightarrow 10413 - 612 = 99^2$, $S_{99 \times 99} := 1091475$, $T_{9801} := 10395^2$,
 $E := \{1225, 1227, \dots, 20823, 20825\}$ or $E := \{6125, 6126, \dots, 15924, 15925\}$
5. **(612, 23405, 23413)** $\Rightarrow 23413 - 612 = 151^2$, $S_{151 \times 151} := 3627775$, $T_{22801} := 23405^2$,
 $E := \{1225, 1227, \dots, 46823, 46825\}$ or $E := \{12625, 12626, \dots, 35424, 35425\}$
6. **(612, 93635, 93637)** $\Rightarrow 93637 - 612 = 305^2$, $S_{305 \times 305} := 28745945$, $T_{93025} := 93635^2$,
 $E := \{1225, 1227, \dots, 187271, 187273\}$ or $E := \{47737, 47738, \dots, 140760, 140761\}$

■ **Number 613**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$613^2 + 187884^2 := 187885^2$$

■ Number 614

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$614^2 + 94248^2 := 94250^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(614, 94248, 94250)** $\Rightarrow 94250 - 614 = 306^2$, $S_{306 \times 306} := 29028384$, $T_{93636} := 94248^2$,
 $E := \{1229, 1231, \dots, 188497, 188499\}$

■ Number 615

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$615^2 + 728^2 := 953^2$$

$$615^2 + 820^2 := 1025^2$$

$$615^2 + 1476^2 := 1599^2$$

$$615^2 + 2484^2 := 2559^2$$

$$615^2 + 4180^2 := 4225^2$$

$$615^2 + 4592^2 := 4633^2$$

$$615^2 + 7552^2 := 7577^2$$

$$615^2 + 12600^2 := 12615^2$$

$$615^2 + 21008^2 := 21017^2$$

$$615^2 + 37820^2 := 37825^2$$

$$615^2 + 63036^2 := 63039^2$$

$$615^2 + 189112^2 := 189113^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(615, 21008, 21017)** $\Rightarrow 21017 - 21008 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 126075$, $T_9 := 615^2$,
 $E := \{42017, 42019, \dots, 42031, 42033\}$ or $E := \{42021, 42022, \dots, 42028, 42029\}$
2. **(615, 7552, 7577)** $\Rightarrow 7577 - 7552 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 75645$, $T_{25} := 615^2$,
 $E := \{15105, 15107, \dots, 15151, 15153\}$ or $E := \{15117, 15118, \dots, 15140, 15141\}$
3. **(615, 728, 953)** $\Rightarrow 953 - 728 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 25215$, $T_{225} := 615^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 1903, 1905\}$ or $E := \{1569, 1570, \dots, 1792, 1793\}$

■ Number 616

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$616^2 + 663^2 := 905^2$$

$$616^2 + 735^2 := 959^2$$

$$616^2 + 870^2 := 1066^2$$

$$616^2 + 990^2 := 1166^2$$

$$616^2 + 1155^2 := 1309^2$$

$$616^2 + 1638^2 := 1750^2$$

$$616^2 + 1887^2 := 1985^2$$

$$616^2 + 2112^2 := 2200^2$$

$$616^2 + 3360^2 := 3416^2$$

$$616^2 + 4290^2 := 4334^2$$

$$616^2 + 5913^2 := 5945^2$$

$$616^2 + 6762^2 := 6790^2$$

$$616^2 + 8613^2 := 8635^2$$

$$616^2 + 11850^2 := 11866^2$$

$$616^2 + 13545^2 := 13559^2$$

$$616^2 + 23712^2 := 23720^2$$

$$616^2 + 47430^2 := 47434^2$$

$$616^2 + 94863^2 := 94865^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(616, 11850, 11866)** $\Rightarrow 11866 - 11850 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 94864$, $T_{16} := 616^2$,
 $E := \{23701, 23703, \dots, 23729, 23731\}$
2. **(616, 870, 1066)** $\Rightarrow 1066 - 870 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 27104$, $T_{196} := 616^2$,
 $E := \{1741, 1743, \dots, 2129, 2131\}$
3. **(616, 663, 905)** $\Rightarrow 905 - 616 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 25857$, $T_{289} := 663^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 1807, 1809\}$ or $E := \{1377, 1378, \dots, 1664, 1665\}$
4. **(616, 5913, 5945)** $\Rightarrow 5945 - 616 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 478953$, $T_{5329} := 5913^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 11887, 11889\}$ or $E := \{3897, 3898, \dots, 9224, 9225\}$
5. **(616, 1887, 1985)** $\Rightarrow 1985 - 616 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 96237$, $T_{1369} := 1887^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 3967, 3969\}$ or $E := \{1917, 1918, \dots, 3284, 3285\}$
6. **(616, 23712, 23720)** $\Rightarrow 23720 - 616 = 152^2$, $S_{152 \times 152} := 3699072$, $T_{23104} := 23712^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 47437, 47439\}$
7. **(616, 94863, 94865)** $\Rightarrow 94865 - 616 = 307^2$, $S_{307 \times 307} := 29312667$, $T_{94249} := 94863^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 189727, 189729\}$ or $E := \{48357, 48358, \dots, 142604, 142605\}$

■ Number 617

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$617^2 + 190344^2 := 190345^2$$

■ Number 618

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$618^2 + 824^2 := 1030^2$$

$$618^2 + 10600^2 := 10618^2$$

$$618^2 + 31824^2 := 31830^2$$

$$618^2 + 95480^2 := 95482^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(618, 10600, 10618)** $\Rightarrow 10618 - 618 = 100^2$, $S_{100 \times 100} := 1123600$, $T_{10000} := 10600^2$,
 $E := \{1237, 1239, \dots, 21233, 21235\}$
2. **(618, 95480, 95482)** $\Rightarrow 95482 - 618 = 308^2$, $S_{308 \times 308} := 29598800$, $T_{94864} := 95480^2$,
 $E := \{1237, 1239, \dots, 190961, 190963\}$

■ Number 619

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$619^2 + 191580^2 := 191581^2$$

■ Number 620

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$620^2 + 651^2 := 899^2$$

$$620^2 + 861^2 := 1061^2$$

$$620^2 + 1488^2 := 1612^2$$

$$620^2 + 1872^2 := 1972^2$$

$$620^2 + 3069^2 := 3131^2$$

$$620^2 + 3819^2 := 3869^2$$

$$620^2 + 4785^2 := 4825^2$$

$$620^2 + 9600^2 := 9620^2$$

$$620^2 + 19215^2 := 19225^2$$

$$620^2 + 24021^2 := 24029^2$$

$$620^2 + 48048^2 := 48052^2$$

$$620^2 + 96099^2 := 96101^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(620, 1872, 1972)** $\Rightarrow 1972 - 1872 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 38440$, $T_{100} := 620^2$,
 $E := \{3745, 3747, \dots, 3941, 3943\}$
2. **(620, 861, 1061)** $\Rightarrow 1061 - 620 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 35301$, $T_{441} := 861^2$,
 $E := \{1241, 1243, \dots, 2119, 2121\}$ or $E := \{1461, 1462, \dots, 1900, 1901\}$
3. **(620, 3819, 3869)** $\Rightarrow 3869 - 620 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 255873$, $T_{3249} := 3819^2$,
 $E := \{1241, 1243, \dots, 7735, 7737\}$ or $E := \{2865, 2866, \dots, 6112, 6113\}$
4. **(620, 24021, 24029)** $\Rightarrow 24029 - 620 = 153^2$, $S_{153 \times 153} := 3771297$, $T_{23409} := 24021^2$,
 $E := \{1241, 1243, \dots, 48055, 48057\}$ or $E := \{12945, 12946, \dots, 36352, 36353\}$
5. **(620, 96099, 96101)** $\Rightarrow 96101 - 620 = 309^2$, $S_{309 \times 309} := 29886789$, $T_{95481} := 96099^2$,
 $E := \{1241, 1243, \dots, 192199, 192201\}$ or $E := \{48981, 48982, \dots, 144460, 144461\}$

■ Number 621

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$621^2 + 672^2 := 915^2$$

$$621^2 + 828^2 := 1035^2$$

$$621^2 + 2340^2 := 2421^2$$

$$621^2 + 2760^2 := 2829^2$$

$$621^2 + 7128^2 := 7155^2$$

$$621^2 + 8372^2 := 8395^2$$

$$621^2 + 21420^2 := 21429^2$$

$$621^2 + 64272^2 := 64275^2$$

$$621^2 + 192820^2 := 192821^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(621, 21420, 21429)** $\Rightarrow 21429 - 21420 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 128547$, $T_9 := 621^2$,
 $E := \{42841, 42843, \dots, 42855, 42857\}$ or $E := \{42845, 42846, \dots, 42852, 42853\}$

2. **(621, 2340, 2421)** $\Rightarrow 2421 - 2340 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 42849$, $T_{81} := 621^2$,
 $E := \{4681, 4683, \dots, 4839, 4841\}$ or $E := \{4721, 4722, \dots, 4800, 4801\}$

■ Number 622

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$622^2 + 96720^2 := 96722^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(622, 96720, 96722)** $\Rightarrow 96722 - 622 = 310^2$, $S_{310 \times 310} := 30176640$, $T_{96100} := 96720^2$,
 $E := \{1245, 1247, \dots, 193441, 193443\}$

■ Number 623

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$623^2 + 2136^2 := 2225^2$$

$$623^2 + 3936^2 := 3985^2$$

$$623^2 + 27720^2 := 27727^2$$

$$623^2 + 194064^2 := 194065^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(623, 3936, 3985)** $\Rightarrow 3985 - 3936 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 55447$, $T_{49} := 623^2$,
 $E := \{7873, 7875, \dots, 7967, 7969\}$ or $E := \{7897, 7898, \dots, 7944, 7945\}$

■ Number 624

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$624^2 + 715^2 := 949^2$	$624^2 + 2457^2 := 2535^2$	$624^2 + 8100^2 := 8124^2$
$624^2 + 832^2 := 1040^2$	$624^2 + 2668^2 := 2740^2$	$624^2 + 10807^2 := 10825^2$
$624^2 + 918^2 := 1110^2$	$624^2 + 3010^2 := 3074^2$	$624^2 + 12160^2 := 12176^2$
$624^2 + 1170^2 := 1326^2$	$624^2 + 3718^2 := 3770^2$	$624^2 + 16218^2 := 16230^2$
$624^2 + 1280^2 := 1424^2$	$624^2 + 4032^2 := 4080^2$	$624^2 + 24332^2 := 24340^2$
$624^2 + 1457^2 := 1585^2$	$624^2 + 5390^2 := 5426^2$	$624^2 + 32445^2 := 32451^2$
$624^2 + 1820^2 := 1924^2$	$624^2 + 6068^2 := 6100^2$	$624^2 + 48670^2 := 48674^2$
$624^2 + 1980^2 := 2076^2$	$624^2 + 7475^2 := 7501^2$	$624^2 + 97343^2 := 97345^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(624, 12160, 12176)** $\Rightarrow 12176 - 12160 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 97344$, $T_{16} := 624^2$,
 $E := \{24321, 24323, \dots, 24349, 24351\}$
2. **(624, 5390, 5426)** $\Rightarrow 5426 - 5390 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 64896$, $T_{36} := 624^2$,
 $E := \{10781, 10783, \dots, 10849, 10851\}$
3. **(624, 3010, 3074)** $\Rightarrow 3074 - 3010 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 48672$, $T_{64} := 624^2$,
 $E := \{6021, 6023, \dots, 6145, 6147\}$
4. **(624, 1280, 1424)** $\Rightarrow 1424 - 1280 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 32448$, $T_{144} := 624^2$,
 $E := \{2561, 2563, \dots, 2845, 2847\}$
5. **(624, 1457, 1585)** $\Rightarrow 1585 - 624 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 68479$, $T_{961} := 1457^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 3167, 3169\}$ or $E := \{1729, 1730, \dots, 2688, 689\}$
6. **(624, 2668, 2740)** $\Rightarrow 2740 - 624 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 154744$, $T_{2116} := 2668^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 5477, 5479\}$
7. **(624, 6068, 6100)** $\Rightarrow 6100 - 624 = 74^2$, $S_{74 \times 74} := 497576$, $T_{5476} := 6068^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 12197, 12199\}$
8. **(624, 10807, 10825)** $\Rightarrow 10825 - 624 = 101^2$, $S_{101 \times 101} := 1156349$, $T_{10201} := 10807^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 21647, 21649\}$ or $E := \{6349, 6350, \dots, 16548, 16549\}$
9. **(624, 24332, 24340)** $\Rightarrow 24340 - 624 = 154^2$, $S_{154 \times 154} := 3844456$, $T_{23716} := 24332^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 48677, 48679\}$
10. **(624, 97343, 97345)** $\Rightarrow 97345 - 624 = 311^2$, $S_{311 \times 311} := 30468359$, $T_{96721} := 97343^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 194687, 194689\}$ or $E := \{49609, 49610, \dots, 146328, 146329\}$

■ Number 625

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$625^2 + 1500^2 := 1625^2$$

$$625^2 + 7800^2 := 7825^2$$

$$625^2 + 39060^2 := 39065^2$$

$$625^2 + 195312^2 := 195313^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(625, 7800, 7825)** $\Rightarrow 7825 - 7800 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 78125$, $T_{25} := 625^2$,
 $E := \{15601, 15603, \dots, 15647, 15649\}$ or $E := \{15613, 15614, \dots, 15636, 15637\}$

■ Number 626

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$626^2 + 97968^2 := 97970^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(626, 97968, 97970)** $\Rightarrow 97970 - 626 = 312^2$, $S_{312 \times 312} := 30761952$, $T_{97344} := 97968^2$,
 $E := \{1253, 1255, \dots, 195937, 195939\}$

■ Number 627

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$627^2 + 836^2 := 1045^2$$

$$627^2 + 1064^2 := 1235^2$$

$$627^2 + 1564^2 := 1685^2$$

$$627^2 + 1936^2 := 2035^2$$

$$627^2 + 3420^2 := 3477^2$$

$$627^2 + 5940^2 := 5973^2$$

$$627^2 + 10336^2 := 10355^2$$

$$627^2 + 17864^2 := 17875^2$$

$$627^2 + 21836^2 := 21845^2$$

$$627^2 + 65520^2 := 65523^2$$

$$627^2 + 196564^2 := 196565^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(627, 21836, 21845)** $\Rightarrow 21845 - 21836 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 131043$, $T_9 := 627^2$,
 $E := \{43673, 43675, \dots, 43687, 43689\}$ or $E := \{43677, 43678, \dots, 43684, 43685\}$
2. **(627, 1564, 1685)** $\Rightarrow 1685 - 1564 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 35739$, $T_{121} := 627^2$,
 $E := \{3129, 3131, \dots, 3367, 3369\}$ or $E := \{3189, 3190, \dots, 3308, 3309\}$

■ Number 628

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$628^2 + 24645^2 := 24653^2$$

$$628^2 + 49296^2 := 49300^2$$

$$628^2 + 98595^2 := 98597^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(628, 24645, 24653)** $\Rightarrow 24653 - 628 = 155^2$, $S_{155 \times 155} := 3918555$, $T_{24025} := 24645^2$,
 $E := \{1257, 1259, \dots, 49303, 49305\}$ or $E := \{13269, 13270, \dots, 37292, 37293\}$

2. **(628, 98595, 98597)** $\Rightarrow 98597 - 628 = 313^2$, $S_{313 \times 313} := 31057425$, $T_{97969} := 98595^2$,
 $E := \{1257, 1259, \dots, 197191, 197193\}$ or $E := \{50241, 50242, \dots, 148208, 148209\}$

■ Number 629

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$629^2 + 5328^2 := 5365^2$$

$$629^2 + 11628^2 := 11645^2$$

$$629^2 + 197820^2 := 197821^2$$

■ Number 630

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$630^2 + 840^2 := 1050^2$$

$$630^2 + 1144^2 := 1306^2$$

$$630^2 + 1248^2 := 1398^2$$

$$630^2 + 1512^2 := 1638^2$$

$$630^2 + 1976^2 := 2074^2$$

$$630^2 + 2160^2 := 2250^2$$

$$630^2 + 2800^2 := 2870^2$$

$$630^2 + 3648^2 := 3702^2$$

$$630^2 + 3944^2 := 3994^2$$

$$630^2 + 4704^2 := 4746^2$$

$$630^2 + 6600^2 := 6630^2$$

$$630^2 + 11016^2 := 11034^2$$

$$630^2 + 14168^2 := 14182^2$$

$$630^2 + 19840^2 := 19850^2$$

$$630^2 + 33072^2 := 33078^2$$

$$630^2 + 99224^2 := 99226^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(630, 1144, 1306)** $\Rightarrow 1306 - 630 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 50336$, $T_{676} := 1144^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 2609, 2611\}$

2. **(630, 1976, 2074)** $\Rightarrow 2074 - 630 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 102752$, $T_{1444} := 1976^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 4145, 4147\}$
3. **(630, 3944, 3994)** $\Rightarrow 3994 - 630 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 268192$, $T_{3364} := 3944^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 7985, 7987\}$
4. **(630, 11016, 11034)** $\Rightarrow 11034 - 630 = 102^2$, $S_{102 \times 102} := 1189728$, $T_{10404} := 11016^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 22065, 22067\}$
5. **(630, 99224, 99226)** $\Rightarrow 99226 - 630 = 314^2$, $S_{314 \times 314} := 31354784$, $T_{98596} := 99224^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 198449, 198451\}$

■ Number 631

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$631^2 + 199080^2 := 199081^2$$

■ Number 632

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$632^2 + 1185^2 := 1343^2$$

$$632^2 + 6225^2 := 6257^2$$

$$632^2 + 12474^2 := 12490^2$$

$$632^2 + 24960^2 := 24968^2$$

$$632^2 + 49926^2 := 49930^2$$

$$632^2 + 99855^2 := 99857^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(632, 12474, 12490)** $\Rightarrow 12490 - 12474 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 99856$, $T_{16} := 632^2$,
 $E := \{24949, 24951, \dots, 24977, 24979\}$
2. **(632, 6225, 6257)** $\Rightarrow 6257 - 632 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 516675$, $T_{5625} := 6225^2$,
 $E := \{1265, 1267, \dots, 12511, 12513\}$ or $E := \{4077, 4078, \dots, 9700, 9701\}$
3. **(632, 24960, 24968)** $\Rightarrow 24968 - 632 = 156^2$, $S_{156 \times 156} := 3993600$, $T_{24336} := 24960^2$,
 $E := \{1265, 1267, \dots, 49933, 49935\}$
4. **(632, 99855, 99857)** $\Rightarrow 99857 - 632 = 315^2$, $S_{315 \times 315} := 31654035$, $T_{99225} := 99855^2$,
 $E := \{1265, 1267, \dots, 199711, 199713\}$ or $E := \{50877, 50878, \dots, 150100, 150101\}$

■ Number 633

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$633^2 + 844^2 := 1055^2$$

$$633^2 + 66780^2 := 66783^2$$

$$633^2 + 22256^2 := 22265^2$$

$$633^2 + 200344^2 := 200345^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(633, 22256, 22265)** $\Rightarrow 22265 - 22256 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 133563$, $T_9 := 633^2$,
 $E := \{44513, 44515, \dots, 44527, 44529\}$ or $E := \{44517, 44518, \dots, 44524, 44525\}$

■ Number 634

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$634^2 + 100488^2 := 100490^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(634, 100488, 100490)** $\Rightarrow 100490 - 634 = 316^2$, $S_{316 \times 316} := 31955184$, $T_{99856} := 100488^2$,
 $E := \{1269, 1271, \dots, 200977, 200979\}$

■ Number 635

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$635^2 + 1524^2 := 1651^2$$

$$635^2 + 40320^2 := 40325^2$$

$$635^2 + 8052^2 := 8077^2$$

$$635^2 + 201612^2 := 201613^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(635, 8052, 8077)** $\Rightarrow 8077 - 8052 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 80645$, $T_{25} := 635^2$,
 $E := \{16105, 16107, \dots, 16151, 16153\}$ or $E := \{16117, 16118, \dots, 16140, 16141\}$

■ Number 636

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$636^2 + 848^2 := 1060^2$$

$$636^2 + 8415^2 := 8439^2$$

$$636^2 + 33705^2 := 33711^2$$

$$636^2 + 1855^2 := 1961^2$$

$$636^2 + 11227^2 := 11245^2$$

$$636^2 + 50560^2 := 50564^2$$

$$636^2 + 2773^2 := 2845^2$$

$$636^2 + 16848^2 := 16860^2$$

$$636^2 + 101123^2 := 101125^2$$

$$636^2 + 5600^2 := 5636^2$$

$$636^2 + 25277^2 := 25285^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(636, 5600, 5636)** $\Rightarrow 5636 - 5600 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 67416$, $T_{36} := 636^2$,
 $E := \{11201, 11203, \dots, 11269, 11271\}$
2. **(636, 2773, 2845)** $\Rightarrow 2845 - 636 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 163607$, $T_{2209} := 2773^2$,
 $E := \{1273, 1275, \dots, 5687, 5689\}$ or $E := \{2377, 2378, \dots, 4584, 4585\}$
3. **(636, 11227, 11245)** $\Rightarrow 11245 - 636 = 103^2$, $S_{103 \times 103} := 1223743$, $T_{10609} := 11227^2$,
 $E := \{1273, 1275, \dots, 22487, 22489\}$ or $E := \{6577, 6578, \dots, 17184, 17185\}$
4. **(636, 25277, 25285)** $\Rightarrow 25285 - 636 = 157^2$, $S_{157 \times 157} := 4069597$, $T_{24649} := 25277^2$,
 $E := \{1273, 1275, \dots, 50567, 50569\}$ or $E := \{13597, 13598, \dots, 38244, 38245\}$
5. **(636, 101123, 101125)** $\Rightarrow 101125 - 636 = 317^2$, $S_{317 \times 317} := 32258237$, $T_{100489} := 101123^2$,
 $E := \{1273, 1275, \dots, 202247, 202249\}$ or $E := \{51517, 51518, \dots, 152004, 152005\}$

■ **Number 637**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$637^2 + 1116^2 := 1285^2$	$637^2 + 15600^2 := 15613^2$
$637^2 + 2184^2 := 2275^2$	$637^2 + 28980^2 := 28987^2$
$637^2 + 4116^2 := 4165^2$	$637^2 + 202884^2 := 202885^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(637, 4116, 4165)** $\Rightarrow 4165 - 4116 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 57967$, $T_{49} := 637^2$,
 $E := \{8233, 8235, \dots, 8327, 8329\}$ or $E := \{8257, 8258, \dots, 8304, 8305\}$
2. **(637, 1116, 1285)** $\Rightarrow 1285 - 1116 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 31213$, $T_{169} := 637^2$,
 $E := \{2233, 2235, \dots, 2567, 2569\}$ or $E := \{2317, 2318, \dots, 2484, 2485\}$

■ **Number 638**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$638^2 + 720^2 := 962^2$	$638^2 + 9240^2 := 9262^2$
$638^2 + 3480^2 := 3538^2$	$638^2 + 101760^2 := 101762^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(638, 720, 962)** $\Rightarrow 962 - 638 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 28800$, $T_{324} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{1277, 1279, \dots, 1921, 1923\}$
2. **(638, 101760, 101762)** $\Rightarrow 101762 - 638 = 318^2$, $S_{318 \times 318} := 32563200$, $T_{101124} := 101760^2$,
 $E := \{1277, 1279, \dots, 203521, 203523\}$

■ Number 639

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$639^2 + 852^2 := 1065^2$	$639^2 + 22680^2 := 22689^2$
$639^2 + 2480^2 := 2561^2$	$639^2 + 68052^2 := 68055^2$
$639^2 + 2840^2 := 2911^2$	$639^2 + 204160^2 := 204161^2$
$639^2 + 7548^2 := 7575^2$	

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(639, 22680, 22689)** $\Rightarrow 22689 - 22680 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 136107$, $T_9 := 639^2$,
 $E := \{45361, 45363, \dots, 45375, 45377\}$ or $E := \{45365, 45366, \dots, 45372, 45373\}$
2. **(639, 2480, 2561)** $\Rightarrow 2561 - 2480 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 45369$, $T_{81} := 639^2$,
 $E := \{4961, 4963, \dots, 5119, 5121\}$ or $E := \{5001, 5002, \dots, 5080, 5081\}$

■ Number 640

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$640^2 + 672^2 := 928^2$	$640^2 + 2520^2 := 2600^2$	$640^2 + 10230^2 := 10250^2$
$640^2 + 924^2 := 1124^2$	$640^2 + 3168^2 := 3232^2$	$640^2 + 12792^2 := 12808^2$
$640^2 + 1200^2 := 1360^2$	$640^2 + 4071^2 := 4121^2$	$640^2 + 20475^2 := 20485^2$
$640^2 + 1536^2 := 1664^2$	$640^2 + 5100^2 := 5140^2$	$640^2 + 25596^2 := 25604^2$
$640^2 + 1998^2 := 2098^2$	$640^2 + 6384^2 := 6416^2$	$640^2 + 51198^2 := 51202^2$
		$640^2 + 102399^2 := 102401^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(640, 12792, 12808)** $\Rightarrow 12808 - 12792 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 102400$, $T_{16} := 640^2$,
 $E := \{25585, 25587, \dots, 25613, 25615\}$

2. **(640, 3168, 3232)** $\Rightarrow 3232 - 3168 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 51200$, $T_{64} := 640^2$,
 $E := \{6337, 6339, \dots, 6461, 6463\}$
3. **(640, 1998, 2098)** $\Rightarrow 2098 - 1998 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 40960$, $T_{100} := 640^2$,
 $E := \{3997, 3999, \dots, 4193, 4195\}$
4. **(640, 672, 928)** $\Rightarrow 928 - 672 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 25600$, $T_{256} := 640^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 1853, 1855\}$
5. **(640, 924, 1124)** $\Rightarrow 1124 - 640 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 38808$, $T_{484} := 924^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 2245, 2247\}$
6. **(640, 1536, 1664)** $\Rightarrow 1664 - 640 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 73728$, $T_{1024} := 1536^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 3325, 3327\}$
7. **(640, 4071, 4121)** $\Rightarrow 4121 - 640 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 280899$, $T_{3481} := 4071^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 8239, 8241\}$ or $E := \{3021, 3022, \dots, 6500, 6501\}$
8. **(640, 6384, 6416)** $\Rightarrow 6416 - 640 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 536256$, $T_{5776} := 6384^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 12829, 12831\}$
9. **(640, 25596, 25604)** $\Rightarrow 25604 - 640 = 158^2$, $S_{158 \times 158} := 4146552$, $T_{24964} := 25596^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 51205, 51207\}$
10. **(640, 102399, 102401)** $\Rightarrow 102401 - 640 = 319^2$, $S_{319 \times 319} := 32870079$, $T_{101761} := 102399^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 204799, 204801\}$ or $E := \{52161, 52162, \dots, 153920, 153921\}$

■ Number 641

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$641^2 + 205440^2 := 205441^2$$

■ Number 642

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$642^2 + 856^2 := 1070^2$$

$$642^2 + 11440^2 := 11458^2$$

$$642^2 + 34344^2 := 34350^2$$

$$642^2 + 103040^2 := 103042^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(642, 11440, 11458)** $\Rightarrow 11458 - 642 = 104^2$, $S_{104 \times 104} := 1258400$, $T_{10816} := 11440^2$,
 $E := \{1285, 1287, \dots, 22913, 22915\}$

2. **(642, 103040, 103042)** $\Rightarrow 103042 - 642 = 320^2$, $S_{320 \times 320} := 33178880$, $T_{102400} := 103040^2$,
 $E := \{1285, 1287, \dots, 206081, 206083\}$

■ Number 643

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$643^2 + 206724^2 := 206725^2$$

■ Number 644

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$644^2 + 960^2 := 1156^2$$

$$644^2 + 1035^2 := 1219^2$$

$$644^2 + 2067^2 := 2165^2$$

$$644^2 + 2208^2 := 2300^2$$

$$644^2 + 3675^2 := 3731^2$$

$$644^2 + 4485^2 := 4531^2$$

$$644^2 + 7392^2 := 7420^2$$

$$644^2 + 14805^2 := 14819^2$$

$$644^2 + 25917^2 := 25925^2$$

$$644^2 + 51840^2 := 51844^2$$

$$644^2 + 103683^2 := 103685^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(644, 960, 1156)** $\Rightarrow 1156 - 960 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 29624$, $T_{196} := 644^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 2309, 2311\}$

2. **(644, 2067, 2165)** $\Rightarrow 2165 - 644 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 109551$, $T_{1521} := 2067^2$,
 $E := \{1289, 1291, \dots, 4327, 4329\}$ or $E := \{2049, 2050, \dots, 3568, 3569\}$

3. **(644, 25917, 25925)** $\Rightarrow 25925 - 644 = 159^2$, $S_{159 \times 159} := 4224471$, $T_{25281} := 25917^2$,
 $E := \{1289, 1291, \dots, 51847, 51849\}$ or $E := \{13929, 13930, \dots, 39208, 39209\}$

4. **(644, 103683, 103685)** $\Rightarrow 103685 - 644 = 321^2$, $S_{321 \times 321} := 33489609$, $T_{103041} := 103683^2$,
 $E := \{1289, 1291, \dots, 207367, 207369\}$ or $E := \{52809, 52810, \dots, 155848, 155849\}$

■ Number 645

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$645^2 + 812^2 := 1037^2$$

$$645^2 + 860^2 := 1075^2$$

$$645^2 + 1548^2 := 1677^2$$

$$645^2 + 2736^2 := 2811^2$$

$$645^2 + 4600^2 := 4645^2$$

$$645^2 + 4816^2 := 4859^2$$

$$645^2 + 8308^2 := 8333^2$$

$$645^2 + 13860^2 := 13875^2$$

$$645^2 + 23108^2 := 23117^2$$

$$645^2 + 41600^2 := 41605^2$$

$$645^2 + 69336^2 := 69339^2$$

$$645^2 + 208012^2 := 208013^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(645, 23108, 23117)** $\Rightarrow 23117 - 23108 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 138675$, $T_9 := 645^2$,
 $E := \{46217, 46219, \dots, 46231, 46233\}$ or $E := \{46221, 46222, \dots, 46228, 46229\}$
2. **(645, 8308, 8333)** $\Rightarrow 8333 - 8308 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 83205$, $T_{25} := 645^2$,
 $E := \{16617, 16619, \dots, 16663, 16665\}$ or $E := \{16629, 16630, \dots, 16652, 16653\}$
3. **(645, 812, 1037)** $\Rightarrow 1037 - 812 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 27735$, $T_{225} := 645^2$,
 $E := \{1625, 1627, \dots, 2071, 2073\}$ or $E := \{1737, 1738, \dots, 1960, 1961\}$

■ Number 646

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$646^2 + 5472^2 := 5510^2$$

$$646^2 + 6120^2 := 6154^2$$

$$646^2 + 104328^2 := 104330^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(646, 104328, 104330)** $\Rightarrow 104330 - 646 = 322^2$, $S_{322 \times 322} := 33802272$, $T_{103684} := 104328^2$,
 $E := \{1293, 1295, \dots, 208657, 208659\}$

■ Number 647

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$647^2 + 209304^2 := 209305^2$$

■ Number 648

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$648^2 + 864^2 := 1080^2$	$648^2 + 3861^2 := 3915^2$	$648^2 + 13114^2 := 13130^2$
$648^2 + 1215^2 := 1377^2$	$648^2 + 4350^2 := 4398^2$	$648^2 + 17490^2 := 17502^2$
$648^2 + 1386^2 := 1530^2$	$648^2 + 5814^2 := 5850^2$	$648^2 + 26240^2 := 26248^2$
$648^2 + 1890^2 := 1998^2$	$648^2 + 6545^2 := 6577^2$	$648^2 + 34989^2 := 34995^2$
$648^2 + 2139^2 := 2235^2$	$648^2 + 8736^2 := 8760^2$	$648^2 + 52486^2 := 52490^2$
$648^2 + 2880^2 := 2952^2$	$648^2 + 11655^2 := 11673^2$	$648^2 + 104975^2 := 104977^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(648, 13114, 13130)** $\Rightarrow 13130 - 13114 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 104976$, $T_{16} := 648^2$,
 $E := \{26229, 26231, \dots, 26257, 26259\}$
2. **(648, 5814, 5850)** $\Rightarrow 5850 - 5814 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 69984$, $T_{36} := 648^2$,
 $E := \{11629, 11631, \dots, 11697, 11699\}$
3. **(648, 1386, 1530)** $\Rightarrow 1530 - 1386 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 34992$, $T_{144} := 648^2$,
 $E := \{2773, 2775, \dots, 3057, 3059\}$
4. **(648, 1215, 1377)** $\Rightarrow 1377 - 648 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 54675$, $T_{729} := 1215^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 2751, 2753\}$ or $E := \{1661, 1662, \dots, 2388, 2389\}$
5. **(648, 2880, 2952)** $\Rightarrow 2952 - 648 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 172800$, $T_{2304} := 2880^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 5901, 5903\}$
6. **(648, 6545, 6577)** $\Rightarrow 6577 - 648 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 556325$, $T_{5929} := 6545^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 13151, 13153\}$ or $E := \{4261, 4262, \dots, 10188, 10189\}$
7. **(648, 11655, 11673)** $\Rightarrow 11673 - 648 = 105^2$, $S_{105 \times 105} := 1293705$, $T_{11025} := 11655^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 23343, 23345\}$ or $E := \{6809, 6810, \dots, 17832, 17833\}$
8. **(648, 26240, 26248)** $\Rightarrow 26248 - 648 = 160^2$, $S_{160 \times 160} := 4303360$, $T_{25600} := 26240^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 52493, 52495\}$
9. **(648, 104975, 104977)** $\Rightarrow 104977 - 648 = 323^2$, $S_{323 \times 323} := 34116875$, $T_{104329} := 104975^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 209951, 209953\}$ or $E := \{53461, 53462, \dots, 157788, 157789\}$

■ Number 649

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$649^2 + 1680^2 := 1801^2$	$649^2 + 19140^2 := 19151^2$
$649^2 + 3540^2 := 3599^2$	$649^2 + 210600^2 := 210601^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(649, 1680, 1801)** $\Rightarrow 1801 - 1680 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 38291$, $T_{121} := 649^2$,
 $E := \{3361, 3363, \dots, 3599, 3601\}$ or $E := \{3421, 3422, \dots, 3540, 3541\}$

■ **Number 650**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$650^2 + 720^2 := 970^2$	$650^2 + 8112^2 := 8138^2$
$650^2 + 1560^2 := 1690^2$	$650^2 + 21120^2 := 21130^2$
$650^2 + 4200^2 := 4250^2$	$650^2 + 105624^2 := 105626^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(650, 4200, 4250)** $\Rightarrow 4250 - 650 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 294000$, $T_{3600} := 4200^2$,
 $E := \{1301, 1303, \dots, 8497, 8499\}$
2. **(650, 105624, 105626)** $\Rightarrow 105626 - 650 = 324^2$, $S_{324 \times 324} := 34433424$, $T_{104976} := 105624^2$,
 $E := \{1301, 1303, \dots, 211249, 211251\}$

■ **Number 651**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$651^2 + 868^2 := 1085^2$	$651^2 + 4300^2 := 4349^2$	$651^2 + 30268^2 := 30275^2$
$651^2 + 1368^2 := 1515^2$	$651^2 + 6820^2 := 6851^2$	$651^2 + 70632^2 := 70635^2$
$651^2 + 2232^2 := 2325^2$	$651^2 + 10080^2 := 10101^2$	$651^2 + 211900^2 := 211901^2$
$651^2 + 3332^2 := 3395^2$	$651^2 + 23540^2 := 23549^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(651, 23540, 23549)** $\Rightarrow 23549 - 23540 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 141267$, $T_9 := 651^2$,
 $E := \{47081, 47083, \dots, 47095, 47097\}$ or $E := \{47085, 47086, \dots, 47092, 47093\}$
2. **(651, 4300, 4349)** $\Rightarrow 4349 - 4300 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 60543$, $T_{49} := 651^2$,
 $E := \{8601, 8603, \dots, 8695, 8697\}$ or $E := \{8625, 8626, \dots, 8672, 8673\}$

■ Number 652

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$652^2 + 26565^2 := 26573^2$$

$$652^2 + 53136^2 := 53140^2$$

$$652^2 + 106275^2 := 106277^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(652, 26565, 26573)** $\Rightarrow 26573 - 652 = 161^2$, $S_{161 \times 161} := 4383225$, $T_{25921} := 26565^2$,
 $E := \{1305, 1307, \dots, 53143, 53145\}$ or $E := \{14265, 14266, \dots, 40184, 40185\}$

2. **(652, 106275, 106277)** $\Rightarrow 106277 - 652 = 325^2$, $S_{325 \times 325} := 34751925$, $T_{105625} := 106275^2$,
 $E := \{1305, 1307, \dots, 21251, 21253\}$ or $E := \{54117, 54118, \dots, 159740, 159741\}$

■ Number 653

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$653^2 + 213204^2 := 213205^2$$

■ Number 654

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$654^2 + 872^2 := 1090^2$$

$$654^2 + 11872^2 := 11890^2$$

$$654^2 + 35640^2 := 35646^2$$

$$654^2 + 106928^2 := 106930^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(654, 11872, 11890)** $\Rightarrow 11890 - 654 = 106^2$, $S_{106 \times 106} := 1329664$, $T_{11236} := 11872^2$,
 $E := \{1309, 1311, \dots, 23777, 23779\}$

2. **(654, 106928, 106930)** $\Rightarrow 106930 - 654 = 326^2$, $S_{326 \times 326} := 35072384$, $T_{106276} := 106928^2$,
 $E := \{1309, 1311, \dots, 213857, 213859\}$

■ Number 655

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$655^2 + 1572^2 := 1703^2$$

$$655^2 + 8568^2 := 8593^2$$

$$655^2 + 42900^2 := 42905^2$$

$$655^2 + 214512^2 := 214513^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(655, 8568, 8593)** $\Rightarrow 8593 - 8568 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 85805$, $T_{25} := 655^2$,
 $E := \{17137, 17139, \dots, 17183, 17185\}$ or $E := \{17149, 17150, \dots, 17172, 17173\}$

■ Number 656

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$656^2 + 1230^2 := 1394^2$$

$$656^2 + 1617^2 := 1745^2$$

$$656^2 + 2583^2 := 2665^2$$

$$656^2 + 3330^2 := 3394^2$$

$$656^2 + 6708^2 := 6740^2$$

$$656^2 + 13440^2 := 13456^2$$

$$656^2 + 26892^2 := 26900^2$$

$$656^2 + 53790^2 := 53794^2$$

$$656^2 + 107583^2 := 107585^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(656, 13440, 13456)** $\Rightarrow 13456 - 13440 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 107584$, $T_{16} := 656^2$,
 $E := \{26881, 26883, \dots, 26909, 26911\}$
2. **(656, 3330, 3394)** $\Rightarrow 3394 - 3330 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 53792$, $T_{64} := 656^2$,
 $E := \{6661, 6663, \dots, 6785, 6787\}$
3. **(656, 1617, 1745)** $\Rightarrow 1745 - 656 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 79233$, $T_{1089} := 1617^2$,
 $E := \{1313, 1315, \dots, 3487, 3489\}$ or $E := \{1857, 1858, \dots, 2944, 2945\}$
4. **(656, 6708, 6740)** $\Rightarrow 6740 - 656 = 78^2$, $S_{78 \times 78} := 576888$, $T_{6084} := 6708^2$,
 $E := \{1313, 1315, \dots, 13477, 13479\}$
5. **(656, 26892, 26900)** $\Rightarrow 26900 - 656 = 162^2$, $S_{162 \times 162} := 4464072$, $T_{26244} := 26892^2$,
 $E := \{1313, 1315, \dots, 53797, 53799\}$
6. **(656, 107583, 107585)** $\Rightarrow 107585 - 656 = 327^2$, $S_{327 \times 327} := 35394807$, $T_{106929} := 107583^2$,
 $E := \{1313, 1315, \dots, 215167, 215169\}$ or $E := \{54777, 54778, \dots, 161704, 161705\}$

■ Number 657

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$657^2 + 876^2 := 1095^2$$

$$657^2 + 2624^2 := 2705^2$$

$$657^2 + 2920^2 := 2993^2$$

$$657^2 + 7980^2 := 8007^2$$

$$657^2 + 23976^2 := 23985^2$$

$$657^2 + 71940^2 := 71943^2$$

$$657^2 + 215824^2 := 215825^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(657, 23976, 23985)** $\Rightarrow 23985 - 23976 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 143883$, $T_9 := 657^2$,
 $E := \{47953, 47955, \dots, 47967, 47969\}$ or $E := \{47957, 47958, \dots, 47964, 47965\}$
2. **(657, 2624, 2705)** $\Rightarrow 2705 - 2624 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 47961$, $T_{81} := 657^2$,
 $E := \{5249, 5251, \dots, 5407, 5409\}$ or $E := \{5289, 5290, \dots, 5368, 5369\}$

■ Number 658

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$658^2 + 2160^2 := 2258^2$$

$$658^2 + 2256^2 := 2350^2$$

$$658^2 + 15456^2 := 15470^2$$

$$658^2 + 108240^2 := 108242^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(658, 2160, 2258)** $\Rightarrow 2258 - 658 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 116640$, $T_{1600} := 2160^2$,
 $E := \{1317, 1319, \dots, 4513, 4515\}$
2. **(658, 108240, 108242)** $\Rightarrow 108242 - 658 = 328^2$, $S_{328 \times 328} := 35719200$, $T_{107584} := 108240^2$,
 $E := \{1317, 1319, \dots, 216481, 216483\}$

■ Number 659

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$659^2 + 217140^2 := 217141^2$$

■ Number 660

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$660^2 + 693^2 := 957^2$	$660^2 + 2128^2 := 2228^2$	$660^2 + 7245^2 := 7275^2$
$660^2 + 779^2 := 1021^2$	$660^2 + 2375^2 := 2465^2$	$660^2 + 9063^2 := 9087^2$
$660^2 + 880^2 := 1100^2$	$660^2 + 2431^2 := 2519^2$	$660^2 + 9889^2 := 9911^2$
$660^2 + 989^2 := 1189^2$	$660^2 + 2989^2 := 3061^2$	$660^2 + 10880^2 := 10900^2$
$660^2 + 1001^2 := 1199^2$	$660^2 + 3267^2 := 3333^2$	$660^2 + 12091^2 := 12109^2$
$660^2 + 1120^2 := 1300^2$	$660^2 + 3600^2 := 3660^2$	$660^2 + 18144^2 := 18156^2$
$660^2 + 1377^2 := 1527^2$	$660^2 + 4331^2 := 4381^2$	$660^2 + 21775^2 := 21785^2$
$660^2 + 1584^2 := 1716^2$	$660^2 + 4928^2 := 4972^2$	$660^2 + 27221^2 := 27229^2$
$660^2 + 1755^2 := 1875^2$	$660^2 + 5425^2 := 5465^2$	$660^2 + 36297^2 := 36303^2$
$660^2 + 1925^2 := 2035^2$	$660^2 + 6032^2 := 6068^2$	$660^2 + 54448^2 := 54452^2$
		$660^2 + 108899^2 := 108901^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(660, 6032, 6068)** $\Rightarrow 6068 - 6032 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 72600$, $T_{36} := 660^2$,
 $E := \{12065, 12067, \dots, 12133, 12135\}$
2. **(660, 2128, 2228)** $\Rightarrow 2228 - 2128 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 43560$, $T_{100} := 660^2$,
 $E := \{4257, 4259, \dots, 4453, 4455\}$
3. **(660, 779, 1021)** $\Rightarrow 1021 - 660 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 31939$, $T_{361} := 779^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 2039, 2041\}$ or $E := \{1501, 1502, \dots, 1860, 1861\}$
4. **(660, 989, 1189)** $\Rightarrow 1189 - 660 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 42527$, $T_{529} := 989^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 2375, 2377\}$ or $E := \{1585, 1586, \dots, 2112, 2113\}$
5. **(660, 2989, 3061)** $\Rightarrow 3061 - 660 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 182329$, $T_{2401} := 2989^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 6119, 6121\}$ or $E := \{2521, 2522, \dots, 4920, 4921\}$
6. **(660, 4331, 4381)** $\Rightarrow 4381 - 660 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 307501$, $T_{3721} := 4331^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 8759, 8761\}$ or $E := \{3181, 3182, \dots, 6900, 6901\}$
7. **(660, 12091, 12109)** $\Rightarrow 12109 - 660 = 107^2$, $S_{107 \times 107} := 1366283$, $T_{11449} := 12091^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 24215, 24217\}$ or $E := \{7045, 7046, \dots, 18492, 18493\}$
8. **(660, 27221, 27229)** $\Rightarrow 27229 - 660 = 163^2$, $S_{163 \times 163} := 4545907$, $T_{26569} := 27221^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 54455, 54457\}$ or $E := \{14605, 14606, \dots, 41172, 41173\}$
9. **(660, 108899, 108901)** $\Rightarrow 108901 - 660 = 329^2$, $S_{329 \times 329} := 36045569$, $T_{108241} := 108899^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 217799, 217801\}$ or $E := \{55441, 55442, \dots, 163680, 163681\}$

■ Number 661

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$661^2 + 218460^2 := 218461^2$$

■ Number 662

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$662^2 + 109560^2 := 109562^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(662, 109560, 109562)** $\Rightarrow 109562 - 662 = 330^2$, $S_{330 \times 330} := 36373920$, $T_{108900} := 109560^2$,
 $E := \{1325, 1327, \dots, 219121, 219123\}$

■ Number 663

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$663^2 + 884^2 := 1105^2$$

$$663^2 + 1216^2 := 1385^2$$

$$663^2 + 1360^2 := 1513^2$$

$$663^2 + 1820^2 := 1937^2$$

$$663^2 + 4284^2 := 4335^2$$

$$663^2 + 5616^2 := 5655^2$$

$$663^2 + 12920^2 := 12937^2$$

$$663^2 + 16900^2 := 16913^2$$

$$663^2 + 24416^2 := 24425^2$$

$$663^2 + 73260^2 := 73263^2$$

$$663^2 + 219784^2 := 219785^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(663, 24416, 24425)** $\Rightarrow 24425 - 24416 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 146523$, $T_9 := 663^2$,
 $E := \{48833, 48835, \dots, 48847, 48849\}$ or $E := \{48837, 48838, \dots, 48844, 48845\}$
2. **(663, 1216, 1385)** $\Rightarrow 1385 - 1216 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 33813$, $T_{169} := 663^2$,
 $E := \{2433, 2435, \dots, 2767, 2769\}$ or $E := \{2517, 2518, \dots, 2684, 2685\}$

■ Number 664

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$664^2 + 1245^2 := 1411^2$$

$$664^2 + 6873^2 := 6905^2$$

$$664^2 + 13770^2 := 13786^2$$

$$664^2 + 27552^2 := 27560^2$$

$$664^2 + 55110^2 := 55114^2$$

$$664^2 + 110223^2 := 110225^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(664, 13770, 13786)** $\Rightarrow 13786 - 13770 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 110224$, $T_{16} := 664^2$,
 $E := \{27541, 27543, \dots, 27569, 27571\}$
2. **(664, 6873, 6905)** $\Rightarrow 6905 - 664 = 79^2$, $S_{79 \times 79} := 597951$, $T_{6241} := 6873^2$,
 $E := \{1329, 1331, \dots, 13807, 13809\}$ or $E := \{4449, 4450, \dots, 10688, 10689\}$
3. **(664, 27552, 27560)** $\Rightarrow 27560 - 664 = 164^2$, $S_{164 \times 164} := 4628736$, $T_{26896} := 27552^2$,
 $E := \{1329, 1331, \dots, 55117, 55119\}$
4. **(664, 110223, 110225)** $\Rightarrow 110225 - 664 = 331^2$, $S_{331 \times 331} := 36704259$, $T_{109561} := 110223^2$,
 $E := \{1329, 1331, \dots, 220447, 220449\}$ or $E := \{56109, 56110, \dots, 165668, 165669\}$

■ **Number 665**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$665^2 + 780^2 := 1025^2$	$665^2 + 4488^2 := 4537^2$	$665^2 + 31584^2 := 31591^2$
$665^2 + 1176^2 := 1351^2$	$665^2 + 6300^2 := 6335^2$	$665^2 + 44220^2 := 44225^2$
$665^2 + 1596^2 := 1729^2$	$665^2 + 8832^2 := 8857^2$	$665^2 + 221112^2 := 221113^2$
$665^2 + 2280^2 := 2375^2$	$665^2 + 11628^2 := 11647^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(665, 8832, 8857)** $\Rightarrow 8857 - 8832 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 88445$, $T_{25} := 665^2$,
 $E := \{17665, 17667, \dots, 17711, 17713\}$ or $E := \{17677, 17678, \dots, 17700, 17701\}$
2. **(665, 4488, 4537)** $\Rightarrow 4537 - 4488 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 63175$, $T_{49} := 665^2$,
 $E := \{8977, 8979, \dots, 9071, 9073\}$ or $E := \{9001, 9002, \dots, 9048, 9049\}$

■ **Number 666**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$666^2 + 888^2 := 1110^2$	$666^2 + 12312^2 := 12330^2$
$666^2 + 1288^2 := 1450^2$	$666^2 + 36960^2 := 36966^2$
$666^2 + 2960^2 := 3034^2$	$666^2 + 110888^2 := 110890^2$
$666^2 + 4080^2 := 4134^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(666, 1288, 1450)** $\Rightarrow 1450 - 666 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 59248$, $T_{784} := 1288^2$,
 $E := \{1333, 1335, \dots, 2897, 2899\}$
2. **(666, 12312, 12330)** $\Rightarrow 12330 - 666 = 108^2$, $S_{108 \times 108} := 1403568$, $T_{11664} := 12312^2$,
 $E := \{1333, 1335, \dots, 24657, 24659\}$
3. **(666, 110888, 110890)** $\Rightarrow 110890 - 666 = 332^2$, $S_{332 \times 332} := 37036592$, $T_{110224} := 110888^2$,
 $E := \{1333, 1335, \dots, 221777, 221779\}$

■ Number 667

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned}667^2 + 7656^2 &:= 7685^2 \\667^2 + 9660^2 &:= 9683^2 \\667^2 + 222444^2 &:= 222445^2\end{aligned}$$

■ Number 668

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned}668^2 + 27885^2 &:= 27893^2 \\668^2 + 55776^2 &:= 55780^2 \\668^2 + 111555^2 &:= 111557^2\end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(668, 27885, 27893)** $\Rightarrow 27893 - 668 = 165^2$, $S_{165 \times 165} := 4712565$, $T_{27225} := 27885^2$,
 $E := \{1337, 1339, \dots, 55783, 55785\}$ or $E := \{14949, 14950, \dots, 42172, 42173\}$
2. **(668, 111555, 111557)** $\Rightarrow 111557 - 668 = 333^2$, $S_{333 \times 333} := 37370925$, $T_{110889} := 111555^2$,
 $E := \{1337, 1339, \dots, 223111, 223113\}$ or $E := \{56781, 56782, \dots, 167668, 167669\}$

■ Number 669

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$669^2 + 892^2 := 1115^2$$

$$669^2 + 24860^2 := 24869^2$$

$$669^2 + 74592^2 := 74595^2$$

$$669^2 + 223780^2 := 223781^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(669, 24860, 24869)** $\Rightarrow 24869 - 24860 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 149187$, $T_9 := 669^2$,
 $E := \{49721, 49723, \dots, 49735, 49737\}$ or $E := \{49725, 49726, \dots, 49732, 49733\}$

■ Number 670

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$670^2 + 1608^2 := 1742^2$$

$$670^2 + 4464^2 := 4514^2$$

$$670^2 + 22440^2 := 22450^2$$

$$670^2 + 112224^2 := 112226^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(670, 4464, 4514)** $\Rightarrow 4514 - 670 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 321408$, $T_{3844} := 4464^2$,
 $E := \{1341, 1343, \dots, 9025, 9027\}$
2. **(670, 112224, 112226)** $\Rightarrow 112226 - 670 = 334^2$, $S_{334 \times 334} := 37707264$, $T_{111556} := 112224^2$,
 $E := \{1341, 1343, \dots, 224449, 224451\}$

■ Number 671

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$671^2 + 1800^2 := 1921^2$$

$$671^2 + 3660^2 := 3721^2$$

$$671^2 + 20460^2 := 20471^2$$

$$671^2 + 225120^2 := 225121^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(671, 1800, 1921)** $\Rightarrow 1921 - 1800 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 40931$, $T_{121} := 671^2$,
 $E := \{3601, 3603, \dots, 3839, 3841\}$ or $E := \{3661, 3662, \dots, 3780, 3781\}$

■ Number 672

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$672^2 + 754^2 := 1010^2$	$672^2 + 2255^2 := 2353^2$	$672^2 + 8050^2 := 8078^2$
$672^2 + 770^2 := 1022^2$	$672^2 + 2304^2 := 2400^2$	$672^2 + 9396^2 := 9420^2$
$672^2 + 896^2 := 1120^2$	$672^2 + 2646^2 := 2730^2$	$672^2 + 12535^2 := 12553^2$
$672^2 + 1054^2 := 1250^2$	$672^2 + 3100^2 := 3172^2$	$672^2 + 14104^2 := 14120^2$
$672^2 + 1080^2 := 1272^2$	$672^2 + 3496^2 := 3560^2$	$672^2 + 16121^2 := 16135^2$
$672^2 + 1260^2 := 1428^2$	$672^2 + 4004^2 := 4060^2$	$672^2 + 18810^2 := 18822^2$
$672^2 + 1496^2 := 1640^2$	$672^2 + 4680^2 := 4728^2$	$672^2 + 28220^2 := 28228^2$
$672^2 + 1700^2 := 1828^2$	$672^2 + 5355^2 := 5397^2$	$672^2 + 37629^2 := 37635^2$
$672^2 + 1729^2 := 1855^2$	$672^2 + 6254^2 := 6290^2$	$672^2 + 56446^2 := 56450^2$
$672^2 + 1960^2 := 2072^2$	$672^2 + 7040^2 := 7072^2$	$672^2 + 112895^2 := 112897^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(672, 14104, 14120)** $\Rightarrow 14120 - 14104 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 112896$, $T_{16} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{28209, 28211, \dots, 28237, 28239\}$
2. **(672, 6254, 6290)** $\Rightarrow 6290 - 6254 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 75264$, $T_{36} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{12509, 12511, \dots, 12577, 12579\}$
3. **(672, 3496, 3560)** $\Rightarrow 3560 - 3496 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 56448$, $T_{64} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{6993, 6995, \dots, 7117, 7119\}$
4. **(672, 1496, 1640)** $\Rightarrow 1640 - 1496 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 37632$, $T_{144} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{2993, 2995, \dots, 3277, 3279\}$
5. **(672, 1054, 1250)** $\Rightarrow 1250 - 1054 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 32256$, $T_{196} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{2109, 2111, \dots, 2497, 2499\}$
6. **(672, 754, 1010)** $\Rightarrow 1010 - 754 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 28224$, $T_{256} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{1509, 1511, \dots, 2017, 2019\}$
7. **(672, 1700, 1828)** $\Rightarrow 1828 - 672 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 85000$, $T_{1156} := 1700^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 3653, 3655\}$
8. **(672, 2255, 2353)** $\Rightarrow 2353 - 672 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 124025$, $T_{1681} := 2255^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 4703, 4705\}$ or $E := \{2185, 2186, \dots, 3864, 3865\}$
9. **(672, 3100, 3172)** $\Rightarrow 3172 - 672 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 192200$, $T_{2500} := 3100^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 6341, 6343\}$
10. **(672, 7040, 7072)** $\Rightarrow 7072 - 672 = 80^2$, $S_{80 \times 80} := 619520$, $T_{6400} := 7040^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 14141, 14143\}$
11. **(672, 12535, 12553)** $\Rightarrow 12553 - 672 = 109^2$, $S_{109 \times 109} := 1441525$, $T_{11881} := 12535^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 25103, 25105\}$ or $E := \{7285, 7286, \dots, 19164, 19165\}$

12. **(672, 28220, 28228)** $\Rightarrow 28228 - 672 = 166^2$, $S_{166 \times 166} := 4797400$, $T_{27556} := 28220^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 56453, 56455\}$

13. **(672, 112895, 112897)** $\Rightarrow 112897 - 672 = 335^2$, $S_{335 \times 335} := 38045615$, $T_{112225} := 112895^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 225791, 225793\}$ or $E := \{57457, 57458, \dots, 169680, 169681\}$

■ Number 673

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$673^2 + 226464^2 := 226465^2$$

■ Number 674

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$674^2 + 113568^2 := 113570^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(674, 113568, 113570)** $\Rightarrow 113570 - 674 = 336^2$, $S_{336 \times 336} := 38385984$, $T_{112896} := 113568^2$,
 $E := \{1349, 1351, \dots, 227137, 227139\}$

■ Number 675

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$675^2 + 816^2 := 1059^2$$

$$675^2 + 900^2 := 1125^2$$

$$675^2 + 1620^2 := 1755^2$$

$$675^2 + 1760^2 := 1885^2$$

$$675^2 + 2772^2 := 2853^2$$

$$675^2 + 3000^2 := 3075^2$$

$$675^2 + 5040^2 := 5085^2$$

$$675^2 + 8424^2 := 8451^2$$

$$675^2 + 9100^2 := 9125^2$$

$$675^2 + 15180^2 := 15195^2$$

$$675^2 + 25308^2 := 25317^2$$

$$675^2 + 45560^2 := 45565^2$$

$$675^2 + 75936^2 := 75939^2$$

$$675^2 + 227812^2 := 227813^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(675, 25308, 25317)** $\Rightarrow 25317 - 25308 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 151875$, $T_9 := 675^2$,
 $E := \{50617, 50619, \dots, 50631, 50633\}$ or $E := \{50621, 50622, \dots, 50628, 50629\}$
2. **(675, 9100, 9125)** $\Rightarrow 9125 - 9100 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 91125$, $T_{25} := 675^2$,
 $E := \{18201, 18203, \dots, 18247, 18249\}$ or $E := \{18213, 18214, \dots, 18236, 18237\}$

3. **(675, 2772, 2853)** $\Rightarrow 2853 - 2772 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 50625$, $T_{81} := 675^2$,
 $E := \{5545, 5547, \dots, 5703, 5705\}$ or $E := \{5585, 5586, \dots, 5664, 5665\}$
4. **(675, 900, 1125)** $\Rightarrow 1125 - 900 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 30375$, $T_{225} := 675^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 2247, 2249\}$ or $E := \{1913, 1914, \dots, 2136, 2137\}$

■ Number 676

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 676^2 + 2145^2 := 2249^2 & 676^2 + 28557^2 := 28565^2 \\ 676^2 + 4368^2 := 4420^2 & 676^2 + 57120^2 := 57124^2 \\ 676^2 + 8775^2 := 8801^2 & 676^2 + 114243^2 := 114245^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(676, 28557, 28565)** $\Rightarrow 28565 - 676 = 167^2$, $S_{167 \times 167} := 4883247$, $T_{27889} := 28557^2$,
 $E := \{1353, 1355, \dots, 57127, 57129\}$ or $E := \{15297, 15298, \dots, 43184, 43185\}$
2. **(676, 114243, 114245)** $\Rightarrow 114245 - 676 = 337^2$, $S_{337 \times 337} := 38728377$, $T_{113569} := 114243^2$,
 $E := \{1353, 1355, \dots, 228487, 228489\}$ or $E := \{58137, 58138, \dots, 171704, 171705\}$

■ Number 677

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$677^2 + 229164^2 := 229165^2$$

■ Number 678

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 678^2 + 904^2 := 1130^2 & 678^2 + 38304^2 := 38310^2 \\ 678^2 + 12760^2 := 12778^2 & 678^2 + 114920^2 := 114922^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(678, 12760, 12778)** $\Rightarrow 12778 - 678 = 110^2$, $S_{110 \times 110} := 1480160$, $T_{12100} := 12760^2$,
 $E := \{1357, 1359, \dots, 25553, 25555\}$

2. **(678, 114920, 114922)** $\Rightarrow 114922 - 678 = 338^2$, $S_{338 \times 338} := 39072800$, $T_{114244} := 114920^2$,
 $E := \{1357, 1359, \dots, 229841, 229843\}$

■ Number 679

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$679^2 + 2328^2 := 2425^2$$

$$679^2 + 4680^2 := 4729^2$$

$$679^2 + 32928^2 := 32935^2$$

$$679^2 + 230520^2 := 230521^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(679, 4680, 4729)** $\Rightarrow 4729 - 4680 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 65863$, $T_{49} := 679^2$,
 $E := \{9361, 9363, \dots, 9455, 9457\}$ or $E := \{9385, 9386, \dots, 9432, 9433\}$

■ Number 680

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$680^2 + 714^2 := 986^2$$

$$680^2 + 1056^2 := 1256^2$$

$$680^2 + 1275^2 := 1445^2$$

$$680^2 + 1365^2 := 1525^2$$

$$680^2 + 1632^2 := 1768^2$$

$$680^2 + 2262^2 := 2362^2$$

$$680^2 + 2850^2 := 2930^2$$

$$680^2 + 3366^2 := 3434^2$$

$$680^2 + 4599^2 := 4649^2$$

$$680^2 + 5760^2 := 5800^2$$

$$680^2 + 6783^2 := 6817^2$$

$$680^2 + 7209^2 := 7241^2$$

$$680^2 + 11550^2 := 11570^2$$

$$680^2 + 14442^2 := 14458^2$$

$$680^2 + 23115^2 := 23125^2$$

$$680^2 + 28896^2 := 28904^2$$

$$680^2 + 57798^2 := 57802^2$$

$$680^2 + 115599^2 := 115601^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(680, 14442, 14458)** $\Rightarrow 14458 - 14442 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 115600$, $T_{16} := 680^2$,
 $E := \{28885, 28887, \dots, 28913, 28915\}$
2. **(680, 2262, 2362)** $\Rightarrow 2362 - 2262 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 46240$, $T_{100} := 680^2$,
 $E := \{4525, 4527, \dots, 4721, 4723\}$
3. **(680, 1056, 1256)** $\Rightarrow 1256 - 680 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 46464$, $T_{576} := 1056^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 2509, 2511\}$
4. **(680, 4599, 4649)** $\Rightarrow 4649 - 680 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 335727$, $T_{3969} := 4599^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 9295, 9297\}$ or $E := \{3345, 3346, \dots, 7312, 7313\}$
5. **(680, 7209, 7241)** $\Rightarrow 7241 - 680 = 81^2$, $S_{81 \times 81} := 641601$, $T_{6561} := 7209^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 14479, 14481\}$ or $E := \{4641, 4642, \dots, 11200, 11201\}$

6. **(680, 28896, 28904)** $\Rightarrow 28904 - 680 = 168^2$, $S_{168 \times 168} := 4970112$, $T_{28224} := 28896^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 57805, 57807\}$

7. **(680, 115599, 115601)** $\Rightarrow 115601 - 680 = 339^2$, $S_{339 \times 339} := 39419259$, $T_{114921} := 115599^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 231199, 231201\}$ or $E := \{58821, 58822, \dots, 173740, 173741\}$

■ Number 681

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$681^2 + 908^2 := 1135^2$$

$$681^2 + 25760^2 := 25769^2$$

$$681^2 + 77292^2 := 77295^2$$

$$681^2 + 231880^2 := 231881^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(681, 25760, 25769)** $\Rightarrow 25769 - 25760 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 154587$, $T_9 := 681^2$,
 $E := \{51521, 51523, \dots, 51535, 51537\}$ or $E := \{51525, 51526, \dots, 51532, 51533\}$

■ Number 682

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$682^2 + 840^2 := 1082^2$$

$$682^2 + 3720^2 := 3782^2$$

$$682^2 + 10560^2 := 10582^2$$

$$682^2 + 116280^2 := 116282^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(682, 840, 1082)** $\Rightarrow 1082 - 682 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 35280$, $T_{400} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{1365, 1367, \dots, 2161, 2163\}$
2. **(682, 116280, 116282)** $\Rightarrow 116282 - 682 = 340^2$, $S_{340 \times 340} := 39767760$, $T_{115600} := 116280^2$,
 $E := \{1365, 1367, \dots, 232561, 232563\}$

■ Number 683

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$683^2 + 233244^2 := 23345^2$$

■ Number 684

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$684^2 + 912^2 := 1140^2$$

$$684^2 + 975^2 := 1191^2$$

$$684^2 + 1363^2 := 1525^2$$

$$684^2 + 1463^2 := 1615^2$$

$$684^2 + 1995^2 := 2109^2$$

$$684^2 + 2112^2 := 2220^2$$

$$684^2 + 3040^2 := 3116^2$$

$$684^2 + 3213^2 := 3285^2$$

$$684^2 + 4305^2 := 4359^2$$

$$684^2 + 6137^2 := 6175^2$$

$$684^2 + 6480^2 := 6516^2$$

$$684^2 + 9735^2 := 9759^2$$

$$684^2 + 12987^2 := 13005^2$$

$$684^2 + 19488^2 := 19500^2$$

$$684^2 + 29237^2 := 29245^2$$

$$684^2 + 38985^2 := 38991^2$$

$$684^2 + 58480^2 := 58484^2$$

$$684^2 + 116963^2 := 116965^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(684, 6480, 6516)** $\Rightarrow 6516 - 6480 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 77976$, $T_{36} := 684^2$,
 $E := \{12961, 12963, \dots, 13029, 13031\}$
2. **(684, 1363, 1525)** $\Rightarrow 1525 - 684 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 64061$, $T_{841} := 1363^2$,
 $E := \{1369, 1371, \dots, 3047, 3049\}$ or $E := \{1789, 1790, \dots, 2628, 2629\}$
3. **(684, 3213, 3285)** $\Rightarrow 3285 - 684 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 202419$, $T_{2601} := 3213^2$,
 $E := \{1369, 1371, \dots, 6567, 6569\}$ or $E := \{2669, 2670, \dots, 5268, 5269\}$
4. **(684, 12987, 13005)** $\Rightarrow 13005 - 684 = 111^2$, $S_{111 \times 111} := 1519479$, $T_{12321} := 12987^2$,
 $E := \{1369, 1371, \dots, 26007, 26009\}$ or $E := \{7529, 7530, \dots, 19848, 19849\}$
5. **(684, 29237, 29245)** $\Rightarrow 29245 - 684 = 169^2$, $S_{169 \times 169} := 5058001$, $T_{28561} := 29237^2$,
 $E := \{1369, 1371, \dots, 58487, 58489\}$ or $E := \{15649, 15650, \dots, 44208, 44209\}$
6. **(684, 116963, 116965)** $\Rightarrow 116965 - 684 = 341^2$, $S_{341 \times 341} := 40118309$, $T_{116281} := 116963^2$,
 $E := \{1369, 1371, \dots, 233927, 233929\}$ or $E := \{59509, 59510, \dots, 175788, 175789\}$

■ Number 685

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$685^2 + 1644^2 := 1781^2$$

$$685^2 + 9372^2 := 9397^2$$

$$685^2 + 46920^2 := 46925^2$$

$$685^2 + 234612^2 := 234613^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(685, 9372, 9397)** $\Rightarrow 9397 - 9372 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 93845$, $T_{25} := 685^2$,
 $E := \{18745, 18747, \dots, 18791, 18793\}$ or $E := \{18757, 18758, \dots, 18780, 18781\}$

■ Number 686

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$686^2 + 2352^2 := 2450^2$$

$$686^2 + 16800^2 := 16814^2$$

$$686^2 + 117648^2 := 117650^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(686, 2352, 2450)** $\Rightarrow 2450 - 686 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 131712$, $T_{1764} := 2352^2$,
 $E := \{1373, 1375, \dots, 4897, 4899\}$

2. **(686, 117648, 117650)** $\Rightarrow 117650 - 686 = 342^2$, $S_{342 \times 342} := 40470912$, $T_{116964} := 117648^2$,
 $E := \{1373, 1375, \dots, 235297, 235299\}$

■ Number 687

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$687^2 + 916^2 := 1145^2$$

$$687^2 + 26216^2 := 26225^2$$

$$687^2 + 78660^2 := 78663^2$$

$$687^2 + 235984^2 := 235985^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(687, 26216, 26225)** $\Rightarrow 26225 - 26216 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 157323$, $T_9 := 687^2$,
 $E := \{52433, 52435, \dots, 52447, 52449\}$ or $E := \{52437, 52438, \dots, 52444, 52445\}$

■ Number 688

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$688^2 + 1290^2 := 1462^2$$

$$688^2 + 1785^2 := 1913^2$$

$$688^2 + 2709^2 := 2795^2$$

$$688^2 + 3666^2 := 3730^2$$

$$688^2 + 7380^2 := 7412^2$$

$$688^2 + 14784^2 := 14800^2$$

$$688^2 + 29580^2 := 29588^2$$

$$688^2 + 59166^2 := 59170^2$$

$$688^2 + 118335^2 := 118337^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(688, 14784, 14800)** $\Rightarrow 14800 - 14784 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 118336$, $T_{16} := 688^2$,
 $E := \{29569, 29571, \dots, 29597, 29599\}$

2. **(688, 3666, 3730)** $\Rightarrow 3730 - 3666 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 59168$, $T_{64} := 688^2$,
 $E := \{7333, 7335, \dots, 7457, 7459\}$
3. **(688, 1785, 1913)** $\Rightarrow 1913 - 688 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 91035$, $T_{1225} := 1785^2$,
 $E := \{1377, 1379, \dots, 3823, 3825\}$ or $E := \{1989, 1990, \dots, 3212, 3213\}$
4. **(688, 7380, 7412)** $\Rightarrow 7412 - 688 = 82^2$, $S_{82 \times 82} := 664200$, $T_{6724} := 7380^2$,
 $E := \{1377, 1379, \dots, 14821, 14823\}$
5. **(688, 29580, 29588)** $\Rightarrow 29588 - 688 = 170^2$, $S_{170 \times 170} := 5146920$, $T_{28900} := 29580^2$,
 $E := \{1377, 1379, \dots, 59173, 59175\}$
6. **(688, 118335, 118337)** $\Rightarrow 118337 - 688 = 343^2$, $S_{343 \times 343} := 40825575$, $T_{117649} := 118335^2$,
 $E := \{1377, 1379, \dots, 236671, 236673\}$ or $E := \{60201, 60202, \dots, 177848, 177849\}$

■ Number 689

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$689^2 + 1320^2 := 1489^2$$

$$689^2 + 4452^2 := 4505^2$$

$$689^2 + 18252^2 := 18265^2$$

$$689^2 + 237360^2 := 237361^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(689, 1320, 1489)** $\Rightarrow 1489 - 1320 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 36517$, $T_{169} := 689^2$,
 $E := \{2641, 2643, \dots, 2975, 2977\}$ or $E := \{2725, 2726, \dots, 2892, 2893\}$

■ Number 690

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$690^2 + 920^2 := 1150^2$$

$$690^2 + 1512^2 := 1662^2$$

$$690^2 + 1656^2 := 1794^2$$

$$690^2 + 2600^2 := 2690^2$$

$$690^2 + 4736^2 := 4786^2$$

$$690^2 + 5152^2 := 5198^2$$

$$690^2 + 7920^2 := 7950^2$$

$$690^2 + 13216^2 := 13234^2$$

$$690^2 + 23800^2 := 23810^2$$

$$690^2 + 39672^2 := 39678^2$$

$$690^2 + 119024^2 := 119026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(690, 4736, 4786)** $\Rightarrow 4786 - 690 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 350464$, $T_{4096} := 4736^2$,
 $E := \{1381, 1383, \dots, 9569, 9571\}$
2. **(690, 13216, 13234)** $\Rightarrow 13234 - 690 = 112^2$, $S_{112 \times 112} := 1559488$, $T_{12544} := 13216^2$,
 $E := \{1381, 1383, \dots, 26465, 26467\}$

3. **(690, 119024, 119026)** $\Rightarrow 119026 - 690 = 344^2$, $S_{344 \times 344} := 41182304$, $T_{118336} := 119024^2$,
 $E := \{1381, 1383, \dots, 238049, 238051\}$

■ Number 690

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$691^2 + 238740^2 := 238741^2$$

■ Number 692

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$692^2 + 29925^2 := 29933^2$$

$$692^2 + 59856^2 := 59860^2$$

$$692^2 + 119715^2 := 119717^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(692, 29925, 29933)** $\Rightarrow 29933 - 692 = 171^2$, $S_{171 \times 171} := 5236875$, $T_{29241} := 29925^2$,
 $E := \{1385, 1387, \dots, 59863, 59865\}$ or $E := \{16005, 16006, \dots, 45244, 45245\}$

2. **(692, 119715, 119717)** $\Rightarrow 119717 - 692 = 345^2$, $S_{345 \times 345} := 41541105$, $T_{119025} := 119715^2$,
 $E := \{1385, 1387, \dots, 239431, 239433\}$ or $E := \{60897, 60898, \dots, 179920, 179921\}$

■ Number 693

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$693^2 + 924^2 := 1155^2$$

$$693^2 + 1176^2 := 1365^2$$

$$693^2 + 1560^2 := 1707^2$$

$$693^2 + 1924^2 := 2045^2$$

$$693^2 + 2376^2 := 2475^2$$

$$693^2 + 2924^2 := 3005^2$$

$$693^2 + 3080^2 := 3157^2$$

$$693^2 + 3780^2 := 3843^2$$

$$693^2 + 4876^2 := 4925^2$$

$$693^2 + 7260^2 := 7293^2$$

$$693^2 + 8880^2 := 8907^2$$

$$693^2 + 11424^2 := 11445^2$$

$$693^2 + 21824^2 := 21835^2$$

$$693^2 + 26676^2 := 26685^2$$

$$693^2 + 34300^2 := 34307^2$$

$$693^2 + 80040^2 := 80043^2$$

$$693^2 + 240124^2 := 240125^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(693, 26676, 26685)** $\Rightarrow 26685 - 26676 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 160083$, $T_9 := 693^2$,
 $E := \{53353, 53355, \dots, 53367, 53369\}$ or $E := \{53357, 53358, \dots, 53364, 53365\}$
2. **(693, 4876, 4925)** $\Rightarrow 4925 - 4876 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 68607$, $T_{49} := 693^2$,
 $E := \{9753, 9755, \dots, 9847, 9849\}$ or $E := \{9777, 9778, \dots, 9824, 9825\}$
3. **(693, 2924, 3005)** $\Rightarrow 3005 - 2924 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 53361$, $T_{81} := 693^2$,
 $E := \{5849, 5851, \dots, 6007, 6009\}$ or $E := \{5889, 5890, \dots, 5968, 5969\}$
4. **(693, 1924, 2045)** $\Rightarrow 2045 - 1924 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 43659$, $T_{121} := 693^2$,
 $E := \{3849, 3851, \dots, 4087, 4089\}$ or $E := \{3909, 3910, \dots, 4028, 4029\}$

■ Number 694

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$694^2 + 120408^2 := 120410^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(694, 120408, 120410)** $\Rightarrow 120410 - 694 = 346^2$, $S_{346 \times 346} := 41901984$, $T_{119716} := 120408^2$,
 $E := \{1389, 1391, \dots, 240817, 240819\}$

■ Number 695

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$695^2 + 1668^2 := 1807^2$$

$$695^2 + 9648^2 := 9673^2$$

$$695^2 + 48300^2 := 48305^2$$

$$695^2 + 241512^2 := 241513^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(695, 9648, 9673)** $\Rightarrow 9673 - 9648 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 96605$, $T_{25} := 695^2$,
 $E := \{19297, 19299, \dots, 19343, 19345\}$ or $E := \{19309, 19310, \dots, 19332, 19333\}$

■ Number 696

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$696^2 + 697^2 := 985^2$$

$$696^2 + 928^2 := 1160^2$$

$$696^2 + 1305^2 := 1479^2$$

$$696^2 + 1610^2 := 1754^2$$

$$696^2 + 2030^2 := 2146^2$$

$$696^2 + 2475^2 := 2571^2$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 696^2 + 3328^2 := 3400^2 & \\
 696^2 + 4147^2 := 4205^2 & 696^2 + 13447^2 := 13465^2 \\
 696^2 + 5022^2 := 5070^2 & 696^2 + 15130^2 := 15146^2 \\
 696^2 + 6710^2 := 6746^2 & 696^2 + 20178^2 := 20190^2 \\
 696^2 + 7553^2 := 7585^2 & 696^2 + 30272^2 := 30280^2 \\
 696^2 + 10080^2 := 10104^2 & 696^2 + 40365^2 := 40371^2 \\
 & 696^2 + 60550^2 := 60554^2 \\
 & 696^2 + 121103^2 := 121105^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(696, 15130, 15146)** $\Rightarrow 15146 - 15130 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 121104$, $T_{16} := 696^2$,
 $E := \{30261, 30263, \dots, 30289, 30291\}$
2. **(696, 6710, 6746)** $\Rightarrow 6746 - 6710 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 80736$, $T_{36} := 696^2$,
 $E := \{13421, 13423, \dots, 13489, 13491\}$
3. **(696, 1610, 1754)** $\Rightarrow 1754 - 1610 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 40368$, $T_{144} := 696^2$,
 $E := \{3221, 3223, \dots, 3505, 3507\}$
4. **(696, 697, 985)** $\Rightarrow 985 - 696 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 28577$, $T_{289} := 697^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 1967, 1969\}$ or $E := \{1537, 1538, \dots, 1824, 1825\}$
5. **(696, 3328, 3400)** $\Rightarrow 3400 - 696 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 212992$, $T_{2704} := 3328^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 6797, 6799\}$
6. **(696, 7553, 7585)** $\Rightarrow 7585 - 696 = 83^2$, $S_{83 \times 83} := 687323$, $T_{6889} := 7553^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 15167, 15169\}$ or $E := \{4837, 4838, \dots, 11724, 11725\}$
7. **(696, 13447, 13465)** $\Rightarrow 13465 - 696 = 113^2$, $S_{113 \times 113} := 1600193$, $T_{12769} := 13447^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 26927, 26929\}$ or $E := \{7777, 7778, \dots, 20544, 20545\}$
8. **(696, 30272, 30280)** $\Rightarrow 30280 - 696 = 172^2$, $S_{172 \times 172} := 5327872$, $T_{29584} := 30272^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 60557, 60559\}$
9. **(696, 121103, 121105)** $\Rightarrow 121105 - 696 = 347^2$, $S_{347 \times 347} := 42264947$, $T_{120409} := 121103^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 242207, 242209\}$ or $E := \{61597, 61598, \dots, 182004, 182005\}$

■ **Number 697**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 697^2 + 5904^2 := 5945^2 & \\
 697^2 + 14280^2 := 14297^2 & \\
 697^2 + 242904^2 := 242905^2 &
 \end{array}$$

■ Number 698

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$698^2 + 121800^2 := 121802^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(698, 121800, 121802)** $\Rightarrow 121802 - 698 = 348^2$, $S_{348 \times 348} := 42630000$, $T_{121104} := 121800^2$,
 $E := \{1397, 1399, \dots, 243601, 243603\}$

■ Number 699

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$699^2 + 932^2 := 1165^2$$

$$699^2 + 27140^2 := 27149^2$$

$$699^2 + 81432^2 := 81435^2$$

$$699^2 + 244300^2 := 244301^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(699, 27140, 27149)** $\Rightarrow 27149 - 27140 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 162867$, $T_9 := 699^2$,
 $E := \{54281, 54283, \dots, 54295, 54297\}$ or $E := \{54285, 54286, \dots, 54292, 54293\}$

■ Number 700

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$700^2 + 735^2 := 1015^2$$

$$700^2 + 855^2 := 1105^2$$

$$700^2 + 1125^2 := 1325^2$$

$$700^2 + 1152^2 := 1348^2$$

$$700^2 + 1680^2 := 1820^2$$

$$700^2 + 2400^2 := 2500^2$$

$$700^2 + 2451^2 := 2549^2$$

$$700^2 + 3465^2 := 3535^2$$

$$700^2 + 4347^2 := 4403^2$$

$$700^2 + 4875^2 := 4925^2$$

$$700^2 + 6105^2 := 6145^2$$

$$700^2 + 8736^2 := 8764^2$$

$$700^2 + 12240^2 := 12260^2$$

$$700^2 + 17493^2 := 17507^2$$

$$700^2 + 24495^2 := 24505^2$$

$$700^2 + 30621^2 := 30629^2$$

$$700^2 + 61248^2 := 61252^2$$

$$700^2 + 122499^2 := 122501^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(700, 2400, 2500)** $\Rightarrow 2500 - 2400 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 49000$, $T_{100} := 700^2$,
 $E := \{4801, 4803, \dots, 4997, 4999\}$
2. **(700, 1152, 1348)** $\Rightarrow 1348 - 1152 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 35000$, $T_{196} := 700^2$,
 $E := \{2305, 2307, \dots, 2693, 2695\}$

3. **(700, 1125, 1325)** $\Rightarrow 1325 - 700 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 50625$, $T_{625} := 1125^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 2647, 2649\}$ or $E := \{1713, 1714, \dots, 2336, 2337\}$
4. **(700, 2451, 2549)** $\Rightarrow 2549 - 700 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 139707$, $T_{1849} := 2451^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 5095, 5097\}$ or $E := \{2325, 2326, \dots, 4172, 4173\}$
5. **(700, 4875, 4925)** $\Rightarrow 4925 - 700 = 65^2$, $S_{65 \times 65} := 365625$, $T_{4225} := 4875^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 9847, 9849\}$ or $E := \{3513, 3514, \dots, 7736, 7737\}$
6. **(700, 30621, 30629)** $\Rightarrow 30629 - 700 = 173^2$, $S_{173 \times 173} := 5419917$, $T_{29929} := 30621^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 61255, 61257\}$ or $E := \{16365, 16366, \dots, 46292, 46293\}$
7. **(700, 122499, 122501)** $\Rightarrow 122501 - 700 = 349^2$, $S_{349 \times 349} := 42997149$, $T_{121801} := 122499^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 244999, 245001\}$ or $E := \{62301, 62302, \dots, 184100, 184101\}$

2.8 Pythagorean Triples: 701 to 800

■ Number 701

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$701^2 + 245700^2 := 245701^2$$

■ Number 702

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$702^2 + 936^2 := 1170^2$$

$$702^2 + 1440^2 := 1602^2$$

$$702^2 + 3120^2 := 3198^2$$

$$702^2 + 4536^2 := 4590^2$$

$$702^2 + 9464^2 := 9490^2$$

$$702^2 + 13680^2 := 13698^2$$

$$702^2 + 41064^2 := 41070^2$$

$$702^2 + 123200^2 := 123202^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(702, 1440, 1602)** $\Rightarrow 1602 - 702 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 69120$, $T_{900} := 1440^2$,
 $E := \{1405, 1407, \dots, 3201, 3203\}$
2. **(702, 13680, 13698)** $\Rightarrow 13698 - 702 = 114^2$, $S_{114 \times 114} := 1641600$, $T_{12996} := 13680^2$,
 $E := \{1405, 1407, \dots, 27393, 27395\}$
3. **(702, 123200, 123202)** $\Rightarrow 123202 - 702 = 350^2$, $S_{350 \times 350} := 43366400$, $T_{122500} := 123200^2$,
 $E := \{1405, 1407, \dots, 246401, 246403\}$

■ Number 703

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$703^2 + 6660^2 := 6697^2$$

$$703^2 + 12996^2 := 13015^2$$

$$703^2 + 247104^2 := 247105^2$$

■ Number 704

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$704^2 + 840^2 := 1096^2$$

$$704^2 + 903^2 := 1145^2$$

$$704^2 + 1320^2 := 1496^2$$

$$704^2 + 1872^2 := 2000^2$$

$$704^2 + 2772^2 := 2860^2$$

$$704^2 + 3840^2 := 3904^2$$

$$704^2 + 5610^2 := 5654^2$$

$$704^2 + 7728^2 := 7760^2$$

$$704^2 + 11253^2 := 11275^2$$

$$704^2 + 15480^2 := 15496^2$$

$$704^2 + 30972^2 := 30980^2$$

$$704^2 + 61950^2 := 61954^2$$

$$704^2 + 123903^2 := 123905^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(704, 15480, 15496)** $\Rightarrow 15496 - 15480 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 123904$, $T_{16} := 704^2$,
 $E := \{30961, 30963, \dots, 30989, 30991\}$
2. **(704, 3840, 3904)** $\Rightarrow 3904 - 3840 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 61952$, $T_{64} := 704^2$,
 $E := \{7681, 7683, \dots, 7805, 7807\}$
3. **(704, 840, 1096)** $\Rightarrow 1096 - 840 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 30976$, $T_{256} := 704^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 2189, 2191\}$
4. **(704, 903, 1145)** $\Rightarrow 1145 - 704 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 38829$, $T_{441} := 903^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 2287, 2289\}$ or $E := \{1629, 1630, \dots, 2068, 2069\}$
5. **(704, 1872, 2000)** $\Rightarrow 2000 - 704 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 97344$, $T_{1296} := 1872^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 3997, 3999\}$
6. **(704, 7728, 7760)** $\Rightarrow 7760 - 704 = 84^2$, $S_{84 \times 84} := 710976$, $T_{7056} := 7728^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 15517, 15519\}$
7. **(704, 30972, 30980)** $\Rightarrow 30980 - 704 = 174^2$, $S_{174 \times 174} := 5513016$, $T_{30276} := 30972^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 61957, 61959\}$
8. **(704, 123903, 123905)** $\Rightarrow 123905 - 704 = 351^2$, $S_{351 \times 351} := 43737759$, $T_{123201} := 123903^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 247807, 247809\}$ or $E := \{63009, 63010, \dots, 186208, 186209\}$

■ Number 705

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$705^2 + 940^2 := 1175^2$$

$$705^2 + 992^2 := 1217^2$$

$$705^2 + 1692^2 := 1833^2$$

$$705^2 + 3276^2 := 3351^2$$

$$705^2 + 5264^2 := 5311^2$$

$$705^2 + 5500^2 := 5545^2$$

$$705^2 + 9928^2 := 9953^2$$

$$705^2 + 16560^2 := 16575^2$$

$$705^2 + 27608^2 := 27617^2$$

$$705^2 + 49700^2 := 49705^2$$

$$705^2 + 82836^2 := 82839^2$$

$$705^2 + 248512^2 := 248513^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(705, 27608, 27617)** $\Rightarrow 27617 - 27608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 165675$, $T_9 := 705^2$,
 $E := \{55217, 55219, \dots, 55231, 55233\}$ or $E := \{55221, 55222, \dots, 55228, 55229\}$
2. **(705, 9928, 9953)** $\Rightarrow 9953 - 9928 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 99405$, $T_{25} := 705^2$,
 $E := \{19857, 19859, \dots, 19903, 19905\}$ or $E := \{19869, 19870, \dots, 19892, 19893\}$
3. **(705, 992, 1217)** $\Rightarrow 1217 - 992 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 33135$, $T_{225} := 705^2$,
 $E := \{1985, 1987, \dots, 2431, 2433\}$ or $E := \{2097, 2098, \dots, 2320, 2321\}$

■ Number 706

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$706^2 + 124608^2 := 124610^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(706, 124608, 124610)** $\Rightarrow 124610 - 706 = 352^2$, $S_{352 \times 352} := 44111232$, $T_{123904} := 124608^2$,
 $E := \{1413, 1415, \dots, 249217, 249219\}$

■ Number 707

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$707^2 + 2424^2 := 2525^2$$

$$707^2 + 5076^2 := 5125^2$$

$$707^2 + 35700^2 := 35707^2$$

$$707^2 + 249924^2 := 249925^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(707, 5076, 5125)** $\Rightarrow 5125 - 5076 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 71407$, $T_{49} := 707^2$,
 $E := \{10153, 10155, \dots, 10247, 10249\}$ or $E := \{10177, 10178, \dots, 10224, 10225\}$

■ Number 708

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$708^2 + 944^2 := 1180^2$$

$$708^2 + 2065^2 := 2183^2$$

$$708^2 + 3445^2 := 3517^2$$

$$708^2 + 6944^2 := 6980^2$$

$$708^2 + 10431^2 := 10455^2$$

$$708^2 + 13915^2 := 13933^2$$

$$708^2 + 20880^2 := 20892^2$$

$$708^2 + 31325^2 := 31333^2$$

$$708^2 + 41769^2 := 41775^2$$

$$708^2 + 62656^2 := 62660^2$$

$$708^2 + 125315^2 := 125317^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(708, 6944, 6980)** $\Rightarrow 6980 - 6944 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 83544$, $T_{36} := 708^2$,
 $E := \{13889, 13891, \dots, 13957, 13959\}$

2. **(708, 3445, 3517)** $\Rightarrow 3517 - 708 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 223925$, $T_{2809} := 3445^2$,
 $E := \{1417, 1419, \dots, 7031, 7033\}$ or $E := \{2821, 2822, \dots, 5628, 5629\}$

3. **(708, 13915, 13933)** $\Rightarrow 13933 - 708 = 115^2$, $S_{115 \times 115} := 1683715$, $T_{13225} := 13915^2$,
 $E := \{1417, 1419, \dots, 27863, 27865\}$ or $E := \{8029, 8030, \dots, 21252, 21253\}$

4. **(708, 31325, 31333)** $\Rightarrow 31333 - 708 = 175^2$, $S_{175 \times 175} := 5607175$, $T_{30625} := 31325^2$,
 $E := \{1417, 1419, \dots, 62663, 62665\}$ or $E := \{16729, 16730, \dots, 47352, 47353\}$

5. **(708, 125315, 125317)** $\Rightarrow 125317 - 708 = 353^2$, $S_{353 \times 353} := 44486825$, $T_{124609} := 125315^2$,
 $E := \{1417, 1419, \dots, 250631, 250633\}$ or $E := \{63721, 63722, \dots, 188328, 188329\}$

■ Number 709

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$709^2 + 251340^2 := 251341^2$$

■ Number 710

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$710^2 + 1704^2 := 1846^2$$

$$710^2 + 5016^2 := 5066^2$$

$$710^2 + 25200^2 := 25210^2$$

$$710^2 + 126024^2 := 126026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(710, 5016, 5066)** $\Rightarrow 5066 - 710 = 66^2$, $S_{66 \times 66} := 381216$, $T_{4356} := 5016^2$,
 $E := \{1421, 1423, \dots, 10129, 10131\}$
2. **(710, 126024, 126026)** $\Rightarrow 126026 - 710 = 354^2$, $S_{354 \times 354} := 44864544$, $T_{125316} := 126024^2$,
 $E := \{1421, 1423, \dots, 252049, 252051\}$

■ Number 711

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 711^2 + 948^2 := 1185^2 & 711^2 + 28080^2 := 28089^2 \\
 711^2 + 3080^2 := 3161^2 & 711^2 + 84252^2 := 84255^2 \\
 711^2 + 3160^2 := 3239^2 & 711^2 + 252760^2 := 252761^2 \\
 711^2 + 9348^2 := 9375^2 &
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(711, 28080, 28089)** $\Rightarrow 28089 - 28080 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 168507$, $T_9 := 711^2$,
 $E := \{56161, 56163, \dots, 56175, 56177\}$ or $E := \{56165, 56166, \dots, 56172, 56173\}$
2. **(711, 3080, 3161)** $\Rightarrow 3161 - 3080 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 56169$, $T_{81} := 711^2$,
 $E := \{6161, 6163, \dots, 6319, 6321\}$ or $E := \{6201, 6202, \dots, 6280, 6281\}$

■ Number 712

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 712^2 + 1335^2 := 1513^2 & 712^2 + 31680^2 := 31688^2 \\
 712^2 + 7905^2 := 7937^2 & 712^2 + 63366^2 := 63370^2 \\
 712^2 + 15834^2 := 15850^2 & 712^2 + 126735^2 := 126737^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(712, 15834, 15850)** $\Rightarrow 15850 - 15834 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 126736$, $T_{16} := 712^2$,
 $E := \{31669, 31671, \dots, 31697, 31699\}$
2. **(712, 7905, 7937)** $\Rightarrow 7937 - 712 = 85^2$, $S_{85 \times 85} := 735165$, $T_{7225} := 7905^2$,
 $E := \{1425, 1427, \dots, 15871, 15873\}$ or $E := \{5037, 5038, \dots, 12260, 12261\}$
3. **(712, 31680, 31688)** $\Rightarrow 31688 - 712 = 176^2$, $S_{176 \times 176} := 5702400$, $T_{30976} := 31680^2$,
 $E := \{1425, 1427, \dots, 63373, 63375\}$

4. **(712, 126735, 126737)** $\Rightarrow 126737 - 712 = 355^2$, $S_{355 \times 355} := 45244395$, $T_{126025} := 126735^2$,
 $E := \{1425, 1427, \dots, 253471, 253473\}$ or $E := \{64437, 64438, \dots, 190460, 190461\}$

■ Number 713

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 713^2 + 8184^2 &:= 8215^2 \\ 713^2 + 11040^2 &:= 11063^2 \\ 713^2 + 254184^2 &:= 254185^2 \end{aligned}$$

■ Number 714

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll} 714^2 + 720^2 &:= 1014^2 & 714^2 + 2552^2 &:= 2650^2 & 714^2 + 18200^2 &:= 18214^2 \\ 714^2 + 952^2 &:= 1190^2 & 714^2 + 6048^2 &:= 6090^2 & 714^2 + 42480^2 &:= 42486^2 \\ 714^2 + 1960^2 &:= 2086^2 & 714^2 + 7480^2 &:= 7514^2 & 714^2 + 127448^2 &:= 127450^2 \\ 714^2 + 2448^2 &:= 2550^2 & 714^2 + 14152^2 &:= 14170^2 & & \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- (714, 2552, 2650)** $\Rightarrow 2650 - 714 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 148016$, $T_{1936} := 2552^2$,
 $E := \{1429, 1431, \dots, 5297, 5299\}$
- (714, 14152, 14170)** $\Rightarrow 14170 - 714 = 116^2$, $S_{116 \times 116} := 1726544$, $T_{13456} := 14152^2$,
 $E := \{1429, 1431, \dots, 28337, 28339\}$
- (714, 127448, 127450)** $\Rightarrow 127450 - 714 = 356^2$, $S_{356 \times 356} := 45626384$, $T_{126736} := 127448^2$,
 $E := \{1429, 1431, \dots, 254897, 254899\}$

■ Number 715

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 715^2 + 1428^2 &:= 1597^2 \\ 715^2 + 1716^2 &:= 1859^2 \\ 715^2 + 2052^2 &:= 2173^2 \\ 715^2 + 3900^2 &:= 3965^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$715^2 + 4620^2 := 4675^2$$

$$715^2 + 792^2 := 1067^2$$

$$715^2 + 10212^2 := 10237^2$$

$$715^2 + 19656^2 := 19669^2$$

$$715^2 + 23232^2 := 23243^2$$

$$715^2 + 51120^2 := 51125^2$$

$$715^2 + 255612^2 := 255613^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(715, 10212, 10237)** $\Rightarrow 10237 - 10212 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 102245$, $T_{25} := 715^2$,
 $E := \{20425, 20427, \dots, 20471, 20473\}$ or $E := \{20437, 20438, \dots, 20460, 20461\}$
2. **(715, 2052, 2173)** $\Rightarrow 2173 - 2052 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 46475$, $T_{121} := 715^2$,
 $E := \{4105, 4107, \dots, 4343, 4345\}$ or $E := \{4165, 4166, \dots, 4284, 4285\}$
3. **(715, 1428, 1597)** $\Rightarrow 1597 - 1428 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 39325$, $T_{169} := 715^2$,
 $E := \{2857, 2859, \dots, 3191, 3193\}$ or $E := \{2941, 2942, \dots, 3108, 3109\}$

■ Number 716

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$716^2 + 32037^2 := 32045^2$$

$$716^2 + 64080^2 := 64084^2$$

$$716^2 + 128163^2 := 128165^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(716, 32037, 32045)** $\Rightarrow 32045 - 716 = 177^2$, $S_{177 \times 177} := 5798697$, $T_{31329} := 32037^2$,
 $E := \{1433, 1435, \dots, 64087, 64089\}$ or $E := \{17097, 17098, \dots, 48424, 48425\}$
2. **(716, 128163, 128165)** $\Rightarrow 128165 - 716 = 357^2$, $S_{357 \times 357} := 46010517$, $T_{127449} := 128163^2$,
 $E := \{1433, 1435, \dots, 256327, 256329\}$ or $E := \{65157, 65158, \dots, 192604, 192605\}$

■ Number 717

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$717^2 + 956^2 := 1195^2$$

$$717^2 + 28556^2 := 28565^2$$

$$717^2 + 85680^2 := 85683^2$$

$$717^2 + 257044^2 := 257045^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(717, 28556, 28565)** $\Rightarrow 28565 - 28556 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 171363$, $T_9 := 717^2$,
 $E := \{57113, 57115, \dots, 57127, 57129\}$ or $E := \{57117, 57118, \dots, 57124, 57125\}$

■ Number 718

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$718^2 + 128880^2 := 128882^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(718, 128880, 128882)** $\Rightarrow 128882 - 718 = 358^2$, $S_{358 \times 358} := 46396800$, $T_{128164} := 128880^2$,
 $E := \{1437, 1439, \dots, 257761, 257763\}$

■ Number 719

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$719^2 + 258480^2 := 258481^2$$

■ Number 720

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$720^2 + 756^2 := 1044^2$$

$$720^2 + 825^2 := 1095^2$$

$$720^2 + 960^2 := 1200^2$$

$$720^2 + 1092^2 := 1308^2$$

$$720^2 + 1196^2 := 1396^2$$

$$720^2 + 1254^2 := 1446^2$$

$$720^2 + 1350^2 := 1530^2$$

$$720^2 + 1519^2 := 1681^2$$

$$720^2 + 1540^2 := 1700^2$$

$$720^2 + 1653^2 := 1803^2$$

$$720^2 + 1728^2 := 1872^2$$

$$720^2 + 1961^2 := 2089^2$$

$$720^2 + 2100^2 := 2220^2$$

$$720^2 + 2346^2 := 2454^2$$

$$720^2 + 2542^2 := 2642^2$$

$$720^2 + 2652^2 := 2748^2$$

$$720^2 + 2835^2 := 2925^2$$

$$720^2 + 3200^2 := 3280^2$$

$$720^2 + 3564^2 := 3636^2$$

$$720^2 + 4018^2 := 4082^2$$

$$720^2 + 4290^2 := 4350^2$$

$$720^2 + 4773^2 := 4827^2$$

$$720^2 + 5159^2 := 5209^2$$

$$720^2 + 5376^2 := 5424^2$$

$$720^2 + 6460^2 := 6500^2$$

$$720^2 + 7182^2 := 7218^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 720^2 + 8084^2 &:= 8116^2 \\
 720^2 + 8625^2 &:= 8655^2 \\
 720^2 + 10788^2 &:= 10812^2 \\
 720^2 + 12950^2 &:= 12970^2 \\
 720^2 + 14391^2 &:= 14409^2 \\
 720^2 + 16192^2 &:= 16208^2 \\
 720^2 + 21594^2 &:= 21606^2 \\
 720^2 + 25915^2 &:= 25925^2 \\
 720^2 + 32396^2 &:= 32404^2 \\
 720^2 + 43197^2 &:= 43203^2 \\
 720^2 + 64798^2 &:= 64802^2 \\
 720^2 + 129599^2 &:= 129601^2
 \end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(720, 16192, 16208)** $\Rightarrow 16208 - 16192 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 129600$, $T_{16} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{32385, 32387, \dots, 32413, 32415\}$
2. **(720, 7182, 7218)** $\Rightarrow 7218 - 7182 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 86400$, $T_{36} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{14365, 14367, \dots, 14433, 14435\}$
3. **(720, 4018, 4082)** $\Rightarrow 4082 - 4018 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 64800$, $T_{64} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{8037, 8039, \dots, 8161, 8163\}$
4. **(720, 2542, 2642)** $\Rightarrow 2642 - 2542 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 51840$, $T_{100} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{5085, 5087, \dots, 5281, 5283\}$
5. **(720, 1728, 1872)** $\Rightarrow 1872 - 1728 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 43200$, $T_{144} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{3457, 3459, \dots, 3741, 3743\}$
6. **(720, 756, 1044)** $\Rightarrow 1044 - 720 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 31752$, $T_{324} := 756^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 2085, 2087\}$
7. **(720, 1196, 1396)** $\Rightarrow 1396 - 720 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 55016$, $T_{676} := 1196^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 2789, 2791\}$
8. **(720, 1519, 1681)** $\Rightarrow 1681 - 720 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 74431$, $T_{961} := 1519^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 3359, 3361\}$ or $E := \{1921, 1922, \dots, 2880, 2881\}$
9. **(720, 1961, 2089)** $\Rightarrow 2089 - 720 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 103933$, $T_{1369} := 1961^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 4175, 4177\}$ or $E := \{2125, 2126, \dots, 3492, 3493\}$
10. **(720, 3564, 3636)** $\Rightarrow 3636 - 720 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 235224$, $T_{2916} := 3564^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 7269, 7271\}$

11. **(720, 5159, 5209)** $\Rightarrow 5209 - 720 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 397243$, $T_{4489} := 5159^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 10415, 10417\}$ or $E := \{3685, 3686, \dots, 8172, 8173\}$
12. **(720, 8084, 8116)** $\Rightarrow 8116 - 720 = 86^2$, $S_{86 \times 86} := 759896$, $T_{7396} := 8084^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 16229, 16231\}$
13. **(720, 14391, 14409)** $\Rightarrow 14409 - 720 = 117^2$, $S_{117 \times 117} := 1770093$, $T_{13689} := 14391^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 28815, 28817\}$ or $E := \{8285, 8286, \dots, 21972, 21973\}$
14. **(720, 32396, 32404)** $\Rightarrow 32404 - 720 = 178^2$, $S_{178 \times 178} := 5896072$, $T_{31684} := 32396^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 64805, 64807\}$
15. **(720, 129599, 129601)** $\Rightarrow 129601 - 720 = 359^2$, $S_{359 \times 359} := 46785239$, $T_{128881} := 129599^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 259199, 259201\}$ or $E := \{65881, 65882, \dots, 194760, 194761\}$

■ Number 721

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$721^2 + 2472^2 := 2575^2$$

$$721^2 + 5280^2 := 5329^2$$

$$721^2 + 37128^2 := 37135^2$$

$$721^2 + 259920^2 := 259921^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(721, 5280, 5329)** $\Rightarrow 5329 - 5280 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 74263$, $T_{49} := 721^2$,
 $E := \{10561, 10563, \dots, 10655, 10657\}$ or $E := \{10585, 10586, \dots, 10632, 10633\}$

■ Number 722

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$722^2 + 6840^2 := 6878^2$$

$$722^2 + 130320^2 := 130322^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(722, 130320, 130322)** $\Rightarrow 130322 - 722 = 360^2$, $S_{360 \times 360} := 47175840$, $T_{129600} := 130320^2$,
 $E := \{1445, 1447, \dots, 260641, 260643\}$

■ Number 723

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$723^2 + 964^2 := 1205^2$$

$$723^2 + 29036^2 := 29045^2$$

$$723^2 + 87120^2 := 87123^2$$

$$723^2 + 261364^2 := 261365^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(723, 29036, 29045)** $\Rightarrow 29045 - 29036 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 174243$, $T_9 := 723^2$,
 $E := \{58073, 58075, \dots, 58087, 58089\}$ or $E := \{58077, 58078, \dots, 58084, 58085\}$

■ Number 724

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$724^2 + 32757^2 := 32765^2$$

$$724^2 + 65520^2 := 65524^2$$

$$724^2 + 131043^2 := 131045^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(724, 32757, 32765)** $\Rightarrow 32765 - 724 = 179^2$, $S_{179 \times 179} := 5994531$, $T_{32041} := 32757^2$,
 $E := \{1449, 1451, \dots, 65527, 65529\}$ or $E := \{17469, 17470, \dots, 49508, 49509\}$
2. **(724, 131043, 131045)** $\Rightarrow 131045 - 724 = 361^2$, $S_{361 \times 361} := 47568609$, $T_{130321} := 131043^2$,
 $E := \{1449, 1451, \dots, 262087, 262089\}$ or $E := \{66609, 66610, \dots, 196928, 196929\}$

■ Number 725

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$725^2 + 1740^2 := 1885^2$$

$$725^2 + 2040^2 := 2165^2$$

$$725^2 + 9048^2 := 9077^2$$

$$725^2 + 10500^2 := 10525^2$$

$$725^2 + 52560^2 := 52565^2$$

$$725^2 + 262812^2 := 262813^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(725, 10500, 10525)** $\Rightarrow 10525 - 10500 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 105125$, $T_{25} := 725^2$,
 $E := \{21001, 21003, \dots, 21047, 21049\}$ or $E := \{21013, 21014, \dots, 21036, 21037\}$

■ Number 726

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 726^2 + 968^2 & := 1210^2 \\
 726^2 + 1232^2 & := 1430^2 \\
 726^2 + 3960^2 & := 4026^2 \\
 726^2 + 11968^2 & := 11990^2 \\
 726^2 + 14632^2 & := 14650^2 \\
 726^2 + 43920^2 & := 43926^2 \\
 726^2 + 131768^2 & := 131770^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(726, 968, 1210)** $\Rightarrow 1210 - 726 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 42592$, $T_{484} := 968^2$,
 $E := \{1453, 1455, \dots, 2417, 2419\}$
2. **(726, 14632, 14650)** $\Rightarrow 14650 - 726 = 118^2$, $S_{118 \times 118} := 1814368$, $T_{13924} := 14632^2$,
 $E := \{1453, 1455, \dots, 29297, 29299\}$
3. **(726, 131768, 131770)** $\Rightarrow 131770 - 726 = 362^2$, $S_{362 \times 362} := 47963552$, $T_{131044} := 131768^2$,
 $E := \{1453, 1455, \dots, 263537, 263539\}$

■ Number 727

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$727^2 + 264264^2 := 264265^2$$

■ Number 728

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 728^2 + 1071^2 & := 1295^2 & 728^2 + 2655^2 & := 2753^2 & 728^2 + 16554^2 & := 16570^2 \\
 728^2 + 1170^2 & := 1378^2 & 728^2 + 4704^2 & := 4760^2 & 728^2 + 18921^2 & := 18935^2 \\
 728^2 + 1254^2 & := 1450^2 & 728^2 + 5070^2 & := 5122^2 & 728^2 + 33120^2 & := 33128^2 \\
 728^2 + 1365^2 & := 1547^2 & 728^2 + 8265^2 & := 8297^2 & 728^2 + 66246^2 & := 66250^2 \\
 728^2 + 2310^2 & := 2422^2 & 728^2 + 9450^2 & := 9478^2 & 728^2 + 132495^2 & := 132497^2 \\
 728^2 + 2496^2 & := 2600^2 & 728^2 + 10179^2 & := 10205^2 & &
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(728, 16554, 16570)** $\Rightarrow 16570 - 16554 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 132496$, $T_{16} := 728^2$,
 $E := \{33109, 33111, \dots, 33137, 33139\}$
2. **(728, 1254, 1450)** $\Rightarrow 1450 - 1254 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 37856$, $T_{196} := 728^2$,
 $E := \{2509, 2511, \dots, 2897, 2899\}$

3. **(728, 2655, 2753)** $\Rightarrow 2753 - 728 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 156645$, $T_{2025} := 2655^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 5503, 5505\}$ or $E := \{2469, 2470, \dots, 4492, 4493\}$
4. **(728, 8265, 8297)** $\Rightarrow 8297 - 728 = 87^2$, $S_{87 \times 87} := 785175$, $T_{7569} := 8265^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 16591, 16593\}$ or $E := \{5241, 5242, \dots, 12808, 12809\}$
5. **(728, 33120, 33128)** $\Rightarrow 33128 - 728 = 180^2$, $S_{180 \times 180} := 6094080$, $T_{32400} := 33120^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 66253, 66255\}$
6. **(728, 132495, 132497)** $\Rightarrow 132497 - 728 = 363^2$, $S_{363 \times 363} := 48360675$, $T_{131769} := 132495^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 264991, 264993\}$ or $E := \{67341, 67342, \dots, 199108, 199109\}$

■ Number 729

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 729^2 + 972^2 := 1215^2 & 729^2 + 29520^2 := 29529^2 \\
 729^2 + 3240^2 := 3321^2 & 729^2 + 88572^2 := 88575^2 \\
 729^2 + 9828^2 := 9855^2 & 729^2 + 265720^2 := 265721^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(729, 29520, 29529)** $\Rightarrow 29529 - 29520 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 177147$, $T_9 := 729^2$,
 $E := \{59041, 59043, \dots, 59055, 59057\}$ or $E := \{59045, 59046, \dots, 59052, 59053\}$
2. **(729, 3240, 3321)** $\Rightarrow 3321 - 3240 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 59049$, $T_{81} := 729^2$,
 $E := \{6481, 6483, \dots, 6639, 6641\}$ or $E := \{6521, 6522, \dots, 6600, 6601\}$

■ Number 730

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 730^2 + 1752^2 := 1898^2 & 730^2 + 26640^2 := 26650^2 \\
 730^2 + 5304^2 := 5354^2 & 730^2 + 133224^2 := 133226^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(730, 5304, 5354)** $\Rightarrow 5354 - 730 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 413712$, $T_{4624} := 5304^2$,
 $E := \{1461, 1463, \dots, 10705, 10707\}$
2. **(730, 133224, 133226)** $\Rightarrow 133226 - 730 = 364^2$, $S_{364 \times 364} := 48759984$, $T_{132496} := 133224^2$,
 $E := \{1461, 1463, \dots, 266449, 266451\}$

■ Number 731

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$731^2 + 780^2 := 1069^2$$

$$731^2 + 6192^2 := 6235^2$$

$$731^2 + 15708^2 := 15725^2$$

$$731^2 + 267180^2 := 267181^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(731, 780, 1069)** $\Rightarrow 1069 - 780 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 31433$, $T_{289} := 731^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 2135, 2137\}$ or $E := \{1705, 1706, \dots, 1992, 1993\}$

■ Number 732

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$732^2 + 976^2 := 1220^2$$

$$732^2 + 2135^2 := 2257^2$$

$$732^2 + 3685^2 := 3757^2$$

$$732^2 + 7424^2 := 7460^2$$

$$732^2 + 11151^2 := 11175^2$$

$$732^2 + 14875^2 := 14893^2$$

$$732^2 + 22320^2 := 22332^2$$

$$732^2 + 33485^2 := 33493^2$$

$$732^2 + 44649^2 := 44655^2$$

$$732^2 + 66976^2 := 66980^2$$

$$732^2 + 133955^2 := 133957^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(732, 7424, 7460)** $\Rightarrow 7460 - 7424 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 89304$, $T_{36} := 732^2$,
 $E := \{14849, 14851, \dots, 14917, 14919\}$
2. **(732, 3685, 3757)** $\Rightarrow 3757 - 732 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 246895$, $T_{3025} := 3685^2$,
 $E := \{1465, 1467, \dots, 7511, 7513\}$ or $E := \{2977, 2978, \dots, 6000, 6001\}$
3. **(732, 14875, 14893)** $\Rightarrow 14893 - 732 = 119^2$, $S_{119 \times 119} := 1859375$, $T_{14161} := 14875^2$,
 $E := \{1465, 1467, \dots, 29783, 29785\}$ or $E := \{8545, 8546, \dots, 22704, 22705\}$
4. **(732, 33485, 33493)** $\Rightarrow 33493 - 732 = 181^2$, $S_{181 \times 181} := 6194725$, $T_{32761} := 33485^2$,
 $E := \{1465, 1467, \dots, 66983, 66985\}$ or $E := \{17845, 17846, \dots, 50604, 50605\}$
5. **(732, 133955, 133957)** $\Rightarrow 133957 - 732 = 365^2$, $S_{365 \times 365} := 49161485$, $T_{133225} := 133955^2$,
 $E := \{1465, 1467, \dots, 267911, 267913\}$ or $E := \{68077, 68078, \dots, 201300, 201301\}$

■ Number 733

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$733^2 + 268644^2 := 268645^2$$

■ Number 734

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$734^2 + 134688^2 := 134690^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(734, 134688, 134690)** $\Rightarrow 134690 - 734 = 366^2$, $S_{366 \times 366} := 49565184$, $T_{133956} := 134688^2$,
 $E := \{1469, 1471, \dots, 269377, 269379\}$

■ Number 735

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$735^2 + 980^2 := 1225^2$$

$$735^2 + 1088^2 := 1313^2$$

$$735^2 + 1456^2 := 1631^2$$

$$735^2 + 1764^2 := 1911^2$$

$$735^2 + 2520^2 := 2625^2$$

$$735^2 + 3564^2 := 3639^2$$

$$735^2 + 4256^2 := 4319^2$$

$$735^2 + 5488^2 := 5537^2$$

$$735^2 + 5980^2 := 6025^2$$

$$735^2 + 7700^2 := 7735^2$$

$$735^2 + 10792^2 := 10817^2$$

$$735^2 + 12852^2 := 12873^2$$

$$735^2 + 18000^2 := 18015^2$$

$$735^2 + 30008^2 := 30017^2$$

$$735^2 + 38584^2 := 38591^2$$

$$735^2 + 54020^2 := 54025^2$$

$$735^2 + 90036^2 := 90039^2$$

$$735^2 + 270112^2 := 270113^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(735, 30008, 30017)** $\Rightarrow 30017 - 30008 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 180075$, $T_9 := 735^2$,
 $E := \{60017, 60019, \dots, 60031, 60033\}$ or $E := \{60021, 60022, \dots, 60028, 60029\}$
2. **(735, 10792, 10817)** $\Rightarrow 10817 - 10792 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 108045$, $T_{25} := 735^2$,
 $E := \{21585, 21587, \dots, 21631, 21633\}$ or $E := \{21597, 21598, \dots, 21620, 21621\}$
3. **(735, 5488, 5537)** $\Rightarrow 5537 - 5488 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 77175$, $T_{49} := 735^2$,
 $E := \{10977, 10979, \dots, 11071, 11073\}$ or $E := \{11001, 11002, \dots, 11048, 11049\}$
4. **(735, 1088, 1313)** $\Rightarrow 1313 - 1088 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 36015$, $T_{225} := 735^2$,
 $E := \{2177, 2179, \dots, 2623, 2625\}$ or $E := \{2289, 2290, \dots, 2512, 2513\}$

■ Number 736

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 736^2 + 930^2 &:= 1186^2 \\ 736^2 + 1380^2 &:= 1564^2 \\ 736^2 + 2052^2 &:= 2180^2 \\ 736^2 + 2898^2 &:= 2990^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 736^2 + 4200^2 &:= 4264^2 \\ 736^2 + 5865^2 &:= 5911^2 \\ 736^2 + 8448^2 &:= 8480^2 \\ 736^2 + 16920^2 &:= 16936^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 736^2 + 33852^2 &:= 33860^2 \\ 736^2 + 67710^2 &:= 67714^2 \\ 736^2 + 135423^2 &:= 135425^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(736, 16920, 16936)** $\Rightarrow 16936 - 16920 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 135424$, $T_{16} := 736^2$,
 $E := \{33841, 33843, \dots, 33869, 33871\}$
2. **(736, 4200, 4264)** $\Rightarrow 4264 - 4200 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 67712$, $T_{64} := 736^2$,
 $E := \{8401, 8403, \dots, 8525, 8527\}$
3. **(736, 930, 1186)** $\Rightarrow 1186 - 930 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 33856$, $T_{256} := 736^2$,
 $E := \{1861, 1863, \dots, 2369, 2371\}$
4. **(736, 2052, 2180)** $\Rightarrow 2180 - 736 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 110808$, $T_{1444} := 2052^2$,
 $E := \{1473, 1475, \dots, 4357, 4359\}$
5. **(736, 8448, 8480)** $\Rightarrow 8480 - 736 = 88^2$, $S_{88 \times 88} := 811008$, $T_{7744} := 8448^2$,
 $E := \{1473, 1475, \dots, 16957, 16959\}$
6. **(736, 33852, 33860)** $\Rightarrow 33860 - 736 = 182^2$, $S_{182 \times 182} := 6296472$, $T_{33124} := 33852^2$,
 $E := \{1473, 1475, \dots, 67717, 67719\}$
7. **(736, 135423, 135425)** $\Rightarrow 135425 - 736 = 367^2$, $S_{367 \times 367} := 49971087$, $T_{134689} := 135423^2$,
 $E := \{1473, 1475, \dots, 270847, 270849\}$ or $E := \{68817, 68818, \dots, 203504, 203505\}$

■ Number 737

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 737^2 + 2184^2 &:= 2305^2 \\ 737^2 + 4020^2 &:= 4087^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 737^2 + 24684^2 &:= 24695^2 \\ 737^2 + 271584^2 &:= 271585^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(737, 2184, 2305)** $\Rightarrow 2305 - 2184 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 49379$, $T_{121} := 737^2$,
 $E := \{4369, 4371, \dots, 4607, 4609\}$ or $E := \{4429, 4430, \dots, 4548, 4549\}$

■ Number 738

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 738^2 + 984^2 := 1230^2 & 738^2 + 15120^2 := 15138^2 \\
 738^2 + 1600^2 := 1762^2 & 738^2 + 45384^2 := 45390^2 \\
 738^2 + 3280^2 := 3362^2 & 738^2 + 136160^2 := 136162^2 \\
 738^2 + 5016^2 := 5070^2 &
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(738, 1600, 1762)** $\Rightarrow 1762 - 738 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 80000$, $T_{1024} := 1600^2$,
 $E := \{1477, 1479, \dots, 3521, 3523\}$
2. **(738, 15120, 15138)** $\Rightarrow 15138 - 738 = 120^2$, $S_{120 \times 120} := 1905120$, $T_{14400} := 15120^2$,
 $E := \{1477, 1479, \dots, 30273, 30275\}$
3. **(738, 136160, 136162)** $\Rightarrow 136162 - 738 = 368^2$, $S_{368 \times 368} := 50379200$, $T_{135424} := 136160^2$,
 $E := \{1477, 1479, \dots, 272321, 272323\}$

■ Number 739

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$739^2 + 273060^2 := 273061^2$$

■ Number 740

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 740^2 + 777^2 := 1073^2 & 740^2 + 3663^2 := 3737^2 & 740^2 + 27375^2 := 27385^2 \\
 740^2 + 1269^2 := 1469^2 & 740^2 + 5451^2 := 5501^2 & 740^2 + 34221^2 := 34229^2 \\
 740^2 + 1776^2 := 1924^2 & 740^2 + 6825^2 := 6865^2 & 740^2 + 68448^2 := 68452^2 \\
 740^2 + 2688^2 := 2788^2 & 740^2 + 13680^2 := 13700^2 & 740^2 + 136899^2 := 136901^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(740, 2688, 2788)** $\Rightarrow 2788 - 2688 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 54760$, $T_{100} := 740^2$,
 $E := \{5377, 5379, \dots, 5573, 5575\}$
2. **(740, 1269, 1469)** $\Rightarrow 1469 - 740 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 59643$, $T_{729} := 1269^2$,
 $E := \{1481, 1483, \dots, 2935, 2937\}$ or $E := \{1845, 1846, \dots, 2572, 2573\}$
3. **(740, 5451, 5501)** $\Rightarrow 5501 - 740 = 69^2$, $S_{69 \times 69} := 430629$, $T_{4761} := 5451^2$,
 $E := \{1481, 1483, \dots, 10999, 11001\}$ or $E := \{3861, 3862, \dots, 8620, 8621\}$

4. **(740, 34221, 34229)** $\Rightarrow 34229 - 740 = 183^2$, $S_{183 \times 183} := 6399327$, $T_{33489} := 34221^2$,
 $E := \{1481, 1483, \dots, 68455, 68457\}$ or $E := \{18225, 18226, \dots, 51712, 51713\}$
5. **(740, 136899, 136901)** $\Rightarrow 136901 - 740 = 369^2$, $S_{369 \times 369} := 50789529$, $T_{136161} := 136899^2$,
 $E := \{1481, 1483, \dots, 273799, 273801\}$ or $E := \{69561, 69562, \dots, 205720, 205721\}$

■ Number 741

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$741^2 + 988^2 := 1235^2$$

$$741^2 + 1520^2 := 1691^2$$

$$741^2 + 1540^2 := 1709^2$$

$$741^2 + 2288^2 := 2405^2$$

$$741^2 + 4788^2 := 4845^2$$

$$741^2 + 7020^2 := 7059^2$$

$$741^2 + 14440^2 := 14459^2$$

$$741^2 + 21112^2 := 21125^2$$

$$741^2 + 30500^2 := 30509^2$$

$$741^2 + 91512^2 := 91515^2$$

$$741^2 + 274540^2 := 274541^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(741, 30500, 30509)** $\Rightarrow 30509 - 30500 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 183027$, $T_9 := 741^2$,
 $E := \{61001, 61003, \dots, 61015, 61017\}$ or $E := \{61005, 61006, \dots, 61012, 61013\}$
2. **(741, 1540, 1709)** $\Rightarrow 1709 - 1540 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 42237$, $T_{169} := 741^2$,
 $E := \{3081, 3083, \dots, 3415, 3417\}$ or $E := \{3165, 3166, \dots, 3332, 3333\}$

■ Number 742

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$742^2 + 2544^2 := 2650^2$$

$$742^2 + 2760^2 := 2858^2$$

$$742^2 + 19656^2 := 19670^2$$

$$742^2 + 137640^2 := 137642^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(742, 2760, 2858)** $\Rightarrow 2858 - 742 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 165600$, $T_{2116} := 2760^2$,
 $E := \{1485, 1487, \dots, 5713, 5715\}$
2. **(742, 137640, 137642)** $\Rightarrow 137642 - 742 = 370^2$, $S_{370 \times 370} := 51202080$, $T_{136900} := 137640^2$,
 $E := \{1485, 1487, \dots, 275281, 275283\}$

■ Number 743

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$743^2 + 276024^2 := 276025^2$$

■ Number 744

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$744^2 + 817^2 := 1105^2$$

$$744^2 + 992^2 := 1240^2$$

$$744^2 + 1395^2 := 1581^2$$

$$744^2 + 1850^2 := 1994^2$$

$$744^2 + 2170^2 := 2294^2$$

$$744^2 + 2835^2 := 2931^2$$

$$744^2 + 3808^2 := 3880^2$$

$$744^2 + 4433^2 := 4495^2$$

$$744^2 + 5742^2 := 5790^2$$

$$744^2 + 7670^2 := 7706^2$$

$$744^2 + 8633^2 := 8665^2$$

$$744^2 + 11520^2 := 11544^2$$

$$744^2 + 15367^2 := 15385^2$$

$$744^2 + 17290^2 := 17306^2$$

$$744^2 + 23058^2 := 23070^2$$

$$744^2 + 34592^2 := 34600^2$$

$$744^2 + 46125^2 := 46131^2$$

$$744^2 + 69190^2 := 69194^2$$

$$744^2 + 138383^2 := 138385^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(744, 17290, 17306)** $\Rightarrow 17306 - 17290 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 138384$, $T_{16} := 744^2$,
 $E := \{34581, 34583, \dots, 34609, 34611\}$
2. **(744, 7670, 7706)** $\Rightarrow 7706 - 7670 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 92256$, $T_{36} := 744^2$,
 $E := \{15341, 15343, \dots, 15409, 15411\}$
3. **(744, 1850, 1994)** $\Rightarrow 1994 - 1850 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 46128$, $T_{144} := 744^2$,
 $E := \{3701, 3703, \dots, 3985, 3987\}$
4. **(744, 817, 1105)** $\Rightarrow 1105 - 744 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 35131$, $T_{361} := 817^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 2207, 2209\}$ or $E := \{1669, 1670, \dots, 2028, 2029\}$
5. **(744, 3808, 3880)** $\Rightarrow 3880 - 744 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 258944$, $T_{3136} := 3808^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 7757, 7759\}$
6. **(744, 8633, 8665)** $\Rightarrow 8665 - 744 = 89^2$, $S_{89 \times 89} := 837401$, $T_{7921} := 8633^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 17327, 17329\}$ or $E := \{5449, 5450, \dots, 13368, 13369\}$
7. **(744, 15367, 15385)** $\Rightarrow 15385 - 744 = 121^2$, $S_{121 \times 121} := 1951609$, $T_{14641} := 15367^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 30767, 30769\}$ or $E := \{8809, 8810, \dots, 23448, 23449\}$
8. **(744, 34592, 34600)** $\Rightarrow 34600 - 744 = 184^2$, $S_{184 \times 184} := 6503296$, $T_{33856} := 34592^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 69197, 69199\}$

9. **(744, 138383, 138385)** $\Rightarrow 138385 - 744 = 371^2$, $S_{371 \times 371} := 51616859$, $T_{137641} := 138383^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 276767, 276769\}$ or $E := \{70309, 70310, \dots, 207948, 207949\}$

■ Number 745

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$745^2 + 1788^2 := 1937^2$$

$$745^2 + 11088^2 := 11113^2$$

$$745^2 + 55500^2 := 55505^2$$

$$745^2 + 277512^2 := 277513^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(745, 11088, 11113)** $\Rightarrow 11113 - 11088 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 111005$, $T_{25} := 745^2$,
 $E := \{22177, 22179, \dots, 22223, 22225\}$ or $E := \{22189, 22190, \dots, 22212, 22213\}$

■ Number 746

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$746^2 + 139128^2 := 139130^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(746, 139128, 139130)** $\Rightarrow 139130 - 746 = 372^2$, $S_{372 \times 372} := 52033872$, $T_{138384} := 139128^2$,
 $E := \{1493, 1495, \dots, 278257, 278259\}$

■ Number 747

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$747^2 + 996^2 := 1245^2$$

$$747^2 + 3320^2 := 3403^2$$

$$747^2 + 3404^2 := 3485^2$$

$$747^2 + 10320^2 := 10347^2$$

$$747^2 + 30996^2 := 31005^2$$

$$747^2 + 93000^2 := 93003^2$$

$$747^2 + 279004^2 := 279005^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(747, 30996, 31005)** $\Rightarrow 31005 - 30996 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 186003$, $T_9 := 747^2$,
 $E := \{61993, 61995, \dots, 62007, 62009\}$ or $E := \{61997, 61998, \dots, 62004, 62005\}$

2. **(747, 3404, 3485)** $\Rightarrow 3485 - 3404 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 62001$, $T_{81} := 747^2$,
 $E := \{6809, 6811, \dots, 6967, 6969\}$ or $E := \{6849, 6850, \dots, 6928, 6929\}$

■ Number 748

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$748^2 + 1035^2 := 1277^2$$

$$748^2 + 1989^2 := 2125^2$$

$$748^2 + 3135^2 := 3223^2$$

$$748^2 + 4080^2 := 4148^2$$

$$748^2 + 6336^2 := 6380^2$$

$$748^2 + 8211^2 := 8245^2$$

$$748^2 + 12705^2 := 12727^2$$

$$748^2 + 34965^2 := 34973^2$$

$$748^2 + 69936^2 := 69940^2$$

$$748^2 + 139875^2 := 139877^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(748, 1035, 1277)** $\Rightarrow 1277 - 748 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 46575$, $T_{529} := 1035^2$,
 $E := \{1497, 1499, \dots, 2551, 2553\}$ or $E := \{1761, 1762, \dots, 2288, 2289\}$

2. **(748, 34965, 34973)** $\Rightarrow 34973 - 748 = 185^2$, $S_{185 \times 185} := 6608385$, $T_{34225} := 34965^2$,
 $E := \{1497, 1499, \dots, 69943, 69945\}$ or $E := \{18609, 18610, \dots, 52832, 52833\}$

3. **(748, 139875, 139877)** $\Rightarrow 139877 - 748 = 373^2$, $S_{373 \times 373} := 52453125$, $T_{139129} := 139875^2$,
 $E := \{1497, 1499, \dots, 279751, 279753\}$ or $E := \{71061, 71062, \dots, 210188, 210189\}$

■ Number 749

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$749^2 + 2568^2 := 2675^2$$

$$749^2 + 5700^2 := 5749^2$$

$$749^2 + 40068^2 := 40075^2$$

$$749^2 + 280500^2 := 280501^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(749, 5700, 5749)** $\Rightarrow 5749 - 5700 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 80143$, $T_{49} := 749^2$,
 $E := \{11401, 11403, \dots, 11495, 11497\}$ or $E := \{11425, 11426, \dots, 11472, 11473\}$

■ Number 750

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$750^2 + 1000^2 := 1250^2$$

$$750^2 + 1800^2 := 1950^2$$

$$750^2 + 3080^2 := 3170^2$$

$$750^2 + 5600^2 := 5650^2$$

$$750^2 + 9360^2 := 9390^2$$

$$750^2 + 15616^2 := 15634^2$$

$$750^2 + 28120^2 := 28130^2$$

$$750^2 + 46872^2 := 46878^2$$

$$750^2 + 140624^2 := 140626^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(750, 5600, 5650)** $\Rightarrow 5650 - 750 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 448000$, $T_{4900} := 5600^2$,
 $E := \{1501, 1503, \dots, 11297, 11299\}$
2. **(750, 15616, 15634)** $\Rightarrow 15634 - 750 = 122^2$, $S_{122 \times 122} := 1998848$, $T_{14884} := 15616^2$,
 $E := \{1501, 1503, \dots, 31265, 31267\}$
3. **(750, 140624, 140626)** $\Rightarrow 140626 - 750 = 374^2$, $S_{374 \times 374} := 52874624$, $T_{139876} := 140624^2$,
 $E := \{1501, 1503, \dots, 281249, 281251\}$

■ Number 751

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$751^2 + 282000^2 := 282001^2$$

■ Number 752

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$752^2 + 1410^2 := 1598^2$$

$$752^2 + 2145^2 := 2273^2$$

$$752^2 + 2961^2 := 3055^2$$

$$752^2 + 4386^2 := 4450^2$$

$$752^2 + 8820^2 := 8852^2$$

$$752^2 + 17664^2 := 17680^2$$

$$752^2 + 35340^2 := 35348^2$$

$$752^2 + 70686^2 := 70690^2$$

$$752^2 + 141375^2 := 141377^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(752, 17664, 17680)** $\Rightarrow 17680 - 17664 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 141376$, $T_{16} := 752^2$,
 $E := \{35329, 35331, \dots, 35357, 35359\}$
2. **(752, 4386, 4450)** $\Rightarrow 4450 - 4386 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 70688$, $T_{64} := 752^2$,
 $E := \{8773, 8775, \dots, 8897, 8899\}$
3. **(752, 2145, 2273)** $\Rightarrow 2273 - 752 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 117975$, $T_{1521} := 2145^2$,
 $E := \{1505, 1507, \dots, 4543, 4545\}$ or $E := \{2265, 2266, \dots, 3784, 3785\}$

4. **(752, 8820, 8852)** $\Rightarrow 8852 - 752 = 90^2$, $S_{90 \times 90} := 864360$, $T_{8100} := 8820^2$,
 $E := \{1505, 1507, \dots, 17701, 17703\}$
5. **(752, 35340, 35348)** $\Rightarrow 35348 - 752 = 186^2$, $S_{186 \times 186} := 6714600$, $T_{34596} := 35340^2$,
 $E := \{1505, 1507, \dots, 70693, 70695\}$
6. **(752, 141375, 141377)** $\Rightarrow 141377 - 752 = 375^2$, $S_{375 \times 375} := 53298375$, $T_{140625} := 141375^2$,
 $E := \{1505, 1507, \dots, 282751, 282753\}$ or $E := \{71817, 71818, \dots, 212440, 212441\}$

■ Number 753

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$753^2 + 1004^2 := 1255^2$$

$$753^2 + 31496^2 := 31505^2$$

$$753^2 + 94500^2 := 94503^2$$

$$753^2 + 283504^2 := 283505^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(753, 31496, 31505)** $\Rightarrow 31505 - 31496 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 189003$, $T_9 := 753^2$,
 $E := \{62993, 62995, \dots, 63007, 63009\}$ or $E := \{62997, 62998, \dots, 63004, 63005\}$

■ Number 754

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$754^2 + 4872^2 := 4930^2$$

$$754^2 + 10920^2 := 10946^2$$

$$754^2 + 142128^2 := 142130^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(754, 142128, 142130)** $\Rightarrow 142130 - 754 = 376^2$, $S_{376 \times 376} := 53724384$, $T_{141376} := 142128^2$,
 $E := \{1509, 1511, \dots, 284257, 284259\}$

■ Number 755

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$755^2 + 1812^2 := 1963^2$$

$$755^2 + 11388^2 := 11413^2$$

$$755^2 + 285012^2 := 285013^2$$

$$755^2 + 57000^2 := 57005^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(755, 11388, 11413)** $\Rightarrow 11413 - 11388 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 114005$, $T_{25} := 755^2$,
 $E := \{22777, 22779, \dots, 22823, 22825\}$ or $E := \{22789, 22790, \dots, 22812, 22813\}$

■ **Number 756**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$756^2 + 825^2 := 1119^2$	$756^2 + 2867^2 := 2965^2$	$756^2 + 11895^2 := 11919^2$
$756^2 + 1008^2 := 1260^2$	$756^2 + 3360^2 := 3444^2$	$756^2 + 15867^2 := 15885^2$
$756^2 + 1215^2 := 1431^2$	$756^2 + 3933^2 := 4005^2$	$756^2 + 20405^2 := 20419^2$
$756^2 + 1360^2 := 1556^2$	$756^2 + 5075^2 := 5131^2$	$756^2 + 23808^2 := 23820^2$
$756^2 + 1617^2 := 1785^2$	$756^2 + 5265^2 := 5319^2$	$756^2 + 35717^2 := 35725^2$
$756^2 + 1683^2 := 1845^2$	$756^2 + 6783^2 := 6825^2$	$756^2 + 47625^2 := 47631^2$
$756^2 + 2205^2 := 2331^2$	$756^2 + 7920^2 := 7956^2$	$756^2 + 71440^2 := 71444^2$
$756^2 + 2592^2 := 2700^2$	$756^2 + 10192^2 := 10220^2$	$756^2 + 142883^2 := 142885^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(756, 7920, 7956)** $\Rightarrow 7956 - 7920 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 95256$, $T_{36} := 756^2$,
 $E := \{15841, 15843, \dots, 15909, 15911\}$
2. **(756, 1360, 1556)** $\Rightarrow 1556 - 1360 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 40824$, $T_{196} := 756^2$,
 $E := \{2721, 2723, \dots, 3109, 3111\}$
3. **(756, 1683, 1845)** $\Rightarrow 1845 - 756 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 85833$, $T_{1089} := 1683^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 3687, 3689\}$ or $E := \{2057, 2058, \dots, 3144, 3145\}$
4. **(756, 2867, 2965)** $\Rightarrow 2965 - 756 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 174887$, $T_{2209} := 2867^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 5927, 5929\}$ or $E := \{2617, 2618, \dots, 4824, 4825\}$
5. **(756, 3933, 4005)** $\Rightarrow 4005 - 756 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 271377$, $T_{3249} := 3933^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 8007, 8009\}$ or $E := \{3137, 3138, \dots, 6384, 6385\}$
6. **(756, 15867, 15885)** $\Rightarrow 15885 - 756 = 123^2$, $S_{123 \times 123} := 2046843$, $T_{15129} := 15867^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 31767, 31769\}$ or $E := \{9077, 9078, \dots, 24204, 24205\}$
7. **(756, 35717, 35725)** $\Rightarrow 35725 - 756 = 187^2$, $S_{187 \times 187} := 6821947$, $T_{34969} := 35717^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 71447, 71449\}$ or $E := \{18997, 18998, \dots, 53964, 53965\}$
8. **(756, 142883, 142885)** $\Rightarrow 142885 - 756 = 377^2$, $S_{377 \times 377} := 54152657$, $T_{142129} := 142883^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 285767, 285769\}$ or $E := \{72577, 72578, \dots, 214704, 214705\}$

■ Number 757

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$757^2 + 286524^2 := 286525^2$$

■ Number 758

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$758^2 + 143640^2 := 143642^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(758, 143640, 143642)** $\Rightarrow 143642 - 758 = 378^2$, $S_{378 \times 378} := 54583200$, $T_{142884} := 143640^2$,
 $E := \{1517, 1519, \dots, 287281, 287283\}$

■ Number 759

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$759^2 + 1012^2 := 1265^2$$

$$759^2 + 1288^2 := 1495^2$$

$$759^2 + 2320^2 := 2441^2$$

$$759^2 + 2860^2 := 2959^2$$

$$759^2 + 4140^2 := 4209^2$$

$$759^2 + 8712^2 := 8745^2$$

$$759^2 + 12512^2 := 12535^2$$

$$759^2 + 26180^2 := 26191^2$$

$$759^2 + 32000^2 := 32009^2$$

$$759^2 + 96012^2 := 96015^2$$

$$759^2 + 288040^2 := 288041^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(759, 32000, 32009)** $\Rightarrow 32009 - 32000 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 192027$, $T_9 := 759^2$,
 $E := \{64001, 64003, \dots, 64015, 64017\}$ or $E := \{64005, 64006, \dots, 64012, 64013\}$
2. **(759, 2320, 2441)** $\Rightarrow 2441 - 2320 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 52371$, $T_{121} := 759^2$,
 $E := \{4641, 4643, \dots, 4879, 4881\}$ or $E := \{4701, 4702, \dots, 4820, 4821\}$

■ Number 760

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$760^2 + 798^2 := 1102^2$$

$$760^2 + 1344^2 := 1544^2$$

$$760^2 + 1425^2 := 1615^2$$

$$760^2 + 1725^2 := 1885^2$$

$$760^2 + 1824^2 := 1976^2$$

$$760^2 + 2828^2 := 2928^2$$

$$760^2 + 3570^2 := 3650^2$$

$$760^2 + 3762^2 := 3838^2$$

$$760^2 + 5751^2 := 5801^2$$

$$760^2 + 7200^2 := 7240^2$$

$$760^2 + 7581^2 := 7619^2$$

$$760^2 + 9009^2 := 9041^2$$

$$760^2 + 14430^2 := 14450^2$$

$$760^2 + 18042^2 := 18058^2$$

$$760^2 + 28875^2 := 28885^2$$

$$760^2 + 36096^2 := 36104^2$$

$$760^2 + 72198^2 := 72202^2$$

$$760^2 + 144399^2 := 144401^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(760, 18042, 18058)** $\Rightarrow 18058 - 18042 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 144400$, $T_{16} := 760^2$,
 $E := \{36085, 36087, \dots, 36113, 36115\}$
2. **(760, 2838, 2938)** $\Rightarrow 2938 - 2838 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 57760$, $T_{100} := 760^2$,
 $E := \{5677, 5679, \dots, 5873, 5875\}$
3. **(760, 1344, 1544)** $\Rightarrow 1544 - 760 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 64512$, $T_{784} := 1344^2$,
 $E := \{1521, 1523, \dots, 3085, 3087\}$
4. **(760, 5751, 5801)** $\Rightarrow 5801 - 760 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 465831$, $T_{5041} := 5751^2$,
 $E := \{1521, 1523, \dots, 11599, 11601\}$ or $E := \{4041, 4042, \dots, 9080, 9081\}$
5. **(760, 9009, 9041)** $\Rightarrow 9041 - 760 = 91^2$, $S_{91 \times 91} := 891891$, $T_{8281} := 9009^2$,
 $E := \{1521, 1523, \dots, 18079, 18081\}$ or $E := \{5661, 5662, \dots, 13940, 13941\}$
6. **(760, 36096, 36104)** $\Rightarrow 36104 - 760 = 188^2$, $S_{188 \times 188} := 6930432$, $T_{35344} := 36096^2$,
 $E := \{1521, 1523, \dots, 72205, 72207\}$
7. **(760, 144399, 144401)** $\Rightarrow 144401 - 760 = 379^2$, $S_{379 \times 379} := 55016019$, $T_{143641} := 144399^2$,
 $E := \{1521, 1523, \dots, 288799, 288801\}$ or $E := \{73341, 73342, \dots, 216980, 216981\}$

■ Number 761

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$761^2 + 289560^2 := 289561^2$$

■ Number 762

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$762^2 + 1016^2 := 1270^2$$

$$762^2 + 16120^2 := 16138^2$$

$$762^2 + 48384^2 := 48390^2$$

$$762^2 + 145160^2 := 145162^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(762, 16120, 16138)** $\Rightarrow 16138 - 762 = 124^2$, $S_{124 \times 124} := 2095600$, $T_{15376} := 16120^2$,
 $E := \{1525, 1527, \dots, 32273, 32275\}$
2. **(762, 145160, 145162)** $\Rightarrow 145162 - 762 = 380^2$, $S_{380 \times 380} := 55451120$, $T_{144400} := 145160^2$,
 $E := \{1525, 1527, \dots, 290321, 290323\}$

■ Number 763

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$763^2 + 2616^2 := 2725^2$$

$$763^2 + 5916^2 := 5965^2$$

$$763^2 + 41580^2 := 41587^2$$

$$763^2 + 291084^2 := 291085^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(763, 5916, 5965)** $\Rightarrow 5965 - 5916 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 83167$, $T_{49} := 763^2$,
 $E := \{11833, 11835, \dots, 11927, 11929\}$ or $E := \{11857, 11858, \dots, 11904, 11905\}$

■ Number 764

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$764^2 + 36477^2 := 36485^2$$

$$764^2 + 72960^2 := 72964^2$$

$$764^2 + 145923^2 := 145925^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(764, 36477, 36485)** $\Rightarrow 36485 - 764 = 189^2$, $S_{189 \times 189} := 7040061$, $T_{35721} := 36477^2$,
 $E := \{1529, 1531, \dots, 72967, 72969\}$ or $E := \{19389, 19390, \dots, 55108, 55109\}$
2. **(764, 145923, 145925)** $\Rightarrow 145925 - 764 = 381^2$, $S_{381 \times 381} := 55888509$, $T_{145161} := 145923^2$,
 $E := \{1529, 1531, \dots, 291847, 291849\}$ or $E := \{74109, 74110, \dots, 219268, 219269\}$

■ Number 765

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$765^2 + 868^2 := 1157^2$	$765^2 + 3572^2 := 3653^2$	$765^2 + 17204^2 := 17221^2$
$765^2 + 1020^2 := 1275^2$	$765^2 + 3864^2 := 3939^2$	$765^2 + 19500^2 := 19515^2$
$765^2 + 1188^2 := 1413^2$	$765^2 + 5712^2 := 5763^2$	$765^2 + 32508^2 := 32517^2$
$765^2 + 1836^2 := 1989^2$	$765^2 + 6480^2 := 6525^2$	$765^2 + 58520^2 := 58525^2$
$765^2 + 2100^2 := 2235^2$	$765^2 + 10824^2 := 10851^2$	$765^2 + 97536^2 := 97539^2$
$765^2 + 3400^2 := 3485^2$	$765^2 + 11692^2 := 11717^2$	$765^2 + 292612^2 := 292613^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(765, 32508, 32517)** $\Rightarrow 32517 - 32508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 195075$, $T_9 := 765^2$,
 $E := \{65017, 65019, \dots, 65031, 65033\}$ or $E := \{65021, 65022, \dots, 65028, 65029\}$
2. **(765, 11692, 11717)** $\Rightarrow 11717 - 11692 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 117045$, $T_{25} := 765^2$,
 $E := \{23385, 23387, \dots, 23431, 23433\}$ or $E := \{23397, 23398, \dots, 23420, 23421\}$
3. **(765, 3572, 3653)** $\Rightarrow 3653 - 3572 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 65025$, $T_{81} := 765^2$,
 $E := \{7145, 7147, \dots, 7303, 7305\}$ or $E := \{7185, 7186, \dots, 7264, 7265\}$
4. **(765, 1188, 1413)** $\Rightarrow 1413 - 1188 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 39015$, $T_{225} := 765^2$,
 $E := \{2377, 2379, \dots, 2823, 2825\}$ or $E := \{2489, 2490, \dots, 2712, 2713\}$
5. **(765, 868, 1157)** $\Rightarrow 1157 - 868 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 34425$, $T_{289} := 765^2$,
 $E := \{1737, 1739, \dots, 2311, 2313\}$ or $E := \{1881, 1882, \dots, 2168, 2169\}$

■ Number 766

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$766^2 + 146688^2 := 146690^2$$

■ Number 767

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$767^2 + 1656^2 := 1825^2$	$767^2 + 22620^2 := 22633^2$
$767^2 + 4956^2 := 5015^2$	$767^2 + 294144^2 := 294145^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(767, 1656, 1825)** $\Rightarrow 1825 - 1656 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 45253$, $T_{169} := 767^2$,
 $E := \{3313, 3315, \dots, 3647, 3649\}$ or $E := \{3397, 3398, \dots, 3564, 3565\}$

2. **(766, 146688, 146690)** $\Rightarrow 146690 - 766 = 382^2$, $S_{382 \times 382} := 56328192$, $T_{145924} := 146688^2$,
 $E := \{1533, 1535, \dots, 293377, 293379\}$

■ Number 768

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$768^2 + 880^2 := 1168^2$$

$$768^2 + 1024^2 := 1280^2$$

$$768^2 + 1440^2 := 1632^2$$

$$768^2 + 1976^2 := 2120^2$$

$$768^2 + 2240^2 := 2368^2$$

$$768^2 + 3024^2 := 3120^2$$

$$768^2 + 4060^2 := 4132^2$$

$$768^2 + 4576^2 := 4640^2$$

$$768^2 + 6120^2 := 6168^2$$

$$768^2 + 8174^2 := 8210^2$$

$$768^2 + 9200^2 := 9232^2$$

$$768^2 + 12276^2 := 12300^2$$

$$768^2 + 16375^2 := 16393^2$$

$$768^2 + 18424^2 := 18440^2$$

$$768^2 + 24570^2 := 24582^2$$

$$768^2 + 36860^2 := 36868^2$$

$$768^2 + 49149^2 := 49155^2$$

$$768^2 + 73726^2 := 73730^2$$

$$768^2 + 147455^2 := 147457^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(768, 18424, 18440)** $\Rightarrow 18440 - 18424 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 147456$, $T_{16} := 768^2$,
 $E := \{36849, 36851, \dots, 36877, 36879\}$

2. **(768, 8174, 8210)** $\Rightarrow 8210 - 8174 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 98304$, $T_{36} := 768^2$,
 $E := \{16349, 16351, \dots, 16417, 16419\}$

3. **(768, 4576, 4640)** $\Rightarrow 4640 - 4576 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 73728$, $T_{64} := 768^2$,
 $E := \{9153, 9155, \dots, 9277, 9279\}$

4. **(768, 1976, 2120)** $\Rightarrow 2120 - 1976 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 49152$, $T_{144} := 768^2$,
 $E := \{3953, 3955, \dots, 4237, 4239\}$

5. **(768, 1024, 1280)** $\Rightarrow 1280 - 1024 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 36864$, $T_{256} := 768^2$,
 $E := \{2049, 2051, \dots, 2557, 2559\}$

6. **(768, 880, 1168)** $\Rightarrow 1168 - 768 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 38720$, $T_{400} := 880^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 2333, 2335\}$

7. **(768, 2240, 2368)** $\Rightarrow 2368 - 768 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 125440$, $T_{1600} := 2240^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 4733, 4735\}$

8. **(768, 4060, 4132)** $\Rightarrow 4132 - 768 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 284200$, $T_{3364} := 4060^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 8261, 8263\}$

9. **(768, 9200, 9232)** $\Rightarrow 9232 - 768 = 92^2$, $S_{92 \times 92} := 920000$, $T_{8464} := 9200^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 18461, 18463\}$

10. **(768, 16375, 16393)** $\Rightarrow 16393 - 768 = 125^2$, $S_{125 \times 125} := 2145125$, $T_{15625} := 16375^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 32783, 32785\}$ or $E := \{9349, 9350, \dots, 24972, 24973\}$
11. **(768, 36860, 36868)** $\Rightarrow 36868 - 768 = 190^2$, $S_{190 \times 190} := 7150840$, $T_{36100} := 36860^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 73733, 73735\}$
12. **(768, 147455, 147457)** $\Rightarrow 147457 - 768 = 383^2$, $S_{383 \times 383} := 56770175$, $T_{146689} := 147455^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 294911, 294913\}$ or $E := \{74881, 74882, \dots, 221568, 221569\}$

■ Number 769

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$769^2 + 295680^2 := 295681^2$$

■ Number 770

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$770^2 + 1104^2 := 1346^2$$

$$770^2 + 1848^2 := 2002^2$$

$$770^2 + 2640^2 := 2750^2$$

$$770^2 + 2976^2 := 3074^2$$

$$770^2 + 4200^2 := 4270^2$$

$$770^2 + 5904^2 := 5954^2$$

$$770^2 + 13464^2 := 13486^2$$

$$770^2 + 21168^2 := 21182^2$$

$$770^2 + 29640^2 := 29650^2$$

$$770^2 + 148224^2 := 148226^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(770, 1104, 1346)** $\Rightarrow 1346 - 770 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 50784$, $T_{576} := 1104^2$,
 $E := \{1541, 1543, \dots, 2689, 2691\}$
2. **(770, 2976, 3074)** $\Rightarrow 3074 - 770 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 184512$, $T_{2304} := 2976^2$,
 $E := \{1541, 1543, \dots, 6145, 6147\}$
3. **(770, 5904, 5954)** $\Rightarrow 5954 - 770 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 484128$, $T_{5184} := 5904^2$,
 $E := \{1541, 1543, \dots, 11905, 11907\}$
4. **(770, 148224, 148226)** $\Rightarrow 148226 - 770 = 384^2$, $S_{384 \times 384} := 57214464$, $T_{147456} := 148224^2$,
 $E := \{1541, 1543, \dots, 296449, 296451\}$

■ Number 771

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$771^2 + 1028^2 := 1285^2$$

$$771^2 + 33020^2 := 33029^2$$

$$771^2 + 99072^2 := 99075^2$$

$$771^2 + 297220^2 := 297221^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(771, 33020, 33029)** $\Rightarrow 33029 - 33020 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 198147$, $T_9 := 771^2$,
 $E := \{66041, 66043, \dots, 66055, 66057\}$ or $E := \{66045, 66046, \dots, 66052, 66053\}$

■ Number 772

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$772^2 + 37245^2 := 37253^2$$

$$772^2 + 74496^2 := 74500^2$$

$$772^2 + 148995^2 := 148997^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(772, 37245, 37253)** $\Rightarrow 37253 - 772 = 191^2$, $S_{191 \times 191} := 7262775$, $T_{36481} := 37245^2$,
 $E := \{1545, 1547, \dots, 74503, 74505\}$ or $E := \{19785, 19786, \dots, 56264, 56265\}$
2. **(772, 148995, 148997)** $\Rightarrow 148997 - 772 = 385^2$, $S_{385 \times 385} := 57661065$, $T_{148225} := 148995^2$,
 $E := \{1545, 1547, \dots, 297991, 297993\}$ or $E := \{75657, 75658, \dots, 223880, 223881\}$

■ Number 773

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$773^2 + 298764^2 := 298765^2$$

■ Number 774

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$774^2 + 1032^2 := 1290^2$$

$$774^2 + 1768^2 := 1930^2$$

$$774^2 + 3440^2 := 3526^2$$

$$774^2 + 5520^2 := 5574^2$$

$$774^2 + 16632^2 := 16650^2$$

$$774^2 + 49920^2 := 49926^2$$

$$774^2 + 149768^2 := 149770^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(774, 16632, 16650)** $\Rightarrow 16650 - 774 = 126^2$, $S_{126 \times 126} := 2195424$, $T_{15876} := 16632^2$,
 $E := \{1549, 1551, \dots, 33297, 33299\}$
2. **(774, 1768, 1930)** $\Rightarrow 1930 - 774 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 91936$, $T_{1156} := 1768^2$,
 $E := \{1549, 1551, \dots, 3857, 3859\}$
3. **(774, 149768, 149770)** $\Rightarrow 149770 - 774 = 386^2$, $S_{386 \times 386} := 58109984$, $T_{148996} := 149768^2$,
 $E := \{1549, 1551, \dots, 299537, 299539\}$

■ Number 775

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$775^2 + 1860^2 := 2015^2$	$775^2 + 12000^2 := 12025^2$
$775^2 + 2340^2 := 2465^2$	$775^2 + 60060^2 := 60065^2$
$775^2 + 9672^2 := 9703^2$	$775^2 + 300312^2 := 300313^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(775, 12000, 12025)** $\Rightarrow 12025 - 12000 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 120125$, $T_{25} := 775^2$,
 $E := \{24001, 24003, \dots, 24047, 24049\}$ or $E := \{24013, 24014, \dots, 24036, 24037\}$

■ Number 776

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$776^2 + 1455^2 := 1649^2$	$776^2 + 37632^2 := 37640^2$
$776^2 + 9393^2 := 9425^2$	$776^2 + 75270^2 := 75274^2$
$776^2 + 18810^2 := 18826^2$	$776^2 + 150543^2 := 150545^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(776, 18810, 18826)** $\Rightarrow 18826 - 18810 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 150544$, $T_{16} := 776^2$,
 $E := \{37621, 37623, \dots, 37649, 37651\}$

2. **(776, 9393, 9425)** $\Rightarrow 9425 - 776 = 93^2$, $S_{93 \times 93} := 948693$, $T_{8649} := 9393^2$,
 $E := \{1553, 1555, \dots, 18847, 18849\}$ or $E := \{5877, 5878, \dots, 14524, 14525\}$
3. **(776, 37632, 37640)** $\Rightarrow 37640 - 776 = 192^2$, $S_{192 \times 192} := 7375872$, $T_{36864} := 37632^2$,
 $E := \{1553, 1555, \dots, 75277, 75279\}$
4. **(776, 150543, 150545)** $\Rightarrow 150545 - 776 = 387^2$, $S_{387 \times 387} := 58561227$, $T_{149769} := 150543^2$,
 $E := \{1553, 1555, \dots, 301087, 301089\}$ or $E := \{76437, 76438, \dots, 226204, 226205\}$

■ Number 777

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$777^2 + 1036^2 := 1295^2$$

$$777^2 + 1980^2 := 2127^2$$

$$777^2 + 2664^2 := 2775^2$$

$$777^2 + 4760^2 := 4823^2$$

$$777^2 + 6136^2 := 6185^2$$

$$777^2 + 8140^2 := 8177^2$$

$$777^2 + 14364^2 := 14385^2$$

$$777^2 + 33536^2 := 33545^2$$

$$777^2 + 43120^2 := 43127^2$$

$$777^2 + 100620^2 := 100623^2$$

$$777^2 + 301864^2 := 301865^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(777, 33536, 33545)** $\Rightarrow 33545 - 33536 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 201243$, $T_9 := 777^2$,
 $E := \{67073, 67075, \dots, 67087, 67089\}$ or $E := \{67077, 67078, \dots, 67084, 67085\}$
2. **(777, 6136, 6185)** $\Rightarrow 6185 - 6136 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 86247$, $T_{49} := 777^2$,
 $E := \{12273, 12275, \dots, 12367, 12369\}$ or $E := \{12297, 12298, \dots, 12344, 12345\}$

■ Number 778

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$778^2 + 151320^2 := 151322^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(778, 151320, 151322)** $\Rightarrow 151322 - 778 = 388^2$, $S_{388 \times 388} := 59014800$, $T_{150544} := 151320^2$,
 $E := \{1557, 1559, \dots, 302641, 302643\}$

■ Number 779

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 779^2 + 7380^2 &:= 7421^2 \\ 779^2 + 15960^2 &:= 15979^2 \\ 779^2 + 303420^2 &:= 303421^2 \end{aligned}$$

■ Number 780

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$780^2 + 819^2 := 1131^2$	$780^2 + 2873^2 := 2977^2$	$780^2 + 10125^2 := 10155^2$
$780^2 + 864^2 := 1164^2$	$780^2 + 2992^2 := 3092^2$	$780^2 + 11687^2 := 11713^2$
$780^2 + 1040^2 := 1300^2$	$780^2 + 3335^2 := 3425^2$	$780^2 + 12663^2 := 12687^2$
$780^2 + 1183^2 := 1417^2$	$780^2 + 3861^2 := 3939^2$	$780^2 + 15200^2 := 15220^2$
$780^2 + 1421^2 := 1621^2$	$780^2 + 4189^2 := 4261^2$	$780^2 + 16891^2 := 16909^2$
$780^2 + 1600^2 := 1780^2$	$780^2 + 5040^2 := 5100^2$	$780^2 + 25344^2 := 25356^2$
$780^2 + 1872^2 := 2028^2$	$780^2 + 5824^2 := 5876^2$	$780^2 + 30415^2 := 30425^2$
$780^2 + 1953^2 := 2103^2$	$780^2 + 6059^2 := 6109^2$	$780^2 + 38021^2 := 38029^2$
$780^2 + 2275^2 := 2405^2$	$780^2 + 7585^2 := 7625^2$	$780^2 + 50697^2 := 50703^2$
$780^2 + 2475^2 := 2595^2$	$780^2 + 8432^2 := 8468^2$	$780^2 + 76048^2 := 76052^2$
		$780^2 + 152099^2 := 152101^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(780, 8432, 8468)** $\Rightarrow 8468 - 8432 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 101400$, $T_{36} := 780^2$,
 $E := \{16865, 16867, \dots, 16933, 16935\}$
2. **(780, 2992, 3092)** $\Rightarrow 3092 - 2992 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 60840$, $T_{100} := 780^2$,
 $E := \{5985, 5987, \dots, 6181, 6183\}$
3. **(780, 1421, 1621)** $\Rightarrow 1621 - 780 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 69629$, $T_{841} := 1421^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 3239, 3241\}$ or $E := \{1981, 1982, \dots, 2820, 2821\}$
4. **(780, 4189, 4261)** $\Rightarrow 4261 - 780 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 297419$, $T_{3481} := 4189^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 8519, 8521\}$ or $E := \{3301, 3302, \dots, 6780, 6781\}$
5. **(780, 6059, 6109)** $\Rightarrow 6109 - 780 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 502897$, $T_{5329} := 6059^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 12215, 12217\}$ or $E := \{4225, 4226, \dots, 9552, 9553\}$
6. **(780, 16891, 16909)** $\Rightarrow 16909 - 780 = 127^2$, $S_{127 \times 127} := 2246503$, $T_{16129} := 16891^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 33815, 33817\}$ or $E := \{9625, 9626, \dots, 25752, 25753\}$

7. **(780, 38021, 38029)** $\Rightarrow 38029 - 780 = 193^2$, $S_{193 \times 193} := 7490137$, $T_{37249} := 38021^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 76055, 76057\}$ or $E := \{20185, 20186, \dots, 57432, 57433\}$
8. **(780, 152099, 152101)** $\Rightarrow 152101 - 780 = 389^2$, $S_{389 \times 389} := 59470709$, $T_{151321} := 152099^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 304199, 304201\}$ or $E := \{77221, 77222, \dots, 228540, 228541\}$

■ Number 781

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$781^2 + 2460^2 := 2581^2$$

$$781^2 + 4260^2 := 4331^2$$

$$781^2 + 27720^2 := 27731^2$$

$$781^2 + 304980^2 := 304981^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(781, 2460, 2581)** $\Rightarrow 2581 - 2460 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 55451$, $T_{121} := 781^2$,
 $E := \{4921, 4923, \dots, 5159, 5161\}$ or $E := \{4981, 4982, \dots, 5100, 5101\}$

■ Number 782

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$782^2 + 6624^2 := 6670^2$$

$$782^2 + 8976^2 := 9010^2$$

$$782^2 + 152880^2 := 152882^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(782, 152880, 152882)** $\Rightarrow 152882 - 782 = 390^2$, $S_{390 \times 390} := 59928960$, $T_{152100} := 152880^2$,
 $E := \{1565, 1567, \dots, 305761, 305763\}$

■ Number 783

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$783^2 + 1044^2 := 1305^2$$

$$783^2 + 1140^2 := 1383^2$$

$$783^2 + 3480^2 := 3567^2$$

$$783^2 + 3744^2 := 3825^2$$

$$783^2 + 10556^2 := 10585^2$$

$$783^2 + 11340^2 := 11367^2$$

$$783^2 + 34056^2 := 34065^2$$

$$783^2 + 102180^2 := 102183^2$$

$$783^2 + 306544^2 := 306545^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(783, 34056, 34065)** $\Rightarrow 34065 - 34056 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 204363$, $T_9 := 783^2$,
 $E := \{68113, 68115, \dots, 68127, 68129\}$ or $E := \{68117, 68118, \dots, 68124, 68125\}$
2. **(783, 3744, 3825)** $\Rightarrow 3825 - 3744 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 68121$, $T_{81} := 783^2$,
 $E := \{7489, 7491, \dots, 7647, 7649\}$ or $E := \{7529, 7530, \dots, 7608, 7609\}$

■ **Number 784**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$784^2 + 1260^2 := 1484^2$	$784^2 + 4770^2 := 4834^2$	$784^2 + 21945^2 := 21959^2$
$784^2 + 1470^2 := 1666^2$	$784^2 + 5460^2 := 5516^2$	$784^2 + 38412^2 := 38420^2$
$784^2 + 2337^2 := 2465^2$	$784^2 + 9588^2 := 9620^2$	$784^2 + 76830^2 := 76834^2$
$784^2 + 2688^2 := 2800^2$	$784^2 + 10962^2 := 10990^2$	$784^2 + 153663^2 := 153665^2$
$784^2 + 3087^2 := 3185^2$	$784^2 + 19200^2 := 19216^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(784, 19200, 19216)** $\Rightarrow 19216 - 19200 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 153664$, $T_{16} := 784^2$,
 $E := \{38401, 38403, \dots, 38429, 38431\}$
2. **(784, 4770, 4834)** $\Rightarrow 4834 - 4770 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 76832$, $T_{64} := 784^2$,
 $E := \{9541, 9543, \dots, 9665, 9667\}$
3. **(784, 1470, 1666)** $\Rightarrow 1666 - 1470 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 43904$, $T_{196} := 784^2$,
 $E := \{2941, 2943, \dots, 3329, 3331\}$
4. **(784, 2337, 2465)** $\Rightarrow 2465 - 784 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 133209$, $T_{1681} := 2337^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 4927, 4929\}$ or $E := \{2409, 2410, \dots, 4088, 4089\}$
5. **(784, 3087, 3185)** $\Rightarrow 3185 - 784 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 194481$, $T_{2401} := 3087^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 6367, 6369\}$ or $E := \{2769, 2770, \dots, 5168, 5169\}$
6. **(784, 9588, 9620)** $\Rightarrow 9620 - 784 = 94^2$, $S_{94 \times 94} := 977976$, $T_{8836} := 9588^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 19237, 19239\}$
7. **(784, 38412, 38420)** $\Rightarrow 38420 - 784 = 194^2$, $S_{194 \times 194} := 7605576$, $T_{37636} := 38412^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 76837, 76839\}$
8. **(784, 153663, 153665)** $\Rightarrow 153665 - 784 = 391^2$, $S_{391 \times 391} := 60389559$, $T_{152881} := 153663^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 307327, 307329\}$ or $E := \{78009, 78010, \dots, 230888, 230889\}$

■ Number 785

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$785^2 + 1884^2 := 2041^2$$

$$785^2 + 61620^2 := 61625^2$$

$$785^2 + 12312^2 := 12337^2$$

$$785^2 + 308112^2 := 308113^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(785, 12312, 12337)** $\Rightarrow 12337 - 12312 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 123245$, $T_{25} := 785^2$,
 $E := \{24625, 24627, \dots, 24671, 24673\}$ or $E := \{24637, 24638, \dots, 24660, 24661\}$

■ Number 786

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$786^2 + 1048^2 := 1310^2$$

$$786^2 + 17152^2 := 17170^2$$

$$786^2 + 51480^2 := 51486^2$$

$$786^2 + 154448^2 := 154450^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(786, 17152, 17170)** $\Rightarrow 17170 - 786 = 128^2$, $S_{128 \times 128} := 2298368$, $T_{16384} := 17152^2$,
 $E := \{1573, 1575, \dots, 34337, 34339\}$
2. **(786, 154448, 154450)** $\Rightarrow 154450 - 786 = 392^2$, $S_{392 \times 392} := 60852512$, $T_{153664} := 154448^2$,
 $E := \{1573, 1575, \dots, 308897, 308899\}$

■ Number 787

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$787^2 + 309684^2 := 309685^2$$

■ Number 788

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$788^2 + 38805^2 := 38813^2$$

$$788^2 + 77616^2 := 77620^2$$

$$788^2 + 155235^2 := 155237^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(788, 38805, 38813)** $\Rightarrow 38813 - 788 = 195^2$, $S_{195 \times 195} := 7722195$, $T_{38805} := 38805^2$,
 $E := \{1577, 1579, \dots, 77623, 77625\}$ or $E := \{20589, 20590, \dots, 58612, 58613\}$
2. **(788, 155235, 155237)** $\Rightarrow 155237 - 788 = 393^2$, $S_{393 \times 393} := 61317825$, $T_{154449} := 155235^2$,
 $E := \{1577, 1579, \dots, 310471, 310473\}$ or $E := \{78801, 78802, \dots, 233248, 233249\}$

■ Number 789

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll} 789^2 + 1052^2 := 1315^2 & 789^2 + 103752^2 := 103755^2 \\ 789^2 + 34580^2 := 34589^2 & 789^2 + 311260^2 := 311261^2 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(789, 34580, 34589)** $\Rightarrow 34589 - 34580 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 207507$, $T_9 := 789^2$,
 $E := \{69161, 69163, \dots, 69175, 69177\}$ or $E := \{69165, 69166, \dots, 69172, 69173\}$

■ Number 790

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll} 790^2 + 1896^2 := 2054^2 & 790^2 + 31200^2 := 31210^2 \\ 790^2 + 6216^2 := 6266^2 & 790^2 + 156024^2 := 156026^2 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(790, 6216, 6266)** $\Rightarrow 6266 - 790 = 74^2$, $S_{74 \times 74} := 522144$, $T_{5476} := 6216^2$,
 $E := \{1581, 1583, \dots, 12529, 12531\}$
2. **(790, 156024, 156026)** $\Rightarrow 156026 - 790 = 394^2$, $S_{394 \times 394} := 61785504$, $T_{155236} := 156024^2$,
 $E := \{1581, 1583, \dots, 312049, 312051\}$

■ Number 791

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$791^2 + 2712^2 := 2825^2$$

$$791^2 + 6360^2 := 6409^2$$

$$791^2 + 44688^2 := 44695^2$$

$$791^2 + 312840^2 := 312841^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(791, 6360, 6409)** $\Rightarrow 6409 - 6360 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 89383$, $T_{49} := 791^2$,
 $E := \{12721, 12723, \dots, 12815, 12817\}$ or $E := \{12745, 12746, \dots, 12792, 12793\}$

■ Number 792

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$792^2 + 806^2 := 1130^2$$

$$792^2 + 945^2 := 1233^2$$

$$792^2 + 1056^2 := 1320^2$$

$$792^2 + 1175^2 := 1417^2$$

$$792^2 + 1344^2 := 1560^2$$

$$792^2 + 1485^2 := 1683^2$$

$$792^2 + 1694^2 := 1870^2$$

$$792^2 + 1855^2 := 2017^2$$

$$792^2 + 2106^2 := 2250^2$$

$$792^2 + 2310^2 := 2442^2$$

$$792^2 + 2850^2 := 2958^2$$

$$792^2 + 3219^2 := 3315^2$$

$$792^2 + 3520^2 := 3608^2$$

$$792^2 + 4320^2 := 4392^2$$

$$792^2 + 4719^2 := 4785^2$$

$$792^2 + 5781^2 := 5835^2$$

$$792^2 + 6510^2 := 6558^2$$

$$792^2 + 7106^2 := 7150^2$$

$$792^2 + 8694^2 := 8730^2$$

$$792^2 + 9785^2 := 9817^2$$

$$792^2 + 13056^2 := 13080^2$$

$$792^2 + 14245^2 := 14267^2$$

$$792^2 + 17415^2 := 17433^2$$

$$792^2 + 19594^2 := 19610^2$$

$$792^2 + 26130^2 := 26142^2$$

$$792^2 + 39200^2 := 39208^2$$

$$792^2 + 52269^2 := 52275^2$$

$$792^2 + 78406^2 := 78410^2$$

$$792^2 + 156815^2 := 156817^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(792, 19594, 19610)** $\Rightarrow 19610 - 19594 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 156816$, $T_{16} := 792^2$,
 $E := \{39189, 39191, \dots, 39217, 39219\}$
2. **(792, 8694, 8730)** $\Rightarrow 8730 - 8694 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 104544$, $T_{36} := 792^2$,
 $E := \{17389, 17391, \dots, 17457, 17459\}$
3. **(792, 2106, 2250)** $\Rightarrow 2250 - 2106 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 52272$, $T_{144} := 792^2$,
 $E := \{4213, 4215, \dots, 4497, 4499\}$
4. **(792, 806, 1130)** $\Rightarrow 1130 - 806 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 34848$, $T_{324} := 792^2$,
 $E := \{1613, 1615, \dots, 2257, 2259\}$
5. **(792, 945, 1233)** $\Rightarrow 1233 - 792 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 42525$, $T_{441} := 945^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 2463, 2465\}$ or $E := \{1805, 1806, \dots, 2244, 2245\}$
6. **(792, 1175, 1417)** $\Rightarrow 1417 - 792 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 55225$, $T_{625} := 1175^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 2831, 2833\}$ or $E := \{1897, 1898, \dots, 2520, 2521\}$

7. **(792, 1855, 2017)** $\Rightarrow 2017 - 792 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 98315$, $T_{1225} := 1855^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 4031, 4033\}$ or $E := \{2197, 2198, \dots, 3420, 3421\}$
8. **(792, 4320, 4392)** $\Rightarrow 4392 - 792 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 311040$, $T_{3600} := 4320^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 8781, 8783\}$
9. **(792, 9785, 9817)** $\Rightarrow 9817 - 792 = 95^2$, $S_{95 \times 95} := 1007855$, $T_{9025} := 9785^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 19631, 19633\}$ or $E := \{6097, 6098, \dots, 15120, 15121\}$
10. **(792, 17415, 17433)** $\Rightarrow 17433 - 792 = 129^2$, $S_{129 \times 129} := 2351025$, $T_{16641} := 17415^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 34863, 34865\}$ or $E := \{9905, 9906, \dots, 26544, 26545\}$
11. **(792, 39200, 39208)** $\Rightarrow 39208 - 792 = 196^2$, $S_{196 \times 196} := 7840000$, $T_{38416} := 39200^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 78413, 78415\}$
12. **(792, 156815, 156817)** $\Rightarrow 156817 - 792 = 395^2$, $S_{395 \times 395} := 62255555$, $T_{156025} := 156815^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 313631, 313633\}$ or $E := \{79597, 79598, \dots, 235620, 235621\}$

■ Number 793

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$793^2 + 1776^2 := 1945^2$$

$$793^2 + 5124^2 := 5185^2$$

$$793^2 + 24180^2 := 24193^2$$

$$793^2 + 314424^2 := 314425^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(793, 1776, 1945)** $\Rightarrow 1945 - 1776 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 48373$, $T_{169} := 793^2$,
 $E := \{3553, 3555, \dots, 3887, 3889\}$ or $E := \{3637, 3638, \dots, 3804, 3805\}$

■ Number 794

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$794^2 + 157608^2 := 157610^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(794, 157608, 157610)** $\Rightarrow 157610 - 794 = 396^2$, $S_{396 \times 396} := 62727984$, $T_{156816} := 157608^2$,
 $E := \{1589, 1591, \dots, 315217, 315219\}$

■ Number 795

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 795^2 + 1060^2 &:= 1325^2 \\ 795^2 + 1292^2 &:= 1517^2 \\ 795^2 + 1908^2 &:= 2067^2 \\ 795^2 + 4176^2 &:= 4251^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 795^2 + 5936^2 &:= 5989^2 \\ 795^2 + 7000^2 &:= 7045^2 \\ 795^2 + 12628^2 &:= 12653^2 \\ 795^2 + 21060^2 &:= 21075^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 795^2 + 35108^2 &:= 35117^2 \\ 795^2 + 63200^2 &:= 63205^2 \\ 795^2 + 105336^2 &:= 105339^2 \\ 795^2 + 316012^2 &:= 316013^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(795, 35108, 35117)** $\Rightarrow 35117 - 35108 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 210675$, $T_9 := 795^2$,
 $E := \{70217, 70219, \dots, 70231, 70233\}$ or $E := \{70221, 70222, \dots, 70228, 70229\}$
2. **(795, 12628, 12653)** $\Rightarrow 12653 - 12628 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 126405$, $T_{25} := 795^2$,
 $E := \{25257, 25259, \dots, 25303, 25305\}$ or $E := \{25269, 25270, \dots, 25292, 25293\}$
3. **(795, 1292, 1517)** $\Rightarrow 1517 - 1292 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 42135$, $T_{225} := 795^2$,
 $E := \{2585, 2587, \dots, 3031, 3033\}$ or $E := \{2697, 2698, \dots, 2920, 2921\}$

■ Number 796

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned} 796^2 + 39597^2 &:= 39605^2 \\ 796^2 + 79200^2 &:= 79204^2 \\ 796^2 + 158403^2 &:= 158405^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(796, 39597, 39605)** $\Rightarrow 39605 - 796 = 197^2$, $S_{197 \times 197} := 7958997$, $T_{38809} := 39597^2$,
 $E := \{1593, 1595, \dots, 79207, 79209\}$ or $E := \{20997, 20998, \dots, 59804, 59805\}$
2. **(796, 158403, 158405)** $\Rightarrow 158405 - 796 = 397^2$, $S_{397 \times 397} := 63202797$, $T_{157609} := 158403^2$,
 $E := \{1593, 1595, \dots, 316807, 316809\}$ or $E := \{80397, 80398, \dots, 238004, 238005\}$

■ Number 797

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$797^2 + 317604^2 := 317605^2$$

■ Number 798

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$798^2 + 936^2 := 1230^2$$

$$798^2 + 1064^2 := 1330^2$$

$$798^2 + 2464^2 := 2590^2$$

$$798^2 + 2736^2 := 2850^2$$

$$798^2 + 3200^2 := 3298^2$$

$$798^2 + 7560^2 := 7602^2$$

$$798^2 + 8360^2 := 8398^2$$

$$798^2 + 17680^2 := 17698^2$$

$$798^2 + 22736^2 := 22750^2$$

$$798^2 + 53064^2 := 53070^2$$

$$798^2 + 159200^2 := 159202^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(798, 3200, 3298)** $\Rightarrow 3298 - 798 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 204800$, $T_{2500} := 3200^2$,
 $E := \{1597, 1599, \dots, 6593, 6595\}$

2. **(798, 17680, 17698)** $\Rightarrow 17698 - 798 = 130^2$, $S_{130 \times 130} := 2404480$, $T_{16900} := 17680^2$,
 $E := \{1597, 1599, \dots, 35393, 35395\}$

3. **(798, 159200, 159202)** $\Rightarrow 159202 - 798 = 398^2$, $S_{398 \times 398} := 63680000$, $T_{158404} := 159200^2$,
 $E := \{1597, 1599, \dots, 318401, 318403\}$

■ Number 799

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$799^2 + 960^2 := 1249^2$$

$$799^2 + 6768^2 := 6815^2$$

$$799^2 + 18768^2 := 18785^2$$

$$799^2 + 319200^2 := 319201^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(799, 960, 1249)** $\Rightarrow 1249 - 960 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 37553$, $T_{289} := 799^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 2495, 2497\}$ or $E := \{2065, 2066, \dots, 2352, 2353\}$

■ Number 800

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$800^2 + 840^2 := 1160^2$$

$$800^2 + 1122^2 := 1378^2$$

$$800^2 + 1155^2 := 1405^2$$

$$800^2 + 1500^2 := 1700^2$$

$$800^2 + 1920^2 := 2080^2$$

$$800^2 + 2436^2 := 2564^2$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 800^2 + 3150^2 := 3250^2 & \\
 800^2 + 3960^2 := 4040^2 & 800^2 + 15990^2 := 16010^2 \\
 800^2 + 4968^2 := 5032^2 & 800^2 + 19992^2 := 20008^2 \\
 800^2 + 6375^2 := 6425^2 & 800^2 + 31995^2 := 32005^2 \\
 800^2 + 7980^2 := 8020^2 & 800^2 + 39996^2 := 40004^2 \\
 800^2 + 9984^2 := 10016^2 & 800^2 + 79998^2 := 80002^2 \\
 & 800^2 + 159999^2 := 160001^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(800, 19992, 20008)** $\Rightarrow 20008 - 19992 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 160000$, $T_{16} := 800^2$,
 $E := \{39985, 39987, \dots, 40013, 40015\}$
2. **(800, 4968, 5032)** $\Rightarrow 5032 - 4968 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 80000$, $T_{64} := 800^2$,
 $E := \{9937, 9939, \dots, 10061, 10063\}$
3. **(800, 3150, 3250)** $\Rightarrow 3250 - 3150 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 64000$, $T_{100} := 800^2$,
 $E := \{6301, 6303, \dots, 6497, 6499\}$
4. **(800, 1122, 1378)** $\Rightarrow 1378 - 1122 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 40000$, $T_{256} := 800^2$,
 $E := \{2245, 2247, \dots, 2753, 2755\}$
5. **(800, 1500, 1700)** $\Rightarrow 1700 - 800 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 75000$, $T_{900} := 1500^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 3397, 3399\}$
6. **(800, 2436, 2564)** $\Rightarrow 2564 - 800 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 141288$, $T_{1764} := 2436^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 5125, 5127\}$
7. **(800, 6375, 6425)** $\Rightarrow 6425 - 800 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 541875$, $T_{5625} := 6375^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 12847, 12849\}$ or $E := \{4413, 4414, \dots, 10036, 10037\}$
8. **(800, 9984, 10016)** $\Rightarrow 10016 - 800 = 96^2$, $S_{96 \times 96} := 1038336$, $T_{9216} := 9984^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 20029, 20031\}$
9. **(800, 39996, 40004)** $\Rightarrow 40004 - 800 = 198^2$, $S_{198 \times 198} := 8079192$, $T_{39204} := 39996^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 80005, 80007\}$
10. **(800, 159999, 160001)** $\Rightarrow 160001 - 800 = 399^2$, $S_{399 \times 399} := 64159599$, $T_{159201} := 159999^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 319999, 320001\}$ or $E := \{81201, 81202, \dots, 240400, 240401\}$

2.9 Pythagorean Triples: 801 to 900

■ Number 801

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$801^2 + 1068^2 := 1335^2$$

$$801^2 + 3560^2 := 3649^2$$

$$801^2 + 3920^2 := 4001^2$$

$$801^2 + 11868^2 := 11895^2$$

$$801^2 + 35640^2 := 35649^2$$

$$801^2 + 106932^2 := 106935^2$$

$$801^2 + 320800^2 := 320801^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(801, 35640, 35649)** $\Rightarrow 35649 - 35640 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 213867$, $T_9 := 801^2$,
 $E := \{71281, 71283, \dots, 71295, 71297\}$ or $E := \{71285, 71286, \dots, 71292, 71293\}$
2. **(801, 3920, 4001)** $\Rightarrow 4001 - 3920 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 71289$, $T_{81} := 801^2$,
 $E := \{7841, 7843, \dots, 7999, 8001\}$ or $E := \{7881, 7882, \dots, 7960, 7961\}$

■ Number 802

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$802^2 + 160800^2 := 160802^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(802, 160800, 160802)** $\Rightarrow 160802 - 802 = 400^2$, $S_{400 \times 400} := 64641600$, $T_{160000} := 160800^2$,
 $E := \{1605, 1607, \dots, 321601, 321603\}$

■ Number 803

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$803^2 + 2604^2 := 2725^2$$

$$803^2 + 4380^2 := 4453^2$$

$$803^2 + 29304^2 := 29315^2$$

$$803^2 + 322404^2 := 322405^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(803, 2604, 2725)** $\Rightarrow 2725 - 2604 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 58619$, $T_{121} := 803^2$,
 $E := \{5209, 5211, \dots, 5447, 5449\}$ or $E := \{5269, 5270, \dots, 5388, 5389\}$

■ Number 804

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned} 804^2 + 1072^2 &:= 1340^2 \\ 804^2 + 2345^2 &:= 2479^2 \\ 804^2 + 4453^2 &:= 4525^2 \\ 804^2 + 8960^2 &:= 8996^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 804^2 + 13455^2 &:= 13479^2 \\ 804^2 + 17947^2 &:= 17965^2 \\ 804^2 + 26928^2 &:= 26940^2 \\ 804^2 + 40397^2 &:= 40405^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 804^2 + 53865^2 &:= 53871^2 \\ 804^2 + 80800^2 &:= 80804^2 \\ 804^2 + 161603^2 &:= 161605^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(804, 8960, 8996)** $\Rightarrow 8996 - 8960 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 107736$, $T_{36} := 804^2$,
 $E := \{17921, 17923, \dots, 17989, 17991\}$
2. **(804, 4453, 4525)** $\Rightarrow 4525 - 804 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 325069$, $T_{3721} := 4453^2$,
 $E := \{1609, 1611, \dots, 9047, 9049\}$ or $E := \{3469, 3470, \dots, 7188, 7189\}$
3. **(804, 17947, 17965)** $\Rightarrow 17965 - 804 = 131^2$, $S_{131 \times 131} := 2458739$, $T_{17161} := 17947^2$,
 $E := \{1609, 1611, \dots, 35927, 35929\}$ or $E := \{10189, 10190, \dots, 27348, 27349\}$
4. **(804, 40397, 40405)** $\Rightarrow 40405 - 804 = 199^2$, $S_{199 \times 199} := 8200591$, $T_{39601} := 40397^2$,
 $E := \{1609, 1611, \dots, 80807, 80809\}$ or $E := \{21409, 21410, \dots, 61008, 61009\}$
5. **(804, 161603, 161605)** $\Rightarrow 161605 - 804 = 401^2$, $S_{401 \times 401} := 65126009$, $T_{160801} := 161603^2$,
 $E := \{1609, 1611, \dots, 323207, 323209\}$ or $E := \{82009, 82010, \dots, 242808, 242809\}$

■ Number 805

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 805^2 + 1200^2 &:= 1445^2 \\ 805^2 + 1764^2 &:= 1939^2 \\ 805^2 + 1932^2 &:= 2093^2 \\ 805^2 + 2760^2 &:= 2875^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 805^2 + 6588^2 &:= 6637^2 \\ 805^2 + 9240^2 &:= 9275^2 \\ 805^2 + 12948^2 &:= 12973^2 \\ 805^2 + 14076^2 &:= 14099^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 805^2 + 46284^2 &:= 46291^2 \\ 805^2 + 64800^2 &:= 64805^2 \\ 805^2 + 324012^2 &:= 324013^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(805, 12948, 12973)** $\Rightarrow 12973 - 12948 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 129605$, $T_{25} := 805^2$,
 $E := \{25897, 25899, \dots, 25943, 25945\}$ or $E := \{25909, 25910, \dots, 25932, 25933\}$
2. **(805, 6588, 6637)** $\Rightarrow 6637 - 6588 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 92575$, $T_{49} := 805^2$,
 $E := \{13177, 13179, \dots, 13271, 13273\}$ or $E := \{13201, 13202, \dots, 13248, 13249\}$

■ Number 806

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$806^2 + 5208^2 := 5270^2$$

$$806^2 + 12480^2 := 12506^2$$

$$806^2 + 162408^2 := 162410^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(806, 162408, 162410)** $\Rightarrow 162410 - 806 = 402^2$, $S_{402 \times 402} := 65612832$, $T_{161604} := 162408^2$,
 $E := \{1613, 1615, \dots, 324817, 324819\}$

■ Number 807

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$807^2 + 1076^2 := 1345^2$$

$$807^2 + 36176^2 := 36185^2$$

$$807^2 + 108540^2 := 108543^2$$

$$807^2 + 325624^2 := 325625^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(807, 36176, 36185)** $\Rightarrow 36185 - 36176 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 217083$, $T_9 := 807^2$,
 $E := \{72353, 72355, \dots, 72367, 72369\}$ or $E := \{72357, 72358, \dots, 72364, 72365\}$

■ Number 808

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$808^2 + 1515^2 := 1717^2$$

$$808^2 + 10185^2 := 10217^2$$

$$808^2 + 20394^2 := 20410^2$$

$$808^2 + 40800^2 := 40808^2$$

$$808^2 + 81606^2 := 81610^2$$

$$808^2 + 163215^2 := 163217^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(808, 20394, 20410)** $\Rightarrow 20410 - 20394 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 163216$, $T_{16} := 808^2$,
 $E := \{40789, 40791, \dots, 40817, 40819\}$
2. **(808, 10185, 10217)** $\Rightarrow 10217 - 808 = 97^2$, $S_{97 \times 97} := 1069425$, $T_{9409} := 10185^2$,
 $E := \{1617, 1619, \dots, 20431, 20433\}$ or $E := \{6321, 6322, \dots, 15728, 15729\}$
3. **(808, 40800, 40808)** $\Rightarrow 40808 - 808 = 200^2$, $S_{200 \times 200} := 8323200$, $T_{40000} := 40800^2$,
 $E := \{1617, 1619, \dots, 81613, 81615\}$

4. **(808, 163215, 163217)** $\Rightarrow 163217 - 808 = 403^2$, $S_{403 \times 403} := 66102075$, $T_{162409} := 163215^2$,
 $E := \{1617, 1619, \dots, 326431, 326433\}$ or $E := \{82821, 82822, \dots, 245228, 245229\}$

■ Number 809

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$809^2 + 327240^2 := 327241^2$$

■ Number 810

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$810^2 + 1080^2 := 1350^2$$

$$810^2 + 1944^2 := 2106^2$$

$$810^2 + 2112^2 := 2262^2$$

$$810^2 + 3600^2 := 3690^2$$

$$810^2 + 6048^2 := 6102^2$$

$$810^2 + 6536^2 := 6586^2$$

$$810^2 + 10920^2 := 10950^2$$

$$810^2 + 18216^2 := 18234^2$$

$$810^2 + 32800^2 := 32810^2$$

$$810^2 + 54672^2 := 54678^2$$

$$810^2 + 164024^2 := 164026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(810, 1944, 2106)** $\Rightarrow 2106 - 810 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 104976$, $T_{1296} := 1944^2$,
 $E := \{1621, 1623, \dots, 4209, 4211\}$
2. **(810, 6536, 6586)** $\Rightarrow 6586 - 810 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 562096$, $T_{5776} := 6536^2$,
 $E := \{1621, 1623, \dots, 13169, 13171\}$
3. **(810, 18216, 18234)** $\Rightarrow 18234 - 810 = 132^2$, $S_{132 \times 132} := 2513808$, $T_{17424} := 18216^2$,
 $E := \{1621, 1623, \dots, 36465, 36467\}$
4. **(810, 164024, 164026)** $\Rightarrow 164026 - 810 = 404^2$, $S_{404 \times 404} := 66593744$, $T_{163216} := 164024^2$,
 $E := \{1621, 1623, \dots, 328049, 328051\}$

■ Number 811

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$811^2 + 328860^2 := 328861^2$$

■ Number 812

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$812^2 + 1305^2 := 1537^2$$

$$812^2 + 1584^2 := 1780^2$$

$$812^2 + 2784^2 := 2900^2$$

$$812^2 + 3315^2 := 3413^2$$

$$812^2 + 5655^2 := 5713^2$$

$$812^2 + 5859^2 := 5915^2$$

$$812^2 + 11760^2 := 11788^2$$

$$812^2 + 23541^2 := 23555^2$$

$$812^2 + 41205^2 := 41213^2$$

$$812^2 + 82416^2 := 82420^2$$

$$812^2 + 164835^2 := 164837^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(812, 1584, 1780)** $\Rightarrow 1780 - 1584 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 47096$, $T_{196} := 812^2$,
 $E := \{3169, 3171, \dots, 3557, 3559\}$

2. **(812, 3315, 3413)** $\Rightarrow 3413 - 812 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 215475$, $T_{2601} := 3315^2$,
 $E := \{1625, 1627, \dots, 6823, 6825\}$ or $E := \{2925, 2926, \dots, 5524, 5525\}$

3. **(812, 41205, 41213)** $\Rightarrow 41213 - 812 = 201^2$, $S_{201 \times 201} := 8447025$, $T_{40401} := 41205^2$,
 $E := \{1625, 1627, \dots, 82423, 82425\}$ or $E := \{21825, 21826, \dots, 62224, 62225\}$

4. **(812, 164835, 164837)** $\Rightarrow 164837 - 812 = 405^2$, $S_{405 \times 405} := 67087845$, $T_{164025} := 164835^2$,
 $E := \{1625, 1627, \dots, 329671, 329673\}$ or $E := \{83637, 83638, \dots, 247660, 247661\}$

■ Number 813

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$813^2 + 1084^2 := 1355^2$$

$$813^2 + 36716^2 := 36725^2$$

$$813^2 + 110160^2 := 110163^2$$

$$813^2 + 330484^2 := 330485^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(813, 36716, 36725)** $\Rightarrow 36725 - 36716 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 220323$, $T_9 := 813^2$,
 $E := \{73433, 73435, \dots, 73447, 73449\}$ or $E := \{73437, 73438, \dots, 73444, 73445\}$

■ Number 814

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$814^2 + 1248^2 := 1490^2$$

$$814^2 + 4440^2 := 4514^2$$

$$814^2 + 15048^2 := 15070^2$$

$$814^2 + 165648^2 := 165650^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(814, 1248, 1490)** $\Rightarrow 1490 - 814 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 59904$, $T_{676} := 1248^2$,
 $E := \{1629, 1631, \dots, 2977, 2979\}$

2. **(814, 165648, 165650)** $\Rightarrow 165650 - 814 = 406^2$, $S_{406 \times 406} := 67584384$, $T_{164836} := 165648^2$,
 $E := \{1629, 1631, \dots, 331297, 331299\}$

■ Number 815

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$815^2 + 1956^2 := 2119^2$$

$$815^2 + 13272^2 := 13297^2$$

$$815^2 + 66420^2 := 66425^2$$

$$815^2 + 332112^2 := 332113^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(815, 13272, 13297)** $\Rightarrow 13297 - 13272 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 132845$, $T_{25} := 815^2$,
 $E := \{26545, 26547, \dots, 26591, 26593\}$ or $E := \{26557, 26558, \dots, 26580, 26581\}$

■ Number 816

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$816^2 + 935^2 := 1241^2$$

$$816^2 + 1012^2 := 1300^2$$

$$816^2 + 1088^2 := 1360^2$$

$$816^2 + 1530^2 := 1734^2$$

$$816^2 + 1638^2 := 1830^2$$

$$816^2 + 2240^2 := 2384^2$$

$$816^2 + 2380^2 := 2516^2$$

$$816^2 + 2537^2 := 2665^2$$

$$816^2 + 3213^2 := 3315^2$$

$$816^2 + 3420^2 := 3516^2$$

$$816^2 + 4588^2 := 4660^2$$

$$816^2 + 4862^2 := 4930^2$$

$$816^2 + 5170^2 := 5234^2$$

$$816^2 + 6912^2 := 6960^2$$

$$816^2 + 9230^2 := 9266^2$$

$$816^2 + 9775^2 := 9809^2$$

$$816^2 + 10388^2 := 10420^2$$

$$816^2 + 13860^2 := 13884^2$$

$$816^2 + 18487^2 := 18505^2$$

$$816^2 + 20800^2 := 20816^2$$

$$816^2 + 27738^2 := 27750^2$$

$$816^2 + 41612^2 := 41620^2$$

$$816^2 + 55485^2 := 55491^2$$

$$816^2 + 83230^2 := 83234^2$$

$$816^2 + 166463^2 := 166465^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(816, 20800, 20816)** $\Rightarrow 20816 - 20800 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 166464$, $T_{16} := 816^2$,
 $E := \{41601, 41603, \dots, 41629, 41631\}$

2. **(816, 9230, 9266)** $\Rightarrow 9266 - 9230 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 110976$, $T_{36} := 816^2$,
 $E := \{18461, 18463, \dots, 18529, 18531\}$
3. **(816, 5170, 5234)** $\Rightarrow 5234 - 5170 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 83232$, $T_{64} := 816^2$,
 $E := \{10341, 10343, \dots, 10465, 10467\}$
4. **(816, 2240, 2384)** $\Rightarrow 2384 - 2240 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 55488$, $T_{144} := 816^2$,
 $E := \{4481, 4483, \dots, 4765, 4767\}$
5. **(816, 1012, 1300)** $\Rightarrow 1300 - 816 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 46552$, $T_{484} := 1012^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 2597, 2599\}$
6. **(816, 2537, 2665)** $\Rightarrow 2665 - 816 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 149683$, $T_{1849} := 2537^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 5327, 5329\}$ or $E := \{2557, 2558, \dots, 4404, 4405\}$
7. **(816, 4588, 4660)** $\Rightarrow 4660 - 816 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 339512$, $T_{3844} := 4588^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 9317, 9319\}$
8. **(816, 10388, 10420)** $\Rightarrow 10420 - 816 = 98^2$, $S_{98 \times 98} := 1101128$, $T_{9604} := 10388^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 20837, 20839\}$
9. **(816, 18487, 18505)** $\Rightarrow 18505 - 816 = 133^2$, $S_{133 \times 133} := 2569693$, $T_{17689} := 18487^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 37007, 37009\}$ or $E := \{10477, 10478, \dots, 28164, 28165\}$
10. **(816, 41612, 41620)** $\Rightarrow 41620 - 816 = 202^2$, $S_{202 \times 202} := 8572072$, $T_{40804} := 41612^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 83237, 83239\}$
11. **(816, 166463, 166465)** $\Rightarrow 166465 - 816 = 407^2$, $S_{407 \times 407} := 68083367$, $T_{165649} := 166463^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 332927, 332929\}$ or $E := \{84457, 84458, \dots, 250104, 250105\}$

■ Number 817

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$817^2 + 7740^2 := 7783^2$$

$$817^2 + 17556^2 := 17575^2$$

$$817^2 + 333744^2 := 333745^2$$

■ Number 818

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$818^2 + 167280^2 := 167282^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(818, 167280, 167282)** $\Rightarrow 167282 - 818 = 408^2$, $S_{408 \times 408} := 68584800$, $T_{166464} := 167280^2$,
 $E := \{1637, 1639, \dots, 334561, 334563\}$

■ Number 819

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$819^2 + 1092^2 := 1365^2$$

$$819^2 + 1680^2 := 1869^2$$

$$819^2 + 1900^2 := 2069^2$$

$$819^2 + 2208^2 := 2355^2$$

$$819^2 + 2808^2 := 2925^2$$

$$819^2 + 3640^2 := 3731^2$$

$$819^2 + 4100^2 := 4181^2$$

$$819^2 + 5292^2 := 5355^2$$

$$819^2 + 6820^2 := 6869^2$$

$$819^2 + 8580^2 := 8619^2$$

$$819^2 + 12408^2 := 12435^2$$

$$819^2 + 15960^2 := 15981^2$$

$$819^2 + 25792^2 := 25805^2$$

$$819^2 + 37260^2 := 37269^2$$

$$819^2 + 47908^2 := 47915^2$$

$$819^2 + 111792^2 := 111795^2$$

$$819^2 + 335380^2 := 335381^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(819, 37260, 37269)** $\Rightarrow 37269 - 37260 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 223587$, $T_9 := 819^2$,
 $E := \{74521, 74523, \dots, 74535, 74537\}$ or $E := \{74525, 74526, \dots, 74532, 74533\}$
2. **(819, 6820, 6869)** $\Rightarrow 6869 - 6820 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 95823$, $T_{49} := 819^2$,
 $E := \{13641, 13643, \dots, 13735, 13737\}$ or $E := \{13665, 13666, \dots, 13712, 13713\}$
3. **(819, 4100, 4181)** $\Rightarrow 4181 - 4100 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 74529$, $T_{81} := 819^2$,
 $E := \{8201, 8203, \dots, 8359, 8361\}$ or $E := \{8241, 8242, \dots, 8320, 8321\}$
4. **(819, 1900, 2069)** $\Rightarrow 2069 - 1900 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 51597$, $T_{169} := 819^2$,
 $E := \{3801, 3803, \dots, 4135, 4137\}$ or $E := \{3885, 3886, \dots, 4052, 4053\}$

■ Number 820

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$820^2 + 861^2 := 1189^2$$

$$820^2 + 1581^2 := 1781^2$$

$$820^2 + 1968^2 := 2132^2$$

$$820^2 + 3312^2 := 3412^2$$

$$820^2 + 4059^2 := 4141^2$$

$$820^2 + 6699^2 := 6749^2$$

$$820^2 + 8385^2 := 8425^2$$

$$820^2 + 16800^2 := 16820^2$$

$$820^2 + 33615^2 := 33625^2$$

$$820^2 + 42021^2 := 42029^2$$

$$820^2 + 84048^2 := 84052^2$$

$$820^2 + 168099^2 := 168101^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(820, 3312, 3412)** $\Rightarrow 3412 - 3312 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 67240$, $T_{100} := 820^2$,
 $E := \{6625, 6627, \dots, 6821, 6823\}$
2. **(820, 1581, 1781)** $\Rightarrow 1781 - 820 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 80631$, $T_{961} := 1581^2$,
 $E := \{1641, 1643, \dots, 3559, 3561\}$ or $E := \{2121, 2122, \dots, 3080, 3081\}$

3. **(820, 6699, 6749)** $\Rightarrow 6749 - 820 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 582813$, $T_{5929} := 6699^2$,
 $E := \{1641, 1643, \dots, 13495, 13497\}$ or $E := \{4605, 4606, \dots, 10532, 10533\}$
4. **(820, 42021, 42029)** $\Rightarrow 42029 - 820 = 203^2$, $S_{203 \times 203} := 8698347$, $T_{41209} := 42021^2$,
 $E := \{1641, 1643, \dots, 84055, 84057\}$ or $E := \{22245, 22246, \dots, 63452, 63453\}$
5. **(820, 168099, 168101)** $\Rightarrow 168101 - 820 = 409^2$, $S_{409 \times 409} := 69088689$, $T_{167281} := 168099^2$,
 $E := \{1641, 1643, \dots, 336199, 336201\}$ or $E := \{85281, 85282, \dots, 252560, 252561\}$

■ Number 821

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$821^2 + 337020^2 := 337021^2$$

■ Number 822

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$822^2 + 1096^2 := 1370^2$$

$$822^2 + 18760^2 := 18778^2$$

$$822^2 + 56304^2 := 56310^2$$

$$822^2 + 168920^2 := 168922^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(822, 18760, 18778)** $\Rightarrow 18778 - 822 = 134^2$, $S_{134 \times 134} := 2626400$, $T_{17956} := 18760^2$,
 $E := \{1645, 1647, \dots, 37553, 37555\}$
2. **(822, 168920, 168922)** $\Rightarrow 168922 - 822 = 410^2$, $S_{410 \times 410} := 69595040$, $T_{168100} := 168920^2$,
 $E := \{1645, 1647, \dots, 337841, 337843\}$

■ Number 823

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$823^2 + 338664^2 := 338665^2$$

■ Number 824

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$824^2 + 1545^2 := 1751^2$$

$$824^2 + 10593^2 := 10625^2$$

$$824^2 + 21210^2 := 21226^2$$

$$824^2 + 42432^2 := 42440^2$$

$$824^2 + 84870^2 := 84874^2$$

$$824^2 + 169743^2 := 169745^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(824, 21210, 21226)** $\Rightarrow 21226 - 21210 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 169744$, $T_{16} := 824^2$,
 $E := \{42421, 42423, \dots, 42449, 42451\}$
2. **(824, 10593, 10625)** $\Rightarrow 10625 - 824 = 99^2$, $S_{99 \times 99} := 1133451$, $T_{9801} := 10593^2$,
 $E := \{1649, 1651, \dots, 21247, 21249\}$ or $E := \{6549, 6550, \dots, 16348, 16349\}$
3. **(824, 42432, 42440)** $\Rightarrow 42440 - 824 = 204^2$, $S_{204 \times 204} := 8825856$, $T_{41616} := 42432^2$,
 $E := \{1649, 1651, \dots, 84877, 84879\}$
4. **(824, 169743, 169745)** $\Rightarrow 169745 - 824 = 411^2$, $S_{411 \times 411} := 70103859$, $T_{168921} := 169743^2$,
 $E := \{1649, 1651, \dots, 339487, 339489\}$ or $E := \{86109, 86110, \dots, 255028, 255029\}$

■ Number 825

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$825^2 + 1100^2 := 1375^2$$

$$825^2 + 1400^2 := 1625^2$$

$$825^2 + 1980^2 := 2145^2$$

$$825^2 + 2660^2 := 2785^2$$

$$825^2 + 2752^2 := 2873^2$$

$$825^2 + 3388^2 := 3487^2$$

$$825^2 + 4500^2 := 4575^2$$

$$825^2 + 6160^2 := 6215^2$$

$$825^2 + 7540^2 := 7585^2$$

$$825^2 + 10296^2 := 10329^2$$

$$825^2 + 13600^2 := 13625^2$$

$$825^2 + 22680^2 := 22695^2$$

$$825^2 + 30932^2 := 30943^2$$

$$825^2 + 37808^2 := 37817^2$$

$$825^2 + 68060^2 := 68065^2$$

$$825^2 + 113436^2 := 113439^2$$

$$825^2 + 340312^2 := 340313^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(825, 37808, 37817)** $\Rightarrow 37817 - 37808 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 226875$, $T_9 := 825^2$,
 $E := \{75617, 75619, \dots, 75631, 75633\}$ or $E := \{75621, 75622, \dots, 75628, 75629\}$
2. **(825, 13600, 13625)** $\Rightarrow 13625 - 13600 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 136125$, $T_{25} := 825^2$,
 $E := \{27201, 27203, \dots, 27247, 27249\}$ or $E := \{27213, 27214, \dots, 27236, 27237\}$
3. **(825, 2752, 2873)** $\Rightarrow 2873 - 2752 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 61875$, $T_{121} := 825^2$,
 $E := \{5505, 5507, \dots, 5743, 5745\}$ or $E := \{5565, 5566, \dots, 5684, 5685\}$
4. **(825, 1400, 1625)** $\Rightarrow 1625 - 1400 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 45375$, $T_{225} := 825^2$,
 $E := \{2801, 2803, \dots, 3247, 3249\}$ or $E := \{2913, 2914, \dots, 3136, 3137\}$

■ Number 826

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$826^2 + 2832^2 := 2950^2$$

$$826^2 + 3432^2 := 3530^2$$

$$826^2 + 24360^2 := 24374^2$$

$$826^2 + 170568^2 := 170570^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(826, 3432, 3530)** $\Rightarrow 3530 - 826 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 226512$, $T_{2704} := 3432^2$,
 $E := \{1653, 1655, \dots, 7057, 7059\}$

2. **(826, 170568, 170570)** $\Rightarrow 170570 - 826 = 412^2$, $S_{412 \times 412} := 70615152$, $T_{169744} := 170568^2$,
 $E := \{1653, 1655, \dots, 341137, 341139\}$

■ Number 827

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$827^2 + 341964^2 := 341965^2$$

■ Number 828

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$828^2 + 896^2 := 1220^2$$

$$828^2 + 1104^2 := 1380^2$$

$$828^2 + 1479^2 := 1695^2$$

$$828^2 + 1771^2 := 1955^2$$

$$828^2 + 2035^2 := 2197^2$$

$$828^2 + 2415^2 := 2553^2$$

$$828^2 + 3120^2 := 3228^2$$

$$828^2 + 3680^2 := 3772^2$$

$$828^2 + 4725^2 := 4797^2$$

$$828^2 + 6321^2 := 6375^2$$

$$828^2 + 7429^2 := 7475^2$$

$$828^2 + 9504^2 := 9540^2$$

$$828^2 + 14271^2 := 14295^2$$

$$828^2 + 19035^2 := 19053^2$$

$$828^2 + 28560^2 := 28572^2$$

$$828^2 + 42845^2 := 42853^2$$

$$828^2 + 57129^2 := 57135^2$$

$$828^2 + 85696^2 := 85700^2$$

$$828^2 + 171395^2 := 171397^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(828, 9504, 9540)** $\Rightarrow 9540 - 9504 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 114264$, $T_{36} := 828^2$,
 $E := \{19009, 19011, \dots, 19077, 19079\}$

2. **(828, 896, 1220)** $\Rightarrow 1220 - 896 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 38088$, $T_{324} := 828^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 2437, 2439\}$

3. **(828, 2035, 2197)** $\Rightarrow 2197 - 828 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 111925$, $T_{1369} := 2035^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 4391, 4393\}$ or $E := \{2341, 2342, \dots, 3708, 3709\}$
4. **(828, 4725, 4797)** $\Rightarrow 4797 - 828 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 354375$, $T_{3969} := 4725^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 9591, 9593\}$ or $E := \{3641, 3642, \dots, 7608, 7609\}$
5. **(828, 19035, 19053)** $\Rightarrow 19053 - 828 = 135^2$, $S_{135 \times 135} := 2683935$, $T_{18225} := 19035^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 38103, 38105\}$ or $E := \{10769, 10770, \dots, 28992, 28993\}$
6. **(828, 42845, 42853)** $\Rightarrow 42853 - 828 = 205^2$, $S_{205 \times 205} := 8954605$, $T_{42025} := 42845^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 85703, 85705\}$ or $E := \{22669, 22670, \dots, 64692, 64693\}$
7. **(828, 171395, 171397)** $\Rightarrow 171397 - 828 = 413^2$, $S_{413 \times 413} := 71128925$, $T_{170569} := 171395^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 342791, 342793\}$ or $E := \{86941, 86942, \dots, 257508, 257509\}$

■ Number 829

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$829^2 + 343620^2 := 343621^2$$

■ Number 830

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$830^2 + 1992^2 := 2158^2$$

$$830^2 + 6864^2 := 6914^2$$

$$830^2 + 34440^2 := 34450^2$$

$$830^2 + 172224^2 := 172226^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(830, 6864, 6914)** $\Rightarrow 6914 - 830 = 78^2$, $S_{78 \times 78} := 604032$, $T_{6084} := 6864^2$,
 $E := \{1661, 1663, \dots, 13825, 13827\}$
2. **(830, 172224, 172226)** $\Rightarrow 172226 - 830 = 414^2$, $S_{414 \times 414} := 71645184$, $T_{171396} := 172224^2$,
 $E := \{1661, 1663, \dots, 344449, 344451\}$

■ Number 831

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$831^2 + 1108^2 := 1385^2$$

$$831^2 + 38360^2 := 38369^2$$

$$831^2 + 115092^2 := 115095^2$$

$$831^2 + 345280^2 := 345281^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(831, 38360, 38369)** $\Rightarrow 38369 - 38360 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 230187$, $T_9 := 831^2$,
 $E := \{76721, 76723, \dots, 76735, 76737\}$ or $E := \{76725, 76726, \dots, 76732, 76733\}$

■ Number 832

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$832^2 + 855^2 := 1193^2$$

$$832^2 + 1224^2 := 1480^2$$

$$832^2 + 1560^2 := 1768^2$$

$$832^2 + 2640^2 := 2768^2$$

$$832^2 + 3276^2 := 3380^2$$

$$832^2 + 5376^2 := 5440^2$$

$$832^2 + 6630^2 := 6682^2$$

$$832^2 + 10800^2 := 10832^2$$

$$832^2 + 13299^2 := 13325^2$$

$$832^2 + 21624^2 := 21640^2$$

$$832^2 + 43260^2 := 43268^2$$

$$832^2 + 86526^2 := 86530^2$$

$$832^2 + 173055^2 := 173057^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(832, 21624, 21640)** $\Rightarrow 21640 - 21624 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 173056$, $T_{16} := 832^2$,
 $E := \{43249, 43251, \dots, 43277, 43279\}$
2. **(832, 5376, 5440)** $\Rightarrow 5440 - 5376 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 86528$, $T_{64} := 832^2$,
 $E := \{10753, 10755, \dots, 10877, 10879\}$
3. **(832, 1224, 1480)** $\Rightarrow 1480 - 1224 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 43264$, $T_{256} := 832^2$,
 $E := \{2449, 2451, \dots, 2957, 2959\}$
4. **(832, 855, 1193)** $\Rightarrow 1193 - 832 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 38475$, $T_{361} := 855^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 2383, 2385\}$ or $E := \{1845, 1846, \dots, 2204, 2205\}$
5. **(832, 2640, 2768)** $\Rightarrow 2768 - 832 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 158400$, $T_{1936} := 2640^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 5533, 5535\}$
6. **(832, 10800, 10832)** $\Rightarrow 10832 - 832 = 100^2$, $S_{100 \times 100} := 1166400$, $T_{10000} := 10800^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 21661, 21663\}$
7. **(832, 43260, 43268)** $\Rightarrow 43268 - 832 = 206^2$, $S_{206 \times 206} := 9084600$, $T_{42436} := 43260^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 86533, 86535\}$
8. **(832, 173055, 173057)** $\Rightarrow 173057 - 832 = 415^2$, $S_{415 \times 415} := 72163935$, $T_{172225} := 173055^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 346111, 346113\}$ or $E := \{87777, 87778, \dots, 260000, 260001\}$

■ Number 833

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$833^2 + 840^2 := 1183^2$$

$$833^2 + 1056^2 := 1345^2$$

$$833^2 + 2856^2 := 2975^2$$

$$833^2 + 7056^2 := 7105^2$$

$$833^2 + 20400^2 := 20417^2$$

$$833^2 + 49560^2 := 49567^2$$

$$833^2 + 346944^2 := 346945^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(833, 7056, 7105)** $\Rightarrow 7105 - 7056 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 99127$, $T_{49} := 833^2$,
 $E := \{14113, 14115, \dots, 14207, 14209\}$ or $E := \{14137, 14138, \dots, 14184, 14185\}$
2. **(833, 1056, 1345)** $\Rightarrow 1345 - 1056 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 40817$, $T_{289} := 833^2$,
 $E := \{2113, 2115, \dots, 2687, 2689\}$ or $E := \{2257, 2258, \dots, 2544, 2545\}$

■ Number 834

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$834^2 + 1112^2 := 1390^2$$

$$834^2 + 19312^2 := 19330^2$$

$$834^2 + 57960^2 := 57966^2$$

$$834^2 + 173888^2 := 173890^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(834, 19312, 19330)** $\Rightarrow 19330 - 834 = 136^2$, $S_{136 \times 136} := 2742304$, $T_{18496} := 19312^2$,
 $E := \{1669, 1671, \dots, 38657, 38659\}$
2. **(834, 173888, 173890)** $\Rightarrow 173890 - 834 = 416^2$, $S_{416 \times 416} := 72685184$, $T_{173056} := 173888^2$,
 $E := \{1669, 1671, \dots, 347777, 347779\}$

■ Number 835

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$835^2 + 2004^2 := 2171^2$$

$$835^2 + 13932^2 := 13957^2$$

$$835^2 + 69720^2 := 69725^2$$

$$835^2 + 348612^2 := 348613^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(835, 13932, 13957)** $\Rightarrow 13957 - 13932 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 139445$, $T_{25} := 835^2$,
 $E := \{27865, 27867, \dots, 27911, 27913\}$ or $E := \{27877, 27878, \dots, 27900, 27901\}$

■ **Number 836**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$836^2 + 1323^2 := 1565^2$$

$$836^2 + 2223^2 := 2375^2$$

$$836^2 + 3927^2 := 4015^2$$

$$836^2 + 4560^2 := 4636^2$$

$$836^2 + 7920^2 := 7964^2$$

$$836^2 + 9177^2 := 9215^2$$

$$836^2 + 15873^2 := 15895^2$$

$$836^2 + 43677^2 := 43685^2$$

$$836^2 + 87360^2 := 87364^2$$

$$836^2 + 174723^2 := 174725^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(836, 1323, 1565)** $\Rightarrow 1565 - 836 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 64827$, $T_{729} := 1323^2$,
 $E := \{1673, 1675, \dots, 3127, 3129\}$ or $E := \{2037, 2038, \dots, 2764, 2765\}$
2. **(836, 43677, 43685)** $\Rightarrow 43685 - 836 = 207^2$, $S_{207 \times 207} := 9215847$, $T_{42849} := 43677^2$,
 $E := \{1673, 1675, \dots, 87367, 87369\}$ or $E := \{23097, 23098, \dots, 65944, 65945\}$
3. **(836, 174723, 174725)** $\Rightarrow 174725 - 836 = 417^2$, $S_{417 \times 417} := 73208937$, $T_{173889} := 174723^2$,
 $E := \{1673, 1675, \dots, 349447, 349449\}$ or $E := \{88617, 88618, \dots, 262504, 262505\}$

■ **Number 837**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$837^2 + 1116^2 := 1395^2$$

$$837^2 + 1320^2 := 1563^2$$

$$837^2 + 3720^2 := 3813^2$$

$$837^2 + 38916^2 := 38925^2$$

$$837^2 + 116760^2 := 116763^2$$

$$837^2 + 350284^2 := 350285^2$$

$$837^2 + 4284^2 := 4365^2$$

$$837^2 + 11284^2 := 11315^2$$

$$837^2 + 12960^2 := 12987^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(837, 38916, 38925)** $\Rightarrow 38925 - 38916 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 233523$, $T_9 := 837^2$,
 $E := \{77833, 77835, \dots, 77847, 77849\}$ or $E := \{77837, 77838, \dots, 77844, 77845\}$

2. **(837, 4284, 4365)** $\Rightarrow 4365 - 4284 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 77841$, $T_{81} := 837^2$,
 $E := \{8569, 8571, \dots, 8727, 8729\}$ or $E := \{8609, 8610, \dots, 8688, 8689\}$

■ Number 838

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$838^2 + 175560^2 := 175562^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

• **(838, 175560, 175562)** $\Rightarrow 175562 - 838 = 418^2$, $S_{418 \times 418} := 73735200$, $T_{174724} := 175560^2$,
 $E := \{1677, 1679, \dots, 351121, 351123\}$

■ Number 839

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$839^2 + 351960^2 := 351961^2$$

■ Number 840

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$840^2 + 882^2 := 1218^2$$

$$840^2 + 1026^2 := 1326^2$$

$$840^2 + 1053^2 := 1347^2$$

$$840^2 + 1081^2 := 1369^2$$

$$840^2 + 1120^2 := 1400^2$$

$$840^2 + 1274^2 := 1526^2$$

$$840^2 + 1350^2 := 1590^2$$

$$840^2 + 1463^2 := 1687^2$$

$$840^2 + 1575^2 := 1785^2$$

$$840^2 + 1664^2 := 1864^2$$

$$840^2 + 1702^2 := 1898^2$$

$$840^2 + 1870^2 := 2050^2$$

$$840^2 + 2016^2 := 2184^2$$

$$840^2 + 2125^2 := 2285^2$$

$$840^2 + 2277^2 := 2427^2$$

$$840^2 + 2378^2 := 2522^2$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 840^2 + 2450^2 := 2590^2 & \\
 840^2 + 2737^2 := 2863^2 & 840^2 + 8379^2 := 8421^2 \\
 840^2 + 2880^2 := 3000^2 & 840^2 + 8800^2 := 8840^2 \\
 840^2 + 3094^2 := 3206^2 & 840^2 + 9782^2 := 9818^2 \\
 840^2 + 3478^2 := 3578^2 & 840^2 + 11009^2 := 11041^2 \\
 840^2 + 3551^2 := 3649^2 & 840^2 + 11745^2 := 11775^2 \\
 840^2 + 3627^2 := 3723^2 & 840^2 + 12586^2 := 12614^2 \\
 840^2 + 3875^2 := 3965^2 & 840^2 + 14688^2 := 14712^2 \\
 840^2 + 4158^2 := 4242^2 & 840^2 + 17630^2 := 17650^2 \\
 840^2 + 4370^2 := 4450^2 & 840^2 + 19591^2 := 19609^2 \\
 840^2 + 4864^2 := 4936^2 & 840^2 + 22042^2 := 22058^2 \\
 840^2 + 5005^2 := 5075^2 & 840^2 + 25193^2 := 25207^2 \\
 840^2 + 5850^2 := 5910^2 & 840^2 + 29394^2 := 29406^2 \\
 840^2 + 6272^2 := 6328^2 & 840^2 + 35275^2 := 35285^2 \\
 840^2 + 7031^2 := 7081^2 & 840^2 + 44096^2 := 44104^2 \\
 840^2 + 7326^2 := 7374^2 & 840^2 + 58797^2 := 58803^2 \\
 & 840^2 + 88198^2 := 88202^2 \\
 & 840^2 + 176399^2 := 176401^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(840, 22042, 22058)** $\Rightarrow 22058 - 22042 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 176400$, $T_{16} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{44085, 44087, \dots, 44113, 44115\}$
2. **(840, 9782, 9818)** $\Rightarrow 9818 - 9782 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 117600$, $T_{36} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{19565, 19567, \dots, 19633, 19635\}$
3. **(840, 3478, 3578)** $\Rightarrow 3578 - 3478 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 70560$, $T_{100} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{6957, 6959, \dots, 7153, 7155\}$
4. **(840, 2378, 2522)** $\Rightarrow 2522 - 2378 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 58800$, $T_{144} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{4757, 4759, \dots, 5041, 5043\}$
5. **(840, 1702, 1898)** $\Rightarrow 1898 - 1702 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 50400$, $T_{196} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{3405, 3407, \dots, 3793, 3795\}$
6. **(840, 1081, 1369)** $\Rightarrow 1369 - 840 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 50807$, $T_{529} := 1081^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 2735, 2737\}$ or $E := \{1945, 1946, \dots, 2472, 2473\}$
7. **(840, 1664, 1864)** $\Rightarrow 1864 - 840 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 86528$, $T_{1024} := 1664^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 3725, 3727\}$
8. **(840, 3551, 3649)** $\Rightarrow 3649 - 840 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 237917$, $T_{2809} := 3551^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 7295, 7297\}$ or $E := \{3085, 3086, \dots, 5892, 5893\}$

9. **(840, 44096, 44104)** $\Rightarrow 44104 - 840 = 208^2$, $S_{208 \times 208} := 9348352$, $T_{43264} := 44096^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 88205, 88207\}$
10. **(840, 4864, 4936)** $\Rightarrow 4936 - 840 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 369664$, $T_{4096} := 4864^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 9869, 9871\}$
11. **(840, 7031, 7081)** $\Rightarrow 7081 - 840 = 79^2$, $S_{79 \times 79} := 625759$, $T_{6241} := 7031^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 14159, 14161\}$ or $E := \{4801, 4802, \dots, 11040, 11041\}$
12. **(840, 11009, 11041)** $\Rightarrow 11041 - 840 = 101^2$, $S_{101 \times 101} := 1199981$, $T_{10201} := 11009^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 22079, 22081\}$ or $E := \{6781, 6782, \dots, 16980, 16981\}$
13. **(840, 19591, 19609)** $\Rightarrow 19609 - 840 = 137^2$, $S_{137 \times 137} := 2801513$, $T_{18769} := 19591^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 39215, 39217\}$ or $E := \{11065, 11066, \dots, 29832, 29833\}$
14. **(840, 176399, 176401)** $\Rightarrow 176401 - 840 = 419^2$, $S_{419 \times 419} := 74263979$, $T_{175561} := 176399^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 352799, 352801\}$ or $E := \{89461, 89462, \dots, 265020, 265021\}$

■ Number 841

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$841^2 + 12180^2 := 12209^2$$

$$841^2 + 353640^2 := 353641^2$$

■ Number 842

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$842^2 + 177240^2 := 177242^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(842, 177240, 177242)** $\Rightarrow 177242 - 842 = 420^2$, $S_{420 \times 420} := 74795280$, $T_{176400} := 177240^2$,
 $E := \{1685, 1687, \dots, 354481, 354483\}$

■ Number 843

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$843^2 + 1124^2 := 1405^2$$

$$843^2 + 39476^2 := 39485^2$$

$$843^2 + 118440^2 := 118443^2$$

$$843^2 + 355324^2 := 355325^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(843, 39476, 39485)** $\Rightarrow 39485 - 39476 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 236883$, $T_9 := 843^2$,
 $E := \{78953, 78955, \dots, 78967, 78969\}$ or $E := \{78957, 78958, \dots, 78964, 78965\}$

■ Number 844

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$844^2 + 44517^2 := 44525^2$$

$$844^2 + 89040^2 := 89044^2$$

$$844^2 + 178083^2 := 178085^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(844, 44517, 44525)** $\Rightarrow 44525 - 844 = 209^2$, $S_{209 \times 209} := 9482121$, $T_{43681} := 44517^2$,
 $E := \{1689, 1691, \dots, 89047, 89049\}$ or $E := \{23529, 23530, \dots, 67208, 67209\}$
2. **(844, 178083, 178085)** $\Rightarrow 178085 - 844 = 421^2$, $S_{421 \times 421} := 75329109$, $T_{177241} := 178083^2$,
 $E := \{1689, 1691, \dots, 356167, 356169\}$ or $E := \{90309, 90310, \dots, 267548, 267549\}$

■ Number 845

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$845^2 + 936^2 := 1261^2$$

$$845^2 + 2028^2 := 2197^2$$

$$845^2 + 5460^2 := 5525^2$$

$$845^2 + 14268^2 := 14293^2$$

$$845^2 + 27456^2 := 27469^2$$

$$845^2 + 71400^2 := 71405^2$$

$$845^2 + 357012^2 := 357013^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(845, 14268, 14293)** $\Rightarrow 14293 - 14268 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 142805$, $T_{25} := 845^2$,
 $E := \{28537, 28539, \dots, 28583, 28585\}$ or $E := \{28549, 28550, \dots, 28572, 28573\}$
2. **(845, 2028, 2197)** $\Rightarrow 2197 - 2028 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 54925$, $T_{169} := 845^2$,
 $E := \{4057, 4059, \dots, 4391, 4393\}$ or $E := \{4141, 4142, \dots, 4308, 4309\}$

■ Number 846

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$846^2 + 1128^2 := 1410^2$$

$$846^2 + 2128^2 := 2290^2$$

$$846^2 + 3760^2 := 3854^2$$

$$846^2 + 6600^2 := 6654^2$$

$$846^2 + 19872^2 := 19890^2$$

$$846^2 + 59640^2 := 59646^2$$

$$846^2 + 178928^2 := 178930^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(846, 2128, 2290)** $\Rightarrow 2290 - 846 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 119168$, $T_{1444} := 2128^2$,
 $E := \{1693, 1695, \dots, 4577, 4579\}$

2. **(846, 19872, 19890)** $\Rightarrow 19890 - 846 = 138^2$, $S_{138 \times 138} := 2861568$, $T_{19044} := 19872^2$,
 $E := \{1693, 1695, \dots, 39777, 39779\}$

3. **(846, 178928, 178930)** $\Rightarrow 178930 - 846 = 422^2$, $S_{422 \times 422} := 75865472$, $T_{178084} := 178928^2$,
 $E := \{1693, 1695, \dots, 357857, 357859\}$

■ Number 847

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$847^2 + 2904^2 := 3025^2$$

$$847^2 + 4620^2 := 4697^2$$

$$847^2 + 7296^2 := 7345^2$$

$$847^2 + 32604^2 := 32615^2$$

$$847^2 + 51240^2 := 51247^2$$

$$847^2 + 358704^2 := 358705^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(847, 7296, 7345)** $\Rightarrow 7345 - 7296 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 102487$, $T_{49} := 847^2$,
 $E := \{14593, 14595, \dots, 14687, 14689\}$ or $E := \{14617, 14618, \dots, 14664, 14665\}$

2. **(847, 2904, 3025)** $\Rightarrow 3025 - 2904 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 65219$, $T_{121} := 847^2$,
 $E := \{5809, 5811, \dots, 6047, 6049\}$ or $E := \{5869, 5870, \dots, 5988, 5989\}$

■ Number 848

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$848^2 + 1590^2 := 1802^2$$

$$848^2 + 2745^2 := 2873^2$$

$$848^2 + 3339^2 := 3445^2$$

$$848^2 + 5586^2 := 5650^2$$

$$848^2 + 11220^2 := 11252^2$$

$$848^2 + 22464^2 := 22480^2$$

$$848^2 + 44940^2 := 44948^2$$

$$848^2 + 89886^2 := 89890^2$$

$$848^2 + 179775^2 := 179777^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(848, 22464, 22480)** $\Rightarrow 22480 - 22464 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 179776$, $T_{16} := 848^2$,
 $E := \{44929, 44931, \dots, 44957, 44959\}$
2. **(848, 5586, 5650)** $\Rightarrow 5650 - 5586 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 89888$, $T_{64} := 848^2$,
 $E := \{11173, 11175, \dots, 11297, 11299\}$
3. **(848, 2745, 2873)** $\Rightarrow 2873 - 848 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 167445$, $T_{2025} := 2745^2$,
 $E := \{1697, 1699, \dots, 5743, 5745\}$ or $E := \{2709, 2710, \dots, 4732, 4733\}$
4. **(848, 11220, 11252)** $\Rightarrow 11252 - 848 = 102^2$, $S_{102 \times 102} := 1234200$, $T_{10404} := 11220^2$,
 $E := \{1697, 1699, \dots, 22501, 22503\}$
5. **(848, 44940, 44948)** $\Rightarrow 44948 - 848 = 210^2$, $S_{210 \times 210} := 9617160$, $T_{44100} := 44940^2$,
 $E := \{1697, 1699, \dots, 89893, 89895\}$
6. **(848, 179775, 179777)** $\Rightarrow 179777 - 848 = 423^2$, $S_{423 \times 423} := 76404375$, $T_{178929} := 179775^2$,
 $E := \{1697, 1699, \dots, 359551, 359553\}$ or $E := \{91161, 91162, \dots, 270088, 270089\}$

■ Number 849

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$849^2 + 1132^2 := 1415^2$$

$$849^2 + 40040^2 := 40049^2$$

$$849^2 + 120132^2 := 120135^2$$

$$849^2 + 360400^2 := 360401^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(849, 40040, 40049)** $\Rightarrow 40049 - 40040 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 240267$, $T_9 := 849^2$,
 $E := \{80081, 80083, \dots, 80095, 80097\}$ or $E := \{80085, 80086, \dots, 80092, 80093\}$

■ Number 850

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$850^2 + 1320^2 := 1570^2$$

$$850^2 + 2040^2 := 2210^2$$

$$850^2 + 7200^2 := 7250^2$$

$$850^2 + 10608^2 := 10642^2$$

$$850^2 + 36120^2 := 36130^2$$

$$850^2 + 180624^2 := 180626^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(850, 7200, 7250)** $\Rightarrow 7250 - 850 = 80^2$, $S_{80 \times 80} := 648000$, $T_{6400} := 7200^2$,
 $E := \{1701, 1703, \dots, 14497, 14499\}$
2. **(850, 180624, 180626)** $\Rightarrow 180626 - 850 = 424^2$, $S_{424 \times 424} := 76945824$, $T_{179776} := 180624^2$,
 $E := \{1701, 1703, \dots, 361249, 361251\}$

■ Number 851

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$851^2 + 9768^2 := 9805^2$$

$$851^2 + 15732^2 := 15755^2$$

$$851^2 + 362100^2 := 362101^2$$

■ Number 852

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$852^2 + 1136^2 := 1420^2$	$852^2 + 15111^2 := 15135^2$	$852^2 + 60489^2 := 60495^2$
$852^2 + 2485^2 := 2627^2$	$852^2 + 20155^2 := 20173^2$	$852^2 + 90736^2 := 90740^2$
$852^2 + 5005^2 := 5077^2$	$852^2 + 30240^2 := 30252^2$	$852^2 + 181475^2 := 181477^2$
$852^2 + 10064^2 := 10100^2$	$852^2 + 45365^2 := 45373^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(852, 10064, 10100)** $\Rightarrow 10100 - 10064 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 120984$, $T_{36} := 852^2$,
 $E := \{20129, 20131, \dots, 20197, 20199\}$
2. **(852, 5005, 5077)** $\Rightarrow 5077 - 852 = 65^2$, $S_{65 \times 65} := 385385$, $T_{4225} := 5005^2$,
 $E := \{1705, 1707, \dots, 10151, 10153\}$ or $E := \{3817, 3818, \dots, 8040, 8041\}$
3. **(852, 20155, 20173)** $\Rightarrow 20173 - 852 = 139^2$, $S_{139 \times 139} := 2922475$, $T_{19321} := 20155^2$,
 $E := \{1705, 1707, \dots, 40343, 40345\}$ or $E := \{11365, 11366, \dots, 30684, 30685\}$
4. **(852, 45365, 45373)** $\Rightarrow 45373 - 852 = 211^2$, $S_{211 \times 211} := 9753475$, $T_{44521} := 45365^2$,
 $E := \{1705, 1707, \dots, 90743, 90745\}$ or $E := \{23965, 23966, \dots, 68484, 68485\}$

5. **(852, 181475, 181477)** $\Rightarrow 181477 - 852 = 425^2$, $S_{425 \times 425} := 77489825$, $T_{180625} := 181475^2$,
 $E := \{1705, 1707, \dots, 362951, 362953\}$ or $E := \{92017, 92018, \dots, 272640, 272641\}$

■ Number 853

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$853^2 + 363804^2 := 363805^2$$

■ Number 854

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$854^2 + 2928^2 := 3050^2$$

$$854^2 + 26040^2 := 26054^2$$

$$854^2 + 3672^2 := 3770^2$$

$$854^2 + 182328^2 := 182330^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(854, 3672, 3770)** $\Rightarrow 3770 - 854 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 249696$, $T_{2916} := 3672^2$,
 $E := \{1709, 1711, \dots, 7537, 7539\}$
2. **(854, 182328, 182330)** $\Rightarrow 182330 - 854 = 426^2$, $S_{426 \times 426} := 78036384$, $T_{181476} := 182328^2$,
 $E := \{1709, 1711, \dots, 364657, 364659\}$

■ Number 855

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$855^2 + 1140^2 := 1425^2$$

$$855^2 + 4836^2 := 4911^2$$

$$855^2 + 24360^2 := 24375^2$$

$$855^2 + 1512^2 := 1737^2$$

$$855^2 + 6384^2 := 6441^2$$

$$855^2 + 40608^2 := 40617^2$$

$$855^2 + 2052^2 := 2223^2$$

$$855^2 + 8100^2 := 8145^2$$

$$855^2 + 73100^2 := 73105^2$$

$$855^2 + 2640^2 := 2775^2$$

$$855^2 + 13524^2 := 13551^2$$

$$855^2 + 121836^2 := 121839^2$$

$$855^2 + 3800^2 := 3895^2$$

$$855^2 + 14608^2 := 14633^2$$

$$855^2 + 365512^2 := 365513^2$$

$$855^2 + 4472^2 := 4553^2$$

$$855^2 + 19228^2 := 19247^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(855, 40608, 40617)** $\Rightarrow 40617 - 40608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 243675$, $T_9 := 855^2$,
 $E := \{81217, 81219, \dots, 81231, 81233\}$ or $E := \{81221, 81222, \dots, 81228, 81229\}$
2. **(855, 14608, 14633)** $\Rightarrow 14633 - 14608 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 146205$, $T_{25} := 855^2$,
 $E := \{29217, 29219, \dots, 29263, 29265\}$ or $E := \{29229, 29230, \dots, 29252, 29253\}$
3. **(855, 4472, 4553)** $\Rightarrow 4553 - 4472 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 81225$, $T_{81} := 855^2$,
 $E := \{8945, 8947, \dots, 9103, 9105\}$ or $E := \{8985, 8986, \dots, 9064, 9065\}$
4. **(855, 1512, 1737)** $\Rightarrow 1737 - 1512 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 48735$, $T_{225} := 855^2$,
 $E := \{3025, 3027, \dots, 3471, 3473\}$ or $E := \{3137, 3138, \dots, 3360, 3361\}$

■ Number 856

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$856^2 + 1605^2 := 1819^2$$

$$856^2 + 22890^2 := 22906^2$$

$$856^2 + 91590^2 := 91594^2$$

$$856^2 + 11433^2 := 11465^2$$

$$856^2 + 45792^2 := 45800^2$$

$$856^2 + 183183^2 := 183185^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(856, 22890, 22906)** $\Rightarrow 22906 - 22890 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 183184$, $T_{16} := 856^2$,
 $E := \{45781, 45783, \dots, 45809, 45811\}$
2. **(856, 11433, 11465)** $\Rightarrow 11465 - 856 = 103^2$, $S_{103 \times 103} := 1269063$, $T_{10609} := 11433^2$,
 $E := \{1713, 1715, \dots, 22927, 22929\}$ or $E := \{7017, 7018, \dots, 17624, 17625\}$
3. **(856, 45792, 45800)** $\Rightarrow 45800 - 856 = 212^2$, $S_{212 \times 212} := 9891072$, $T_{44944} := 45792^2$,
 $E := \{1713, 1715, \dots, 91597, 91599\}$
4. **(856, 183183, 183185)** $\Rightarrow 183185 - 856 = 427^2$, $S_{427 \times 427} := 78585507$, $T_{182329} := 183183^2$,
 $E := \{1713, 1715, \dots, 366367, 366369\}$ or $E := \{92877, 92878, \dots, 275204, 275205\}$

■ Number 857

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$857^2 + 367224^2 := 367225^2$$

■ Number 858

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$858^2 + 920^2 := 1258^2$	$858^2 + 1760^2 := 1958^2$	$858^2 + 16720^2 := 16742^2$
$858^2 + 1144^2 := 1430^2$	$858^2 + 4680^2 := 4758^2$	$858^2 + 20440^2 := 20458^2$
$858^2 + 1400^2 := 1642^2$	$858^2 + 5544^2 := 5610^2$	$858^2 + 61344^2 := 61350^2$
$858^2 + 1456^2 := 1690^2$	$858^2 + 14144^2 := 14170^2$	$858^2 + 184040^2 := 184042^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(858, 920, 1258)** $\Rightarrow 1258 - 858 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 42320$, $T_{400} := 920^2$,
 $E := \{1717, 1719, \dots, 2513, 2515\}$
2. **(858, 1400, 1642)** $\Rightarrow 1642 - 858 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 70000$, $T_{784} := 1400^2$,
 $E := \{1717, 1719, \dots, 3281, 3283\}$
3. **(858, 20440, 20458)** $\Rightarrow 20458 - 858 = 140^2$, $S_{140 \times 140} := 2984240$, $T_{19600} := 20440^2$,
 $E := \{1717, 1719, \dots, 40913, 40915\}$
4. **(858, 184040, 184042)** $\Rightarrow 184042 - 858 = 428^2$, $S_{428 \times 428} := 79137200$, $T_{183184} := 184040^2$,
 $E := \{1717, 1719, \dots, 368081, 368083\}$

■ Number 859

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$859^2 + 368940^2 := 368941^2$$

■ Number 860

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$860^2 + 903^2 := 1247^2$	$860^2 + 4257^2 := 4343^2$	$860^2 + 36975^2 := 36985^2$
$860^2 + 1749^2 := 1949^2$	$860^2 + 7371^2 := 7421^2$	$860^2 + 46221^2 := 46229^2$
$860^2 + 2064^2 := 2236^2$	$860^2 + 9225^2 := 9265^2$	$860^2 + 92448^2 := 92452^2$
$860^2 + 3648^2 := 3748^2$	$860^2 + 18480^2 := 18500^2$	$860^2 + 184899^2 := 184901^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(860, 3648, 3748)** $\Rightarrow 3748 - 3648 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 73960$, $T_{100} := 860^2$,
 $E := \{7297, 7299, \dots, 7493, 7495\}$
2. **(860, 1749, 1949)** $\Rightarrow 1949 - 860 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 92697$, $T_{1089} := 1749^2$,
 $E := \{1721, 1723, \dots, 3895, 3897\}$ or $E := \{2265, 2266, \dots, 3352, 3353\}$

3. **(860, 7371, 7421)** $\Rightarrow 7421 - 860 = 81^2$, $S_{81 \times 81} := 670761$, $T_{6561} := 7371^2$,
 $E := \{1721, 1723, \dots, 14839, 14841\}$ or $E := \{5001, 5002, \dots, 11560, 11561\}$
4. **(860, 46221, 46229)** $\Rightarrow 46229 - 860 = 213^2$, $S_{213 \times 213} := 10029957$, $T_{45369} := 46221^2$,
 $E := \{1721, 1723, \dots, 92455, 92457\}$ or $E := \{24405, 24406, \dots, 69772, 69773\}$
5. **(860, 184899, 184901)** $\Rightarrow 184901 - 860 = 429^2$, $S_{429 \times 429} := 79691469$, $T_{184041} := 184899^2$,
 $E := \{1721, 1723, \dots, 369799, 369801\}$ or $E := \{93741, 93742, \dots, 277780, 277781\}$

■ Number 861

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$861^2 + 1148^2 := 1435^2$$

$$861^2 + 2448^2 := 2595^2$$

$$861^2 + 2952^2 := 3075^2$$

$$861^2 + 5852^2 := 5915^2$$

$$861^2 + 7540^2 := 7589^2$$

$$861^2 + 9020^2 := 9061^2$$

$$861^2 + 17640^2 := 17661^2$$

$$861^2 + 41180^2 := 41189^2$$

$$861^2 + 52948^2 := 52955^2$$

$$861^2 + 123552^2 := 123555^2$$

$$861^2 + 370660^2 := 370661^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(861, 41180, 41189)** $\Rightarrow 41189 - 41180 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 247107$, $T_9 := 861^2$,
 $E := \{82361, 82363, \dots, 82375, 82377\}$ or $E := \{82365, 82366, \dots, 82372, 82373\}$
2. **(861, 7540, 7589)** $\Rightarrow 7589 - 7540 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 105903$, $T_{49} := 861^2$,
 $E := \{15081, 15083, \dots, 15175, 15177\}$ or $E := \{15105, 15106, \dots, 15152, 15153\}$

■ Number 862

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$862^2 + 185760^2 := 185762^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(862, 185760, 185762)** $\Rightarrow 185762 - 862 = 430^2$, $S_{430 \times 430} := 80248320$, $T_{184900} := 185760^2$,
 $E := \{1725, 1727, \dots, 371521, 371523\}$

■ Number 863

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$863^2 + 372384^2 := 372385^2$$

■ Number 864

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$864^2 + 990^2 := 1314^2$$

$$864^2 + 1152^2 := 1440^2$$

$$864^2 + 1330^2 := 1586^2$$

$$864^2 + 1620^2 := 1836^2$$

$$864^2 + 1848^2 := 2040^2$$

$$864^2 + 2223^2 := 2385^2$$

$$864^2 + 2520^2 := 2664^2$$

$$864^2 + 2852^2 := 2980^2$$

$$864^2 + 3402^2 := 3510^2$$

$$864^2 + 3840^2 := 3936^2$$

$$864^2 + 5148^2 := 5220^2$$

$$864^2 + 5800^2 := 5864^2$$

$$864^2 + 6885^2 := 6939^2$$

$$864^2 + 7752^2 := 7800^2$$

$$864^2 + 10350^2 := 10386^2$$

$$864^2 + 11648^2 := 11680^2$$

$$864^2 + 15540^2 := 15564^2$$

$$864^2 + 20727^2 := 20745^2$$

$$864^2 + 23320^2 := 23336^2$$

$$864^2 + 31098^2 := 31110^2$$

$$864^2 + 46652^2 := 46660^2$$

$$864^2 + 62205^2 := 62211^2$$

$$864^2 + 93310^2 := 93314^2$$

$$864^2 + 186623^2 := 186625^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(864, 23320, 23336)** $\Rightarrow 23336 - 23320 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 186624$, $T_{16} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{46641, 46643, \dots, 46669, 46671\}$
2. **(864, 10350, 10386)** $\Rightarrow 10386 - 10350 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 124416$, $T_{36} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{20701, 20703, \dots, 20769, 20771\}$
3. **(864, 5800, 5864)** $\Rightarrow 5864 - 5800 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 93312$, $T_{64} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{11601, 11603, \dots, 11725, 11727\}$
4. **(864, 2520, 2664)** $\Rightarrow 2664 - 2520 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 62208$, $T_{144} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{5041, 5043, \dots, 5325, 5327\}$
5. **(864, 1330, 1586)** $\Rightarrow 1586 - 1330 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 46656$, $T_{256} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{2661, 2663, \dots, 3169, 3171\}$
6. **(864, 990, 1314)** $\Rightarrow 1314 - 990 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 41472$, $T_{324} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 2625, 2627\}$
7. **(864, 1152, 1440)** $\Rightarrow 1440 - 864 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 55296$, $T_{576} := 1152^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 2877, 2879\}$
8. **(864, 2223, 2385)** $\Rightarrow 2385 - 864 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 126711$, $T_{1521} := 2223^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 4767, 4769\}$ or $E := \{2489, 2490, \dots, 4008, 4009\}$
9. **(864, 2852, 2980)** $\Rightarrow 2980 - 864 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 176824$, $T_{2116} := 2852^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 5957, 5959\}$
10. **(864, 5148, 5220)** $\Rightarrow 5220 - 864 = 66^2$, $S_{66 \times 66} := 401544$, $T_{4356} := 5148^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 10437, 10439\}$

11. **(864, 11648, 11680)** $\Rightarrow 11680 - 864 = 104^2$, $S_{104 \times 104} := 1304576$, $T_{10816} := 11648^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 23357, 23359\}$
12. **(864, 20727, 20745)** $\Rightarrow 20745 - 864 = 141^2$, $S_{141 \times 141} := 3046869$, $T_{19881} := 20727^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 41487, 41489\}$ or $E := \{11669, 11670, \dots, 31548, 31549\}$
13. **(864, 46652, 46660)** $\Rightarrow 46660 - 864 = 214^2$, $S_{214 \times 214} := 10170136$, $T_{45796} := 46652^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 93317, 93319\}$
14. **(864, 186623, 186625)** $\Rightarrow 186625 - 864 = 431^2$, $S_{431 \times 431} := 80807759$, $T_{185761} := 186623^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 373247, 373249\}$ or $E := \{94609, 94610, \dots, 280368, 280369\}$

■ Number 865

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$865^2 + 2076^2 := 2249^2$$

$$865^2 + 14952^2 := 14977^2$$

$$865^2 + 74820^2 := 74825^2$$

$$865^2 + 374112^2 := 374113^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(865, 14952, 14977)** $\Rightarrow 14977 - 14952 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 149645$, $T_{25} := 865^2$,
 $E := \{29905, 29907, \dots, 29951, 29953\}$ or $E := \{29917, 29918, \dots, 29940, 29941\}$

■ Number 866

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$866^2 + 187488^2 := 187490^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(866, 187488, 187490)** $\Rightarrow 187490 - 866 = 432^2$, $S_{432 \times 432} := 81369792$, $T_{186624} := 187488^2$,
 $E := \{1733, 1735, \dots, 374977, 374979\}$

■ Number 867

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$867^2 + 1156^2 := 1445^2$$

$$867^2 + 2380^2 := 2533^2$$

$$867^2 + 7344^2 := 7395^2$$

$$867^2 + 22100^2 := 22117^2$$

$$867^2 + 41756^2 := 41765^2$$

$$867^2 + 125280^2 := 125283^2$$

$$867^2 + 375844^2 := 375845^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(867, 41756, 41765)** $\Rightarrow 41765 - 41756 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 250563$, $T_9 := 867^2$,
 $E := \{83513, 83515, \dots, 83527, 83529\}$ or $E := \{83517, 83518, \dots, 83524, 83525\}$
2. **(867, 1156, 1445)** $\Rightarrow 1445 - 1156 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 44217$, $T_{289} := 867^2$,
 $E := \{2313, 2315, \dots, 2887, 2889\}$ or $E := \{2457, 2458, \dots, 2744, 2745\}$

■ Number 868

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$868^2 + 1395^2 := 1643^2$	$868^2 + 6045^2 := 6107^2$	$868^2 + 47085^2 := 47093^2$
$868^2 + 1824^2 := 2020^2$	$868^2 + 6699^2 := 6755^2$	$868^2 + 94176^2 := 94180^2$
$868^2 + 2976^2 := 3100^2$	$868^2 + 13440^2 := 13468^2$	$868^2 + 188355^2 := 188357^2$
$868^2 + 3795^2 := 3893^2$	$868^2 + 26901^2 := 26915^2$	

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(868, 1824, 2020)** $\Rightarrow 2020 - 1824 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 53816$, $T_{196} := 868^2$,
 $E := \{3649, 3651, \dots, 4037, 4039\}$
2. **(868, 3795, 3893)** $\Rightarrow 3893 - 868 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 261855$, $T_{3025} := 3795^2$,
 $E := \{1737, 1739, \dots, 7783, 7785\}$ or $E := \{3249, 3250, \dots, 6272, 6273\}$
3. **(868, 47085, 47093)** $\Rightarrow 47093 - 868 = 215^2$, $S_{215 \times 215} := 10311615$, $T_{46225} := 47085^2$,
 $E := \{1737, 1739, \dots, 94183, 94185\}$ or $E := \{24849, 24850, \dots, 71072, 71073\}$
4. **(868, 188355, 188357)** $\Rightarrow 188357 - 868 = 433^2$, $S_{433 \times 433} := 81934425$, $T_{187489} := 188355^2$,
 $E := \{1737, 1739, \dots, 376711, 376713\}$ or $E := \{95481, 95482, \dots, 282968, 282969\}$

■ Number 869

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$869^2 + 3060^2 := 3181^2$$

$$869^2 + 4740^2 := 4819^2$$

$$869^2 + 34320^2 := 34331^2$$

$$869^2 + 377580^2 := 377581^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(869, 3060, 3181)** $\Rightarrow 3181 - 3060 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 68651$, $T_{121} := 869^2$,
 $E := \{6121, 6123, \dots, 6359, 6361\}$ or $E := \{6181, 6182, \dots, 6300, 6301\}$

■ Number 870

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$870^2 + 1160^2 := 1450^2$$

$$870^2 + 2088^2 := 2262^2$$

$$870^2 + 2448^2 := 2598^2$$

$$870^2 + 4160^2 := 4250^2$$

$$870^2 + 6496^2 := 6554^2$$

$$870^2 + 7544^2 := 7594^2$$

$$870^2 + 12600^2 := 12630^2$$

$$870^2 + 21016^2 := 21034^2$$

$$870^2 + 37840^2 := 37850^2$$

$$870^2 + 63072^2 := 63078^2$$

$$870^2 + 189224^2 := 189226^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(870, 7544, 7594)** $\Rightarrow 7594 - 870 = 82^2$, $S_{82 \times 82} := 694048$, $T_{6724} := 7544^2$,
 $E := \{1741, 1743, \dots, 15185, 15187\}$
2. **(870, 21016, 21034)** $\Rightarrow 21034 - 870 = 142^2$, $S_{142 \times 142} := 3110368$, $T_{20164} := 21016^2$,
 $E := \{1741, 1743, \dots, 42065, 42067\}$
3. **(870, 189224, 189226)** $\Rightarrow 189226 - 870 = 434^2$, $S_{434 \times 434} := 82501664$, $T_{188356} := 189224^2$,
 $E := \{1741, 1743, \dots, 378449, 378451\}$

■ Number 871

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$871^2 + 2160^2 := 2329^2$$

$$871^2 + 5628^2 := 5695^2$$

$$871^2 + 29172^2 := 29185^2$$

$$871^2 + 379320^2 := 379321^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(871, 2160, 2329)** $\Rightarrow 2329 - 2160 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 58357$, $T_{169} := 871^2$,
 $E := \{4321, 4323, \dots, 4655, 4657\}$ or $E := \{4405, 4406, \dots, 4572, 4573\}$

■ Number 872

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$872^2 + 1635^2 := 1853^2$$

$$872^2 + 11865^2 := 11897^2$$

$$872^2 + 23754^2 := 23770^2$$

$$872^2 + 47520^2 := 47528^2$$

$$872^2 + 95046^2 := 95050^2$$

$$872^2 + 190095^2 := 190097^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(872, 23754, 23770)** $\Rightarrow 23770 - 23754 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 190096$, $T_{16} := 872^2$,
 $E := \{47509, 47511, \dots, 47537, 47539\}$
2. **(872, 11865, 11897)** $\Rightarrow 11897 - 872 = 105^2$, $S_{105 \times 105} := 1340745$, $T_{11025} := 11865^2$,
 $E := \{1745, 1747, \dots, 23791, 23793\}$ or $E := \{7257, 7258, \dots, 18280, 18281\}$
3. **(872, 47520, 47528)** $\Rightarrow 47528 - 872 = 216^2$, $S_{216 \times 216} := 10454400$, $T_{46656} := 47520^2$,
 $E := \{1745, 1747, \dots, 95053, 95055\}$
4. **(872, 190095, 190097)** $\Rightarrow 190097 - 872 = 435^2$, $S_{435 \times 435} := 83071515$, $T_{189225} := 190095^2$,
 $E := \{1745, 1747, \dots, 380191, 380193\}$ or $E := \{96357, 96358, \dots, 285580, 285581\}$

■ Number 873

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$873^2 + 1164^2 := 1455^2$$

$$873^2 + 3880^2 := 3977^2$$

$$873^2 + 4664^2 := 4745^2$$

$$873^2 + 14100^2 := 14127^2$$

$$873^2 + 42336^2 := 42345^2$$

$$873^2 + 127020^2 := 127023^2$$

$$873^2 + 381064^2 := 381065^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(873, 42336, 42345)** $\Rightarrow 42345 - 42336 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 254043$, $T_9 := 873^2$,
 $E := \{84673, 84675, \dots, 84687, 84689\}$ or $E := \{84677, 84678, \dots, 84684, 84685\}$
2. **(873, 4664, 4745)** $\Rightarrow 4745 - 4664 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 84681$, $T_{81} := 873^2$,
 $E := \{9329, 9331, \dots, 9487, 9489\}$ or $E := \{9369, 9370, \dots, 9448, 9449\}$

■ Number 874

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned} 874^2 + 8280^2 &:= 8326^2 \\ 874^2 + 10032^2 &:= 10070^2 \\ 874^2 + 190968^2 &:= 190970^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(874, 190968, 190970)** $\Rightarrow 190970 - 874 = 436^2$, $S_{436 \times 436} := 83643984$, $T_{19096} := 190968^2$,
 $E := \{1749, 1751, \dots, 381937, 381939\}$

■ Number 875

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{lll} 875^2 + 1440^2 := 1685^2 & 875^2 + 7788^2 := 7837^2 & 875^2 + 54684^2 := 54691^2 \\ 875^2 + 2100^2 := 2275^2 & 875^2 + 10920^2 := 10955^2 & 875^2 + 76560^2 := 76565^2 \\ 875^2 + 3000^2 := 3125^2 & 875^2 + 15300^2 := 15325^2 & 875^2 + 382812^2 := 382813^2 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- (875, 15300, 15325)** $\Rightarrow 15325 - 15300 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 153125$, $T_{25} := 875^2$,
 $E := \{30601, 30603, \dots, 30647, 30649\}$ or $E := \{30613, 30614, \dots, 30636, 30637\}$
- (875, 7788, 7837)** $\Rightarrow 7837 - 7788 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 109375$, $T_{49} := 875^2$,
 $E := \{15577, 15579, \dots, 15671, 15673\}$ or $E := \{15601, 15602, \dots, 15648, 15649\}$

■ Number 876

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{lll} 876^2 + 1168^2 := 1460^2 & 876^2 + 15975^2 := 15999^2 & 876^2 + 63945^2 := 63951^2 \\ 876^2 + 2555^2 := 2701^2 & 876^2 + 21307^2 := 21325^2 & 876^2 + 95920^2 := 95924^2 \\ 876^2 + 5293^2 := 5365^2 & 876^2 + 31968^2 := 31980^2 & 876^2 + 191843^2 := 191845^2 \\ 876^2 + 10640^2 := 10676^2 & 876^2 + 47957^2 := 47965^2 & \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- (876, 10640, 10676)** $\Rightarrow 10676 - 10640 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 127896$, $T_{36} := 876^2$,
 $E := \{21281, 21283, \dots, 21349, 21351\}$
- (876, 5293, 5365)** $\Rightarrow 5365 - 876 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 418147$, $T_{4489} := 5293^2$,
 $E := \{1753, 1755, \dots, 10727, 10729\}$ or $E := \{3997, 3998, \dots, 8484, 8485\}$

3. **(876, 21307, 21325)** $\Rightarrow 21325 - 876 = 143^2$, $S_{143 \times 143} := 3174743$, $T_{20449} := 21307^2$,
 $E := \{1753, 1755, \dots, 42647, 42649\}$ or $E := \{11977, 11978, \dots, 32424, 32425\}$
4. **(876, 47957, 47965)** $\Rightarrow 47965 - 876 = 217^2$, $S_{217 \times 217} := 10598497$, $T_{47089} := 47957^2$,
 $E := \{1753, 1755, \dots, 95927, 95929\}$ or $E := \{25297, 25298, \dots, 72384, 72385\}$
5. **(876, 191843, 191845)** $\Rightarrow 191845 - 876 = 437^2$, $S_{437 \times 437} := 84219077$, $T_{190969} := 191843^2$,
 $E := \{1753, 1755, \dots, 383687, 383689\}$ or $E := \{97237, 97238, \dots, 288204, 288205\}$

■ Number 877

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$877^2 + 384564^2 := 384565^2$$

■ Number 878

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$878^2 + 192720^2 := 192722^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(878, 192720, 192722)** $\Rightarrow 192722 - 878 = 438^2$, $S_{438 \times 438} := 84796800$, $T_{191844} := 192720^2$,
 $E := \{1757, 1759, \dots, 385441, 385443\}$

■ Number 879

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$879^2 + 1172^2 := 1465^2$$

$$879^2 + 42920^2 := 42929^2$$

$$879^2 + 128772^2 := 128775^2$$

$$879^2 + 386320^2 := 386321^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(879, 42920, 42929)** $\Rightarrow 42929 - 42920 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 257547$, $T_9 := 879^2$,
 $E := \{85841, 85843, \dots, 85855, 85857\}$ or $E := \{85845, 85846, \dots, 85852, 85853\}$

■ Number 880

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$880^2 + 924^2 := 1276^2$	$880^2 + 3465^2 := 3575^2$	$880^2 + 12084^2 := 12116^2$
$880^2 + 1050^2 := 1370^2$	$880^2 + 3822^2 := 3922^2$	$880^2 + 17589^2 := 17611^2$
$880^2 + 1479^2 := 1721^2$	$880^2 + 4356^2 := 4444^2$	$880^2 + 19350^2 := 19370^2$
$880^2 + 1650^2 := 1870^2$	$880^2 + 4800^2 := 4880^2$	$880^2 + 24192^2 := 24208^2$
$880^2 + 1836^2 := 2036^2$	$880^2 + 6018^2 := 6082^2$	$880^2 + 38715^2 := 38725^2$
$880^2 + 2112^2 := 2288^2$	$880^2 + 7719^2 := 7769^2$	$880^2 + 48396^2 := 48404^2$
$880^2 + 2340^2 := 2500^2$	$880^2 + 8778^2 := 8822^2$	$880^2 + 96798^2 := 96802^2$
$880^2 + 2961^2 := 3089^2$	$880^2 + 9660^2 := 9700^2$	$880^2 + 193599^2 := 193601^2$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(880, 24192, 24208)** $\Rightarrow 24208 - 24192 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 193600$, $T_{16} := 880^2$,
 $E := \{48385, 48387, \dots, 48413, 48415\}$
2. **(880, 6018, 6082)** $\Rightarrow 6082 - 6018 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 96800$, $T_{64} := 880^2$,
 $E := \{12037, 12039, \dots, 12161, 12163\}$
3. **(880, 3822, 3922)** $\Rightarrow 3922 - 3822 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 77440$, $T_{100} := 880^2$,
 $E := \{7645, 7647, \dots, 7841, 7843\}$
4. **(880, 1479, 1721)** $\Rightarrow 1721 - 880 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 75429$, $T_{841} := 1479^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 3439, 3441\}$ or $E := \{2181, 2182, \dots, 3020, 3021\}$
5. **(880, 1836, 2036)** $\Rightarrow 2036 - 880 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 99144$, $T_{1156} := 1836^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 4069, 4071\}$
6. **(880, 2961, 3089)** $\Rightarrow 3089 - 880 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 186543$, $T_{2209} := 2961^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 6175, 6177\}$ or $E := \{2865, 2866, \dots, 5072, 5073\}$
7. **(880, 7719, 7769)** $\Rightarrow 7769 - 880 = 83^2$, $S_{83 \times 83} := 717867$, $T_{6889} := 7719^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 15535, 15537\}$ or $E := \{5205, 5206, \dots, 12092, 12093\}$
8. **(880, 12084, 12116)** $\Rightarrow 12116 - 880 = 106^2$, $S_{106 \times 106} := 1377576$, $T_{11236} := 12084^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 24229, 24231\}$
9. **(880, 48396, 48404)** $\Rightarrow 48404 - 880 = 218^2$, $S_{218 \times 218} := 10743912$, $T_{47524} := 48396^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 96805, 96807\}$
10. **(880, 193599, 193601)** $\Rightarrow 193601 - 880 = 439^2$, $S_{439 \times 439} := 85377159$, $T_{192721} := 193599^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 387199, 387201\}$ or $E := \{98121, 98122, \dots, 290840, 290841\}$

■ Number 881

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$881^2 + 388080^2 := 388081^2$$

■ Number 882

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$882^2 + 1176^2 := 1470^2$$

$$882^2 + 2320^2 := 2482^2$$

$$882^2 + 3024^2 := 3150^2$$

$$882^2 + 3920^2 := 4018^2$$

$$882^2 + 7176^2 := 7230^2$$

$$882^2 + 9240^2 := 9282^2$$

$$882^2 + 21600^2 := 21618^2$$

$$882^2 + 27776^2 := 27790^2$$

$$882^2 + 64824^2 := 64830^2$$

$$882^2 + 194480^2 := 194482^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

$$1. \text{ (882, 2320, 2482)} \Rightarrow 2482 - 882 = 40^2, S_{40 \times 40} := 134560, T_{1600} := 2320^2, \\ E := \{1765, 1767, \dots, 4961, 4963\}$$

$$2. \text{ (882, 3920, 4018)} \Rightarrow 4018 - 882 = 56^2, S_{56 \times 56} := 274400, T_{3136} := 3920^2, \\ E := \{1765, 1767, \dots, 8033, 8035\}$$

$$3. \text{ (882, 21600, 21618)} \Rightarrow 21618 - 882 = 144^2, S_{144 \times 144} := 3240000, T_{20736} := 21600^2, \\ E := \{1765, 1767, \dots, 43233, 43235\}$$

$$4. \text{ (882, 194480, 194482)} \Rightarrow 194482 - 882 = 440^2, S_{440 \times 440} := 85960160, T_{193600} := 194480^2, \\ E := \{1765, 1767, \dots, 388961, 388963\}$$

■ Number 883

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$883^2 + 389844^2 := 389845^2$$

■ Number 884

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$884^2 + 987^2 := 1325^2$$

$$884^2 + 2805^2 := 2941^2$$

$$884^2 + 3705^2 := 3809^2$$

$$884^2 + 5712^2 := 5780^2$$

$$884^2 + 7488^2 := 7540^2$$

$$884^2 + 11475^2 := 11509^2$$

$$884^2 + 15015^2 := 15041^2$$

$$884^2 + 48837^2 := 48845^2$$

$$884^2 + 97680^2 := 97684^2$$

$$884^2 + 195363^2 := 195365^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(884, 987, 1325)** $\Rightarrow 1325 - 884 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 46389$, $T_{441} := 987^2$,
 $E := \{1769, 1771, \dots, 2647, 2649\}$ or $E := \{1989, 1990, \dots, 2428, 2429\}$
2. **(884, 48837, 48845)** $\Rightarrow 48845 - 884 = 219^2$, $S_{219 \times 219} := 10890651$, $T_{47961} := 48837^2$,
 $E := \{1769, 1771, \dots, 97687, 97689\}$ or $E := \{25749, 25750, \dots, 73708, 73709\}$
3. **(884, 195363, 195365)** $\Rightarrow 195365 - 884 = 441^2$, $S_{441 \times 441} := 86545809$, $T_{194481} := 195363^2$,
 $E := \{1769, 1771, \dots, 390727, 390729\}$ or $E := \{99009, 99010, \dots, 293488, 293489\}$

■ Number 885

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$885^2 + 1180^2 := 1475^2$	$885^2 + 6608^2 := 6667^2$	$885^2 + 43508^2 := 43517^2$
$885^2 + 1628^2 := 1853^2$	$885^2 + 8680^2 := 8725^2$	$885^2 + 78320^2 := 78325^2$
$885^2 + 2124^2 := 2301^2$	$885^2 + 15652^2 := 15677^2$	$885^2 + 130536^2 := 130539^2$
$885^2 + 5184^2 := 5259^2$	$885^2 + 26100^2 := 26115^2$	$885^2 + 391612^2 := 391613^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(885, 43508, 43517)** $\Rightarrow 43517 - 43508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 261075$, $T_9 := 885^2$,
 $E := \{87017, 87019, \dots, 87031, 87033\}$ or $E := \{87021, 87022, \dots, 87028, 87029\}$
2. **(885, 15652, 15677)** $\Rightarrow 15677 - 15652 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 156645$, $T_{25} := 885^2$,
 $E := \{31305, 31307, \dots, 31351, 31353\}$ or $E := \{31317, 31318, \dots, 31340, 31341\}$
3. **(885, 1628, 1853)** $\Rightarrow 1853 - 1628 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 52215$, $T_{225} := 885^2$,
 $E := \{3257, 3259, \dots, 3703, 3705\}$ or $E := \{3369, 3370, \dots, 3592, 3593\}$

■ Number 886

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$886^2 + 196248^2 := 196250^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(886, 196248, 196250)** $\Rightarrow 196250 - 886 = 442^2$, $S_{442 \times 442} := 87134112$, $T_{195364} := 196248^2$,
 $E := \{1773, 1775, \dots, 392497, 392499\}$

■ Number 887

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$887^2 + 393384^2 := 393385^2$$

■ Number 888

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$888^2 + 1184^2 := 1480^2$$

$$888^2 + 1225^2 := 1513^2$$

$$888^2 + 1665^2 := 1887^2$$

$$888^2 + 2590^2 := 2738^2$$

$$888^2 + 2666^2 := 2810^2$$

$$888^2 + 4059^2 := 4155^2$$

$$888^2 + 5291^2 := 5365^2$$

$$888^2 + 5440^2 := 5512^2$$

$$888^2 + 8190^2 := 8238^2$$

$$888^2 + 10934^2 := 10970^2$$

$$888^2 + 12305^2 := 12337^2$$

$$888^2 + 16416^2 := 16440^2$$

$$888^2 + 21895^2 := 21913^2$$

$$888^2 + 24634^2 := 24650^2$$

$$888^2 + 32850^2 := 32862^2$$

$$888^2 + 49280^2 := 49288^2$$

$$888^2 + 65709^2 := 65715^2$$

$$888^2 + 98566^2 := 98570^2$$

$$888^2 + 197135^2 := 197137^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(888, 24634, 24650)** $\Rightarrow 24650 - 24634 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 197136$, $T_{16} := 888^2$,
 $E := \{49269, 49271, \dots, 49297, 49299\}$
2. **(888, 10934, 10970)** $\Rightarrow 10970 - 10934 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 131424$, $T_{36} := 888^2$,
 $E := \{21869, 21871, \dots, 21937, 21939\}$
3. **(888, 2666, 2810)** $\Rightarrow 2810 - 2666 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 65712$, $T_{144} := 888^2$,
 $E := \{5333, 5335, \dots, 5617, 5619\}$
4. **(888, 1225, 1513)** $\Rightarrow 1513 - 888 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 60025$, $T_{625} := 1225^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 3023, 3025\}$ or $E := \{2089, 2090, \dots, 2712, 2713\}$
5. **(888, 5440, 5512)** $\Rightarrow 5512 - 888 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 435200$, $T_{4624} := 5440^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 11021, 11023\}$
6. **(888, 12305, 12337)** $\Rightarrow 12337 - 888 = 107^2$, $S_{107 \times 107} := 1415075$, $T_{11449} := 12305^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 24671, 24673\}$ or $E := \{7501, 7502, \dots, 18948, 18949\}$
7. **(888, 21895, 21913)** $\Rightarrow 21913 - 888 = 145^2$, $S_{145 \times 145} := 3306145$, $T_{21025} := 21895^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 43823, 43825\}$ or $E := \{12289, 12290, \dots, 33312, 33313\}$
8. **(888, 49280, 49288)** $\Rightarrow 49288 - 888 = 220^2$, $S_{220 \times 220} := 11038720$, $T_{48400} := 49280^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 98573, 98575\}$
9. **(888, 197135, 197137)** $\Rightarrow 197137 - 888 = 443^2$, $S_{443 \times 443} := 87725075$, $T_{196249} := 197135^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 394271, 394273\}$ or $E := \{99901, 99902, \dots, 296148, 296149\}$

■ Number 889

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$889^2 + 3048^2 := 3175^2$$

$$889^2 + 8040^2 := 8089^2$$

$$889^2 + 56448^2 := 56455^2$$

$$889^2 + 395160^2 := 395161^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(889, 8040, 8089)** $\Rightarrow 8089 - 8040 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 112903$, $T_{49} := 889^2$,
 $E := \{16081, 16083, \dots, 16175, 16177\}$ or $E := \{16105, 16106, \dots, 16152, 16153\}$

■ Number 890

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$890^2 + 2136^2 := 2314^2$$

$$890^2 + 7896^2 := 7946^2$$

$$890^2 + 39600^2 := 39610^2$$

$$890^2 + 198024^2 := 198026^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- (890, 7896, 7946)** $\Rightarrow 7946 - 890 = 84^2$, $S_{84 \times 84} := 742224$, $T_{7056} := 7896^2$,
 $E := \{1781, 1783, \dots, 15889, 15891\}$
- (890, 198024, 198026)** $\Rightarrow 198026 - 890 = 444^2$, $S_{444 \times 444} := 88318704$, $T_{197136} := 198024^2$,
 $E := \{1781, 1783, \dots, 396049, 396051\}$

■ Number 891

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$891^2 + 912^2 := 1275^2$$

$$891^2 + 1188^2 := 1485^2$$

$$891^2 + 1512^2 := 1755^2$$

$$891^2 + 3220^2 := 3341^2$$

$$891^2 + 3960^2 := 4059^2$$

$$891^2 + 4860^2 := 4941^2$$

$$891^2 + 12012^2 := 12045^2$$

$$891^2 + 14688^2 := 14715^2$$

$$891^2 + 36080^2 := 36091^2$$

$$891^2 + 44100^2 := 44109^2$$

$$891^2 + 132312^2 := 132315^2$$

$$891^2 + 396940^2 := 396941^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- (891, 44100, 44109)** $\Rightarrow 44109 - 44100 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 264627$, $T_9 := 891^2$,
 $E := \{88201, 88203, \dots, 88215, 88217\}$ or $E := \{88205, 88206, \dots, 88212, 88213\}$

2. **(891, 4860, 4941)** $\Rightarrow 4941 - 4860 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 88209$, $T_{81} := 891^2$,
 $E := \{9721, 9723, \dots, 9879, 9881\}$ or $E := \{9761, 9762, \dots, 9840, 9841\}$
3. **(891, 3220, 3341)** $\Rightarrow 3341 - 3220 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 72171$, $T_{121} := 891^2$,
 $E := \{6441, 6443, \dots, 6679, 6681\}$ or $E := \{6501, 6502, \dots, 6620, 6621\}$

■ Number 892

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$892^2 + 49725^2 := 49733^2$$

$$892^2 + 99456^2 := 99460^2$$

$$892^2 + 198915^2 := 198917^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(892, 49725, 49733)** $\Rightarrow 49733 - 892 = 221^2$, $S_{221 \times 221} := 11188125$, $T_{48841} := 49725^2$,
 $E := \{1785, 1787, \dots, 99463, 99465\}$ or $E := \{26205, 26206, \dots, 75044, 75045\}$
2. **(892, 198915, 198917)** $\Rightarrow 198917 - 892 = 445^2$, $S_{445 \times 445} := 88915005$, $T_{198025} := 198915^2$,
 $E := \{1785, 1787, \dots, 397831, 397833\}$ or $E := \{100797, 100798, \dots, 298820, 298821\}$

■ Number 893

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$893^2 + 924^2 := 1285^2$$

$$893^2 + 8460^2 := 8507^2$$

$$893^2 + 20976^2 := 20995^2$$

$$893^2 + 398724^2 := 398725^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(893, 924, 1285)** $\Rightarrow 1285 - 924 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 41971$, $T_{361} := 893^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 2567, 2569\}$ or $E := \{2029, 2030, \dots, 2388, 2389\}$

■ Number 894

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$894^2 + 1192^2 := 1490^2$$

$$894^2 + 22192^2 := 22210^2$$

$$894^2 + 66600^2 := 66606^2$$

$$894^2 + 199808^2 := 199810^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(894, 22192, 22210)** $\Rightarrow 22210 - 894 = 146^2$, $S_{146 \times 146} := 3373184$, $T_{21316} := 22192^2$,
 $E := \{1789, 1791, \dots, 44417, 44419\}$
2. **(894, 199808, 199810)** $\Rightarrow 199810 - 894 = 446^2$, $S_{446 \times 446} := 89513984$, $T_{198916} := 199808^2$,
 $E := \{1789, 1791, \dots, 399617, 399619\}$

■ Number 895

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$895^2 + 2148^2 := 2327^2$$

$$895^2 + 16008^2 := 16033^2$$

$$895^2 + 80100^2 := 80105^2$$

$$895^2 + 400512^2 := 400513^2$$

(b) **Magic Squares**

- **(895, 16008, 16033)** $\Rightarrow 16033 - 16008 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 160205$, $T_{25} := 895^2$,
 $E := \{32017, 32019, \dots, 32063, 32065\}$ or $E := \{32029, 32030, \dots, 32052, 32053\}$

■ Number 896

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$896^2 + 1440^2 := 1696^2$	$896^2 + 4047^2 := 4145^2$	$896^2 + 25080^2 := 25096^2$
$896^2 + 1680^2 := 1904^2$	$896^2 + 6240^2 := 6304^2$	$896^2 + 28665^2 := 28679^2$
$896^2 + 1950^2 := 2146^2$	$896^2 + 7140^2 := 7196^2$	$896^2 + 50172^2 := 50180^2$
$896^2 + 3072^2 := 3200^2$	$896^2 + 12528^2 := 12560^2$	$896^2 + 100350^2 := 100354^2$
$896^2 + 3528^2 := 3640^2$	$896^2 + 14322^2 := 14350^2$	$896^2 + 200703^2 := 200705^2$

(b) **Magic Squares**

1. **(896, 25080, 25096)** $\Rightarrow 25096 - 25080 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 200704$, $T_{16} := 896^2$,
 $E := \{50161, 50163, \dots, 50189, 50191\}$
2. **(896, 6240, 6304)** $\Rightarrow 6304 - 6240 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 100352$, $T_{64} := 896^2$,
 $E := \{12481, 12483, \dots, 12605, 12607\}$
3. **(896, 1950, 2146)** $\Rightarrow 2146 - 1950 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 57344$, $T_{196} := 896^2$,
 $E := \{3901, 3903, \dots, 4289, 4291\}$

4. **(896, 1440, 1696)** $\Rightarrow 1696 - 1440 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 50176$, $T_{256} := 896^2$,
 $E := \{2881, 2883, \dots, 3389, 3391\}$
5. **(896, 3072, 3200)** $\Rightarrow 3200 - 896 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 196608$, $T_{2304} := 3072^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 6397, 6399\}$
6. **(896, 4047, 4145)** $\Rightarrow 4145 - 896 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 287337$, $T_{3249} := 4047^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 8287, 8289\}$ or $E := \{3417, 3418, \dots, 6664, 6665\}$
7. **(896, 12528, 12560)** $\Rightarrow 12560 - 896 = 108^2$, $S_{108 \times 108} := 1453248$, $T_{11664} := 12528^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 25117, 25119\}$
8. **(896, 50172, 50180)** $\Rightarrow 50180 - 896 = 222^2$, $S_{222 \times 222} := 11338872$, $T_{49284} := 50172^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 100357, 100359\}$
9. **(896, 200703, 200705)** $\Rightarrow 200705 - 896 = 447^2$, $S_{447 \times 447} := 90115647$, $T_{199809} := 200703^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 401407, 401409\}$ or $E := \{101697, 101698, \dots, 301504, 301505\}$

■ Number 897

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$897^2 + 1196^2 := 1495^2$$

$$897^2 + 1840^2 := 2047^2$$

$$897^2 + 2296^2 := 2465^2$$

$$897^2 + 3380^2 := 3497^2$$

$$897^2 + 5796^2 := 5865^2$$

$$897^2 + 10296^2 := 10335^2$$

$$897^2 + 17480^2 := 17503^2$$

$$897^2 + 30940^2 := 30953^2$$

$$897^2 + 44696^2 := 44705^2$$

$$897^2 + 134100^2 := 134103^2$$

$$897^2 + 402304^2 := 402305^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

1. **(897, 44696, 44705)** $\Rightarrow 44705 - 44696 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 268203$, $T_9 := 897^2$,
 $E := \{89393, 89395, \dots, 89407, 89409\}$ or $E := \{89397, 89398, \dots, 89404, 89405\}$
2. **(897, 2296, 2465)** $\Rightarrow 2465 - 2296 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 61893$, $T_{169} := 897^2$,
 $E := \{4593, 4595, \dots, 4927, 4929\}$ or $E := \{4677, 4678, \dots, 4844, 4845\}$

■ Number 898

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$898^2 + 201600^2 := 201602^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

- **(898, 201600, 201602)** $\Rightarrow 201602 - 898 = 448^2$, $S_{448 \times 448} := 90720000$, $T_{200704} := 201600^2$,
 $E := \{1797, 1799, \dots, 403201, 403203\}$

■ Number 899

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$899^2 + 13020^2 := 13051^2$$

$$899^2 + 13920^2 := 13949^2$$

$$899^2 + 404100^2 := 404101^2$$

■ Number 900

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$900^2 + 945^2 := 1305^2$$

$$900^2 + 1088^2 := 1412^2$$

$$900^2 + 1200^2 := 1500^2$$

$$900^2 + 1365^2 := 1635^2$$

$$900^2 + 1495^2 := 1745^2$$

$$900^2 + 1767^2 := 1983^2$$

$$900^2 + 1925^2 := 2125^2$$

$$900^2 + 2160^2 := 2340^2$$

$$900^2 + 2419^2 := 2581^2$$

$$900^2 + 2625^2 := 2775^2$$

$$900^2 + 3315^2 := 3435^2$$

$$900^2 + 3696^2 := 3804^2$$

$$900^2 + 4000^2 := 4100^2$$

$$900^2 + 4455^2 := 4545^2$$

$$900^2 + 5589^2 := 5661^2$$

$$900^2 + 6720^2 := 6780^2$$

$$900^2 + 7473^2 := 7527^2$$

$$900^2 + 8075^2 := 8125^2$$

$$900^2 + 10105^2 := 10145^2$$

$$900^2 + 11232^2 := 11268^2$$

$$900^2 + 13485^2 := 13515^2$$

$$900^2 + 16863^2 := 16887^2$$

$$900^2 + 20240^2 := 20260^2$$

$$900^2 + 22491^2 := 22509^2$$

$$900^2 + 33744^2 := 33756^2$$

$$900^2 + 40495^2 := 40505^2$$

$$900^2 + 50621^2 := 50629^2$$

$$900^2 + 67497^2 := 67503^2$$

$$900^2 + 101248^2 := 101252^2$$

$$900^2 + 202499^2 := 202501^2$$

(b) Magic Squares

$$1. \text{ (900, 11232, 11268)} \Rightarrow 11268 - 11232 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 135000, T_{36} := 900^2, \\ E := \{22465, 22467, \dots, 22533, 22535\}$$

$$2. \text{ (900, 4000, 4100)} \Rightarrow 4100 - 4000 = 10^2, S_{10 \times 10} := 81000, T_{100} := 900^2, \\ E := \{8001, 8003, \dots, 8197, 8199\}$$

$$3. \text{ (900, 1088, 1412)} \Rightarrow 1412 - 1088 = 18^2, S_{18 \times 18} := 45000, T_{324} := 900^2, \\ E := \{2177, 2179, \dots, 2821, 2823\}$$

$$4. \text{ (900, 1925, 2125)} \Rightarrow 2125 - 900 = 35^2, S_{35 \times 35} := 105875, T_{1225} := 1925^2, \\ E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 4247, 4249\} \text{ or } E := \{2413, 2414, \dots, 3636, 3637\}$$

$$5. \text{ (900, 2419, 2581)} \Rightarrow 2581 - 900 = 41^2, S_{41 \times 41} := 142721, T_{1681} := 2419^2, \\ E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 5159, 5161\} \text{ or } E := \{2641, 2642, \dots, 4320, 4321\}$$

$$6. \text{ (900, 5589, 5661)} \Rightarrow 5661 - 900 = 69^2, S_{69 \times 69} := 452709, T_{4761} := 5589^2, \\ E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 11319, 11321\} \text{ or } E := \{4181, 4182, \dots, 8940, 8941\}$$

$$7. \text{ (900, 8075, 8125)} \Rightarrow 8125 - 900 = 85^2, S_{85 \times 85} := 767125, T_{7225} := 8075^2, \\ E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 16247, 16249\} \text{ or } E := \{5413, 5414, \dots, 12636, 12637\}$$

8. **(900, 22491, 22509)** $\Rightarrow 22509 - 900 = 147^2$, $S_{147 \times 147} := 3441123$, $T_{21609} := 22491^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 45015, 45017\}$ or $E := \{12605, 12606, \dots, 34212, 34213\}$
9. **(900, 50621, 50629)** $\Rightarrow 50629 - 900 = 223^2$, $S_{223 \times 223} := 11490967$, $T_{49729} := 50621^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 101255, 101257\}$ or $E := \{26665, 26666, \dots, 76392, 76393\}$
10. **(900, 202499, 202501)** $\Rightarrow 202501 - 900 = 449^2$, $S_{449 \times 449} := 91327049$, $T_{201601} := 202499^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 404999, 405001\}$ or $E := \{102601, 102602, \dots, 304200, 304201\}$

2.10 Pythagorean Triples: 901 to 1000

■ Number 901

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$901^2 + 1260^2 := 1549^2$$

$$901^2 + 7632^2 := 7685^2$$

$$901^2 + 23868^2 := 23885^2$$

$$901^2 + 405900^2 := 405901^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(901, 1260, 1549)** $\Rightarrow 1549 - 1260 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 47753$, $T_{289} := 901^2$,
 $E := \{2521, 2523, \dots, 3095, 3097\}$ or $E := \{2665, 2666, \dots, 2952, 2953\}$

■ Number 902

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$902^2 + 1560^2 := 1802^2$$

$$902^2 + 4920^2 := 5002^2$$

$$902^2 + 18480^2 := 18502^2$$

$$902^2 + 203400^2 := 203402^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(902, 1560, 1802)** $\Rightarrow 1802 - 902 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 81120$, $T_{900} := 1560^2$,
 $E := \{1805, 1807, \dots, 3601, 3603\}$
2. **(902, 203400, 203402)** $\Rightarrow 203402 - 902 = 450^2$, $S_{450 \times 450} := 91936800$, $T_{202500} := 203400^2$,
 $E := \{1805, 1807, \dots, 406801, 406803\}$

■ Number 903

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 903^2 + 1204^2 &:= 1505^2 \\ 903^2 + 2700^2 &:= 2847^2 \\ 903^2 + 3096^2 &:= 3225^2 \\ 903^2 + 6440^2 &:= 6503^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 903^2 + 8296^2 &:= 8345^2 \\ 903^2 + 9460^2 &:= 9503^2 \\ 903^2 + 19404^2 &:= 19425^2 \\ 903^2 + 45296^2 &:= 45305^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 903^2 + 58240^2 &:= 58247^2 \\ 903^2 + 135900^2 &:= 135903^2 \\ 903^2 + 407704^2 &:= 407705^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Square**

1. **(903, 45296, 45305)** $\Rightarrow 45305 - 45296 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 271803$, $T_9 := 903^2$,
 $E := \{90593, 90595, \dots, 90607, 90609\}$ or $E := \{90597, 90598, \dots, 90604, 90605\}$
2. **(903, 8296, 8345)** $\Rightarrow 8345 - 8296 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 116487$, $T_{49} := 903^2$,
 $E := \{16593, 16595, \dots, 16687, 16689\}$ or $E := \{16617, 16618, \dots, 16664, 16665\}$

■ Number 904

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned} 904^2 + 1695^2 &:= 1921^2 \\ 904^2 + 12753^2 &:= 12785^2 \\ 904^2 + 25530^2 &:= 25546^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 904^2 + 51072^2 &:= 51080^2 \\ 904^2 + 102150^2 &:= 102154^2 \\ 904^2 + 204303^2 &:= 204305^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Square**

1. **(904, 25530, 25546)** $\Rightarrow 25546 - 25530 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 204304$, $T_{16} := 904^2$,
 $E := \{51061, 51063, \dots, 51089, 51091\}$
2. **(904, 12753, 12785)** $\Rightarrow 12785 - 904 = 109^2$, $S_{109 \times 109} := 1492101$, $T_{11881} := 12753^2$,
 $E := \{1809, 1811, \dots, 25567, 25569\}$ or $E := \{7749, 7750, \dots, 19628, 19629\}$
3. **(904, 51072, 51080)** $\Rightarrow 51080 - 904 = 224^2$, $S_{224 \times 224} := 11644416$, $T_{50176} := 51072^2$,
 $E := \{1809, 1811, \dots, 102157, 102159\}$
4. **(904, 204303, 204305)** $\Rightarrow 204305 - 904 = 451^2$, $S_{451 \times 451} := 92549259$, $T_{203401} := 204303^2$,
 $E := \{1809, 1811, \dots, 408607, 408609\}$ or $E := \{103509, 103510, \dots, 306908, 306909\}$

■ Number 905

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{aligned} 905^2 + 2172^2 &:= 2353^2 \\ 905^2 + 16368^2 &:= 16393^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$905^2 + 81900^2 := 81905^2$$

$$905^2 + 409512^2 := 409513^2$$

(b) **Magic Square**

- **(905, 16368, 16393)** $\Rightarrow 16393 - 16368 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 163805$, $T_{25} := 905^2$,

$$E := \{32737, 32739, \dots, 32783, 32785\} \text{ or } E := \{32749, 32750, \dots, 32772, 32773\}$$

■ Number 906

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$906^2 + 1208^2 := 1510^2$$

$$906^2 + 68400^2 := 68406^2$$

$$906^2 + 22792^2 := 22810^2$$

$$906^2 + 205208^2 := 205210^2$$

(b) **Magic Square**

1. **(906, 22792, 22810)** $\Rightarrow 22810 - 906 = 148^2$, $S_{148 \times 148} := 3509968$, $T_{21904} := 22792^2$,
 $E := \{1813, 1815, \dots, 45617, 45619\}$

2. **(906, 205208, 205210)** $\Rightarrow 205210 - 906 = 452^2$, $S_{452 \times 452} := 93164432$, $T_{204304} := 205208^2$,
 $E := \{1813, 1815, \dots, 410417, 410419\}$

■ Number 907

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$907^2 + 411324^2 := 411325^2$$

■ Number 908

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$908^2 + 51525^2 := 51533^2$$

$$908^2 + 103056^2 := 103060^2$$

$$908^2 + 206115^2 := 206117^2$$

(b) **Magic Square**

1. **(908, 51525, 51533)** $\Rightarrow 51533 - 908 = 225^2$, $S_{225 \times 225} := 11799225$, $T_{50625} := 51525^2$,

$$E := \{1817, 1819, \dots, 103063, 103065\} \text{ or } E := \{27129, 27130, \dots, 77752, 77753\}$$

2. **(908, 206115, 206117)** $\Rightarrow 206117 - 908 = 453^2$, $S_{453 \times 453} := 93782325$, $T_{205209} := 206115^2$,
 $E := \{1817, 1819, \dots, 412231, 412233\}$ or $E := \{104421, 104422, \dots, 309628, 309629\}$

■ Number 909

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 909^2 + 1212^2 := 1515^2 & 909^2 + 45900^2 := 45909^2 \\ 909^2 + 4040^2 := 4141^2 & 909^2 + 137712^2 := 137715^2 \\ 909^2 + 5060^2 := 5141^2 & 909^2 + 413140^2 := 413141^2 \\ 909^2 + 15288^2 := 15315^2 & \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(909, 45900, 45909)** $\Rightarrow 45909 - 45900 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 275427$, $T_9 := 909^2$,
 $E := \{91801, 91803, \dots, 91815, 91817\}$ or $E := \{91805, 91806, \dots, 91812, 91813\}$
2. **(909, 5060, 5141)** $\Rightarrow 5141 - 5060 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 91809$, $T_{81} := 909^2$,
 $E := \{10121, 10123, \dots, 10279, 10281\}$ or $E := \{10161, 10162, \dots, 10240, 10241\}$

■ Number 910

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll} 910^2 + 1008^2 := 1358^2 & 910^2 + 4176^2 := 4274^2 & 910^2 + 29568^2 := 29582^2 \\ 910^2 + 1056^2 := 1394^2 & 910^2 + 5880^2 := 5950^2 & 910^2 + 41400^2 := 41410^2 \\ 910^2 + 2184^2 := 2366^2 & 910^2 + 8256^2 := 8306^2 & 910^2 + 207024^2 := 207026^2 \\ 910^2 + 3120^2 := 3250^2 & 910^2 + 15912^2 := 15938^2 & \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(910, 1056, 1394)** $\Rightarrow 1394 - 910 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 50688$, $T_{484} := 1056^2$,
 $E := \{1821, 1823, \dots, 2785, 2787\}$
2. **(910, 4176, 4274)** $\Rightarrow 4274 - 910 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 300672$, $T_{3364} := 4176^2$,
 $E := \{1821, 1823, \dots, 8545, 8547\}$
3. **(910, 8256, 8306)** $\Rightarrow 8306 - 910 = 86^2$, $S_{86 \times 86} := 792576$, $T_{7396} := 8256^2$,
 $E := \{1821, 1823, \dots, 16609, 16611\}$
4. **(910, 207024, 207026)** $\Rightarrow 207026 - 910 = 454^2$, $S_{454 \times 454} := 94402944$, $T_{206116} := 207024^2$,
 $E := \{1821, 1823, \dots, 414049, 414051\}$

■ Number 911

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$911^2 + 414960^2 := 414961^2$$

■ Number 912

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$912^2 + 1045^2 := 1387^2$$

$$912^2 + 1216^2 := 1520^2$$

$$912^2 + 1300^2 := 1588^2$$

$$912^2 + 1710^2 := 1938^2$$

$$912^2 + 2070^2 := 2262^2$$

$$912^2 + 2660^2 := 2812^2$$

$$912^2 + 2816^2 := 2960^2$$

$$912^2 + 3185^2 := 3313^2$$

$$912^2 + 3591^2 := 3705^2$$

$$912^2 + 4284^2 := 4380^2$$

$$912^2 + 5434^2 := 5510^2$$

$$912^2 + 5740^2 := 5812^2$$

$$912^2 + 6466^2 := 6530^2$$

$$912^2 + 8640^2 := 8688^2$$

$$912^2 + 10925^2 := 10963^2$$

$$912^2 + 11534^2 := 11570^2$$

$$912^2 + 12980^2 := 13012^2$$

$$912^2 + 17316^2 := 17340^2$$

$$912^2 + 23095^2 := 23113^2$$

$$912^2 + 25984^2 := 26000^2$$

$$912^2 + 34650^2 := 34662^2$$

$$912^2 + 51980^2 := 51988^2$$

$$912^2 + 69309^2 := 69315^2$$

$$912^2 + 103966^2 := 103970^2$$

$$912^2 + 207935^2 := 207937^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(912, 25984, 26000)** $\Rightarrow 26000 - 25984 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 207936$, $T_{16} := 912^2$,
 $E := \{51969, 51971, \dots, 51997, 51999\}$
2. **(912, 11534, 11570)** $\Rightarrow 11570 - 11534 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 138624$, $T_{36} := 912^2$,
 $E := \{23069, 23071, \dots, 23137, 23139\}$
3. **(912, 6466, 6530)** $\Rightarrow 6530 - 6466 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 103968$, $T_{64} := 912^2$,
 $E := \{12933, 12935, \dots, 13057, 13059\}$
4. **(912, 2816, 2960)** $\Rightarrow 2960 - 2816 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 69312$, $T_{144} := 912^2$,
 $E := \{5633, 5635, \dots, 5917, 5919\}$
5. **(912, 1300, 1588)** $\Rightarrow 1588 - 912 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 65000$, $T_{676} := 1300^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 3173, 3175\}$
6. **(912, 3185, 3313)** $\Rightarrow 3313 - 912 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 207025$, $T_{2401} := 3185^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 6623, 6625\}$ or $E := \{3025, 3026, \dots, 5424, 5425\}$
7. **(912, 5740, 5812)** $\Rightarrow 5812 - 912 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 470680$, $T_{4900} := 5740^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 11621, 11623\}$
8. **(912, 12980, 13012)** $\Rightarrow 13012 - 912 = 110^2$, $S_{110 \times 110} := 1531640$, $T_{12100} := 12980^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 26021, 26023\}$

9. **(912, 207935, 207937)** $\Rightarrow 207937 - 912 = 455^2$, $S_{455 \times 455} := 95026295$, $T_{207025} := 207935^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 415871, 415873\}$ or $E := \{105337, 105338, \dots, 312360, 312361\}$
10. **(912, 23095, 23113)** $\Rightarrow 23113 - 912 = 149^2$, $S_{149 \times 149} := 3579725$, $T_{22201} := 23095^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 46223, 46225\}$ or $E := \{12925, 12926, \dots, 35124, 35125\}$
11. **(912, 51980, 51988)** $\Rightarrow 51988 - 912 = 226^2$, $S_{226 \times 226} := 11955400$, $T_{51076} := 51980^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 103973, 103975\}$

■ Number 913

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$913^2 + 3384^2 := 3505^2$$

$$913^2 + 37884^2 := 37895^2$$

$$913^2 + 4980^2 := 5063^2$$

$$913^2 + 416784^2 := 416785^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(913, 3384, 3505)** $\Rightarrow 3505 - 3384 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 75779$, $T_{121} := 913^2$,
 $E := \{6769, 6771, \dots, 7007, 7009\}$ or $E := \{6829, 6830, \dots, 6948, 6949\}$

■ Number 914

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$914^2 + 208848^2 := 208850^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(914, 208848, 208850)** $\Rightarrow 208850 - 914 = 456^2$, $S_{456 \times 456} := 95652384$, $T_{207936} := 208848^2$,
 $E := \{1829, 1831, \dots, 417697, 417699\}$

■ Number 915

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$915^2 + 1220^2 := 1525^2$$

$$915^2 + 6832^2 := 6893^2$$

$$915^2 + 46508^2 := 46517^2$$

$$915^2 + 1748^2 := 1973^2$$

$$915^2 + 9280^2 := 9325^2$$

$$915^2 + 83720^2 := 83725^2$$

$$915^2 + 2196^2 := 2379^2$$

$$915^2 + 16732^2 := 16757^2$$

$$915^2 + 139536^2 := 139539^2$$

$$915^2 + 5544^2 := 5619^2$$

$$915^2 + 27900^2 := 27915^2$$

$$915^2 + 418612^2 := 418613^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(915, 46508, 46517)** $\Rightarrow 46517 - 46508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 279075$, $T_9 := 915^2$,
 $E := \{93017, 93019, \dots, 93031, 93033\}$ or $E := \{93021, 93022, \dots, 93028, 93029\}$
2. **(915, 16732, 16757)** $\Rightarrow 16757 - 16732 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 167445$, $T_{25} := 915^2$,
 $E := \{33465, 33467, \dots, 33511, 33513\}$ or $E := \{33477, 33478, \dots, 33500, 33501\}$
3. **(915, 1748, 1973)** $\Rightarrow 1973 - 1748 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 55815$, $T_{225} := 915^2$,
 $E := \{3497, 3499, \dots, 3943, 3945\}$ or $E := \{3609, 3610, \dots, 3832, 3833\}$

■ Number 916

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$916^2 + 52437^2 := 52445^2$$

$$916^2 + 104880^2 := 104884^2$$

$$916^2 + 209763^2 := 209765^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(916, 52437, 52445)** $\Rightarrow 52445 - 916 = 227^2$, $S_{227 \times 227} := 12112947$, $T_{51529} := 52437^2$,
 $E := \{1833, 1835, \dots, 104887, 104889\}$ or $E := \{27597, 27598, \dots, 79124, 79125\}$
2. **(916, 209763, 209765)** $\Rightarrow 209765 - 916 = 457^2$, $S_{457 \times 457} := 96281217$, $T_{208849} := 209763^2$,
 $E := \{1833, 1835, \dots, 419527, 419529\}$ or $E := \{106257, 106258, \dots, 315104, 315105\}$

■ Number 917

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$917^2 + 3144^2 := 3275^2$$

$$917^2 + 8556^2 := 8605^2$$

$$917^2 + 60060^2 := 60067^2$$

$$917^2 + 420444^2 := 420445^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(917, 8556, 8605)** $\Rightarrow 8605 - 8556 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 120127$, $T_{49} := 917^2$,
 $E := \{17113, 17115, \dots, 17207, 17209\}$ or $E := \{17137, 17138, \dots, 17184, 17185\}$

■ Number 918

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 918^2 + 1224^2 &:= 1530^2 \\ 918^2 + 2520^2 &:= 2682^2 \\ 918^2 + 4080^2 &:= 4182^2 \\ 918^2 + 7776^2 &:= 7830^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 918^2 + 12376^2 &:= 12410^2 \\ 918^2 + 23400^2 &:= 23418^2 \\ 918^2 + 70224^2 &:= 70230^2 \\ 918^2 + 210680^2 &:= 210682^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) **Magic Square**

1. **(918, 2520, 2682)** $\Rightarrow 2682 - 918 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 151200$, $T_{1764} := 2520^2$,
 $E := \{1837, 1839, \dots, 5361, 5363\}$
2. **(918, 23400, 23418)** $\Rightarrow 23418 - 918 = 150^2$, $S_{150 \times 150} := 3650400$, $T_{22500} := 23400^2$,
 $E := \{1837, 1839, \dots, 46833, 46835\}$
3. **(918, 210680, 210682)** $\Rightarrow 210682 - 918 = 458^2$, $S_{458 \times 458} := 96912800$, $T_{209764} := 210680^2$,
 $E := \{1837, 1839, \dots, 421361, 421363\}$

■ **Number 919**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$919^2 + 422280^2 := 422281^2$$

■ **Number 920**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$920^2 + 966^2 := 1334^2$	$920^2 + 4554^2 := 4646^2$	$920^2 + 21150^2 := 21170^2$
$920^2 + 1725^2 := 1955^2$	$920^2 + 5250^2 := 5330^2$	$920^2 + 26442^2 := 26458^2$
$920^2 + 2016^2 := 2216^2$	$920^2 + 8439^2 := 8489^2$	$920^2 + 42315^2 := 42325^2$
$920^2 + 2208^2 := 2392^2$	$920^2 + 9177^2 := 9223^2$	$920^2 + 52896^2 := 52904^2$
$920^2 + 2565^2 := 2725^2$	$920^2 + 10560^2 := 10600^2$	$920^2 + 105798^2 := 105802^2$
$920^2 + 4182^2 := 4282^2$	$920^2 + 13209^2 := 13241^2$	$920^2 + 211599^2 := 211601^2$

(b) **Magic Square**

1. **(920, 26442, 26458)** $\Rightarrow 26458 - 26442 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 211600$, $T_{16} := 920^2$,
 $E := \{52885, 52887, \dots, 52913, 52915\}$
2. **(920, 4182, 4282)** $\Rightarrow 4282 - 4182 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 84640$, $T_{100} := 920^2$,
 $E := \{8365, 8367, \dots, 8561, 8563\}$

3. **(920, 2016, 2216)** $\Rightarrow 2216 - 920 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 112896$, $T_{1296} := 2016^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 4429, 4431\}$
4. **(920, 8439, 8489)** $\Rightarrow 8489 - 920 = 87^2$, $S_{87 \times 87} := 818583$, $T_{7569} := 8439^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 16975, 16977\}$ or $E := \{5625, 5626, \dots, 13192, 13193\}$
5. **(920, 13209, 13241)** $\Rightarrow 13241 - 920 = 111^2$, $S_{111 \times 111} := 1571871$, $T_{12321} := 13209^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 26479, 26481\}$ or $E := \{8001, 8002, \dots, 20320, 20321\}$
6. **(920, 52896, 52904)** $\Rightarrow 52904 - 920 = 228^2$, $S_{228 \times 228} := 12271872$, $T_{51984} := 52896^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 105805, 105807\}$
7. **(920, 211599, 211601)** $\Rightarrow 211601 - 920 = 459^2$, $S_{459 \times 459} := 97547139$, $T_{210681} := 211599^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 423199, 423201\}$ or $E := \{107181, 107182, \dots, 317860, 317861\}$

■ Number 921

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$921^2 + 1228^2 := 1535^2$$

$$921^2 + 141372^2 := 141375^2$$

$$921^2 + 47120^2 := 47129^2$$

$$921^2 + 424120^2 := 424121^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(921, 47120, 47129)** $\Rightarrow 47129 - 47120 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 282747$, $T_9 := 921^2$,
 $E := \{94241, 94243, \dots, 94255, 94257\}$ or $E := \{94245, 94246, \dots, 94252, 94253\}$

■ Number 922

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$922^2 + 212520^2 := 212522^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(922, 212520, 212522)** $\Rightarrow 212522 - 922 = 460^2$, $S_{460 \times 460} := 98184240$, $T_{211600} := 212520^2$,
 $E := \{1845, 1847, \dots, 425041, 425043\}$

■ Number 923

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$923^2 + 2436^2 := 2605^2$$

$$923^2 + 5964^2 := 6035^2$$

$$923^2 + 32760^2 := 32773^2$$

$$923^2 + 425964^2 := 425965^2$$

(b) **Magic Square**

- **(923, 2436, 2605)** $\Rightarrow 2605 - 2436 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 65533$, $T_{169} := 923^2$,
 $E := \{4873, 4875, \dots, 5207, 5209\}$ or $E := \{4957, 4958, \dots, 5124, 5125\}$

■ Number 924

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$924^2 + 1232^2 := 1540^2$$

$$924^2 + 1305^2 := 1599^2$$

$$924^2 + 1485^2 := 1749^2$$

$$924^2 + 1568^2 := 1820^2$$

$$924^2 + 1643^2 := 1885^2$$

$$924^2 + 2057^2 := 2255^2$$

$$924^2 + 2080^2 := 2276^2$$

$$924^2 + 2457^2 := 2625^2$$

$$924^2 + 2695^2 := 2849^2$$

$$924^2 + 3168^2 := 3300^2$$

$$924^2 + 3325^2 := 3451^2$$

$$924^2 + 4307^2 := 4405^2$$

$$924^2 + 4807^2 := 4895^2$$

$$924^2 + 5040^2 := 5124^2$$

$$924^2 + 5893^2 := 5965^2$$

$$924^2 + 6435^2 := 6501^2$$

$$924^2 + 7595^2 := 7651^2$$

$$924^2 + 9680^2 := 9724^2$$

$$924^2 + 10143^2 := 10185^2$$

$$924^2 + 11840^2 := 11876^2$$

$$924^2 + 15232^2 := 15260^2$$

$$924^2 + 17775^2 := 17799^2$$

$$924^2 + 19393^2 := 19415^2$$

$$924^2 + 23707^2 := 23725^2$$

$$924^2 + 30485^2 := 30499^2$$

$$924^2 + 35568^2 := 35580^2$$

$$924^2 + 53357^2 := 53365^2$$

$$924^2 + 71145^2 := 71151^2$$

$$924^2 + 106720^2 := 106724^2$$

$$924^2 + 213443^2 := 213445^2$$

(b) **Magic Square**

1. **(924, 11840, 11876)** $\Rightarrow 11876 - 11840 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 142296$, $T_{36} := 924^2$,
 $E := \{23681, 23683, \dots, 23749, 23751\}$
2. **(924, 2080, 2276)** $\Rightarrow 2276 - 2080 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 60984$, $T_{196} := 924^2$,
 $E := \{4161, 4163, \dots, 4549, 4551\}$
3. **(924, 1643, 1885)** $\Rightarrow 1885 - 924 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 87079$, $T_{961} := 1643^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 3767, 3769\}$ or $E := \{2329, 2330, \dots, 3288, 3289\}$
4. **(924, 4307, 4405)** $\Rightarrow 4405 - 924 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 314411$, $T_{3481} := 4307^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 8807, 8809\}$ or $E := \{3589, 3590, \dots, 7068, 7069\}$
5. **(924, 5893, 5965)** $\Rightarrow 5965 - 924 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 489119$, $T_{5041} := 5893^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 11927, 11929\}$ or $E := \{4369, 4370, \dots, 9408, 9409\}$
6. **(924, 23707, 23725)** $\Rightarrow 23725 - 924 = 151^2$, $S_{151 \times 151} := 3721999$, $T_{22801} := 23707^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 47447, 47449\}$ or $E := \{13249, 13250, \dots, 36048, 36049\}$
7. **(924, 53357, 53365)** $\Rightarrow 53365 - 924 = 229^2$, $S_{229 \times 229} := 12432181$, $T_{52441} := 53357^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 106727, 106729\}$ or $E := \{28069, 28070, \dots, 80508, 80509\}$

8. **(924, 213443, 213445)** $\Rightarrow 213445 - 924 = 461^2$, $S_{461 \times 461} := 98824109$, $T_{212521} := 213443^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 426887, 426889\}$ or $E := \{108109, 108110, \dots, 320628, 320629\}$

■ Number 925

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$925^2 + 2220^2 := 2405^2$$

$$925^2 + 3360^2 := 3485^2$$

$$925^2 + 11544^2 := 11581^2$$

$$925^2 + 17100^2 := 17125^2$$

$$925^2 + 85560^2 := 85565^2$$

$$925^2 + 427812^2 := 427813^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(925, 17100, 17125)** $\Rightarrow 17125 - 17100 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 171125$, $T_{25} := 925^2$,
 $E := \{34201, 34203, \dots, 34247, 34249\}$ or $E := \{34213, 34214, \dots, 34236, 34237\}$

■ Number 926

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$926^2 + 214368^2 := 214370^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(926, 214368, 214370)** $\Rightarrow 214370 - 926 = 462^2$, $S_{462 \times 462} := 99466752$, $T_{213444} := 214368^2$,
 $E := \{1853, 1855, \dots, 428737, 428739\}$

■ Number 927

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$927^2 + 1236^2 := 1545^2$$

$$927^2 + 4120^2 := 4223^2$$

$$927^2 + 5264^2 := 5345^2$$

$$927^2 + 15900^2 := 15927^2$$

$$927^2 + 47736^2 := 47745^2$$

$$927^2 + 143220^2 := 143223^2$$

$$927^2 + 429664^2 := 429665^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(927, 47736, 47745)** $\Rightarrow 47745 - 47736 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 286443$, $T_9 := 927^2$,
 $E := \{95473, 95475, \dots, 95487, 95489\}$ or $E := \{95477, 95478, \dots, 95484, 95485\}$

2. **(927, 5264, 5345)** $\Rightarrow 5345 - 5264 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 95481$, $T_{81} := 927^2$,
 $E := \{10529, 10531, \dots, 10687, 10689\}$ or $E := \{10569, 10570, \dots, 10648, 10649\}$

■ Number 928

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$928^2 + 1554^2 := 1810^2$$

$$928^2 + 1740^2 := 1972^2$$

$$928^2 + 3300^2 := 3428^2$$

$$928^2 + 3654^2 := 3770^2$$

$$928^2 + 6696^2 := 6760^2$$

$$928^2 + 7395^2 := 7453^2$$

$$928^2 + 13440^2 := 13472^2$$

$$928^2 + 26904^2 := 26920^2$$

$$928^2 + 53820^2 := 53828^2$$

$$928^2 + 107646^2 := 107650^2$$

$$928^2 + 215295^2 := 215297^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(928, 26904, 26920)** $\Rightarrow 26920 - 26904 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 215296$, $T_{16} := 928^2$,
 $E := \{53809, 53811, \dots, 53837, 53839\}$

2. **(928, 6696, 6760)** $\Rightarrow 6760 - 6696 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 107648$, $T_{64} := 928^2$,
 $E := \{13393, 13395, \dots, 13517, 13519\}$

3. **(928, 1554, 1810)** $\Rightarrow 1810 - 1554 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 53824$, $T_{256} := 928^2$,
 $E := \{3109, 3111, \dots, 3617, 3619\}$

4. **(928, 3300, 3428)** $\Rightarrow 3428 - 928 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 217800$, $T_{2500} := 3300^2$,
 $E := \{1857, 1859, \dots, 6853, 6855\}$

5. **(928, 13440, 13472)** $\Rightarrow 13472 - 928 = 112^2$, $S_{112 \times 112} := 1612800$, $T_{12544} := 13440^2$,
 $E := \{1857, 1859, \dots, 26941, 26943\}$

6. **(928, 53820, 53828)** $\Rightarrow 53828 - 928 = 230^2$, $S_{230 \times 230} := 12593880$, $T_{52900} := 53820^2$,
 $E := \{1857, 1859, \dots, 107653, 107655\}$

7. **(928, 215295, 215297)** $\Rightarrow 215297 - 928 = 463^2$, $S_{463 \times 463} := 100112175$, $T_{214369} := 215295^2$,
 $E := \{1857, 1859, \dots, 430591, 430593\}$ or $E := \{109041, 109042, \dots, 323408, 323409\}$

■ Number 929

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$929^2 + 431520^2 := 431521^2$$

■ Number 930

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$930^2 + 1240^2 := 1550^2$$

$$930^2 + 2232^2 := 2418^2$$

$$930^2 + 2808^2 := 2958^2$$

$$930^2 + 4760^2 := 4850^2$$

$$930^2 + 6944^2 := 7006^2$$

$$930^2 + 8624^2 := 8674^2$$

$$930^2 + 14400^2 := 14430^2$$

$$930^2 + 24016^2 := 24034^2$$

$$930^2 + 43240^2 := 43250^2$$

$$930^2 + 72072^2 := 72078^2$$

$$930^2 + 216224^2 := 216226^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(930, 8624, 8674)** $\Rightarrow 8674 - 930 = 88^2$, $S_{88 \times 88} := 845152$, $T_{7744} := 8624^2$,
 $E := \{1861, 1863, \dots, 17345, 17347\}$

2. **(930, 24016, 24034)** $\Rightarrow 24034 - 930 = 152^2$, $S_{152 \times 152} := 3794528$, $T_{23104} := 24016^2$,
 $E := \{1861, 1863, \dots, 48065, 48067\}$

3. **(930, 216224, 216226)** $\Rightarrow 216226 - 930 = 464^2$, $S_{464 \times 464} := 100760384$, $T_{215296} := 216224^2$,
 $E := \{1861, 1863, \dots, 432449, 432451\}$

■ Number 931

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$931^2 + 1020^2 := 1381^2$$

$$931^2 + 1092^2 := 1435^2$$

$$931^2 + 3192^2 := 3325^2$$

$$931^2 + 8820^2 := 8869^2$$

$$931^2 + 22800^2 := 22819^2$$

$$931^2 + 61908^2 := 61915^2$$

$$931^2 + 433380^2 := 433381^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(931, 8820, 8869)** $\Rightarrow 8869 - 8820 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 123823$, $T_{49} := 931^2$,
 $E := \{17641, 17643, \dots, 17735, 17737\}$ or $E := \{17665, 17666, \dots, 17712, 17713\}$

2. **(931, 1020, 1381)** $\Rightarrow 1381 - 1020 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 45619$, $T_{361} := 931^2$,
 $E := \{2041, 2043, \dots, 2759, 2761\}$ or $E := \{2221, 2222, \dots, 2580, 2581\}$

■ Number 932

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$932^2 + 54285^2 := 54293^2$$

$$932^2 + 108576^2 := 108580^2$$

$$932^2 + 217155^2 := 217157^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(932, 54285, 54293)** $\Rightarrow 54293 - 932 = 231^2$, $S_{231 \times 231} := 12756975$, $T_{53361} := 54285^2$,
 $E := \{1865, 1867, \dots, 108583, 108585\}$ or $E := \{28545, 28546, \dots, 81904, 81905\}$

2. **(932, 217155, 217157)** $\Rightarrow 217157 - 932 = 465^2$, $S_{465 \times 465} := 101411385$, $T_{216225} := 217155^2$,
 $E := \{1865, 1867, \dots, 434311, 434313\}$ or $E := \{109977, 109978, \dots, 326200, 326201\}$

■ Number 933

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$933^2 + 1244^2 := 1555^2$$

$$933^2 + 48356^2 := 48365^2$$

$$933^2 + 145080^2 := 145083^2$$

$$933^2 + 435244^2 := 435245^2$$

(b) Magic Square

• **(933, 48356, 48365)** $\Rightarrow 48365 - 48356 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 290163$, $T_9 := 933^2$,
 $E := \{96713, 96715, \dots, 96727, 96729\}$ or $E := \{96717, 96718, \dots, 96724, 96725\}$

■ Number 934

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$934^2 + 218088^2 := 218090^2$$

(b) Magic Square

• **(934, 218088, 218090)** $\Rightarrow 218090 - 934 = 466^2$, $S_{466 \times 466} := 102065184$, $T_{217156} := 218088^2$,
 $E := \{1869, 1871, \dots, 436177, 436179\}$

■ Number 935

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$935^2 + 1368^2 := 1657^2$	$935^2 + 5100^2 := 5185^2$	$935^2 + 39732^2 := 39743^2$
$935^2 + 1452^2 := 1727^2$	$935^2 + 7920^2 := 7975^2$	$935^2 + 87420^2 := 87425^2$
$935^2 + 2244^2 := 2431^2$	$935^2 + 17472^2 := 17497^2$	$935^2 + 437112^2 := 437113^2$
$935^2 + 3552^2 := 3673^2$	$935^2 + 25704^2 := 25721^2$	

(b) Magic Square

1. **(935, 17472, 17497)** $\Rightarrow 17497 - 17472 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 174845$, $T_{25} := 935^2$,
 $E := \{34945, 34947, \dots, 34991, 34993\}$ or $E := \{34957, 34958, \dots, 34980, 34981\}$
2. **(935, 3552, 3673)** $\Rightarrow 3673 - 3552 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 79475$, $T_{121} := 935^2$,
 $E := \{7105, 7107, \dots, 7343, 7345\}$ or $E := \{7165, 7166, \dots, 7284, 7285\}$
3. **(935, 1368, 1657)** $\Rightarrow 1657 - 1368 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 51425$, $T_{289} := 935^2$,
 $E := \{2737, 2739, \dots, 3311, 3313\}$ or $E := \{2881, 2882, \dots, 3168, 3169\}$

■ Number 936

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$936^2 + 1127^2 := 1465^2$	$936^2 + 4002^2 := 4110^2$	$936^2 + 16835^2 := 16861^2$
$936^2 + 1190^2 := 1514^2$	$936^2 + 4160^2 := 4264^2$	$936^2 + 18240^2 := 18264^2$
$936^2 + 1248^2 := 1560^2$	$936^2 + 4515^2 := 4611^2$	$936^2 + 24327^2 := 24345^2$
$936^2 + 1377^2 := 1665^2$	$936^2 + 5577^2 := 5655^2$	$936^2 + 27370^2 := 27386^2$
$936^2 + 1755^2 := 1989^2$	$936^2 + 6048^2 := 6120^2$	$936^2 + 36498^2 := 36510^2$
$936^2 + 1920^2 := 2136^2$	$936^2 + 8085^2 := 8139^2$	$936^2 + 54752^2 := 54760^2$
$936^2 + 2002^2 := 2210^2$	$936^2 + 8398^2 := 8450^2$	$936^2 + 73005^2 := 73011^2$
$936^2 + 2623^2 := 2785^2$	$936^2 + 9102^2 := 9150^2$	$936^2 + 109510^2 := 109514^2$
$936^2 + 2730^2 := 2886^2$	$936^2 + 12150^2 := 12186^2$	$936^2 + 219023^2 := 219025^2$
$936^2 + 2970^2 := 3114^2$	$936^2 + 13673^2 := 13705^2$	

(b) Magic Square

1. **(936, 27370, 27386)** $\Rightarrow 27386 - 27370 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 219024$, $T_{16} := 936^2$,
 $E := \{54741, 54743, \dots, 54769, 54771\}$
2. **(936, 12150, 12186)** $\Rightarrow 12186 - 12150 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 146016$, $T_{36} := 936^2$,
 $E := \{24301, 24303, \dots, 24369, 24371\}$
3. **(936, 2970, 3114)** $\Rightarrow 3114 - 2970 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 73008$, $T_{144} := 936^2$,
 $E := \{5941, 5943, \dots, 6225, 6227\}$

4. **(936, 1190, 1514)** $\Rightarrow 1514 - 1190 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 48672$, $T_{324} := 936^2$,
 $E := \{2381, 2383, \dots, 3025, 3027\}$
5. **(936, 1127, 1465)** $\Rightarrow 1465 - 936 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 55223$, $T_{529} := 1127^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 2927, 2929\}$ or $E := \{2137, 2138, \dots, 2664, 2665\}$
6. **(936, 1377, 1665)** $\Rightarrow 1665 - 936 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 70227$, $T_{729} := 1377^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 3327, 3329\}$ or $E := \{2237, 2238, \dots, 2964, 2965\}$
7. **(936, 2623, 2785)** $\Rightarrow 2785 - 936 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 160003$, $T_{1849} := 2623^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 5567, 5569\}$ or $E := \{2797, 2798, \dots, 4644, 4645\}$
8. **(936, 6048, 6120)** $\Rightarrow 6120 - 936 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 508032$, $T_{5184} := 6048^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 12237, 12239\}$
9. **(936, 13673, 13705)** $\Rightarrow 13705 - 936 = 113^2$, $S_{113 \times 113} := 1654433$, $T_{12769} := 13673^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 27407, 27409\}$ or $E := \{8257, 8258, \dots, 21024, 21025\}$
10. **(936, 24327, 24345)** $\Rightarrow 24345 - 936 = 153^2$, $S_{153 \times 153} := 3867993$, $T_{23409} := 24327^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 48687, 48689\}$ or $E := \{13577, 13578, \dots, 36984, 36985\}$
11. **(936, 54752, 54760)** $\Rightarrow 54760 - 936 = 232^2$, $S_{232 \times 232} := 12921472$, $T_{53824} := 54752^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 109517, 109519\}$
12. **(936, 219023, 219025)** $\Rightarrow 219025 - 936 = 467^2$, $S_{467 \times 467} := 102721787$, $T_{218089} := 219023^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 438047, 438049\}$ or $E := \{110917, 110918, \dots, 329004, 329005\}$

■ Number 937

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$937^2 + 438984^2 := 438985^2$$

■ Number 938

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$938^2 + 3216^2 := 3350^2$$

$$938^2 + 4440^2 := 4538^2$$

$$938^2 + 31416^2 := 31430^2$$

$$938^2 + 219960^2 := 219962^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(938, 4440, 4538)** $\Rightarrow 4538 - 938 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 328560$, $T_{3600} := 4440^2$,
 $E := \{1877, 1879, \dots, 9073, 9075\}$

2. **(938, 219960, 219962)** $\Rightarrow 219962 - 938 = 468^2$, $S_{468 \times 468} := 103381200$, $T_{219024} := 219960^2$,
 $E := \{1877, 1879, \dots, 439921, 439923\}$

■ Number 939

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 939^2 + 1252^2 := 1565^2 & 939^2 + 146952^2 := 146955^2 \\ 939^2 + 48980^2 := 48989^2 & 939^2 + 440860^2 := 440861^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(939, 48980, 48989)** $\Rightarrow 48989 - 48980 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 293907$, $T_9 := 939^2$,
 $E := \{97961, 97963, \dots, 97975, 97977\}$ or $E := \{97965, 97966, \dots, 97972, 97973\}$

■ Number 940

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll} 940^2 + 987^2 := 1363^2 & 940^2 + 4653^2 := 4747^2 & 940^2 + 44175^2 := 44185^2 \\ 940^2 + 2109^2 := 2309^2 & 940^2 + 8811^2 := 8861^2 & 940^2 + 55221^2 := 55229^2 \\ 940^2 + 2256^2 := 2444^2 & 940^2 + 11025^2 := 11065^2 & 940^2 + 110448^2 := 110452^2 \\ 940^2 + 4368^2 := 4468^2 & 940^2 + 22080^2 := 22100^2 & 940^2 + 220899^2 := 220901^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(940, 4368, 4468)** $\Rightarrow 4468 - 4368 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 88360$, $T_{100} := 940^2$,
 $E := \{8737, 8739, \dots, 8933, 8935\}$
2. **(940, 2109, 2309)** $\Rightarrow 2309 - 940 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 120213$, $T_{1369} := 2109^2$,
 $E := \{1881, 1883, \dots, 4615, 4617\}$ or $E := \{2565, 2566, \dots, 3932, 3933\}$
3. **(940, 8811, 8861)** $\Rightarrow 8861 - 940 = 89^2$, $S_{89 \times 89} := 872289$, $T_{7921} := 8811^2$,
 $E := \{1881, 1883, \dots, 17719, 17721\}$ or $E := \{5841, 5842, \dots, 13760, 13761\}$
4. **(940, 55221, 55229)** $\Rightarrow 55229 - 940 = 233^2$, $S_{233 \times 233} := 13087377$, $T_{54289} := 55221^2$,
 $E := \{1881, 1883, \dots, 110455, 110457\}$ or $E := \{29025, 29026, \dots, 83312, 83313\}$
5. **(940, 220899, 220901)** $\Rightarrow 220901 - 940 = 469^2$, $S_{469 \times 469} := 104043429$, $T_{219961} := 220899^2$,
 $E := \{1881, 1883, \dots, 441799, 441801\}$ or $E := \{111861, 111862, \dots, 331820, 331821\}$

■ Number 941

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$941^2 + 442740^2 := 442741^2$$

■ Number 942

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$942^2 + 1256^2 := 1570^2$$

$$942^2 + 24640^2 := 24658^2$$

$$942^2 + 73944^2 := 73950^2$$

$$942^2 + 221840^2 := 221842^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(942, 24640, 24658)** $\Rightarrow 24658 - 942 = 154^2$, $S_{154 \times 154} := 3942400$, $T_{23716} := 24640^2$,
 $E := \{1885, 1887, \dots, 49313, 49315\}$

2. **(942, 221840, 221842)** $\Rightarrow 221842 - 942 = 470^2$, $S_{470 \times 470} := 104708480$, $T_{220900} := 221840^2$,
 $E := \{1885, 1887, \dots, 443681, 443683\}$

■ Number 943

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$943^2 + 10824^2 := 10865^2$$

$$943^2 + 19320^2 := 19343^2$$

$$943^2 + 444624^2 := 444625^2$$

■ Number 944

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$944^2 + 1770^2 := 2006^2$$

$$944^2 + 3417^2 := 3545^2$$

$$944^2 + 3717^2 := 3835^2$$

$$944^2 + 6930^2 := 6994^2$$

$$944^2 + 13908^2 := 13940^2$$

$$944^2 + 27840^2 := 27856^2$$

$$944^2 + 55692^2 := 55700^2$$

$$944^2 + 111390^2 := 111394^2$$

$$944^2 + 222783^2 := 222785^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(944, 27840, 27856)** $\Rightarrow 27856 - 27840 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 222784$, $T_{16} := 944^2$,
 $E := \{55681, 55683, \dots, 55709, 55711\}$
2. **(944, 6930, 6994)** $\Rightarrow 6994 - 6930 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 111392$, $T_{64} := 944^2$,
 $E := \{13861, 13863, \dots, 13985, 13987\}$
3. **(944, 3417, 3545)** $\Rightarrow 3545 - 944 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 228939$, $T_{2601} := 3417^2$,
 $E := \{1889, 1891, \dots, 7087, 7089\}$ or $E := \{3189, 3190, \dots, 5788, 5789\}$
4. **(944, 13908, 13940)** $\Rightarrow 13940 - 944 = 114^2$, $S_{114 \times 114} := 1696776$, $T_{12996} := 13908^2$,
 $E := \{1889, 1891, \dots, 27877, 27879\}$
5. **(944, 55692, 55700)** $\Rightarrow 55700 - 944 = 234^2$, $S_{234 \times 234} := 13254696$, $T_{54756} := 55692^2$,
 $E := \{1889, 1891, \dots, 111397, 111399\}$
6. **(944, 222783, 222785)** $\Rightarrow 222785 - 944 = 471^2$, $S_{471 \times 471} := 105376359$, $T_{221841} := 222783^2$,
 $E := \{1889, 1891, \dots, 445567, 445569\}$ or $E := \{112809, 112810, \dots, 334648, 334649\}$

■ Number 945

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$945^2 + 1260^2 := 1575^2$$

$$945^2 + 1700^2 := 1945^2$$

$$945^2 + 1716^2 := 1959^2$$

$$945^2 + 1872^2 := 2097^2$$

$$945^2 + 2268^2 := 2457^2$$

$$945^2 + 2464^2 := 2639^2$$

$$945^2 + 2964^2 := 3111^2$$

$$945^2 + 3240^2 := 3375^2$$

$$945^2 + 4200^2 := 4305^2$$

$$945^2 + 5472^2 := 5553^2$$

$$945^2 + 5916^2 := 5991^2$$

$$945^2 + 7056^2 := 7119^2$$

$$945^2 + 9088^2 := 9137^2$$

$$945^2 + 9900^2 := 9945^2$$

$$945^2 + 12740^2 := 12775^2$$

$$945^2 + 16524^2 := 16551^2$$

$$945^2 + 17848^2 := 17873^2$$

$$945^2 + 21252^2 := 21273^2$$

$$945^2 + 29760^2 := 29775^2$$

$$945^2 + 49608^2 := 49617^2$$

$$945^2 + 63784^2 := 63791^2$$

$$945^2 + 89300^2 := 89305^2$$

$$946^2 + 20328^2 := 20350^2$$

$$945^2 + 148836^2 := 148839^2$$

$$945^2 + 446512^2 := 446513^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(945, 49608, 49617)** $\Rightarrow 49617 - 49608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 297675$, $T_9 := 945^2$,
 $E := \{99217, 99219, \dots, 99231, 99233\}$ or $E := \{99221, 99222, \dots, 99228, 99229\}$
2. **(945, 17848, 17873)** $\Rightarrow 17873 - 17848 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 178605$, $T_{25} := 945^2$,
 $E := \{35697, 35699, \dots, 35743, 35745\}$ or $E := \{35709, 35710, \dots, 35732, 35733\}$
3. **(945, 9088, 9137)** $\Rightarrow 9137 - 9088 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 127575$, $T_{49} := 945^2$,
 $E := \{18177, 18179, \dots, 18271, 18273\}$ or $E := \{18201, 18202, \dots, 18248, 18249\}$

4. **(945, 5472, 5553)** $\Rightarrow 5553 - 5472 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 99225$, $T_{81} := 945^2$,
 $E := \{10945, 10947, \dots, 11103, 11105\}$ or $E := \{10985, 10986, \dots, 11064, 11065\}$
5. **(945, 1872, 2097)** $\Rightarrow 2097 - 1872 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 59535$, $T_{225} := 945^2$,
 $E := \{3745, 3747, \dots, 4191, 4193\}$ or $E := \{3857, 3858, \dots, 4080, 4081\}$

■ Number 946

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 946^2 + 1728^2 &:= 1970^2 \\ 946^2 + 5160^2 &:= 5246^2 \\ 946^2 + 223728^2 &:= 223730^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(946, 1728, 1970)** $\Rightarrow 1970 - 946 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 93312$, $T_{1024} := 1728^2$,
 $E := \{1893, 1895, \dots, 3937, 3939\}$
2. **(946, 223728, 223730)** $\Rightarrow 223730 - 946 = 472^2$, $S_{472 \times 472} := 106047072$, $T_{222784} := 223728^2$,
 $E := \{1893, 1895, \dots, 447457, 447459\}$

■ Number 947

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$947^2 + 448404^2 := 448405^2$$

■ Number 948

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$948^2 + 1264^2 := 1580^2$	$948^2 + 18711^2 := 18735^2$	$948^2 + 74889^2 := 74895^2$
$948^2 + 2765^2 := 2923^2$	$948^2 + 24955^2 := 24973^2$	$948^2 + 112336^2 := 112340^2$
$948^2 + 6205^2 := 6277^2$	$948^2 + 37440^2 := 37452^2$	$948^2 + 224675^2 := 224677^2$
$948^2 + 12464^2 := 12500^2$	$948^2 + 56165^2 := 56173^2$	

(b) Magic Square

1. **(948, 12464, 12500)** $\Rightarrow 12500 - 12464 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 149784$, $T_{36} := 948^2$,
 $E := \{24929, 24931, \dots, 24997, 24999\}$
2. **(948, 6205, 6277)** $\Rightarrow 6277 - 948 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 527425$, $T_{5329} := 6205^2$,
 $E := \{1897, 1899, \dots, 12551, 12553\}$ or $E := \{4561, 4562, \dots, 9888, 9889\}$
3. **(948, 24955, 24973)** $\Rightarrow 24973 - 948 = 155^2$, $S_{155 \times 155} := 4017755$, $T_{24025} := 24955^2$,
 $E := \{1897, 1899, \dots, 49943, 49945\}$ or $E := \{13909, 13910, \dots, 37932, 37933\}$
4. **(948, 56165, 56173)** $\Rightarrow 56173 - 948 = 235^2$, $S_{235 \times 235} := 13423435$, $T_{55225} := 56165^2$,
 $E := \{1897, 1899, \dots, 112343, 112345\}$ or $E := \{29509, 29510, \dots, 84732, 84733\}$
5. **(948, 224675, 224677)** $\Rightarrow 224677 - 948 = 473^2$, $S_{473 \times 473} := 106720625$, $T_{223729} := 224675^2$,
 $E := \{1897, 1899, \dots, 449351, 449353\}$ or $E := \{113761, 113762, \dots, 337488, 337489\}$

■ Number 949

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$949^2 + 2580^2 := 2749^2$$

$$949^2 + 6132^2 := 6205^2$$

$$949^2 + 34632^2 := 34645^2$$

$$949^2 + 450300^2 := 450301^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(949, 2580, 2749)** $\Rightarrow 2749 - 2580 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 69277$, $T_{169} := 949^2$,
 $E := \{5161, 5163, \dots, 5495, 5497\}$ or $E := \{5245, 5246, \dots, 5412, 5413\}$

■ Number 950

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$950^2 + 1680^2 := 1930^2$$

$$950^2 + 2280^2 := 2470^2$$

$$950^2 + 9000^2 := 9050^2$$

$$950^2 + 11856^2 := 11894^2$$

$$950^2 + 45120^2 := 45130^2$$

$$950^2 + 225624^2 := 225626^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(950, 9000, 9050)** $\Rightarrow 9050 - 950 = 90^2$, $S_{90 \times 90} := 900000$, $T_{8100} := 9000^2$,
 $E := \{1901, 1903, \dots, 18097, 18099\}$
2. **(950, 225624, 225626)** $\Rightarrow 225626 - 950 = 474^2$, $S_{474 \times 474} := 107397024$, $T_{224676} := 225624^2$,
 $E := \{1901, 1903, \dots, 451249, 451251\}$

■ Number 951

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$951^2 + 1268^2 := 1585^2$$

$$951^2 + 50240^2 := 50249^2$$

$$951^2 + 150732^2 := 150735^2$$

$$951^2 + 452200^2 := 452201^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(951, 50240, 50249)** $\Rightarrow 50249 - 50240 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 301467$, $T_9 := 951^2$,
 $E := \{100481, 100483, \dots, 100495, 100497\}$ or $E := \{100485, 100486, \dots, 100492, 100493\}$

■ Number 952

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$952^2 + 960^2 := 1352^2$$

$$952^2 + 1530^2 := 1802^2$$

$$952^2 + 1785^2 := 2023^2$$

$$952^2 + 1911^2 := 2135^2$$

$$952^2 + 2214^2 := 2410^2$$

$$952^2 + 3264^2 := 3400^2$$

$$952^2 + 3990^2 := 4102^2$$

$$952^2 + 4575^2 := 4673^2$$

$$952^2 + 6630^2 := 6698^2$$

$$952^2 + 8064^2 := 8120^2$$

$$952^2 + 13311^2 := 13345^2$$

$$952^2 + 14145^2 := 14177^2$$

$$952^2 + 16170^2 := 16198^2$$

$$952^2 + 28314^2 := 28330^2$$

$$952^2 + 32361^2 := 32375^2$$

$$952^2 + 56640^2 := 56648^2$$

$$952^2 + 113286^2 := 113290^2$$

$$952^2 + 226575^2 := 226577^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(952, 28314, 28330)** $\Rightarrow 28330 - 28314 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 226576$, $T_{16} := 952^2$,
 $E := \{56629, 56631, \dots, 56657, 56659\}$
2. **(952, 2214, 2410)** $\Rightarrow 2410 - 2214 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 64736$, $T_{196} := 952^2$,
 $E := \{4429, 4431, \dots, 4817, 4819\}$
3. **(952, 960, 1352)** $\Rightarrow 1352 - 952 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 46080$, $T_{400} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 2701, 2703\}$
4. **(952, 4575, 4673)** $\Rightarrow 4673 - 952 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 343125$, $T_{3721} := 4575^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 9343, 9345\}$ or $E := \{3765, 3766, \dots, 7484, 7485\}$
5. **(952, 14145, 14177)** $\Rightarrow 14177 - 952 = 115^2$, $S_{115 \times 115} := 1739835$, $T_{13225} := 14145^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 28351, 28353\}$ or $E := \{8517, 8518, \dots, 21740, 21741\}$
6. **(952, 56640, 56648)** $\Rightarrow 56648 - 952 = 236^2$, $S_{236 \times 236} := 13593600$, $T_{55696} := 56640^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 113293, 113295\}$
7. **(952, 226575, 226577)** $\Rightarrow 226577 - 952 = 475^2$, $S_{475 \times 475} := 108076275$, $T_{225625} := 226575^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 453151, 453153\}$ or $E := \{114717, 114718, \dots, 340340, 340341\}$

■ Number 953

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$953^2 + 454104^2 := 454105^2$$

■ Number 954

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$954^2 + 1272^2 := 1590^2$$

$$954^2 + 2728^2 := 2890^2$$

$$954^2 + 4240^2 := 4346^2$$

$$954^2 + 8400^2 := 8454^2$$

$$954^2 + 25272^2 := 25290^2$$

$$954^2 + 75840^2 := 75846^2$$

$$954^2 + 227528^2 := 227530^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(954, 2728, 2890)** $\Rightarrow 2890 - 954 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 169136$, $T_{1936} := 2728^2$,
 $E := \{1909, 1911, \dots, 5777, 5779\}$

2. **(954, 25272, 25290)** $\Rightarrow 25290 - 954 = 156^2$, $S_{156 \times 156} := 4094064$, $T_{24336} := 25272^2$,
 $E := \{1909, 1911, \dots, 50577, 50579\}$

3. **(954, 227528, 227530)** $\Rightarrow 227530 - 954 = 476^2$, $S_{476 \times 476} := 108758384$, $T_{226576} := 227528^2$,
 $E := \{1909, 1911, \dots, 455057, 455059\}$

■ Number 955

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$955^2 + 2292^2 := 2483^2$$

$$955^2 + 18228^2 := 18253^2$$

$$955^2 + 91200^2 := 91205^2$$

$$955^2 + 456012^2 := 456013^2$$

(b) Magic Square

• **(955, 18228, 18253)** $\Rightarrow 18253 - 18228 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 182405$, $T_{25} := 955^2$,
 $E := \{36457, 36459, \dots, 36503, 36505\}$ or $E := \{36469, 36470, \dots, 36492, 36493\}$

■ Number 956

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$956^2 + 57117^2 := 57125^2$$

$$956^2 + 114240^2 := 114244^2$$

$$956^2 + 228483^2 := 228485^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(956, 57117, 57125)** $\Rightarrow 57125 - 956 = 237^2$, $S_{237 \times 237} := 13765197$, $T_{56169} := 57117^2$,
 $E := \{1913, 1915, \dots, 114247, 114249\}$ or $E := \{29997, 29998, \dots, 86164, 86165\}$

2. **(956, 228483, 228485)** $\Rightarrow 228485 - 956 = 477^2$, $S_{477 \times 477} := 109443357$, $T_{227529} := 228483^2$,
 $E := \{1913, 1915, \dots, 456967, 456969\}$ or $E := \{115677, 115678, \dots, 343204, 343205\}$

■ Number 957

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$957^2 + 1080^2 := 1443^2$$

$$957^2 + 1276^2 := 1595^2$$

$$957^2 + 1624^2 := 1885^2$$

$$957^2 + 3724^2 := 3845^2$$

$$957^2 + 4576^2 := 4675^2$$

$$957^2 + 5220^2 := 5307^2$$

$$957^2 + 13860^2 := 13893^2$$

$$957^2 + 15776^2 := 15805^2$$

$$957^2 + 41624^2 := 41635^2$$

$$957^2 + 50876^2 := 50885^2$$

$$957^2 + 152640^2 := 152643^2$$

$$957^2 + 457924^2 := 457925^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(957, 50876, 50885)** $\Rightarrow 50885 - 50876 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 305283$, $T_9 := 957^2$,
 $E := \{101753, 101755, \dots, 101767, 101769\}$ or $E := \{101757, 101758, \dots, 101764, 101765\}$

2. **(957, 3724, 3845)** $\Rightarrow 3845 - 3724 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 83259$, $T_{121} := 957^2$,
 $E := \{7449, 7451, \dots, 7687, 7689\}$ or $E := \{7509, 7510, \dots, 7628, 7629\}$

■ Number 958

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$958^2 + 229440^2 := 229442^2$$

(b) **Magic Square**

- **(958, 229440, 229442)** $\Rightarrow 229442 - 958 = 478^2$, $S_{478 \times 478} := 110131200$, $T_{228484} := 229440^2$,
 $E := \{1917, 1919, \dots, 458881, 458883\}$

■ Number 959

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$959^2 + 3288^2 := 3425^2$$

$$959^2 + 9360^2 := 9409^2$$

$$959^2 + 65688^2 := 65695^2$$

$$959^2 + 459840^2 := 459841^2$$

(b) **Magic Square**

- **(959, 9360, 9409)** $\Rightarrow 9409 - 9360 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 131383$, $T_{49} := 959^2$,
 $E := \{18721, 18723, \dots, 18815, 18817\}$ or $E := \{18745, 18746, \dots, 18792, 18793\}$

■ Number 960

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$960^2 + 1008^2 := 1392^2$$

$$960^2 + 1100^2 := 1460^2$$

$$960^2 + 1280^2 := 1600^2$$

$$960^2 + 1386^2 := 1686^2$$

$$960^2 + 1456^2 := 1744^2$$

$$960^2 + 1672^2 := 1928^2$$

$$960^2 + 1800^2 := 2040^2$$

$$960^2 + 2204^2 := 2404^2$$

$$960^2 + 2304^2 := 2496^2$$

$$960^2 + 2470^2 := 2650^2$$

$$960^2 + 2800^2 := 2960^2$$

$$960^2 + 2997^2 := 3147^2$$

$$960^2 + 3128^2 := 3272^2$$

$$960^2 + 3536^2 := 3664^2$$

$$960^2 + 3780^2 := 3900^2$$

$$960^2 + 4558^2 := 4658^2$$

$$960^2 + 4752^2 := 4848^2$$

$$960^2 + 5075^2 := 5165^2$$

$$960^2 + 5720^2 := 5800^2$$

$$960^2 + 6364^2 := 6436^2$$

$$960^2 + 7168^2 := 7232^2$$

$$960^2 + 7650^2 := 7710^2$$

$$960^2 + 9191^2 := 9241^2$$

$$960^2 + 9576^2 := 9624^2$$

$$960^2 + 11500^2 := 11540^2$$

$$960^2 + 12782^2 := 12818^2$$

$$960^2 + 14384^2 := 14416^2$$

$$960^2 + 15345^2 := 15375^2$$

$$960^2 + 19188^2 := 19212^2$$

$$960^2 + 23030^2 := 23050^2$$

$$960^2 + 25591^2 := 25609^2$$

$$960^2 + 28792^2 := 28808^2$$

$$960^2 + 38394^2 := 38406^2$$

$$960^2 + 46075^2 := 46085^2$$

$$960^2 + 57596^2 := 57604^2$$

$$960^2 + 76797^2 := 76803^2$$

$$960^2 + 115198^2 := 115202^2$$

$$960^2 + 230399^2 := 230401^2$$

(b) **Magic Square**

1. **(960, 28792, 28808)** $\Rightarrow 28808 - 28792 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 230400$, $T_{16} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{57585, 57587, \dots, 57613, 57615\}$

2. **(960, 12782, 12818)** $\Rightarrow 12818 - 12782 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 153600$, $T_{36} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{25565, 25567, \dots, 25633, 25635\}$
3. **(960, 7168, 7232)** $\Rightarrow 7232 - 7168 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 115200$, $T_{64} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{14337, 14339, \dots, 14461, 14463\}$
4. **(960, 4558, 4658)** $\Rightarrow 4658 - 4558 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 92160$, $T_{100} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{9117, 9119, \dots, 9313, 9315\}$
5. **(960, 3128, 3272)** $\Rightarrow 3272 - 3128 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 76800$, $T_{144} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{6257, 6259, \dots, 6541, 6543\}$
6. **(960, 1672, 1928)** $\Rightarrow 1928 - 1672 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 57600$, $T_{256} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{3345, 3347, \dots, 3853, 3855\}$
7. **(960, 1456, 1744)** $\Rightarrow 1744 - 960 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 75712$, $T_{784} := 1456^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 3485, 3487\}$
8. **(960, 2204, 2404)** $\Rightarrow 2404 - 960 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 127832$, $T_{1444} := 2204^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 4805, 4807\}$
9. **(960, 3536, 3664)** $\Rightarrow 3664 - 960 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 240448$, $T_{2704} := 3536^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 7325, 7327\}$
10. **(960, 6364, 6436)** $\Rightarrow 6436 - 960 = 74^2$, $S_{74 \times 74} := 547304$, $T_{5476} := 6364^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 12869, 12871\}$
11. **(960, 9191, 9241)** $\Rightarrow 9241 - 960 = 91^2$, $S_{91 \times 91} := 928291$, $T_{8281} := 9191^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 18479, 18481\}$ or $E := \{6061, 6062, \dots, 14340, 14341\}$
12. **(960, 14384, 14416)** $\Rightarrow 14416 - 960 = 116^2$, $S_{116 \times 116} := 1783616$, $T_{13456} := 14384^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 28829, 28831\}$
13. **(960, 25591, 25609)** $\Rightarrow 25609 - 960 = 157^2$, $S_{157 \times 157} := 4171333$, $T_{24649} := 25591^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 51215, 51217\}$ or $E := \{14245, 14246, \dots, 38892, 38893\}$
14. **(960, 57596, 57604)** $\Rightarrow 57604 - 960 = 238^2$, $S_{238 \times 238} := 13938232$, $T_{56644} := 57596^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 115205, 115207\}$
15. **(960, 230399, 230401)** $\Rightarrow 230401 - 960 = 479^2$, $S_{479 \times 479} := 110821919$, $T_{229441} := 230399^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 460799, 460801\}$ or $E := \{116641, 116642, \dots, 346080, 346081\}$

■ Number 961

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$961^2 + 14880^2 := 14911^2$$

$$961^2 + 461760^2 := 461761^2$$

■ Number 962

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$962^2 + 1200^2 := 1538^2$$

$$962^2 + 6216^2 := 6290^2$$

$$962^2 + 17784^2 := 17810^2$$

$$962^2 + 231360^2 := 231362^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(962, 1200, 1538)** $\Rightarrow 1538 - 962 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 60000$, $T_{576} := 1200^2$,
 $E := \{1925, 1927, \dots, 3073, 3075\}$

2. **(962, 231360, 231362)** $\Rightarrow 231362 - 962 = 480^2$, $S_{480 \times 480} := 111515520$, $T_{230400} := 231360^2$,
 $E := \{1925, 1927, \dots, 462721, 462723\}$

■ Number 963

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$963^2 + 1284^2 := 1605^2$$

$$963^2 + 4280^2 := 4387^2$$

$$963^2 + 5684^2 := 5765^2$$

$$963^2 + 17160^2 := 17187^2$$

$$963^2 + 51516^2 := 51525^2$$

$$963^2 + 154560^2 := 154563^2$$

$$963^2 + 463684^2 := 463685^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(963, 51516, 51525)** $\Rightarrow 51525 - 51516 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 309123$, $T_9 := 963^2$,
 $E := \{103033, 103035, \dots, 103047, 103049\}$ or $E := \{103037, 103038, \dots, 103044, 103045\}$

2. **(963, 5684, 5765)** $\Rightarrow 5765 - 5684 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 103041$, $T_{81} := 963^2$,
 $E := \{11369, 11371, \dots, 11527, 11529\}$ or $E := \{11409, 11410, \dots, 11488, 11489\}$

■ Number 964

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$964^2 + 58077^2 := 58085^2$$

$$964^2 + 116160^2 := 116164^2$$

$$964^2 + 232323^2 := 232325^2$$

(b) **Magic Square**

1. **(964, 58077, 58085)** $\Rightarrow 58085 - 964 = 239^2$, $S_{239 \times 239} := 14112711$, $T_{57121} := 58077^2$,
 $E := \{1929, 1931, \dots, 116167, 116169\}$ or $E := \{30489, 30490, \dots, 87608, 87609\}$
2. **(964, 232323, 232325)** $\Rightarrow 232325 - 964 = 481^2$, $S_{481 \times 481} := 112212009$, $T_{231361} := 232323^2$,
 $E := \{1929, 1931, \dots, 464647, 464649\}$ or $E := \{117609, 117610, \dots, 348968, 348969\}$

■ Number 965

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll} 965^2 + 2316^2 := 2509^2 & 965^2 + 93120^2 := 93125^2 \\ 965^2 + 18612^2 := 18637^2 & 965^2 + 465612^2 := 465613^2 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Square**

- **(965, 18612, 18637)** $\Rightarrow 18637 - 18612 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 186245$, $T_{25} := 965^2$,
 $E := \{37225, 37227, \dots, 37271, 37273\}$ or $E := \{37237, 37238, \dots, 37260, 37261\}$

■ Number 966

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{lll} 966^2 + 1288^2 := 1610^2 & 966^2 + 4712^2 := 4810^2 & 966^2 + 33320^2 := 33334^2 \\ 966^2 + 1440^2 := 1734^2 & 966^2 + 10120^2 := 10166^2 & 966^2 + 77760^2 := 77766^2 \\ 966^2 + 3312^2 := 3450^2 & 966^2 + 11088^2 := 11130^2 & 966^2 + 233288^2 := 233290^2 \\ 966^2 + 3640^2 := 3766^2 & 966^2 + 25912^2 := 25930^2 & \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Square**

1. **(966, 4712, 4810)** $\Rightarrow 4810 - 966 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 358112$, $T_{3844} := 4712^2$,
 $E := \{1933, 1935, \dots, 9617, 9619\}$
2. **(966, 25912, 25930)** $\Rightarrow 25930 - 966 = 158^2$, $S_{158 \times 158} := 4249568$, $T_{24964} := 25912^2$,
 $E := \{1933, 1935, \dots, 51857, 51859\}$
3. **(966, 233288, 233290)** $\Rightarrow 233290 - 966 = 482^2$, $S_{482 \times 482} := 112911392$, $T_{232324} := 233288^2$,
 $E := \{1933, 1935, \dots, 466577, 466579\}$

■ Number 967

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$967^2 + 467544^2 := 467545^2$$

■ Number 968

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$968^2 + 1155^2 := 1507^2$$

$$968^2 + 1815^2 := 2057^2$$

$$968^2 + 2574^2 := 2750^2$$

$$968^2 + 5280^2 := 5368^2$$

$$968^2 + 10626^2 := 10670^2$$

$$968^2 + 14625^2 := 14657^2$$

$$968^2 + 21285^2 := 21307^2$$

$$968^2 + 29274^2 := 29290^2$$

$$968^2 + 58560^2 := 58568^2$$

$$968^2 + 117126^2 := 117130^2$$

$$968^2 + 234255^2 := 234257^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(968, 29274, 29290)** $\Rightarrow 29290 - 29274 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 234256$, $T_{16} := 968^2$,
 $E := \{58549, 58551, \dots, 58577, 58579\}$
2. **(968, 1815, 2057)** $\Rightarrow 2057 - 968 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 99825$, $T_{1089} := 1815^2$,
 $E := \{1937, 1939, \dots, 4111, 4113\}$ or $E := \{2481, 2482, \dots, 3568, 3569\}$
3. **(968, 14625, 14657)** $\Rightarrow 14657 - 968 = 117^2$, $S_{117 \times 117} := 1828125$, $T_{13689} := 14625^2$,
 $E := \{1937, 1939, \dots, 29311, 29313\}$ or $E := \{8781, 8782, \dots, 22468, 22469\}$
4. **(968, 58560, 58568)** $\Rightarrow 58568 - 968 = 240^2$, $S_{240 \times 240} := 14288640$, $T_{57600} := 58560^2$,
 $E := \{1937, 1939, \dots, 117133, 117135\}$
5. **(968, 234255, 234257)** $\Rightarrow 234257 - 968 = 483^2$, $S_{483 \times 483} := 113613675$, $T_{233289} := 234255^2$,
 $E := \{1937, 1939, \dots, 468511, 468513\}$ or $E := \{118581, 118582, \dots, 351868, 351869\}$

■ Number 969

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$969^2 + 1120^2 := 1481^2$$

$$969^2 + 1292^2 := 1615^2$$

$$969^2 + 1480^2 := 1769^2$$

$$969^2 + 2660^2 := 2831^2$$

$$969^2 + 2992^2 := 3145^2$$

$$969^2 + 8208^2 := 8265^2$$

$$969^2 + 9180^2 := 9231^2$$

$$969^2 + 24700^2 := 24719^2$$

$$969^2 + 27608^2 := 27625^2$$

$$969^2 + 52160^2 := 52169^2$$

$$969^2 + 156492^2 := 156495^2$$

$$969^2 + 469480^2 := 469481^2$$

(b) **Magic Square**

1. **(969, 52160, 52169)** $\Rightarrow 52169 - 52160 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 312987$, $T_9 := 969^2$,
 $E := \{104321, 104323, \dots, 104335, 104337\}$ or $E := \{104325, 104326, \dots, 104332, 104333\}$
2. **(969, 1480, 1769)** $\Rightarrow 1769 - 1480 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 55233$, $T_{289} := 969^2$,
 $E := \{2961, 2963, \dots, 3535, 3537\}$ or $E := \{3105, 3106, \dots, 3392, 3393\}$
3. **(969, 1120, 1481)** $\Rightarrow 1481 - 1120 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 49419$, $T_{361} := 969^2$,
 $E := \{2241, 2243, \dots, 2959, 2961\}$ or $E := \{2421, 2422, \dots, 2780, 2781\}$

■ **Number 970**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 970^2 + 2328^2 := 2522^2 & 970^2 + 47040^2 := 47050^2 \\
 970^2 + 9384^2 := 9434^2 & 970^2 + 235224^2 := 235226^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) **Magic Square**

1. **(970, 9384, 9434)** $\Rightarrow 9434 - 970 = 92^2$, $S_{92 \times 92} := 957168$, $T_{8464} := 9384^2$,
 $E := \{1941, 1943, \dots, 18865, 18867\}$
2. **(970, 235224, 235226)** $\Rightarrow 235226 - 970 = 484^2$, $S_{484 \times 484} := 114318864$, $T_{234256} := 235224^2$,
 $E := \{1941, 1943, \dots, 470449, 470451\}$

■ **Number 971**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$971^2 + 471420^2 := 471421^2$$

■ **Number 972**

(a) **Pythagorean Triples**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 972^2 + 1296^2 := 1620^2 \\
 972^2 + 2079^2 := 2295^2 \\
 972^2 + 2835^2 := 2997^2 \\
 972^2 + 4320^2 := 4428^2 \\
 972^2 + 6525^2 := 6597^2
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 972^2 + 8721^2 := 8775^2 & \\
 972^2 + 13104^2 := 13140^2 & 972^2 + 59045^2 := 59053^2 \\
 972^2 + 19671^2 := 19695^2 & 972^2 + 78729^2 := 78735^2 \\
 972^2 + 26235^2 := 26253^2 & 972^2 + 118096^2 := 118100^2 \\
 972^2 + 39360^2 := 39372^2 & 972^2 + 236195^2 := 236197^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(972, 13104, 13140)** $\Rightarrow 13140 - 13104 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 157464$, $T_{36} := 972^2$,
 $E := \{26209, 26211, \dots, 26277, 26279\}$
2. **(972, 1296, 1620)** $\Rightarrow 1620 - 1296 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 52488$, $T_{324} := 972^2$,
 $E := \{2593, 2595, \dots, 3237, 3239\}$
3. **(972, 2835, 2997)** $\Rightarrow 2997 - 972 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 178605$, $T_{2025} := 2835^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 5991, 5993\}$ or $E := \{2957, 2958, \dots, 4980, 4981\}$
4. **(972, 6525, 6597)** $\Rightarrow 6597 - 972 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 567675$, $T_{5625} := 6525^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 13191, 13193\}$ or $E := \{4757, 4758, \dots, 10380, 10381\}$
5. **(972, 26235, 26253)** $\Rightarrow 26253 - 972 = 159^2$, $S_{159 \times 159} := 4328775$, $T_{25281} := 26235^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 52503, 52505\}$ or $E := \{14585, 14586, \dots, 39864, 39865\}$
6. **(972, 59045, 59053)** $\Rightarrow 59053 - 972 = 241^2$, $S_{241 \times 241} := 14466025$, $T_{58081} := 59045^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 118103, 118105\}$ or $E := \{30985, 30986, \dots, 89064, 89065\}$
7. **(972, 236195, 236197)** $\Rightarrow 236197 - 972 = 485^2$, $S_{485 \times 485} := 115026965$, $T_{235225} := 236195^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 472391, 472393\}$ or $E := \{119557, 119558, \dots, 354780, 354781\}$

■ Number 973

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 973^2 + 3336^2 := 3475^2 & 973^2 + 67620^2 := 67627^2 \\
 973^2 + 9636^2 := 9685^2 & 973^2 + 473364^2 := 473365^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(973, 9636, 9685)** $\Rightarrow 9685 - 9636 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 135247$, $T_{49} := 973^2$,
 $E := \{19273, 19275, \dots, 19367, 19369\}$ or $E := \{19297, 19298, \dots, 19344, 19345\}$

■ Number 974

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$974^2 + 237168^2 := 237170^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(974, 237168, 237170)** $\Rightarrow 237170 - 974 = 486^2$, $S_{486 \times 486} := 115737984$, $T_{236196} := 237168^2$,
 $E := \{1949, 1951, \dots, 474337, 474339\}$

■ Number 975

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$975^2 + 1080^2 := 1455^2$$

$$975^2 + 1300^2 := 1625^2$$

$$975^2 + 2000^2 := 2225^2$$

$$975^2 + 2340^2 := 2535^2$$

$$975^2 + 2728^2 := 2897^2$$

$$975^2 + 3740^2 := 3865^2$$

$$975^2 + 4004^2 := 4121^2$$

$$975^2 + 6300^2 := 6375^2$$

$$975^2 + 7280^2 := 7345^2$$

$$975^2 + 10540^2 := 10585^2$$

$$975^2 + 12168^2 := 12207^2$$

$$975^2 + 19000^2 := 19025^2$$

$$975^2 + 31680^2 := 31695^2$$

$$975^2 + 36556^2 := 36569^2$$

$$975^2 + 52808^2 := 52817^2$$

$$975^2 + 95060^2 := 95065^2$$

$$975^2 + 158436^2 := 158439^2$$

$$975^2 + 475312^2 := 475313^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(975, 52808, 52817)** $\Rightarrow 52817 - 52808 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 316875$, $T_9 := 975^2$,
 $E := \{105617, 105619, \dots, 105631, 105633\}$ or $E := \{105621, 105622, \dots, 105628, 105629\}$
2. **(975, 19000, 19025)** $\Rightarrow 19025 - 19000 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 190125$, $T_{25} := 975^2$,
 $E := \{38001, 38003, \dots, 38047, 38049\}$ or $E := \{38013, 38014, \dots, 38036, 38037\}$
3. **(975, 2728, 2897)** $\Rightarrow 2897 - 2728 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 73125$, $T_{169} := 975^2$,
 $E := \{5457, 5459, \dots, 5791, 5793\}$ or $E := \{5541, 5542, \dots, 5708, 5709\}$
4. **(975, 2000, 2225)** $\Rightarrow 2225 - 2000 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 63375$, $T_{225} := 975^2$,
 $E := \{4001, 4003, \dots, 4447, 4449\}$ or $E := \{4113, 4114, \dots, 4336, 4337\}$

■ Number 976

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$976^2 + 1830^2 := 2074^2$$

$$976^2 + 3657^2 := 3785^2$$

$$976^2 + 3843^2 := 3965^2$$

$$976^2 + 7410^2 := 7474^2$$

$$976^2 + 14868^2 := 14900^2$$

$$976^2 + 29760^2 := 29776^2$$

$$976^2 + 59532^2 := 59540^2$$

$$976^2 + 119070^2 := 119074^2$$

$$976^2 + 238143^2 := 238145^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(976, 29760, 29776)** $\Rightarrow 29776 - 29760 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 238144$, $T_{16} := 976^2$,
 $E := \{59521, 59523, \dots, 59549, 59551\}$
2. **(976, 7410, 7474)** $\Rightarrow 7474 - 7410 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 119072$, $T_{64} := 976^2$,
 $E := \{14821, 14823, \dots, 14945, 14947\}$
3. **(976, 3657, 3785)** $\Rightarrow 3785 - 976 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 252333$, $T_{2809} := 3657^2$,
 $E := \{1953, 1955, \dots, 7567, 7569\}$ or $E := \{3357, 3358, \dots, 6164, 6165\}$
4. **(976, 14868, 14900)** $\Rightarrow 14900 - 976 = 118^2$, $S_{118 \times 118} := 1873368$, $T_{13924} := 14868^2$,
 $E := \{1953, 1955, \dots, 29797, 29799\}$
5. **(976, 59532, 59540)** $\Rightarrow 59540 - 976 = 242^2$, $S_{242 \times 242} := 14644872$, $T_{58564} := 59532^2$,
 $E := \{1953, 1955, \dots, 119077, 119079\}$
6. **(976, 238143, 238145)** $\Rightarrow 238145 - 976 = 487^2$, $S_{487 \times 487} := 116451927$, $T_{237169} := 238143^2$,
 $E := \{1953, 1955, \dots, 476287, 476289\}$ or $E := \{120537, 120538, \dots, 357704, 357705\}$

■ Number 977

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$977^2 + 477264^2 := 477265^2$$

■ Number 978

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$978^2 + 1304^2 := 1630^2$$

$$978^2 + 26560^2 := 26578^2$$

$$978^2 + 79704^2 := 79710^2$$

$$978^2 + 239120^2 := 239122^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(978, 26560, 26578)** $\Rightarrow 26578 - 978 = 160^2$, $S_{160 \times 160} := 4408960$, $T_{25600} := 26560^2$,
 $E := \{1957, 1959, \dots, 53153, 53155\}$

2. **(978, 239120, 239122)** $\Rightarrow 239122 - 978 = 488^2$, $S_{488 \times 488} := 117168800$, $T_{238144} := 239120^2$,
 $E := \{1957, 1959, \dots, 478241, 478243\}$

■ Number 979

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 979^2 + 3900^2 := 4021^2 & 979^2 + 43560^2 := 43571^2 \\ 979^2 + 5340^2 := 5429^2 & 979^2 + 479220^2 := 479221^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(979, 3900, 4021)** $\Rightarrow 4021 - 3900 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 87131$, $T_{121} := 979^2$,
 $E := \{7801, 7803, \dots, 8039, 8041\}$ or $E := \{7861, 7862, \dots, 7980, 7981\}$

■ Number 980

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll} 980^2 + 1029^2 := 1421^2 & 980^2 + 4752^2 := 4852^2 & 980^2 + 17136^2 := 17164^2 \\ 980^2 + 1197^2 := 1547^2 & 980^2 + 4851^2 := 4949^2 & 980^2 + 24000^2 := 24020^2 \\ 980^2 + 1575^2 := 1855^2 & 980^2 + 6825^2 := 6895^2 & 980^2 + 34293^2 := 34307^2 \\ 980^2 + 2301^2 := 2501^2 & 980^2 + 8547^2 := 8603^2 & 980^2 + 48015^2 := 48025^2 \\ 980^2 + 2352^2 := 2548^2 & 980^2 + 9579^2 := 9629^2 & 980^2 + 60021^2 := 60029^2 \\ 980^2 + 3360^2 := 3500^2 & 980^2 + 11985^2 := 12025^2 & 980^2 + 120048^2 := 120052^2 \\ & & 980^2 + 240099^2 := 240101^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(980, 4752, 4852)** $\Rightarrow 4852 - 4752 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 96040$, $T_{100} := 980^2$,
 $E := \{9505, 9507, \dots, 9701, 9703\}$
2. **(980, 2352, 2548)** $\Rightarrow 2548 - 2352 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 68600$, $T_{196} := 980^2$,
 $E := \{4705, 4707, \dots, 5093, 5095\}$
3. **(980, 1029, 1421)** $\Rightarrow 1421 - 980 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 50421$, $T_{441} := 1029^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 2839, 2841\}$ or $E := \{2181, 2182, \dots, 2620, 2621\}$
4. **(980, 2301, 2501)** $\Rightarrow 2501 - 980 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 135759$, $T_{1521} := 2301^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 4999, 5001\}$ or $E := \{2721, 2722, \dots, 4240, 4241\}$

5. **(980, 4851, 4949)** $\Rightarrow 4949 - 980 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 373527$, $T_{3969} := 4851^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 9895, 9897\}$ or $E := \{3945, 3946, \dots, 7912, 7913\}$
6. **(980, 9579, 9629)** $\Rightarrow 9629 - 980 = 93^2$, $S_{93 \times 93} := 986637$, $T_{8649} := 9579^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 19255, 19257\}$ or $E := \{6285, 6286, \dots, 14932, 14933\}$
7. **(980, 60021, 60029)** $\Rightarrow 60029 - 980 = 243^2$, $S_{243 \times 243} := 14825187$, $T_{59049} := 60021^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 120055, 120057\}$ or $E := \{31485, 31486, \dots, 90532, 90533\}$
8. **(980, 240099, 240101)** $\Rightarrow 240101 - 980 = 489^2$, $S_{489 \times 489} := 117888609$, $T_{239121} := 240099^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 480199, 480201\}$ or $E := \{121521, 121522, \dots, 360640, 360641\}$

■ Number 981

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$981^2 + 1308^2 := 1635^2$$

$$981^2 + 4360^2 := 4469^2$$

$$981^2 + 5900^2 := 5981^2$$

$$981^2 + 17808^2 := 17835^2$$

$$981^2 + 53460^2 := 53469^2$$

$$981^2 + 160392^2 := 160395^2$$

$$981^2 + 481180^2 := 481181^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(981, 53460, 53469)** $\Rightarrow 53469 - 53460 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 320787$, $T_9 := 981^2$,
 $E := \{106921, 106923, \dots, 106935, 106937\}$ or $E := \{106925, 106926, \dots, 106932, 106933\}$
2. **(981, 5900, 5981)** $\Rightarrow 5981 - 5900 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 106929$, $T_{81} := 981^2$,
 $E := \{11801, 11803, \dots, 11959, 11961\}$ or $E := \{11841, 11842, \dots, 11920, 11921\}$

■ Number 982

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$982^2 + 241080^2 := 241082^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(982, 241080, 241082)** $\Rightarrow 241082 - 982 = 490^2$, $S_{490 \times 490} := 118611360$, $T_{240100} := 241080^2$,
 $E := \{1965, 1967, \dots, 482161, 482163\}$

■ Number 983

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$983^2 + 483144^2 := 483145^2$$

■ Number 984

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$984^2 + 1312^2 := 1640^2$$

$$984^2 + 1537^2 := 1825^2$$

$$984^2 + 1845^2 := 2091^2$$

$$984^2 + 2870^2 := 3034^2$$

$$984^2 + 3290^2 := 3434^2$$

$$984^2 + 4995^2 := 5091^2$$

$$984^2 + 5863^2 := 5945^2$$

$$984^2 + 6688^2 := 6760^2$$

$$984^2 + 10062^2 := 10110^2$$

$$984^2 + 13430^2 := 13466^2$$

$$984^2 + 15113^2 := 15145^2$$

$$984^2 + 20160^2 := 20184^2$$

$$984^2 + 26887^2 := 26905^2$$

$$984^2 + 30250^2 := 30266^2$$

$$984^2 + 40338^2 := 40350^2$$

$$984^2 + 60512^2 := 60520^2$$

$$984^2 + 80685^2 := 80691^2$$

$$984^2 + 121030^2 := 121034^2$$

$$984^2 + 242063^2 := 242065^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(984, 30250, 30266)** $\Rightarrow 30266 - 30250 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 242064$, $T_{16} := 984^2$,
 $E := \{60501, 60503, \dots, 60529, 60531\}$
2. **(984, 13430, 13466)** $\Rightarrow 13466 - 13430 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 161376$, $T_{36} := 984^2$,
 $E := \{26861, 26863, \dots, 26929, 26931\}$
3. **(984, 3290, 3434)** $\Rightarrow 3434 - 3290 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 80688$, $T_{144} := 984^2$,
 $E := \{6581, 6583, \dots, 6865, 6867\}$
4. **(984, 1537, 1825)** $\Rightarrow 1825 - 984 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 81461$, $T_{841} := 1537^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 3647, 3649\}$ or $E := \{2389, 2390, \dots, 3228, 3229\}$
5. **(984, 6688, 6760)** $\Rightarrow 6760 - 984 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 588544$, $T_{5776} := 6688^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 13517, 13519\}$
6. **(984, 15113, 15145)** $\Rightarrow 15145 - 984 = 119^2$, $S_{119 \times 119} := 1919351$, $T_{14161} := 15113^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 30287, 30289\}$ or $E := \{9049, 9050, \dots, 23208, 23209\}$
7. **(984, 26887, 26905)** $\Rightarrow 26905 - 984 = 161^2$, $S_{161 \times 161} := 4490129$, $T_{25921} := 26887^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 53807, 53809\}$ or $E := \{14929, 14930, \dots, 40848, 40849\}$
8. **(984, 60512, 60520)** $\Rightarrow 60520 - 984 = 244^2$, $S_{244 \times 244} := 15006976$, $T_{59536} := 60512^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 121037, 121039\}$

9. **(984, 242063, 242065)** $\Rightarrow 242065 - 984 = 491^2$, $S_{491 \times 491} := 119337059$, $T_{241081} := 242063^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 484127, 484129\}$ or $E := \{122509, 122510, \dots, 363588, 363589\}$

■ Number 985

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$985^2 + 2364^2 := 2561^2$$

$$985^2 + 19392^2 := 19417^2$$

$$985^2 + 97020^2 := 97025^2$$

$$985^2 + 485112^2 := 485113^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(985, 19392, 19417)** $\Rightarrow 19417 - 19392 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 194045$, $T_{25} := 985^2$,
 $E := \{38785, 38787, \dots, 38831, 38833\}$ or $E := \{38797, 38798, \dots, 38820, 38821\}$

■ Number 986

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$986^2 + 8352^2 := 8410^2$$

$$986^2 + 14280^2 := 14314^2$$

$$986^2 + 243048^2 := 243050^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(986, 243048, 243050)** $\Rightarrow 243050 - 986 = 492^2$, $S_{492 \times 492} := 120065712$, $T_{242064} := 243048^2$,
 $E := \{1973, 1975, \dots, 486097, 486099\}$

■ Number 983

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$987^2 + 1316^2 := 1645^2$$

$$987^2 + 3240^2 := 3387^2$$

$$987^2 + 3384^2 := 3525^2$$

$$987^2 + 7700^2 := 7763^2$$

$$987^2 + 9916^2 := 9965^2$$

$$987^2 + 10340^2 := 10387^2$$

$$987^2 + 23184^2 := 23205^2$$

$$987^2 + 54116^2 := 54125^2$$

$$987^2 + 69580^2 := 69587^2$$

$$987^2 + 162360^2 := 162363^2$$

$$987^2 + 487084^2 := 487085^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(987, 54116, 54125)** $\Rightarrow 54125 - 54116 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 324723$, $T_9 := 987^2$,
 $E := \{108233, 108235, \dots, 108247, 108249\}$ or $E := \{108237, 108238, \dots, 108244, 108245\}$
2. **(987, 9916, 9965)** $\Rightarrow 9965 - 9916 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 139167$, $T_{49} := 987^2$,
 $E := \{19833, 19835, \dots, 19927, 19929\}$ or $E := \{19857, 19858, \dots, 19904, 19905\}$

■ Number 988

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$988^2 + 1275^2 := 1613^2$$

$$988^2 + 3135^2 := 3287^2$$

$$988^2 + 4641^2 := 4745^2$$

$$988^2 + 6384^2 := 6460^2$$

$$988^2 + 9360^2 := 9412^2$$

$$988^2 + 12825^2 := 12863^2$$

$$988^2 + 18759^2 := 18785^2$$

$$988^2 + 61005^2 := 61013^2$$

$$988^2 + 122016^2 := 122020^2$$

$$988^2 + 244035^2 := 244037^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(988, 1275, 1613)** $\Rightarrow 1613 - 988 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 65025$, $T_{625} := 1275^2$,
 $E := \{1977, 1979, \dots, 3223, 3225\}$ or $E := \{2289, 2290, \dots, 2912, 2913\}$
2. **(988, 61005, 61013)** $\Rightarrow 61013 - 988 = 245^2$, $S_{245 \times 245} := 15190245$, $T_{60025} := 61005^2$,
 $E := \{1977, 1979, \dots, 122023, 122025\}$ or $E := \{31989, 31990, \dots, 92012, 92013\}$
3. **(988, 244035, 244037)** $\Rightarrow 244037 - 988 = 493^2$, $S_{493 \times 493} := 120797325$, $T_{243049} := 244035^2$,
 $E := \{1977, 1979, \dots, 488071, 488073\}$ or $E := \{123501, 123502, \dots, 366548, 366549\}$

■ Number 989

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$989^2 + 11352^2 := 11395^2$$

$$989^2 + 21252^2 := 21275^2$$

$$989^2 + 489060^2 := 489061^2$$

■ Number 990

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 990^2 + 1320^2 &:= 1650^2 \\ 990^2 + 1680^2 &:= 1950^2 \\ 990^2 + 1904^2 &:= 2146^2 \\ 990^2 + 2376^2 &:= 2574^2 \\ 990^2 + 2944^2 &:= 3106^2 \\ 990^2 + 3192^2 &:= 3342^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 990^2 + 4400^2 &:= 4510^2 \\ 990^2 + 5400^2 &:= 5490^2 \\ 990^2 + 7392^2 &:= 7458^2 \\ 990^2 + 9048^2 &:= 9102^2 \\ 990^2 + 9776^2 &:= 9826^2 \\ 990^2 + 16320^2 &:= 16350^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 990^2 + 22264^2 &:= 22286^2 \\ 990^2 + 27216^2 &:= 27234^2 \\ 990^2 + 49000^2 &:= 49010^2 \\ 990^2 + 81672^2 &:= 81678^2 \\ 990^2 + 245024^2 &:= 245026^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(990, 1904, 2146)** $\Rightarrow 2146 - 990 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 106624$, $T_{1156} := 1904^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 4289, 4291\}$
2. **(990, 2944, 3106)** $\Rightarrow 3106 - 990 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 188416$, $T_{2116} := 2944^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 6209, 6211\}$
3. **(990, 9776, 9826)** $\Rightarrow 9826 - 990 = 94^2$, $S_{94 \times 94} := 1016704$, $T_{8836} := 9776^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 19649, 19651\}$
4. **(990, 27216, 27234)** $\Rightarrow 27234 - 990 = 162^2$, $S_{162 \times 162} := 4572288$, $T_{26244} := 27216^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 54465, 54467\}$
5. **(990, 245024, 245026)** $\Rightarrow 245026 - 990 = 494^2$, $S_{494 \times 494} := 121531904$, $T_{244036} := 245024^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 490049, 490051\}$

■ Number 991

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$991^2 + 491040^2 := 491041^2$$

■ Number 992

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{aligned} 992^2 + 1794^2 &:= 2050^2 \\ 992^2 + 1860^2 &:= 2108^2 \\ 992^2 + 3780^2 &:= 3908^2 \\ 992^2 + 3906^2 &:= 4030^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 992^2 + 7656^2 &:= 7720^2 \\ 992^2 + 7905^2 &:= 7967^2 \\ 992^2 + 15360^2 &:= 15392^2 \\ 992^2 + 30744^2 &:= 30760^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 992^2 + 61500^2 &:= 61508^2 \\ 992^2 + 123006^2 &:= 123010^2 \\ 992^2 + 246015^2 &:= 246017^2 \end{aligned}$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(992, 30744, 30760)** $\Rightarrow 30760 - 30744 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 246016$, $T_{16} := 992^2$,
 $E := \{61489, 61491, \dots, 61517, 61519\}$
2. **(992, 7656, 7720)** $\Rightarrow 7720 - 7656 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 123008$, $T_{64} := 992^2$,
 $E := \{15313, 15315, \dots, 15437, 15439\}$
3. **(992, 1794, 2050)** $\Rightarrow 2050 - 1794 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 61504$, $T_{256} := 992^2$,
 $E := \{3589, 3591, \dots, 4097, 4099\}$
4. **(992, 3780, 3908)** $\Rightarrow 3908 - 992 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 264600$, $T_{2916} := 3780^2$,
 $E := \{1985, 1987, \dots, 7813, 7815\}$
5. **(992, 15360, 15392)** $\Rightarrow 15392 - 992 = 120^2$, $S_{120 \times 120} := 1966080$, $T_{14400} := 15360^2$,
 $E := \{1985, 1987, \dots, 30781, 30783\}$
6. **(992, 61500, 61508)** $\Rightarrow 61508 - 992 = 246^2$, $S_{246 \times 246} := 15375000$, $T_{60516} := 61500^2$,
 $E := \{1985, 1987, \dots, 123013, 123015\}$
7. **(992, 246015, 246017)** $\Rightarrow 246017 - 992 = 495^2$, $S_{495 \times 495} := 122269455$, $T_{245025} := 246015^2$,
 $E := \{1985, 1987, \dots, 492031, 492033\}$ or $E := \{124497, 124498, \dots, 369520, 369521\}$

■ Number 993

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 993^2 + 1324^2 := 1655^2 & 993^2 + 164340^2 := 164343^2 \\
 993^2 + 54776^2 := 54785^2 & 993^2 + 493024^2 := 493025^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(993, 54776, 54785)** $\Rightarrow 54785 - 54776 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 328683$, $T_9 := 993^2$,
 $E := \{109553, 109555, \dots, 109567, 109569\}$ or $E := \{109557, 109558, \dots, 109564, 109565\}$

■ Number 994

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 994^2 + 3408^2 := 3550^2 & 994^2 + 35280^2 := 35294^2 \\
 994^2 + 4992^2 := 5090^2 & 994^2 + 247008^2 := 247010^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(994, 4992, 5090)** $\Rightarrow 5090 - 994 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 389376$, $T_{4096} := 4992^2$,
 $E := \{1989, 1991, \dots, 10177, 10179\}$
2. **(994, 247008, 247010)** $\Rightarrow 247010 - 994 = 496^2$, $S_{496 \times 496} := 123009984$, $T_{246016} := 247008^2$,
 $E := \{1989, 1991, \dots, 494017, 494019\}$

■ Number 995

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 995^2 + 2388^2 := 2587^2 & 995^2 + 99000^2 := 99005^2 \\ 995^2 + 19788^2 := 19813^2 & 995^2 + 495012^2 := 495013^2 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(995, 19788, 19813)** $\Rightarrow 19813 - 19788 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 198005$, $T_{25} := 995^2$,
 $E := \{39577, 39579, \dots, 39623, 39625\}$ or $E := \{39589, 39590, \dots, 39612, 39613\}$

■ Number 996

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{lll} 996^2 + 1328^2 := 1660^2 & 996^2 + 20655^2 := 20679^2 & 996^2 + 82665^2 := 82671^2 \\ 996^2 + 2905^2 := 3071^2 & 996^2 + 27547^2 := 27565^2 & 996^2 + 248003^2 := 248005^2 \\ 996^2 + 6853^2 := 6925^2 & 996^2 + 41328^2 := 41340^2 & 996^2 + 124000^2 := 124004^2 \\ 996^2 + 13760^2 := 13796^2 & 996^2 + 61997^2 := 62005^2 & \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(996, 13760, 13796)** $\Rightarrow 13796 - 13760 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 165336$, $T_{36} := 996^2$,
 $E := \{27521, 27523, \dots, 27589, 27591\}$
2. **(996, 6853, 6925)** $\Rightarrow 6925 - 996 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 609917$, $T_{5929} := 6853^2$,
 $E := \{1993, 1995, \dots, 13847, 13849\}$ or $E := \{4957, 4958, \dots, 10884, 10885\}$
3. **(996, 27547, 27565)** $\Rightarrow 27565 - 996 = 163^2$, $S_{163 \times 163} := 4655443$, $T_{26569} := 27547^2$,
 $E := \{1993, 1995, \dots, 55127, 55129\}$ or $E := \{15277, 15278, \dots, 41844, 41845\}$
4. **(996, 61997, 62005)** $\Rightarrow 62005 - 996 = 247^2$, $S_{247 \times 247} := 15561247$, $T_{61009} := 61997^2$,
 $E := \{1993, 1995, \dots, 124007, 124009\}$ or $E := \{32497, 32498, \dots, 93504, 93505\}$
5. **(996, 248003, 248005)** $\Rightarrow 248005 - 996 = 497^2$, $S_{497 \times 497} := 123753497$, $T_{247009} := 248003^2$,
 $E := \{1993, 1995, \dots, 496007, 496009\}$ or $E := \{125497, 125498, \dots, 372504, 372505\}$

■ Number 997

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$997^2 + 497004^2 := 497005^2$$

■ Number 998

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$998^2 + 249000^2 := 249002^2$$

(b) Magic Square

- **(998, 249000, 249002)** $\Rightarrow 249002 - 998 = 498^2$, $S_{498 \times 498} := 124500000$, $T_{248004} := 249000^2$,
 $E := \{1997, 1999, \dots, 498001, 498003\}$

■ Number 999

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$999^2 + 1332^2 := 1665^2$$

$$999^2 + 1932^2 := 2175^2$$

$$999^2 + 4440^2 := 4551^2$$

$$999^2 + 6120^2 := 6201^2$$

$$999^2 + 13468^2 := 13505^2$$

$$999^2 + 18468^2 := 18495^2$$

$$999^2 + 55440^2 := 55449^2$$

$$999^2 + 166332^2 := 166335^2$$

$$999^2 + 499000^2 := 499001^2$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(999, 55440, 55449)** $\Rightarrow 55449 - 55440 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 332667$, $T_9 := 999^2$,
 $E := \{110881, 110883, \dots, 110895, 110897\}$ or $E := \{110885, 110886, \dots, 110892, 110893\}$
2. **(999, 6120, 6201)** $\Rightarrow 6201 - 6120 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 110889$, $T_{81} := 999^2$,
 $E := \{12241, 12243, \dots, 12399, 12401\}$ or $E := \{12281, 12282, \dots, 12360, 12361\}$

■ Number 1000

(a) Pythagorean Triples

$$1000^2 + 1050^2 := 1450^2$$

$$1000^2 + 1875^2 := 2125^2$$

$$1000^2 + 2400^2 := 2600^2$$

$$1000^2 + 3045^2 := 3205^2$$

$$1000^2 + 4950^2 := 5050^2$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 1000^2 + 6210^2 := 6290^2 & \\
 1000^2 + 9975^2 := 10025^2 & 1000^2 + 49995^2 := 50005^2 \\
 1000^2 + 15609^2 := 15641^2 & 1000^2 + 62496^2 := 62504^2 \\
 1000^2 + 24990^2 := 25010^2 & 1000^2 + 12480^2 := 12520^2 \\
 1000^2 + 31242^2 := 31258^2 & 1000^2 + 124998^2 := 125002^2 \\
 & 1000^2 + 249999^2 := 250001^2
 \end{array}$$

(b) Magic Square

1. **(1000, 31242, 31258)** $\Rightarrow 31258 - 31242 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 250000$, $T_{16} := 1000^2$,
 $E := \{62485, 62487, \dots, 62513, 62515\}$
2. **(1000, 4950, 5050)** $\Rightarrow 5050 - 4950 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 100000$, $T_{100} := 1000^2$,
 $E := \{9901, 9903, \dots, 10097, 10099\}$
3. **(1000, 1050, 1450)** $\Rightarrow 1450 - 1050 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 50000$, $T_{400} := 1000^2$,
 $E := \{2101, 2103, \dots, 2897, 2899\}$
4. **(1000, 2400, 2600)** $\Rightarrow 2600 - 1000 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 144000$, $T_{1600} := 2400^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 5197, 5199\}$
5. **(1000, 9975, 10025)** $\Rightarrow 10025 - 1000 = 95^2$, $S_{95 \times 95} := 1047375$, $T_{9025} := 9975^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 20047, 20049\}$ or $E := \{6513, 6514, \dots, 15536, 15537\}$
6. **(1000, 15609, 15641)** $\Rightarrow 15641 - 1000 = 121^2$, $S_{121 \times 121} := 2013561$, $T_{14641} := 15609^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 31279, 31281\}$ or $E := \{9321, 9322, \dots, 23960, 23961\}$
7. **(1000, 62496, 62504)** $\Rightarrow 62504 - 1000 = 248^2$, $S_{248 \times 248} := 15748992$, $T_{61504} := 62496^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 125005, 125007\}$
8. **(1000, 249999, 250001)** $\Rightarrow 250001 - 1000 = 499^2$, $S_{499 \times 499} := 125249499$, $T_{249001} := 249999^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 499999, 500001\}$ or $E := \{126501, 126502, \dots, 375500, 375501\}$

3 Part II: Analysis of Magic Squares

In Part I of this work we have written 5803 Pythagorean triples from 3 to 1000 except 4. Fortunately, there is at least one triple for each sequential number. In each case, the possible magic squares are also written. This section brings magic squares obtained from Pythagorean triples written according to orders. These are for the orders 3 to 1000 except 4. Still, we are unable to say that these are the only possible triples, but at least there is one triple for each natural number from 3 to 1000 except 4. There are total 2172 magic squares arising due to 5803 triples. In subsections below we wrote magic squares in terms of increasing orders of the first term of Pythagorean triples. The following result is written based on the examples studied in subsections below. It is summarized below.

The second result obtained from Section 3 is as follows:

Result 3.1. Let (a, b, c) be a Pythagorean triple, i.e., $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$, where $c > a$ and $c > b$. Let n be a order of magic square. If there exists a magic squares based on the triple (a, b, c) , then following relations hold:

- (i) **First Triple:** $a = n^2 + 2n = n(n + 2)$ or $b = n^2 + 2n = n(n + 2)$;
- (ii) **Gap Between Two Consecutive Triples:** $a = 2n$, or $b = 2n$, a or $b \in \{n(n + 2), n(n + 4), \dots\}$;
- (iii) **Difference Among Terms of a Triple:** $c - b = n^2$ or $c - a = n^2$;
- (iv) **Entries Total Sum:** $T := a^2$ or $T := b^2$.
- (v) **Magic Sum:** $S_{n \times n} := a(2k + n)$ or $b(2k + n)$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$. Alternatively, $S_{n \times n} := \frac{a^2}{n}$ or $S_{n \times n} := \frac{b^2}{n}$, a or $b \in \{n(n + 2), n(n + 4), \dots\}$;

Remark 3. According to formula given in (1), there is no condition on the first two terms of a Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) . Any of two, i.e., either a or b can be bigger than other.

As a consequence of results studied in Sections 4 and 5 given below, we have following observations:

Remark 4. (i) From the examples given in subsections below, we observe that, for the orders 3 to 20 the results are mixed, i.e., first few or initial triples are with b and rest are in a . From orders 21 onward, all the results are in b , where (a, b, c) is a **Pythagorean triple**.

(ii) It is also observed that triples with first member, i.e, when a is even number it generates magic squares of even or odd orders, and when it is odd number, it always generates magic squares of odd orders.

(iii) Magic squares of odd orders can be obtained from entries as odd or natural numbers having the same magic sum. While in case of even order magic squares, the entries are always odd numbers.

(iv) There is always a triple with a as even number generating a magic square.

(v) In the following subsections, we have written particular cases of Result ?? for the orders 3 to 40. The other orders follows the similar lines or follow the Result ?? or Result 3.1.

The subsequent section give the 2172 results obtained from 5803 Pythagorean triples where the first numbers is between 3 to 1000. These are seperated according to order of magic squares. Number-wise complete details with all the 5803 triples is given in author's another work [11]. For more study on **Pythagorean triples** and perfect square sum magic squares can be seen in author's work [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10].

4 Order-Wise Magic Squares

4.1 Magic Squares of Order 3

This subsection brings magic squares of order 3 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **two** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

1. **(15, 8, 17)** $\Rightarrow 17 - 8 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 75$, $T_9 := 15^2$,
 $E := \{17, 19, \dots, 31, 33\}$ or $E := \{21, 22, \dots, 28, 29\}$
2. **(21, 20, 29)** $\Rightarrow 29 - 20 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 147$, $T_9 := 21^2$,
 $E := \{41, 43, \dots, 55, 57\}$ or $E := \{45, 46, \dots, 52, 53\}$
3. **(27, 36, 45)** $\Rightarrow 45 - 36 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 243$, $T_9 := 27^2$,
 $E := \{73, 75, \dots, 87, 89\}$ or $E := \{77, 78, \dots, 84, 85\}$
4. **(33, 56, 65)** $\Rightarrow 65 - 56 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 363$, $T_9 := 33^2$,
 $E := \{113, 115, \dots, 127, 129\}$ or $E := \{117, 118, \dots, 124, 125\}$
5. **(39, 80, 89)** $\Rightarrow 89 - 80 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 507$, $T_9 := 39^2$,
 $E := \{161, 163, \dots, 175, 177\}$ or $E := \{165, 166, \dots, 172, 173\}$
6. **(45, 108, 117)** $\Rightarrow 117 - 108 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 675$, $T_9 := 45^2$,
 $E := \{217, 219, \dots, 231, 233\}$ or $E := \{221, 222, \dots, 228, 229\}$
7. **(51, 140, 149)** $\Rightarrow 149 - 140 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 867$, $T_9 := 51^2$,
 $E := \{281, 283, \dots, 295, 297\}$ or $E := \{285, 286, \dots, 292, 293\}$
8. **(57, 176, 185)** $\Rightarrow 185 - 176 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 1083$, $T_9 := 57^2$,
 $E := \{353, 355, \dots, 367, 369\}$ or $E := \{357, 358, \dots, 364, 365\}$
9. **(63, 216, 225)** $\Rightarrow 225 - 216 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 1323$, $T_9 := 63^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 447, 449\}$ or $E := \{437, 438, \dots, 444, 445\}$
10. **(69, 260, 269)** $\Rightarrow 269 - 260 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 1587$, $T_9 := 69^2$,
 $E := \{521, 523, \dots, 535, 537\}$ or $E := \{525, 526, \dots, 532, 533\}$
11. **(75, 308, 317)** $\Rightarrow 317 - 308 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 1875$, $T_9 := 75^2$,
 $E := \{617, 619, \dots, 631, 633\}$ or $E := \{621, 622, \dots, 628, 629\}$
12. **(81, 360, 369)** $\Rightarrow 369 - 360 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 2187$, $T_9 := 81^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 735, 737\}$ or $E := \{725, 726, \dots, 732, 733\}$
13. **(87, 416, 425)** $\Rightarrow 425 - 416 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 2523$, $T_9 := 87^2$,
 $E := \{833, 835, \dots, 847, 849\}$ or $E := \{837, 838, \dots, 844, 845\}$
14. **(93, 476, 485)** $\Rightarrow 485 - 476 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 2883$, $T_9 := 93^2$,
 $E := \{953, 955, \dots, 967, 969\}$ or $E := \{957, 958, \dots, 964, 965\}$

15. **(99, 540, 549)** $\Rightarrow 549 - 540 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 3267$, $T_9 := 99^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 1095, 1097\}$ or $E := \{1085, 1086, \dots, 1092, 1093\}$
16. **(105, 608, 617)** $\Rightarrow 617 - 608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 3675$, $T_9 := 105^2$,
 $E := \{1217, 1219, \dots, 1231, 1233\}$ or $E := \{1221, 1222, \dots, 1228, 1229\}$
17. **(111, 680, 689)** $\Rightarrow 689 - 680 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 4107$, $T_9 := 111^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 1375, 1377\}$ or $E := \{1365, 1366, \dots, 1372, 1373\}$
18. **(117, 756, 765)** $\Rightarrow 765 - 756 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 4563$, $T_9 := 117^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 1527, 1529\}$ or $E := \{1517, 1518, \dots, 1524, 1525\}$
19. **(123, 836, 845)** $\Rightarrow 845 - 836 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 5043$, $T_9 := 123^2$,
 $E := \{1673, 1675, \dots, 1687, 1689\}$ or $E := \{1677, 1678, \dots, 1684, 1685\}$
20. **(129, 920, 929)** $\Rightarrow 929 - 920 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 5547$, $T_9 := 129^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 1855, 1857\}$ or $E := \{1845, 1846, \dots, 1852, 1853\}$
21. **(135, 1008, 1017)** $\Rightarrow 1017 - 1008 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 6075$, $T_9 := 135^2$,
 $E := \{2017, 2019, \dots, 2031, 2033\}$ or $E := \{2021, 2022, \dots, 2028, 2029\}$
22. **(141, 1100, 1109)** $\Rightarrow 1109 - 1100 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 6627$, $T_9 := 141^2$,
 $E := \{2201, 2203, \dots, 2215, 2217\}$ or $E := \{2205, 2206, \dots, 2212, 2213\}$
23. **(147, 1196, 1205)** $\Rightarrow 1205 - 1196 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 7203$, $T_9 := 147^2$,
 $E := \{2393, 2395, \dots, 2407, 2409\}$ or $E := \{2397, 2398, \dots, 2404, 2405\}$
24. **(153, 1296, 1305)** $\Rightarrow 1305 - 1296 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 7803$, $T_9 := 153^2$,
 $E := \{2593, 2595, \dots, 2607, 2609\}$ or $E := \{2597, 2598, \dots, 2604, 2605\}$
25. **(159, 1400, 1409)** $\Rightarrow 1409 - 1400 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 8427$, $T_9 := 159^2$,
 $E := \{2801, 2803, \dots, 2815, 2817\}$ or $E := \{2805, 2806, \dots, 2812, 2813\}$
26. **(165, 1508, 1517)** $\Rightarrow 1517 - 1508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 9075$, $T_9 := 165^2$,
 $E := \{3017, 3019, \dots, 3031, 3033\}$ or $E := \{3021, 3022, \dots, 3028, 3029\}$
27. **(171, 1620, 1629)** $\Rightarrow 1629 - 1620 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 9747$, $T_9 := 171^2$,
 $E := \{3241, 3243, \dots, 3255, 3257\}$ or $E := \{3245, 3246, \dots, 3252, 3253\}$
28. **(177, 1736, 1745)** $\Rightarrow 1745 - 1736 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 10443$, $T_9 := 177^2$,
 $E := \{3473, 3475, \dots, 3487, 3489\}$ or $E := \{3477, 3478, \dots, 3484, 3485\}$
29. **(183, 1856, 1865)** $\Rightarrow 1865 - 1856 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 11163$, $T_9 := 183^2$,
 $E := \{3713, 3715, \dots, 3727, 3729\}$ or $E := \{3717, 3718, \dots, 3724, 3725\}$
30. **(189, 1980, 1989)** $\Rightarrow 1989 - 1980 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 11907$, $T_9 := 189^2$,
 $E := \{3961, 3963, \dots, 3975, 3977\}$ or $E := \{3965, 3966, \dots, 3972, 3973\}$
31. **(195, 2108, 2117)** $\Rightarrow 2117 - 2108 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 12675$, $T_9 := 195^2$,
 $E := \{4217, 4219, \dots, 4231, 4233\}$ or $E := \{4221, 4222, \dots, 4228, 4229\}$

32. **(201, 2240, 2249)** $\Rightarrow 2249 - 2240 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 13467$, $T_9 := 201^2$,
 $E := \{4481, 4483, \dots, 4495, 4497\}$ or $E := \{4485, 4486, \dots, 4492, 4493\}$
33. **(207, 2376, 2385)** $\Rightarrow 2385 - 2376 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 14283$, $T_9 := 207^2$,
 $E := \{4753, 4755, \dots, 4767, 4769\}$ or $E := \{4757, 4758, \dots, 4764, 4765\}$
34. **(213, 2516, 2525)** $\Rightarrow 2525 - 2516 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 15123$, $T_9 := 213^2$,
 $E := \{5033, 5035, \dots, 5047, 5049\}$ or $E := \{5037, 5038, \dots, 5044, 5045\}$
35. **(219, 2660, 2669)** $\Rightarrow 2669 - 2660 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 15987$, $T_9 := 219^2$,
 $E := \{5321, 5323, \dots, 5335, 5337\}$ or $E := \{5325, 5326, \dots, 5332, 5333\}$
36. **(225, 2808, 2817)** $\Rightarrow 2817 - 2808 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 16875$, $T_9 := 225^2$,
 $E := \{5617, 5619, \dots, 5631, 5633\}$ or $E := \{5621, 5622, \dots, 5628, 5629\}$
37. **(231, 2960, 2969)** $\Rightarrow 2969 - 2960 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 17787$, $T_9 := 231^2$,
 $E := \{5921, 5923, \dots, 5935, 5937\}$ or $E := \{5925, 5926, \dots, 5932, 5933\}$
38. **(237, 3116, 3125)** $\Rightarrow 3125 - 3116 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 18723$, $T_9 := 237^2$,
 $E := \{6233, 6235, \dots, 6247, 6249\}$ or $E := \{6237, 6238, \dots, 6244, 6245\}$
39. **(243, 3276, 3285)** $\Rightarrow 3285 - 3276 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 19683$, $T_9 := 243^2$,
 $E := \{6553, 6555, \dots, 6567, 6569\}$ or $E := \{6557, 6558, \dots, 6564, 6565\}$
40. **(249, 3440, 3449)** $\Rightarrow 3449 - 3440 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 20667$, $T_9 := 249^2$,
 $E := \{6881, 6883, \dots, 6895, 6897\}$ or $E := \{6885, 6886, \dots, 6892, 6893\}$
41. **(255, 3608, 3617)** $\Rightarrow 3617 - 3608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 21675$, $T_9 := 255^2$,
 $E := \{7217, 7219, \dots, 7231, 7233\}$ or $E := \{7221, 7222, \dots, 7228, 7229\}$
42. **(261, 3780, 3789)** $\Rightarrow 3789 - 3780 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 22707$, $T_9 := 261^2$,
 $E := \{7561, 7563, \dots, 7575, 7577\}$ or $E := \{7565, 7566, \dots, 7572, 7573\}$
43. **(267, 3956, 3965)** $\Rightarrow 3965 - 3956 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 23763$, $T_9 := 267^2$,
 $E := \{7913, 7915, \dots, 7927, 7929\}$ or $E := \{7917, 7918, \dots, 7924, 7925\}$
44. **(273, 4136, 4145)** $\Rightarrow 4145 - 4136 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 24843$, $T_9 := 273^2$,
 $E := \{8273, 8275, \dots, 8287, 8289\}$ or $E := \{8277, 8278, \dots, 8284, 8285\}$
45. **(279, 4320, 4329)** $\Rightarrow 4329 - 4320 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 25947$, $T_9 := 279^2$,
 $E := \{8641, 8643, \dots, 8655, 8657\}$ or $E := \{8645, 8646, \dots, 8652, 8653\}$
46. **(285, 4508, 4517)** $\Rightarrow 4517 - 4508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 27075$, $T_9 := 285^2$,
 $E := \{9017, 9019, \dots, 9031, 9033\}$ or $E := \{9021, 9022, \dots, 9028, 9029\}$
47. **(291, 4700, 4709)** $\Rightarrow 4709 - 4700 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 28227$, $T_9 := 291^2$,
 $E := \{9401, 9403, \dots, 9415, 9417\}$ or $E := \{9405, 9406, \dots, 9412, 9413\}$
48. **(297, 4896, 4905)** $\Rightarrow 4905 - 4896 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 29403$, $T_9 := 297^2$,
 $E := \{9793, 9795, \dots, 9807, 9809\}$ or $E := \{9797, 9798, \dots, 9804, 9805\}$

49. **(303, 5096, 5105)** $\Rightarrow 5105 - 5096 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 30603$, $T_9 := 303^2$,
 $E := \{10193, 10195, \dots, 10207, 10209\}$ or $E := \{10197, 10198, \dots, 10204, 10205\}$
50. **(309, 5300, 5309)** $\Rightarrow 5309 - 5300 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 31827$, $T_9 := 309^2$,
 $E := \{10601, 10603, \dots, 10615, 10617\}$ or $E := \{10605, 10606, \dots, 10612, 10613\}$
51. **(315, 5508, 5517)** $\Rightarrow 5517 - 5508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 33075$, $T_9 := 315^2$,
 $E := \{11017, 11019, \dots, 11031, 11033\}$ or $E := \{11021, 11022, \dots, 11028, 11029\}$
52. **(321, 5720, 5729)** $\Rightarrow 5729 - 5720 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 34347$, $T_9 := 321^2$,
 $E := \{11441, 11443, \dots, 11455, 11457\}$ or $E := \{11445, 11446, \dots, 11452, 11453\}$
53. **(327, 5936, 5945)** $\Rightarrow 5945 - 5936 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 35643$, $T_9 := 327^2$,
 $E := \{11873, 11875, \dots, 11887, 11889\}$ or $E := \{11877, 11878, \dots, 11884, 11885\}$
54. **(333, 6156, 6165)** $\Rightarrow 6165 - 6156 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 36963$, $T_9 := 333^2$,
 $E := \{12313, 12315, \dots, 12327, 12329\}$ or $E := \{12317, 12318, \dots, 12324, 12325\}$
55. **(339, 6380, 6389)** $\Rightarrow 6389 - 6380 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 38307$, $T_9 := 339^2$,
 $E := \{12761, 12763, \dots, 12775, 12777\}$ or $E := \{12765, 12766, \dots, 12772, 12773\}$
56. **(345, 6608, 6617)** $\Rightarrow 6617 - 6608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 39675$, $T_9 := 345^2$,
 $E := \{13217, 13219, \dots, 13231, 13233\}$ or $E := \{13221, 13222, \dots, 13228, 13229\}$
57. **(351, 6840, 6849)** $\Rightarrow 6849 - 6840 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 41067$, $T_9 := 351^2$,
 $E := \{13681, 13683, \dots, 13695, 13697\}$ or $E := \{13685, 13686, \dots, 13692, 13693\}$
58. **(357, 7076, 7085)** $\Rightarrow 7085 - 7076 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 42483$, $T_9 := 357^2$,
 $E := \{14153, 14155, \dots, 14167, 14169\}$ or $E := \{14157, 14158, \dots, 14164, 14165\}$
59. **(363, 7316, 7325)** $\Rightarrow 7325 - 7316 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 43923$, $T_9 := 363^2$,
 $E := \{14633, 14635, \dots, 14647, 14649\}$ or $E := \{14637, 14638, \dots, 14644, 14645\}$
60. **(369, 7560, 7569)** $\Rightarrow 7569 - 7560 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 45387$, $T_9 := 369^2$,
 $E := \{15121, 15123, \dots, 15135, 15137\}$ or $E := \{15125, 15126, \dots, 15132, 15133\}$
61. **(375, 7808, 7817)** $\Rightarrow 7817 - 7808 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 46875$, $T_9 := 375^2$,
 $E := \{15617, 15619, \dots, 15631, 15633\}$ or $E := \{15621, 15622, \dots, 15628, 15629\}$
62. **(381, 8060, 8069)** $\Rightarrow 8069 - 8060 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 48387$, $T_9 := 381^2$,
 $E := \{16121, 16123, \dots, 16135, 16137\}$ or $E := \{16125, 16126, \dots, 16132, 16133\}$
63. **(387, 8316, 8325)** $\Rightarrow 8325 - 8316 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 49923$, $T_9 := 387^2$,
 $E := \{16633, 16635, \dots, 16647, 16649\}$ or $E := \{16637, 16638, \dots, 16644, 16645\}$
64. **(393, 8576, 8585)** $\Rightarrow 8585 - 8576 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 51483$, $T_9 := 393^2$,
 $E := \{17153, 17155, \dots, 17167, 17169\}$ or $E := \{17157, 17158, \dots, 17164, 17165\}$
65. **(399, 8840, 8849)** $\Rightarrow 8849 - 8840 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 53067$, $T_9 := 399^2$,
 $E := \{17681, 17683, \dots, 17695, 17697\}$ or $E := \{17685, 17686, \dots, 17692, 17693\}$

66. **(405, 9108, 9117)** $\Rightarrow 9117 - 9108 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 54675$, $T_9 := 405^2$,
 $E := \{18217, 18219, \dots, 18231, 18233\}$ or $E := \{18221, 18222, \dots, 18228, 18229\}$
67. **(411, 9380, 9389)** $\Rightarrow 9389 - 9380 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 56307$, $T_9 := 411^2$,
 $E := \{18761, 18763, \dots, 18775, 18777\}$ or $E := \{18765, 18766, \dots, 18772, 18773\}$
68. **(417, 9656, 9665)** $\Rightarrow 9665 - 9656 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 57963$, $T_9 := 417^2$,
 $E := \{19313, 19315, \dots, 19327, 19329\}$ or $E := \{19317, 19318, \dots, 19324, 19325\}$
69. **(423, 9936, 9945)** $\Rightarrow 9945 - 9936 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 59643$, $T_9 := 423^2$,
 $E := \{19873, 19875, \dots, 19887, 19889\}$ or $E := \{19877, 19878, \dots, 19884, 19885\}$
70. **(429, 10220, 10229)** $\Rightarrow 10229 - 10220 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 61347$, $T_9 := 429^2$,
 $E := \{20441, 20443, \dots, 20455, 20457\}$ or $E := \{20445, 20446, \dots, 20452, 20453\}$
71. **(435, 10508, 10517)** $\Rightarrow 10517 - 10508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 63075$, $T_9 := 435^2$,
 $E := \{21017, 21019, \dots, 21031, 21033\}$ or $E := \{21021, 21022, \dots, 21028, 21029\}$
72. **(441, 10800, 10809)** $\Rightarrow 10809 - 10800 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 64827$, $T_9 := 441^2$,
 $E := \{21601, 21603, \dots, 21615, 21617\}$ or $E := \{21605, 21606, \dots, 21612, 21613\}$
73. **(447, 11096, 11105)** $\Rightarrow 11105 - 11096 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 66603$, $T_9 := 447^2$,
 $E := \{22193, 22195, \dots, 22207, 22209\}$ or $E := \{22197, 22198, \dots, 22204, 22205\}$
74. **(453, 11396, 11405)** $\Rightarrow 11405 - 11396 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 68403$, $T_9 := 453^2$,
 $E := \{22793, 22795, \dots, 22807, 22809\}$ or $E := \{22797, 22798, \dots, 22804, 22805\}$
75. **(459, 11700, 11709)** $\Rightarrow 11709 - 11700 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 70227$, $T_9 := 459^2$,
 $E := \{23401, 23403, \dots, 23415, 23417\}$ or $E := \{23405, 23406, \dots, 23412, 23413\}$
76. **(465, 12008, 12017)** $\Rightarrow 12017 - 12008 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 72075$, $T_9 := 465^2$,
 $E := \{24017, 24019, \dots, 24031, 24033\}$ or $E := \{24021, 24022, \dots, 24028, 24029\}$
77. **(471, 12320, 12329)** $\Rightarrow 12329 - 12320 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 73947$, $T_9 := 471^2$,
 $E := \{24641, 24643, \dots, 24655, 24657\}$ or $E := \{24645, 24646, \dots, 24652, 24653\}$
78. **(477, 12636, 12645)** $\Rightarrow 12645 - 12636 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 75843$, $T_9 := 477^2$,
 $E := \{25273, 25275, \dots, 25287, 25289\}$ or $E := \{25277, 25278, \dots, 25284, 25285\}$
79. **(483, 12956, 12965)** $\Rightarrow 12965 - 12956 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 77763$, $T_9 := 483^2$,
 $E := \{25913, 25915, \dots, 25927, 25929\}$ or $E := \{25917, 25918, \dots, 25924, 25925\}$
80. **(489, 13280, 13289)** $\Rightarrow 13289 - 13280 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 79707$, $T_9 := 489^2$,
 $E := \{26561, 26563, \dots, 26575, 26577\}$ or $E := \{26565, 26566, \dots, 26572, 26573\}$
81. **(495, 13608, 13617)** $\Rightarrow 13617 - 13608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 81675$, $T_9 := 495^2$,
 $E := \{27217, 27219, \dots, 27231, 27233\}$ or $E := \{27221, 27222, \dots, 27228, 27229\}$
82. **(501, 13940, 13949)** $\Rightarrow 13949 - 13940 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 83667$, $T_9 := 501^2$,
 $E := \{27881, 27883, \dots, 27895, 27897\}$ or $E := \{27885, 27886, \dots, 27892, 27893\}$

83. **(507, 14276, 14285)** $\Rightarrow 14285 - 14276 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 85683$, $T_9 := 507^2$,
 $E := \{28553, 28555, \dots, 28567, 28569\}$ or $E := \{28557, 28558, \dots, 28564, 28565\}$
84. **(513, 14616, 14625)** $\Rightarrow 14625 - 14616 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 87723$, $T_9 := 513^2$,
 $E := \{29233, 29235, \dots, 29247, 29249\}$ or $E := \{29237, 29238, \dots, 29244, 29245\}$
85. **(519, 14960, 14969)** $\Rightarrow 14969 - 14960 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 89787$, $T_9 := 519^2$,
 $E := \{29921, 29923, \dots, 29935, 29937\}$ or $E := \{29925, 29926, \dots, 29932, 29933\}$
86. **(525, 15308, 15317)** $\Rightarrow 15317 - 15308 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 91875$, $T_9 := 525^2$,
 $E := \{30617, 30619, \dots, 30631, 30633\}$ or $E := \{30621, 30622, \dots, 30628, 30629\}$
87. **(531, 15660, 15669)** $\Rightarrow 15669 - 15660 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 93987$, $T_9 := 531^2$,
 $E := \{31321, 31323, \dots, 31335, 31337\}$ or $E := \{31325, 31326, \dots, 31332, 31333\}$
88. **(537, 16016, 16025)** $\Rightarrow 16025 - 16016 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 96123$, $T_9 := 537^2$,
 $E := \{32033, 32035, \dots, 32047, 32049\}$ or $E := \{32037, 32038, \dots, 32044, 32045\}$
89. **(543, 16376, 16385)** $\Rightarrow 16385 - 16376 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 98283$, $T_9 := 543^2$,
 $E := \{32753, 32755, \dots, 32767, 32769\}$ or $E := \{32757, 32758, \dots, 32764, 32765\}$
90. **(549, 16740, 16749)** $\Rightarrow 16749 - 16740 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 100467$, $T_9 := 549^2$,
 $E := \{33481, 33483, \dots, 33495, 33497\}$ or $E := \{33485, 33486, \dots, 33492, 33493\}$
91. **(561, 17480, 17489)** $\Rightarrow 17489 - 17480 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 104907$, $T_9 := 561^2$,
 $E := \{34961, 34963, \dots, 34975, 34977\}$ or $E := \{34965, 34966, \dots, 34972, 34973\}$
92. **(555, 17108, 17117)** $\Rightarrow 17117 - 17108 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 102675$, $T_9 := 555^2$,
 $E := \{34217, 34219, \dots, 34231, 34233\}$ or $E := \{34221, 34222, \dots, 34228, 34229\}$
93. **(567, 17856, 17865)** $\Rightarrow 17865 - 17856 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 107163$, $T_9 := 567^2$,
 $E := \{35713, 35715, \dots, 35727, 35729\}$ or $E := \{35717, 35718, \dots, 35724, 35725\}$
94. **(573, 18236, 18245)** $\Rightarrow 18245 - 18236 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 109443$, $T_9 := 573^2$,
 $E := \{36473, 36475, \dots, 36487, 36489\}$ or $E := \{36477, 36478, \dots, 36484, 36485\}$
95. **(579, 18620, 18629)** $\Rightarrow 18629 - 18620 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 111747$, $T_9 := 579^2$,
 $E := \{37241, 37243, \dots, 37255, 37257\}$ or $E := \{37245, 37246, \dots, 37252, 37253\}$
96. **(585, 19008, 19017)** $\Rightarrow 19017 - 19008 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 114075$, $T_9 := 585^2$,
 $E := \{38017, 38019, \dots, 38031, 38033\}$ or $E := \{38021, 38022, \dots, 38028, 38029\}$
97. **(591, 19400, 19409)** $\Rightarrow 19409 - 19400 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 116427$, $T_9 := 591^2$,
 $E := \{38801, 38803, \dots, 38815, 38817\}$ or $E := \{38805, 38806, \dots, 38812, 38813\}$
98. **(597, 19796, 19805)** $\Rightarrow 19805 - 19796 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 118803$, $T_9 := 597^2$,
 $E := \{39593, 39595, \dots, 39607, 39609\}$ or $E := \{39597, 39598, \dots, 39604, 39605\}$
99. **(603, 20196, 20205)** $\Rightarrow 20205 - 20196 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 121203$, $T_9 := 603^2$,
 $E := \{40393, 40395, \dots, 40407, 40409\}$ or $E := \{40397, 40398, \dots, 40404, 40405\}$

100. **(609, 20600, 20609)** $\Rightarrow 20609 - 20600 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 123627$, $T_9 := 609^2$,
 $E := \{41201, 41203, \dots, 41215, 41217\}$ or $E := \{41205, 41206, \dots, 41212, 41213\}$
101. **(615, 21008, 21017)** $\Rightarrow 21017 - 21008 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 126075$, $T_9 := 615^2$,
 $E := \{42017, 42019, \dots, 42031, 42033\}$ or $E := \{42021, 42022, \dots, 42028, 42029\}$
102. **(621, 21420, 21429)** $\Rightarrow 21429 - 21420 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 128547$, $T_9 := 621^2$,
 $E := \{42841, 42843, \dots, 42855, 42857\}$ or $E := \{42845, 42846, \dots, 42852, 42853\}$
103. **(627, 21836, 21845)** $\Rightarrow 21845 - 21836 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 131043$, $T_9 := 627^2$,
 $E := \{43673, 43675, \dots, 43687, 43689\}$ or $E := \{43677, 43678, \dots, 43684, 43685\}$
104. **(633, 22256, 22265)** $\Rightarrow 22265 - 22256 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 133563$, $T_9 := 633^2$,
 $E := \{44513, 44515, \dots, 44527, 44529\}$ or $E := \{44517, 44518, \dots, 44524, 44525\}$
105. **(639, 22680, 22689)** $\Rightarrow 22689 - 22680 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 136107$, $T_9 := 639^2$,
 $E := \{45361, 45363, \dots, 45375, 45377\}$ or $E := \{45365, 45366, \dots, 45372, 45373\}$
106. **(645, 23108, 23117)** $\Rightarrow 23117 - 23108 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 138675$, $T_9 := 645^2$,
 $E := \{46217, 46219, \dots, 46231, 46233\}$ or $E := \{46221, 46222, \dots, 46228, 46229\}$
107. **(651, 23540, 23549)** $\Rightarrow 23549 - 23540 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 141267$, $T_9 := 651^2$,
 $E := \{47081, 47083, \dots, 47095, 47097\}$ or $E := \{47085, 47086, \dots, 47092, 47093\}$
108. **(657, 23976, 23985)** $\Rightarrow 23985 - 23976 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 143883$, $T_9 := 657^2$,
 $E := \{47953, 47955, \dots, 47967, 47969\}$ or $E := \{47957, 47958, \dots, 47964, 47965\}$
109. **(663, 24416, 24425)** $\Rightarrow 24425 - 24416 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 146523$, $T_9 := 663^2$,
 $E := \{48833, 48835, \dots, 48847, 48849\}$ or $E := \{48837, 48838, \dots, 48844, 48845\}$
110. **(669, 24860, 24869)** $\Rightarrow 24869 - 24860 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 149187$, $T_9 := 669^2$,
 $E := \{49721, 49723, \dots, 49735, 49737\}$ or $E := \{49725, 49726, \dots, 49732, 49733\}$
111. **(675, 25308, 25317)** $\Rightarrow 25317 - 25308 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 151875$, $T_9 := 675^2$,
 $E := \{50617, 50619, \dots, 50631, 50633\}$ or $E := \{50621, 50622, \dots, 50628, 50629\}$
112. **(681, 25760, 25769)** $\Rightarrow 25769 - 25760 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 154587$, $T_9 := 681^2$,
 $E := \{51521, 51523, \dots, 51535, 51537\}$ or $E := \{51525, 51526, \dots, 51532, 51533\}$
113. **(687, 26216, 26225)** $\Rightarrow 26225 - 26216 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 157323$, $T_9 := 687^2$,
 $E := \{52433, 52435, \dots, 52447, 52449\}$ or $E := \{52437, 52438, \dots, 52444, 52445\}$
114. **(693, 26676, 26685)** $\Rightarrow 26685 - 26676 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 160083$, $T_9 := 693^2$,
 $E := \{53353, 53355, \dots, 53367, 53369\}$ or $E := \{53357, 53358, \dots, 53364, 53365\}$
115. **(699, 27140, 27149)** $\Rightarrow 27149 - 27140 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 162867$, $T_9 := 699^2$,
 $E := \{54281, 54283, \dots, 54295, 54297\}$ or $E := \{54285, 54286, \dots, 54292, 54293\}$
116. **(705, 27608, 27617)** $\Rightarrow 27617 - 27608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 165675$, $T_9 := 705^2$,
 $E := \{55217, 55219, \dots, 55231, 55233\}$ or $E := \{55221, 55222, \dots, 55228, 55229\}$

117. **(711, 28080, 28089)** $\Rightarrow 28089 - 28080 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 168507$, $T_9 := 711^2$,
 $E := \{56161, 56163, \dots, 56175, 56177\}$ or $E := \{56165, 56166, \dots, 56172, 56173\}$
118. **(717, 28556, 28565)** $\Rightarrow 28565 - 28556 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 171363$, $T_9 := 717^2$,
 $E := \{57113, 57115, \dots, 57127, 57129\}$ or $E := \{57117, 57118, \dots, 57124, 57125\}$
119. **(723, 29036, 29045)** $\Rightarrow 29045 - 29036 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 174243$, $T_9 := 723^2$,
 $E := \{58073, 58075, \dots, 58087, 58089\}$ or $E := \{58077, 58078, \dots, 58084, 58085\}$
120. **(729, 29520, 29529)** $\Rightarrow 29529 - 29520 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 177147$, $T_9 := 729^2$,
 $E := \{59041, 59043, \dots, 59055, 59057\}$ or $E := \{59045, 59046, \dots, 59052, 59053\}$
121. **(735, 30008, 30017)** $\Rightarrow 30017 - 30008 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 180075$, $T_9 := 735^2$,
 $E := \{60017, 60019, \dots, 60031, 60033\}$ or $E := \{60021, 60022, \dots, 60028, 60029\}$
122. **(741, 30500, 30509)** $\Rightarrow 30509 - 30500 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 183027$, $T_9 := 741^2$,
 $E := \{61001, 61003, \dots, 61015, 61017\}$ or $E := \{61005, 61006, \dots, 61012, 61013\}$
123. **(747, 30996, 31005)** $\Rightarrow 31005 - 30996 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 186003$, $T_9 := 747^2$,
 $E := \{61993, 61995, \dots, 62007, 62009\}$ or $E := \{61997, 61998, \dots, 62004, 62005\}$
124. **(753, 31496, 31505)** $\Rightarrow 31505 - 31496 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 189003$, $T_9 := 753^2$,
 $E := \{62993, 62995, \dots, 63007, 63009\}$ or $E := \{62997, 62998, \dots, 63004, 63005\}$
125. **(759, 32000, 32009)** $\Rightarrow 32009 - 32000 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 192027$, $T_9 := 759^2$,
 $E := \{64001, 64003, \dots, 64015, 64017\}$ or $E := \{64005, 64006, \dots, 64012, 64013\}$
126. **(765, 32508, 32517)** $\Rightarrow 32517 - 32508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 195075$, $T_9 := 765^2$,
 $E := \{65017, 65019, \dots, 65031, 65033\}$ or $E := \{65021, 65022, \dots, 65028, 65029\}$
127. **(771, 33020, 33029)** $\Rightarrow 33029 - 33020 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 198147$, $T_9 := 771^2$,
 $E := \{66041, 66043, \dots, 66055, 66057\}$ or $E := \{66045, 66046, \dots, 66052, 66053\}$
128. **(777, 33536, 33545)** $\Rightarrow 33545 - 33536 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 201243$, $T_9 := 777^2$,
 $E := \{67073, 67075, \dots, 67087, 67089\}$ or $E := \{67077, 67078, \dots, 67084, 67085\}$
129. **(783, 34056, 34065)** $\Rightarrow 34065 - 34056 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 204363$, $T_9 := 783^2$,
 $E := \{68113, 68115, \dots, 68127, 68129\}$ or $E := \{68117, 68118, \dots, 68124, 68125\}$
130. **(789, 34580, 34589)** $\Rightarrow 34589 - 34580 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 207507$, $T_9 := 789^2$,
 $E := \{69161, 69163, \dots, 69175, 69177\}$ or $E := \{69165, 69166, \dots, 69172, 69173\}$
131. **(795, 35108, 35117)** $\Rightarrow 35117 - 35108 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 210675$, $T_9 := 795^2$,
 $E := \{70217, 70219, \dots, 70231, 70233\}$ or $E := \{70221, 70222, \dots, 70228, 70229\}$
132. **(801, 35640, 35649)** $\Rightarrow 35649 - 35640 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 213867$, $T_9 := 801^2$,
 $E := \{71281, 71283, \dots, 71295, 71297\}$ or $E := \{71285, 71286, \dots, 71292, 71293\}$
133. **(807, 36176, 36185)** $\Rightarrow 36185 - 36176 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 217083$, $T_9 := 807^2$,
 $E := \{72353, 72355, \dots, 72367, 72369\}$ or $E := \{72357, 72358, \dots, 72364, 72365\}$

134. **(813, 36716, 36725)** $\Rightarrow 36725 - 36716 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 220323$, $T_9 := 813^2$,
 $E := \{73433, 73435, \dots, 73447, 73449\}$ or $E := \{73437, 73438, \dots, 73444, 73445\}$
135. **(819, 37260, 37269)** $\Rightarrow 37269 - 37260 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 223587$, $T_9 := 819^2$,
 $E := \{74521, 74523, \dots, 74535, 74537\}$ or $E := \{74525, 74526, \dots, 74532, 74533\}$
136. **(825, 37808, 37817)** $\Rightarrow 37817 - 37808 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 226875$, $T_9 := 825^2$,
 $E := \{75617, 75619, \dots, 75631, 75633\}$ or $E := \{75621, 75622, \dots, 75628, 75629\}$
137. **(831, 38360, 38369)** $\Rightarrow 38369 - 38360 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 230187$, $T_9 := 831^2$,
 $E := \{76721, 76723, \dots, 76735, 76737\}$ or $E := \{76725, 76726, \dots, 76732, 76733\}$
138. **(837, 38916, 38925)** $\Rightarrow 38925 - 38916 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 233523$, $T_9 := 837^2$,
 $E := \{77833, 77835, \dots, 77847, 77849\}$ or $E := \{77837, 77838, \dots, 77844, 77845\}$
139. **(843, 39476, 39485)** $\Rightarrow 39485 - 39476 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 236883$, $T_9 := 843^2$,
 $E := \{78953, 78955, \dots, 78967, 78969\}$ or $E := \{78957, 78958, \dots, 78964, 78965\}$
140. **(849, 40040, 40049)** $\Rightarrow 40049 - 40040 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 240267$, $T_9 := 849^2$,
 $E := \{80081, 80083, \dots, 80095, 80097\}$ or $E := \{80085, 80086, \dots, 80092, 80093\}$
141. **(855, 40608, 40617)** $\Rightarrow 40617 - 40608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 243675$, $T_9 := 855^2$,
 $E := \{81217, 81219, \dots, 81231, 81233\}$ or $E := \{81221, 81222, \dots, 81228, 81229\}$
142. **(861, 41180, 41189)** $\Rightarrow 41189 - 41180 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 247107$, $T_9 := 861^2$,
 $E := \{82361, 82363, \dots, 82375, 82377\}$ or $E := \{82365, 82366, \dots, 82372, 82373\}$
143. **(867, 41756, 41765)** $\Rightarrow 41765 - 41756 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 250563$, $T_9 := 867^2$,
 $E := \{83513, 83515, \dots, 83527, 83529\}$ or $E := \{83517, 83518, \dots, 83524, 83525\}$
144. **(873, 42336, 42345)** $\Rightarrow 42345 - 42336 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 254043$, $T_9 := 873^2$,
 $E := \{84673, 84675, \dots, 84687, 84689\}$ or $E := \{84677, 84678, \dots, 84684, 84685\}$
145. **(879, 42920, 42929)** $\Rightarrow 42929 - 42920 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 257547$, $T_9 := 879^2$,
 $E := \{85841, 85843, \dots, 85855, 85857\}$ or $E := \{85845, 85846, \dots, 85852, 85853\}$
146. **(885, 43508, 43517)** $\Rightarrow 43517 - 43508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 261075$, $T_9 := 885^2$,
 $E := \{87017, 87019, \dots, 87031, 87033\}$ or $E := \{87021, 87022, \dots, 87028, 87029\}$
147. **(891, 44100, 44109)** $\Rightarrow 44109 - 44100 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 264627$, $T_9 := 891^2$,
 $E := \{88201, 88203, \dots, 88215, 88217\}$ or $E := \{88205, 88206, \dots, 88212, 88213\}$
148. **(897, 44696, 44705)** $\Rightarrow 44705 - 44696 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 268203$, $T_9 := 897^2$,
 $E := \{89393, 89395, \dots, 89407, 89409\}$ or $E := \{89397, 89398, \dots, 89404, 89405\}$
149. **(903, 45296, 45305)** $\Rightarrow 45305 - 45296 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 271803$, $T_9 := 903^2$,
 $E := \{90593, 90595, \dots, 90607, 90609\}$ or $E := \{90597, 90598, \dots, 90604, 90605\}$
150. **(909, 45900, 45909)** $\Rightarrow 45909 - 45900 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 275427$, $T_9 := 909^2$,
 $E := \{91801, 91803, \dots, 91815, 91817\}$ or $E := \{91805, 91806, \dots, 91812, 91813\}$

151. **(915, 46508, 46517)** $\Rightarrow 46517 - 46508 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 279075$, $T_9 := 915^2$,
 $E := \{93017, 93019, \dots, 93031, 93033\}$ or $E := \{93021, 93022, \dots, 93028, 93029\}$
152. **(921, 47120, 47129)** $\Rightarrow 47129 - 47120 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 282747$, $T_9 := 921^2$,
 $E := \{94241, 94243, \dots, 94255, 94257\}$ or $E := \{94245, 94246, \dots, 94252, 94253\}$
153. **(927, 47736, 47745)** $\Rightarrow 47745 - 47736 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 286443$, $T_9 := 927^2$,
 $E := \{95473, 95475, \dots, 95487, 95489\}$ or $E := \{95477, 95478, \dots, 95484, 95485\}$
154. **(933, 48356, 48365)** $\Rightarrow 48365 - 48356 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 290163$, $T_9 := 933^2$,
 $E := \{96713, 96715, \dots, 96727, 96729\}$ or $E := \{96717, 96718, \dots, 96724, 96725\}$
155. **(939, 48980, 48989)** $\Rightarrow 48989 - 48980 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 293907$, $T_9 := 939^2$,
 $E := \{97961, 97963, \dots, 97975, 97977\}$ or $E := \{97965, 97966, \dots, 97972, 97973\}$
156. **(945, 49608, 49617)** $\Rightarrow 49617 - 49608 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 297675$, $T_9 := 945^2$,
 $E := \{99217, 99219, \dots, 99231, 99233\}$ or $E := \{99221, 99222, \dots, 99228, 99229\}$
157. **(951, 50240, 50249)** $\Rightarrow 50249 - 50240 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 301467$, $T_9 := 951^2$,
 $E := \{100481, 100483, \dots, 100495, 100497\}$ or $E := \{100485, 100486, \dots, 100492, 100493\}$
158. **(957, 50876, 50885)** $\Rightarrow 50885 - 50876 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 305283$, $T_9 := 957^2$,
 $E := \{101753, 101755, \dots, 101767, 101769\}$ or $E := \{101757, 101758, \dots, 101764, 101765\}$
159. **(963, 51516, 51525)** $\Rightarrow 51525 - 51516 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 309123$, $T_9 := 963^2$,
 $E := \{103033, 103035, \dots, 103047, 103049\}$ or $E := \{103037, 103038, \dots, 103044, 103045\}$
160. **(969, 52160, 52169)** $\Rightarrow 52169 - 52160 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 312987$, $T_9 := 969^2$,
 $E := \{104321, 104323, \dots, 104335, 104337\}$ or $E := \{104325, 104326, \dots, 104332, 104333\}$
161. **(975, 52808, 52817)** $\Rightarrow 52817 - 52808 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 316875$, $T_9 := 975^2$,
 $E := \{105617, 105619, \dots, 105631, 105633\}$ or $E := \{105621, 105622, \dots, 105628, 105629\}$
162. **(981, 53460, 53469)** $\Rightarrow 53469 - 53460 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 320787$, $T_9 := 981^2$,
 $E := \{106921, 106923, \dots, 106935, 106937\}$ or $E := \{106925, 106926, \dots, 106932, 106933\}$
163. **(987, 54116, 54125)** $\Rightarrow 54125 - 54116 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 324723$, $T_9 := 987^2$,
 $E := \{108233, 108235, \dots, 108247, 108249\}$ or $E := \{108237, 108238, \dots, 108244, 108245\}$
164. **(993, 54776, 54785)** $\Rightarrow 54785 - 54776 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 328683$, $T_9 := 993^2$,
 $E := \{109553, 109555, \dots, 109567, 109569\}$ or $E := \{109557, 109558, \dots, 109564, 109565\}$
165. **(999, 55440, 55449)** $\Rightarrow 55449 - 55440 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 332667$, $T_9 := 999^2$,
 $E := \{110881, 110883, \dots, 110895, 110897\}$ or $E := \{110885, 110886, \dots, 110892, 110893\}$

Result 4.1. *Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:*

(i) *First Triple:*

$$a = 3^2 + 2 \times 3 = 15 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$a = 6 = 2 \times 3 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, a \in \{15, 21, 27, \dots, 993, 999\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - b = 9 = 3^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_9 := a^2 \quad a \in \{15, 21, 27, \dots, 993, 999\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{3 \times 3} := (2k + 3) \times a, \quad k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 164, 165\}, \text{ i.e., } (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{a^2}{3}, \quad a \in \{15, 21, 27, \dots, 993, 999\}.$$

4.2 Magic Squares of Order 4

This subsection brings magic squares of order 4 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **two** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

1. **(24, 10, 26)** $\Rightarrow 26 - 10 = 4^2, S_{4 \times 4} := 144, T_{16} := 24^2,$
 $E := \{21, 23, \dots, 49, 51\}$
2. **(32, 24, 40)** $\Rightarrow 40 - 24 = 4^2, S_{4 \times 4} := 256, T_{16} := 32^2,$
 $E := \{49, 51, \dots, 77, 79\}$
3. **(40, 42, 58)** $\Rightarrow 58 - 42 = 4^2, S_{4 \times 4} := 400, T_{16} := 40^2,$
 $E := \{85, 87, \dots, 113, 115\}$
4. **(48, 64, 80)** $\Rightarrow 80 - 64 = 4^2, S_{4 \times 4} := 576, T_{16} := 48^2,$
 $E := \{129, 131, \dots, 157, 159\}$
5. **(56, 90, 106)** $\Rightarrow 106 - 90 = 4^2, S_{4 \times 4} := 784, T_{16} := 56^2,$
 $E := \{181, 183, \dots, 209, 211\}$
6. **(64, 120, 136)** $\Rightarrow 136 - 120 = 4^2, S_{4 \times 4} := 1024, T_{16} := 64^2,$
 $E := \{241, 243, \dots, 269, 271\}$
7. **(72, 154, 170)** $\Rightarrow 170 - 154 = 4^2, S_{4 \times 4} := 1296, T_{16} := 72^2,$
 $E := \{309, 311, \dots, 337, 339\}$
8. **(80, 192, 208)** $\Rightarrow 208 - 192 = 4^2, S_{4 \times 4} := 1600, T_{16} := 80^2,$
 $E := \{385, 387, \dots, 413, 415\}$
9. **(88, 234, 250)** $\Rightarrow 250 - 234 = 4^2, S_{4 \times 4} := 1936, T_{16} := 88^2,$
 $E := \{469, 471, \dots, 497, 499\}$
10. **(96, 280, 296)** $\Rightarrow 296 - 280 = 4^2, S_{4 \times 4} := 2304, T_{16} := 96^2,$
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 589, 591\}$

11. **(104, 330, 346)** $\Rightarrow 346 - 330 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 2704$, $T_{16} := 104^2$,
 $E := \{661, 663, \dots, 689, 691\}$
12. **(112, 384, 400)** $\Rightarrow 400 - 384 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 3136$, $T_{16} := 112^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 797, 799\}$
13. **(120, 442, 458)** $\Rightarrow 458 - 442 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 3600$, $T_{16} := 120^2$,
 $E := \{885, 887, \dots, 913, 915\}$
14. **(128, 504, 520)** $\Rightarrow 520 - 504 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 4096$, $T_{16} := 128^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 1037, 1039\}$
15. **(136, 570, 586)** $\Rightarrow 586 - 570 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 4624$, $T_{16} := 136^2$,
 $E := \{1141, 1143, \dots, 1169, 1171\}$
16. **(144, 640, 656)** $\Rightarrow 656 - 640 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 5184$, $T_{16} := 144^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 1309, 1311\}$
17. **(152, 714, 730)** $\Rightarrow 730 - 714 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 5776$, $T_{16} := 152^2$,
 $E := \{1429, 1431, \dots, 1457, 1459\}$
18. **(160, 792, 808)** $\Rightarrow 808 - 792 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 6400$, $T_{16} := 160^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 1613, 1615\}$
19. **(168, 874, 890)** $\Rightarrow 890 - 874 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 7056$, $T_{16} := 168^2$,
 $E := \{1749, 1751, \dots, 1777, 1779\}$
20. **(176, 960, 976)** $\Rightarrow 976 - 960 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 7744$, $T_{16} := 176^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 1949, 1951\}$
21. **(184, 1050, 1066)** $\Rightarrow 1066 - 1050 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 8464$, $T_{16} := 184^2$,
 $E := \{2101, 2103, \dots, 2129, 2131\}$
22. **(192, 1144, 1160)** $\Rightarrow 1160 - 1144 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 9216$, $T_{16} := 192^2$,
 $E := \{2289, 2291, \dots, 2317, 2319\}$
23. **(200, 1242, 1258)** $\Rightarrow 1258 - 1242 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 10000$, $T_{16} := 200^2$,
 $E := \{2485, 2487, \dots, 2513, 2515\}$
24. **(208, 1344, 1360)** $\Rightarrow 1360 - 1344 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 10816$, $T_{16} := 208^2$,
 $E := \{2689, 2691, \dots, 2717, 2719\}$
25. **(216, 1450, 1466)** $\Rightarrow 1466 - 1450 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 11664$, $T_{16} := 216^2$,
 $E := \{2901, 2903, \dots, 2929, 2931\}$
26. **(224, 1560, 1576)** $\Rightarrow 1576 - 1560 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 12544$, $T_{16} := 224^2$,
 $E := \{3121, 3123, \dots, 3149, 3151\}$
27. **(232, 1674, 1690)** $\Rightarrow 1690 - 1674 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 13456$, $T_{16} := 232^2$,
 $E := \{3349, 3351, \dots, 3377, 3379\}$

28. **(240, 1792, 1808)** $\Rightarrow 1808 - 1792 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 14400$, $T_{16} := 240^2$,
 $E := \{3585, 3587, \dots, 3613, 3615\}$
29. **(248, 1914, 1930)** $\Rightarrow 1930 - 1914 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 15376$, $T_{16} := 248^2$,
 $E := \{3829, 3831, \dots, 3857, 3859\}$
30. **(256, 2040, 2056)** $\Rightarrow 2056 - 2040 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 16384$, $T_{16} := 256^2$,
 $E := \{4081, 4083, \dots, 4109, 4111\}$
31. **(264, 2170, 2186)** $\Rightarrow 2186 - 2170 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 17424$, $T_{16} := 264^2$,
 $E := \{4341, 4343, \dots, 4369, 4371\}$
32. **(272, 2304, 2320)** $\Rightarrow 2320 - 2304 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 18496$, $T_{16} := 272^2$,
 $E := \{4609, 4611, \dots, 4637, 4639\}$
33. **(280, 2442, 2458)** $\Rightarrow 2458 - 2442 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 19600$, $T_{16} := 280^2$,
 $E := \{4885, 4887, \dots, 4913, 4915\}$
34. **(288, 2584, 2600)** $\Rightarrow 2600 - 2584 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 20736$, $T_{16} := 288^2$,
 $E := \{5169, 5171, \dots, 5197, 5199\}$
35. **(296, 2730, 2746)** $\Rightarrow 2746 - 2730 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 21904$, $T_{16} := 296^2$,
 $E := \{5461, 5463, \dots, 5489, 5491\}$
36. **(304, 2880, 2896)** $\Rightarrow 2896 - 2880 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 23104$, $T_{16} := 304^2$,
 $E := \{5761, 5763, \dots, 5789, 5791\}$
37. **(312, 3034, 3050)** $\Rightarrow 3050 - 3034 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 24336$, $T_{16} := 312^2$,
 $E := \{6069, 6071, \dots, 6097, 6099\}$
38. **(320, 3192, 3208)** $\Rightarrow 3208 - 3192 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 25600$, $T_{16} := 320^2$,
 $E := \{6385, 6387, \dots, 6413, 6415\}$
39. **(328, 3354, 3370)** $\Rightarrow 3370 - 3354 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 26896$, $T_{16} := 328^2$,
 $E := \{6709, 6711, \dots, 6737, 6739\}$
40. **(336, 3520, 3536)** $\Rightarrow 3536 - 3520 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 28224$, $T_{16} := 336^2$,
 $E := \{7041, 7043, \dots, 7069, 7071\}$
41. **(344, 3690, 3706)** $\Rightarrow 3706 - 3690 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 29584$, $T_{16} := 344^2$,
 $E := \{7381, 7383, \dots, 7409, 7411\}$
42. **(352, 3864, 3880)** $\Rightarrow 3880 - 3864 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 30976$, $T_{16} := 352^2$,
 $E := \{7729, 7731, \dots, 7757, 7759\}$
43. **(360, 4042, 4058)** $\Rightarrow 4058 - 4042 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 32400$, $T_{16} := 360^2$,
 $E := \{8085, 8087, \dots, 8113, 8115\}$
44. **(368, 4224, 4240)** $\Rightarrow 4240 - 4224 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 33856$, $T_{16} := 368^2$,
 $E := \{8449, 8451, \dots, 8477, 8479\}$

45. **(376, 4410, 4426)** $\Rightarrow 4426 - 4410 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 35344$, $T_{16} := 376^2$,
 $E := \{8821, 8823, \dots, 8849, 8851\}$
46. **(384, 4600, 4616)** $\Rightarrow 4616 - 4600 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 36864$, $T_{16} := 384^2$,
 $E := \{9201, 9203, \dots, 9229, 9231\}$
47. **(392, 4794, 4810)** $\Rightarrow 4810 - 4794 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 38416$, $T_{16} := 392^2$,
 $E := \{9589, 9591, \dots, 9617, 9619\}$
48. **(400, 4992, 5008)** $\Rightarrow 5008 - 4992 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 40000$, $T_{16} := 400^2$,
 $E := \{9985, 9987, \dots, 10013, 10015\}$
49. **(408, 5194, 5210)** $\Rightarrow 5210 - 5194 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 41616$, $T_{16} := 408^2$,
 $E := \{10389, 10391, \dots, 10417, 10419\}$
50. **(416, 5400, 5416)** $\Rightarrow 5416 - 5400 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 43264$, $T_{16} := 416^2$,
 $E := \{10801, 10803, \dots, 10829, 10831\}$
51. **(424, 5610, 5626)** $\Rightarrow 5626 - 5610 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 44944$, $T_{16} := 424^2$,
 $E := \{11221, 11223, \dots, 11249, 11251\}$
52. **(432, 5824, 5840)** $\Rightarrow 5840 - 5824 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 46656$, $T_{16} := 432^2$,
 $E := \{11649, 11651, \dots, 11677, 11679\}$
53. **(440, 6042, 6058)** $\Rightarrow 6058 - 6042 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 48400$, $T_{16} := 440^2$,
 $E := \{12085, 12087, \dots, 12113, 12115\}$
54. **(448, 6264, 6280)** $\Rightarrow 6280 - 6264 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 50176$, $T_{16} := 448^2$,
 $E := \{12529, 12531, \dots, 12557, 12559\}$
55. **(456, 6490, 6506)** $\Rightarrow 6506 - 6490 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 51984$, $T_{16} := 456^2$,
 $E := \{12981, 12983, \dots, 13009, 13011\}$
56. **(464, 6720, 6736)** $\Rightarrow 6736 - 6720 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 53824$, $T_{16} := 464^2$,
 $E := \{13441, 13443, \dots, 13469, 13471\}$
57. **(472, 6954, 6970)** $\Rightarrow 6970 - 6954 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 55696$, $T_{16} := 472^2$,
 $E := \{13909, 13911, \dots, 13937, 13939\}$
58. **(480, 7192, 7208)** $\Rightarrow 7208 - 7192 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 57600$, $T_{16} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{14385, 14387, \dots, 14413, 14415\}$
59. **(488, 7434, 7450)** $\Rightarrow 7450 - 7434 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 59536$, $T_{16} := 488^2$,
 $E := \{14869, 14871, \dots, 14897, 14899\}$
60. **(496, 7680, 7696)** $\Rightarrow 7696 - 7680 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 61504$, $T_{16} := 496^2$,
 $E := \{15361, 15363, \dots, 15389, 15391\}$
61. **(504, 7930, 7946)** $\Rightarrow 7946 - 7930 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 63504$, $T_{16} := 504^2$,
 $E := \{15861, 15863, \dots, 15889, 15891\}$

62. **(512, 8184, 8200)** $\Rightarrow 8200 - 8184 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 65536$, $T_{16} := 512^2$,
 $E := \{16369, 16371, \dots, 16397, 16399\}$
63. **(520, 8442, 8458)** $\Rightarrow 8458 - 8442 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 67600$, $T_{16} := 520^2$,
 $E := \{16885, 16887, \dots, 16913, 16915\}$
64. **(528, 8704, 8720)** $\Rightarrow 8720 - 8704 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 69696$, $T_{16} := 528^2$,
 $E := \{17409, 17411, \dots, 17437, 17439\}$
65. **(536, 8970, 8986)** $\Rightarrow 8986 - 8970 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 71824$, $T_{16} := 536^2$,
 $E := \{17941, 17943, \dots, 17969, 17971\}$
66. **(544, 9240, 9256)** $\Rightarrow 9256 - 9240 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 73984$, $T_{16} := 544^2$,
 $E := \{18481, 18483, \dots, 18509, 18511\}$
67. **(552, 9514, 9530)** $\Rightarrow 9530 - 9514 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 76176$, $T_{16} := 552^2$,
 $E := \{19029, 19031, \dots, 19057, 19059\}$
68. **(560, 9792, 9808)** $\Rightarrow 9808 - 9792 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 78400$, $T_{16} := 560^2$,
 $E := \{19585, 19587, \dots, 19613, 19615\}$
69. **(568, 10074, 10090)** $\Rightarrow 10090 - 10074 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 80656$, $T_{16} := 568^2$,
 $E := \{20149, 20151, \dots, 20177, 20179\}$
70. **(576, 10360, 10376)** $\Rightarrow 10376 - 10360 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 82944$, $T_{16} := 576^2$,
 $E := \{20721, 20723, \dots, 20749, 20751\}$
71. **(584, 10650, 10666)** $\Rightarrow 10666 - 10650 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 85264$, $T_{16} := 584^2$,
 $E := \{21301, 21303, \dots, 21329, 21331\}$
72. **(592, 10944, 10960)** $\Rightarrow 10960 - 10944 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 87616$, $T_{16} := 592^2$,
 $E := \{21889, 21891, \dots, 21917, 21919\}$
73. **(600, 11242, 11258)** $\Rightarrow 11258 - 11242 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 90000$, $T_{16} := 600^2$,
 $E := \{22485, 22487, \dots, 22513, 22515\}$
74. **(608, 11544, 11560)** $\Rightarrow 11560 - 11544 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 92416$, $T_{16} := 608^2$,
 $E := \{23089, 23091, \dots, 23117, 23119\}$
75. **(616, 11850, 11866)** $\Rightarrow 11866 - 11850 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 94864$, $T_{16} := 616^2$,
 $E := \{23701, 23703, \dots, 23729, 23731\}$
76. **(624, 12160, 12176)** $\Rightarrow 12176 - 12160 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 97344$, $T_{16} := 624^2$,
 $E := \{24321, 24323, \dots, 24349, 24351\}$
77. **(632, 12474, 12490)** $\Rightarrow 12490 - 12474 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 99856$, $T_{16} := 632^2$,
 $E := \{24949, 24951, \dots, 24977, 24979\}$
78. **(640, 12792, 12808)** $\Rightarrow 12808 - 12792 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 102400$, $T_{16} := 640^2$,
 $E := \{25585, 25587, \dots, 25613, 25615\}$

79. **(648, 13114, 13130)** $\Rightarrow 13130 - 13114 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 104976$, $T_{16} := 648^2$,
 $E := \{26229, 26231, \dots, 26257, 26259\}$
80. **(656, 13440, 13456)** $\Rightarrow 13456 - 13440 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 107584$, $T_{16} := 656^2$,
 $E := \{26881, 26883, \dots, 26909, 26911\}$
81. **(664, 13770, 13786)** $\Rightarrow 13786 - 13770 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 110224$, $T_{16} := 664^2$,
 $E := \{27541, 27543, \dots, 27569, 27571\}$
82. **(672, 14104, 14120)** $\Rightarrow 14120 - 14104 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 112896$, $T_{16} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{28209, 28211, \dots, 28237, 28239\}$
83. **(680, 14442, 14458)** $\Rightarrow 14458 - 14442 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 115600$, $T_{16} := 680^2$,
 $E := \{28885, 28887, \dots, 28913, 28915\}$
84. **(688, 14784, 14800)** $\Rightarrow 14800 - 14784 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 118336$, $T_{16} := 688^2$,
 $E := \{29569, 29571, \dots, 29597, 29599\}$
85. **(696, 15130, 15146)** $\Rightarrow 15146 - 15130 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 121104$, $T_{16} := 696^2$,
 $E := \{30261, 30263, \dots, 30289, 30291\}$
86. **(704, 15480, 15496)** $\Rightarrow 15496 - 15480 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 123904$, $T_{16} := 704^2$,
 $E := \{30961, 30963, \dots, 30989, 30991\}$
87. **(712, 15834, 15850)** $\Rightarrow 15850 - 15834 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 126736$, $T_{16} := 712^2$,
 $E := \{31669, 31671, \dots, 31697, 31699\}$
88. **(720, 16192, 16208)** $\Rightarrow 16208 - 16192 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 129600$, $T_{16} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{32385, 32387, \dots, 32413, 32415\}$
89. **(728, 16554, 16570)** $\Rightarrow 16570 - 16554 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 132496$, $T_{16} := 728^2$,
 $E := \{33109, 33111, \dots, 33137, 33139\}$
90. **(736, 16920, 16936)** $\Rightarrow 16936 - 16920 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 135424$, $T_{16} := 736^2$,
 $E := \{33841, 33843, \dots, 33869, 33871\}$
91. **(744, 17290, 17306)** $\Rightarrow 17306 - 17290 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 138384$, $T_{16} := 744^2$,
 $E := \{34581, 34583, \dots, 34609, 34611\}$
92. **(752, 17664, 17680)** $\Rightarrow 17680 - 17664 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 141376$, $T_{16} := 752^2$,
 $E := \{35329, 35331, \dots, 35357, 35359\}$
93. **(760, 18042, 18058)** $\Rightarrow 18058 - 18042 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 144400$, $T_{16} := 760^2$,
 $E := \{36085, 36087, \dots, 36113, 36115\}$
94. **(768, 18424, 18440)** $\Rightarrow 18440 - 18424 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 147456$, $T_{16} := 768^2$,
 $E := \{36849, 36851, \dots, 36877, 36879\}$
95. **(776, 18810, 18826)** $\Rightarrow 18826 - 18810 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 150544$, $T_{16} := 776^2$,
 $E := \{37621, 37623, \dots, 37649, 37651\}$

96. **(784, 19200, 19216)** $\Rightarrow 19216 - 19200 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 153664$, $T_{16} := 784^2$,
 $E := \{38401, 38403, \dots, 38429, 38431\}$
97. **(792, 19594, 19610)** $\Rightarrow 19610 - 19594 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 156816$, $T_{16} := 792^2$,
 $E := \{39189, 39191, \dots, 39217, 39219\}$
98. **(800, 19992, 20008)** $\Rightarrow 20008 - 19992 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 160000$, $T_{16} := 800^2$,
 $E := \{39985, 39987, \dots, 40013, 40015\}$
99. **(808, 20394, 20410)** $\Rightarrow 20410 - 20394 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 163216$, $T_{16} := 808^2$,
 $E := \{40789, 40791, \dots, 40817, 40819\}$
100. **(816, 20800, 20816)** $\Rightarrow 20816 - 20800 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 166464$, $T_{16} := 816^2$,
 $E := \{41601, 41603, \dots, 41629, 41631\}$
101. **(824, 21210, 21226)** $\Rightarrow 21226 - 21210 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 169744$, $T_{16} := 824^2$,
 $E := \{42421, 42423, \dots, 42449, 42451\}$
102. **(832, 21624, 21640)** $\Rightarrow 21640 - 21624 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 173056$, $T_{16} := 832^2$,
 $E := \{43249, 43251, \dots, 43277, 43279\}$
103. **(840, 22042, 22058)** $\Rightarrow 22058 - 22042 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 176400$, $T_{16} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{44085, 44087, \dots, 44113, 44115\}$
104. **(848, 22464, 22480)** $\Rightarrow 22480 - 22464 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 179776$, $T_{16} := 848^2$,
 $E := \{44929, 44931, \dots, 44957, 44959\}$
105. **(856, 22890, 22906)** $\Rightarrow 22906 - 22890 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 183184$, $T_{16} := 856^2$,
 $E := \{45781, 45783, \dots, 45809, 45811\}$
106. **(864, 23320, 23336)** $\Rightarrow 23336 - 23320 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 186624$, $T_{16} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{46641, 46643, \dots, 46669, 46671\}$
107. **(872, 23754, 23770)** $\Rightarrow 23770 - 23754 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 190096$, $T_{16} := 872^2$,
 $E := \{47509, 47511, \dots, 47537, 47539\}$
108. **(880, 24192, 24208)** $\Rightarrow 24208 - 24192 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 193600$, $T_{16} := 880^2$,
 $E := \{48385, 48387, \dots, 48413, 48415\}$
109. **(888, 24634, 24650)** $\Rightarrow 24650 - 24634 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 197136$, $T_{16} := 888^2$,
 $E := \{49269, 49271, \dots, 49297, 49299\}$
110. **(896, 25080, 25096)** $\Rightarrow 25096 - 25080 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 200704$, $T_{16} := 896^2$,
 $E := \{50161, 50163, \dots, 50189, 50191\}$
111. **(904, 25530, 25546)** $\Rightarrow 25546 - 25530 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 204304$, $T_{16} := 904^2$,
 $E := \{51061, 51063, \dots, 51089, 51091\}$
112. **(912, 25984, 26000)** $\Rightarrow 26000 - 25984 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 207936$, $T_{16} := 912^2$,
 $E := \{51969, 51971, \dots, 51997, 51999\}$

113. **(920, 26442, 26458)** $\Rightarrow 26458 - 26442 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 211600$, $T_{16} := 920^2$,
 $E := \{52885, 52887, \dots, 52913, 52915\}$
114. **(928, 26904, 26920)** $\Rightarrow 26920 - 26904 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 215296$, $T_{16} := 928^2$,
 $E := \{53809, 53811, \dots, 53837, 53839\}$
115. **(936, 27370, 27386)** $\Rightarrow 27386 - 27370 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 219024$, $T_{16} := 936^2$,
 $E := \{54741, 54743, \dots, 54769, 54771\}$
116. **(944, 27840, 27856)** $\Rightarrow 27856 - 27840 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 222784$, $T_{16} := 944^2$,
 $E := \{55681, 55683, \dots, 55709, 55711\}$
117. **(952, 28314, 28330)** $\Rightarrow 28330 - 28314 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 226576$, $T_{16} := 952^2$,
 $E := \{56629, 56631, \dots, 56657, 56659\}$
118. **(960, 28792, 28808)** $\Rightarrow 28808 - 28792 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 230400$, $T_{16} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{57585, 57587, \dots, 57613, 57615\}$
119. **(968, 29274, 29290)** $\Rightarrow 29290 - 29274 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 234256$, $T_{16} := 968^2$,
 $E := \{58549, 58551, \dots, 58577, 58579\}$
120. **(976, 29760, 29776)** $\Rightarrow 29776 - 29760 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 238144$, $T_{16} := 976^2$,
 $E := \{59521, 59523, \dots, 59549, 59551\}$
121. **(984, 30250, 30266)** $\Rightarrow 30266 - 30250 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 242064$, $T_{16} := 984^2$,
 $E := \{60501, 60503, \dots, 60529, 60531\}$
122. **(992, 30744, 30760)** $\Rightarrow 30760 - 30744 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 246016$, $T_{16} := 992^2$,
 $E := \{61489, 61491, \dots, 61517, 61519\}$
123. **(1000, 31242, 31258)** $\Rightarrow 31258 - 31242 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 250000$, $T_{16} := 1000^2$,
 $E := \{62485, 62487, \dots, 62513, 62515\}$

Result 4.2. Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:

(i) *First Triple:*

$$a = 4^2 + 2 \times 4 = 24 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$a = 8 = 2 \times 4 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, a \in \{24, 32, 40, \dots, 992, 1000\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - b = 16 = 4^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{16} := a^2, a \in \{24, 32, 40, \dots, 992, 1000\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{4 \times 4} := a \times (2k + 4), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 122, 123\}, \text{i.e., } a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{a^2}{4}, a \in \{24, 32, \dots, 992, 1000\}.$$

4.3 Magic Squares of Order 5

This subsection brings magic squares of order 5 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **three** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

1. **(35, 12, 37)** $\Rightarrow 37 - 12 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 245$, $T_{25} := 35^2$,
 $E := \{25, 27, \dots, 71, 73\}$ or $E := \{37, 38, \dots, 60, 61\}$
2. **(45, 28, 53)** $\Rightarrow 53 - 28 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 405$, $T_{25} := 45^2$,
 $E := \{57, 59, \dots, 103, 105\}$ or $E := \{69, 70, \dots, 92, 93\}$
3. **(55, 48, 73)** $\Rightarrow 73 - 48 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 605$, $T_{25} := 55^2$,
 $E := \{97, 99, \dots, 143, 145\}$ or $E := \{109, 110, \dots, 132, 133\}$
4. **(65, 72, 97)** $\Rightarrow 97 - 72 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 845$, $T_{25} := 65^2$,
 $E := \{145, 147, \dots, 191, 193\}$ or $E := \{157, 158, \dots, 180, 181\}$
5. **(75, 100, 125)** $\Rightarrow 125 - 100 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 1125$, $T_{25} := 75^2$,
 $E := \{201, 203, \dots, 247, 249\}$ or $E := \{213, 214, \dots, 236, 237\}$
6. **(85, 132, 157)** $\Rightarrow 157 - 132 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 1445$, $T_{25} := 85^2$,
 $E := \{265, 267, \dots, 311, 313\}$ or $E := \{277, 278, \dots, 300, 301\}$
7. **(95, 168, 193)** $\Rightarrow 193 - 168 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 1805$, $T_{25} := 95^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 383, 385\}$ or $E := \{349, 350, \dots, 372, 373\}$
8. **(105, 208, 233)** $\Rightarrow 233 - 208 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 2205$, $T_{25} := 105^2$,
 $E := \{417, 419, \dots, 463, 465\}$ or $E := \{429, 430, \dots, 452, 453\}$
9. **(115, 252, 277)** $\Rightarrow 277 - 252 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 2645$, $T_{25} := 115^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 551, 553\}$ or $E := \{517, 518, \dots, 540, 541\}$
10. **(125, 300, 325)** $\Rightarrow 325 - 300 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 3125$, $T_{25} := 125^2$,
 $E := \{601, 603, \dots, 647, 649\}$ or $E := \{613, 614, \dots, 636, 637\}$
11. **(135, 352, 377)** $\Rightarrow 377 - 352 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 3645$, $T_{25} := 135^2$,
 $E := \{705, 707, \dots, 751, 753\}$ or $E := \{717, 718, \dots, 740, 741\}$
12. **(145, 408, 433)** $\Rightarrow 433 - 408 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 4205$, $T_{25} := 145^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 863, 865\}$ or $E := \{829, 830, \dots, 852, 853\}$
13. **(155, 468, 493)** $\Rightarrow 493 - 468 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 4805$, $T_{25} := 155^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 983, 985\}$ or $E := \{949, 950, \dots, 972, 973\}$
14. **(165, 532, 557)** $\Rightarrow 557 - 532 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 5445$, $T_{25} := 165^2$,
 $E := \{1065, 1067, \dots, 1111, 1113\}$ or $E := \{1077, 1078, \dots, 1100, 1101\}$

15. **(175, 600, 625)** $\Rightarrow 625 - 600 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 6125$, $T_{25} := 175^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 1247, 1249\}$ or $E := \{1213, 1214, \dots, 1236, 1237\}$
16. **(185, 672, 697)** $\Rightarrow 697 - 672 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 6845$, $T_{25} := 185^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 1391, 1393\}$ or $E := \{1357, 1358, \dots, 1380, 1381\}$
17. **(195, 748, 773)** $\Rightarrow 773 - 748 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 7605$, $T_{25} := 195^2$,
 $E := \{1497, 1499, \dots, 1543, 1545\}$ or $E := \{1509, 1510, \dots, 1532, 1533\}$
18. **(205, 828, 853)** $\Rightarrow 853 - 828 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 8405$, $T_{25} := 205^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 1703, 1705\}$ or $E := \{1669, 1670, \dots, 1692, 1693\}$
19. **(215, 912, 937)** $\Rightarrow 937 - 912 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 9245$, $T_{25} := 215^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 1871, 1873\}$ or $E := \{1837, 1838, \dots, 1860, 1861\}$
20. **(225, 1000, 1025)** $\Rightarrow 1025 - 1000 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 10125$, $T_{25} := 225^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 2047, 2049\}$ or $E := \{2013, 2014, \dots, 2036, 2037\}$
21. **(235, 1092, 1117)** $\Rightarrow 1117 - 1092 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 11045$, $T_{25} := 235^2$,
 $E := \{2185, 2187, \dots, 2231, 2233\}$ or $E := \{2197, 2198, \dots, 2220, 2221\}$
22. **(245, 1188, 1213)** $\Rightarrow 1213 - 1188 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 12005$, $T_{25} := 245^2$,
 $E := \{2377, 2379, \dots, 2423, 2425\}$ or $E := \{2389, 2390, \dots, 2412, 2413\}$
23. **(255, 1288, 1313)** $\Rightarrow 1313 - 1288 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 13005$, $T_{25} := 255^2$,
 $E := \{2577, 2579, \dots, 2623, 2625\}$ or $E := \{2589, 2590, \dots, 2612, 2613\}$
24. **(265, 1392, 1417)** $\Rightarrow 1417 - 1392 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 14045$, $T_{25} := 265^2$,
 $E := \{2785, 2787, \dots, 2831, 2833\}$ or $E := \{2797, 2798, \dots, 2820, 2821\}$
25. **(275, 1500, 1525)** $\Rightarrow 1525 - 1500 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 15125$, $T_{25} := 275^2$,
 $E := \{3001, 3003, \dots, 3047, 3049\}$ or $E := \{3013, 3014, \dots, 3036, 3037\}$
26. **(285, 1612, 1637)** $\Rightarrow 1637 - 1612 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 16245$, $T_{25} := 285^2$,
 $E := \{3225, 3227, \dots, 3271, 3273\}$ or $E := \{3237, 3238, \dots, 3260, 3261\}$
27. **(295, 1728, 1753)** $\Rightarrow 1753 - 1728 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 17405$, $T_{25} := 295^2$,
 $E := \{3457, 3459, \dots, 3503, 3505\}$ or $E := \{3469, 3470, \dots, 3492, 3493\}$
28. **(305, 1848, 1873)** $\Rightarrow 1873 - 1848 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 18605$, $T_{25} := 305^2$,
 $E := \{3697, 3699, \dots, 3743, 3745\}$ or $E := \{3709, 3710, \dots, 3732, 3733\}$
29. **(315, 1972, 1997)** $\Rightarrow 1997 - 1972 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 19845$, $T_{25} := 315^2$,
 $E := \{3945, 3947, \dots, 3991, 3993\}$ or $E := \{3957, 3958, \dots, 3980, 3981\}$
30. **(325, 2100, 2125)** $\Rightarrow 2125 - 2100 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 21125$, $T_{25} := 325^2$,
 $E := \{4201, 4203, \dots, 4247, 4249\}$ or $E := \{4213, 4214, \dots, 4236, 4237\}$
31. **(335, 2232, 2257)** $\Rightarrow 2257 - 2232 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 22445$, $T_{25} := 335^2$,
 $E := \{4465, 4467, \dots, 4511, 4513\}$ or $E := \{4477, 4478, \dots, 4500, 4501\}$

32. **(345, 2368, 2393)** $\Rightarrow 2393 - 2368 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 23805$, $T_{25} := 345^2$,
 $E := \{4737, 4739, \dots, 4783, 4785\}$ or $E := \{4749, 4750, \dots, 4772, 4773\}$
33. **(355, 2508, 2533)** $\Rightarrow 2533 - 2508 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 25205$, $T_{25} := 355^2$,
 $E := \{5017, 5019, \dots, 5063, 5065\}$ or $E := \{5029, 5030, \dots, 5052, 5053\}$
34. **(365, 2652, 2677)** $\Rightarrow 2677 - 2652 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 26645$, $T_{25} := 365^2$,
 $E := \{5305, 5307, \dots, 5351, 5353\}$ or $E := \{5317, 5318, \dots, 5340, 5341\}$
35. **(375, 2800, 2825)** $\Rightarrow 2825 - 2800 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 28125$, $T_{25} := 375^2$,
 $E := \{5601, 5603, \dots, 5647, 5649\}$ or $E := \{5613, 5614, \dots, 5636, 5637\}$
36. **(385, 2952, 2977)** $\Rightarrow 2977 - 2952 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 29645$, $T_{25} := 385^2$,
 $E := \{5905, 5907, \dots, 5951, 5953\}$ or $E := \{5917, 5918, \dots, 5940, 5941\}$
37. **(395, 3108, 3133)** $\Rightarrow 3133 - 3108 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 31205$, $T_{25} := 395^2$,
 $E := \{6217, 6219, \dots, 6263, 6265\}$ or $E := \{6229, 6230, \dots, 6252, 6253\}$
38. **(405, 3268, 3293)** $\Rightarrow 3293 - 3268 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 32805$, $T_{25} := 405^2$,
 $E := \{6537, 6539, \dots, 6583, 6585\}$ or $E := \{6549, 6550, \dots, 6572, 6573\}$
39. **(415, 3432, 3457)** $\Rightarrow 3457 - 3432 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 34445$, $T_{25} := 415^2$,
 $E := \{6865, 6867, \dots, 6911, 6913\}$ or $E := \{6877, 6878, \dots, 6900, 6901\}$
40. **(425, 3600, 3625)** $\Rightarrow 3625 - 3600 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 36125$, $T_{25} := 425^2$,
 $E := \{7201, 7203, \dots, 7247, 7249\}$ or $E := \{7213, 7214, \dots, 7236, 7237\}$
41. **(435, 3772, 3797)** $\Rightarrow 3797 - 3772 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 37845$, $T_{25} := 435^2$,
 $E := \{7545, 7547, \dots, 7591, 7593\}$ or $E := \{7557, 7558, \dots, 7580, 7581\}$
42. **(445, 3948, 3973)** $\Rightarrow 3973 - 3948 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 39605$, $T_{25} := 445^2$,
 $E := \{7897, 7899, \dots, 7943, 7945\}$ or $E := \{7909, 7910, \dots, 7932, 7933\}$
43. **(455, 4128, 4153)** $\Rightarrow 4153 - 4128 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 41405$, $T_{25} := 455^2$,
 $E := \{8257, 8259, \dots, 8303, 8305\}$ or $E := \{8269, 8270, \dots, 8292, 8293\}$
44. **(465, 4312, 4337)** $\Rightarrow 4337 - 4312 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 43245$, $T_{25} := 465^2$,
 $E := \{8625, 8627, \dots, 8671, 8673\}$ or $E := \{8637, 8638, \dots, 8660, 8661\}$
45. **(475, 4500, 4525)** $\Rightarrow 4525 - 4500 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 45125$, $T_{25} := 475^2$,
 $E := \{9001, 9003, \dots, 9047, 9049\}$ or $E := \{9013, 9014, \dots, 9036, 9037\}$
46. **(485, 4692, 4717)** $\Rightarrow 4717 - 4692 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 47045$, $T_{25} := 485^2$,
 $E := \{9385, 9387, \dots, 9431, 9433\}$ or $E := \{9397, 9398, \dots, 9420, 9421\}$
47. **(495, 4888, 4913)** $\Rightarrow 4913 - 4888 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 49005$, $T_{25} := 495^2$,
 $E := \{9777, 9779, \dots, 9823, 9825\}$ or $E := \{9789, 9790, \dots, 9812, 9813\}$
48. **(505, 5088, 5113)** $\Rightarrow 5113 - 5088 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 51005$, $T_{25} := 505^2$,
 $E := \{10177, 10179, \dots, 10223, 10225\}$ or $E := \{10189, 10190, \dots, 10212, 10213\}$

49. **(515, 5292, 5317)** $\Rightarrow 5317 - 5292 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 53045$, $T_{25} := 515^2$,
 $E := \{10585, 10587, \dots, 10631, 10633\}$ or $E := \{10597, 10598, \dots, 10620, 10621\}$
50. **(525, 5500, 5525)** $\Rightarrow 5525 - 5500 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 55125$, $T_{25} := 525^2$,
 $E := \{11001, 11003, \dots, 11047, 11049\}$ or $E := \{11013, 11014, \dots, 11036, 11037\}$
51. **(535, 5712, 5737)** $\Rightarrow 5737 - 5712 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 57245$, $T_{25} := 535^2$,
 $E := \{11425, 11427, \dots, 11471, 11473\}$ or $E := \{11437, 11438, \dots, 11460, 11461\}$
52. **(545, 5928, 5953)** $\Rightarrow 5953 - 5928 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 59405$, $T_{25} := 545^2$,
 $E := \{11857, 11859, \dots, 11903, 11905\}$ or $E := \{11869, 11870, \dots, 11892, 11893\}$
53. **(555, 6148, 6173)** $\Rightarrow 6173 - 6148 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 61605$, $T_{25} := 555^2$,
 $E := \{12297, 12299, \dots, 12343, 12345\}$ or $E := \{12309, 12310, \dots, 12332, 12333\}$
54. **(565, 6372, 6397)** $\Rightarrow 6397 - 6372 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 63845$, $T_{25} := 565^2$,
 $E := \{12745, 12747, \dots, 12791, 12793\}$ or $E := \{12757, 12758, \dots, 12780, 12781\}$
55. **(575, 6600, 6625)** $\Rightarrow 6625 - 6600 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 66125$, $T_{25} := 575^2$,
 $E := \{13201, 13203, \dots, 13247, 13249\}$ or $E := \{13213, 13214, \dots, 13236, 13237\}$
56. **(585, 6832, 6857)** $\Rightarrow 6857 - 6832 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 68445$, $T_{25} := 585^2$,
 $E := \{13665, 13667, \dots, 13711, 13713\}$ or $E := \{13677, 13678, \dots, 13700, 13701\}$
57. **(595, 7068, 7093)** $\Rightarrow 7093 - 7068 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 70805$, $T_{25} := 595^2$,
 $E := \{14137, 14139, \dots, 14183, 14185\}$ or $E := \{14149, 14150, \dots, 14172, 14173\}$
58. **(605, 7308, 7333)** $\Rightarrow 7333 - 7308 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 73205$, $T_{25} := 605^2$,
 $E := \{14617, 14619, \dots, 14663, 14665\}$ or $E := \{14629, 14630, \dots, 14652, 14653\}$
59. **(615, 7552, 7577)** $\Rightarrow 7577 - 7552 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 75645$, $T_{25} := 615^2$,
 $E := \{15105, 15107, \dots, 15151, 15153\}$ or $E := \{15117, 15118, \dots, 15140, 15141\}$
60. **(625, 7800, 7825)** $\Rightarrow 7825 - 7800 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 78125$, $T_{25} := 625^2$,
 $E := \{15601, 15603, \dots, 15647, 15649\}$ or $E := \{15613, 15614, \dots, 15636, 15637\}$
61. **(635, 8052, 8077)** $\Rightarrow 8077 - 8052 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 80645$, $T_{25} := 635^2$,
 $E := \{16105, 16107, \dots, 16151, 16153\}$ or $E := \{16117, 16118, \dots, 16140, 16141\}$
62. **(645, 8308, 8333)** $\Rightarrow 8333 - 8308 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 83205$, $T_{25} := 645^2$,
 $E := \{16617, 16619, \dots, 16663, 16665\}$ or $E := \{16629, 16630, \dots, 16652, 16653\}$
63. **(655, 8568, 8593)** $\Rightarrow 8593 - 8568 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 85805$, $T_{25} := 655^2$,
 $E := \{17137, 17139, \dots, 17183, 17185\}$ or $E := \{17149, 17150, \dots, 17172, 17173\}$
64. **(665, 8832, 8857)** $\Rightarrow 8857 - 8832 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 88445$, $T_{25} := 665^2$,
 $E := \{17665, 17667, \dots, 17711, 17713\}$ or $E := \{17677, 17678, \dots, 17700, 17701\}$
65. **(675, 9100, 9125)** $\Rightarrow 9125 - 9100 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 91125$, $T_{25} := 675^2$,
 $E := \{18201, 18203, \dots, 18247, 18249\}$ or $E := \{18213, 18214, \dots, 18236, 18237\}$

66. **(685, 9372, 9397)** $\Rightarrow 9397 - 9372 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 93845$, $T_{25} := 685^2$,
 $E := \{18745, 18747, \dots, 18791, 18793\}$ or $E := \{18757, 18758, \dots, 18780, 18781\}$
67. **(695, 9648, 9673)** $\Rightarrow 9673 - 9648 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 96605$, $T_{25} := 695^2$,
 $E := \{19297, 19299, \dots, 19343, 19345\}$ or $E := \{19309, 19310, \dots, 19332, 19333\}$
68. **(705, 9928, 9953)** $\Rightarrow 9953 - 9928 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 99405$, $T_{25} := 705^2$,
 $E := \{19857, 19859, \dots, 19903, 19905\}$ or $E := \{19869, 19870, \dots, 19892, 19893\}$
69. **(715, 10212, 10237)** $\Rightarrow 10237 - 10212 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 102245$, $T_{25} := 715^2$,
 $E := \{20425, 20427, \dots, 20471, 20473\}$ or $E := \{20437, 20438, \dots, 20460, 20461\}$
70. **(725, 10500, 10525)** $\Rightarrow 10525 - 10500 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 105125$, $T_{25} := 725^2$,
 $E := \{21001, 21003, \dots, 21047, 21049\}$ or $E := \{21013, 21014, \dots, 21036, 21037\}$
71. **(735, 10792, 10817)** $\Rightarrow 10817 - 10792 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 108045$, $T_{25} := 735^2$,
 $E := \{21585, 21587, \dots, 21631, 21633\}$ or $E := \{21597, 21598, \dots, 21620, 21621\}$
72. **(745, 11088, 11113)** $\Rightarrow 11113 - 11088 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 111005$, $T_{25} := 745^2$,
 $E := \{22177, 22179, \dots, 22223, 22225\}$ or $E := \{22189, 22190, \dots, 22212, 22213\}$
73. **(755, 11388, 11413)** $\Rightarrow 11413 - 11388 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 114005$, $T_{25} := 755^2$,
 $E := \{22777, 22779, \dots, 22823, 22825\}$ or $E := \{22789, 22790, \dots, 22812, 22813\}$
74. **(765, 11692, 11717)** $\Rightarrow 11717 - 11692 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 117045$, $T_{25} := 765^2$,
 $E := \{23385, 23387, \dots, 23431, 23433\}$ or $E := \{23397, 23398, \dots, 23420, 23421\}$
75. **(775, 12000, 12025)** $\Rightarrow 12025 - 12000 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 120125$, $T_{25} := 775^2$,
 $E := \{24001, 24003, \dots, 24047, 24049\}$ or $E := \{24013, 24014, \dots, 24036, 24037\}$
76. **(785, 12312, 12337)** $\Rightarrow 12337 - 12312 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 123245$, $T_{25} := 785^2$,
 $E := \{24625, 24627, \dots, 24671, 24673\}$ or $E := \{24637, 24638, \dots, 24660, 24661\}$
77. **(795, 12628, 12653)** $\Rightarrow 12653 - 12628 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 126405$, $T_{25} := 795^2$,
 $E := \{25257, 25259, \dots, 25303, 25305\}$ or $E := \{25269, 25270, \dots, 25292, 25293\}$
78. **(805, 12948, 12973)** $\Rightarrow 12973 - 12948 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 129605$, $T_{25} := 805^2$,
 $E := \{25897, 25899, \dots, 25943, 25945\}$ or $E := \{25909, 25910, \dots, 25932, 25933\}$
79. **(815, 13272, 13297)** $\Rightarrow 13297 - 13272 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 132845$, $T_{25} := 815^2$,
 $E := \{26545, 26547, \dots, 26591, 26593\}$ or $E := \{26557, 26558, \dots, 26580, 26581\}$
80. **(825, 13600, 13625)** $\Rightarrow 13625 - 13600 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 136125$, $T_{25} := 825^2$,
 $E := \{27201, 27203, \dots, 27247, 27249\}$ or $E := \{27213, 27214, \dots, 27236, 27237\}$
81. **(835, 13932, 13957)** $\Rightarrow 13957 - 13932 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 139445$, $T_{25} := 835^2$,
 $E := \{27865, 27867, \dots, 27911, 27913\}$ or $E := \{27877, 27878, \dots, 27900, 27901\}$
82. **(845, 14268, 14293)** $\Rightarrow 14293 - 14268 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 142805$, $T_{25} := 845^2$,
 $E := \{28537, 28539, \dots, 28583, 28585\}$ or $E := \{28549, 28550, \dots, 28572, 28573\}$

83. **(855, 14608, 14633)** $\Rightarrow 14633 - 14608 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 146205$, $T_{25} := 855^2$,
 $E := \{29217, 29219, \dots, 29263, 29265\}$ or $E := \{29229, 29230, \dots, 29252, 29253\}$
84. **(865, 14952, 14977)** $\Rightarrow 14977 - 14952 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 149645$, $T_{25} := 865^2$,
 $E := \{29905, 29907, \dots, 29951, 29953\}$ or $E := \{29917, 29918, \dots, 29940, 29941\}$
85. **(875, 15300, 15325)** $\Rightarrow 15325 - 15300 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 153125$, $T_{25} := 875^2$,
 $E := \{30601, 30603, \dots, 30647, 30649\}$ or $E := \{30613, 30614, \dots, 30636, 30637\}$
86. **(885, 15652, 15677)** $\Rightarrow 15677 - 15652 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 156645$, $T_{25} := 885^2$,
 $E := \{31305, 31307, \dots, 31351, 31353\}$ or $E := \{31317, 31318, \dots, 31340, 31341\}$
87. **(895, 16008, 16033)** $\Rightarrow 16033 - 16008 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 160205$, $T_{25} := 895^2$,
 $E := \{32017, 32019, \dots, 32063, 32065\}$ or $E := \{32029, 32030, \dots, 32052, 32053\}$
88. **(905, 16368, 16393)** $\Rightarrow 16393 - 16368 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 163805$, $T_{25} := 905^2$,
 $E := \{32737, 32739, \dots, 32783, 32785\}$ or $E := \{32749, 32750, \dots, 32772, 32773\}$
89. **(915, 16732, 16757)** $\Rightarrow 16757 - 16732 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 167445$, $T_{25} := 915^2$,
 $E := \{33465, 33467, \dots, 33511, 33513\}$ or $E := \{33477, 33478, \dots, 33500, 33501\}$
90. **(925, 17100, 17125)** $\Rightarrow 17125 - 17100 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 171125$, $T_{25} := 925^2$,
 $E := \{34201, 34203, \dots, 34247, 34249\}$ or $E := \{34213, 34214, \dots, 34236, 34237\}$
91. **(935, 17472, 17497)** $\Rightarrow 17497 - 17472 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 174845$, $T_{25} := 935^2$,
 $E := \{34945, 34947, \dots, 34991, 34993\}$ or $E := \{34957, 34958, \dots, 34980, 34981\}$
92. **(945, 17848, 17873)** $\Rightarrow 17873 - 17848 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 178605$, $T_{25} := 945^2$,
 $E := \{35697, 35699, \dots, 35743, 35745\}$ or $E := \{35709, 35710, \dots, 35732, 35733\}$
93. **(955, 18228, 18253)** $\Rightarrow 18253 - 18228 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 182405$, $T_{25} := 955^2$,
 $E := \{36457, 36459, \dots, 36503, 36505\}$ or $E := \{36469, 36470, \dots, 36492, 36493\}$
94. **(965, 18612, 18637)** $\Rightarrow 18637 - 18612 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 186245$, $T_{25} := 965^2$,
 $E := \{37225, 37227, \dots, 37271, 37273\}$ or $E := \{37237, 37238, \dots, 37260, 37261\}$
95. **(975, 19000, 19025)** $\Rightarrow 19025 - 19000 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 190125$, $T_{25} := 975^2$,
 $E := \{38001, 38003, \dots, 38047, 38049\}$ or $E := \{38013, 38014, \dots, 38036, 38037\}$
96. **(985, 19392, 19417)** $\Rightarrow 19417 - 19392 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 194045$, $T_{25} := 985^2$,
 $E := \{38785, 38787, \dots, 38831, 38833\}$ or $E := \{38797, 38798, \dots, 38820, 38821\}$
97. **(995, 19788, 19813)** $\Rightarrow 19813 - 19788 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 198005$, $T_{25} := 995^2$,
 $E := \{39577, 39579, \dots, 39623, 39625\}$ or $E := \{39589, 39590, \dots, 39612, 39613\}$

Result 4.3. Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:

(i) *First Triple:*

$$a = 5^2 + 2 \times 5 = 35 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Between Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$a = 10 = 2 \times 5 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, a \in \{35, 45, 55, \dots, 985, 995\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - b = 25 = 5^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{25} := a^2, a \in \{35, 45, 55, \dots, 985, 995\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{5 \times 5} := (2k + 5) \times a, k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 96, 97\}, \text{i.e., } a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{a^2}{5}, a \in \{35, 45, 55, \dots, 985, 995\};$$

4.4 Magic Squares of Order 6

This subsection brings magic squares of order 6 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **four** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

1. **(48, 14, 50)** $\Rightarrow 50 - 14 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 384, T_{36} := 48^2,$
 $E := \{29, 31, \dots, 97, 99\}$
2. **(60, 32, 68)** $\Rightarrow 68 - 32 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 600, T_{36} := 60^2,$
 $E := \{65, 67, \dots, 133, 135\}$
3. **(72, 54, 90)** $\Rightarrow 90 - 54 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 864, T_{36} := 72^2,$
 $E := \{109, 111, \dots, 177, 179\}$
4. **(84, 80, 116)** $\Rightarrow 116 - 80 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 1176, T_{36} := 84^2,$
 $E := \{161, 163, \dots, 229, 231\}$
5. **(96, 110, 146)** $\Rightarrow 146 - 110 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 1536, T_{36} := 96^2,$
 $E := \{221, 223, \dots, 289, 291\}$
6. **(108, 144, 180)** $\Rightarrow 180 - 144 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 1944, T_{36} := 108^2,$
 $E := \{289, 291, \dots, 357, 359\}$
7. **(120, 182, 218)** $\Rightarrow 218 - 182 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 2400, T_{36} := 120^2,$
 $E := \{365, 367, \dots, 433, 435\}$
8. **(132, 224, 260)** $\Rightarrow 260 - 224 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 2904, T_{36} := 132^2,$
 $E := \{449, 451, \dots, 517, 519\}$
9. **(144, 270, 306)** $\Rightarrow 306 - 270 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 3456, T_{36} := 144^2,$
 $E := \{541, 543, \dots, 609, 611\}$
10. **(156, 320, 356)** $\Rightarrow 356 - 320 = 6^2, S_{6 \times 6} := 4056, T_{36} := 156^2,$
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 709, 711\}$

11. **(168, 374, 410)** $\Rightarrow 410 - 374 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 4704$, $T_{36} := 168^2$,
 $E := \{749, 751, \dots, 817, 819\}$
12. **(180, 432, 468)** $\Rightarrow 468 - 432 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 5400$, $T_{36} := 180^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 933, 935\}$
13. **(192, 494, 530)** $\Rightarrow 530 - 494 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 6144$, $T_{36} := 192^2$,
 $E := \{989, 991, \dots, 1057, 1059\}$
14. **(204, 560, 596)** $\Rightarrow 596 - 560 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 6936$, $T_{36} := 204^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 1189, 1191\}$
15. **(216, 630, 666)** $\Rightarrow 666 - 630 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 7776$, $T_{36} := 216^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 1329, 1331\}$
16. **(228, 704, 740)** $\Rightarrow 740 - 704 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 8664$, $T_{36} := 228^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 1477, 1479\}$
17. **(240, 782, 818)** $\Rightarrow 818 - 782 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 9600$, $T_{36} := 240^2$,
 $E := \{1565, 1567, \dots, 1633, 1635\}$
18. **(252, 864, 900)** $\Rightarrow 900 - 864 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 10584$, $T_{36} := 252^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 1797, 1799\}$
19. **(264, 950, 986)** $\Rightarrow 986 - 950 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 11616$, $T_{36} := 264^2$,
 $E := \{1901, 1903, \dots, 1969, 1971\}$
20. **(276, 1040, 1076)** $\Rightarrow 1076 - 1040 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 12696$, $T_{36} := 276^2$,
 $E := \{2081, 2083, \dots, 2149, 2151\}$
21. **(288, 1134, 1170)** $\Rightarrow 1170 - 1134 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 13824$, $T_{36} := 288^2$,
 $E := \{2269, 2271, \dots, 2337, 2339\}$
22. **(300, 1232, 1268)** $\Rightarrow 1268 - 1232 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 15000$, $T_{36} := 300^2$,
 $E := \{2465, 2467, \dots, 2533, 2535\}$
23. **(312, 1334, 1370)** $\Rightarrow 1370 - 1334 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 16224$, $T_{36} := 312^2$,
 $E := \{2669, 2671, \dots, 2737, 2739\}$
24. **(324, 1440, 1476)** $\Rightarrow 1476 - 1440 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 17496$, $T_{36} := 324^2$,
 $E := \{2881, 2883, \dots, 2949, 2951\}$
25. **(336, 1550, 1586)** $\Rightarrow 1586 - 1550 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 18816$, $T_{36} := 336^2$,
 $E := \{3101, 3103, \dots, 3169, 3171\}$
26. **(348, 1664, 1700)** $\Rightarrow 1700 - 1664 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 20184$, $T_{36} := 348^2$,
 $E := \{3329, 3331, \dots, 3397, 3399\}$
27. **(360, 1782, 1818)** $\Rightarrow 1818 - 1782 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 21600$, $T_{36} := 360^2$,
 $E := \{3565, 3567, \dots, 3633, 3635\}$

28. **(372, 1904, 1940)** $\Rightarrow 1940 - 1904 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 23064$, $T_{36} := 372^2$,
 $E := \{3809, 3811, \dots, 3877, 3879\}$
29. **(384, 2030, 2066)** $\Rightarrow 2066 - 2030 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 24576$, $T_{36} := 384^2$,
 $E := \{4061, 4063, \dots, 4129, 4131\}$
30. **(396, 2160, 2196)** $\Rightarrow 2196 - 2160 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 26136$, $T_{36} := 396^2$,
 $E := \{4321, 4323, \dots, 4389, 4391\}$
31. **(408, 2294, 2330)** $\Rightarrow 2330 - 2294 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 27744$, $T_{36} := 408^2$,
 $E := \{4589, 4591, \dots, 4657, 4659\}$
32. **(420, 2432, 2468)** $\Rightarrow 2468 - 2432 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 29400$, $T_{36} := 420^2$,
 $E := \{4865, 4867, \dots, 4933, 4935\}$
33. **(432, 2574, 2610)** $\Rightarrow 2610 - 2574 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 31104$, $T_{36} := 432^2$,
 $E := \{5149, 5151, \dots, 5217, 5219\}$
34. **(444, 2720, 2756)** $\Rightarrow 2756 - 2720 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 32856$, $T_{36} := 444^2$,
 $E := \{5441, 5443, \dots, 5509, 5511\}$
35. **(456, 2870, 2906)** $\Rightarrow 2906 - 2870 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 34656$, $T_{36} := 456^2$,
 $E := \{5741, 5743, \dots, 5809, 5811\}$
36. **(468, 3024, 3060)** $\Rightarrow 3060 - 3024 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 36504$, $T_{36} := 468^2$,
 $E := \{6049, 6051, \dots, 6117, 6119\}$
37. **(480, 3182, 3218)** $\Rightarrow 3218 - 3182 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 38400$, $T_{36} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{6365, 6367, \dots, 6433, 6435\}$
38. **(492, 3344, 3380)** $\Rightarrow 3380 - 3344 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 40344$, $T_{36} := 492^2$,
 $E := \{6689, 6691, \dots, 6757, 6759\}$
39. **(504, 3510, 3546)** $\Rightarrow 3546 - 3510 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 42336$, $T_{36} := 504^2$,
 $E := \{7021, 7023, \dots, 7089, 7091\}$
40. **(516, 3680, 3716)** $\Rightarrow 3716 - 3680 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 44376$, $T_{36} := 516^2$,
 $E := \{7361, 7363, \dots, 7429, 7431\}$
41. **(528, 3854, 3890)** $\Rightarrow 3890 - 3854 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 46464$, $T_{36} := 528^2$,
 $E := \{7709, 7711, \dots, 7777, 7779\}$
42. **(540, 4032, 4068)** $\Rightarrow 4068 - 4032 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 48600$, $T_{36} := 540^2$,
 $E := \{8065, 8067, \dots, 8133, 8135\}$
43. **(552, 4214, 4250)** $\Rightarrow 4250 - 4214 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 50784$, $T_{36} := 552^2$,
 $E := \{8429, 8431, \dots, 8497, 8499\}$
44. **(564, 4400, 4436)** $\Rightarrow 4436 - 4400 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 53016$, $T_{36} := 564^2$,
 $E := \{8801, 8803, \dots, 8869, 8871\}$

45. **(576, 4590, 4626)** $\Rightarrow 4626 - 4590 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 55296$, $T_{36} := 576^2$,
 $E := \{9181, 9183, \dots, 9249, 9251\}$
46. **(588, 4784, 4820)** $\Rightarrow 4820 - 4784 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 57624$, $T_{36} := 588^2$,
 $E := \{9569, 9571, \dots, 9637, 9639\}$
47. **(600, 4982, 5018)** $\Rightarrow 5018 - 4982 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 60000$, $T_{36} := 600^2$,
 $E := \{9965, 9967, \dots, 10033, 10035\}$
48. **(612, 5184, 5220)** $\Rightarrow 5220 - 5184 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 62424$, $T_{36} := 612^2$,
 $E := \{10369, 10371, \dots, 10437, 10439\}$
49. **(624, 5390, 5426)** $\Rightarrow 5426 - 5390 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 64896$, $T_{36} := 624^2$,
 $E := \{10781, 10783, \dots, 10849, 10851\}$
50. **(636, 5600, 5636)** $\Rightarrow 5636 - 5600 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 67416$, $T_{36} := 636^2$,
 $E := \{11201, 11203, \dots, 11269, 11271\}$
51. **(648, 5814, 5850)** $\Rightarrow 5850 - 5814 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 69984$, $T_{36} := 648^2$,
 $E := \{11629, 11631, \dots, 11697, 11699\}$
52. **(660, 6032, 6068)** $\Rightarrow 6068 - 6032 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 72600$, $T_{36} := 660^2$,
 $E := \{12065, 12067, \dots, 12133, 12135\}$
53. **(672, 6254, 6290)** $\Rightarrow 6290 - 6254 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 75264$, $T_{36} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{12509, 12511, \dots, 12577, 12579\}$
54. **(684, 6480, 6516)** $\Rightarrow 6516 - 6480 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 77976$, $T_{36} := 684^2$,
 $E := \{12961, 12963, \dots, 13029, 13031\}$
55. **(696, 6710, 6746)** $\Rightarrow 6746 - 6710 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 80736$, $T_{36} := 696^2$,
 $E := \{13421, 13423, \dots, 13489, 13491\}$
56. **(708, 6944, 6980)** $\Rightarrow 6980 - 6944 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 83544$, $T_{36} := 708^2$,
 $E := \{13889, 13891, \dots, 13957, 13959\}$
57. **(720, 7182, 7218)** $\Rightarrow 7218 - 7182 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 86400$, $T_{36} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{14365, 14367, \dots, 14433, 14435\}$
58. **(732, 7424, 7460)** $\Rightarrow 7460 - 7424 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 89304$, $T_{36} := 732^2$,
 $E := \{14849, 14851, \dots, 14917, 14919\}$
59. **(744, 7670, 7706)** $\Rightarrow 7706 - 7670 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 92256$, $T_{36} := 744^2$,
 $E := \{15341, 15343, \dots, 15409, 15411\}$
60. **(756, 7920, 7956)** $\Rightarrow 7956 - 7920 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 95256$, $T_{36} := 756^2$,
 $E := \{15841, 15843, \dots, 15909, 15911\}$
61. **(768, 8174, 8210)** $\Rightarrow 8210 - 8174 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 98304$, $T_{36} := 768^2$,
 $E := \{16349, 16351, \dots, 16417, 16419\}$

62. **(780, 8432, 8468)** $\Rightarrow 8468 - 8432 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 101400$, $T_{36} := 780^2$,
 $E := \{16865, 16867, \dots, 16933, 16935\}$
63. **(792, 8694, 8730)** $\Rightarrow 8730 - 8694 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 104544$, $T_{36} := 792^2$,
 $E := \{17389, 17391, \dots, 17457, 17459\}$
64. **(804, 8960, 8996)** $\Rightarrow 8996 - 8960 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 107736$, $T_{36} := 804^2$,
 $E := \{17921, 17923, \dots, 17989, 17991\}$
65. **(816, 9230, 9266)** $\Rightarrow 9266 - 9230 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 110976$, $T_{36} := 816^2$,
 $E := \{18461, 18463, \dots, 18529, 18531\}$
66. **(828, 9504, 9540)** $\Rightarrow 9540 - 9504 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 114264$, $T_{36} := 828^2$,
 $E := \{19009, 19011, \dots, 19077, 19079\}$
67. **(840, 9782, 9818)** $\Rightarrow 9818 - 9782 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 117600$, $T_{36} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{19565, 19567, \dots, 19633, 19635\}$
68. **(852, 10064, 10100)** $\Rightarrow 10100 - 10064 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 120984$, $T_{36} := 852^2$,
 $E := \{20129, 20131, \dots, 20197, 20199\}$
69. **(864, 10350, 10386)** $\Rightarrow 10386 - 10350 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 124416$, $T_{36} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{20701, 20703, \dots, 20769, 20771\}$
70. **(876, 10640, 10676)** $\Rightarrow 10676 - 10640 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 127896$, $T_{36} := 876^2$,
 $E := \{21281, 21283, \dots, 21349, 21351\}$
71. **(888, 10934, 10970)** $\Rightarrow 10970 - 10934 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 131424$, $T_{36} := 888^2$,
 $E := \{21869, 21871, \dots, 21937, 21939\}$
72. **(900, 11232, 11268)** $\Rightarrow 11268 - 11232 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 135000$, $T_{36} := 900^2$,
 $E := \{22465, 22467, \dots, 22533, 22535\}$
73. **(912, 11534, 11570)** $\Rightarrow 11570 - 11534 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 138624$, $T_{36} := 912^2$,
 $E := \{23069, 23071, \dots, 23137, 23139\}$
74. **(924, 11840, 11876)** $\Rightarrow 11876 - 11840 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 142296$, $T_{36} := 924^2$,
 $E := \{23681, 23683, \dots, 23749, 23751\}$
75. **(936, 12150, 12186)** $\Rightarrow 12186 - 12150 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 146016$, $T_{36} := 936^2$,
 $E := \{24301, 24303, \dots, 24369, 24371\}$
76. **(948, 12464, 12500)** $\Rightarrow 12500 - 12464 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 149784$, $T_{36} := 948^2$,
 $E := \{24929, 24931, \dots, 24997, 24999\}$
77. **(960, 12782, 12818)** $\Rightarrow 12818 - 12782 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 153600$, $T_{36} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{25565, 25567, \dots, 25633, 25635\}$
78. **(972, 13104, 13140)** $\Rightarrow 13140 - 13104 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 157464$, $T_{36} := 972^2$,
 $E := \{26209, 26211, \dots, 26277, 26279\}$

79. **(984, 13430, 13466)** $\Rightarrow 13466 - 13430 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 161376$, $T_{36} := 984^2$,
 $E := \{26861, 26863, \dots, 26929, 26931\}$
80. **(996, 13760, 13796)** $\Rightarrow 13796 - 13760 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 165336$, $T_{36} := 996^2$,
 $E := \{27521, 27523, \dots, 27589, 27591\}$

Result 4.4. Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $a = 6^2 + 2 \times 6 = 48 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Between Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $a = 12 = 2 \times 6 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $a \in \{48, 60, 72, \dots, 984, 996\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - b = 25 = 5^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{36} := a^2$ $a \in \{48, 60, 72, \dots, 984, 996\};$
- (v) *Magic Sum:*
 $S_{6 \times 6} := a \times (2k + 6)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 79, 80\}$, i.e., $a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.
 Alternatively, $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{a^2}{6}$, $a \in \{48, 60, 72, \dots, 984, 996\};$

4.5 Magic Squares of Order 7

This subsection brings magic squares of order 7 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **four** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

- (63, 16, 65)** $\Rightarrow 65 - 16 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 567$, $T_{49} := 63^2$,
 $E := \{33, 35, \dots, 127, 129\}$ or $E := \{57, 58, \dots, 104, 105\}$
- (77, 36, 85)** $\Rightarrow 85 - 36 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 847$, $T_{49} := 77^2$,
 $E := \{73, 75, \dots, 167, 169\}$ or $E := \{97, 98, \dots, 144, 145\}$
- (91, 60, 109)** $\Rightarrow 109 - 60 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 1183$, $T_{49} := 91^2$,
 $E := \{121, 123, \dots, 215, 217\}$ or $E := \{145, 146, \dots, 192, 193\}$
- (105, 88, 137)** $\Rightarrow 137 - 88 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 1575$, $T_{49} := 105^2$,
 $E := \{177, 179, \dots, 271, 273\}$ or $E := \{201, 202, \dots, 248, 249\}$
- (119, 120, 169)** $\Rightarrow 169 - 120 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 2023$, $T_{49} := 119^2$,
 $E := \{241, 243, \dots, 335, 337\}$ or $E := \{265, 266, \dots, 312, 313\}$
- (133, 156, 205)** $\Rightarrow 205 - 156 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 2527$, $T_{49} := 133^2$,
 $E := \{313, 315, \dots, 407, 409\}$ or $E := \{337, 338, \dots, 384, 385\}$

7. **(147, 196, 245)** $\Rightarrow 245 - 196 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 3087$, $T_{49} := 147^2$,
 $E := \{393, 395, \dots, 487, 489\}$ or $E := \{417, 418, \dots, 464, 465\}$
8. **(161, 240, 289)** $\Rightarrow 289 - 240 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 3703$, $T_{49} := 161^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 575, 577\}$ or $E := \{505, 506, \dots, 552, 553\}$
9. **(175, 288, 337)** $\Rightarrow 337 - 288 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 4375$, $T_{49} := 175^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 671, 673\}$ or $E := \{601, 602, \dots, 648, 649\}$
10. **(189, 340, 389)** $\Rightarrow 389 - 340 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 5103$, $T_{49} := 189^2$,
 $E := \{681, 683, \dots, 775, 777\}$ or $E := \{705, 706, \dots, 752, 753\}$
11. **(203, 396, 445)** $\Rightarrow 445 - 396 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 5887$, $T_{49} := 203^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 887, 889\}$ or $E := \{817, 818, \dots, 864, 865\}$
12. **(217, 456, 505)** $\Rightarrow 505 - 456 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 6727$, $T_{49} := 217^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 1007, 1009\}$ or $E := \{937, 938, \dots, 984, 985\}$
13. **(231, 520, 569)** $\Rightarrow 569 - 520 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 7623$, $T_{49} := 231^2$,
 $E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 1135, 1137\}$ or $E := \{1065, 1066, \dots, 1112, 1113\}$
14. **(245, 588, 637)** $\Rightarrow 637 - 588 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 8575$, $T_{49} := 245^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 1271, 1273\}$ or $E := \{1201, 1202, \dots, 1248, 1249\}$
15. **(259, 660, 709)** $\Rightarrow 709 - 660 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 9583$, $T_{49} := 259^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 1415, 1417\}$ or $E := \{1345, 1346, \dots, 1392, 1393\}$
16. **(273, 736, 785)** $\Rightarrow 785 - 736 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 10647$, $T_{49} := 273^2$,
 $E := \{1473, 1475, \dots, 1567, 1569\}$ or $E := \{1497, 1498, \dots, 1544, 1545\}$
17. **(287, 816, 865)** $\Rightarrow 865 - 816 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 11767$, $T_{49} := 287^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 1727, 1729\}$ or $E := \{1657, 1658, \dots, 1704, 1705\}$
18. **(301, 900, 949)** $\Rightarrow 949 - 900 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 12943$, $T_{49} := 301^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 1895, 1897\}$ or $E := \{1825, 1826, \dots, 1872, 1873\}$
19. **(315, 988, 1037)** $\Rightarrow 1037 - 988 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 14175$, $T_{49} := 315^2$,
 $E := \{1977, 1979, \dots, 2071, 2073\}$ or $E := \{2001, 2002, \dots, 2048, 2049\}$
20. **(329, 1080, 1129)** $\Rightarrow 1129 - 1080 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 15463$, $T_{49} := 329^2$,
 $E := \{2161, 2163, \dots, 2255, 2257\}$ or $E := \{2185, 2186, \dots, 2232, 2233\}$
21. **(343, 1176, 1225)** $\Rightarrow 1225 - 1176 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 16807$, $T_{49} := 343^2$,
 $E := \{2353, 2355, \dots, 2447, 2449\}$ or $E := \{2377, 2378, \dots, 2424, 2425\}$
22. **(357, 1276, 1325)** $\Rightarrow 1325 - 1276 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 18207$, $T_{49} := 357^2$,
 $E := \{2553, 2555, \dots, 2647, 2649\}$ or $E := \{2577, 2578, \dots, 2624, 2625\}$
23. **(371, 1380, 1429)** $\Rightarrow 1429 - 1380 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 19663$, $T_{49} := 371^2$,
 $E := \{2761, 2763, \dots, 2855, 2857\}$ or $E := \{2785, 2786, \dots, 2832, 2833\}$

24. **(385, 1488, 1537)** $\Rightarrow 1537 - 1488 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 21175$, $T_{49} := 385^2$,
 $E := \{2977, 2979, \dots, 3071, 3073\}$ or $E := \{3001, 3002, \dots, 3048, 3049\}$
25. **(399, 1600, 1649)** $\Rightarrow 1649 - 1600 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 22743$, $T_{49} := 399^2$,
 $E := \{3201, 3203, \dots, 3295, 3297\}$ or $E := \{3225, 3226, \dots, 3272, 3273\}$
26. **(413, 1716, 1765)** $\Rightarrow 1765 - 1716 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 24367$, $T_{49} := 413^2$,
 $E := \{3433, 3435, \dots, 3527, 3529\}$ or $E := \{3457, 3458, \dots, 3504, 3505\}$
27. **(427, 1836, 1885)** $\Rightarrow 1885 - 1836 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 26047$, $T_{49} := 427^2$,
 $E := \{3673, 3675, \dots, 3767, 3769\}$ or $E := \{3697, 3698, \dots, 3744, 3745\}$
28. **(441, 1960, 2009)** $\Rightarrow 2009 - 1960 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 27783$, $T_{49} := 441^2$,
 $E := \{3921, 3923, \dots, 4015, 4017\}$ or $E := \{3945, 3946, \dots, 3992, 3993\}$
29. **(455, 2088, 2137)** $\Rightarrow 2137 - 2088 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 29575$, $T_{49} := 455^2$,
 $E := \{4177, 4179, \dots, 4271, 4273\}$ or $E := \{4201, 4202, \dots, 4248, 4249\}$
30. **(469, 2220, 2269)** $\Rightarrow 2269 - 2220 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 31423$, $T_{49} := 469^2$,
 $E := \{4441, 4443, \dots, 4535, 4537\}$ or $E := \{4465, 4466, \dots, 4512, 4513\}$
31. **(483, 2356, 2405)** $\Rightarrow 2405 - 2356 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 33327$, $T_{49} := 483^2$,
 $E := \{4713, 4715, \dots, 4807, 4809\}$ or $E := \{4737, 4738, \dots, 4784, 4785\}$
32. **(497, 2496, 2545)** $\Rightarrow 2545 - 2496 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 35287$, $T_{49} := 497^2$,
 $E := \{4993, 4995, \dots, 5087, 5089\}$ or $E := \{5017, 5018, \dots, 5064, 5065\}$
33. **(511, 2640, 2689)** $\Rightarrow 2689 - 2640 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 37303$, $T_{49} := 511^2$,
 $E := \{5281, 5283, \dots, 5375, 5377\}$ or $E := \{5305, 5306, \dots, 5352, 5353\}$
34. **(525, 2788, 2837)** $\Rightarrow 2837 - 2788 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 39375$, $T_{49} := 525^2$,
 $E := \{5577, 5579, \dots, 5671, 5673\}$ or $E := \{5601, 5602, \dots, 5648, 5649\}$
35. **(539, 2940, 2989)** $\Rightarrow 2989 - 2940 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 41503$, $T_{49} := 539^2$,
 $E := \{5881, 5883, \dots, 5975, 5977\}$ or $E := \{5905, 5906, \dots, 5952, 5953\}$
36. **(553, 3096, 3145)** $\Rightarrow 3145 - 3096 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 43687$, $T_{49} := 553^2$,
 $E := \{6193, 6195, \dots, 6287, 6289\}$ or $E := \{6217, 6218, \dots, 6264, 6265\}$
37. **(567, 3256, 3305)** $\Rightarrow 3305 - 3256 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 45927$, $T_{49} := 567^2$,
 $E := \{6513, 6515, \dots, 6607, 6609\}$ or $E := \{6537, 6538, \dots, 6584, 6585\}$
38. **(581, 3420, 3469)** $\Rightarrow 3469 - 3420 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 48223$, $T_{49} := 581^2$,
 $E := \{6841, 6843, \dots, 6935, 6937\}$ or $E := \{6865, 6866, \dots, 6912, 6913\}$
39. **(595, 3588, 3637)** $\Rightarrow 3637 - 3588 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 50575$, $T_{49} := 595^2$,
 $E := \{7177, 7179, \dots, 7271, 7273\}$ or $E := \{7201, 7202, \dots, 7248, 7249\}$
40. **(609, 3760, 3809)** $\Rightarrow 3809 - 3760 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 52983$, $T_{49} := 609^2$,
 $E := \{7521, 7523, \dots, 7615, 7617\}$ or $E := \{7545, 7546, \dots, 7592, 7593\}$

41. **(623, 3936, 3985)** $\Rightarrow 3985 - 3936 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 55447$, $T_{49} := 623^2$,
 $E := \{7873, 7875, \dots, 7967, 7969\}$ or $E := \{7897, 7898, \dots, 7944, 7945\}$
42. **(637, 4116, 4165)** $\Rightarrow 4165 - 4116 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 57967$, $T_{49} := 637^2$,
 $E := \{8233, 8235, \dots, 8327, 8329\}$ or $E := \{8257, 8258, \dots, 8304, 8305\}$
43. **(651, 4300, 4349)** $\Rightarrow 4349 - 4300 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 60543$, $T_{49} := 651^2$,
 $E := \{8601, 8603, \dots, 8695, 8697\}$ or $E := \{8625, 8626, \dots, 8672, 8673\}$
44. **(665, 4488, 4537)** $\Rightarrow 4537 - 4488 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 63175$, $T_{49} := 665^2$,
 $E := \{8977, 8979, \dots, 9071, 9073\}$ or $E := \{9001, 9002, \dots, 9048, 9049\}$
45. **(679, 4680, 4729)** $\Rightarrow 4729 - 4680 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 65863$, $T_{49} := 679^2$,
 $E := \{9361, 9363, \dots, 9455, 9457\}$ or $E := \{9385, 9386, \dots, 9432, 9433\}$
46. **(693, 4876, 4925)** $\Rightarrow 4925 - 4876 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 68607$, $T_{49} := 693^2$,
 $E := \{9753, 9755, \dots, 9847, 9849\}$ or $E := \{9777, 9778, \dots, 9824, 9825\}$
47. **(707, 5076, 5125)** $\Rightarrow 5125 - 5076 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 71407$, $T_{49} := 707^2$,
 $E := \{10153, 10155, \dots, 10247, 10249\}$ or $E := \{10177, 10178, \dots, 10224, 10225\}$
48. **(721, 5280, 5329)** $\Rightarrow 5329 - 5280 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 74263$, $T_{49} := 721^2$,
 $E := \{10561, 10563, \dots, 10655, 10657\}$ or $E := \{10585, 10586, \dots, 10632, 10633\}$
49. **(735, 5488, 5537)** $\Rightarrow 5537 - 5488 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 77175$, $T_{49} := 735^2$,
 $E := \{10977, 10979, \dots, 11071, 11073\}$ or $E := \{11001, 11002, \dots, 11048, 11049\}$
50. **(749, 5700, 5749)** $\Rightarrow 5749 - 5700 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 80143$, $T_{49} := 749^2$,
 $E := \{11401, 11403, \dots, 11495, 11497\}$ or $E := \{11425, 11426, \dots, 11472, 11473\}$
51. **(763, 5916, 5965)** $\Rightarrow 5965 - 5916 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 83167$, $T_{49} := 763^2$,
 $E := \{11833, 11835, \dots, 11927, 11929\}$ or $E := \{11857, 11858, \dots, 11904, 11905\}$
52. **(777, 6136, 6185)** $\Rightarrow 6185 - 6136 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 86247$, $T_{49} := 777^2$,
 $E := \{12273, 12275, \dots, 12367, 12369\}$ or $E := \{12297, 12298, \dots, 12344, 12345\}$
53. **(791, 6360, 6409)** $\Rightarrow 6409 - 6360 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 89383$, $T_{49} := 791^2$,
 $E := \{12721, 12723, \dots, 12815, 12817\}$ or $E := \{12745, 12746, \dots, 12792, 12793\}$
54. **(805, 6588, 6637)** $\Rightarrow 6637 - 6588 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 92575$, $T_{49} := 805^2$,
 $E := \{13177, 13179, \dots, 13271, 13273\}$ or $E := \{13201, 13202, \dots, 13248, 13249\}$
55. **(819, 6820, 6869)** $\Rightarrow 6869 - 6820 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 95823$, $T_{49} := 819^2$,
 $E := \{13641, 13643, \dots, 13735, 13737\}$ or $E := \{13665, 13666, \dots, 13712, 13713\}$
56. **(833, 7056, 7105)** $\Rightarrow 7105 - 7056 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 99127$, $T_{49} := 833^2$,
 $E := \{14113, 14115, \dots, 14207, 14209\}$ or $E := \{14137, 14138, \dots, 14184, 14185\}$
57. **(847, 7296, 7345)** $\Rightarrow 7345 - 7296 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 102487$, $T_{49} := 847^2$,
 $E := \{14593, 14595, \dots, 14687, 14689\}$ or $E := \{14617, 14618, \dots, 14664, 14665\}$

58. **(861, 7540, 7589)** $\Rightarrow 7589 - 7540 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 105903$, $T_{49} := 861^2$,
 $E := \{15081, 15083, \dots, 15175, 15177\}$ or $E := \{15105, 15106, \dots, 15152, 15153\}$
59. **(875, 7788, 7837)** $\Rightarrow 7837 - 7788 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 109375$, $T_{49} := 875^2$,
 $E := \{15577, 15579, \dots, 15671, 15673\}$ or $E := \{15601, 15602, \dots, 15648, 15649\}$
60. **(889, 8040, 8089)** $\Rightarrow 8089 - 8040 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 112903$, $T_{49} := 889^2$,
 $E := \{16081, 16083, \dots, 16175, 16177\}$ or $E := \{16105, 16106, \dots, 16152, 16153\}$
61. **(903, 8296, 8345)** $\Rightarrow 8345 - 8296 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 116487$, $T_{49} := 903^2$,
 $E := \{16593, 16595, \dots, 16687, 16689\}$ or $E := \{16617, 16618, \dots, 16664, 16665\}$
62. **(917, 8556, 8605)** $\Rightarrow 8605 - 8556 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 120127$, $T_{49} := 917^2$,
 $E := \{17113, 17115, \dots, 17207, 17209\}$ or $E := \{17137, 17138, \dots, 17184, 17185\}$
63. **(931, 8820, 8869)** $\Rightarrow 8869 - 8820 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 123823$, $T_{49} := 931^2$,
 $E := \{17641, 17643, \dots, 17735, 17737\}$ or $E := \{17665, 17666, \dots, 17712, 17713\}$
64. **(945, 9088, 9137)** $\Rightarrow 9137 - 9088 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 127575$, $T_{49} := 945^2$,
 $E := \{18177, 18179, \dots, 18271, 18273\}$ or $E := \{18201, 18202, \dots, 18248, 18249\}$
65. **(959, 9360, 9409)** $\Rightarrow 9409 - 9360 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 131383$, $T_{49} := 959^2$,
 $E := \{18721, 18723, \dots, 18815, 18817\}$ or $E := \{18745, 18746, \dots, 18792, 18793\}$
66. **(973, 9636, 9685)** $\Rightarrow 9685 - 9636 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 135247$, $T_{49} := 973^2$,
 $E := \{19273, 19275, \dots, 19367, 19369\}$ or $E := \{19297, 19298, \dots, 19344, 19345\}$
67. **(987, 9916, 9965)** $\Rightarrow 9965 - 9916 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 139167$, $T_{49} := 987^2$,
 $E := \{19833, 19835, \dots, 19927, 19929\}$ or $E := \{19857, 19858, \dots, 19904, 19905\}$

Result 4.5. Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $a = 7^2 + 2 \times 7 = 63 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $a = 14 = 2 \times 7 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $a \in \{63, 77, 91, \dots, 973, 987\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - b = 49 = 7^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:* $T_{49} := a^2;$
- (v) *Magic Sum:*
 $S_{7 \times 7} := a \times (2k + 7)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 66, 67\}$, i.e., $a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.
 Alternatively, $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{a^2}{7}$, $a \in \{63, 77, 91, \dots, 973, 987\}$.

4.6 Magic Squares of Order 8

This subsection brings magic squares of order 8 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **five** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

1. **(80, 18, 82)** $\Rightarrow 82 - 18 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 800$, $T_{64} := 80^2$,
 $E := \{37, 39, \dots, 161, 163\}$
2. **(96, 40, 104)** $\Rightarrow 104 - 40 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 1152$, $T_{64} := 96^2$,
 $E := \{81, 83, \dots, 205, 207\}$
3. **(112, 66, 130)** $\Rightarrow 130 - 66 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 1568$, $T_{64} := 112^2$,
 $E := \{133, 135, \dots, 257, 259\}$
4. **(128, 96, 160)** $\Rightarrow 160 - 96 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 2048$, $T_{64} := 128^2$,
 $E := \{193, 195, \dots, 317, 319\}$
5. **(144, 130, 194)** $\Rightarrow 194 - 130 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 2592$, $T_{64} := 144^2$,
 $E := \{261, 263, \dots, 385, 387\}$
6. **(160, 168, 232)** $\Rightarrow 232 - 168 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 3200$, $T_{64} := 160^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 461, 463\}$
7. **(176, 210, 274)** $\Rightarrow 274 - 210 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 3872$, $T_{64} := 176^2$,
 $E := \{421, 423, \dots, 545, 547\}$
8. **(192, 256, 320)** $\Rightarrow 320 - 256 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4608$, $T_{64} := 192^2$,
 $E := \{513, 515, \dots, 637, 639\}$
9. **(208, 306, 370)** $\Rightarrow 370 - 306 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 5408$, $T_{64} := 208^2$,
 $E := \{613, 615, \dots, 737, 739\}$
10. **(224, 360, 424)** $\Rightarrow 424 - 360 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 6272$, $T_{64} := 224^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 845, 847\}$
11. **(240, 418, 482)** $\Rightarrow 482 - 418 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 7200$, $T_{64} := 240^2$,
 $E := \{837, 839, \dots, 961, 963\}$
12. **(256, 480, 544)** $\Rightarrow 544 - 480 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 8192$, $T_{64} := 256^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 1085, 1087\}$
13. **(272, 546, 610)** $\Rightarrow 610 - 546 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 9248$, $T_{64} := 272^2$,
 $E := \{1093, 1095, \dots, 1217, 1219\}$
14. **(288, 616, 680)** $\Rightarrow 680 - 616 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 10368$, $T_{64} := 288^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 1357, 1359\}$
15. **(304, 690, 754)** $\Rightarrow 754 - 690 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 11552$, $T_{64} := 304^2$,
 $E := \{1381, 1383, \dots, 1505, 1507\}$

16. **(320, 768, 832)** $\Rightarrow 832 - 768 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 12800$, $T_{64} := 320^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 1661, 1663\}$
17. **(336, 850, 914)** $\Rightarrow 914 - 850 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 14112$, $T_{64} := 336^2$,
 $E := \{1701, 1703, \dots, 1825, 1827\}$
18. **(352, 936, 1000)** $\Rightarrow 1000 - 936 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 15488$, $T_{64} := 352^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 1997, 1999\}$
19. **(368, 1026, 1090)** $\Rightarrow 1090 - 1026 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 16928$, $T_{64} := 368^2$,
 $E := \{2053, 2055, \dots, 2177, 2179\}$
20. **(384, 1120, 1184)** $\Rightarrow 1184 - 1120 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 18432$, $T_{64} := 384^2$,
 $E := \{2241, 2243, \dots, 2365, 2367\}$
21. **(400, 1218, 1282)** $\Rightarrow 1282 - 1218 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 20000$, $T_{64} := 400^2$,
 $E := \{2437, 2439, \dots, 2561, 2563\}$
22. **(416, 1320, 1384)** $\Rightarrow 1384 - 1320 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 21632$, $T_{64} := 416^2$,
 $E := \{2641, 2643, \dots, 2765, 2767\}$
23. **(432, 1426, 1490)** $\Rightarrow 1490 - 1426 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 23328$, $T_{64} := 432^2$,
 $E := \{2853, 2855, \dots, 2977, 2979\}$
24. **(448, 1536, 1600)** $\Rightarrow 1600 - 1536 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 25088$, $T_{64} := 448^2$,
 $E := \{3073, 3075, \dots, 3197, 3199\}$
25. **(464, 1650, 1714)** $\Rightarrow 1714 - 1650 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 26912$, $T_{64} := 464^2$,
 $E := \{3301, 3303, \dots, 3425, 3427\}$
26. **(480, 1768, 1832)** $\Rightarrow 1832 - 1768 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 28800$, $T_{64} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{3537, 3539, \dots, 3661, 3663\}$
27. **(496, 1890, 1954)** $\Rightarrow 1954 - 1890 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 30752$, $T_{64} := 496^2$,
 $E := \{3781, 3783, \dots, 3905, 3907\}$
28. **(512, 2016, 2080)** $\Rightarrow 2080 - 2016 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 32768$, $T_{64} := 512^2$,
 $E := \{4033, 4035, \dots, 4157, 4159\}$
29. **(528, 2146, 2210)** $\Rightarrow 2210 - 2146 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 34848$, $T_{64} := 528^2$,
 $E := \{4293, 4295, \dots, 4417, 4419\}$
30. **(544, 2280, 2344)** $\Rightarrow 2344 - 2280 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 36992$, $T_{64} := 544^2$,
 $E := \{4561, 4563, \dots, 4685, 4687\}$
31. **(560, 2418, 2482)** $\Rightarrow 2482 - 2418 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 39200$, $T_{64} := 560^2$,
 $E := \{4837, 4839, \dots, 4961, 4963\}$
32. **(576, 2560, 2624)** $\Rightarrow 2624 - 2560 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 41472$, $T_{64} := 576^2$,
 $E := \{5121, 5123, \dots, 5245, 5247\}$

33. **(592, 2706, 2770)** $\Rightarrow 2770 - 2706 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 43808$, $T_{64} := 592^2$,
 $E := \{5413, 5415, \dots, 5537, 5539\}$
34. **(608, 2856, 2920)** $\Rightarrow 2920 - 2856 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 46208$, $T_{64} := 608^2$,
 $E := \{5713, 5715, \dots, 5837, 5839\}$
35. **(624, 3010, 3074)** $\Rightarrow 3074 - 3010 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 48672$, $T_{64} := 624^2$,
 $E := \{6021, 6023, \dots, 6145, 6147\}$
36. **(640, 3168, 3232)** $\Rightarrow 3232 - 3168 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 51200$, $T_{64} := 640^2$,
 $E := \{6337, 6339, \dots, 6461, 6463\}$
37. **(656, 3330, 3394)** $\Rightarrow 3394 - 3330 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 53792$, $T_{64} := 656^2$,
 $E := \{6661, 6663, \dots, 6785, 6787\}$
38. **(672, 3496, 3560)** $\Rightarrow 3560 - 3496 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 56448$, $T_{64} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{6993, 6995, \dots, 7117, 7119\}$
39. **(688, 3666, 3730)** $\Rightarrow 3730 - 3666 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 59168$, $T_{64} := 688^2$,
 $E := \{7333, 7335, \dots, 7457, 7459\}$
40. **(704, 3840, 3904)** $\Rightarrow 3904 - 3840 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 61952$, $T_{64} := 704^2$,
 $E := \{7681, 7683, \dots, 7805, 7807\}$
41. **(720, 4018, 4082)** $\Rightarrow 4082 - 4018 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 64800$, $T_{64} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{8037, 8039, \dots, 8161, 8163\}$
42. **(736, 4200, 4264)** $\Rightarrow 4264 - 4200 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 67712$, $T_{64} := 736^2$,
 $E := \{8401, 8403, \dots, 8525, 8527\}$
43. **(752, 4386, 4450)** $\Rightarrow 4450 - 4386 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 70688$, $T_{64} := 752^2$,
 $E := \{8773, 8775, \dots, 8897, 8899\}$
44. **(768, 4576, 4640)** $\Rightarrow 4640 - 4576 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 73728$, $T_{64} := 768^2$,
 $E := \{9153, 9155, \dots, 9277, 9279\}$
45. **(784, 4770, 4834)** $\Rightarrow 4834 - 4770 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 76832$, $T_{64} := 784^2$,
 $E := \{9541, 9543, \dots, 9665, 9667\}$
46. **(800, 4968, 5032)** $\Rightarrow 5032 - 4968 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 80000$, $T_{64} := 800^2$,
 $E := \{9937, 9939, \dots, 10061, 10063\}$
47. **(816, 5170, 5234)** $\Rightarrow 5234 - 5170 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 83232$, $T_{64} := 816^2$,
 $E := \{10341, 10343, \dots, 10465, 10467\}$
48. **(832, 5376, 5440)** $\Rightarrow 5440 - 5376 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 86528$, $T_{64} := 832^2$,
 $E := \{10753, 10755, \dots, 10877, 10879\}$
49. **(848, 5586, 5650)** $\Rightarrow 5650 - 5586 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 89888$, $T_{64} := 848^2$,
 $E := \{11173, 11175, \dots, 11297, 11299\}$

50. **(864, 5800, 5864)** $\Rightarrow 5864 - 5800 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 93312$, $T_{64} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{11601, 11603, \dots, 11725, 11727\}$
51. **(880, 6018, 6082)** $\Rightarrow 6082 - 6018 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 96800$, $T_{64} := 880^2$,
 $E := \{12037, 12039, \dots, 12161, 12163\}$
52. **(896, 6240, 6304)** $\Rightarrow 6304 - 6240 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 100352$, $T_{64} := 896^2$,
 $E := \{12481, 12483, \dots, 12605, 12607\}$
53. **(912, 6466, 6530)** $\Rightarrow 6530 - 6466 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 103968$, $T_{64} := 912^2$,
 $E := \{12933, 12935, \dots, 13057, 13059\}$
54. **(928, 6696, 6760)** $\Rightarrow 6760 - 6696 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 107648$, $T_{64} := 928^2$,
 $E := \{13393, 13395, \dots, 13517, 13519\}$
55. **(944, 6930, 6994)** $\Rightarrow 6994 - 6930 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 111392$, $T_{64} := 944^2$,
 $E := \{13861, 13863, \dots, 13985, 13987\}$
56. **(960, 7168, 7232)** $\Rightarrow 7232 - 7168 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 115200$, $T_{64} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{14337, 14339, \dots, 14461, 14463\}$
57. **(976, 7410, 7474)** $\Rightarrow 7474 - 7410 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 119072$, $T_{64} := 976^2$,
 $E := \{14821, 14823, \dots, 14945, 14947\}$
58. **(992, 7656, 7720)** $\Rightarrow 7720 - 7656 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 123008$, $T_{64} := 992^2$,
 $E := \{15313, 15315, \dots, 15437, 15439\}$

Result 4.6. *Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:*

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $a = 8^2 + 2 \times 8 = 80 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $a = 16 = 2 \times 8 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, a \in \{80, 96, \dots, 976, 992\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - b = 64 = 8^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{64} := a^2, a \in \{80, 96, \dots, 976, 992\};$
- (v) *Magic Sum:*
 $S_{8 \times 8} := a \times (2k + 8), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 57, 58\}, \text{i.e., } a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$
 Alternatively, $S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{a^2}{8}, a \in \{80, 96, \dots, 976, 992\}.$

4.7 Magic Squares of Order 9

This subsection brings magic squares of order 9 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **six** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

1. **(99, 20, 101)** $\Rightarrow 101 - 20 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 1089$, $T_{81} := 99^2$,
 $E := \{41, 43, \dots, 199, 201\}$ or $E := \{81, 82, \dots, 160, 161\}$
2. **(117, 44, 125)** $\Rightarrow 125 - 44 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 1521$, $T_{81} := 117^2$,
 $E := \{89, 91, \dots, 247, 249\}$ or $E := \{129, 130, \dots, 208, 209\}$
3. **(135, 72, 153)** $\Rightarrow 153 - 72 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 2025$, $T_{81} := 135^2$,
 $E := \{145, 147, \dots, 303, 305\}$ or $E := \{185, 186, \dots, 264, 265\}$
4. **(153, 104, 185)** $\Rightarrow 185 - 104 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 2601$, $T_{81} := 153^2$,
 $E := \{209, 211, \dots, 367, 369\}$ or $E := \{249, 250, \dots, 328, 329\}$
5. **(171, 140, 221)** $\Rightarrow 221 - 140 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 3249$, $T_{81} := 171^2$,
 $E := \{281, 283, \dots, 439, 441\}$ or $E := \{321, 322, \dots, 400, 401\}$
6. **(189, 180, 261)** $\Rightarrow 261 - 180 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 3969$, $T_{81} := 189^2$,
 $E := \{361, 363, \dots, 519, 521\}$ or $E := \{401, 402, \dots, 480, 481\}$
7. **(207, 224, 305)** $\Rightarrow 305 - 224 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 4761$, $T_{81} := 207^2$,
 $E := \{449, 451, \dots, 607, 609\}$ or $E := \{489, 490, \dots, 568, 569\}$
8. **(225, 272, 353)** $\Rightarrow 353 - 272 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 5625$, $T_{81} := 225^2$,
 $E := \{545, 547, \dots, 703, 705\}$ or $E := \{585, 586, \dots, 664, 665\}$
9. **(243, 324, 405)** $\Rightarrow 405 - 324 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 6561$, $T_{81} := 243^2$,
 $E := \{649, 651, \dots, 807, 809\}$ or $E := \{689, 690, \dots, 768, 769\}$
10. **(261, 380, 461)** $\Rightarrow 461 - 380 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 7569$, $T_{81} := 261^2$,
 $E := \{761, 763, \dots, 919, 921\}$ or $E := \{801, 802, \dots, 880, 881\}$
11. **(279, 440, 521)** $\Rightarrow 521 - 440 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 8649$, $T_{81} := 279^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 1039, 1041\}$ or $E := \{921, 922, \dots, 1000, 1001\}$
12. **(297, 504, 585)** $\Rightarrow 585 - 504 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 9801$, $T_{81} := 297^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 1167, 1169\}$ or $E := \{1049, 1050, \dots, 1128, 1129\}$
13. **(315, 572, 653)** $\Rightarrow 653 - 572 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 11025$, $T_{81} := 315^2$,
 $E := \{1145, 1147, \dots, 1303, 1305\}$ or $E := \{1185, 1186, \dots, 1264, 1265\}$
14. **(333, 644, 725)** $\Rightarrow 725 - 644 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 12321$, $T_{81} := 333^2$,
 $E := \{1289, 1291, \dots, 1447, 1449\}$ or $E := \{1329, 1330, \dots, 1408, 1409\}$
15. **(351, 720, 801)** $\Rightarrow 801 - 720 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 13689$, $T_{81} := 351^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 1599, 1601\}$ or $E := \{1481, 1482, \dots, 1560, 1561\}$

16. **(369, 800, 881)** $\Rightarrow 881 - 800 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 15129$, $T_{81} := 369^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 1759, 1761\}$ or $E := \{1641, 1642, \dots, 1720, 1721\}$
17. **(387, 884, 965)** $\Rightarrow 965 - 884 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 16641$, $T_{81} := 387^2$,
 $E := \{1769, 1771, \dots, 1927, 1929\}$ or $E := \{1809, 1810, \dots, 1888, 1889\}$
18. **(405, 972, 1053)** $\Rightarrow 1053 - 972 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 18225$, $T_{81} := 405^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 2103, 2105\}$ or $E := \{1985, 1986, \dots, 2064, 2065\}$
19. **(423, 1064, 1145)** $\Rightarrow 1145 - 1064 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 19881$, $T_{81} := 423^2$,
 $E := \{2129, 2131, \dots, 2287, 2289\}$ or $E := \{2169, 2170, \dots, 2248, 2249\}$
20. **(441, 1160, 1241)** $\Rightarrow 1241 - 1160 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 21609$, $T_{81} := 441^2$,
 $E := \{2321, 2323, \dots, 2479, 2481\}$ or $E := \{2361, 2362, \dots, 2440, 2441\}$
21. **(459, 1260, 1341)** $\Rightarrow 1341 - 1260 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 23409$, $T_{81} := 459^2$,
 $E := \{2521, 2523, \dots, 2679, 2681\}$ or $E := \{2561, 2562, \dots, 2640, 2641\}$
22. **(477, 1364, 1445)** $\Rightarrow 1445 - 1364 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 25281$, $T_{81} := 477^2$,
 $E := \{2729, 2731, \dots, 2887, 2889\}$ or $E := \{2769, 2770, \dots, 2848, 2849\}$
23. **(495, 1472, 1553)** $\Rightarrow 1553 - 1472 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 27225$, $T_{81} := 495^2$,
 $E := \{2945, 2947, \dots, 3103, 3105\}$ or $E := \{2985, 2986, \dots, 3064, 3065\}$
24. **(513, 1584, 1665)** $\Rightarrow 1665 - 1584 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 29241$, $T_{81} := 513^2$,
 $E := \{3169, 3171, \dots, 3327, 3329\}$ or $E := \{3209, 3210, \dots, 3288, 3289\}$
25. **(531, 1700, 1781)** $\Rightarrow 1781 - 1700 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 31329$, $T_{81} := 531^2$,
 $E := \{3401, 3403, \dots, 3559, 3561\}$ or $E := \{3441, 3442, \dots, 3520, 3521\}$
26. **(549, 1820, 1901)** $\Rightarrow 1901 - 1820 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 33489$, $T_{81} := 549^2$,
 $E := \{3641, 3643, \dots, 3799, 3801\}$ or $E := \{3681, 3682, \dots, 3760, 3761\}$
27. **(567, 1944, 2025)** $\Rightarrow 2025 - 1944 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 35721$, $T_{81} := 567^2$,
 $E := \{3889, 3891, \dots, 4047, 4049\}$ or $E := \{3929, 3930, \dots, 4008, 4009\}$
28. **(585, 2072, 2153)** $\Rightarrow 2153 - 2072 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 38025$, $T_{81} := 585^2$,
 $E := \{4145, 4147, \dots, 4303, 4305\}$ or $E := \{4185, 4186, \dots, 4264, 4265\}$
29. **(603, 2204, 2285)** $\Rightarrow 2285 - 2204 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 40401$, $T_{81} := 603^2$,
 $E := \{4409, 4411, \dots, 4567, 4569\}$ or $E := \{4449, 4450, \dots, 4528, 4529\}$
30. **(621, 2340, 2421)** $\Rightarrow 2421 - 2340 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 42849$, $T_{81} := 621^2$,
 $E := \{4681, 4683, \dots, 4839, 4841\}$ or $E := \{4721, 4722, \dots, 4800, 4801\}$
31. **(639, 2480, 2561)** $\Rightarrow 2561 - 2480 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 45369$, $T_{81} := 639^2$,
 $E := \{4961, 4963, \dots, 5119, 5121\}$ or $E := \{5001, 5002, \dots, 5080, 5081\}$
32. **(657, 2624, 2705)** $\Rightarrow 2705 - 2624 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 47961$, $T_{81} := 657^2$,
 $E := \{5249, 5251, \dots, 5407, 5409\}$ or $E := \{5289, 5290, \dots, 5368, 5369\}$

33. **(675, 2772, 2853)** $\Rightarrow 2853 - 2772 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 50625$, $T_{81} := 675^2$,
 $E := \{5545, 5547, \dots, 5703, 5705\}$ or $E := \{5585, 5586, \dots, 5664, 5665\}$
34. **(693, 2924, 3005)** $\Rightarrow 3005 - 2924 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 53361$, $T_{81} := 693^2$,
 $E := \{5849, 5851, \dots, 6007, 6009\}$ or $E := \{5889, 5890, \dots, 5968, 5969\}$
35. **(711, 3080, 3161)** $\Rightarrow 3161 - 3080 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 56169$, $T_{81} := 711^2$,
 $E := \{6161, 6163, \dots, 6319, 6321\}$ or $E := \{6201, 6202, \dots, 6280, 6281\}$
36. **(729, 3240, 3321)** $\Rightarrow 3321 - 3240 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 59049$, $T_{81} := 729^2$,
 $E := \{6481, 6483, \dots, 6639, 6641\}$ or $E := \{6521, 6522, \dots, 6600, 6601\}$
37. **(747, 3404, 3485)** $\Rightarrow 3485 - 3404 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 62001$, $T_{81} := 747^2$,
 $E := \{6809, 6811, \dots, 6967, 6969\}$ or $E := \{6849, 6850, \dots, 6928, 6929\}$
38. **(765, 3572, 3653)** $\Rightarrow 3653 - 3572 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 65025$, $T_{81} := 765^2$,
 $E := \{7145, 7147, \dots, 7303, 7305\}$ or $E := \{7185, 7186, \dots, 7264, 7265\}$
39. **(783, 3744, 3825)** $\Rightarrow 3825 - 3744 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 68121$, $T_{81} := 783^2$,
 $E := \{7489, 7491, \dots, 7647, 7649\}$ or $E := \{7529, 7530, \dots, 7608, 7609\}$
40. **(801, 3920, 4001)** $\Rightarrow 4001 - 3920 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 71289$, $T_{81} := 801^2$,
 $E := \{7841, 7843, \dots, 7999, 8001\}$ or $E := \{7881, 7882, \dots, 7960, 7961\}$
41. **(819, 4100, 4181)** $\Rightarrow 4181 - 4100 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 74529$, $T_{81} := 819^2$,
 $E := \{8201, 8203, \dots, 8359, 8361\}$ or $E := \{8241, 8242, \dots, 8320, 8321\}$
42. **(837, 4284, 4365)** $\Rightarrow 4365 - 4284 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 77841$, $T_{81} := 837^2$,
 $E := \{8569, 8571, \dots, 8727, 8729\}$ or $E := \{8609, 8610, \dots, 8688, 8689\}$
43. **(855, 4472, 4553)** $\Rightarrow 4553 - 4472 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 81225$, $T_{81} := 855^2$,
 $E := \{8945, 8947, \dots, 9103, 9105\}$ or $E := \{8985, 8986, \dots, 9064, 9065\}$
44. **(873, 4664, 4745)** $\Rightarrow 4745 - 4664 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 84681$, $T_{81} := 873^2$,
 $E := \{9329, 9331, \dots, 9487, 9489\}$ or $E := \{9369, 9370, \dots, 9448, 9449\}$
45. **(891, 4860, 4941)** $\Rightarrow 4941 - 4860 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 88209$, $T_{81} := 891^2$,
 $E := \{9721, 9723, \dots, 9879, 9881\}$ or $E := \{9761, 9762, \dots, 9840, 9841\}$
46. **(909, 5060, 5141)** $\Rightarrow 5141 - 5060 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 91809$, $T_{81} := 909^2$,
 $E := \{10121, 10123, \dots, 10279, 10281\}$ or $E := \{10161, 10162, \dots, 10240, 10241\}$
47. **(927, 5264, 5345)** $\Rightarrow 5345 - 5264 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 95481$, $T_{81} := 927^2$,
 $E := \{10529, 10531, \dots, 10687, 10689\}$ or $E := \{10569, 10570, \dots, 10648, 10649\}$
48. **(945, 5472, 5553)** $\Rightarrow 5553 - 5472 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 99225$, $T_{81} := 945^2$,
 $E := \{10945, 10947, \dots, 11103, 11105\}$ or $E := \{10985, 10986, \dots, 11064, 11065\}$
49. **(963, 5684, 5765)** $\Rightarrow 5765 - 5684 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 103041$, $T_{81} := 963^2$,
 $E := \{11369, 11371, \dots, 11527, 11529\}$ or $E := \{11409, 11410, \dots, 11488, 11489\}$

50. **(981, 5900, 5981)** $\Rightarrow 5981 - 5900 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 106929$, $T_{81} := 981^2$,
 $E := \{11801, 11803, \dots, 11959, 11961\}$ or $E := \{11841, 11842, \dots, 11920, 11921\}$
51. **(999, 6120, 6201)** $\Rightarrow 6201 - 6120 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 110889$, $T_{81} := 999^2$,
 $E := \{12241, 12243, \dots, 12399, 12401\}$ or $E := \{12281, 12282, \dots, 12360, 12361\}$

Result 4.7. Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $a = 9^2 + 2 \times 9 = 99 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $a = 18 = 2 \times 9 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $a \in \{99, 117, 135, \dots, 981, 999\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - b = 81 = 9^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{81} := a^2$, $a \in \{99, 117, 135, \dots, 981, 999\};$
- (v) *Magic Sum:*
 $S_{9 \times 9} := a \times (2k + 9)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 50, 51\}$, i.e., $a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.
 Alternatively, $S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{a^2}{9}$, $a \in \{99, 117, 135, \dots, 981, 999\}$.

4.8 Magic Squares of Order 10

This subsection brings magic squares of order 10 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **seven** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

1. **(120, 22, 122)** $\Rightarrow 122 - 22 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 1440$, $T_{100} := 120^2$,
 $E := \{45, 47, \dots, 241, 243\}$
2. **(140, 48, 148)** $\Rightarrow 148 - 48 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 1960$, $T_{100} := 140^2$,
 $E := \{97, 99, \dots, 293, 295\}$
3. **(160, 78, 178)** $\Rightarrow 178 - 78 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 2560$, $T_{100} := 160^2$,
 $E := \{157, 159, \dots, 353, 355\}$
4. **(180, 112, 212)** $\Rightarrow 212 - 112 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 3240$, $T_{100} := 180^2$,
 $E := \{225, 227, \dots, 421, 423\}$
5. **(200, 150, 250)** $\Rightarrow 250 - 150 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 4000$, $T_{100} := 200^2$,
 $E := \{301, 303, \dots, 497, 499\}$
6. **(220, 192, 292)** $\Rightarrow 292 - 192 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 4840$, $T_{100} := 220^2$,
 $E := \{385, 387, \dots, 581, 583\}$

7. **(240, 238, 338)** $\Rightarrow 338 - 238 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5760$, $T_{100} := 240^2$,
 $E := \{477, 479, \dots, 673, 675\}$
8. **(260, 288, 388)** $\Rightarrow 388 - 288 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 6760$, $T_{100} := 260^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 773, 775\}$
9. **(280, 342, 442)** $\Rightarrow 442 - 342 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 7840$, $T_{100} := 280^2$,
 $E := \{685, 687, \dots, 881, 883\}$
10. **(300, 400, 500)** $\Rightarrow 500 - 400 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 9000$, $T_{100} := 300^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 997, 999\}$
11. **(320, 462, 562)** $\Rightarrow 562 - 462 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 10240$, $T_{100} := 320^2$,
 $E := \{925, 927, \dots, 1121, 1123\}$
12. **(340, 528, 628)** $\Rightarrow 628 - 528 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 11560$, $T_{100} := 340^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 1253, 1255\}$
13. **(360, 598, 698)** $\Rightarrow 698 - 598 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 12960$, $T_{100} := 360^2$,
 $E := \{1197, 1199, \dots, 1393, 1395\}$
14. **(380, 672, 772)** $\Rightarrow 772 - 672 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 14440$, $T_{100} := 380^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 1541, 1543\}$
15. **(400, 750, 850)** $\Rightarrow 850 - 750 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 16000$, $T_{100} := 400^2$,
 $E := \{1501, 1503, \dots, 1697, 1699\}$
16. **(420, 832, 932)** $\Rightarrow 932 - 832 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 17640$, $T_{100} := 420^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 1861, 1863\}$
17. **(440, 918, 1018)** $\Rightarrow 1018 - 918 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 19360$, $T_{100} := 440^2$,
 $E := \{1837, 1839, \dots, 2033, 2035\}$
18. **(460, 1008, 1108)** $\Rightarrow 1108 - 1008 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 21160$, $T_{100} := 460^2$,
 $E := \{2017, 2019, \dots, 2213, 2215\}$
19. **(480, 1102, 1202)** $\Rightarrow 1202 - 1102 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 23040$, $T_{100} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{2205, 2207, \dots, 2401, 2403\}$
20. **(500, 1200, 1300)** $\Rightarrow 1300 - 1200 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 25000$, $T_{100} := 500^2$,
 $E := \{2401, 2403, \dots, 2597, 2599\}$
21. **(520, 1302, 1402)** $\Rightarrow 1402 - 1302 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 27040$, $T_{100} := 520^2$,
 $E := \{2605, 2607, \dots, 2801, 2803\}$
22. **(540, 1408, 1508)** $\Rightarrow 1508 - 1408 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 29160$, $T_{100} := 540^2$,
 $E := \{2817, 2819, \dots, 3013, 3015\}$
23. **(560, 1518, 1618)** $\Rightarrow 1618 - 1518 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 31360$, $T_{100} := 560^2$,
 $E := \{3037, 3039, \dots, 3233, 3235\}$

24. **(580, 1632, 1732)** $\Rightarrow 1732 - 1632 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 33640$, $T_{100} := 580^2$,
 $E := \{3265, 3267, \dots, 3461, 3463\}$
25. **(600, 1750, 1850)** $\Rightarrow 1850 - 1750 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 36000$, $T_{100} := 600^2$,
 $E := \{3501, 3503, \dots, 3697, 3699\}$
26. **(620, 1872, 1972)** $\Rightarrow 1972 - 1872 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 38440$, $T_{100} := 620^2$,
 $E := \{3745, 3747, \dots, 3941, 3943\}$
27. **(640, 1998, 2098)** $\Rightarrow 2098 - 1998 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 40960$, $T_{100} := 640^2$,
 $E := \{3997, 3999, \dots, 4193, 4195\}$
28. **(660, 2128, 2228)** $\Rightarrow 2228 - 2128 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 43560$, $T_{100} := 660^2$,
 $E := \{4257, 4259, \dots, 4453, 4455\}$
29. **(680, 2262, 2362)** $\Rightarrow 2362 - 2262 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 46240$, $T_{100} := 680^2$,
 $E := \{4525, 4527, \dots, 4721, 4723\}$
30. **(700, 2400, 2500)** $\Rightarrow 2500 - 2400 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 49000$, $T_{100} := 700^2$,
 $E := \{4801, 4803, \dots, 4997, 4999\}$
31. **(720, 2542, 2642)** $\Rightarrow 2642 - 2542 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 51840$, $T_{100} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{5085, 5087, \dots, 5281, 5283\}$
32. **(740, 2688, 2788)** $\Rightarrow 2788 - 2688 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 54760$, $T_{100} := 740^2$,
 $E := \{5377, 5379, \dots, 5573, 5575\}$
33. **(760, 2838, 2938)** $\Rightarrow 2938 - 2838 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 57760$, $T_{100} := 760^2$,
 $E := \{5677, 5679, \dots, 5873, 5875\}$
34. **(780, 2992, 3092)** $\Rightarrow 3092 - 2992 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 60840$, $T_{100} := 780^2$,
 $E := \{5985, 5987, \dots, 6181, 6183\}$
35. **(800, 3150, 3250)** $\Rightarrow 3250 - 3150 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 64000$, $T_{100} := 800^2$,
 $E := \{6301, 6303, \dots, 6497, 6499\}$
36. **(820, 3312, 3412)** $\Rightarrow 3412 - 3312 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 67240$, $T_{100} := 820^2$,
 $E := \{6625, 6627, \dots, 6821, 6823\}$
37. **(840, 3478, 3578)** $\Rightarrow 3578 - 3478 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 70560$, $T_{100} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{6957, 6959, \dots, 7153, 7155\}$
38. **(860, 3648, 3748)** $\Rightarrow 3748 - 3648 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 73960$, $T_{100} := 860^2$,
 $E := \{7297, 7299, \dots, 7493, 7495\}$
39. **(880, 3822, 3922)** $\Rightarrow 3922 - 3822 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 77440$, $T_{100} := 880^2$,
 $E := \{7645, 7647, \dots, 7841, 7843\}$
40. **(900, 4000, 4100)** $\Rightarrow 4100 - 4000 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 81000$, $T_{100} := 900^2$,
 $E := \{8001, 8003, \dots, 8197, 8199\}$

41. **(920, 4182, 4282)** $\Rightarrow 4282 - 4182 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 84640$, $T_{100} := 920^2$,
 $E := \{8365, 8367, \dots, 8561, 8563\}$
42. **(940, 4368, 4468)** $\Rightarrow 4468 - 4368 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 88360$, $T_{100} := 940^2$,
 $E := \{8737, 8739, \dots, 8933, 8935\}$
43. **(960, 4558, 4658)** $\Rightarrow 4658 - 4558 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 92160$, $T_{100} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{9117, 9119, \dots, 9313, 9315\}$
44. **(980, 4752, 4852)** $\Rightarrow 4852 - 4752 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 96040$, $T_{100} := 980^2$,
 $E := \{9505, 9507, \dots, 9701, 9703\}$
45. **(1000, 4950, 5050)** $\Rightarrow 5050 - 4950 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 100000$, $T_{100} := 1000^2$,
 $E := \{9901, 9903, \dots, 10097, 10099\}$

Result 4.8. Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $a = 10^2 + 2 \times 10 = 120 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $a = 20 = 2 \times 10 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, a \in \{120, 140, \dots, 980, 1000\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - b = 100 = 10^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{100} := a^2, a \in \{120, 140, \dots, 980, 1000\};$
- (v) *Magic Sums:*
 $S_{10 \times 10} := a \times (2k + 10), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 44, 45\}, \text{i.e., } a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$
 Alternatively, $S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{a^2}{10}, a \in \{120, 140, \dots, 980, 1000\}.$

4.9 Magic Squares of Order 11

This subsection brings magic squares of order 11 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **seven** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

1. **(143, 24, 145)** $\Rightarrow 145 - 24 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 1859$, $T_{121} := 143^2$,
 $E := \{49, 51, \dots, 287, 289\}$ or $E := \{109, 110, \dots, 228, 229\}$
2. **(165, 52, 173)** $\Rightarrow 173 - 52 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 2475$, $T_{121} := 165^2$,
 $E := \{105, 107, \dots, 343, 345\}$ or $E := \{165, 166, \dots, 284, 285\}$
3. **(187, 84, 205)** $\Rightarrow 205 - 84 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 3179$, $T_{121} := 187^2$,
 $E := \{169, 171, \dots, 407, 409\}$ or $E := \{229, 230, \dots, 348, 349\}$

4. **(209, 120, 241)** $\Rightarrow 241 - 120 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 3971$, $T_{121} := 209^2$,
 $E := \{241, 243, \dots, 479, 481\}$ or $E := \{301, 302, \dots, 420, 421\}$
5. **(231, 160, 281)** $\Rightarrow 281 - 160 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 4851$, $T_{121} := 231^2$,
 $E := \{321, 323, \dots, 559, 561\}$ or $E := \{381, 382, \dots, 500, 501\}$
6. **(253, 204, 325)** $\Rightarrow 325 - 204 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 5819$, $T_{121} := 253^2$,
 $E := \{409, 411, \dots, 647, 649\}$ or $E := \{469, 470, \dots, 588, 589\}$
7. **(275, 252, 373)** $\Rightarrow 373 - 252 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 6875$, $T_{121} := 275^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 743, 745\}$ or $E := \{565, 566, \dots, 684, 685\}$
8. **(297, 304, 425)** $\Rightarrow 425 - 304 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 8019$, $T_{121} := 297^2$,
 $E := \{609, 611, \dots, 847, 849\}$ or $E := \{669, 670, \dots, 788, 789\}$
9. **(319, 360, 481)** $\Rightarrow 481 - 360 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 9251$, $T_{121} := 319^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 959, 961\}$ or $E := \{781, 782, \dots, 900, 901\}$
10. **(341, 420, 541)** $\Rightarrow 541 - 420 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 10571$, $T_{121} := 341^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 1079, 1081\}$ or $E := \{901, 902, \dots, 1020, 1021\}$
11. **(363, 484, 605)** $\Rightarrow 605 - 484 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 11979$, $T_{121} := 363^2$,
 $E := \{969, 971, \dots, 1207, 1209\}$ or $E := \{1029, 1030, \dots, 1148, 1149\}$
12. **(385, 552, 673)** $\Rightarrow 673 - 552 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 13475$, $T_{121} := 385^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 1343, 1345\}$ or $E := \{1165, 1166, \dots, 1284, 1285\}$
13. **(407, 624, 745)** $\Rightarrow 745 - 624 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 15059$, $T_{121} := 407^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 1487, 1489\}$ or $E := \{1309, 1310, \dots, 1428, 1429\}$
14. **(429, 700, 821)** $\Rightarrow 821 - 700 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 16731$, $T_{121} := 429^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 1639, 1641\}$ or $E := \{1461, 1462, \dots, 1580, 1581\}$
15. **(451, 780, 901)** $\Rightarrow 901 - 780 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 18491$, $T_{121} := 451^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 1799, 1801\}$ or $E := \{1621, 1622, \dots, 1740, 1741\}$
16. **(473, 864, 985)** $\Rightarrow 985 - 864 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 20339$, $T_{121} := 473^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 1967, 1969\}$ or $E := \{1789, 1790, \dots, 1908, 1909\}$
17. **(495, 952, 1073)** $\Rightarrow 1073 - 952 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 22275$, $T_{121} := 495^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 2143, 2145\}$ or $E := \{1965, 1966, \dots, 2084, 2085\}$
18. **(517, 1044, 1165)** $\Rightarrow 1165 - 1044 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 24299$, $T_{121} := 517^2$,
 $E := \{2089, 2091, \dots, 2327, 2329\}$ or $E := \{2149, 2150, \dots, 2268, 2269\}$
19. **(539, 1140, 1261)** $\Rightarrow 1261 - 1140 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 26411$, $T_{121} := 539^2$,
 $E := \{2281, 2283, \dots, 2519, 2521\}$ or $E := \{2341, 2342, \dots, 2460, 2461\}$
20. **(561, 1240, 1361)** $\Rightarrow 1361 - 1240 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 28611$, $T_{121} := 561^2$,
 $E := \{2481, 2483, \dots, 2719, 2721\}$ or $E := \{2541, 2542, \dots, 2660, 2661\}$

21. **(583, 1344, 1465)** $\Rightarrow 1465 - 1344 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 30899$, $T_{121} := 583^2$,
 $E := \{2689, 2691, \dots, 2927, 2929\}$ or $E := \{2749, 2750, \dots, 2868, 2869\}$
22. **(605, 1452, 1573)** $\Rightarrow 1573 - 1452 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 33275$, $T_{121} := 605^2$,
 $E := \{2905, 2907, \dots, 3143, 3145\}$ or $E := \{2965, 2966, \dots, 3084, 3085\}$
23. **(627, 1564, 1685)** $\Rightarrow 1685 - 1564 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 35739$, $T_{121} := 627^2$,
 $E := \{3129, 3131, \dots, 3367, 3369\}$ or $E := \{3189, 3190, \dots, 3308, 3309\}$
24. **(649, 1680, 1801)** $\Rightarrow 1801 - 1680 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 38291$, $T_{121} := 649^2$,
 $E := \{3361, 3363, \dots, 3599, 3601\}$ or $E := \{3421, 3422, \dots, 3540, 3541\}$
25. **(671, 1800, 1921)** $\Rightarrow 1921 - 1800 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 40931$, $T_{121} := 671^2$,
 $E := \{3601, 3603, \dots, 3839, 3841\}$ or $E := \{3661, 3662, \dots, 3780, 3781\}$
26. **(693, 1924, 2045)** $\Rightarrow 2045 - 1924 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 43659$, $T_{121} := 693^2$,
 $E := \{3849, 3851, \dots, 4087, 4089\}$ or $E := \{3909, 3910, \dots, 4028, 4029\}$
27. **(715, 2052, 2173)** $\Rightarrow 2173 - 2052 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 46475$, $T_{121} := 715^2$,
 $E := \{4105, 4107, \dots, 4343, 4345\}$ or $E := \{4165, 4166, \dots, 4284, 4285\}$
28. **(737, 2184, 2305)** $\Rightarrow 2305 - 2184 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 49379$, $T_{121} := 737^2$,
 $E := \{4369, 4371, \dots, 4607, 4609\}$ or $E := \{4429, 4430, \dots, 4548, 4549\}$
29. **(759, 2320, 2441)** $\Rightarrow 2441 - 2320 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 52371$, $T_{121} := 759^2$,
 $E := \{4641, 4643, \dots, 4879, 4881\}$ or $E := \{4701, 4702, \dots, 4820, 4821\}$
30. **(781, 2460, 2581)** $\Rightarrow 2581 - 2460 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 55451$, $T_{121} := 781^2$,
 $E := \{4921, 4923, \dots, 5159, 5161\}$ or $E := \{4981, 4982, \dots, 5100, 5101\}$
31. **(803, 2604, 2725)** $\Rightarrow 2725 - 2604 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 58619$, $T_{121} := 803^2$,
 $E := \{5209, 5211, \dots, 5447, 5449\}$ or $E := \{5269, 5270, \dots, 5388, 5389\}$
32. **(825, 2752, 2873)** $\Rightarrow 2873 - 2752 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 61875$, $T_{121} := 825^2$,
 $E := \{5505, 5507, \dots, 5743, 5745\}$ or $E := \{5565, 5566, \dots, 5684, 5685\}$
33. **(847, 2904, 3025)** $\Rightarrow 3025 - 2904 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 65219$, $T_{121} := 847^2$,
 $E := \{5809, 5811, \dots, 6047, 6049\}$ or $E := \{5869, 5870, \dots, 5988, 5989\}$
34. **(869, 3060, 3181)** $\Rightarrow 3181 - 3060 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 68651$, $T_{121} := 869^2$,
 $E := \{6121, 6123, \dots, 6359, 6361\}$ or $E := \{6181, 6182, \dots, 6300, 6301\}$
35. **(891, 3220, 3341)** $\Rightarrow 3341 - 3220 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 72171$, $T_{121} := 891^2$,
 $E := \{6441, 6443, \dots, 6679, 6681\}$ or $E := \{6501, 6502, \dots, 6620, 6621\}$
36. **(913, 3384, 3505)** $\Rightarrow 3505 - 3384 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 75779$, $T_{121} := 913^2$,
 $E := \{6769, 6771, \dots, 7007, 7009\}$ or $E := \{6829, 6830, \dots, 6948, 6949\}$
37. **(935, 3552, 3673)** $\Rightarrow 3673 - 3552 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 79475$, $T_{121} := 935^2$,
 $E := \{7105, 7107, \dots, 7343, 7345\}$ or $E := \{7165, 7166, \dots, 7284, 7285\}$

38. **(957, 3724, 3845)** $\Rightarrow 3845 - 3724 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 83259$, $T_{121} := 957^2$,
 $E := \{7449, 7451, \dots, 7687, 7689\}$ or $E := \{7509, 7510, \dots, 7628, 7629\}$
39. **(979, 3900, 4021)** $\Rightarrow 4021 - 3900 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 87131$, $T_{121} := 979^2$,
 $E := \{7801, 7803, \dots, 8039, 8041\}$ or $E := \{7861, 7862, \dots, 7980, 7981\}$

Result 4.9. Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $a = 11^2 + 2 \times 11 = 143 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $a = 22 = 2 \times 11 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $a \in \{143, 165, \dots, 957, 979\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - b = 121 = 11^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{121} := a^2$, $a \in \{143, 165, \dots, 957, 979\};$
- (v) *Magic Sums:*
 $S_{11 \times 11} := a \times (2k + 11)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 38, 39\}$, i.e., $a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.
 Alternatively, $S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{a^2}{11}$, $a \in \{143, 165, \dots, 957, 979\}$.

4.10 Magic Squares of Order 12

This subsection brings magic squares of order 12 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **eight** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

- (168, 26, 170)** $\Rightarrow 170 - 26 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 2352$, $T_{144} := 168^2$,
 $E := \{53, 55, \dots, 337, 339\}$
- (192, 56, 200)** $\Rightarrow 200 - 56 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 3072$, $T_{144} := 192^2$,
 $E := \{113, 115, \dots, 397, 399\}$
- (216, 90, 234)** $\Rightarrow 234 - 90 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 3888$, $T_{144} := 216^2$,
 $E := \{181, 183, \dots, 465, 467\}$
- (240, 128, 272)** $\Rightarrow 272 - 128 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 4800$, $T_{144} := 240^2$,
 $E := \{257, 259, \dots, 541, 543\}$
- (264, 170, 314)** $\Rightarrow 314 - 170 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 5808$, $T_{144} := 264^2$,
 $E := \{341, 343, \dots, 625, 627\}$
- (288, 216, 360)** $\Rightarrow 360 - 216 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6912$, $T_{144} := 288^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 717, 719\}$

7. **(312, 266, 410)** $\Rightarrow 410 - 266 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 8112$, $T_{144} := 312^2$,
 $E := \{533, 535, \dots, 817, 819\}$
8. **(336, 320, 464)** $\Rightarrow 464 - 320 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 9408$, $T_{144} := 336^2$,
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 925, 927\}$
9. **(360, 378, 522)** $\Rightarrow 522 - 378 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 10800$, $T_{144} := 360^2$,
 $E := \{757, 759, \dots, 1041, 1043\}$
10. **(384, 440, 584)** $\Rightarrow 584 - 440 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 12288$, $T_{144} := 384^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 1165, 1167\}$
11. **(408, 506, 650)** $\Rightarrow 650 - 506 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 13872$, $T_{144} := 408^2$,
 $E := \{1013, 1015, \dots, 1297, 1299\}$
12. **(432, 576, 720)** $\Rightarrow 720 - 576 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 15552$, $T_{144} := 432^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 1437, 1439\}$
13. **(456, 650, 794)** $\Rightarrow 794 - 650 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 17328$, $T_{144} := 456^2$,
 $E := \{1301, 1303, \dots, 1585, 1587\}$
14. **(480, 728, 872)** $\Rightarrow 872 - 728 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 19200$, $T_{144} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 1741, 1743\}$
15. **(504, 810, 954)** $\Rightarrow 954 - 810 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 21168$, $T_{144} := 504^2$,
 $E := \{1621, 1623, \dots, 1905, 1907\}$
16. **(528, 896, 1040)** $\Rightarrow 1040 - 896 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 23232$, $T_{144} := 528^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 2077, 2079\}$
17. **(552, 986, 1130)** $\Rightarrow 1130 - 986 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 25392$, $T_{144} := 552^2$,
 $E := \{1973, 1975, \dots, 2257, 2259\}$
18. **(576, 1080, 1224)** $\Rightarrow 1224 - 1080 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 27648$, $T_{144} := 576^2$,
 $E := \{2161, 2163, \dots, 2445, 2447\}$
19. **(600, 1178, 1322)** $\Rightarrow 1322 - 1178 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 30000$, $T_{144} := 600^2$,
 $E := \{2357, 2359, \dots, 2641, 2643\}$
20. **(624, 1280, 1424)** $\Rightarrow 1424 - 1280 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 32448$, $T_{144} := 624^2$,
 $E := \{2561, 2563, \dots, 2845, 2847\}$
21. **(648, 1386, 1530)** $\Rightarrow 1530 - 1386 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 34992$, $T_{144} := 648^2$,
 $E := \{2773, 2775, \dots, 3057, 3059\}$
22. **(672, 1496, 1640)** $\Rightarrow 1640 - 1496 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 37632$, $T_{144} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{2993, 2995, \dots, 3277, 3279\}$
23. **(696, 1610, 1754)** $\Rightarrow 1754 - 1610 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 40368$, $T_{144} := 696^2$,
 $E := \{3221, 3223, \dots, 3505, 3507\}$

24. **(720, 1728, 1872)** $\Rightarrow 1872 - 1728 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 43200$, $T_{144} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{3457, 3459, \dots, 3741, 3743\}$
25. **(744, 1850, 1994)** $\Rightarrow 1994 - 1850 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 46128$, $T_{144} := 744^2$,
 $E := \{3701, 3703, \dots, 3985, 3987\}$
26. **(768, 1976, 2120)** $\Rightarrow 2120 - 1976 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 49152$, $T_{144} := 768^2$,
 $E := \{3953, 3955, \dots, 4237, 4239\}$
27. **(792, 2106, 2250)** $\Rightarrow 2250 - 2106 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 52272$, $T_{144} := 792^2$,
 $E := \{4213, 4215, \dots, 4497, 4499\}$
28. **(816, 2240, 2384)** $\Rightarrow 2384 - 2240 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 55488$, $T_{144} := 816^2$,
 $E := \{4481, 4483, \dots, 4765, 4767\}$
29. **(840, 2378, 2522)** $\Rightarrow 2522 - 2378 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 58800$, $T_{144} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{4757, 4759, \dots, 5041, 5043\}$
30. **(864, 2520, 2664)** $\Rightarrow 2664 - 2520 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 62208$, $T_{144} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{5041, 5043, \dots, 5325, 5327\}$
31. **(888, 2666, 2810)** $\Rightarrow 2810 - 2666 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 65712$, $T_{144} := 888^2$,
 $E := \{5333, 5335, \dots, 5617, 5619\}$
32. **(912, 2816, 2960)** $\Rightarrow 2960 - 2816 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 69312$, $T_{144} := 912^2$,
 $E := \{5633, 5635, \dots, 5917, 5919\}$
33. **(936, 2970, 3114)** $\Rightarrow 3114 - 2970 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 73008$, $T_{144} := 936^2$,
 $E := \{5941, 5943, \dots, 6225, 6227\}$
34. **(960, 3128, 3272)** $\Rightarrow 3272 - 3128 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 76800$, $T_{144} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{6257, 6259, \dots, 6541, 6543\}$
35. **(984, 3290, 3434)** $\Rightarrow 3434 - 3290 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 80688$, $T_{144} := 984^2$,
 $E := \{6581, 6583, \dots, 6865, 6867\}$

Result 4.10. *Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:*

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $a = 12^2 + 2 \times 12 = 168 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $a = 24 = 2 \times 12 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, a \in \{168, 192, \dots, 960, 984\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - b = 144 = 12^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{144} := a^2, a \in \{168, 192, \dots, 960, 984\};$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{12 \times 12} := a \times (2k + 12), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 34, 35\}, \text{ i.e., } a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{12 \times 12} := \frac{a^2}{12}, a \in \{168, 192, \dots, 960, 984\}.$$

4.11 Magic Squares of Order 13

This subsection brings magic squares of order 13 generated by Pythagorean triples, $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **nine** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

1. **(195, 28, 197)** $\Rightarrow 197 - 28 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 2925$, $T_{169} := 195^2$,
 $E := \{57, 59, \dots, 391, 393\}$ or $E := \{141, 142, \dots, 308, 309\}$
2. **(221, 60, 229)** $\Rightarrow 229 - 60 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 3757$, $T_{169} := 221^2$,
 $E := \{121, 123, \dots, 455, 457\}$ or $E := \{205, 206, \dots, 372, 373\}$
3. **(247, 96, 265)** $\Rightarrow 265 - 96 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 4693$, $T_{169} := 247^2$,
 $E := \{193, 195, \dots, 527, 529\}$ or $E := \{277, 278, \dots, 444, 445\}$
4. **(273, 136, 305)** $\Rightarrow 305 - 136 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 5733$, $T_{169} := 273^2$,
 $E := \{273, 275, \dots, 607, 609\}$ or $E := \{357, 358, \dots, 524, 525\}$
5. **(299, 180, 349)** $\Rightarrow 349 - 180 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 6877$, $T_{169} := 299^2$,
 $E := \{361, 363, \dots, 695, 697\}$ or $E := \{445, 446, \dots, 612, 613\}$
6. **(325, 228, 397)** $\Rightarrow 397 - 228 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 8125$, $T_{169} := 325^2$,
 $E := \{457, 459, \dots, 791, 793\}$ or $E := \{541, 542, \dots, 708, 709\}$
7. **(351, 280, 449)** $\Rightarrow 449 - 280 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 9477$, $T_{169} := 351^2$,
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 895, 897\}$ or $E := \{645, 646, \dots, 812, 813\}$
8. **(377, 336, 505)** $\Rightarrow 505 - 336 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 10933$, $T_{169} := 377^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 1007, 1009\}$ or $E := \{757, 758, \dots, 924, 925\}$
9. **(403, 396, 565)** $\Rightarrow 565 - 396 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 12493$, $T_{169} := 403^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 1127, 1129\}$ or $E := \{877, 878, \dots, 1044, 1045\}$
10. **(429, 460, 629)** $\Rightarrow 629 - 460 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 14157$, $T_{169} := 429^2$,
 $E := \{921, 923, \dots, 1255, 1257\}$ or $E := \{1005, 1006, \dots, 1172, 1173\}$
11. **(455, 528, 697)** $\Rightarrow 697 - 528 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 15925$, $T_{169} := 455^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 1391, 1393\}$ or $E := \{1141, 1142, \dots, 1308, 1309\}$
12. **(481, 600, 769)** $\Rightarrow 769 - 600 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 17797$, $T_{169} := 481^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 1535, 1537\}$ or $E := \{1285, 1286, \dots, 1452, 1453\}$
13. **(507, 676, 845)** $\Rightarrow 845 - 676 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 19773$, $T_{169} := 507^2$,
 $E := \{1353, 1355, \dots, 1687, 1689\}$ or $E := \{1437, 1438, \dots, 1604, 1605\}$

14. **(533, 756, 925)** $\Rightarrow 925 - 756 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 21853$, $T_{169} := 533^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 1847, 1849\}$ or $E := \{1597, 1598, \dots, 1764, 1765\}$
15. **(559, 840, 1009)** $\Rightarrow 1009 - 840 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 24037$, $T_{169} := 559^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 2015, 2017\}$ or $E := \{1765, 1766, \dots, 1932, 1933\}$
16. **(585, 928, 1097)** $\Rightarrow 1097 - 928 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 26325$, $T_{169} := 585^2$,
 $E := \{1857, 1859, \dots, 2191, 2193\}$ or $E := \{1941, 1942, \dots, 2108, 2109\}$
17. **(611, 1020, 1189)** $\Rightarrow 1189 - 1020 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 28717$, $T_{169} := 611^2$,
 $E := \{2041, 2043, \dots, 2375, 2377\}$ or $E := \{2125, 2126, \dots, 2292, 2293\}$
18. **(637, 1116, 1285)** $\Rightarrow 1285 - 1116 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 31213$, $T_{169} := 637^2$,
 $E := \{2233, 2235, \dots, 2567, 2569\}$ or $E := \{2317, 2318, \dots, 2484, 2485\}$
19. **(663, 1216, 1385)** $\Rightarrow 1385 - 1216 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 33813$, $T_{169} := 663^2$,
 $E := \{2433, 2435, \dots, 2767, 2769\}$ or $E := \{2517, 2518, \dots, 2684, 2685\}$
20. **(689, 1320, 1489)** $\Rightarrow 1489 - 1320 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 36517$, $T_{169} := 689^2$,
 $E := \{2641, 2643, \dots, 2975, 2977\}$ or $E := \{2725, 2726, \dots, 2892, 2893\}$
21. **(715, 1428, 1597)** $\Rightarrow 1597 - 1428 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 39325$, $T_{169} := 715^2$,
 $E := \{2857, 2859, \dots, 3191, 3193\}$ or $E := \{2941, 2942, \dots, 3108, 3109\}$
22. **(741, 1540, 1709)** $\Rightarrow 1709 - 1540 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 42237$, $T_{169} := 741^2$,
 $E := \{3081, 3083, \dots, 3415, 3417\}$ or $E := \{3165, 3166, \dots, 3332, 3333\}$
23. **(767, 1656, 1825)** $\Rightarrow 1825 - 1656 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 45253$, $T_{169} := 767^2$,
 $E := \{3313, 3315, \dots, 3647, 3649\}$ or $E := \{3397, 3398, \dots, 3564, 3565\}$
24. **(793, 1776, 1945)** $\Rightarrow 1945 - 1776 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 48373$, $T_{169} := 793^2$,
 $E := \{3553, 3555, \dots, 3887, 3889\}$ or $E := \{3637, 3638, \dots, 3804, 3805\}$
25. **(819, 1900, 2069)** $\Rightarrow 2069 - 1900 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 51597$, $T_{169} := 819^2$,
 $E := \{3801, 3803, \dots, 4135, 4137\}$ or $E := \{3885, 3886, \dots, 4052, 4053\}$
26. **(845, 2028, 2197)** $\Rightarrow 2197 - 2028 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 54925$, $T_{169} := 845^2$,
 $E := \{4057, 4059, \dots, 4391, 4393\}$ or $E := \{4141, 4142, \dots, 4308, 4309\}$
27. **(871, 2160, 2329)** $\Rightarrow 2329 - 2160 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 58357$, $T_{169} := 871^2$,
 $E := \{4321, 4323, \dots, 4655, 4657\}$ or $E := \{4405, 4406, \dots, 4572, 4573\}$
28. **(897, 2296, 2465)** $\Rightarrow 2465 - 2296 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 61893$, $T_{169} := 897^2$,
 $E := \{4593, 4595, \dots, 4927, 4929\}$ or $E := \{4677, 4678, \dots, 4844, 4845\}$
29. **(923, 2436, 2605)** $\Rightarrow 2605 - 2436 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 65533$, $T_{169} := 923^2$,
 $E := \{4873, 4875, \dots, 5207, 5209\}$ or $E := \{4957, 4958, \dots, 5124, 5125\}$
30. **(949, 2580, 2749)** $\Rightarrow 2749 - 2580 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 69277$, $T_{169} := 949^2$,
 $E := \{5161, 5163, \dots, 5495, 5497\}$ or $E := \{5245, 5246, \dots, 5412, 5413\}$

$$31. \text{ (975, 2728, 2897)} \Rightarrow 2897 - 2728 = 13^2, S_{13 \times 13} := 73125, T_{169} := 975^2, \\ E := \{5457, 5459, \dots, 5791, 5793\} \text{ or } E := \{5541, 5542, \dots, 5708, 5709\}$$

Result 4.11. Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:

(i) *First Triple:*

$$a = 13^2 + 2 \times 13 = 195 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$a = 26 = 2 \times 13 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, a \in \{195, 221, \dots, 949, 975\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - b = 169 = 13^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{169} := a^2, a \in \{195, 221, \dots, 949, 975\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{13 \times 13} := a \times (2k + 13), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 30, 31\}, \text{ i.e., } a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{a^2}{13}, a \in \{195, 221, \dots, 949, 975\}.$$

4.12 Magic Squares of Order 14

This subsection brings magic squares of order 14 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **nine** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

$$1. \text{ (224, 30, 226)} \Rightarrow 226 - 30 = 14^2, S_{14 \times 14} := 3584, T_{196} := 224^2, \\ E := \{61, 63, \dots, 449, 451\}$$

$$2. \text{ (252, 64, 260)} \Rightarrow 260 - 64 = 14^2, S_{14 \times 14} := 4536, T_{196} := 252^2, \\ E := \{129, 131, \dots, 517, 519\}$$

$$3. \text{ (280, 102, 298)} \Rightarrow 298 - 102 = 14^2, S_{14 \times 14} := 5600, T_{196} := 280^2, \\ E := \{205, 207, \dots, 593, 595\}$$

$$4. \text{ (308, 144, 340)} \Rightarrow 340 - 144 = 14^2, S_{14 \times 14} := 6776, T_{196} := 308^2, \\ E := \{289, 291, \dots, 677, 679\}$$

$$5. \text{ (336, 190, 386)} \Rightarrow 386 - 190 = 14^2, S_{14 \times 14} := 8064, T_{196} := 336^2, \\ E := \{381, 383, \dots, 769, 771\}$$

$$6. \text{ (364, 240, 436)} \Rightarrow 436 - 240 = 14^2, S_{14 \times 14} := 9464, T_{196} := 364^2, \\ E := \{481, 483, \dots, 869, 871\}$$

$$7. \text{ (392, 294, 490)} \Rightarrow 490 - 294 = 14^2, S_{14 \times 14} := 10976, T_{196} := 392^2, \\ E := \{589, 591, \dots, 977, 979\}$$

8. **(420, 352, 548)** $\Rightarrow 548 - 352 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 12600$, $T_{196} := 420^2$,
 $E := \{705, 707, \dots, 1093, 1095\}$
9. **(448, 414, 610)** $\Rightarrow 610 - 414 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 14336$, $T_{196} := 448^2$,
 $E := \{829, 831, \dots, 1217, 1219\}$
10. **(476, 480, 676)** $\Rightarrow 676 - 480 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 16184$, $T_{196} := 476^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 1349, 1351\}$
11. **(504, 550, 746)** $\Rightarrow 746 - 550 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 18144$, $T_{196} := 504^2$,
 $E := \{1101, 1103, \dots, 1489, 1491\}$
12. **(532, 624, 820)** $\Rightarrow 820 - 624 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 20216$, $T_{196} := 532^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 1637, 1639\}$
13. **(560, 702, 898)** $\Rightarrow 898 - 702 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 22400$, $T_{196} := 560^2$,
 $E := \{1405, 1407, \dots, 1793, 1795\}$
14. **(588, 784, 980)** $\Rightarrow 980 - 784 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 24696$, $T_{196} := 588^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 1957, 1959\}$
15. **(616, 870, 1066)** $\Rightarrow 1066 - 870 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 27104$, $T_{196} := 616^2$,
 $E := \{1741, 1743, \dots, 2129, 2131\}$
16. **(644, 960, 1156)** $\Rightarrow 1156 - 960 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 29624$, $T_{196} := 644^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 2309, 2311\}$
17. **(672, 1054, 1250)** $\Rightarrow 1250 - 1054 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 32256$, $T_{196} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{2109, 2111, \dots, 2497, 2499\}$
18. **(700, 1152, 1348)** $\Rightarrow 1348 - 1152 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 35000$, $T_{196} := 700^2$,
 $E := \{2305, 2307, \dots, 2693, 2695\}$
19. **(728, 1254, 1450)** $\Rightarrow 1450 - 1254 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 37856$, $T_{196} := 728^2$,
 $E := \{2509, 2511, \dots, 2897, 2899\}$
20. **(756, 1360, 1556)** $\Rightarrow 1556 - 1360 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 40824$, $T_{196} := 756^2$,
 $E := \{2721, 2723, \dots, 3109, 3111\}$
21. **(784, 1470, 1666)** $\Rightarrow 1666 - 1470 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 43904$, $T_{196} := 784^2$,
 $E := \{2941, 2943, \dots, 3329, 3331\}$
22. **(812, 1584, 1780)** $\Rightarrow 1780 - 1584 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 47096$, $T_{196} := 812^2$,
 $E := \{3169, 3171, \dots, 3557, 3559\}$
23. **(840, 1702, 1898)** $\Rightarrow 1898 - 1702 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 50400$, $T_{196} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{3405, 3407, \dots, 3793, 3795\}$
24. **(868, 1824, 2020)** $\Rightarrow 2020 - 1824 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 53816$, $T_{196} := 868^2$,
 $E := \{3649, 3651, \dots, 4037, 4039\}$

25. **(896, 1950, 2146)** $\Rightarrow 2146 - 1950 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 57344$, $T_{196} := 896^2$,
 $E := \{3901, 3903, \dots, 4289, 4291\}$
26. **(924, 2080, 2276)** $\Rightarrow 2276 - 2080 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 60984$, $T_{196} := 924^2$,
 $E := \{4161, 4163, \dots, 4549, 4551\}$
27. **(952, 2214, 2410)** $\Rightarrow 2410 - 2214 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 64736$, $T_{196} := 952^2$,
 $E := \{4429, 4431, \dots, 4817, 4819\}$
28. **(980, 2352, 2548)** $\Rightarrow 2548 - 2352 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 68600$, $T_{196} := 980^2$,
 $E := \{4705, 4707, \dots, 5093, 5095\}$

Result 4.12. *Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:*

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $a = 14^2 + 2 \times 14 = 224 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $a = 24 = 2 \times 12 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $a \in \{224, 252, \dots, 952, 980\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - b = 196 = 14^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{196} := a^2$, $a \in \{224, 252, \dots, 952, 980\};$
- (v) *Magic Sums:*
 $S_{14 \times 14} := a \times (2k + 14)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 27, 28\}$, *i.e.*, $a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.
 Alternatively, $S_{14 \times 14} := \frac{a^2}{14}$, $a \in \{224, 252, \dots, 952, 980\}$.

4.13 Magic Squares of Order 15

This subsection brings magic squares of order 15 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **ten** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

- (255, 32, 257)** $\Rightarrow 257 - 32 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 4335$, $T_{225} := 255^2$,
 $E := \{65, 67, \dots, 511, 513\}$ or $E := \{177, 178, \dots, 400, 401\}$
- (285, 68, 293)** $\Rightarrow 293 - 68 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 5415$, $T_{225} := 285^2$,
 $E := \{137, 139, \dots, 583, 585\}$ or $E := \{249, 250, \dots, 472, 473\}$
- (315, 108, 333)** $\Rightarrow 333 - 108 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 6615$, $T_{225} := 315^2$,
 $E := \{217, 219, \dots, 663, 665\}$ or $E := \{329, 330, \dots, 552, 553\}$
- (345, 152, 377)** $\Rightarrow 377 - 152 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 7935$, $T_{225} := 345^2$,
 $E := \{305, 307, \dots, 751, 753\}$ or $E := \{417, 418, \dots, 640, 641\}$

5. **(375, 200, 425)** $\Rightarrow 425 - 200 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 9375$, $T_{225} := 375^2$,
 $E := \{401, 403, \dots, 847, 849\}$ or $E := \{513, 514, \dots, 736, 737\}$
6. **(405, 252, 477)** $\Rightarrow 477 - 252 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 10935$, $T_{225} := 405^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 951, 953\}$ or $E := \{617, 618, \dots, 840, 841\}$
7. **(435, 308, 533)** $\Rightarrow 533 - 308 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 12615$, $T_{225} := 435^2$,
 $E := \{617, 619, \dots, 1063, 1065\}$ or $E := \{729, 730, \dots, 952, 953\}$
8. **(465, 368, 593)** $\Rightarrow 593 - 368 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 14415$, $T_{225} := 465^2$,
 $E := \{737, 739, \dots, 1183, 1185\}$ or $E := \{849, 850, \dots, 1072, 1073\}$
9. **(495, 432, 657)** $\Rightarrow 657 - 432 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 16335$, $T_{225} := 495^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 1311, 1313\}$ or $E := \{977, 978, \dots, 1200, 1201\}$
10. **(525, 500, 725)** $\Rightarrow 725 - 500 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 18375$, $T_{225} := 525^2$,
 $E := \{1001, 1003, \dots, 1447, 1449\}$ or $E := \{1113, 1114, \dots, 1336, 1337\}$
11. **(555, 572, 797)** $\Rightarrow 797 - 572 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 20535$, $T_{225} := 555^2$,
 $E := \{1145, 1147, \dots, 1591, 1593\}$ or $E := \{1257, 1258, \dots, 1480, 1481\}$
12. **(585, 648, 873)** $\Rightarrow 873 - 648 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 22815$, $T_{225} := 585^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 1743, 1745\}$ or $E := \{1409, 1410, \dots, 1632, 1633\}$
13. **(615, 728, 953)** $\Rightarrow 953 - 728 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 25215$, $T_{225} := 615^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 1903, 1905\}$ or $E := \{1569, 1570, \dots, 1792, 1793\}$
14. **(645, 812, 1037)** $\Rightarrow 1037 - 812 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 27735$, $T_{225} := 645^2$,
 $E := \{1625, 1627, \dots, 2071, 2073\}$ or $E := \{1737, 1738, \dots, 1960, 1961\}$
15. **(675, 900, 1125)** $\Rightarrow 1125 - 900 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 30375$, $T_{225} := 675^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 2247, 2249\}$ or $E := \{1913, 1914, \dots, 2136, 2137\}$
16. **(705, 992, 1217)** $\Rightarrow 1217 - 992 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 33135$, $T_{225} := 705^2$,
 $E := \{1985, 1987, \dots, 2431, 2433\}$ or $E := \{2097, 2098, \dots, 2320, 2321\}$
17. **(735, 1088, 1313)** $\Rightarrow 1313 - 1088 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 36015$, $T_{225} := 735^2$,
 $E := \{2177, 2179, \dots, 2623, 2625\}$ or $E := \{2289, 2290, \dots, 2512, 2513\}$
18. **(765, 1188, 1413)** $\Rightarrow 1413 - 1188 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 39015$, $T_{225} := 765^2$,
 $E := \{2377, 2379, \dots, 2823, 2825\}$ or $E := \{2489, 2490, \dots, 2712, 2713\}$
19. **(795, 1292, 1517)** $\Rightarrow 1517 - 1292 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 42135$, $T_{225} := 795^2$,
 $E := \{2585, 2587, \dots, 3031, 3033\}$ or $E := \{2697, 2698, \dots, 2920, 2921\}$
20. **(825, 1400, 1625)** $\Rightarrow 1625 - 1400 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 45375$, $T_{225} := 825^2$,
 $E := \{2801, 2803, \dots, 3247, 3249\}$ or $E := \{2913, 2914, \dots, 3136, 3137\}$
21. **(855, 1512, 1737)** $\Rightarrow 1737 - 1512 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 48735$, $T_{225} := 855^2$,
 $E := \{3025, 3027, \dots, 3471, 3473\}$ or $E := \{3137, 3138, \dots, 3360, 3361\}$

22. **(885, 1628, 1853)** $\Rightarrow 1853 - 1628 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 52215$, $T_{225} := 885^2$,
 $E := \{3257, 3259, \dots, 3703, 3705\}$ or $E := \{3369, 3370, \dots, 3592, 3593\}$
23. **(915, 1748, 1973)** $\Rightarrow 1973 - 1748 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 55815$, $T_{225} := 915^2$,
 $E := \{3497, 3499, \dots, 3943, 3945\}$ or $E := \{3609, 3610, \dots, 3832, 3833\}$
24. **(945, 1872, 2097)** $\Rightarrow 2097 - 1872 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 59535$, $T_{225} := 945^2$,
 $E := \{3745, 3747, \dots, 4191, 4193\}$ or $E := \{3857, 3858, \dots, 4080, 4081\}$
25. **(975, 2000, 2225)** $\Rightarrow 2225 - 2000 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 63375$, $T_{225} := 975^2$,
 $E := \{4001, 4003, \dots, 4447, 4449\}$ or $E := \{4113, 4114, \dots, 4336, 4337\}$

Result 4.13. *Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:*

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $a = 15^2 + 2 \times 15 = 255 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $a = 20 = 2 \times 15 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $a \in \{255, 285, \dots, 945, 975\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - b = 225 = 15^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{225} := a^2$, $a \in \{255, 285, \dots, 945, 975\};$
- (v) *Magic Sums:*
 $S_{15 \times 15} := a \times (2k + 15)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 24, 25\}$, i.e., $a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.
 Alternatively, $S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{a^2}{15}$, $a \in \{255, 285, \dots, 945, 975\}$.

4.14 Magic Squares of Order 16

This subsection brings magic squares of order 16 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **ten** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

1. **(288, 34, 290)** $\Rightarrow 290 - 34 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 5184$, $T_{256} := 288^2$,
 $E := \{69, 71, \dots, 577, 579\}$
2. **(320, 72, 328)** $\Rightarrow 328 - 72 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 6400$, $T_{256} := 320^2$,
 $E := \{145, 147, \dots, 653, 655\}$
3. **(352, 114, 370)** $\Rightarrow 370 - 114 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 7744$, $T_{256} := 352^2$,
 $E := \{229, 231, \dots, 737, 739\}$
4. **(384, 160, 416)** $\Rightarrow 416 - 160 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 9216$, $T_{256} := 384^2$,
 $E := \{321, 323, \dots, 829, 831\}$

5. **(416, 210, 466)** $\Rightarrow 466 - 210 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 10816$, $T_{256} := 416^2$,
 $E := \{421, 423, \dots, 929, 931\}$
6. **(448, 264, 520)** $\Rightarrow 520 - 264 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 12544$, $T_{256} := 448^2$,
 $E := \{529, 531, \dots, 1037, 1039\}$
7. **(480, 322, 578)** $\Rightarrow 578 - 322 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 14400$, $T_{256} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{645, 647, \dots, 1153, 1155\}$
8. **(512, 384, 640)** $\Rightarrow 640 - 384 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 16384$, $T_{256} := 512^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 1277, 1279\}$
9. **(544, 450, 706)** $\Rightarrow 706 - 450 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 18496$, $T_{256} := 544^2$,
 $E := \{901, 903, \dots, 1409, 1411\}$
10. **(576, 520, 776)** $\Rightarrow 776 - 520 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 20736$, $T_{256} := 576^2$,
 $E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 1549, 1551\}$
11. **(594, 608, 850)** $\Rightarrow 850 - 594 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 23104$, $T_{256} := 608^2$,
 $E := \{1189, 1191, \dots, 1697, 1699\}$
12. **(640, 672, 928)** $\Rightarrow 928 - 672 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 25600$, $T_{256} := 640^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 1853, 1855\}$
13. **(672, 754, 1010)** $\Rightarrow 1010 - 754 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 28224$, $T_{256} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{1509, 1511, \dots, 2017, 2019\}$
14. **(704, 840, 1096)** $\Rightarrow 1096 - 840 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 30976$, $T_{256} := 704^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 2189, 2191\}$
15. **(736, 930, 1186)** $\Rightarrow 1186 - 930 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 33856$, $T_{256} := 736^2$,
 $E := \{1861, 1863, \dots, 2369, 2371\}$
16. **(768, 1024, 1280)** $\Rightarrow 1280 - 1024 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 36864$, $T_{256} := 768^2$,
 $E := \{2049, 2051, \dots, 2557, 2559\}$
17. **(800, 1122, 1378)** $\Rightarrow 1378 - 1122 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 40000$, $T_{256} := 800^2$,
 $E := \{2245, 2247, \dots, 2753, 2755\}$
18. **(832, 1224, 1480)** $\Rightarrow 1480 - 1224 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 43264$, $T_{256} := 832^2$,
 $E := \{2449, 2451, \dots, 2957, 2959\}$
19. **(864, 1330, 1586)** $\Rightarrow 1586 - 1330 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 46656$, $T_{256} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{2661, 2663, \dots, 3169, 3171\}$
20. **(896, 1440, 1696)** $\Rightarrow 1696 - 1440 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 50176$, $T_{256} := 896^2$,
 $E := \{2881, 2883, \dots, 3389, 3391\}$
21. **(928, 1554, 1810)** $\Rightarrow 1810 - 1554 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 53824$, $T_{256} := 928^2$,
 $E := \{3109, 3111, \dots, 3617, 3619\}$

22. **(960, 1672, 1928)** $\Rightarrow 1928 - 1672 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 57600$, $T_{256} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{3345, 3347, \dots, 3853, 3855\}$
23. **(992, 1794, 2050)** $\Rightarrow 2050 - 1794 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 61504$, $T_{256} := 992^2$,
 $E := \{3589, 3591, \dots, 4097, 4099\}$

Result 4.14. *Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:*

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $a = 16^2 + 2 \times 16 = 288 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $a = 32 = 2 \times 16 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $a \in \{288, 320, \dots, 960, 992\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - b = 256 = 16^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{256} := a^2$, $a \in \{288, 320, \dots, 960, 992\};$
- (v) *Magic Sums:*
 $S_{16 \times 16} := a \times (2k + 16)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 22, 23\}$, *i.e.*, $a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.
 Alternatively, $S_{16 \times 16} := \frac{a^2}{16}$, $a \in \{288, 320, \dots, 960, 992\}$.

4.15 Magic Squares of Order 17

This subsection brings magic squares of order 17 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **twelve** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

- (323, 36, 325)** $\Rightarrow 325 - 36 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 6137$, $T_{289} := 323^2$,
 $E := \{73, 75, \dots, 647, 649\}$ or $E := \{217, 218, \dots, 504, 505\}$
- (357, 76, 365)** $\Rightarrow 365 - 76 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 7497$, $T_{289} := 357^2$,
 $E := \{153, 155, \dots, 727, 729\}$ or $E := \{297, 298, \dots, 584, 585\}$
- (391, 120, 409)** $\Rightarrow 409 - 120 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 8993$, $T_{289} := 391^2$,
 $E := \{241, 243, \dots, 815, 817\}$ or $E := \{385, 386, \dots, 672, 673\}$
- (425, 168, 457)** $\Rightarrow 457 - 168 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 10625$, $T_{289} := 425^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 911, 913\}$ or $E := \{481, 482, \dots, 768, 769\}$
- (459, 220, 509)** $\Rightarrow 509 - 220 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 12393$, $T_{289} := 459^2$,
 $E := \{441, 443, \dots, 1015, 1017\}$ or $E := \{585, 586, \dots, 872, 873\}$
- (493, 276, 565)** $\Rightarrow 565 - 276 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 14297$, $T_{289} := 493^2$,
 $E := \{553, 555, \dots, 1127, 1129\}$ or $E := \{697, 698, \dots, 984, 985\}$

7. **(527, 336, 625)** $\Rightarrow 625 - 336 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 16337$, $T_{289} := 527^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 1247, 1249\}$ or $E := \{817, 818, \dots, 1104, 1105\}$
8. **(561, 400, 689)** $\Rightarrow 689 - 400 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 18513$, $T_{289} := 561^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 1375, 1377\}$ or $E := \{945, 946, \dots, 1232, 1233\}$
9. **(595, 468, 757)** $\Rightarrow 757 - 468 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 20825$, $T_{289} := 595^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 1511, 1513\}$ or $E := \{1081, 1082, \dots, 1368, 1369\}$
10. **(629, 540, 829)** $\Rightarrow 829 - 540 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 23273$, $T_{289} := 629^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 1655, 1657\}$ or $E := \{1225, 1226, \dots, 1512, 1513\}$
11. **(663, 616, 905)** $\Rightarrow 905 - 616 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 25857$, $T_{289} := 663^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 1807, 1809\}$ or $E := \{1377, 1378, \dots, 1664, 1665\}$
12. **(697, 696, 985)** $\Rightarrow 985 - 696 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 28577$, $T_{289} := 697^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 1967, 1969\}$ or $E := \{1537, 1538, \dots, 1824, 1825\}$
13. **(731, 780, 1069)** $\Rightarrow 1069 - 780 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 31433$, $T_{289} := 731^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 2135, 2137\}$ or $E := \{1705, 1706, \dots, 1992, 1993\}$
14. **(765, 868, 1157)** $\Rightarrow 1157 - 868 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 34425$, $T_{289} := 765^2$,
 $E := \{1737, 1739, \dots, 2311, 2313\}$ or $E := \{1881, 1882, \dots, 2168, 2169\}$
15. **(799, 960, 1249)** $\Rightarrow 1249 - 960 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 37553$, $T_{289} := 799^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 2495, 2497\}$ or $E := \{2065, 2066, \dots, 2352, 2353\}$
16. **(833, 1056, 1345)** $\Rightarrow 1345 - 1056 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 40817$, $T_{289} := 833^2$,
 $E := \{2113, 2115, \dots, 2687, 2689\}$ or $E := \{2257, 2258, \dots, 2544, 2545\}$
17. **(867, 1156, 1445)** $\Rightarrow 1445 - 1156 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 44217$, $T_{289} := 867^2$,
 $E := \{2313, 2315, \dots, 2887, 2889\}$ or $E := \{2457, 2458, \dots, 2744, 2745\}$
18. **(901, 1260, 1549)** $\Rightarrow 1549 - 1260 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 47753$, $T_{289} := 901^2$,
 $E := \{2521, 2523, \dots, 3095, 3097\}$ or $E := \{2665, 2666, \dots, 2952, 2953\}$
19. **(935, 1368, 1657)** $\Rightarrow 1657 - 1368 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 51425$, $T_{289} := 935^2$,
 $E := \{2737, 2739, \dots, 3311, 3313\}$ or $E := \{2881, 2882, \dots, 3168, 3169\}$
20. **(969, 1480, 1769)** $\Rightarrow 1769 - 1480 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 55233$, $T_{289} := 969^2$,
 $E := \{2961, 2963, \dots, 3535, 3537\}$ or $E := \{3105, 3106, \dots, 3392, 3393\}$

Result 4.15. *Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:*

(i) *First Triple:*

$$a = 17^2 + 2 \times 17 = 323 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$a = 34 = 2 \times 17 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, a \in \{323, 357, \dots, 935, 969\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - b = 289 = 17^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{289} := a^2, a \in \{323, 357, \dots, 935, 969\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{17 \times 17} := a \times (2k + 17), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 19, 20\}, \text{i.e., } a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{a^2}{17}, a \in \{323, 357, \dots, 935, 969\}.$$

4.16 Magic Squares of Order 18

This subsection brings magic squares of order 18 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **twelve** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Below are respective examples:

1. **(360, 38, 362)** $\Rightarrow 362 - 38 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 7200$, $T_{324} := 360^2$,
 $E := \{77, 79, \dots, 721, 723\}$
2. **(396, 80, 404)** $\Rightarrow 404 - 80 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 8712$, $T_{324} := 396^2$,
 $E := \{161, 163, \dots, 805, 807\}$
3. **(432, 126, 450)** $\Rightarrow 450 - 126 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 10368$, $T_{324} := 432^2$,
 $E := \{253, 255, \dots, 897, 899\}$
4. **(469, 176, 500)** $\Rightarrow 500 - 176 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 12168$, $T_{324} := 468^2$,
 $E := \{353, 355, \dots, 997, 999\}$
5. **(504, 230, 554)** $\Rightarrow 554 - 230 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 14112$, $T_{324} := 504^2$,
 $E := \{461, 463, \dots, 1105, 1107\}$
6. **(540, 288, 612)** $\Rightarrow 612 - 288 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 16200$, $T_{324} := 540^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 1221, 1223\}$
7. **(576, 350, 674)** $\Rightarrow 674 - 350 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 18432$, $T_{324} := 576^2$,
 $E := \{701, 703, \dots, 1345, 1347\}$
8. **(612, 416, 740)** $\Rightarrow 740 - 416 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 20808$, $T_{324} := 612^2$,
 $E := \{833, 835, \dots, 1477, 1479\}$
9. **(648, 486, 810)** $\Rightarrow 810 - 486 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 23328$, $T_{324} := 648^2$,
 $E := \{973, 975, \dots, 1617, 1619\}$
10. **(684, 560, 884)** $\Rightarrow 884 - 560 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 25992$, $T_{324} := 684^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 1765, 1767\}$

11. **(720, 638, 962)** $\Rightarrow 962 - 638 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 28800$, $T_{324} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{1277, 1279, \dots, 1921, 1923\}$
12. **(756, 720, 1044)** $\Rightarrow 1044 - 720 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 31752$, $T_{324} := 756^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 2085, 2087\}$
13. **(792, 806, 1130)** $\Rightarrow 1130 - 806 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 34848$, $T_{324} := 792^2$,
 $E := \{1613, 1615, \dots, 2257, 2259\}$
14. **(828, 896, 1220)** $\Rightarrow 1220 - 896 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 38088$, $T_{324} := 828^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 2437, 2439\}$
15. **(864, 990, 1314)** $\Rightarrow 1314 - 990 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 41472$, $T_{324} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 2625, 2627\}$
16. **(900, 1088, 1412)** $\Rightarrow 1412 - 1088 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 45000$, $T_{324} := 900^2$,
 $E := \{2177, 2179, \dots, 2821, 2823\}$
17. **(936, 1190, 1514)** $\Rightarrow 1514 - 1190 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 48672$, $T_{324} := 936^2$,
 $E := \{2381, 2383, \dots, 3025, 3027\}$
18. **(972, 1296, 1620)** $\Rightarrow 1620 - 1296 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 52488$, $T_{324} := 972^2$,
 $E := \{2593, 2595, \dots, 3237, 3239\}$

Result 4.16. *Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:*

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $a = 18^2 + 2 \times 18 = 360 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $a = 36 = 2 \times 18 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $a \in \{360, 396, \dots, 936, 972\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - b = 324 = 18^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{324} := a^2$, $a \in \{360, 396, \dots, 936, 972\};$
- (v) *Magic Sums:*
 $S_{18 \times 18} := a \times (2k + 18)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18\}$, *i.e.*, $a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.
 Alternatively, $S_{18 \times 18} := \frac{a^2}{18}$, $a \in \{360, 396, \dots, 936, 972\}$.

4.17 Magic Squares of Order 19

This subsection brings magic squares of order 19 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **thirteen** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Also, we observe that out 16 there are 13 triples, where we change the order of a and b . Below are respective examples:

1. **(399, 40, 401)** $\Rightarrow 401 - 40 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 8379$, $T_{361} := 399^2$,
 $E := \{81, 83, \dots, 799, 801\}$ or $E := \{261, 262, \dots, 620, 621\}$
2. **(437, 84, 445)** $\Rightarrow 445 - 84 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 10051$, $T_{361} := 437^2$,
 $E := \{169, 171, \dots, 887, 889\}$ or $E := \{349, 350, \dots, 708, 709\}$
3. **(475, 132, 493)** $\Rightarrow 493 - 132 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 11875$, $T_{361} := 475^2$,
 $E := \{265, 267, \dots, 983, 985\}$ or $E := \{445, 446, \dots, 804, 805\}$
4. **(513, 184, 545)** $\Rightarrow 545 - 184 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 13851$, $T_{361} := 513^2$,
 $E := \{369, 371, \dots, 1087, 1089\}$ or $E := \{549, 550, \dots, 908, 909\}$
5. **(551, 240, 601)** $\Rightarrow 601 - 240 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 15979$, $T_{361} := 551^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 1199, 1201\}$ or $E := \{661, 662, \dots, 1020, 1021\}$
6. **(589, 300, 661)** $\Rightarrow 661 - 300 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 18259$, $T_{361} := 589^2$,
 $E := \{601, 603, \dots, 1319, 1321\}$ or $E := \{781, 782, \dots, 1140, 1141\}$
7. **(627, 364, 725)** $\Rightarrow 725 - 364 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 20691$, $T_{361} := 627^2$,
 $E := \{729, 731, \dots, 1447, 1449\}$ or $E := \{909, 910, \dots, 1268, 1269\}$
8. **(665, 432, 793)** $\Rightarrow 793 - 432 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 23275$, $T_{361} := 665^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 1583, 1585\}$ or $E := \{1045, 1046, \dots, 1404, 1405\}$
9. **(703, 504, 865)** $\Rightarrow 865 - 504 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 26011$, $T_{361} := 703^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 1727, 1729\}$ or $E := \{1189, 1190, \dots, 1548, 1549\}$
10. **(741, 580, 941)** $\Rightarrow 941 - 580 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 28899$, $T_{361} := 741^2$,
 $E := \{1161, 1163, \dots, 1879, 1881\}$ or $E := \{1341, 1342, \dots, 1700, 1701\}$
11. **(779, 660, 1021)** $\Rightarrow 1021 - 660 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 31939$, $T_{361} := 779^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 2039, 2041\}$ or $E := \{1501, 1502, \dots, 1860, 1861\}$
12. **(817, 744, 1105)** $\Rightarrow 1105 - 744 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 35131$, $T_{361} := 817^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 2207, 2209\}$ or $E := \{1669, 1670, \dots, 2028, 2029\}$
13. **(855, 832, 1193)** $\Rightarrow 1193 - 832 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 38475$, $T_{361} := 855^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 2383, 2385\}$ or $E := \{1845, 1846, \dots, 2204, 2205\}$
14. **(893, 924, 1285)** $\Rightarrow 1285 - 924 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 41971$, $T_{361} := 893^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 2567, 2569\}$ or $E := \{2029, 2030, \dots, 2388, 2389\}$
15. **(931, 1020, 1381)** $\Rightarrow 1381 - 1020 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 45619$, $T_{361} := 931^2$,
 $E := \{2041, 2043, \dots, 2759, 2761\}$ or $E := \{2221, 2222, \dots, 2580, 2581\}$
16. **(969, 1120, 1481)** $\Rightarrow 1481 - 1120 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 49419$, $T_{361} := 969^2$,
 $E := \{2241, 2243, \dots, 2959, 2961\}$ or $E := \{2421, 2422, \dots, 2780, 2781\}$

Result 4.17. *Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:*

(i) *First Triple:*

$$a = 19^2 + 2 \times 19 = 399 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$a = 38 = 2 \times 19 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, a \in \{399, 437, \dots, 931, 969\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - b = 361 = 19^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{361} := a^2, a \in \{399, 437, \dots, 931, 969\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{19 \times 19} := a \times (2k + 19), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 15, 16\}, \text{i.e., } a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{19 \times 19} := \frac{a^2}{19}, a \in \{399, 437, \dots, 931, 969\}.$$

4.18 Magic Squares of Order 20

This subsection brings magic squares of order 20 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$. In order to have uniformity in results, the orders of a and b are changed in the first **fourteen** triples written in **brown**. In these case, $a > b$, while for other cases, $b > a$. Also, we observe that out 15 there are 14 triples, where we change the order of a and b . Below are respective examples:

1. **(440, 42, 442)** $\Rightarrow 442 - 42 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 9680$, $T_{400} := 440^2$,
 $E := \{85, 87, \dots, 881, 883\}$
2. **(480, 88, 488)** $\Rightarrow 488 - 88 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 11520$, $T_{400} := 480^2$,
 $E := \{177, 179, \dots, 973, 975\}$
3. **(520, 138, 538)** $\Rightarrow 538 - 138 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 13520$, $T_{400} := 520^2$,
 $E := \{277, 279, \dots, 1073, 1075\}$
4. **(560, 192, 592)** $\Rightarrow 592 - 192 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 15680$, $T_{400} := 560^2$,
 $E := \{385, 387, \dots, 1181, 1183\}$
5. **(600, 250, 650)** $\Rightarrow 650 - 250 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 18000$, $T_{400} := 600^2$,
 $E := \{501, 503, \dots, 1297, 1299\}$
6. **(640, 312, 712)** $\Rightarrow 712 - 312 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 20480$, $T_{400} := 640^2$,
 $E := \{625, 627, \dots, 1421, 1423\}$
7. **(680, 378, 778)** $\Rightarrow 778 - 378 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 23120$, $T_{400} := 680^2$,
 $E := \{757, 759, \dots, 1553, 1555\}$
8. **(720, 448, 848)** $\Rightarrow 848 - 448 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 25920$, $T_{400} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{897, 899, \dots, 1693, 1695\}$

9. **(760, 522, 922)** $\Rightarrow 922 - 522 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 28880$, $T_{400} := 760^2$,
 $E := \{1045, 1047, \dots, 1841, 1843\}$
10. **(800, 600, 1000)** $\Rightarrow 1000 - 600 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 32000$, $T_{400} := 800^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 1997, 1999\}$
11. **(840, 682, 1082)** $\Rightarrow 1082 - 682 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 35280$, $T_{400} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{1365, 1367, \dots, 2161, 2163\}$
12. **(880, 768, 1168)** $\Rightarrow 1168 - 768 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 38720$, $T_{400} := 880^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 2333, 2335\}$
13. **(920, 858, 1258)** $\Rightarrow 1258 - 858 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 42320$, $T_{400} := 920^2$,
 $E := \{1717, 1719, \dots, 2513, 2515\}$
14. **(960, 952, 1352)** $\Rightarrow 1352 - 952 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 46080$, $T_{400} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 2701, 2703\}$
15. **(1000, 1050, 1450)** $\Rightarrow 1450 - 1050 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 50000$, $T_{400} := 1000^2$,
 $E := \{2101, 2103, \dots, 2897, 2899\}$

Result 4.18. *Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:*

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $a = 20^2 + 2 \times 20 = 440 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $a = 40 = 2 \times 20 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $a \in \{440, 480, \dots, 960, 1000\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and Second Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - b = 400 = 20^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{11} := a^2$, $a \in \{440, 480, \dots, 960, 1000\};$
- (v) *Magic Sums:*
 $S_{20 \times 20} := a \times (2k + 20)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 14, 15\}$, *i.e.*, $a \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.
 Alternatively, $S_{20 \times 20} := \frac{a^2}{20}$, $a \in \{440, 480, \dots, 960, 1000\}$.

4.19 Magic Squares of Order 21

This subsection brings magic squares of order 21 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(44, 483, 485)** $\Rightarrow 485 - 44 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 11109$, $T_{441} := 483^2$,
 $E := \{89, 91, \dots, 967, 969\}$ or $E := \{309, 310, \dots, 748, 749\}$
2. **(92, 525, 533)** $\Rightarrow 533 - 92 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 13125$, $T_{441} := 525^2$,
 $E := \{185, 187, \dots, 1063, 1065\}$ or $E := \{405, 406, \dots, 844, 845\}$

3. **(144, 567, 585)** $\Rightarrow 585 - 144 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 15309$, $T_{441} := 567^2$,
 $E := \{289, 291, \dots, 1167, 1169\}$ or $E := \{509, 510, \dots, 948, 949\}$
4. **(200, 609, 641)** $\Rightarrow 641 - 200 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 17661$, $T_{441} := 609^2$,
 $E := \{401, 403, \dots, 1279, 1281\}$ or $E := \{621, 622, \dots, 1060, 1061\}$
5. **(260, 651, 701)** $\Rightarrow 701 - 260 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 20181$, $T_{441} := 651^2$,
 $E := \{521, 523, \dots, 1399, 1401\}$ or $E := \{741, 742, \dots, 1180, 1181\}$
6. **(324, 693, 765)** $\Rightarrow 765 - 324 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 22869$, $T_{441} := 693^2$,
 $E := \{649, 651, \dots, 1527, 1529\}$ or $E := \{869, 870, \dots, 1308, 1309\}$
7. **(392, 735, 833)** $\Rightarrow 833 - 392 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 25725$, $T_{441} := 735^2$,
 $E := \{785, 787, \dots, 1663, 1665\}$ or $E := \{1005, 1006, \dots, 1444, 1445\}$
8. **(464, 777, 905)** $\Rightarrow 905 - 464 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 28749$, $T_{441} := 777^2$,
 $E := \{929, 931, \dots, 1807, 1809\}$ or $E := \{1149, 1150, \dots, 1588, 1589\}$
9. **(540, 819, 981)** $\Rightarrow 981 - 540 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 31941$, $T_{441} := 819^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 1959, 1961\}$ or $E := \{1301, 1302, \dots, 1740, 1741\}$
10. **(620, 861, 1061)** $\Rightarrow 1061 - 620 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 35301$, $T_{441} := 861^2$,
 $E := \{1241, 1243, \dots, 2119, 2121\}$ or $E := \{1461, 1462, \dots, 1900, 1901\}$
11. **(704, 903, 1145)** $\Rightarrow 1145 - 704 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 38829$, $T_{441} := 903^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 2287, 2289\}$ or $E := \{1629, 1630, \dots, 2068, 2069\}$
12. **(792, 945, 1233)** $\Rightarrow 1233 - 792 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 42525$, $T_{441} := 945^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 2463, 2465\}$ or $E := \{1805, 1806, \dots, 2244, 2245\}$
13. **(884, 987, 1325)** $\Rightarrow 1325 - 884 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 46389$, $T_{441} := 987^2$,
 $E := \{1769, 1771, \dots, 2647, 2649\}$ or $E := \{1989, 1990, \dots, 2428, 2429\}$
14. **(980, 1029, 1421)** $\Rightarrow 1421 - 980 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 50421$, $T_{441} := 1029^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 2839, 2841\}$ or $E := \{2181, 2182, \dots, 2620, 2621\}$

Remark 5. In the magic squares of orders 3 to 20 we worked with mixed triples, i.e., first few are a and the others are with b . This required us to change the order of a and b . From order 21 onwards, the results are based on values of b .

Result 4.19. Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:

- (i) **First Triple:**
 $b = 21^2 + 2 \times 21 = 483 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) **Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:**
 $b = 42 = 2 \times 21 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $b \in \{483, 525, \dots, 987, 1029\};$
- (iii) **Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:**
 $c - a = 441 = 21^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{441} := b^2, a \in \{483, 525, \dots, 987, 1029\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{21 \times 21} := b \times (2k + 21), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 13, 14\}, \text{ i.e., } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{21 \times 21} := \frac{b^2}{21}, b \in \{483, 525, \dots, 987, 1029\}.$$

4.20 Magic Squares of Orders 22-25 : Blocks of 13

• Magic Squares of Order 22

This subsection brings magic squares of order 22 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(46, 528, 530)** $\Rightarrow 530 - 46 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 12672$, $T_{484} := 528^2$,
 $E := \{93, 95, \dots, 1057, 1059\}$
2. **(96, 572, 580)** $\Rightarrow 580 - 96 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 14872$, $T_{484} := 572^2$,
 $E := \{193, 195, \dots, 1157, 1159\}$
3. **(150, 616, 634)** $\Rightarrow 634 - 150 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 17248$, $T_{484} := 616^2$,
 $E := \{301, 303, \dots, 1265, 1267\}$
4. **(208, 660, 692)** $\Rightarrow 692 - 208 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 19800$, $T_{484} := 660^2$,
 $E := \{417, 419, \dots, 1381, 1383\}$
5. **(270, 704, 754)** $\Rightarrow 754 - 270 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 22528$, $T_{484} := 704^2$,
 $E := \{541, 543, \dots, 1505, 1507\}$
6. **(336, 748, 820)** $\Rightarrow 820 - 336 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 25432$, $T_{484} := 748^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 1637, 1639\}$
7. **(406, 792, 890)** $\Rightarrow 890 - 406 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 28512$, $T_{484} := 792^2$,
 $E := \{813, 815, \dots, 1777, 1779\}$
8. **(480, 836, 964)** $\Rightarrow 964 - 480 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 31768$, $T_{484} := 836^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 1925, 1927\}$
9. **(558, 880, 1042)** $\Rightarrow 1042 - 558 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 35200$, $T_{484} := 880^2$,
 $E := \{1117, 1119, \dots, 2081, 2083\}$
10. **(640, 924, 1124)** $\Rightarrow 1124 - 640 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 38808$, $T_{484} := 924^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 2245, 2247\}$
11. **(726, 968, 1210)** $\Rightarrow 1210 - 726 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 42592$, $T_{484} := 968^2$,
 $E := \{1453, 1455, \dots, 2417, 2419\}$

12. **(816, 1012, 1300)** $\Rightarrow 1300 - 816 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 46552$, $T_{484} := 1012^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 2597, 2599\}$
13. **(910, 1056, 1394)** $\Rightarrow 1394 - 910 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 50688$, $T_{484} := 1056^2$,
 $E := \{1821, 1823, \dots, 2785, 2787\}$

Result 4.20. *Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:*

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $b = 22^2 + 2 \times 22 = 528 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $b = 44 = 2 \times 22 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $b \in \{528, 572, \dots, 1012, 1056\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - a = 484 = 22^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{484} := b^2$, $a \in \{528, 572, \dots, 1012, 1056\};$
- (v) *Magic Sums:*
 $S_{22 \times 22} := b \times (2k + 22)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 12, 13\}$, *i.e.*, $b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.
 Alternatively, $S_{22 \times 22} := \frac{b^2}{22}$, $b \in \{528, 572, \dots, 1012, 1056\}$.

• Magic Squares of Order 23

This subsection brings magic squares of order 23 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(48, 575, 577)** $\Rightarrow 577 - 48 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 14375$, $T_{529} := 575^2$,
 $E := \{97, 99, \dots, 1151, 1153\}$ or $E := \{361, 362, \dots, 888, 889\}$
2. **(100, 621, 629)** $\Rightarrow 629 - 100 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 16767$, $T_{529} := 621^2$,
 $E := \{201, 203, \dots, 1255, 1257\}$ or $E := \{465, 466, \dots, 992, 993\}$
3. **(156, 667, 685)** $\Rightarrow 685 - 156 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 19343$, $T_{529} := 667^2$,
 $E := \{313, 315, \dots, 1367, 1369\}$ or $E := \{577, 578, \dots, 1104, 1105\}$
4. **(216, 713, 745)** $\Rightarrow 745 - 216 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 22103$, $T_{529} := 713^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 1487, 1489\}$ or $E := \{697, 698, \dots, 1224, 1225\}$
5. **(280, 759, 809)** $\Rightarrow 809 - 280 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 25047$, $T_{529} := 759^2$,
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 1615, 1617\}$ or $E := \{825, 826, \dots, 1352, 1353\}$
6. **(348, 805, 877)** $\Rightarrow 877 - 348 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 28175$, $T_{529} := 805^2$,
 $E := \{697, 699, \dots, 1751, 1753\}$ or $E := \{961, 962, \dots, 1488, 1489\}$
7. **(420, 851, 949)** $\Rightarrow 949 - 420 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 31487$, $T_{529} := 851^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 1895, 1897\}$ or $E := \{1105, 1106, \dots, 1632, 1633\}$

8. **(496, 897, 1025)** $\Rightarrow 1025 - 496 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 34983$, $T_{529} := 897^2$,
 $E := \{993, 995, \dots, 2047, 2049\}$ or $E := \{1257, 1258, \dots, 1784, 1785\}$
9. **(576, 943, 1105)** $\Rightarrow 1105 - 576 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 38663$, $T_{529} := 943^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 2207, 2209\}$ or $E := \{1417, 1418, \dots, 1944, 1945\}$
10. **(660, 989, 1189)** $\Rightarrow 1189 - 660 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 42527$, $T_{529} := 989^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 2375, 2377\}$ or $E := \{1585, 1586, \dots, 2112, 2113\}$
11. **(748, 1035, 1277)** $\Rightarrow 1277 - 748 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 46575$, $T_{529} := 1035^2$,
 $E := \{1497, 1499, \dots, 2551, 2553\}$ or $E := \{1761, 1762, \dots, 2288, 2289\}$
12. **(840, 1081, 1369)** $\Rightarrow 1369 - 840 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 50807$, $T_{529} := 1081^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 2735, 2737\}$ or $E := \{1945, 1946, \dots, 2472, 2473\}$
13. **(936, 1127, 1465)** $\Rightarrow 1465 - 936 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 55223$, $T_{529} := 1127^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 2927, 2929\}$ or $E := \{2137, 2138, \dots, 2664, 2665\}$

Result 4.21. Based on above triples, we observe the following interesting facts:

- (i) *First Triple:*
 $b = 23^2 + 2 \times 23 = 575 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$
- (ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*
 $b = 46 = 2 \times 23 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $b \in \{575, 621, \dots, 1081, 1127\};$
- (iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*
 $c - a = 529 = 23^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$
- (iv) *Total Entries Sum:*
 $T_{529} := b^2$, $a \in \{575, 621, \dots, 1081, 1127\};$
- (v) *Magic Sums:*
 $S_{23 \times 23} := b \times (2k + 23)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 12, 13\}$, i.e., $b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.
 Alternatively, $S_{23 \times 23} := \frac{b^2}{23}$, $b \in \{575, 621, \dots, 1081, 1127\}$.

• Magic Squares of Order 24

This subsection brings magic squares of order 24 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(50, 624, 626)** $\Rightarrow 626 - 50 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 16224$, $T_{576} := 624^2$,
 $E := \{101, 103, \dots, 1249, 1251\}$
2. **(104, 672, 680)** $\Rightarrow 680 - 104 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 18816$, $T_{576} := 672^2$,
 $E := \{209, 211, \dots, 1357, 1359\}$
3. **(162, 720, 738)** $\Rightarrow 738 - 162 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 21600$, $T_{576} := 720^2$,
 $E := \{325, 327, \dots, 1473, 1475\}$

4. **(224, 768, 800)** $\Rightarrow 800 - 224 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 24576$, $T_{576} := 768^2$,
 $E := \{449, 451, \dots, 1597, 1599\}$
5. **(290, 816, 866)** $\Rightarrow 866 - 290 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 27744$, $T_{576} := 816^2$,
 $E := \{581, 583, \dots, 1729, 1731\}$
6. **(360, 864, 936)** $\Rightarrow 936 - 360 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 31104$, $T_{576} := 864^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 1869, 1871\}$
7. **(434, 912, 1010)** $\Rightarrow 1010 - 434 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 34656$, $T_{576} := 912^2$,
 $E := \{869, 871, \dots, 2017, 2019\}$
8. **(512, 960, 1088)** $\Rightarrow 1088 - 512 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 38400$, $T_{576} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{1025, 1027, \dots, 2173, 2175\}$
9. **(594, 1008, 1170)** $\Rightarrow 1170 - 594 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 42336$, $T_{576} := 1008^2$,
 $E := \{1189, 1191, \dots, 2337, 2339\}$
10. **(680, 1056, 1256)** $\Rightarrow 1256 - 680 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 46464$, $T_{576} := 1056^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 2509, 2511\}$
11. **(770, 1104, 1346)** $\Rightarrow 1346 - 770 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 50784$, $T_{576} := 1104^2$,
 $E := \{1541, 1543, \dots, 2689, 2691\}$
12. **(864, 1152, 1440)** $\Rightarrow 1440 - 864 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 55296$, $T_{576} := 1152^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 2877, 2879\}$
13. **(962, 1200, 1538)** $\Rightarrow 1538 - 962 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 60000$, $T_{576} := 1200^2$,
 $E := \{1925, 1927, \dots, 3073, 3075\}$

Result 4.22. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 24^2 + 2 \times 24 = 26 \times 24 = 624 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 48 = 2 \times 24 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{624, 672, \dots, 1152, 1200\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 576 = 24^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{576} := b^2, a \in \{624, 672, \dots, 1152, 1200\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{24 \times 24} := b \times (2k + 24), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 12, 13\}, \text{i.e., } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{24 \times 24} := \frac{b^2}{24}, b \in \{624, 672, \dots, 1152, 1200\}.$$

• Magic Squares of Order 25

This subsection brings magic squares of order 25 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(52, 675, 677)** $\Rightarrow 677 - 52 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 18225$, $T_{625} := 675^2$,
 $E := \{105, 107, \dots, 1351, 1353\}$ or $E := \{417, 418, \dots, 1040, 1041\}$
2. **(108, 725, 733)** $\Rightarrow 733 - 108 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 21025$, $T_{625} := 725^2$,
 $E := \{217, 219, \dots, 1463, 1465\}$ or $E := \{529, 530, \dots, 1152, 1153\}$
3. **(168, 775, 793)** $\Rightarrow 793 - 168 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 24025$, $T_{625} := 775^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 1583, 1585\}$ or $E := \{649, 650, \dots, 1272, 1273\}$
4. **(232, 825, 857)** $\Rightarrow 857 - 232 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 27225$, $T_{625} := 825^2$,
 $E := \{465, 467, \dots, 1711, 1713\}$ or $E := \{777, 778, \dots, 1400, 1401\}$
5. **(300, 875, 925)** $\Rightarrow 925 - 300 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 30625$, $T_{625} := 875^2$,
 $E := \{601, 603, \dots, 1847, 1849\}$ or $E := \{913, 914, \dots, 1536, 1537\}$
6. **(372, 925, 997)** $\Rightarrow 997 - 372 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 34225$, $T_{625} := 925^2$,
 $E := \{745, 747, \dots, 1991, 1993\}$ or $E := \{1057, 1058, \dots, 1680, 1681\}$
7. **(448, 975, 1073)** $\Rightarrow 1073 - 448 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 38025$, $T_{625} := 975^2$,
 $E := \{897, 899, \dots, 2143, 2145\}$ or $E := \{1209, 1210, \dots, 1832, 1833\}$
8. **(528, 1025, 1153)** $\Rightarrow 1153 - 528 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 42025$, $T_{625} := 1025^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 2303, 2305\}$ or $E := \{1369, 1370, \dots, 1992, 1993\}$
9. **(612, 1075, 1237)** $\Rightarrow 1237 - 612 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 46225$, $T_{625} := 1075^2$,
 $E := \{1225, 1227, \dots, 2471, 2473\}$ or $E := \{1537, 1538, \dots, 2160, 2161\}$
10. **(700, 1125, 1325)** $\Rightarrow 1325 - 700 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 50625$, $T_{625} := 1125^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 2647, 2649\}$ or $E := \{1713, 1714, \dots, 2336, 2337\}$
11. **(792, 1175, 1417)** $\Rightarrow 1417 - 792 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 55225$, $T_{625} := 1175^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 2831, 2833\}$ or $E := \{1897, 1898, \dots, 2520, 2521\}$
12. **(888, 1225, 1513)** $\Rightarrow 1513 - 888 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 60025$, $T_{625} := 1225^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 3023, 3025\}$ or $E := \{2089, 2090, \dots, 2712, 2713\}$
13. **(988, 1275, 1613)** $\Rightarrow 1613 - 988 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 65025$, $T_{625} := 1275^2$,
 $E := \{1977, 1979, \dots, 3223, 3225\}$ or $E := \{2289, 2290, \dots, 2912, 2913\}$

Result 4.23. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 25^2 + 2 \times 25 = 27 \times 25 = 675 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 50 = 2 \times 25 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{675, 725, \dots, 1225, 1275\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 625 = 25^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{625} := b^2, a \in \{675, 725, \dots, 1225, 1275\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{25 \times 25} := b \times (2k + 25), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 12, 13\}, \text{i.e., } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{25 \times 25} := \frac{b^2}{25}, b \in \{675, 725, \dots, 1225, 1275\}.$$

4.21 Magic Squares of Orders 26-29 : Blocks of 12

• Magic Squares of Order 26

This subsection brings magic squares of order 26 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(54, 728, 730)** $\Rightarrow 730 - 54 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 20384$, $T_{676} := 728^2$,
 $E := \{109, 111, \dots, 1457, 1459\}$
2. **(112, 780, 788)** $\Rightarrow 788 - 112 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 23400$, $T_{676} := 780^2$,
 $E := \{225, 227, \dots, 1573, 1575\}$
3. **(174, 832, 850)** $\Rightarrow 850 - 174 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 26624$, $T_{676} := 832^2$,
 $E := \{349, 351, \dots, 1697, 1699\}$
4. **(240, 884, 916)** $\Rightarrow 916 - 240 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 30056$, $T_{676} := 884^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 1829, 1831\}$
5. **(310, 936, 986)** $\Rightarrow 986 - 310 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 33696$, $T_{676} := 936^2$,
 $E := \{621, 623, \dots, 1969, 1971\}$
6. **(384, 988, 1060)** $\Rightarrow 1060 - 384 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 37544$, $T_{676} := 988^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 2117, 2119\}$
7. **(462, 1040, 1138)** $\Rightarrow 1138 - 462 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 41600$, $T_{676} := 1040^2$,
 $E := \{925, 927, \dots, 2273, 2275\}$
8. **(544, 1092, 1220)** $\Rightarrow 1220 - 544 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 45864$, $T_{676} := 1092^2$,
 $E := \{1089, 1091, \dots, 2437, 2439\}$
9. **(630, 1144, 1306)** $\Rightarrow 1306 - 630 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 50336$, $T_{676} := 1144^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 2609, 2611\}$
10. **(720, 1196, 1396)** $\Rightarrow 1396 - 720 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 55016$, $T_{676} := 1196^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 2789, 2791\}$

11. **(814, 1248, 1490)** $\Rightarrow 1490 - 814 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 59904$, $T_{676} := 1248^2$,
 $E := \{1629, 1631, \dots, 2977, 2979\}$
12. **(912, 1300, 1588)** $\Rightarrow 1588 - 912 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 65000$, $T_{676} := 1300^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 3173, 3175\}$

Result 4.24. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 26^2 + 2 \times 26 = 28 \times 26 = 728 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 52 = 2 \times 26 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{728, 780, \dots, 1248, 1300\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 676 = 26^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{676} := b^2, a \in \{728, 780, \dots, 1248, 1300\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{26 \times 26} := b \times (2k + 26), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 11, 12\}, \text{i.e., } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{26 \times 26} := \frac{b^2}{26}, b \in \{728, 780, \dots, 1248, 1300\}.$$

• Magic Squares of Order 27

This subsection brings magic squares of order 27 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(56, 783, 785)** $\Rightarrow 785 - 56 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 22707$, $T_{729} := 783^2$,
 $E := \{113, 115, \dots, 1567, 1569\}$ or $E := \{477, 478, \dots, 1204, 1205\}$
2. **(116, 837, 845)** $\Rightarrow 845 - 116 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 25947$, $T_{729} := 837^2$,
 $E := \{233, 235, \dots, 1687, 1689\}$ or $E := \{597, 598, \dots, 1324, 1325\}$
3. **(180, 891, 909)** $\Rightarrow 909 - 180 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 29403$, $T_{729} := 891^2$,
 $E := \{361, 363, \dots, 1815, 1817\}$ or $E := \{725, 726, \dots, 1452, 1453\}$
4. **(248, 945, 977)** $\Rightarrow 977 - 248 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 33075$, $T_{729} := 945^2$,
 $E := \{497, 499, \dots, 1951, 1953\}$ or $E := \{861, 862, \dots, 1588, 1589\}$
5. **(320, 999, 1049)** $\Rightarrow 1049 - 320 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 36963$, $T_{729} := 999^2$,
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 2095, 2097\}$ or $E := \{1005, 1006, \dots, 1732, 1733\}$
6. **(396, 1053, 1125)** $\Rightarrow 1125 - 396 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 41067$, $T_{729} := 1053^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 2247, 2249\}$ or $E := \{1157, 1158, \dots, 1884, 1885\}$
7. **(476, 1107, 1205)** $\Rightarrow 1205 - 476 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 45387$, $T_{729} := 1107^2$,
 $E := \{953, 955, \dots, 2407, 2409\}$ or $E := \{1317, 1318, \dots, 2044, 2045\}$

8. **(560, 1161, 1289)** $\Rightarrow 1289 - 560 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 49923$, $T_{729} := 1161^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 2575, 2577\}$ or $E := \{1485, 1486, \dots, 2212, 2213\}$
9. **(648, 1215, 1377)** $\Rightarrow 1377 - 648 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 54675$, $T_{729} := 1215^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 2751, 2753\}$ or $E := \{1661, 1662, \dots, 2388, 2389\}$
10. **(740, 1269, 1469)** $\Rightarrow 1469 - 740 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 59643$, $T_{729} := 1269^2$,
 $E := \{1481, 1483, \dots, 2935, 2937\}$ or $E := \{1845, 1846, \dots, 2572, 2573\}$
11. **(836, 1323, 1565)** $\Rightarrow 1565 - 836 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 64827$, $T_{729} := 1323^2$,
 $E := \{1673, 1675, \dots, 3127, 3129\}$ or $E := \{2037, 2038, \dots, 2764, 2765\}$
12. **(936, 1377, 1665)** $\Rightarrow 1665 - 936 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 70227$, $T_{729} := 1377^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 3327, 3329\}$ or $E := \{2237, 2238, \dots, 2964, 2965\}$

Result 4.25. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 27^2 + 2 \times 27 = 29 \times 27 = 783 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 54 = 2 \times 27 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{783, 837, \dots, 1323, 1377\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 729 = 27^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{729} := b^2, a \in \{783, 837, \dots, 1323, 1377\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{27 \times 27} := a \times (2k + 27), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 11, 12\}, \text{i.e., } a \text{ or } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{27 \times 27} := \frac{b^2}{27}, b \in \{783, 837, \dots, 1323, 1377\}.$$

• **Magic Squares of Order 28**

This subsection brings magic squares of order 28 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(58, 840, 842)** $\Rightarrow 842 - 58 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 25200$, $T_{784} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{117, 119, \dots, 1681, 1683\}$
2. **(120, 896, 904)** $\Rightarrow 904 - 120 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 28672$, $T_{784} := 896^2$,
 $E := \{241, 243, \dots, 1805, 1807\}$
3. **(186, 952, 970)** $\Rightarrow 970 - 186 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 32368$, $T_{784} := 952^2$,
 $E := \{373, 375, \dots, 1937, 1939\}$
4. **(256, 1008, 1040)** $\Rightarrow 1040 - 256 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 36288$, $T_{784} := 1008^2$,
 $E := \{513, 515, \dots, 2077, 2079\}$

5. **(330, 1064, 1114)** $\Rightarrow 1114 - 330 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 40432$, $T_{784} := 1064^2$,
 $E := \{661, 663, \dots, 2225, 2227\}$
6. **(408, 1120, 1192)** $\Rightarrow 1192 - 408 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 44800$, $T_{784} := 1120^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 2381, 2383\}$
7. **(490, 1176, 1274)** $\Rightarrow 1274 - 490 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 49392$, $T_{784} := 1176^2$,
 $E := \{981, 983, \dots, 2545, 2547\}$
8. **(576, 1232, 1360)** $\Rightarrow 1360 - 576 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 54208$, $T_{784} := 1232^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 2717, 2719\}$
9. **(666, 1288, 1450)** $\Rightarrow 1450 - 666 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 59248$, $T_{784} := 1288^2$,
 $E := \{1333, 1335, \dots, 2897, 2899\}$
10. **(760, 1344, 1544)** $\Rightarrow 1544 - 760 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 64512$, $T_{784} := 1344^2$,
 $E := \{1521, 1523, \dots, 3085, 3087\}$
11. **(858, 1400, 1642)** $\Rightarrow 1642 - 858 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 70000$, $T_{784} := 1400^2$,
 $E := \{1717, 1719, \dots, 3281, 3283\}$
12. **(960, 1456, 1744)** $\Rightarrow 1744 - 960 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 75712$, $T_{784} := 1456^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 3485, 3487\}$

Result 4.26. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 28^2 + 2 \times 28 = 30 \times 28 = 840 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 56 = 2 \times 28 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{840, 896, \dots, 1400, 1456\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 784 = 28^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{784} := b^2, a \in \{840, 896, \dots, 1400, 1456\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{28 \times 28} := a \times (2k + 28), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 11, 12\}, \text{i.e., } a \text{ or } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{28 \times 28} := \frac{b^2}{28}, b \in \{840, 896, \dots, 1400, 1456\}.$$

• Magic Squares of Order 29

This subsection brings magic squares of order 29 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(60, 899, 901)** $\Rightarrow 901 - 60 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 27869$, $T_{841} := 899^2$,
 $E := \{121, 123, \dots, 1799, 1801\}$ or $E := \{541, 542, \dots, 1380, 1381\}$

2. **(124, 957, 965)** $\Rightarrow 965 - 124 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 31581$, $T_{841} := 957^2$,
 $E := \{249, 251, \dots, 1927, 1929\}$ or $E := \{669, 670, \dots, 1508, 1509\}$
3. **(192, 1015, 1033)** $\Rightarrow 1033 - 192 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 35525$, $T_{841} := 1015^2$,
 $E := \{385, 387, \dots, 2063, 2065\}$ or $E := \{805, 806, \dots, 1644, 1645\}$
4. **(264, 1073, 1105)** $\Rightarrow 1105 - 264 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 39701$, $T_{841} := 1073^2$,
 $E := \{529, 531, \dots, 2207, 2209\}$ or $E := \{949, 950, \dots, 1788, 1789\}$
5. **(340, 1131, 1181)** $\Rightarrow 1181 - 340 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 44109$, $T_{841} := 1131^2$,
 $E := \{681, 683, \dots, 2359, 2361\}$ or $E := \{1101, 1102, \dots, 1940, 1941\}$
6. **(420, 1189, 1261)** $\Rightarrow 1261 - 420 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 48749$, $T_{841} := 1189^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 2519, 2521\}$ or $E := \{1261, 1262, \dots, 2100, 2101\}$
7. **(504, 1247, 1345)** $\Rightarrow 1345 - 504 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 53621$, $T_{841} := 1247^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 2687, 2689\}$ or $E := \{1429, 1430, \dots, 2268, 2269\}$
8. **(592, 1305, 1433)** $\Rightarrow 1433 - 592 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 58725$, $T_{841} := 1305^2$,
 $E := \{1185, 1187, \dots, 2863, 2865\}$ or $E := \{1605, 1606, \dots, 2444, 2445\}$
9. **(684, 1363, 1525)** $\Rightarrow 1525 - 684 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 64061$, $T_{841} := 1363^2$,
 $E := \{1369, 1371, \dots, 3047, 3049\}$ or $E := \{1789, 1790, \dots, 2628, 2629\}$
10. **(780, 1421, 1621)** $\Rightarrow 1621 - 780 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 69629$, $T_{841} := 1421^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 3239, 3241\}$ or $E := \{1981, 1982, \dots, 2820, 2821\}$
11. **(880, 1479, 1721)** $\Rightarrow 1721 - 880 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 75429$, $T_{841} := 1479^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 3439, 3441\}$ or $E := \{2181, 2182, \dots, 3020, 3021\}$
12. **(984, 1537, 1825)** $\Rightarrow 1825 - 984 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 81461$, $T_{841} := 1537^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 3647, 3649\}$ or $E := \{2389, 2390, \dots, 3228, 3229\}$

Result 4.27. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 29^2 + 2 \times 29 = 31 \times 29 = 899 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 58 = 2 \times 29 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{899, 957, \dots, 1479, 1537\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 841 = 29^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{841} := b^2, a \in \{899, 957, \dots, 1479, 1537\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{29 \times 29} := a \times (2k + 29), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 11, 12\}, \text{i.e., } a \text{ or } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{29 \times 29} := \frac{b^2}{29}, b \in \{899, 957, \dots, 1479, 1537\}.$$

4.22 Magic Squares of Orders 30-34 : Blocks of 11

• Magic Squares of Order 30

This subsection brings magic squares of order 30 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(62, 960, 962)** $\Rightarrow 962 - 62 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 30720$, $T_{900} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{125, 127, \dots, 1921, 1923\}$
2. **(128, 1020, 1028)** $\Rightarrow 1028 - 128 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 34680$, $T_{900} := 1020^2$,
 $E := \{257, 259, \dots, 2053, 2055\}$
3. **(198, 1080, 1098)** $\Rightarrow 1098 - 198 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 38880$, $T_{900} := 1080^2$,
 $E := \{397, 399, \dots, 2193, 2195\}$
4. **(272, 1140, 1172)** $\Rightarrow 1172 - 272 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 43320$, $T_{900} := 1140^2$,
 $E := \{545, 547, \dots, 2341, 2343\}$
5. **(350, 1200, 1250)** $\Rightarrow 1250 - 350 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 48000$, $T_{900} := 1200^2$,
 $E := \{701, 703, \dots, 2497, 2499\}$
6. **(432, 1260, 1332)** $\Rightarrow 1332 - 432 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 52920$, $T_{900} := 1260^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 2661, 2663\}$
7. **(518, 1320, 1418)** $\Rightarrow 1418 - 518 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 58080$, $T_{900} := 1320^2$,
 $E := \{1037, 1039, \dots, 2833, 2835\}$
8. **(608, 1380, 1508)** $\Rightarrow 1508 - 608 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 63480$, $T_{900} := 1380^2$,
 $E := \{1217, 1219, \dots, 3013, 3015\}$
9. **(702, 1440, 1602)** $\Rightarrow 1602 - 702 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 69120$, $T_{900} := 1440^2$,
 $E := \{1405, 1407, \dots, 3201, 3203\}$
10. **(800, 1500, 1700)** $\Rightarrow 1700 - 800 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 75000$, $T_{900} := 1500^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 3397, 3399\}$
11. **(902, 1560, 1802)** $\Rightarrow 1802 - 902 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 81120$, $T_{900} := 1560^2$,
 $E := \{1805, 1807, \dots, 3601, 3603\}$

Result 4.28. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 30^2 + 2 \times 30 = 32 \times 30 = 960 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 60 = 2 \times 30 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{960, 1020, \dots, 1500, 1560\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 900 = 30^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{900} := b^2, a \in \{960, 1020, \dots, 1500, 1560\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{30 \times 30} := a \times (2k + 30), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 10, 11\}, \text{ i.e., } a \text{ or } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{30 \times 30} := \frac{b^2}{30}, b \in \{960, 1020, \dots, 1500, 1560\}.$$

• Magic Squares of Order 31

This subsection brings magic squares of order 31 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(64, 1023, 1025)** $\Rightarrow 1025 - 64 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 33759$, $T_{961} := 1023^2$,
 $E := \{129, 131, \dots, 2047, 2049\}$ or $E := \{609, 610, \dots, 1568, 1569\}$
2. **(132, 1085, 1093)** $\Rightarrow 1093 - 132 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 37975$, $T_{961} := 1085^2$,
 $E := \{265, 267, \dots, 2183, 2185\}$ or $E := \{745, 746, \dots, 1704, 1705\}$
3. **(204, 1147, 1165)** $\Rightarrow 1165 - 204 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 42439$, $T_{961} := 1147^2$,
 $E := \{409, 411, \dots, 2327, 2329\}$ or $E := \{889, 890, \dots, 1848, 1849\}$
4. **(280, 1209, 1241)** $\Rightarrow 1241 - 280 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 47151$, $T_{961} := 1209^2$,
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 2479, 2481\}$ or $E := \{1041, 1042, \dots, 2000, 2001\}$
5. **(360, 1271, 1321)** $\Rightarrow 1321 - 360 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 52111$, $T_{961} := 1271^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 2639, 2641\}$ or $E := \{1201, 1202, \dots, 2160, 2161\}$
6. **(444, 1333, 1405)** $\Rightarrow 1405 - 444 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 57319$, $T_{961} := 1333^2$,
 $E := \{889, 891, \dots, 2807, 2809\}$ or $E := \{1369, 1370, \dots, 2328, 2329\}$
7. **(532, 1395, 1493)** $\Rightarrow 1493 - 532 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 62775$, $T_{961} := 1395^2$,
 $E := \{1065, 1067, \dots, 2983, 2985\}$ or $E := \{1545, 1546, \dots, 2504, 2505\}$
8. **(624, 1457, 1585)** $\Rightarrow 1585 - 624 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 68479$, $T_{961} := 1457^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 3167, 3169\}$ or $E := \{1729, 1730, \dots, 2688, 689\}$
9. **(720, 1519, 1681)** $\Rightarrow 1681 - 720 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 74431$, $T_{961} := 1519^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 3359, 3361\}$ or $E := \{1921, 1922, \dots, 2880, 2881\}$
10. **(820, 1581, 1781)** $\Rightarrow 1781 - 820 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 80631$, $T_{961} := 1581^2$,
 $E := \{1641, 1643, \dots, 3559, 3561\}$ or $E := \{2121, 2122, \dots, 3080, 3081\}$
11. **(924, 1643, 1885)** $\Rightarrow 1885 - 924 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 87079$, $T_{961} := 1643^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 3767, 3769\}$ or $E := \{2329, 2330, \dots, 3288, 3289\}$

Result 4.29. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 31^2 + 2 \times 31 = 33 \times 31 = 1023 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 62 = 2 \times 31 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{1023, 1085, \dots, 1581, 1643\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 961 = 31^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{961} := b^2, a \in \{1023, 1085, \dots, 1581, 1643\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{31 \times 31} := a \times (2k + 31), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 10, 11\}, \text{i.e., } a \text{ or } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{31 \times 31} := \frac{b^2}{31}, b \in \{1023, 1085, \dots, 1581, 1643\}.$$

• Magic Squares of Order 32

This subsection brings magic squares of order 32 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(66, 1088, 1090)** $\Rightarrow 1090 - 66 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 36992$, $T_{1024} := 1088^2$,
 $E := \{133, 135, \dots, 2177, 2179\}$
2. **(136, 1152, 1160)** $\Rightarrow 1160 - 136 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 41472$, $T_{1024} := 1152^2$,
 $E := \{273, 275, \dots, 2317, 2319\}$
3. **(210, 1216, 1234)** $\Rightarrow 1234 - 210 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 46208$, $T_{1024} := 1216^2$,
 $E := \{421, 423, \dots, 2465, 2467\}$
4. **(288, 1280, 1312)** $\Rightarrow 1312 - 288 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 51200$, $T_{1024} := 1280^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 2621, 2623\}$
5. **(370, 1344, 1394)** $\Rightarrow 1394 - 370 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 56448$, $T_{1024} := 1344^2$,
 $E := \{741, 743, \dots, 2785, 2787\}$
6. **(456, 1408, 1480)** $\Rightarrow 1480 - 456 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 61952$, $T_{1024} := 1408^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 2957, 2959\}$
7. **(546, 1472, 1570)** $\Rightarrow 1570 - 546 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 67712$, $T_{1024} := 1472^2$,
 $E := \{1093, 1095, \dots, 3137, 3139\}$
8. **(640, 1536, 1664)** $\Rightarrow 1664 - 640 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 73728$, $T_{1024} := 1536^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 3325, 3327\}$
9. **(738, 1600, 1762)** $\Rightarrow 1762 - 738 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 80000$, $T_{1024} := 1600^2$,
 $E := \{1477, 1479, \dots, 3521, 3523\}$
10. **(840, 1664, 1864)** $\Rightarrow 1864 - 840 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 86528$, $T_{1024} := 1664^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 3725, 3727\}$

11. **(946, 1728, 1970)** $\Rightarrow 1970 - 946 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 93312$, $T_{1024} := 1728^2$,
 $E := \{1893, 1895, \dots, 3937, 3939\}$

Result 4.30. (i) *First Triple:*

$b = 32^2 + 2 \times 32 = 34 \times 32 = 1088 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$b = 64 = 2 \times 32 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $b \in \{1088, 1152, \dots, 1664, 1728\};$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$c - a = 1024 = 32^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$T_{1024} := b^2$, $a \in \{1088, 1152, \dots, 1664, 1728\};$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$S_{32 \times 32} := a \times (2k + 32)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 10, 11\}$, i.e., a or $b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.

Alternatively, $S_{32 \times 32} := \frac{b^2}{32}$, $b \in \{1088, 1152, \dots, 1664, 1728\}$.

• Magic Squares of Order 33

This subsection brings magic squares of order 33 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(68, 1155, 1157)** $\Rightarrow 1157 - 68 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 40425$, $T_{1089} := 1155^2$,
 $E := \{137, 139, \dots, 2311, 2313\}$ or $E := \{681, 682, \dots, 1768, 1769\}$
2. **(140, 1221, 1229)** $\Rightarrow 1229 - 140 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 45177$, $T_{1089} := 1221^2$,
 $E := \{281, 283, \dots, 2455, 2457\}$ or $E := \{825, 826, \dots, 1912, 1913\}$
3. **(216, 1287, 1305)** $\Rightarrow 1305 - 216 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 50193$, $T_{1089} := 1287^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 2607, 2609\}$ or $E := \{977, 978, \dots, 2064, 2065\}$
4. **(296, 1353, 1385)** $\Rightarrow 1385 - 296 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 55473$, $T_{1089} := 1353^2$,
 $E := \{593, 595, \dots, 2767, 2769\}$ or $E := \{1137, 1138, \dots, 2224, 2225\}$
5. **(380, 1419, 1469)** $\Rightarrow 1469 - 380 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 61017$, $T_{1089} := 1419^2$,
 $E := \{761, 763, \dots, 2935, 2937\}$ or $E := \{1305, 1306, \dots, 2392, 2393\}$
6. **(468, 1485, 1557)** $\Rightarrow 1557 - 468 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 66825$, $T_{1089} := 1485^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 3111, 3113\}$ or $E := \{1481, 1482, \dots, 2568, 2569\}$
7. **(560, 1551, 1649)** $\Rightarrow 1649 - 560 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 72897$, $T_{1089} := 1551^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 3295, 3297\}$ or $E := \{1665, 1666, \dots, 2752, 2753\}$
8. **(656, 1617, 1745)** $\Rightarrow 1745 - 656 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 79233$, $T_{1089} := 1617^2$,
 $E := \{1313, 1315, \dots, 3487, 3489\}$ or $E := \{1857, 1858, \dots, 2944, 2945\}$

9. **(756, 1683, 1845)** $\Rightarrow 1845 - 756 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 85833$, $T_{1089} := 1683^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 3687, 3689\}$ or $E := \{2057, 2058, \dots, 3144, 3145\}$
10. **(860, 1749, 1949)** $\Rightarrow 1949 - 860 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 92697$, $T_{1089} := 1749^2$,
 $E := \{1721, 1723, \dots, 3895, 3897\}$ or $E := \{2265, 2266, \dots, 3352, 3353\}$
11. **(968, 1815, 2057)** $\Rightarrow 2057 - 968 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 99825$, $T_{1089} := 1815^2$,
 $E := \{1937, 1939, \dots, 4111, 4113\}$ or $E := \{2481, 2482, \dots, 3568, 3569\}$

Result 4.31. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 33^2 + 2 \times 33 = 35 \times 33 = 1155 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 66 = 2 \times 33 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{1155, 1221, \dots, 1749, 1815\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 1089 = 33^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{1089} := b^2, a \in \{1155, 1221, \dots, 1749, 1815\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{33 \times 33} := a \times (2k + 33), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 10, 11\}, \text{i.e., } a \text{ or } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{33 \times 33} := \frac{b^2}{33}, b \in \{1155, 1221, \dots, 1749, 1815\}.$$

• Magic Squares of Order 34

This subsection brings magic squares of order 34 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(70, 1224, 1226)** $\Rightarrow 1226 - 70 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 44064$, $T_{1156} := 1224^2$,
 $E := \{141, 143, \dots, 2449, 2451\}$
2. **(144, 1292, 1300)** $\Rightarrow 1300 - 144 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 49096$, $T_{1156} := 1292^2$,
 $E := \{289, 291, \dots, 2597, 2599\}$
3. **(222, 1360, 1378)** $\Rightarrow 1378 - 222 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 54400$, $T_{1156} := 1360^2$,
 $E := \{445, 447, \dots, 2753, 2755\}$
4. **(304, 1428, 1460)** $\Rightarrow 1460 - 304 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 59976$, $T_{1156} := 1428^2$,
 $E := \{609, 611, \dots, 2917, 2919\}$
5. **(390, 1496, 1546)** $\Rightarrow 1546 - 390 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 65824$, $T_{1156} := 1496^2$,
 $E := \{781, 783, \dots, 3089, 3091\}$
6. **(480, 1564, 1636)** $\Rightarrow 1636 - 480 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 71944$, $T_{1156} := 1564^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 3269, 3271\}$

7. **(574, 1632, 1730)** $\Rightarrow 1730 - 574 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 78336$, $T_{1156} := 1632^2$,
 $E := \{1149, 1151, \dots, 3457, 3459\}$
8. **(672, 1700, 1828)** $\Rightarrow 1828 - 672 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 85000$, $T_{1156} := 1700^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 3653, 3655\}$
9. **(774, 1768, 1930)** $\Rightarrow 1930 - 774 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 91936$, $T_{1156} := 1768^2$,
 $E := \{1549, 1551, \dots, 3857, 3859\}$
10. **(880, 1836, 2036)** $\Rightarrow 2036 - 880 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 99144$, $T_{1156} := 1836^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 4069, 4071\}$
11. **(990, 1904, 2146)** $\Rightarrow 2146 - 990 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 106624$, $T_{1156} := 1904^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 4289, 4291\}$

Result 4.32. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 34^2 + 2 \times 34 = 36 \times 34 = 1224 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 68 = 2 \times 34 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{1224, 1292, \dots, 1836, 1904\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 1156 = 34^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{1156} := b^2, a \in \{1224, 1292, \dots, 1836, 1904\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{34 \times 34} := a \times (2k + 34), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 10, 11\}, \text{i.e., } a \text{ or } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{34 \times 34} := \frac{b^2}{34}, b \in \{1224, 1292, \dots, 1836, 1904\}.$$

4.23 Magic Squares of Orders 35-40 : Blocks of 10

• Magic Squares of Order 35

This subsection brings magic squares of order 35 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(72, 1295, 1297)** $\Rightarrow 1297 - 72 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 47915$, $T_{1225} := 1295^2$,
 $E := \{145, 147, \dots, 2591, 2593\}$ or $E := \{757, 758, \dots, 1980, 1981\}$
2. **(148, 1365, 1373)** $\Rightarrow 1373 - 148 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 53235$, $T_{1225} := 1365^2$,
 $E := \{297, 299, \dots, 2743, 2745\}$ or $E := \{909, 910, \dots, 2132, 2133\}$
3. **(228, 1435, 1453)** $\Rightarrow 1453 - 228 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 58835$, $T_{1225} := 1435^2$,
 $E := \{457, 459, \dots, 2903, 2905\}$ or $E := \{1069, 1070, \dots, 2292, 2293\}$
4. **(312, 1505, 1537)** $\Rightarrow 1537 - 312 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 64715$, $T_{1225} := 1505^2$,
 $E := \{625, 627, \dots, 3071, 3073\}$ or $E := \{1237, 1238, \dots, 2460, 2461\}$

5. **(400, 1575, 1625)** $\Rightarrow 1625 - 400 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 70875$, $T_{1225} := 1575^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 3247, 3249\}$ or $E := \{1413, 1414, \dots, 2636, 2637\}$
6. **(492, 1645, 1717)** $\Rightarrow 1717 - 492 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 77315$, $T_{1225} := 1645^2$,
 $E := \{985, 987, \dots, 3431, 3433\}$ or $E := \{1597, 1598, \dots, 2820, 2821\}$
7. **(588, 1715, 1813)** $\Rightarrow 1813 - 588 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 84035$, $T_{1225} := 1715^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 3623, 3625\}$ or $E := \{1789, 1790, \dots, 3012, 3013\}$
8. **(688, 1785, 1913)** $\Rightarrow 1913 - 688 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 91035$, $T_{1225} := 1785^2$,
 $E := \{1377, 1379, \dots, 3823, 3825\}$ or $E := \{1989, 1990, \dots, 3212, 3213\}$
9. **(792, 1855, 2017)** $\Rightarrow 2017 - 792 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 98315$, $T_{1225} := 1855^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 4031, 4033\}$ or $E := \{2197, 2198, \dots, 3420, 3421\}$
10. **(900, 1925, 2125)** $\Rightarrow 2125 - 900 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 105875$, $T_{1225} := 1925^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 4247, 4249\}$ or $E := \{2413, 2414, \dots, 3636, 3637\}$

Result 4.33. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 35^2 + 2 \times 35 = 37 \times 35 = 1295 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 70 = 2 \times 35 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{1295, 1365, \dots, 1855, 1925\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 1225 = 35^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{1225} := b^2, a \in \{1295, 1365, \dots, 1855, 1925\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{35 \times 35} := a \times (2k + 35), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 9, 10\}, \text{i.e., } a \text{ or } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{35 \times 35} := \frac{b^2}{35}, b \in \{1295, 1365, \dots, 1855, 1925\}.$$

• Magic Squares of Order 36

This subsection brings magic squares of order 36 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(74, 1368, 1370)** $\Rightarrow 1370 - 74 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 51984$, $T_{1296} := 1368^2$,
 $E := \{149, 151, \dots, 2737, 2739\}$
2. **(152, 1440, 1448)** $\Rightarrow 1448 - 152 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 57600$, $T_{1296} := 1440^2$,
 $E := \{305, 307, \dots, 2893, 2895\}$
3. **(234, 1512, 1530)** $\Rightarrow 1530 - 234 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 63504$, $T_{1296} := 1512^2$,
 $E := \{469, 471, \dots, 3057, 3059\}$

4. **(320, 1584, 1616)** $\Rightarrow 1616 - 320 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 69696$, $T_{1296} := 1584^2$,
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 3229, 3231\}$
5. **(410, 1656, 1706)** $\Rightarrow 1706 - 410 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 76176$, $T_{1296} := 1656^2$,
 $E := \{821, 823, \dots, 3409, 3411\}$
6. **(504, 1728, 1800)** $\Rightarrow 1800 - 504 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 82944$, $T_{1296} := 1728^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 3597, 3599\}$
7. **(602, 1800, 1898)** $\Rightarrow 1898 - 602 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 90000$, $T_{1296} := 1800^2$,
 $E := \{1205, 1207, \dots, 3793, 3795\}$
8. **(704, 1872, 2000)** $\Rightarrow 2000 - 704 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 97344$, $T_{1296} := 1872^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 3997, 3999\}$
9. **(810, 1944, 2106)** $\Rightarrow 2106 - 810 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 104976$, $T_{1296} := 1944^2$,
 $E := \{1621, 1623, \dots, 4209, 4211\}$
10. **(920, 2016, 2216)** $\Rightarrow 2216 - 920 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 112896$, $T_{1296} := 2016^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 4429, 4431\}$

Result 4.34. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 36^2 + 2 \times 36 = 38 \times 36 = 1368 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 72 = 2 \times 36 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{1368, 1440, \dots, 1944, 2016\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 1296 = 36^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{1296} := b^2, a \in \{1368, 1440, \dots, 1944, 2016\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{36 \times 36} := a \times (2k + 36), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 9, 10\}, \text{i.e., } a \text{ or } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{36 \times 36} := \frac{b^2}{36}, b \in \{1368, 1440, \dots, 1944, 2016\}.$$

• **Magic Squares of Order 37**

This subsection brings magic squares of order 37 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(76, 1443, 1445)** $\Rightarrow 1445 - 76 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 56277$, $T_{1369} := 1443^2$,
 $E := \{153, 155, \dots, 2887, 2889\}$ or $E := \{837, 838, \dots, 2204, 2205\}$
2. **(156, 1517, 1525)** $\Rightarrow 1525 - 156 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 62197$, $T_{1369} := 1517^2$,
 $E := \{313, 315, \dots, 3047, 3049\}$ or $E := \{997, 998, \dots, 2364, 2365\}$

3. **(240, 1591, 1609)** $\Rightarrow 1609 - 240 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 68413$, $T_{1369} := 1591^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 3215, 3217\}$ or $E := \{1165, 1166, \dots, 2532, 2533\}$
4. **(328, 1665, 1697)** $\Rightarrow 1697 - 328 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 74925$, $T_{1369} := 1665^2$,
 $E := \{657, 659, \dots, 3391, 3393\}$ or $E := \{1341, 1342, \dots, 2708, 2709\}$
5. **(420, 1739, 1789)** $\Rightarrow 1789 - 420 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 81733$, $T_{1369} := 1739^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 3575, 3577\}$ or $E := \{1525, 1526, \dots, 2892, 2893\}$
6. **(516, 1813, 1885)** $\Rightarrow 1885 - 516 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 88837$, $T_{1369} := 1813^2$,
 $E := \{1033, 1035, \dots, 3767, 3769\}$ or $E := \{1717, 1718, \dots, 3084, 3085\}$
7. **(616, 1887, 1985)** $\Rightarrow 1985 - 616 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 96237$, $T_{1369} := 1887^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 3967, 3969\}$ or $E := \{1917, 1918, \dots, 3284, 3285\}$
8. **(720, 1961, 2089)** $\Rightarrow 2089 - 720 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 103933$, $T_{1369} := 1961^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 4175, 4177\}$ or $E := \{2125, 2126, \dots, 3492, 3493\}$
9. **(828, 2035, 2197)** $\Rightarrow 2197 - 828 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 111925$, $T_{1369} := 2035^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 4391, 4393\}$ or $E := \{2341, 2342, \dots, 3708, 3709\}$
10. **(940, 2109, 2309)** $\Rightarrow 2309 - 940 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 120213$, $T_{1369} := 2109^2$,
 $E := \{1881, 1883, \dots, 4615, 4617\}$ or $E := \{2565, 2566, \dots, 3932, 3933\}$

Result 4.35. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 37^2 + 2 \times 37 = 39 \times 37 = 1443 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 74 = 2 \times 37 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{1443, 1517, \dots, 20354, 2109\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 1369 = 37^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{1369} := b^2, a \in \{1443, 1517, \dots, 20354, 2109\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{37 \times 37} := a \times (2k + 37), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 9, 10\}, \text{i.e., } a \text{ or } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{37 \times 37} := \frac{b^2}{37}, b \in \{1443, 1517, \dots, 20354, 2109\}.$$

• Magic Squares of Order 38

This subsection brings magic squares of order 38 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(78, 1520, 1522)** $\Rightarrow 1522 - 78 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 60800$, $T_{1444} := 1520^2$,
 $E := \{157, 159, \dots, 3041, 3043\}$

2. **(160, 1596, 1604)** $\Rightarrow 1604 - 160 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 67032$, $T_{1444} := 1596^2$,
 $E := \{321, 323, \dots, 3205, 3207\}$
3. **(246, 1672, 1690)** $\Rightarrow 1690 - 246 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 73568$, $T_{1444} := 1672^2$,
 $E := \{493, 495, \dots, 3377, 3379\}$
4. **(336, 1748, 1780)** $\Rightarrow 1780 - 336 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 80408$, $T_{1444} := 1748^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 3557, 3559\}$
5. **(430, 1824, 1874)** $\Rightarrow 1874 - 430 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 87552$, $T_{1444} := 1824^2$,
 $E := \{861, 863, \dots, 3745, 3747\}$
6. **(528, 1900, 1972)** $\Rightarrow 1972 - 528 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 95000$, $T_{1444} := 1900^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 3941, 3943\}$
7. **(630, 1976, 2074)** $\Rightarrow 2074 - 630 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 102752$, $T_{1444} := 1976^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 4145, 4147\}$
8. **(736, 2052, 2180)** $\Rightarrow 2180 - 736 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 110808$, $T_{1444} := 2052^2$,
 $E := \{1473, 1475, \dots, 4357, 4359\}$
9. **(846, 2128, 2290)** $\Rightarrow 2290 - 846 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 119168$, $T_{1444} := 2128^2$,
 $E := \{1693, 1695, \dots, 4577, 4579\}$
10. **(960, 2204, 2404)** $\Rightarrow 2404 - 960 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 127832$, $T_{1444} := 2204^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 4805, 4807\}$

Result 4.36. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 38^2 + 2 \times 38 = 40 \times 38 = 1520 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 76 = 2 \times 38 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{1520, 1596, \dots, 2128, 2204\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 1444 = 38^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{1444} := b^2, a \in \{1520, 1596, \dots, 2128, 2204\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{38 \times 38} := a \times (2k + 38), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 9, 10\}, \text{i.e., } a \text{ or } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{38 \times 38} := \frac{b^2}{38}, b \in \{1520, 1596, \dots, 2128, 2204\}.$$

• Magic Squares of Order 39

This subsection brings magic squares of order 39 generated by Pythagorean triples , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(80, 1599, 1601)** $\Rightarrow 1601 - 80 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 65559$, $T_{1521} := 1599^2$,
 $E := \{161, 163, \dots, 3199, 3201\}$ or $E := \{921, 922, \dots, 2440, 2441\}$

2. **(164, 1677, 1685)** $\Rightarrow 1685 - 164 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 72111$, $T_{1521} := 1677^2$,
 $E := \{329, 331, \dots, 3367, 3369\}$ or $E := \{1089, 1090, \dots, 2608, 2609\}$
3. **(252, 1755, 1773)** $\Rightarrow 1773 - 252 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 78975$, $T_{1521} := 1755^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 3543, 3545\}$ or $E := \{1265, 1266, \dots, 2784, 2785\}$
4. **(344, 1833, 1865)** $\Rightarrow 1865 - 344 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 86151$, $T_{1521} := 1833^2$,
 $E := \{689, 691, \dots, 3727, 3729\}$ or $E := \{1449, 1450, \dots, 2968, 2969\}$
5. **(440, 1911, 1961)** $\Rightarrow 1961 - 440 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 93639$, $T_{1521} := 1911^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 3919, 3921\}$ or $E := \{1641, 1642, \dots, 3160, 3161\}$
6. **(540, 1989, 2061)** $\Rightarrow 2061 - 540 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 101439$, $T_{1521} := 1989^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 4119, 4121\}$ or $E := \{1841, 1842, \dots, 3360, 3361\}$
7. **(644, 2067, 2165)** $\Rightarrow 2165 - 644 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 109551$, $T_{1521} := 2067^2$,
 $E := \{1289, 1291, \dots, 4327, 4329\}$ or $E := \{2049, 2050, \dots, 3568, 3569\}$
8. **(752, 2145, 2273)** $\Rightarrow 2273 - 752 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 117975$, $T_{1521} := 2145^2$,
 $E := \{1505, 1507, \dots, 4543, 4545\}$ or $E := \{2265, 2266, \dots, 3784, 3785\}$
9. **(864, 2223, 2385)** $\Rightarrow 2385 - 864 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 126711$, $T_{1521} := 2223^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 4767, 4769\}$ or $E := \{2489, 2490, \dots, 4008, 4009\}$
10. **(980, 2301, 2501)** $\Rightarrow 2501 - 980 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 135759$, $T_{1521} := 2301^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 4999, 5001\}$ or $E := \{2721, 2722, \dots, 4240, 4241\}$

Result 4.37. (i) *First Triple:*

$b = 39^2 + 2 \times 39 = 41 \times 39 = 1599 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$b = 78 = 2 \times 39 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}$, $b \in \{1599, 1601, \dots, 2223, 2301\};$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$c - a = 1521 = 39^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$T_{1521} := b^2$, $a \in \{1599, 1601, \dots, 2223, 2301\};$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$S_{39 \times 39} := a \times (2k + 39)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 9, 10\}$, i.e., a or $b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square})$.

Alternatively, $S_{39 \times 39} := \frac{b^2}{39}$, $b \in \{1599, 1601, \dots, 2223, 2301\}$.

• **Magic Squares of Order 40**

This subsection brings magic squares of order 40 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(82, 1680, 1682)** $\Rightarrow 1682 - 82 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 70560$, $T_{1600} := 1680^2$,
 $E := \{165, 167, \dots, 3361, 3363\}$
2. **(168, 1760, 1768)** $\Rightarrow 1768 - 168 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 77440$, $T_{1600} := 1760^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 3533, 3535\}$
3. **(258, 1840, 1858)** $\Rightarrow 1858 - 258 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 84640$, $T_{1600} := 1840^2$,
 $E := \{517, 519, \dots, 3713, 3715\}$
4. **(352, 1920, 1952)** $\Rightarrow 1952 - 352 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 92160$, $T_{1600} := 1920^2$,
 $E := \{705, 707, \dots, 3901, 3903\}$
5. **(450, 2000, 2050)** $\Rightarrow 2050 - 450 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 100000$, $T_{1600} := 2000^2$,
 $E := \{901, 903, \dots, 4097, 4099\}$
6. **(552, 2080, 2152)** $\Rightarrow 2152 - 552 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 108160$, $T_{1600} := 2080^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 4301, 4303\}$
7. **(658, 2160, 2258)** $\Rightarrow 2258 - 658 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 116640$, $T_{1600} := 2160^2$,
 $E := \{1317, 1319, \dots, 4513, 4515\}$
8. **(768, 2240, 2368)** $\Rightarrow 2368 - 768 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 125440$, $T_{1600} := 2240^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 4733, 4735\}$
9. **(882, 2320, 2482)** $\Rightarrow 2482 - 882 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 134560$, $T_{1600} := 2320^2$,
 $E := \{1765, 1767, \dots, 4961, 4963\}$
10. **(1000, 2400, 2600)** $\Rightarrow 2600 - 1000 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 144000$, $T_{1600} := 2400^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 5197, 5199\}$

Result 4.38. (i) *First Triple:*

$$b = 40^2 + 2 \times 40 = 42 \times 40 = 1680 := \text{square of order of magic square} + 2 \times \text{order of magic square};$$

(ii) *Gap Among Two Consecutive Triples:*

$$b = 80 = 2 \times 40 = 2 \times \text{order of magic square}, b \in \{1680, 1760, \dots, 2320, 2400\};$$

(iii) *Difference Among Third and First Terms of a Triple:*

$$c - a = 1600 = 40^2 := \text{square of order of magic square};$$

(iv) *Total Entries Sum:*

$$T_{1600} := b^2, a \in \{1680, 1760, \dots, 2320, 2400\};$$

(v) *Magic Sums:*

$$S_{40 \times 40} := a \times (2k + 40), k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 9, 10\}, \text{i.e., } a \text{ or } b \times (2k + \text{Order of Magic Square}).$$

$$\text{Alternatively, } S_{40 \times 40} := \frac{b^2}{40}, b \in \{1680, 1760, \dots, 2320, 2400\}.$$

4.24 Magic Squares of Orders 41-46: Blocks of 9

• Magic Squares of Order 41

This subsection brings magic squares of order 41 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(84, 1763, 1765)** $\Rightarrow 1765 - 84 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 75809$, $T_{1681} := 1763^2$,
 $E := \{169, 171, \dots, 3527, 3529\}$ or $E := \{1009, 1010, \dots, 2688, 2689\}$
2. **(172, 1845, 1853)** $\Rightarrow 1853 - 172 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 83025$, $T_{1681} := 1845^2$,
 $E := \{345, 347, \dots, 3703, 3705\}$ or $E := \{1185, 1186, \dots, 2864, 2865\}$
3. **(264, 1927, 1945)** $\Rightarrow 1945 - 264 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 90569$, $T_{1681} := 1927^2$,
 $E := \{529, 531, \dots, 3887, 3889\}$ or $E := \{1369, 1370, \dots, 3048, 3049\}$
4. **(360, 2009, 2041)** $\Rightarrow 2041 - 360 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 98441$, $T_{1681} := 2009^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 4079, 4081\}$ or $E := \{1561, 1562, \dots, 3240, 3241\}$
5. **(460, 2091, 2141)** $\Rightarrow 2141 - 460 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 106641$, $T_{1681} := 2091^2$,
 $E := \{921, 923, \dots, 4279, 4281\}$ or $E := \{1761, 1762, \dots, 3440, 3441\}$
6. **(564, 2173, 2245)** $\Rightarrow 2245 - 564 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 115169$, $T_{1681} := 2173^2$,
 $E := \{1129, 1131, \dots, 4487, 4489\}$ or $E := \{1969, 1970, \dots, 3648, 3649\}$
7. **(672, 2255, 2353)** $\Rightarrow 2353 - 672 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 124025$, $T_{1681} := 2255^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 4703, 4705\}$ or $E := \{2185, 2186, \dots, 3864, 3865\}$
8. **(784, 2337, 2465)** $\Rightarrow 2465 - 784 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 133209$, $T_{1681} := 2337^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 4927, 4929\}$ or $E := \{2409, 2410, \dots, 4088, 4089\}$
9. **(900, 2419, 2581)** $\Rightarrow 2581 - 900 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 142721$, $T_{1681} := 2419^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 5159, 5161\}$ or $E := \{2641, 2642, \dots, 4320, 4321\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 42

This subsection brings magic squares of order 42 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(86, 1848, 1850)** $\Rightarrow 1850 - 86 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 81312$, $T_{1764} := 1848^2$,
 $E := \{173, 175, \dots, 3697, 3699\}$
2. **(176, 1932, 1940)** $\Rightarrow 1940 - 176 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 88872$, $T_{1764} := 1932^2$,
 $E := \{353, 355, \dots, 3877, 3879\}$
3. **(270, 2016, 2034)** $\Rightarrow 2034 - 270 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 96768$, $T_{1764} := 2016^2$,
 $E := \{541, 543, \dots, 4065, 4067\}$

4. **(368, 2100, 2132)** $\Rightarrow 2132 - 368 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 105000$, $T_{1764} := 2100^2$,
 $E := \{737, 739, \dots, 4261, 4263\}$
5. **(470, 2184, 2234)** $\Rightarrow 2234 - 470 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 113568$, $T_{1764} := 2184^2$,
 $E := \{941, 943, \dots, 4465, 4467\}$
6. **(576, 2268, 2340)** $\Rightarrow 2340 - 576 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 122472$, $T_{1764} := 2268^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 4677, 4679\}$
7. **(686, 2352, 2450)** $\Rightarrow 2450 - 686 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 131712$, $T_{1764} := 2352^2$,
 $E := \{1373, 1375, \dots, 4897, 4899\}$
8. **(800, 2436, 2564)** $\Rightarrow 2564 - 800 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 141288$, $T_{1764} := 2436^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 5125, 5127\}$
9. **(918, 2520, 2682)** $\Rightarrow 2682 - 918 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 151200$, $T_{1764} := 2520^2$,
 $E := \{1837, 1839, \dots, 5361, 5363\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 43

This subsection brings magic squares of order 43 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(88, 1935, 1937)** $\Rightarrow 1937 - 88 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 87075$, $T_{1849} := 1935^2$,
 $E := \{177, 179, \dots, 3871, 3873\}$ or $E := \{1101, 1102, \dots, 2948, 2949\}$
2. **(180, 2021, 2029)** $\Rightarrow 2029 - 180 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 94987$, $T_{1849} := 2021^2$,
 $E := \{361, 363, \dots, 4055, 4057\}$ or $E := \{1285, 1286, \dots, 3132, 3133\}$
3. **(276, 2107, 2125)** $\Rightarrow 2125 - 276 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 103243$, $T_{1849} := 2107^2$,
 $E := \{553, 555, \dots, 4247, 4249\}$ or $E := \{1477, 1478, \dots, 3324, 3325\}$
4. **(376, 2193, 2225)** $\Rightarrow 2225 - 376 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 111843$, $T_{1849} := 2193^2$,
 $E := \{753, 755, \dots, 4447, 4449\}$ or $E := \{1677, 1678, \dots, 3524, 3525\}$
5. **(480, 2279, 2329)** $\Rightarrow 2329 - 480 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 120787$, $T_{1849} := 2279^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 4655, 4657\}$ or $E := \{1885, 1886, \dots, 3732, 3733\}$
6. **(588, 2365, 2437)** $\Rightarrow 2437 - 588 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 130075$, $T_{1849} := 2365^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 4871, 4873\}$ or $E := \{2101, 2102, \dots, 3948, 3949\}$
7. **(700, 2451, 2549)** $\Rightarrow 2549 - 700 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 139707$, $T_{1849} := 2451^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 5095, 5097\}$ or $E := \{2325, 2326, \dots, 4172, 4173\}$
8. **(816, 2537, 2665)** $\Rightarrow 2665 - 816 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 149683$, $T_{1849} := 2537^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 5327, 5329\}$ or $E := \{2557, 2558, \dots, 4404, 4405\}$
9. **(936, 2623, 2785)** $\Rightarrow 2785 - 936 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 160003$, $T_{1849} := 2623^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 5567, 5569\}$ or $E := \{2797, 2798, \dots, 4644, 4645\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 44

This subsection brings magic squares of order 44 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(90, 2024, 2026)** $\Rightarrow 2026 - 90 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 93104$, $T_{1936} := 2024^2$,
 $E := \{181, 183, \dots, 4049, 4051\}$
2. **(184, 2112, 2120)** $\Rightarrow 2120 - 184 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 101376$, $T_{1936} := 2112^2$,
 $E := \{369, 371, \dots, 4237, 4239\}$
3. **(282, 2200, 2218)** $\Rightarrow 2218 - 282 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 110000$, $T_{1936} := 2200^2$,
 $E := \{565, 567, \dots, 4433, 4435\}$
4. **(384, 2288, 2320)** $\Rightarrow 2320 - 384 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 118976$, $T_{1936} := 2288^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 4637, 4639\}$
5. **(490, 2376, 2426)** $\Rightarrow 2426 - 490 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 128304$, $T_{1936} := 2376^2$,
 $E := \{981, 983, \dots, 4849, 4851\}$
6. **(600, 2464, 2536)** $\Rightarrow 2536 - 600 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 137984$, $T_{1936} := 2464^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 5069, 5071\}$
7. **(714, 2552, 2650)** $\Rightarrow 2650 - 714 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 148016$, $T_{1936} := 2552^2$,
 $E := \{1429, 1431, \dots, 5297, 5299\}$
8. **(832, 2640, 2768)** $\Rightarrow 2768 - 832 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 158400$, $T_{1936} := 2640^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 5533, 5535\}$
9. **(954, 2728, 2890)** $\Rightarrow 2890 - 954 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 169136$, $T_{1936} := 2728^2$,
 $E := \{1909, 1911, \dots, 5777, 5779\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 45

This subsection brings magic squares of order 45 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(92, 2115, 2117)** $\Rightarrow 2117 - 92 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 99405$, $T_{2025} := 2115^2$,
 $E := \{185, 187, \dots, 4231, 4233\}$ or $E := \{1197, 1198, \dots, 3220, 3221\}$
2. **(188, 2205, 2213)** $\Rightarrow 2213 - 188 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 108045$, $T_{2025} := 2205^2$,
 $E := \{377, 379, \dots, 4423, 4425\}$ or $E := \{1389, 1390, \dots, 3412, 3413\}$
3. **(288, 2295, 2313)** $\Rightarrow 2313 - 288 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 117045$, $T_{2025} := 2295^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 4623, 4625\}$ or $E := \{1589, 1590, \dots, 3612, 3613\}$
4. **(392, 2385, 2417)** $\Rightarrow 2417 - 392 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 126405$, $T_{2025} := 2385^2$,
 $E := \{785, 787, \dots, 4831, 4833\}$ or $E := \{1797, 1798, \dots, 3820, 3821\}$

5. **(500, 2475, 2525)** $\Rightarrow 2525 - 500 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 136125$, $T_{2025} := 2475^2$,
 $E := \{1001, 1003, \dots, 5047, 5049\}$ or $E := \{2013, 2014, \dots, 4036, 4037\}$
6. **(612, 2565, 2637)** $\Rightarrow 2637 - 612 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 146205$, $T_{2025} := 2565^2$,
 $E := \{1225, 1227, \dots, 5271, 5273\}$ or $E := \{2237, 2238, \dots, 4260, 4261\}$
7. **(728, 2655, 2753)** $\Rightarrow 2753 - 728 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 156645$, $T_{2025} := 2655^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 5503, 5505\}$ or $E := \{2469, 2470, \dots, 4492, 4493\}$
8. **(848, 2745, 2873)** $\Rightarrow 2873 - 848 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 167445$, $T_{2025} := 2745^2$,
 $E := \{1697, 1699, \dots, 5743, 5745\}$ or $E := \{2709, 2710, \dots, 4732, 4733\}$
9. **(972, 2835, 2997)** $\Rightarrow 2997 - 972 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 178605$, $T_{2025} := 2835^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 5991, 5993\}$ or $E := \{2957, 2958, \dots, 4980, 4981\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 46

This subsection brings magic squares of order 46 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(94, 2208, 2210)** $\Rightarrow 2210 - 94 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 105984$, $T_{2116} := 2208^2$,
 $E := \{189, 191, \dots, 4417, 4419\}$
2. **(192, 2300, 2308)** $\Rightarrow 2308 - 192 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 115000$, $T_{2116} := 2300^2$,
 $E := \{385, 387, \dots, 4613, 4615\}$
3. **(294, 2392, 2410)** $\Rightarrow 2410 - 294 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 124384$, $T_{2116} := 2392^2$,
 $E := \{589, 591, \dots, 4817, 4819\}$
4. **(400, 2484, 2516)** $\Rightarrow 2516 - 400 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 134136$, $T_{2116} := 2484^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 5029, 5031\}$
5. **(510, 2576, 2626)** $\Rightarrow 2626 - 510 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 144256$, $T_{2116} := 2576^2$,
 $E := \{1021, 1023, \dots, 5249, 5251\}$
6. **(624, 2668, 2740)** $\Rightarrow 2740 - 624 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 154744$, $T_{2116} := 2668^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 5477, 5479\}$
7. **(742, 2760, 2858)** $\Rightarrow 2858 - 742 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 165600$, $T_{2116} := 2760^2$,
 $E := \{1485, 1487, \dots, 5713, 5715\}$
8. **(864, 2852, 2980)** $\Rightarrow 2980 - 864 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 176824$, $T_{2116} := 2852^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 5957, 5959\}$
9. **(990, 2944, 3106)** $\Rightarrow 3106 - 990 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 188416$, $T_{2116} := 2944^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 6209, 6211\}$

4.25 Magic Squares of Orders 47-54: Blocks of 8

• Magic Squares of Order 47

This subsection brings magic squares of order 47 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(96, 2303, 2305)** $\Rightarrow 2305 - 96 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 112847$, $T_{2209} := 2303^2$,
 $E := \{193, 195, \dots, 4607, 4609\}$ or $E := \{1297, 1298, \dots, 3504, 3505\}$
2. **(196, 2397, 2405)** $\Rightarrow 2405 - 196 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 122247$, $T_{2209} := 2397^2$,
 $E := \{393, 395, \dots, 4807, 4809\}$ or $E := \{1497, 1498, \dots, 3704, 3705\}$
3. **(300, 2491, 2509)** $\Rightarrow 2509 - 300 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 132023$, $T_{2209} := 2491^2$,
 $E := \{601, 603, \dots, 5015, 5017\}$ or $E := \{1705, 1706, \dots, 3912, 3913\}$
4. **(408, 2585, 2617)** $\Rightarrow 2617 - 408 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 142175$, $T_{2209} := 2585^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 5231, 5233\}$ or $E := \{1921, 1922, \dots, 4128, 4129\}$
5. **(520, 2679, 2729)** $\Rightarrow 2729 - 520 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 152703$, $T_{2209} := 2679^2$,
 $E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 5455, 5457\}$ or $E := \{2145, 2146, \dots, 4352, 4353\}$
6. **(636, 2773, 2845)** $\Rightarrow 2845 - 636 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 163607$, $T_{2209} := 2773^2$,
 $E := \{1273, 1275, \dots, 5687, 5689\}$ or $E := \{2377, 2378, \dots, 4584, 4585\}$
7. **(756, 2867, 2965)** $\Rightarrow 2965 - 756 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 174887$, $T_{2209} := 2867^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 5927, 5929\}$ or $E := \{2617, 2618, \dots, 4824, 4825\}$
8. **(880, 2961, 3089)** $\Rightarrow 3089 - 880 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 186543$, $T_{2209} := 2961^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 6175, 6177\}$ or $E := \{2865, 2866, \dots, 5072, 5073\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 48

This subsection brings magic squares of order 48 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(98, 2400, 2402)** $\Rightarrow 2402 - 98 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 120000$, $T_{2304} := 2400^2$,
 $E := \{197, 199, \dots, 4801, 4803\}$
2. **(200, 2496, 2504)** $\Rightarrow 2504 - 200 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 129792$, $T_{2304} := 2496^2$,
 $E := \{401, 403, \dots, 5005, 5007\}$
3. **(306, 2592, 2610)** $\Rightarrow 2610 - 306 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 139968$, $T_{2304} := 2592^2$,
 $E := \{613, 615, \dots, 5217, 5219\}$
4. **(416, 2688, 2720)** $\Rightarrow 2720 - 416 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 150528$, $T_{2304} := 2688^2$,
 $E := \{833, 835, \dots, 5437, 5439\}$

5. **(530, 2784, 2834)** $\Rightarrow 2834 - 530 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 161472$, $T_{2304} := 2784^2$,
 $E := \{1061, 1063, \dots, 5665, 5667\}$
6. **(648, 2880, 2952)** $\Rightarrow 2952 - 648 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 172800$, $T_{2304} := 2880^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 5901, 5903\}$
7. **(770, 2976, 3074)** $\Rightarrow 3074 - 770 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 184512$, $T_{2304} := 2976^2$,
 $E := \{1541, 1543, \dots, 6145, 6147\}$
8. **(896, 3072, 3200)** $\Rightarrow 3200 - 896 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 196608$, $T_{2304} := 3072^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 6397, 6399\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 49

This subsection brings magic squares of order 49 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(100, 2499, 2501)** $\Rightarrow 2501 - 100 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 127449$, $T_{2401} := 2499^2$,
 $E := \{201, 203, \dots, 4999, 5001\}$ or $E := \{1401, 1402, \dots, 3800, 3801\}$
2. **(204, 2597, 2605)** $\Rightarrow 2605 - 204 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 137641$, $T_{2401} := 2597^2$,
 $E := \{409, 411, \dots, 5207, 5209\}$ or $E := \{1609, 1610, \dots, 4008, 4009\}$
3. **(312, 2695, 2713)** $\Rightarrow 2713 - 312 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 148225$, $T_{2401} := 2695^2$,
 $E := \{625, 627, \dots, 5423, 5425\}$ or $E := \{1825, 1826, \dots, 4224, 4225\}$
4. **(424, 2793, 2825)** $\Rightarrow 2825 - 424 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 159201$, $T_{2401} := 2793^2$,
 $E := \{849, 851, \dots, 5647, 5649\}$ or $E := \{2049, 2050, \dots, 4448, 4449\}$
5. **(540, 2891, 2941)** $\Rightarrow 2941 - 540 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 170569$, $T_{2401} := 2891^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 5879, 5881\}$ or $E := \{2281, 2282, \dots, 4680, 4681\}$
6. **(660, 2989, 3061)** $\Rightarrow 3061 - 660 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 182329$, $T_{2401} := 2989^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 6119, 6121\}$ or $E := \{2521, 2522, \dots, 4920, 4921\}$
7. **(784, 3087, 3185)** $\Rightarrow 3185 - 784 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 194481$, $T_{2401} := 3087^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 6367, 6369\}$ or $E := \{2769, 2770, \dots, 5168, 5169\}$
8. **(912, 3185, 3313)** $\Rightarrow 3313 - 912 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 207025$, $T_{2401} := 3185^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 6623, 6625\}$ or $E := \{3025, 3026, \dots, 5424, 5425\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 50

This subsection brings magic squares of order 50 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(102, 2600, 2602)** $\Rightarrow 2602 - 102 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 135200$, $T_{2500} := 2600^2$,
 $E := \{205, 207, \dots, 5201, 5203\}$

2. **(208, 2700, 2708)** $\Rightarrow 2708 - 208 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 145800$, $T_{2500} := 2700^2$,
 $E := \{417, 419, \dots, 5413, 5415\}$
3. **(318, 2800, 2818)** $\Rightarrow 2818 - 318 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 156800$, $T_{2500} := 2800^2$,
 $E := \{637, 639, \dots, 5633, 5635\}$
4. **(432, 2900, 2932)** $\Rightarrow 2932 - 432 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 168200$, $T_{2500} := 2900^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 5861, 5863\}$
5. **(550, 3000, 3050)** $\Rightarrow 3050 - 550 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 180000$, $T_{2500} := 3000^2$,
 $E := \{1101, 1103, \dots, 6097, 6099\}$
6. **(672, 3100, 3172)** $\Rightarrow 3172 - 672 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 192200$, $T_{2500} := 3100^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 6341, 6343\}$
7. **(798, 3200, 3298)** $\Rightarrow 3298 - 798 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 204800$, $T_{2500} := 3200^2$,
 $E := \{1597, 1599, \dots, 6593, 6595\}$
8. **(928, 3300, 3428)** $\Rightarrow 3428 - 928 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 217800$, $T_{2500} := 3300^2$,
 $E := \{1857, 1859, \dots, 6853, 6855\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 51

This subsection brings magic squares of order 51 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(104, 2703, 2705)** $\Rightarrow 2705 - 104 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 143259$, $T_{2601} := 2703^2$,
 $E := \{209, 211, \dots, 5407, 5409\}$ or $E := \{1509, 1510, \dots, 4108, 4109\}$
2. **(212, 2805, 2813)** $\Rightarrow 2813 - 212 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 154275$, $T_{2601} := 2805^2$,
 $E := \{425, 427, \dots, 5623, 5625\}$ or $E := \{1725, 1726, \dots, 4324, 4325\}$
3. **(324, 2907, 2925)** $\Rightarrow 2925 - 324 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 165699$, $T_{2601} := 2907^2$,
 $E := \{649, 651, \dots, 5847, 5849\}$ or $E := \{1949, 1950, \dots, 4548, 4549\}$
4. **(440, 3009, 3041)** $\Rightarrow 3041 - 440 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 177531$, $T_{2601} := 3009^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 6079, 6081\}$ or $E := \{2181, 2182, \dots, 4780, 4781\}$
5. **(560, 3111, 3161)** $\Rightarrow 3161 - 560 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 189771$, $T_{2601} := 3111^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 6319, 6321\}$ or $E := \{2421, 2422, \dots, 5020, 5021\}$
6. **(684, 3213, 3285)** $\Rightarrow 3285 - 684 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 202419$, $T_{2601} := 3213^2$,
 $E := \{1369, 1371, \dots, 6567, 6569\}$ or $E := \{2669, 2670, \dots, 5268, 5269\}$
7. **(812, 3315, 3413)** $\Rightarrow 3413 - 812 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 215475$, $T_{2601} := 3315^2$,
 $E := \{1625, 1627, \dots, 6823, 6825\}$ or $E := \{2925, 2926, \dots, 5524, 5525\}$
8. **(944, 3417, 3545)** $\Rightarrow 3545 - 944 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 228939$, $T_{2601} := 3417^2$,
 $E := \{1889, 1891, \dots, 7087, 7089\}$ or $E := \{3189, 3190, \dots, 5788, 5789\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 52

This subsection brings magic squares of order 52 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(106, 2808, 2810)** $\Rightarrow 2810 - 106 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 151632$, $T_{2704} := 2808^2$,
 $E := \{213, 215, \dots, 5617, 5619\}$
2. **(216, 2912, 2920)** $\Rightarrow 2920 - 216 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 163072$, $T_{2704} := 2912^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 5837, 5839\}$
3. **(330, 3016, 3034)** $\Rightarrow 3034 - 330 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 174928$, $T_{2704} := 3016^2$,
 $E := \{661, 663, \dots, 6065, 6067\}$
4. **(448, 3120, 3152)** $\Rightarrow 3152 - 448 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 187200$, $T_{2704} := 3120^2$,
 $E := \{897, 899, \dots, 6301, 6303\}$
5. **(570, 3224, 3274)** $\Rightarrow 3274 - 570 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 199888$, $T_{2704} := 3224^2$,
 $E := \{1141, 1143, \dots, 6545, 6547\}$
6. **(696, 3328, 3400)** $\Rightarrow 3400 - 696 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 212992$, $T_{2704} := 3328^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 6797, 6799\}$
7. **(826, 3432, 3530)** $\Rightarrow 3530 - 826 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 226512$, $T_{2704} := 3432^2$,
 $E := \{1653, 1655, \dots, 7057, 7059\}$
8. **(960, 3536, 3664)** $\Rightarrow 3664 - 960 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 240448$, $T_{2704} := 3536^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 7325, 7327\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 53

This subsection brings magic squares of order 53 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(108, 2915, 2917)** $\Rightarrow 2917 - 108 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 160325$, $T_{2809} := 2915^2$,
 $E := \{217, 219, \dots, 5831, 5833\}$ or $E := \{1621, 1622, \dots, 4428, 4429\}$
2. **(220, 3021, 3029)** $\Rightarrow 3029 - 220 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 172197$, $T_{2809} := 3021^2$,
 $E := \{441, 443, \dots, 6055, 6057\}$ or $E := \{1845, 1846, \dots, 4652, 4653\}$
3. **(336, 3127, 3145)** $\Rightarrow 3145 - 336 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 184493$, $T_{2809} := 3127^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 6287, 6289\}$ or $E := \{2077, 2078, \dots, 4884, 4885\}$
4. **(456, 3233, 3265)** $\Rightarrow 3265 - 456 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 197213$, $T_{2809} := 3233^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 6527, 6529\}$ or $E := \{2317, 2318, \dots, 5124, 5125\}$
5. **(580, 3339, 3389)** $\Rightarrow 3389 - 580 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 210357$, $T_{2809} := 3339^2$,
 $E := \{1161, 1163, \dots, 6775, 6777\}$ or $E := \{2565, 2566, \dots, 5372, 5373\}$

6. **(708, 3445, 3517)** $\Rightarrow 3517 - 708 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 223925$, $T_{2809} := 3445^2$,
 $E := \{1417, 1419, \dots, 7031, 7033\}$ or $E := \{2821, 2822, \dots, 5628, 5629\}$
7. **(840, 3551, 3649)** $\Rightarrow 3649 - 840 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 237917$, $T_{2809} := 3551^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 7295, 7297\}$ or $E := \{3085, 3086, \dots, 5892, 5893\}$
8. **(976, 3657, 3785)** $\Rightarrow 3785 - 976 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 252333$, $T_{2809} := 3657^2$,
 $E := \{1953, 1955, \dots, 7567, 7569\}$ or $E := \{3357, 3358, \dots, 6164, 6165\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 54

This subsection brings magic squares of order 54 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(110, 3024, 3026)** $\Rightarrow 3026 - 110 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 169344$, $T_{2916} := 3024^2$,
 $E := \{221, 223, \dots, 6049, 6051\}$
2. **(224, 3132, 3140)** $\Rightarrow 3140 - 224 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 181656$, $T_{2916} := 3132^2$,
 $E := \{449, 451, \dots, 6277, 6279\}$
3. **(342, 3240, 3258)** $\Rightarrow 3258 - 342 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 194400$, $T_{2916} := 3240^2$,
 $E := \{685, 687, \dots, 6513, 6515\}$
4. **(464, 3348, 3380)** $\Rightarrow 3380 - 464 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 207576$, $T_{2916} := 3348^2$,
 $E := \{929, 931, \dots, 6757, 6759\}$
5. **(590, 3456, 3506)** $\Rightarrow 3506 - 590 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 221184$, $T_{2916} := 3456^2$,
 $E := \{1181, 1183, \dots, 7009, 7011\}$
6. **(720, 3564, 3636)** $\Rightarrow 3636 - 720 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 235224$, $T_{2916} := 3564^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 7269, 7271\}$
7. **(854, 3672, 3770)** $\Rightarrow 3770 - 854 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 249696$, $T_{2916} := 3672^2$,
 $E := \{1709, 1711, \dots, 7537, 7539\}$
8. **(992, 3780, 3908)** $\Rightarrow 3908 - 992 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 264600$, $T_{2916} := 3780^2$,
 $E := \{1985, 1987, \dots, 7813, 7815\}$

4.26 Magic Squares of Orders 55-64: Blocks of 7

• Magic Squares of Order 55

This subsection brings magic squares of order 55 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(112, 3135, 3137)** $\Rightarrow 3137 - 112 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 178695$, $T_{3025} := 3135^2$,
 $E := \{225, 227, \dots, 6271, 6273\}$ or $E := \{1737, 1738, \dots, 4760, 4761\}$

2. **(228, 3245, 3253)** $\Rightarrow 3253 - 228 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 191455$, $T_{3025} := 3245^2$,
 $E := \{457, 459, \dots, 6503, 6505\}$ or $E := \{1969, 1970, \dots, 4992, 4993\}$
3. **(348, 3355, 3373)** $\Rightarrow 3373 - 348 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 204655$, $T_{3025} := 3355^2$,
 $E := \{697, 699, \dots, 6743, 6745\}$ or $E := \{2209, 2210, \dots, 5232, 5233\}$
4. **(472, 3465, 3497)** $\Rightarrow 3497 - 472 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 218295$, $T_{3025} := 3465^2$,
 $E := \{945, 947, \dots, 6991, 6993\}$ or $E := \{2457, 2458, \dots, 5480, 5481\}$
5. **(600, 3575, 3625)** $\Rightarrow 3625 - 600 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 232375$, $T_{3025} := 3575^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 7247, 7249\}$ or $E := \{2713, 2714, \dots, 5736, 5737\}$
6. **(732, 3685, 3757)** $\Rightarrow 3757 - 732 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 246895$, $T_{3025} := 3685^2$,
 $E := \{1465, 1467, \dots, 7511, 7513\}$ or $E := \{2977, 2978, \dots, 6000, 6001\}$
7. **(868, 3795, 3893)** $\Rightarrow 3893 - 868 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 261855$, $T_{3025} := 3795^2$,
 $E := \{1737, 1739, \dots, 7783, 7785\}$ or $E := \{3249, 3250, \dots, 6272, 6273\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 56

This subsection brings magic squares of order 56 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(114, 3248, 3250)** $\Rightarrow 3250 - 114 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 188384$, $T_{3136} := 3248^2$,
 $E := \{229, 231, \dots, 6497, 6499\}$
2. **(232, 3360, 3368)** $\Rightarrow 3368 - 232 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 201600$, $T_{3136} := 3360^2$,
 $E := \{465, 467, \dots, 6733, 6735\}$
3. **(354, 3472, 3490)** $\Rightarrow 3490 - 354 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 215264$, $T_{3136} := 3472^2$,
 $E := \{709, 711, \dots, 6977, 6979\}$
4. **(480, 3584, 3616)** $\Rightarrow 3616 - 480 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 229376$, $T_{3136} := 3584^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 7229, 7231\}$
5. **(610, 3696, 3746)** $\Rightarrow 3746 - 610 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 243936$, $T_{3136} := 3696^2$,
 $E := \{1221, 1223, \dots, 7489, 7491\}$
6. **(744, 3808, 3880)** $\Rightarrow 3880 - 744 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 258944$, $T_{3136} := 3808^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 7757, 7759\}$
7. **(882, 3920, 4018)** $\Rightarrow 4018 - 882 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 274400$, $T_{3136} := 3920^2$,
 $E := \{1765, 1767, \dots, 8033, 8035\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 57

This subsection brings magic squares of order 57 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(116, 3363, 3365)** $\Rightarrow 3365 - 116 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 198417$, $T_{3249} := 3363^2$,
 $E := \{233, 235, \dots, 6727, 6729\}$ or $E := \{1857, 1858, \dots, 5104, 5105\}$
2. **(236, 3477, 3485)** $\Rightarrow 3485 - 236 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 212097$, $T_{3249} := 3477^2$,
 $E := \{473, 475, \dots, 6967, 6969\}$ or $E := \{2097, 2098, \dots, 5344, 5345\}$
3. **(360, 3591, 3609)** $\Rightarrow 3609 - 360 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 226233$, $T_{3249} := 3591^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 7215, 7217\}$ or $E := \{2345, 2346, \dots, 5592, 5593\}$
4. **(488, 3705, 3737)** $\Rightarrow 3737 - 488 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 240825$, $T_{3249} := 3705^2$,
 $E := \{977, 979, \dots, 7471, 7473\}$ or $E := \{2601, 2602, \dots, 5848, 5849\}$
5. **(620, 3819, 3869)** $\Rightarrow 3869 - 620 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 255873$, $T_{3249} := 3819^2$,
 $E := \{1241, 1243, \dots, 7735, 7737\}$ or $E := \{2865, 2866, \dots, 6112, 6113\}$
6. **(756, 3933, 4005)** $\Rightarrow 4005 - 756 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 271377$, $T_{3249} := 3933^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 8007, 8009\}$ or $E := \{3137, 3138, \dots, 6384, 6385\}$
7. **(896, 4047, 4145)** $\Rightarrow 4145 - 896 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 287337$, $T_{3249} := 4047^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 8287, 8289\}$ or $E := \{3417, 3418, \dots, 6664, 6665\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 58

This subsection brings magic squares of order 58 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(118, 3480, 3482)** $\Rightarrow 3482 - 118 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 208800$, $T_{3364} := 3480^2$,
 $E := \{237, 239, \dots, 6961, 6963\}$
2. **(240, 3596, 3604)** $\Rightarrow 3604 - 240 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 222952$, $T_{3364} := 3596^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 7205, 7207\}$
3. **(366, 3712, 3730)** $\Rightarrow 3730 - 366 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 237568$, $T_{3364} := 3712^2$,
 $E := \{733, 735, \dots, 7457, 7459\}$
4. **(496, 3828, 3860)** $\Rightarrow 3860 - 496 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 252648$, $T_{3364} := 3828^2$,
 $E := \{993, 995, \dots, 7717, 7719\}$
5. **(630, 3944, 3994)** $\Rightarrow 3994 - 630 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 268192$, $T_{3364} := 3944^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 7985, 7987\}$
6. **(768, 4060, 4132)** $\Rightarrow 4132 - 768 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 284200$, $T_{3364} := 4060^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 8261, 8263\}$
7. **(910, 4176, 4274)** $\Rightarrow 4274 - 910 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 300672$, $T_{3364} := 4176^2$,
 $E := \{1821, 1823, \dots, 8545, 8547\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 59

This subsection brings magic squares of order 59 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(120, 3599, 3601)** $\Rightarrow 3601 - 120 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 219539$, $T_{3481} := 3599^2$,
 $E := \{241, 243, \dots, 7199, 7201\}$ or $E := \{1981, 1982, \dots, 5460, 5461\}$
2. **(244, 3717, 3725)** $\Rightarrow 3725 - 244 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 234171$, $T_{3481} := 3717^2$,
 $E := \{489, 491, \dots, 7447, 7449\}$ or $E := \{2229, 2230, \dots, 5708, 5709\}$
3. **(372, 3835, 3853)** $\Rightarrow 3853 - 372 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 249275$, $T_{3481} := 3835^2$,
 $E := \{745, 747, \dots, 7703, 7705\}$ or $E := \{2485, 2486, \dots, 5964, 5965\}$
4. **(504, 3953, 3985)** $\Rightarrow 3985 - 504 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 264851$, $T_{3481} := 3953^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 7967, 7969\}$ or $E := \{2749, 2750, \dots, 6228, 6229\}$
5. **(640, 4071, 4121)** $\Rightarrow 4121 - 640 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 280899$, $T_{3481} := 4071^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 8239, 8241\}$ or $E := \{3021, 3022, \dots, 6500, 6501\}$
6. **(780, 4189, 4261)** $\Rightarrow 4261 - 780 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 297419$, $T_{3481} := 4189^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 8519, 8521\}$ or $E := \{3301, 3302, \dots, 6780, 6781\}$
7. **(924, 4307, 4405)** $\Rightarrow 4405 - 924 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 314411$, $T_{3481} := 4307^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 8807, 8809\}$ or $E := \{3589, 3590, \dots, 7068, 7069\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 60

This subsection brings magic squares of order 60 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(122, 3720, 3722)** $\Rightarrow 3722 - 122 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 230640$, $T_{3600} := 3720^2$,
 $E := \{245, 247, \dots, 7441, 7443\}$
2. **(248, 3840, 3848)** $\Rightarrow 3848 - 248 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 245760$, $T_{3600} := 3840^2$,
 $E := \{497, 499, \dots, 7693, 7695\}$
3. **(378, 3960, 3978)** $\Rightarrow 3978 - 378 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 261360$, $T_{3600} := 3960^2$,
 $E := \{757, 759, \dots, 7953, 7955\}$
4. **(512, 4080, 4112)** $\Rightarrow 4112 - 512 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 277440$, $T_{3600} := 4080^2$,
 $E := \{1025, 1027, \dots, 8221, 8223\}$
5. **(650, 4200, 4250)** $\Rightarrow 4250 - 650 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 294000$, $T_{3600} := 4200^2$,
 $E := \{1301, 1303, \dots, 8497, 8499\}$
6. **(792, 4320, 4392)** $\Rightarrow 4392 - 792 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 311040$, $T_{3600} := 4320^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 8781, 8783\}$
7. **(938, 4440, 4538)** $\Rightarrow 4538 - 938 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 328560$, $T_{3600} := 4440^2$,
 $E := \{1877, 1879, \dots, 9073, 9075\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 61

This subsection brings magic squares of order 61 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(124, 3843, 3845)** $\Rightarrow 3845 - 124 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 242109$, $T_{3721} := 3843^2$,
 $E := \{249, 251, \dots, 7687, 7689\}$ or $E := \{2109, 2110, \dots, 5828, 5829\}$
2. **(252, 3965, 3973)** $\Rightarrow 3973 - 252 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 257725$, $T_{3721} := 3965^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 7943, 7945\}$ or $E := \{2365, 2366, \dots, 6084, 6085\}$
3. **(384, 4087, 4105)** $\Rightarrow 4105 - 384 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 273829$, $T_{3721} := 4087^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 8207, 8209\}$ or $E := \{2629, 2630, \dots, 6348, 6349\}$
4. **(520, 4209, 4241)** $\Rightarrow 4241 - 520 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 290421$, $T_{3721} := 4209^2$,
 $E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 8479, 8481\}$ or $E := \{2901, 2902, \dots, 6620, 6621\}$
5. **(660, 4331, 4381)** $\Rightarrow 4381 - 660 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 307501$, $T_{3721} := 4331^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 8759, 8761\}$ or $E := \{3181, 3182, \dots, 6900, 6901\}$
6. **(804, 4453, 4525)** $\Rightarrow 4525 - 804 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 325069$, $T_{3721} := 4453^2$,
 $E := \{1609, 1611, \dots, 9047, 9049\}$ or $E := \{3469, 3470, \dots, 7188, 7189\}$
7. **(952, 4575, 4673)** $\Rightarrow 4673 - 952 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 343125$, $T_{3721} := 4575^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 9343, 9345\}$ or $E := \{3765, 3766, \dots, 7484, 7485\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 62

This subsection brings magic squares of order 62 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(126, 3968, 3970)** $\Rightarrow 3970 - 126 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 253952$, $T_{3844} := 3968^2$,
 $E := \{253, 255, \dots, 7937, 7939\}$
2. **(256, 4092, 4100)** $\Rightarrow 4100 - 256 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 270072$, $T_{3844} := 4092^2$,
 $E := \{513, 515, \dots, 8197, 8199\}$
3. **(390, 4216, 4234)** $\Rightarrow 4234 - 390 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 286688$, $T_{3844} := 4216^2$,
 $E := \{781, 783, \dots, 8465, 8467\}$
4. **(528, 4340, 4372)** $\Rightarrow 4372 - 528 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 303800$, $T_{3844} := 4340^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 8741, 8743\}$
5. **(670, 4464, 4514)** $\Rightarrow 4514 - 670 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 321408$, $T_{3844} := 4464^2$,
 $E := \{1341, 1343, \dots, 9025, 9027\}$
6. **(816, 4588, 4660)** $\Rightarrow 4660 - 816 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 339512$, $T_{3844} := 4588^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 9317, 9319\}$
7. **(966, 4712, 4810)** $\Rightarrow 4810 - 966 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 358112$, $T_{3844} := 4712^2$,
 $E := \{1933, 1935, \dots, 9617, 9619\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 63

This subsection brings magic squares of order 63 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(128, 4095, 4097)** $\Rightarrow 4097 - 128 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 266175$, $T_{3969} := 4095^2$,
 $E := \{257, 259, \dots, 8191, 8193\}$ or $E := \{2241, 2242, \dots, 6208, 6209\}$
2. **(260, 4221, 4229)** $\Rightarrow 4229 - 260 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 282807$, $T_{3969} := 4221^2$,
 $E := \{521, 523, \dots, 8455, 8457\}$ or $E := \{2505, 2506, \dots, 6472, 6473\}$
3. **(396, 4347, 4365)** $\Rightarrow 4365 - 396 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 299943$, $T_{3969} := 4347^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 8727, 8729\}$ or $E := \{2777, 2778, \dots, 6744, 6745\}$
4. **(536, 4473, 4505)** $\Rightarrow 4505 - 536 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 317583$, $T_{3969} := 4473^2$,
 $E := \{1073, 1075, \dots, 9007, 9009\}$ or $E := \{3057, 3058, \dots, 7024, 7025\}$
5. **(680, 4599, 4649)** $\Rightarrow 4649 - 680 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 335727$, $T_{3969} := 4599^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 9295, 9297\}$ or $E := \{3345, 3346, \dots, 7312, 7313\}$
6. **(828, 4725, 4797)** $\Rightarrow 4797 - 828 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 354375$, $T_{3969} := 4725^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 9591, 9593\}$ or $E := \{3641, 3642, \dots, 7608, 7609\}$
7. **(980, 4851, 4949)** $\Rightarrow 4949 - 980 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 373527$, $T_{3969} := 4851^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 9895, 9897\}$ or $E := \{3945, 3946, \dots, 7912, 7913\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 64

This subsection brings magic squares of order 64 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(130, 4224, 4226)** $\Rightarrow 4226 - 130 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 278784$, $T_{4096} := 4224^2$,
 $E := \{261, 263, \dots, 8449, 8451\}$
2. **(264, 4352, 4360)** $\Rightarrow 4360 - 264 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 295936$, $T_{4096} := 4352^2$,
 $E := \{529, 531, \dots, 8717, 8719\}$
3. **(402, 4480, 4498)** $\Rightarrow 4498 - 402 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 313600$, $T_{4096} := 4480^2$,
 $E := \{805, 807, \dots, 8993, 8995\}$
4. **(544, 4608, 4640)** $\Rightarrow 4640 - 544 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 331776$, $T_{4096} := 4608^2$,
 $E := \{1089, 1091, \dots, 9277, 9279\}$
5. **(690, 4736, 4786)** $\Rightarrow 4786 - 690 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 350464$, $T_{4096} := 4736^2$,
 $E := \{1381, 1383, \dots, 9569, 9571\}$
6. **(840, 4864, 4936)** $\Rightarrow 4936 - 840 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 369664$, $T_{4096} := 4864^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 9869, 9871\}$
7. **(994, 4992, 5090)** $\Rightarrow 5090 - 994 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 389376$, $T_{4096} := 4992^2$,
 $E := \{1989, 1991, \dots, 10177, 10179\}$

4.27 Magic Squares of Orders 65-77: Blocks of 6

• Magic Squares of Order 65

This subsection brings magic squares of order 65 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(132, 4355, 4357)** $\Rightarrow 4357 - 132 = 65^2$, $S_{65 \times 65} := 291785$, $T_{4225} := 4355^2$,
 $E := \{265, 267, \dots, 8711, 8713\}$ or $E := \{2377, 2378, \dots, 6600, 6601\}$
2. **(268, 4485, 4493)** $\Rightarrow 4493 - 268 = 65^2$, $S_{65 \times 65} := 309465$, $T_{4225} := 4485^2$,
 $E := \{537, 539, \dots, 8983, 8985\}$ or $E := \{2649, 2650, \dots, 6872, 6873\}$
3. **(408, 4615, 4633)** $\Rightarrow 4633 - 408 = 65^2$, $S_{65 \times 65} := 327665$, $T_{4225} := 4615^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 9263, 9265\}$ or $E := \{2929, 2930, \dots, 7152, 7153\}$
4. **(552, 4745, 4777)** $\Rightarrow 4777 - 552 = 65^2$, $S_{65 \times 65} := 346385$, $T_{4225} := 4745^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 9551, 9553\}$ or $E := \{3217, 3218, \dots, 7440, 7441\}$
5. **(700, 4875, 4925)** $\Rightarrow 4925 - 700 = 65^2$, $S_{65 \times 65} := 365625$, $T_{4225} := 4875^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 9847, 9849\}$ or $E := \{3513, 3514, \dots, 7736, 7737\}$
6. **(852, 5005, 5077)** $\Rightarrow 5077 - 852 = 65^2$, $S_{65 \times 65} := 385385$, $T_{4225} := 5005^2$,
 $E := \{1705, 1707, \dots, 10151, 10153\}$ or $E := \{3817, 3818, \dots, 8040, 8041\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 66

This subsection brings magic squares of order 66 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(134, 4488, 4490)** $\Rightarrow 4490 - 134 = 66^2$, $S_{66 \times 66} := 305184$, $T_{4356} := 4488^2$,
 $E := \{269, 271, \dots, 8977, 8979\}$
2. **(272, 4620, 4628)** $\Rightarrow 4628 - 272 = 66^2$, $S_{66 \times 66} := 323400$, $T_{4356} := 4620^2$,
 $E := \{545, 547, \dots, 9253, 9255\}$
3. **(414, 4752, 4770)** $\Rightarrow 4770 - 414 = 66^2$, $S_{66 \times 66} := 342144$, $T_{4356} := 4752^2$,
 $E := \{829, 831, \dots, 9537, 9539\}$
4. **(560, 4884, 4916)** $\Rightarrow 4916 - 560 = 66^2$, $S_{66 \times 66} := 361416$, $T_{4356} := 4884^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 9829, 9831\}$
5. **(710, 5016, 5066)** $\Rightarrow 5066 - 710 = 66^2$, $S_{66 \times 66} := 381216$, $T_{4356} := 5016^2$,
 $E := \{1421, 1423, \dots, 10129, 10131\}$
6. **(864, 5148, 5220)** $\Rightarrow 5220 - 864 = 66^2$, $S_{66 \times 66} := 401544$, $T_{4356} := 5148^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 10437, 10439\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 67

This subsection brings magic squares of order 67 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(136, 4623, 4625)** $\Rightarrow 4625 - 136 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 318987$, $T_{4489} := 4623^2$,
 $E := \{273, 275, \dots, 9247, 9249\}$ or $E := \{2517, 2518, \dots, 7004, 7005\}$
2. **(276, 4757, 4765)** $\Rightarrow 4765 - 276 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 337747$, $T_{4489} := 4757^2$,
 $E := \{553, 555, \dots, 9527, 9529\}$ or $E := \{2797, 2798, \dots, 7284, 7285\}$
3. **(420, 4891, 4909)** $\Rightarrow 4909 - 420 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 357043$, $T_{4489} := 4891^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 9815, 9817\}$ or $E := \{3085, 3086, \dots, 7572, 7573\}$
4. **(568, 5025, 5057)** $\Rightarrow 5057 - 568 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 376875$, $T_{4489} := 5025^2$,
 $E := \{1137, 1139, \dots, 10111, 10113\}$ or $E := \{3381, 3382, \dots, 7868, 7869\}$
5. **(720, 5159, 5209)** $\Rightarrow 5209 - 720 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 397243$, $T_{4489} := 5159^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 10415, 10417\}$ or $E := \{3685, 3686, \dots, 8172, 8173\}$
6. **(876, 5293, 5365)** $\Rightarrow 5365 - 876 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 418147$, $T_{4489} := 5293^2$,
 $E := \{1753, 1755, \dots, 10727, 10729\}$ or $E := \{3997, 3998, \dots, 8484, 8485\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 68

This subsection brings magic squares of order 68 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(138, 4760, 4762)** $\Rightarrow 4762 - 138 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 333200$, $T_{4624} := 4760^2$,
 $E := \{277, 279, \dots, 9521, 9523\}$
2. **(280, 4896, 4904)** $\Rightarrow 4904 - 280 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 352512$, $T_{4624} := 4896^2$,
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 9805, 9807\}$
3. **(426, 5032, 5050)** $\Rightarrow 5050 - 426 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 372368$, $T_{4624} := 5032^2$,
 $E := \{853, 855, \dots, 10097, 10099\}$
4. **(576, 5168, 5200)** $\Rightarrow 5200 - 576 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 392768$, $T_{4624} := 5168^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 10397, 10399\}$
5. **(730, 5304, 5354)** $\Rightarrow 5354 - 730 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 413712$, $T_{4624} := 5304^2$,
 $E := \{1461, 1463, \dots, 10705, 10707\}$
6. **(888, 5440, 5512)** $\Rightarrow 5512 - 888 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 435200$, $T_{4624} := 5440^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 11021, 11023\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 69

This subsection brings magic squares of order 69 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(140, 4899, 4901)** $\Rightarrow 4901 - 140 = 69^2$, $S_{69 \times 69} := 347829$, $T_{4761} := 4899^2$,
 $E := \{281, 283, \dots, 9799, 9801\}$ or $E := \{2661, 2662, \dots, 7420, 7421\}$
2. **(284, 5037, 5045)** $\Rightarrow 5045 - 284 = 69^2$, $S_{69 \times 69} := 367701$, $T_{4761} := 5037^2$,
 $E := \{569, 571, \dots, 10087, 10089\}$ or $E := \{2949, 2950, \dots, 7708, 7709\}$
3. **(432, 5175, 5193)** $\Rightarrow 5193 - 432 = 69^2$, $S_{69 \times 69} := 388125$, $T_{4761} := 5175^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 10383, 10385\}$ or $E := \{3245, 3246, \dots, 8004, 8005\}$
4. **(584, 5313, 5345)** $\Rightarrow 5345 - 584 = 69^2$, $S_{69 \times 69} := 409101$, $T_{4761} := 5313^2$,
 $E := \{1169, 1171, \dots, 10687, 10689\}$ or $E := \{3549, 3550, \dots, 8308, 8309\}$
5. **(740, 5451, 5501)** $\Rightarrow 5501 - 740 = 69^2$, $S_{69 \times 69} := 430629$, $T_{4761} := 5451^2$,
 $E := \{1481, 1483, \dots, 10999, 11001\}$ or $E := \{3861, 3862, \dots, 8620, 8621\}$
6. **(900, 5589, 5661)** $\Rightarrow 5661 - 900 = 69^2$, $S_{69 \times 69} := 452709$, $T_{4761} := 5589^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 11319, 11321\}$ or $E := \{4181, 4182, \dots, 8940, 8941\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 70

This subsection brings magic squares of order 70 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(142, 5040, 5042)** $\Rightarrow 5042 - 142 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 362880$, $T_{4900} := 5040^2$,
 $E := \{285, 287, \dots, 10081, 10083\}$
2. **(288, 5180, 5188)** $\Rightarrow 5188 - 288 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 383320$, $T_{4900} := 5180^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 10373, 10375\}$
3. **(438, 5320, 5338)** $\Rightarrow 5338 - 438 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 404320$, $T_{4900} := 5320^2$,
 $E := \{877, 879, \dots, 10673, 10675\}$
4. **(592, 5460, 5492)** $\Rightarrow 5492 - 592 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 425880$, $T_{4900} := 5460^2$,
 $E := \{1185, 1187, \dots, 10981, 10983\}$
5. **(750, 5600, 5650)** $\Rightarrow 5650 - 750 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 448000$, $T_{4900} := 5600^2$,
 $E := \{1501, 1503, \dots, 11297, 11299\}$
6. **(912, 5740, 5812)** $\Rightarrow 5812 - 912 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 470680$, $T_{4900} := 5740^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 11621, 11623\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 71

This subsection brings magic squares of order 71 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(144, 5183, 5185)** $\Rightarrow 5185 - 144 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 378359$, $T_{5041} := 5183^2$,
 $E := \{289, 291, \dots, 10367, 10369\}$ or $E := \{2809, 2810, \dots, 7848, 7849\}$
2. **(292, 5325, 5333)** $\Rightarrow 5333 - 292 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 399375$, $T_{5041} := 5325^2$,
 $E := \{585, 587, \dots, 10663, 10665\}$ or $E := \{3105, 3106, \dots, 8144, 8145\}$
3. **(444, 5467, 5485)** $\Rightarrow 5485 - 444 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 420959$, $T_{5041} := 5467^2$,
 $E := \{889, 891, \dots, 10967, 10969\}$ or $E := \{3409, 3410, \dots, 8448, 8449\}$
4. **(600, 5609, 5641)** $\Rightarrow 5641 - 600 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 443111$, $T_{5041} := 5609^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 11279, 11281\}$ or $E := \{3721, 3722, \dots, 8760, 8761\}$
5. **(760, 5751, 5801)** $\Rightarrow 5801 - 760 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 465831$, $T_{5041} := 5751^2$,
 $E := \{1521, 1523, \dots, 11599, 11601\}$ or $E := \{4041, 4042, \dots, 9080, 9081\}$
6. **(924, 5893, 5965)** $\Rightarrow 5965 - 924 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 489119$, $T_{5041} := 5893^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 11927, 11929\}$ or $E := \{4369, 4370, \dots, 9408, 9409\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 72

This subsection brings magic squares of order 72 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(146, 5328, 5330)** $\Rightarrow 5330 - 146 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 394272$, $T_{5184} := 5328^2$,
 $E := \{293, 295, \dots, 10657, 10659\}$
2. **(296, 5472, 5480)** $\Rightarrow 5480 - 296 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 415872$, $T_{5184} := 5472^2$,
 $E := \{593, 595, \dots, 10957, 10959\}$
3. **(450, 5616, 5634)** $\Rightarrow 5634 - 450 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 438048$, $T_{5184} := 5616^2$,
 $E := \{901, 903, \dots, 11265, 11267\}$
4. **(608, 5760, 5792)** $\Rightarrow 5792 - 608 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 460800$, $T_{5184} := 5760^2$,
 $E := \{1217, 1219, \dots, 11581, 11583\}$
5. **(770, 5904, 5954)** $\Rightarrow 5954 - 770 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 484128$, $T_{5184} := 5904^2$,
 $E := \{1541, 1543, \dots, 11905, 11907\}$
6. **(936, 6048, 6120)** $\Rightarrow 6120 - 936 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 508032$, $T_{5184} := 6048^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 12237, 12239\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 73

This subsection brings magic squares of order 73 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(148, 5475, 5477)** $\Rightarrow 5477 - 148 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 410625$, $T_{5329} := 5475^2$,
 $E := \{297, 299, \dots, 10951, 10953\}$ or $E := \{2961, 2962, \dots, 8288, 8289\}$
2. **(300, 5621, 5629)** $\Rightarrow 5629 - 300 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 432817$, $T_{5329} := 5621^2$,
 $E := \{601, 603, \dots, 11255, 11257\}$ or $E := \{3265, 3266, \dots, 8592, 8593\}$
3. **(456, 5767, 5785)** $\Rightarrow 5785 - 456 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 455593$, $T_{5329} := 5767^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 11567, 11569\}$ or $E := \{3577, 3578, \dots, 8904, 8905\}$
4. **(616, 5913, 5945)** $\Rightarrow 5945 - 616 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 478953$, $T_{5329} := 5913^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 11887, 11889\}$ or $E := \{3897, 3898, \dots, 9224, 9225\}$
5. **(780, 6059, 6109)** $\Rightarrow 6109 - 780 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 502897$, $T_{5329} := 6059^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 12215, 12217\}$ or $E := \{4225, 4226, \dots, 9552, 9553\}$
6. **(948, 6205, 6277)** $\Rightarrow 6277 - 948 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 527425$, $T_{5329} := 6205^2$,
 $E := \{1897, 1899, \dots, 12551, 12553\}$ or $E := \{4561, 4562, \dots, 9888, 9889\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 74

This subsection brings magic squares of order 74 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(150, 5624, 5626)** $\Rightarrow 5626 - 150 = 74^2$, $S_{74 \times 74} := 427424$, $T_{5476} := 5624^2$,
 $E := \{301, 303, \dots, 11249, 11251\}$
2. **(304, 5772, 5780)** $\Rightarrow 5780 - 304 = 74^2$, $S_{74 \times 74} := 450216$, $T_{5476} := 5772^2$,
 $E := \{609, 611, \dots, 11557, 11559\}$
3. **(462, 5920, 5938)** $\Rightarrow 5938 - 462 = 74^2$, $S_{74 \times 74} := 473600$, $T_{5476} := 5920^2$,
 $E := \{925, 927, \dots, 11873, 11875\}$
4. **(624, 6068, 6100)** $\Rightarrow 6100 - 624 = 74^2$, $S_{74 \times 74} := 497576$, $T_{5476} := 6068^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 12197, 12199\}$
5. **(790, 6216, 6266)** $\Rightarrow 6266 - 790 = 74^2$, $S_{74 \times 74} := 522144$, $T_{5476} := 6216^2$,
 $E := \{1581, 1583, \dots, 12529, 12531\}$
6. **(960, 6364, 6436)** $\Rightarrow 6436 - 960 = 74^2$, $S_{74 \times 74} := 547304$, $T_{5476} := 6364^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 12869, 12871\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 75

This subsection brings magic squares of order 75 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(152, 5775, 5777)** $\Rightarrow 5777 - 152 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 444675$, $T_{5625} := 5775^2$,
 $E := \{305, 307, \dots, 11551, 11553\}$ or $E := \{3117, 3118, \dots, 8740, 8741\}$
2. **(308, 5925, 5933)** $\Rightarrow 5933 - 308 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 468075$, $T_{5625} := 5925^2$,
 $E := \{617, 619, \dots, 11863, 11865\}$ or $E := \{3429, 3430, \dots, 9052, 9053\}$
3. **(468, 6075, 6093)** $\Rightarrow 6093 - 468 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 492075$, $T_{5625} := 6075^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 12183, 12185\}$ or $E := \{3749, 3750, \dots, 9372, 9373\}$
4. **(632, 6225, 6257)** $\Rightarrow 6257 - 632 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 516675$, $T_{5625} := 6225^2$,
 $E := \{1265, 1267, \dots, 12511, 12513\}$ or $E := \{4077, 4078, \dots, 9700, 9701\}$
5. **(800, 6375, 6425)** $\Rightarrow 6425 - 800 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 541875$, $T_{5625} := 6375^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 12847, 12849\}$ or $E := \{4413, 4414, \dots, 10036, 10037\}$
6. **(972, 6525, 6597)** $\Rightarrow 6597 - 972 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 567675$, $T_{5625} := 6525^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 13191, 13193\}$ or $E := \{4757, 4758, \dots, 10380, 10381\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 76

This subsection brings magic squares of order 76 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(154, 5928, 5930)** $\Rightarrow 5930 - 154 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 462384$, $T_{5776} := 5928^2$,
 $E := \{309, 311, \dots, 11857, 11859\}$
2. **(312, 6080, 6088)** $\Rightarrow 6088 - 312 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 486400$, $T_{5776} := 6080^2$,
 $E := \{625, 627, \dots, 12173, 12175\}$
3. **(474, 6232, 6250)** $\Rightarrow 6250 - 474 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 511024$, $T_{5776} := 6232^2$,
 $E := \{949, 951, \dots, 12497, 12499\}$
4. **(640, 6384, 6416)** $\Rightarrow 6416 - 640 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 536256$, $T_{5776} := 6384^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 12829, 12831\}$
5. **(810, 6536, 6586)** $\Rightarrow 6586 - 810 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 562096$, $T_{5776} := 6536^2$,
 $E := \{1621, 1623, \dots, 13169, 13171\}$
6. **(984, 6688, 6760)** $\Rightarrow 6760 - 984 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 588544$, $T_{5776} := 6688^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 13517, 13519\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 77

This subsection brings magic squares of order 77 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(156, 6083, 6085)** $\Rightarrow 6085 - 156 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 480557$, $T_{5929} := 6083^2$,
 $E := \{313, 315, \dots, 12167, 12169\}$ or $E := \{3277, 3278, \dots, 9204, 9205\}$
2. **(316, 6237, 6245)** $\Rightarrow 6245 - 316 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 505197$, $T_{5929} := 6237^2$,
 $E := \{633, 635, \dots, 12487, 12489\}$ or $E := \{3597, 3598, \dots, 9524, 9525\}$
3. **(480, 6391, 6409)** $\Rightarrow 6409 - 480 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 530453$, $T_{5929} := 6391^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 12815, 12817\}$ or $E := \{3925, 3926, \dots, 9852, 9853\}$
4. **(648, 6545, 6577)** $\Rightarrow 6577 - 648 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 556325$, $T_{5929} := 6545^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 13151, 13153\}$ or $E := \{4261, 4262, \dots, 10188, 10189\}$
5. **(820, 6699, 6749)** $\Rightarrow 6749 - 820 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 582813$, $T_{5929} := 6699^2$,
 $E := \{1641, 1643, \dots, 13495, 13497\}$ or $E := \{4605, 4606, \dots, 10532, 10533\}$
6. **(996, 6853, 6925)** $\Rightarrow 6925 - 996 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 609917$, $T_{5929} := 6853^2$,
 $E := \{1993, 1995, \dots, 13847, 13849\}$ or $E := \{4957, 4958, \dots, 10884, 10885\}$

4.28 Magic Squares of Orders 78-95: Blocks of 5

• Magic Squares of Order 78

This subsection brings magic squares of order 78 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(158, 6240, 6242)** $\Rightarrow 6242 - 158 = 78^2$, $S_{78 \times 78} := 499200$, $T_{6084} := 6240^2$,
 $E := \{317, 319, \dots, 12481, 12483\}$
2. **(320, 6396, 6404)** $\Rightarrow 6404 - 320 = 78^2$, $S_{78 \times 78} := 524472$, $T_{6084} := 6396^2$,
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 12805, 12807\}$
3. **(486, 6552, 6570)** $\Rightarrow 6570 - 486 = 78^2$, $S_{78 \times 78} := 550368$, $T_{6084} := 6552^2$,
 $E := \{973, 975, \dots, 13137, 13139\}$
4. **(656, 6708, 6740)** $\Rightarrow 6740 - 656 = 78^2$, $S_{78 \times 78} := 576888$, $T_{6084} := 6708^2$,
 $E := \{1313, 1315, \dots, 13477, 13479\}$
5. **(830, 6864, 6914)** $\Rightarrow 6914 - 830 = 78^2$, $S_{78 \times 78} := 604032$, $T_{6084} := 6864^2$,
 $E := \{1661, 1663, \dots, 13825, 13827\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 79

This subsection brings magic squares of order 79 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(160, 6399, 6401)** $\Rightarrow 6401 - 160 = 79^2$, $S_{79 \times 79} := 518319$, $T_{6241} := 6399^2$,
 $E := \{321, 323, \dots, 12799, 12801\}$ or $E := \{3441, 3442, \dots, 9680, 9681\}$
2. **(324, 6557, 6565)** $\Rightarrow 6565 - 324 = 79^2$, $S_{79 \times 79} := 544231$, $T_{6241} := 6557^2$,
 $E := \{649, 651, \dots, 13127, 13129\}$ or $E := \{3769, 3770, \dots, 10008, 10009\}$
3. **(492, 6715, 6733)** $\Rightarrow 6733 - 492 = 79^2$, $S_{79 \times 79} := 570775$, $T_{6241} := 6715^2$,
 $E := \{985, 987, \dots, 13463, 13465\}$ or $E := \{4105, 4106, \dots, 10344, 10345\}$
4. **(664, 6873, 6905)** $\Rightarrow 6905 - 664 = 79^2$, $S_{79 \times 79} := 597951$, $T_{6241} := 6873^2$,
 $E := \{1329, 1331, \dots, 13807, 13809\}$ or $E := \{4449, 4450, \dots, 10688, 10689\}$
5. **(840, 7031, 7081)** $\Rightarrow 7081 - 840 = 79^2$, $S_{79 \times 79} := 625759$, $T_{6241} := 7031^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 14159, 14161\}$ or $E := \{4801, 4802, \dots, 11040, 11041\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 80

This subsection brings magic squares of order 80 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(162, 6560, 6562)** $\Rightarrow 6562 - 162 = 80^2$, $S_{80 \times 80} := 537920$, $T_{6400} := 6560^2$,
 $E := \{325, 327, \dots, 13121, 13123\}$
2. **(328, 6720, 6728)** $\Rightarrow 6728 - 328 = 80^2$, $S_{80 \times 80} := 564480$, $T_{6400} := 6720^2$,
 $E := \{657, 659, \dots, 13453, 13455\}$
3. **(498, 6880, 6898)** $\Rightarrow 6898 - 498 = 80^2$, $S_{80 \times 80} := 591680$, $T_{6400} := 6880^2$,
 $E := \{997, 999, \dots, 13793, 13795\}$
4. **(672, 7040, 7072)** $\Rightarrow 7072 - 672 = 80^2$, $S_{80 \times 80} := 619520$, $T_{6400} := 7040^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 14141, 14143\}$
5. **(850, 7200, 7250)** $\Rightarrow 7250 - 850 = 80^2$, $S_{80 \times 80} := 648000$, $T_{6400} := 7200^2$,
 $E := \{1701, 1703, \dots, 14497, 14499\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 81

This subsection brings magic squares of order 81 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(164, 6723, 6725)** $\Rightarrow 6725 - 164 = 81^2$, $S_{81 \times 81} := 558009$, $T_{6561} := 6723^2$,
 $E := \{329, 331, \dots, 13447, 13449\}$ or $E := \{3609, 3610, \dots, 10168, 10169\}$

2. **(332, 6885, 6893)** $\Rightarrow 6893 - 332 = 81^2$, $S_{81 \times 81} := 585225$, $T_{6561} := 6885^2$,
 $E := \{665, 667, \dots, 13783, 13785\}$ or $E := \{3945, 3946, \dots, 10504, 10505\}$
3. **(504, 7047, 7065)** $\Rightarrow 7065 - 504 = 81^2$, $S_{81 \times 81} := 613089$, $T_{6561} := 7047^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 14127, 14129\}$ or $E := \{4289, 4290, \dots, 10848, 10849\}$
4. **(680, 7209, 7241)** $\Rightarrow 7241 - 680 = 81^2$, $S_{81 \times 81} := 641601$, $T_{6561} := 7209^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 14479, 14481\}$ or $E := \{4641, 4642, \dots, 11200, 11201\}$
5. **(860, 7371, 7421)** $\Rightarrow 7421 - 860 = 81^2$, $S_{81 \times 81} := 670761$, $T_{6561} := 7371^2$,
 $E := \{1721, 1723, \dots, 14839, 14841\}$ or $E := \{5001, 5002, \dots, 11560, 11561\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 82

This subsection brings magic squares of order 82 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(166, 6888, 6890)** $\Rightarrow 6890 - 166 = 82^2$, $S_{82 \times 82} := 578592$, $T_{6724} := 6888^2$,
 $E := \{333, 335, \dots, 13777, 13779\}$
2. **(336, 7052, 7060)** $\Rightarrow 7060 - 336 = 82^2$, $S_{82 \times 82} := 606472$, $T_{6724} := 7052^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 14117, 14119\}$
3. **(510, 7216, 7234)** $\Rightarrow 7234 - 510 = 82^2$, $S_{82 \times 82} := 635008$, $T_{6724} := 7216^2$,
 $E := \{1021, 1023, \dots, 14465, 14467\}$
4. **(688, 7380, 7412)** $\Rightarrow 7412 - 688 = 82^2$, $S_{82 \times 82} := 664200$, $T_{6724} := 7380^2$,
 $E := \{1377, 1379, \dots, 14821, 14823\}$
5. **(870, 7544, 7594)** $\Rightarrow 7594 - 870 = 82^2$, $S_{82 \times 82} := 694048$, $T_{6724} := 7544^2$,
 $E := \{1741, 1743, \dots, 15185, 15187\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 83

This subsection brings magic squares of order 83 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(168, 7055, 7057)** $\Rightarrow 7057 - 168 = 83^2$, $S_{83 \times 83} := 599675$, $T_{6889} := 7055^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 14111, 14113\}$ or $E := \{3781, 3782, \dots, 10668, 10669\}$
2. **(340, 7221, 7229)** $\Rightarrow 7229 - 340 = 83^2$, $S_{83 \times 83} := 628227$, $T_{6889} := 7221^2$,
 $E := \{681, 683, \dots, 14455, 14457\}$ or $E := \{4125, 4126, \dots, 11012, 11013\}$
3. **(516, 7387, 7405)** $\Rightarrow 7405 - 516 = 83^2$, $S_{83 \times 83} := 657443$, $T_{6889} := 7387^2$,
 $E := \{1033, 1035, \dots, 14807, 14809\}$ or $E := \{4477, 4478, \dots, 11364, 11365\}$
4. **(696, 7553, 7585)** $\Rightarrow 7585 - 696 = 83^2$, $S_{83 \times 83} := 687323$, $T_{6889} := 7553^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 15167, 15169\}$ or $E := \{4837, 4838, \dots, 11724, 11725\}$

5. **(880, 7719, 7769)** $\Rightarrow 7769 - 880 = 83^2$, $S_{83 \times 83} := 717867$, $T_{6889} := 7719^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 15535, 15537\}$ or $E := \{5205, 5206, \dots, 12092, 12093\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 84

This subsection brings magic squares of order 84 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(170, 7224, 7226)** $\Rightarrow 7226 - 170 = 84^2$, $S_{84 \times 84} := 621264$, $T_{7056} := 7224^2$,
 $E := \{341, 343, \dots, 14449, 14451\}$
2. **(344, 7392, 7400)** $\Rightarrow 7400 - 344 = 84^2$, $S_{84 \times 84} := 650496$, $T_{7056} := 7392^2$,
 $E := \{689, 691, \dots, 14797, 14799\}$
3. **(522, 7560, 7578)** $\Rightarrow 7578 - 522 = 84^2$, $S_{84 \times 84} := 680400$, $T_{7056} := 7560^2$,
 $E := \{1045, 1047, \dots, 15153, 15155\}$
4. **(704, 7728, 7760)** $\Rightarrow 7760 - 704 = 84^2$, $S_{84 \times 84} := 710976$, $T_{7056} := 7728^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 15517, 15519\}$
5. **(890, 7896, 7946)** $\Rightarrow 7946 - 890 = 84^2$, $S_{84 \times 84} := 742224$, $T_{7056} := 7896^2$,
 $E := \{1781, 1783, \dots, 15889, 15891\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 85

This subsection brings magic squares of order 85 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(172, 7395, 7397)** $\Rightarrow 7397 - 172 = 85^2$, $S_{85 \times 85} := 643365$, $T_{7225} := 7395^2$,
 $E := \{345, 347, \dots, 14791, 14793\}$ or $E := \{3957, 3958, \dots, 11180, 11181\}$
2. **(348, 7565, 7573)** $\Rightarrow 7573 - 348 = 85^2$, $S_{85 \times 85} := 673285$, $T_{7225} := 7565^2$,
 $E := \{697, 699, \dots, 15143, 15145\}$ or $E := \{4309, 4310, \dots, 11532, 11533\}$
3. **(528, 7735, 7753)** $\Rightarrow 7753 - 528 = 85^2$, $S_{85 \times 85} := 703885$, $T_{7225} := 7735^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 15503, 15505\}$ or $E := \{4669, 4670, \dots, 11892, 11893\}$
4. **(712, 7905, 7937)** $\Rightarrow 7937 - 712 = 85^2$, $S_{85 \times 85} := 735165$, $T_{7225} := 7905^2$,
 $E := \{1425, 1427, \dots, 15871, 15873\}$ or $E := \{5037, 5038, \dots, 12260, 12261\}$
5. **(900, 8075, 8125)** $\Rightarrow 8125 - 900 = 85^2$, $S_{85 \times 85} := 767125$, $T_{7225} := 8075^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 16247, 16249\}$ or $E := \{5413, 5414, \dots, 12636, 12637\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 86

This subsection brings magic squares of order 86 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(174, 7568, 7570)** $\Rightarrow 7570 - 174 = 86^2$, $S_{86 \times 86} := 665984$, $T_{7396} := 7568^2$,
 $E := \{349, 351, \dots, 15137, 15139\}$
2. **(352, 7740, 7748)** $\Rightarrow 7748 - 352 = 86^2$, $S_{86 \times 86} := 696600$, $T_{7396} := 7740^2$,
 $E := \{705, 707, \dots, 15493, 15495\}$
3. **(534, 7912, 7930)** $\Rightarrow 7930 - 534 = 86^2$, $S_{86 \times 86} := 727904$, $T_{7396} := 7912^2$,
 $E := \{1069, 1071, \dots, 15857, 15859\}$
4. **(720, 8084, 8116)** $\Rightarrow 8116 - 720 = 86^2$, $S_{86 \times 86} := 759896$, $T_{7396} := 8084^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 16229, 16231\}$
5. **(910, 8256, 8306)** $\Rightarrow 8306 - 910 = 86^2$, $S_{86 \times 86} := 792576$, $T_{7396} := 8256^2$,
 $E := \{1821, 1823, \dots, 16609, 16611\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 87

This subsection brings magic squares of order 87 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(176, 7743, 7745)** $\Rightarrow 7745 - 176 = 87^2$, $S_{87 \times 87} := 689127$, $T_{7569} := 7743^2$,
 $E := \{353, 355, \dots, 15487, 15489\}$ or $E := \{4137, 4138, \dots, 11704, 11705\}$
2. **(356, 7917, 7925)** $\Rightarrow 7925 - 356 = 87^2$, $S_{87 \times 87} := 720447$, $T_{7569} := 7917^2$,
 $E := \{713, 715, \dots, 15847, 15849\}$ or $E := \{4497, 4498, \dots, 12064, 12065\}$
3. **(540, 8091, 8109)** $\Rightarrow 8109 - 540 = 87^2$, $S_{87 \times 87} := 752463$, $T_{7569} := 8091^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 16215, 16217\}$ or $E := \{4865, 4866, \dots, 12432, 12433\}$
4. **(728, 8265, 8297)** $\Rightarrow 8297 - 728 = 87^2$, $S_{87 \times 87} := 785175$, $T_{7569} := 8265^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 16591, 16593\}$ or $E := \{5241, 5242, \dots, 12808, 12809\}$
5. **(920, 8439, 8489)** $\Rightarrow 8489 - 920 = 87^2$, $S_{87 \times 87} := 818583$, $T_{7569} := 8439^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 16975, 16977\}$ or $E := \{5625, 5626, \dots, 13192, 13193\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 88

This subsection brings magic squares of order 88 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(178, 7920, 7922)** $\Rightarrow 7922 - 178 = 88^2$, $S_{88 \times 88} := 712800$, $T_{7744} := 7920^2$,
 $E := \{357, 359, \dots, 15841, 15843\}$

2. **(360, 8096, 8104)** $\Rightarrow 8104 - 360 = 88^2$, $S_{88 \times 88} := 744832$, $T_{7744} := 8096^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 16205, 16207\}$
3. **(546, 8272, 8290)** $\Rightarrow 8290 - 546 = 88^2$, $S_{88 \times 88} := 777568$, $T_{7744} := 8272^2$,
 $E := \{1093, 1095, \dots, 16577, 16579\}$
4. **(736, 8448, 8480)** $\Rightarrow 8480 - 736 = 88^2$, $S_{88 \times 88} := 811008$, $T_{7744} := 8448^2$,
 $E := \{1473, 1475, \dots, 16957, 16959\}$
5. **(930, 8624, 8674)** $\Rightarrow 8674 - 930 = 88^2$, $S_{88 \times 88} := 845152$, $T_{7744} := 8624^2$,
 $E := \{1861, 1863, \dots, 17345, 17347\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 89

This subsection brings magic squares of order 89 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(180, 8099, 8101)** $\Rightarrow 8101 - 180 = 89^2$, $S_{89 \times 89} := 737009$, $T_{7921} := 8099^2$,
 $E := \{361, 363, \dots, 16199, 16201\}$ or $E := \{4321, 4322, \dots, 12240, 12241\}$
2. **(364, 8277, 8285)** $\Rightarrow 8285 - 364 = 89^2$, $S_{89 \times 89} := 769761$, $T_{7921} := 8277^2$,
 $E := \{729, 731, \dots, 16567, 16569\}$ or $E := \{4689, 4690, \dots, 12608, 12609\}$
3. **(552, 8455, 8473)** $\Rightarrow 8473 - 552 = 89^2$, $S_{89 \times 89} := 803225$, $T_{7921} := 8455^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 16943, 16945\}$ or $E := \{5065, 5066, \dots, 12984, 12985\}$
4. **(744, 8633, 8665)** $\Rightarrow 8665 - 744 = 89^2$, $S_{89 \times 89} := 837401$, $T_{7921} := 8633^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 17327, 17329\}$ or $E := \{5449, 5450, \dots, 13368, 13369\}$
5. **(940, 8811, 8861)** $\Rightarrow 8861 - 940 = 89^2$, $S_{89 \times 89} := 872289$, $T_{7921} := 8811^2$,
 $E := \{1881, 1883, \dots, 17719, 17721\}$ or $E := \{5841, 5842, \dots, 13760, 13761\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 90

This subsection brings magic squares of order 90 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(182, 8280, 8282)** $\Rightarrow 8282 - 182 = 90^2$, $S_{90 \times 90} := 761760$, $T_{8100} := 8280^2$,
 $E := \{365, 367, \dots, 16561, 16563\}$
2. **(368, 8460, 8468)** $\Rightarrow 8468 - 368 = 90^2$, $S_{90 \times 90} := 795240$, $T_{8100} := 8460^2$,
 $E := \{737, 739, \dots, 16933, 16935\}$
3. **(558, 8640, 8658)** $\Rightarrow 8658 - 558 = 90^2$, $S_{90 \times 90} := 829440$, $T_{8100} := 8640^2$,
 $E := \{1117, 1119, \dots, 17313, 17315\}$
4. **(752, 8820, 8852)** $\Rightarrow 8852 - 752 = 90^2$, $S_{90 \times 90} := 864360$, $T_{8100} := 8820^2$,
 $E := \{1505, 1507, \dots, 17701, 17703\}$

5. **(950, 9000, 9050)** $\Rightarrow 9050 - 950 = 90^2$, $S_{90 \times 90} := 900000$, $T_{8100} := 9000^2$,
 $E := \{1901, 1903, \dots, 18097, 18099\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 91

This subsection brings magic squares of order 91 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(184, 8463, 8465)** $\Rightarrow 8465 - 184 = 91^2$, $S_{91 \times 91} := 787059$, $T_{8281} := 8463^2$,
 $E := \{369, 371, \dots, 16927, 16929\}$ or $E := \{4509, 4510, \dots, 12788, 12789\}$
2. **(372, 8645, 8653)** $\Rightarrow 8653 - 372 = 91^2$, $S_{91 \times 91} := 821275$, $T_{8281} := 8645^2$,
 $E := \{745, 747, \dots, 17303, 17305\}$ or $E := \{4885, 4886, \dots, 13164, 13165\}$
3. **(564, 8827, 8845)** $\Rightarrow 8845 - 564 = 91^2$, $S_{91 \times 91} := 856219$, $T_{8281} := 8827^2$,
 $E := \{1129, 1131, \dots, 17687, 17689\}$ or $E := \{5269, 5270, \dots, 13548, 13549\}$
4. **(760, 9009, 9041)** $\Rightarrow 9041 - 760 = 91^2$, $S_{91 \times 91} := 891891$, $T_{8281} := 9009^2$,
 $E := \{1521, 1523, \dots, 18079, 18081\}$ or $E := \{5661, 5662, \dots, 13940, 13941\}$
5. **(960, 9191, 9241)** $\Rightarrow 9241 - 960 = 91^2$, $S_{91 \times 91} := 928291$, $T_{8281} := 9191^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 18479, 18481\}$ or $E := \{6061, 6062, \dots, 14340, 14341\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 92

This subsection brings magic squares of order 92 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(186, 8648, 8650)** $\Rightarrow 8650 - 186 = 92^2$, $S_{92 \times 92} := 812912$, $T_{8464} := 8648^2$,
 $E := \{373, 375, \dots, 17297, 17299\}$
2. **(376, 8832, 8840)** $\Rightarrow 8840 - 376 = 92^2$, $S_{92 \times 92} := 847872$, $T_{8464} := 8832^2$,
 $E := \{753, 755, \dots, 17677, 17679\}$
3. **(570, 9016, 9034)** $\Rightarrow 9034 - 570 = 92^2$, $S_{92 \times 92} := 883568$, $T_{8464} := 9016^2$,
 $E := \{1141, 1143, \dots, 18065, 18067\}$
4. **(768, 9200, 9232)** $\Rightarrow 9232 - 768 = 92^2$, $S_{92 \times 92} := 920000$, $T_{8464} := 9200^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 18461, 18463\}$
5. **(970, 9384, 9434)** $\Rightarrow 9434 - 970 = 92^2$, $S_{92 \times 92} := 957168$, $T_{8464} := 9384^2$,
 $E := \{1941, 1943, \dots, 18865, 18867\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 93

This subsection brings magic squares of order 93 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(188, 8835, 8837)** $\Rightarrow 8837 - 188 = 93^2$, $S_{93 \times 93} := 839325$, $T_{8649} := 8835^2$,
 $E := \{377, 379, \dots, 17671, 17673\}$ or $E := \{4701, 4702, \dots, 13348, 13349\}$
2. **(380, 9021, 9029)** $\Rightarrow 9029 - 380 = 93^2$, $S_{93 \times 93} := 875037$, $T_{8649} := 9021^2$,
 $E := \{761, 763, \dots, 18055, 18057\}$ or $E := \{5085, 5086, \dots, 13732, 13733\}$
3. **(576, 9207, 9225)** $\Rightarrow 9225 - 576 = 93^2$, $S_{93 \times 93} := 911493$, $T_{8649} := 9207^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 18447, 18449\}$ or $E := \{5477, 5478, \dots, 14124, 14125\}$
4. **(776, 9393, 9425)** $\Rightarrow 9425 - 776 = 93^2$, $S_{93 \times 93} := 948693$, $T_{8649} := 9393^2$,
 $E := \{1553, 1555, \dots, 18847, 18849\}$ or $E := \{5877, 5878, \dots, 14524, 14525\}$
5. **(980, 9579, 9629)** $\Rightarrow 9629 - 980 = 93^2$, $S_{93 \times 93} := 986637$, $T_{8649} := 9579^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 19255, 19257\}$ or $E := \{6285, 6286, \dots, 14932, 14933\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 94

This subsection brings magic squares of order 94 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(190, 9024, 9026)** $\Rightarrow 9026 - 190 = 94^2$, $S_{94 \times 94} := 866304$, $T_{8836} := 9024^2$,
 $E := \{381, 383, \dots, 18049, 18051\}$
2. **(384, 9212, 9220)** $\Rightarrow 9220 - 384 = 94^2$, $S_{94 \times 94} := 902776$, $T_{8836} := 9212^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 18437, 18439\}$
3. **(582, 9400, 9418)** $\Rightarrow 9418 - 582 = 94^2$, $S_{94 \times 94} := 940000$, $T_{8836} := 9400^2$,
 $E := \{1165, 1167, \dots, 18833, 18835\}$
4. **(784, 9588, 9620)** $\Rightarrow 9620 - 784 = 94^2$, $S_{94 \times 94} := 977976$, $T_{8836} := 9588^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 19237, 19239\}$
5. **(990, 9776, 9826)** $\Rightarrow 9826 - 990 = 94^2$, $S_{94 \times 94} := 1016704$, $T_{8836} := 9776^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 19649, 19651\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 95

This subsection brings magic squares of order 95 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(1000, 9975, 10025)** $\Rightarrow 10025 - 1000 = 95^2$, $S_{95 \times 95} := 1047375$, $T_{9025} := 9975^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 20047, 20049\}$ or $E := \{6513, 6514, \dots, 15536, 15537\}$

2. **(192, 9215, 9217)** $\Rightarrow 9217 - 192 = 95^2$, $S_{95 \times 95} := 893855$, $T_{9025} := 9215^2$,
 $E := \{385, 387, \dots, 18431, 18433\}$ or $E := \{4897, 4898, \dots, 13920, 13921\}$
3. **(388, 9405, 9413)** $\Rightarrow 9413 - 388 = 95^2$, $S_{95 \times 95} := 931095$, $T_{9025} := 9405^2$,
 $E := \{777, 779, \dots, 18823, 18825\}$ or $E := \{5289, 5290, \dots, 14312, 14313\}$
4. **(588, 9595, 9613)** $\Rightarrow 9613 - 588 = 95^2$, $S_{95 \times 95} := 969095$, $T_{9025} := 9595^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 19223, 19225\}$ or $E := \{5689, 5690, \dots, 14712, 14713\}$
5. **(792, 9785, 9817)** $\Rightarrow 9817 - 792 = 95^2$, $S_{95 \times 95} := 1007855$, $T_{9025} := 9785^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 19631, 19633\}$ or $E := \{6097, 6098, \dots, 15120, 15121\}$

4.29 Magic Squares of Orders 96-121: Blocks of 4

• Magic Squares of Order 96

This subsection brings magic squares of order 96 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(194, 9408, 9410)** $\Rightarrow 9410 - 194 = 96^2$, $S_{96 \times 96} := 921984$, $T_{9216} := 9408^2$,
 $E := \{389, 391, \dots, 18817, 18819\}$
2. **(392, 9600, 9608)** $\Rightarrow 9608 - 392 = 96^2$, $S_{96 \times 96} := 960000$, $T_{9216} := 9600^2$,
 $E := \{785, 787, \dots, 19213, 19215\}$
3. **(594, 9792, 9810)** $\Rightarrow 9810 - 594 = 96^2$, $S_{96 \times 96} := 998784$, $T_{9216} := 9792^2$,
 $E := \{1189, 1191, \dots, 19617, 19619\}$
4. **(800, 9984, 10016)** $\Rightarrow 10016 - 800 = 96^2$, $S_{96 \times 96} := 1038336$, $T_{9216} := 9984^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 20029, 20031\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 97

This subsection brings magic squares of order 97 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(196, 9603, 9605)** $\Rightarrow 9605 - 196 = 97^2$, $S_{97 \times 97} := 950697$, $T_{9409} := 9603^2$,
 $E := \{393, 395, \dots, 19207, 19209\}$ or $E := \{5097, 5098, \dots, 14504, 14505\}$
2. **(396, 9797, 9805)** $\Rightarrow 9805 - 396 = 97^2$, $S_{97 \times 97} := 989497$, $T_{9409} := 9797^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 19607, 19609\}$ or $E := \{5497, 5498, \dots, 14904, 14905\}$
3. **(600, 9991, 10009)** $\Rightarrow 10009 - 600 = 97^2$, $S_{97 \times 97} := 1029073$, $T_{9409} := 9991^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 20015, 20017\}$ or $E := \{5905, 5906, \dots, 15312, 15313\}$
4. **(808, 10185, 10217)** $\Rightarrow 10217 - 808 = 97^2$, $S_{97 \times 97} := 1069425$, $T_{9409} := 10185^2$,
 $E := \{1617, 1619, \dots, 20431, 20433\}$ or $E := \{6321, 6322, \dots, 15728, 15729\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 98

This subsection brings magic squares of order 98 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(198, 9800, 9802)** $\Rightarrow 9802 - 198 = 98^2$, $S_{98 \times 98} := 980000$, $T_{9604} := 9800^2$,
 $E := \{397, 399, \dots, 19601, 19603\}$
2. **(400, 9996, 10004)** $\Rightarrow 10004 - 400 = 98^2$, $S_{98 \times 98} := 1019592$, $T_{9604} := 9996^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 20005, 20007\}$
3. **(606, 10192, 10210)** $\Rightarrow 10210 - 606 = 98^2$, $S_{98 \times 98} := 1059968$, $T_{9604} := 10192^2$,
 $E := \{1213, 1215, \dots, 20417, 20419\}$
4. **(816, 10388, 10420)** $\Rightarrow 10420 - 816 = 98^2$, $S_{98 \times 98} := 1101128$, $T_{9604} := 10388^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 20837, 20839\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 99

This subsection brings magic squares of order 99 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(200, 9999, 10001)** $\Rightarrow 10001 - 200 = 99^2$, $S_{99 \times 99} := 1009899$, $T_{9801} := 9999^2$,
 $E := \{401, 403, \dots, 19999, 20001\}$ or $E := \{5301, 5302, \dots, 15100, 15101\}$
2. **(404, 10197, 10205)** $\Rightarrow 10205 - 404 = 99^2$, $S_{99 \times 99} := 1050291$, $T_{9801} := 10197^2$,
 $E := \{809, 811, \dots, 20407, 20409\}$ or $E := \{5709, 5710, \dots, 15508, 15509\}$
3. **(612, 10395, 10413)** $\Rightarrow 10413 - 612 = 99^2$, $S_{99 \times 99} := 1091475$, $T_{9801} := 10395^2$,
 $E := \{1225, 1227, \dots, 20823, 20825\}$ or $E := \{6125, 6126, \dots, 15924, 15925\}$
4. **(824, 10593, 10625)** $\Rightarrow 10625 - 824 = 99^2$, $S_{99 \times 99} := 1133451$, $T_{9801} := 10593^2$,
 $E := \{1649, 1651, \dots, 21247, 21249\}$ or $E := \{6549, 6550, \dots, 16348, 16349\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 100

This subsection brings magic squares of order 100 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(202, 10200, 10202)** $\Rightarrow 10202 - 202 = 100^2$, $S_{100 \times 100} := 1040400$, $T_{10000} := 10200^2$,
 $E := \{405, 407, \dots, 20401, 20403\}$
2. **(408, 10400, 10408)** $\Rightarrow 10408 - 408 = 100^2$, $S_{100 \times 100} := 1081600$, $T_{10000} := 10400^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 20813, 20815\}$
3. **(618, 10600, 10618)** $\Rightarrow 10618 - 618 = 100^2$, $S_{100 \times 100} := 1123600$, $T_{10000} := 10600^2$,
 $E := \{1237, 1239, \dots, 21233, 21235\}$
4. **(832, 10800, 10832)** $\Rightarrow 10832 - 832 = 100^2$, $S_{100 \times 100} := 1166400$, $T_{10000} := 10800^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 21661, 21663\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 101

This subsection brings magic squares of order 101 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(204, 10403, 10405)** $\Rightarrow 10405 - 204 = 101^2$, $S_{101 \times 101} := 1071509$, $T_{10201} := 10403^2$,
 $E := \{409, 411, \dots, 20807, 20809\}$ or $E := \{5509, 5510, \dots, 15708, 15709\}$
2. **(412, 10605, 10613)** $\Rightarrow 10613 - 412 = 101^2$, $S_{101 \times 101} := 1113525$, $T_{10201} := 10605^2$,
 $E := \{825, 827, \dots, 21223, 21225\}$ or $E := \{5925, 5926, \dots, 16124, 16125\}$
3. **(624, 10807, 10825)** $\Rightarrow 10825 - 624 = 101^2$, $S_{101 \times 101} := 1156349$, $T_{10201} := 10807^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 21647, 21649\}$ or $E := \{6349, 6350, \dots, 16548, 16549\}$
4. **(840, 11009, 11041)** $\Rightarrow 11041 - 840 = 101^2$, $S_{101 \times 101} := 1199981$, $T_{10201} := 11009^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 22079, 22081\}$ or $E := \{6781, 6782, \dots, 16980, 16981\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 102

This subsection brings magic squares of order 102 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(206, 10608, 10610)** $\Rightarrow 10610 - 206 = 102^2$, $S_{102 \times 102} := 1103232$, $T_{10404} := 10608^2$,
 $E := \{413, 415, \dots, 21217, 21219\}$
2. **(416, 10812, 10820)** $\Rightarrow 10820 - 416 = 102^2$, $S_{102 \times 102} := 1146072$, $T_{10404} := 10812^2$,
 $E := \{833, 835, \dots, 21637, 21639\}$
3. **(630, 11016, 11034)** $\Rightarrow 11034 - 630 = 102^2$, $S_{102 \times 102} := 1189728$, $T_{10404} := 11016^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 22065, 22067\}$
4. **(848, 11220, 11252)** $\Rightarrow 11252 - 848 = 102^2$, $S_{102 \times 102} := 1234200$, $T_{10404} := 11220^2$,
 $E := \{1697, 1699, \dots, 22501, 22503\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 103

This subsection brings magic squares of order 103 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(208, 10815, 10817)** $\Rightarrow 10817 - 208 = 103^2$, $S_{103 \times 103} := 1135575$, $T_{10609} := 10815^2$,
 $E := \{417, 419, \dots, 21631, 21633\}$ or $E := \{5721, 5722, \dots, 16328, 16329\}$
2. **(420, 11021, 11029)** $\Rightarrow 11029 - 420 = 103^2$, $S_{103 \times 103} := 1179247$, $T_{10609} := 11021^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 22055, 22057\}$ or $E := \{6145, 6146, \dots, 16752, 16753\}$
3. **(636, 11227, 11245)** $\Rightarrow 11245 - 636 = 103^2$, $S_{103 \times 103} := 1223743$, $T_{10609} := 11227^2$,
 $E := \{1273, 1275, \dots, 22487, 22489\}$ or $E := \{6577, 6578, \dots, 17184, 17185\}$
4. **(856, 11433, 11465)** $\Rightarrow 11465 - 856 = 103^2$, $S_{103 \times 103} := 1269063$, $T_{10609} := 11433^2$,
 $E := \{1713, 1715, \dots, 22927, 22929\}$ or $E := \{7017, 7018, \dots, 17624, 17625\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 104

This subsection brings magic squares of order 104 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(210, 11024, 11026)** $\Rightarrow 11026 - 210 = 104^2$, $S_{104 \times 104} := 1168544$, $T_{10816} := 11024^2$,
 $E := \{421, 423, \dots, 22049, 22051\}$
2. **(424, 11232, 11240)** $\Rightarrow 11240 - 424 = 104^2$, $S_{104 \times 104} := 1213056$, $T_{10816} := 11232^2$,
 $E := \{849, 851, \dots, 22477, 22479\}$
3. **(642, 11440, 11458)** $\Rightarrow 11458 - 642 = 104^2$, $S_{104 \times 104} := 1258400$, $T_{10816} := 11440^2$,
 $E := \{1285, 1287, \dots, 22913, 22915\}$
4. **(864, 11648, 11680)** $\Rightarrow 11680 - 864 = 104^2$, $S_{104 \times 104} := 1304576$, $T_{10816} := 11648^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 23357, 23359\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 105

This subsection brings magic squares of order 105 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(212, 11235, 11237)** $\Rightarrow 11237 - 212 = 105^2$, $S_{105 \times 105} := 1202145$, $T_{11025} := 11235^2$,
 $E := \{425, 427, \dots, 22471, 22473\}$ or $E := \{5937, 5938, \dots, 16960, 16961\}$
2. **(428, 11445, 11453)** $\Rightarrow 11453 - 428 = 105^2$, $S_{105 \times 105} := 1247505$, $T_{11025} := 11445^2$,
 $E := \{857, 859, \dots, 22903, 22905\}$ or $E := \{6369, 6370, \dots, 17392, 17393\}$
3. **(648, 11655, 11673)** $\Rightarrow 11673 - 648 = 105^2$, $S_{105 \times 105} := 1293705$, $T_{11025} := 11655^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 23343, 23345\}$ or $E := \{6809, 6810, \dots, 17832, 17833\}$
4. **(872, 11865, 11897)** $\Rightarrow 11897 - 872 = 105^2$, $S_{105 \times 105} := 1340745$, $T_{11025} := 11865^2$,
 $E := \{1745, 1747, \dots, 23791, 23793\}$ or $E := \{7257, 7258, \dots, 18280, 18281\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 106

This subsection brings magic squares of order 106 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(214, 11448, 11450)** $\Rightarrow 11450 - 214 = 106^2$, $S_{106 \times 106} := 1236384$, $T_{11236} := 11448^2$,
 $E := \{429, 431, \dots, 22897, 22899\}$
2. **(432, 11660, 11668)** $\Rightarrow 11668 - 432 = 106^2$, $S_{106 \times 106} := 1282600$, $T_{11236} := 11660^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 23333, 23335\}$
3. **(654, 11872, 11890)** $\Rightarrow 11890 - 654 = 106^2$, $S_{106 \times 106} := 1329664$, $T_{11236} := 11872^2$,
 $E := \{1309, 1311, \dots, 23777, 23779\}$
4. **(880, 12084, 12116)** $\Rightarrow 12116 - 880 = 106^2$, $S_{106 \times 106} := 1377576$, $T_{11236} := 12084^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 24229, 24231\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 107

This subsection brings magic squares of order 107 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(216, 11663, 11665)** $\Rightarrow 11665 - 216 = 107^2$, $S_{107 \times 107} := 1271267$, $T_{11449} := 11663^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 23327, 23329\}$ or $E := \{6157, 6158, \dots, 17604, 17605\}$
2. **(436, 11877, 11885)** $\Rightarrow 11885 - 436 = 107^2$, $S_{107 \times 107} := 1318347$, $T_{11449} := 11877^2$,
 $E := \{873, 875, \dots, 23767, 23769\}$ or $E := \{6597, 6598, \dots, 18044, 18045\}$
3. **(660, 12091, 12109)** $\Rightarrow 12109 - 660 = 107^2$, $S_{107 \times 107} := 1366283$, $T_{11449} := 12091^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 24215, 24217\}$ or $E := \{7045, 7046, \dots, 18492, 18493\}$
4. **(888, 12305, 12337)** $\Rightarrow 12337 - 888 = 107^2$, $S_{107 \times 107} := 1415075$, $T_{11449} := 12305^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 24671, 24673\}$ or $E := \{7501, 7502, \dots, 18948, 18949\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 108

This subsection brings magic squares of order 108 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(218, 11880, 11882)** $\Rightarrow 11882 - 218 = 108^2$, $S_{108 \times 108} := 1306800$, $T_{11664} := 11880^2$,
 $E := \{437, 439, \dots, 23761, 23763\}$
2. **(440, 12096, 12104)** $\Rightarrow 12104 - 440 = 108^2$, $S_{108 \times 108} := 1354752$, $T_{11664} := 12096^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 24205, 24207\}$
3. **(666, 12312, 12330)** $\Rightarrow 12330 - 666 = 108^2$, $S_{108 \times 108} := 1403568$, $T_{11664} := 12312^2$,
 $E := \{1333, 1335, \dots, 24657, 24659\}$
4. **(896, 12528, 12560)** $\Rightarrow 12560 - 896 = 108^2$, $S_{108 \times 108} := 1453248$, $T_{11664} := 12528^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 25117, 25119\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 109

This subsection brings magic squares of order 109 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(220, 12099, 12101)** $\Rightarrow 12101 - 220 = 109^2$, $S_{109 \times 109} := 1342989$, $T_{11881} := 12099^2$,
 $E := \{441, 443, \dots, 24199, 24201\}$ or $E := \{6381, 6382, \dots, 18260, 18261\}$
2. **(444, 12317, 12325)** $\Rightarrow 12325 - 444 = 109^2$, $S_{109 \times 109} := 1391821$, $T_{11881} := 12317^2$,
 $E := \{889, 891, \dots, 24647, 24649\}$ or $E := \{6829, 6830, \dots, 18708, 18709\}$
3. **(672, 12535, 12553)** $\Rightarrow 12553 - 672 = 109^2$, $S_{109 \times 109} := 1441525$, $T_{11881} := 12535^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 25103, 25105\}$ or $E := \{7285, 7286, \dots, 19164, 19165\}$
4. **(904, 12753, 12785)** $\Rightarrow 12785 - 904 = 109^2$, $S_{109 \times 109} := 1492101$, $T_{11881} := 12753^2$,
 $E := \{1809, 1811, \dots, 25567, 25569\}$ or $E := \{7749, 7750, \dots, 19628, 19629\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 110

This subsection brings magic squares of order 110 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(222, 12320, 12322)** $\Rightarrow 12322 - 222 = 110^2$, $S_{110 \times 110} := 1379840$, $T_{12100} := 12320^2$,
 $E := \{445, 447, \dots, 24641, 24643\}$
2. **(448, 12540, 12548)** $\Rightarrow 12548 - 448 = 110^2$, $S_{110 \times 110} := 1429560$, $T_{12100} := 12540^2$,
 $E := \{897, 899, \dots, 25093, 25095\}$
3. **(678, 12760, 12778)** $\Rightarrow 12778 - 678 = 110^2$, $S_{110 \times 110} := 1480160$, $T_{12100} := 12760^2$,
 $E := \{1357, 1359, \dots, 25553, 25555\}$
4. **(912, 12980, 13012)** $\Rightarrow 13012 - 912 = 110^2$, $S_{110 \times 110} := 1531640$, $T_{12100} := 12980^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 26021, 26023\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 111

This subsection brings magic squares of order 111 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(224, 12543, 12545)** $\Rightarrow 12545 - 224 = 111^2$, $S_{111 \times 111} := 1417359$, $T_{12321} := 12543^2$,
 $E := \{449, 451, \dots, 25087, 25089\}$ or $E := \{6609, 6610, \dots, 18928, 18929\}$
2. **(452, 12765, 12773)** $\Rightarrow 12773 - 452 = 111^2$, $S_{111 \times 111} := 1467975$, $T_{12321} := 12765^2$,
 $E := \{905, 907, \dots, 25543, 25545\}$ or $E := \{7065, 7066, \dots, 19384, 19385\}$
3. **(684, 12987, 13005)** $\Rightarrow 13005 - 684 = 111^2$, $S_{111 \times 111} := 1519479$, $T_{12321} := 12987^2$,
 $E := \{1369, 1371, \dots, 26007, 26009\}$ or $E := \{7529, 7530, \dots, 19848, 19849\}$
4. **(920, 13209, 13241)** $\Rightarrow 13241 - 920 = 111^2$, $S_{111 \times 111} := 1571871$, $T_{12321} := 13209^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 26479, 26481\}$ or $E := \{8001, 8002, \dots, 20320, 20321\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 112

This subsection brings magic squares of order 112 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(226, 12768, 12770)** $\Rightarrow 12770 - 226 = 112^2$, $S_{112 \times 112} := 1455552$, $T_{12544} := 12768^2$,
 $E := \{453, 455, \dots, 25537, 25539\}$
2. **(456, 12992, 13000)** $\Rightarrow 13000 - 456 = 112^2$, $S_{112 \times 112} := 1507072$, $T_{12544} := 12992^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 25997, 25999\}$
3. **(690, 13216, 13234)** $\Rightarrow 13234 - 690 = 112^2$, $S_{112 \times 112} := 1559488$, $T_{12544} := 13216^2$,
 $E := \{1381, 1383, \dots, 26465, 26467\}$
4. **(928, 13440, 13472)** $\Rightarrow 13472 - 928 = 112^2$, $S_{112 \times 112} := 1612800$, $T_{12544} := 13440^2$,
 $E := \{1857, 1859, \dots, 26941, 26943\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 113

This subsection brings magic squares of order 113 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(228, 12995, 12997)** $\Rightarrow 12997 - 228 = 113^2$, $S_{113 \times 113} := 1494425$, $T_{12769} := 12995^2$,
 $E := \{457, 459, \dots, 25991, 25993\}$ or $E := \{6841, 6842, \dots, 19608, 19609\}$
2. **(460, 13221, 13229)** $\Rightarrow 13229 - 460 = 113^2$, $S_{113 \times 113} := 1546857$, $T_{12769} := 13221^2$,
 $E := \{921, 923, \dots, 26455, 26457\}$ or $E := \{7305, 7306, \dots, 20072, 20073\}$
3. **(696, 13447, 13465)** $\Rightarrow 13465 - 696 = 113^2$, $S_{113 \times 113} := 1600193$, $T_{12769} := 13447^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 26927, 26929\}$ or $E := \{7777, 7778, \dots, 20544, 20545\}$
4. **(936, 13673, 13705)** $\Rightarrow 13705 - 936 = 113^2$, $S_{113 \times 113} := 1654433$, $T_{12769} := 13673^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 27407, 27409\}$ or $E := \{8257, 8258, \dots, 21024, 21025\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 114

This subsection brings magic squares of order 114 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(230, 13224, 13226)** $\Rightarrow 13226 - 230 = 114^2$, $S_{114 \times 114} := 1533984$, $T_{12996} := 13224^2$,
 $E := \{461, 463, \dots, 26449, 26451\}$
2. **(464, 13452, 13460)** $\Rightarrow 13460 - 464 = 114^2$, $S_{114 \times 114} := 1587336$, $T_{12996} := 13452^2$,
 $E := \{929, 931, \dots, 26917, 26919\}$
3. **(702, 13680, 13698)** $\Rightarrow 13698 - 702 = 114^2$, $S_{114 \times 114} := 1641600$, $T_{12996} := 13680^2$,
 $E := \{1405, 1407, \dots, 27393, 27395\}$
4. **(944, 13908, 13940)** $\Rightarrow 13940 - 944 = 114^2$, $S_{114 \times 114} := 1696776$, $T_{12996} := 13908^2$,
 $E := \{1889, 1891, \dots, 27877, 27879\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 115

This subsection brings magic squares of order 115 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(232, 13455, 13457)** $\Rightarrow 13457 - 232 = 115^2$, $S_{115 \times 115} := 1574235$, $T_{13225} := 13455^2$,
 $E := \{465, 467, \dots, 26911, 26913\}$ or $E := \{7077, 7078, \dots, 20300, 20301\}$
2. **(468, 13685, 13693)** $\Rightarrow 13693 - 468 = 115^2$, $S_{115 \times 115} := 1628515$, $T_{13225} := 13685^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 27383, 27385\}$ or $E := \{7549, 7550, \dots, 20772, 20773\}$
3. **(708, 13915, 13933)** $\Rightarrow 13933 - 708 = 115^2$, $S_{115 \times 115} := 1683715$, $T_{13225} := 13915^2$,
 $E := \{1417, 1419, \dots, 27863, 27865\}$ or $E := \{8029, 8030, \dots, 21252, 21253\}$
4. **(952, 14145, 14177)** $\Rightarrow 14177 - 952 = 115^2$, $S_{115 \times 115} := 1739835$, $T_{13225} := 14145^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 28351, 28353\}$ or $E := \{8517, 8518, \dots, 21740, 21741\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 116

This subsection brings magic squares of order 116 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(234, 13688, 13690)** $\Rightarrow 13690 - 234 = 116^2$, $S_{116 \times 116} := 1615184$, $T_{13456} := 13688^2$,
 $E := \{469, 471, \dots, 27377, 27379\}$
2. **(472, 13920, 13928)** $\Rightarrow 13928 - 472 = 116^2$, $S_{116 \times 116} := 1670400$, $T_{13456} := 13920^2$,
 $E := \{945, 947, \dots, 27853, 27855\}$
3. **(714, 14152, 14170)** $\Rightarrow 14170 - 714 = 116^2$, $S_{116 \times 116} := 1726544$, $T_{13456} := 14152^2$,
 $E := \{1429, 1431, \dots, 28337, 28339\}$
4. **(960, 14384, 14416)** $\Rightarrow 14416 - 960 = 116^2$, $S_{116 \times 116} := 1783616$, $T_{13456} := 14384^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 28829, 28831\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 117

This subsection brings magic squares of order 117 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(236, 13923, 13925)** $\Rightarrow 13925 - 236 = 117^2$, $S_{117 \times 117} := 1656837$, $T_{13689} := 13923^2$,
 $E := \{473, 475, \dots, 27847, 27849\}$ or $E := \{7317, 7318, \dots, 21004, 21005\}$
2. **(476, 14157, 14165)** $\Rightarrow 14165 - 476 = 117^2$, $S_{117 \times 117} := 1712997$, $T_{13689} := 14157^2$,
 $E := \{953, 955, \dots, 28327, 28329\}$ or $E := \{7797, 7798, \dots, 21484, 21485\}$
3. **(720, 14391, 14409)** $\Rightarrow 14409 - 720 = 117^2$, $S_{117 \times 117} := 1770093$, $T_{13689} := 14391^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 28815, 28817\}$ or $E := \{8285, 8286, \dots, 21972, 21973\}$
4. **(968, 14625, 14657)** $\Rightarrow 14657 - 968 = 117^2$, $S_{117 \times 117} := 1828125$, $T_{13689} := 14625^2$,
 $E := \{1937, 1939, \dots, 29311, 29313\}$ or $E := \{8781, 8782, \dots, 22468, 22469\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 118

This subsection brings magic squares of order 118 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(238, 14160, 14162)** $\Rightarrow 14162 - 238 = 118^2$, $S_{118 \times 118} := 1699200$, $T_{13924} := 14160^2$,
 $E := \{477, 479, \dots, 28321, 28323\}$
2. **(480, 14396, 14404)** $\Rightarrow 14404 - 480 = 118^2$, $S_{118 \times 118} := 1756312$, $T_{13924} := 14396^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 28805, 28807\}$
3. **(726, 14632, 14650)** $\Rightarrow 14650 - 726 = 118^2$, $S_{118 \times 118} := 1814368$, $T_{13924} := 14632^2$,
 $E := \{1453, 1455, \dots, 29297, 29299\}$
4. **(976, 14868, 14900)** $\Rightarrow 14900 - 976 = 118^2$, $S_{118 \times 118} := 1873368$, $T_{13924} := 14868^2$,
 $E := \{1953, 1955, \dots, 29797, 29799\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 119

This subsection brings magic squares of order 119 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(240, 14399, 14401)** $\Rightarrow 14401 - 240 = 119^2$, $S_{119 \times 119} := 1742279$, $T_{14161} := 14399^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 28799, 28801\}$ or $E := \{7561, 7562, \dots, 21720, 21721\}$
2. **(484, 14637, 14645)** $\Rightarrow 14645 - 484 = 119^2$, $S_{119 \times 119} := 1800351$, $T_{14161} := 14637^2$,
 $E := \{969, 971, \dots, 29287, 29289\}$ or $E := \{8049, 8050, \dots, 22208, 22209\}$
3. **(732, 14875, 14893)** $\Rightarrow 14893 - 732 = 119^2$, $S_{119 \times 119} := 1859375$, $T_{14161} := 14875^2$,
 $E := \{1465, 1467, \dots, 29783, 29785\}$ or $E := \{8545, 8546, \dots, 22704, 22705\}$
4. **(984, 15113, 15145)** $\Rightarrow 15145 - 984 = 119^2$, $S_{119 \times 119} := 1919351$, $T_{14161} := 15113^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 30287, 30289\}$ or $E := \{9049, 9050, \dots, 23208, 23209\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 120

This subsection brings magic squares of order 120 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(242, 14640, 14642)** $\Rightarrow 14642 - 242 = 120^2$, $S_{120 \times 120} := 1786080$, $T_{14400} := 14640^2$,
 $E := \{485, 487, \dots, 29281, 29283\}$
2. **(488, 14880, 14888)** $\Rightarrow 14888 - 488 = 120^2$, $S_{120 \times 120} := 1845120$, $T_{14400} := 14880^2$,
 $E := \{977, 979, \dots, 29773, 29775\}$
3. **(738, 15120, 15138)** $\Rightarrow 15138 - 738 = 120^2$, $S_{120 \times 120} := 1905120$, $T_{14400} := 15120^2$,
 $E := \{1477, 1479, \dots, 30273, 30275\}$
4. **(992, 15360, 15392)** $\Rightarrow 15392 - 992 = 120^2$, $S_{120 \times 120} := 1966080$, $T_{14400} := 15360^2$,
 $E := \{1985, 1987, \dots, 30781, 30783\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 121

This subsection brings magic squares of order 121 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(1000, 15609, 15641)** $\Rightarrow 15641 - 1000 = 121^2$, $S_{121 \times 121} := 2013561$, $T_{14641} := 15609^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 31279, 31281\}$ or $E := \{9321, 9322, \dots, 23960, 23961\}$
2. **(244, 14883, 14885)** $\Rightarrow 14885 - 244 = 121^2$, $S_{121 \times 121} := 1830609$, $T_{14641} := 14883^2$,
 $E := \{489, 491, \dots, 29767, 29769\}$ or $E := \{7809, 7810, \dots, 22448, 22449\}$
3. **(492, 15125, 15133)** $\Rightarrow 15133 - 492 = 121^2$, $S_{121 \times 121} := 1890625$, $T_{14641} := 15125^2$,
 $E := \{985, 987, \dots, 30263, 30265\}$ or $E := \{8305, 8306, \dots, 22944, 22945\}$
4. **(744, 15367, 15385)** $\Rightarrow 15385 - 744 = 121^2$, $S_{121 \times 121} := 1951609$, $T_{14641} := 15367^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 30767, 30769\}$ or $E := \{8809, 8810, \dots, 23448, 23449\}$

4.30 Magic Squares of Orders 122-163: Blocks of 3

• Magic Squares of Order 122

This subsection brings magic squares of order 122 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(246, 15128, 15130)** $\Rightarrow 15130 - 246 = 122^2$, $S_{122 \times 122} := 1875872$, $T_{14884} := 15128^2$,
 $E := \{493, 495, \dots, 30257, 30259\}$
2. **(496, 15372, 15380)** $\Rightarrow 15380 - 496 = 122^2$, $S_{122 \times 122} := 1936872$, $T_{14884} := 15372^2$,
 $E := \{993, 995, \dots, 30757, 30759\}$
3. **(750, 15616, 15634)** $\Rightarrow 15634 - 750 = 122^2$, $S_{122 \times 122} := 1998848$, $T_{14884} := 15616^2$,
 $E := \{1501, 1503, \dots, 31265, 31267\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 123

This subsection brings magic squares of order 123 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(248, 15375, 15377)** $\Rightarrow 15377 - 248 = 123^2$, $S_{123 \times 123} := 1921875$, $T_{15129} := 15375^2$,
 $E := \{497, 499, \dots, 30751, 30753\}$ or $E := \{8061, 8062, \dots, 23188, 23189\}$
2. **(500, 15621, 15629)** $\Rightarrow 15629 - 500 = 123^2$, $S_{123 \times 123} := 1983867$, $T_{15129} := 15621^2$,
 $E := \{1001, 1003, \dots, 31255, 31257\}$ or $E := \{8565, 8566, \dots, 23692, 23693\}$
3. **(756, 15867, 15885)** $\Rightarrow 15885 - 756 = 123^2$, $S_{123 \times 123} := 2046843$, $T_{15129} := 15867^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 31767, 31769\}$ or $E := \{9077, 9078, \dots, 24204, 24205\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 124

This subsection brings magic squares of order 124 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(250, 15624, 15626)** $\Rightarrow 15626 - 250 = 124^2$, $S_{124 \times 124} := 1968624$, $T_{15376} := 15624^2$,
 $E := \{501, 503, \dots, 31249, 31251\}$
2. **(504, 15872, 15880)** $\Rightarrow 15880 - 504 = 124^2$, $S_{124 \times 124} := 2031616$, $T_{15376} := 15872^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 31757, 31759\}$
3. **(762, 16120, 16138)** $\Rightarrow 16138 - 762 = 124^2$, $S_{124 \times 124} := 2095600$, $T_{15376} := 16120^2$,
 $E := \{1525, 1527, \dots, 32273, 32275\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 125

This subsection brings magic squares of order 125 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(252, 15875, 15877)** $\Rightarrow 15877 - 252 = 125^2$, $S_{125 \times 125} := 2016125$, $T_{15625} := 15875^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 31751, 31753\}$ or $E := \{8317, 8318, \dots, 23940, 23941\}$
2. **(508, 16125, 16133)** $\Rightarrow 16133 - 508 = 125^2$, $S_{125 \times 125} := 2080125$, $T_{15625} := 16125^2$,
 $E := \{1017, 1019, \dots, 32263, 32265\}$ or $E := \{8829, 8830, \dots, 24452, 24453\}$
3. **(768, 16375, 16393)** $\Rightarrow 16393 - 768 = 125^2$, $S_{125 \times 125} := 2145125$, $T_{15625} := 16375^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 32783, 32785\}$ or $E := \{9349, 9350, \dots, 24972, 24973\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 126

This subsection brings magic squares of order 126 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(254, 16128, 16130)** $\Rightarrow 16130 - 254 = 126^2$, $S_{126 \times 126} := 2064384$, $T_{15876} := 16128^2$,
 $E := \{509, 511, \dots, 32257, 32259\}$
2. **(512, 16380, 16388)** $\Rightarrow 16388 - 512 = 126^2$, $S_{126 \times 126} := 2129400$, $T_{15876} := 16380^2$,
 $E := \{1025, 1027, \dots, 32773, 32775\}$
3. **(774, 16632, 16650)** $\Rightarrow 16650 - 774 = 126^2$, $S_{126 \times 126} := 2195424$, $T_{15876} := 16632^2$,
 $E := \{1549, 1551, \dots, 33297, 33299\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 127

This subsection brings magic squares of order 127 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(256, 16383, 16385)** $\Rightarrow 16385 - 256 = 127^2$, $S_{127 \times 127} := 2113407$, $T_{16129} := 16383^2$,
 $E := \{513, 515, \dots, 32767, 32769\}$ or $E := \{8577, 8578, \dots, 24704, 24705\}$
2. **(516, 16637, 16645)** $\Rightarrow 16645 - 516 = 127^2$, $S_{127 \times 127} := 2179447$, $T_{16129} := 16637^2$,
 $E := \{1033, 1035, \dots, 33287, 33289\}$ or $E := \{9097, 9098, \dots, 25224, 25225\}$
3. **(780, 16891, 16909)** $\Rightarrow 16909 - 780 = 127^2$, $S_{127 \times 127} := 2246503$, $T_{16129} := 16891^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 33815, 33817\}$ or $E := \{9625, 9626, \dots, 25752, 25753\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 128

This subsection brings magic squares of order 128 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(258, 16640, 16642)** $\Rightarrow 16642 - 258 = 128^2$, $S_{128 \times 128} := 2163200$, $T_{16384} := 16640^2$,
 $E := \{517, 519, \dots, 33281, 33283\}$
2. **(520, 16896, 16904)** $\Rightarrow 16904 - 520 = 128^2$, $S_{128 \times 128} := 2230272$, $T_{16384} := 16896^2$,
 $E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 33805, 33807\}$
3. **(786, 17152, 17170)** $\Rightarrow 17170 - 786 = 128^2$, $S_{128 \times 128} := 2298368$, $T_{16384} := 17152^2$,
 $E := \{1573, 1575, \dots, 34337, 34339\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 129

This subsection brings magic squares of order 129 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(260, 16899, 16901)** $\Rightarrow 16901 - 260 = 129^2$, $S_{129 \times 129} := 2213769$, $T_{16641} := 16899^2$,
 $E := \{521, 523, \dots, 33799, 33801\}$ or $E := \{8841, 8842, \dots, 25480, 25481\}$
2. **(524, 17157, 17165)** $\Rightarrow 17165 - 524 = 129^2$, $S_{129 \times 129} := 2281881$, $T_{16641} := 17157^2$,
 $E := \{1049, 1051, \dots, 34327, 34329\}$ or $E := \{9369, 9370, \dots, 26008, 26009\}$
3. **(792, 17415, 17433)** $\Rightarrow 17433 - 792 = 129^2$, $S_{129 \times 129} := 2351025$, $T_{16641} := 17415^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 34863, 34865\}$ or $E := \{9905, 9906, \dots, 26544, 26545\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 130

This subsection brings magic squares of order 130 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(262, 17160, 17162)** $\Rightarrow 17162 - 262 = 130^2$, $S_{130 \times 130} := 2265120$, $T_{16900} := 17160^2$,
 $E := \{525, 527, \dots, 34321, 34323\}$
2. **(528, 17420, 17428)** $\Rightarrow 17428 - 528 = 130^2$, $S_{130 \times 130} := 2334280$, $T_{16900} := 17420^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 34853, 34855\}$
3. **(798, 17680, 17698)** $\Rightarrow 17698 - 798 = 130^2$, $S_{130 \times 130} := 2404480$, $T_{16900} := 17680^2$,
 $E := \{1597, 1599, \dots, 35393, 35395\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 131

This subsection brings magic squares of order 131 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(264, 17423, 17425)** $\Rightarrow 17425 - 264 = 131^2$, $S_{131 \times 131} := 2317259$, $T_{17161} := 17423^2$,
 $E := \{529, 531, \dots, 34847, 34849\}$ or $E := \{9109, 9110, \dots, 26268, 26269\}$
2. **(532, 17685, 17693)** $\Rightarrow 17693 - 532 = 131^2$, $S_{131 \times 131} := 2387475$, $T_{17161} := 17685^2$,
 $E := \{1065, 1067, \dots, 35383, 35385\}$ or $E := \{9645, 9646, \dots, 26804, 26805\}$

3. **(804, 17947, 17965)** $\Rightarrow 17965 - 804 = 131^2$, $S_{131 \times 131} := 2458739$, $T_{17161} := 17947^2$,
 $E := \{1609, 1611, \dots, 35927, 35929\}$ or $E := \{10189, 10190, \dots, 27348, 27349\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 132

This subsection brings magic squares of order 132 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(266, 17688, 17690)** $\Rightarrow 17690 - 266 = 132^2$, $S_{132 \times 132} := 2370192$, $T_{17424} := 17688^2$,
 $E := \{533, 535, \dots, 35377, 35379\}$
2. **(536, 17952, 17960)** $\Rightarrow 17960 - 536 = 132^2$, $S_{132 \times 132} := 2441472$, $T_{17424} := 17952^2$,
 $E := \{1073, 1075, \dots, 35917, 35919\}$
3. **(810, 18216, 18234)** $\Rightarrow 18234 - 810 = 132^2$, $S_{132 \times 132} := 2513808$, $T_{17424} := 18216^2$,
 $E := \{1621, 1623, \dots, 36465, 36467\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 133

This subsection brings magic squares of order 133 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(268, 17955, 17957)** $\Rightarrow 17957 - 268 = 133^2$, $S_{133 \times 133} := 2423925$, $T_{17689} := 17955^2$,
 $E := \{537, 539, \dots, 35911, 35913\}$ or $E := \{9381, 9382, \dots, 27068, 27069\}$
2. **(540, 18221, 18229)** $\Rightarrow 18229 - 540 = 133^2$, $S_{133 \times 133} := 2496277$, $T_{17689} := 18221^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 36455, 36457\}$ or $E := \{9925, 9926, \dots, 27612, 27613\}$
3. **(816, 18487, 18505)** $\Rightarrow 18505 - 816 = 133^2$, $S_{133 \times 133} := 2569693$, $T_{17689} := 18487^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 37007, 37009\}$ or $E := \{10477, 10478, \dots, 28164, 28165\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 134

This subsection brings magic squares of order 134 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(270, 18224, 18226)** $\Rightarrow 18226 - 270 = 134^2$, $S_{134 \times 134} := 2478464$, $T_{17956} := 18224^2$,
 $E := \{541, 543, \dots, 36449, 36451\}$
2. **(544, 18492, 18500)** $\Rightarrow 18500 - 544 = 134^2$, $S_{134 \times 134} := 2551896$, $T_{17956} := 18492^2$,
 $E := \{1089, 1091, \dots, 36997, 36999\}$
3. **(822, 18760, 18778)** $\Rightarrow 18778 - 822 = 134^2$, $S_{134 \times 134} := 2626400$, $T_{17956} := 18760^2$,
 $E := \{1645, 1647, \dots, 37553, 37555\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 135

This subsection brings magic squares of order 135 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(272, 18495, 18497)** $\Rightarrow 18497 - 272 = 135^2$, $S_{135 \times 135} := 2533815$, $T_{18225} := 18495^2$,
 $E := \{545, 547, \dots, 36991, 36993\}$ or $E := \{9657, 9658, \dots, 27880, 27881\}$
2. **(548, 18765, 18773)** $\Rightarrow 18773 - 548 = 135^2$, $S_{135 \times 135} := 2608335$, $T_{18225} := 18765^2$,
 $E := \{1097, 1099, \dots, 37543, 37545\}$ or $E := \{10209, 10210, \dots, 28432, 28433\}$
3. **(828, 19035, 19053)** $\Rightarrow 19053 - 828 = 135^2$, $S_{135 \times 135} := 2683935$, $T_{18225} := 19035^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 38103, 38105\}$ or $E := \{10769, 10770, \dots, 28992, 28993\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 136

This subsection brings magic squares of order 136 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(274, 18768, 18770)** $\Rightarrow 18770 - 274 = 136^2$, $S_{136 \times 136} := 2589984$, $T_{18496} := 18768^2$,
 $E := \{549, 551, \dots, 37537, 37539\}$
2. **(552, 19040, 19048)** $\Rightarrow 19048 - 552 = 136^2$, $S_{136 \times 136} := 2665600$, $T_{18496} := 19040^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 38093, 38095\}$
3. **(834, 19312, 19330)** $\Rightarrow 19330 - 834 = 136^2$, $S_{136 \times 136} := 2742304$, $T_{18496} := 19312^2$,
 $E := \{1669, 1671, \dots, 38657, 38659\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 137

This subsection brings magic squares of order 137 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(276, 19043, 19045)** $\Rightarrow 19045 - 276 = 137^2$, $S_{137 \times 137} := 2646977$, $T_{18769} := 19043^2$,
 $E := \{553, 555, \dots, 38087, 38089\}$ or $E := \{9937, 9938, \dots, 28704, 28705\}$
2. **(556, 19317, 19325)** $\Rightarrow 19325 - 556 = 137^2$, $S_{137 \times 137} := 2723697$, $T_{18769} := 19317^2$,
 $E := \{1113, 1115, \dots, 38647, 38649\}$ or $E := \{10497, 10498, \dots, 29264, 29265\}$
3. **(840, 19591, 19609)** $\Rightarrow 19609 - 840 = 137^2$, $S_{137 \times 137} := 2801513$, $T_{18769} := 19591^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 39215, 39217\}$ or $E := \{11065, 11066, \dots, 29832, 29833\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 138

This subsection brings magic squares of order 138 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(278, 19320, 19322)** $\Rightarrow 19322 - 278 = 138^2$, $S_{138 \times 138} := 2704800$, $T_{19044} := 19320^2$,
 $E := \{557, 559, \dots, 38641, 38643\}$
2. **(560, 19596, 19604)** $\Rightarrow 19604 - 560 = 138^2$, $S_{138 \times 138} := 2782632$, $T_{19044} := 19596^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 39205, 39207\}$
3. **(846, 19872, 19890)** $\Rightarrow 19890 - 846 = 138^2$, $S_{138 \times 138} := 2861568$, $T_{19044} := 19872^2$,
 $E := \{1693, 1695, \dots, 39777, 39779\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 139

This subsection brings magic squares of order 139 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(280, 19599, 19601)** $\Rightarrow 19601 - 280 = 139^2$, $S_{139 \times 139} := 2763459$, $T_{19321} := 19599^2$,
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 39199, 39201\}$ or $E := \{10221, 10222, \dots, 29540, 29541\}$
2. **(564, 19877, 19885)** $\Rightarrow 19885 - 564 = 139^2$, $S_{139 \times 139} := 2842411$, $T_{19321} := 19877^2$,
 $E := \{1129, 1131, \dots, 39767, 39769\}$ or $E := \{10789, 10790, \dots, 30108, 30109\}$
3. **(852, 20155, 20173)** $\Rightarrow 20173 - 852 = 139^2$, $S_{139 \times 139} := 2922475$, $T_{19321} := 20155^2$,
 $E := \{1705, 1707, \dots, 40343, 40345\}$ or $E := \{11365, 11366, \dots, 30684, 30685\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 140

This subsection brings magic squares of order 140 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(282, 19880, 19882)** $\Rightarrow 19882 - 282 = 140^2$, $S_{140 \times 140} := 2822960$, $T_{19600} := 19880^2$,
 $E := \{565, 567, \dots, 39761, 39763\}$
2. **(568, 20160, 20168)** $\Rightarrow 20168 - 568 = 140^2$, $S_{140 \times 140} := 2903040$, $T_{19600} := 20160^2$,
 $E := \{1137, 1139, \dots, 40333, 40335\}$
3. **(858, 20440, 20458)** $\Rightarrow 20458 - 858 = 140^2$, $S_{140 \times 140} := 2984240$, $T_{19600} := 20440^2$,
 $E := \{1717, 1719, \dots, 40913, 40915\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 141

This subsection brings magic squares of order 141 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(284, 20163, 20165)** $\Rightarrow 20165 - 284 = 141^2$, $S_{141 \times 141} := 2883309$, $T_{19881} := 20163^2$,
 $E := \{569, 571, \dots, 40327, 40329\}$ or $E := \{10509, 10510, \dots, 30388, 30389\}$
2. **(572, 20445, 20453)** $\Rightarrow 20453 - 572 = 141^2$, $S_{141 \times 141} := 2964525$, $T_{19881} := 20445^2$,
 $E := \{1145, 1147, \dots, 40903, 40905\}$ or $E := \{11085, 11086, \dots, 30964, 30965\}$

3. **(864, 20727, 20745)** $\Rightarrow 20745 - 864 = 141^2$, $S_{141 \times 141} := 3046869$, $T_{19881} := 20727^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 41487, 41489\}$ or $E := \{11669, 11670, \dots, 31548, 31549\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 142

This subsection brings magic squares of order 142 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(286, 20448, 20450)** $\Rightarrow 20450 - 286 = 142^2$, $S_{142 \times 142} := 2944512$, $T_{20164} := 20448^2$,
 $E := \{573, 575, \dots, 40897, 40899\}$
2. **(576, 20732, 20740)** $\Rightarrow 20740 - 576 = 142^2$, $S_{142 \times 142} := 3026872$, $T_{20164} := 20732^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 41477, 41479\}$
3. **(870, 21016, 21034)** $\Rightarrow 21034 - 870 = 142^2$, $S_{142 \times 142} := 3110368$, $T_{20164} := 21016^2$,
 $E := \{1741, 1743, \dots, 42065, 42067\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 143

This subsection brings magic squares of order 143 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(288, 20735, 20737)** $\Rightarrow 20737 - 288 = 143^2$, $S_{143 \times 143} := 3006575$, $T_{20449} := 20735^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 41471, 41473\}$ or $E := \{10801, 10802, \dots, 31248, 31249\}$
2. **(580, 21021, 21029)** $\Rightarrow 21029 - 580 = 143^2$, $S_{143 \times 143} := 3090087$, $T_{20449} := 21021^2$,
 $E := \{1161, 1163, \dots, 42055, 42057\}$ or $E := \{11385, 11386, \dots, 31832, 31833\}$
3. **(876, 21307, 21325)** $\Rightarrow 21325 - 876 = 143^2$, $S_{143 \times 143} := 3174743$, $T_{20449} := 21307^2$,
 $E := \{1753, 1755, \dots, 42647, 42649\}$ or $E := \{11977, 11978, \dots, 32424, 32425\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 144

This subsection brings magic squares of order 144 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(290, 21024, 21026)** $\Rightarrow 21026 - 290 = 144^2$, $S_{144 \times 144} := 3069504$, $T_{20736} := 21024^2$,
 $E := \{581, 583, \dots, 42049, 42051\}$
2. **(584, 21312, 21320)** $\Rightarrow 21320 - 584 = 144^2$, $S_{144 \times 144} := 3154176$, $T_{20736} := 21312^2$,
 $E := \{1169, 1171, \dots, 42637, 42639\}$
3. **(882, 21600, 21618)** $\Rightarrow 21618 - 882 = 144^2$, $S_{144 \times 144} := 3240000$, $T_{20736} := 21600^2$,
 $E := \{1765, 1767, \dots, 43233, 43235\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 145

This subsection brings magic squares of order 145 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(292, 21315, 21317)** $\Rightarrow 21317 - 292 = 145^2$, $S_{145 \times 145} := 3133305$, $T_{21025} := 21315^2$,
 $E := \{585, 587, \dots, 42631, 42633\}$ or $E := \{11097, 11098, \dots, 32120, 32121\}$
2. **(588, 21605, 21613)** $\Rightarrow 21613 - 588 = 145^2$, $S_{145 \times 145} := 3219145$, $T_{21025} := 21605^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 43223, 43225\}$ or $E := \{11689, 11690, \dots, 32712, 32713\}$
3. **(888, 21895, 21913)** $\Rightarrow 21913 - 888 = 145^2$, $S_{145 \times 145} := 3306145$, $T_{21025} := 21895^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 43823, 43825\}$ or $E := \{12289, 12290, \dots, 33312, 33313\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 146

This subsection brings magic squares of order 146 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(294, 21608, 21610)** $\Rightarrow 21610 - 294 = 146^2$, $S_{146 \times 146} := 3197984$, $T_{21316} := 21608^2$,
 $E := \{589, 591, \dots, 43217, 43219\}$
2. **(592, 21900, 21908)** $\Rightarrow 21908 - 592 = 146^2$, $S_{146 \times 146} := 3285000$, $T_{21316} := 21900^2$,
 $E := \{1185, 1187, \dots, 43813, 43815\}$
3. **(894, 22192, 22210)** $\Rightarrow 22210 - 894 = 146^2$, $S_{146 \times 146} := 3373184$, $T_{21316} := 22192^2$,
 $E := \{1789, 1791, \dots, 44417, 44419\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 147

This subsection brings magic squares of order 147 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(296, 21903, 21905)** $\Rightarrow 21905 - 296 = 147^2$, $S_{147 \times 147} := 3263547$, $T_{21609} := 21903^2$,
 $E := \{593, 595, \dots, 43807, 43809\}$ or $E := \{11397, 11398, \dots, 33004, 33005\}$
2. **(596, 22197, 22205)** $\Rightarrow 22205 - 596 = 147^2$, $S_{147 \times 147} := 3351747$, $T_{21609} := 22197^2$,
 $E := \{1193, 1195, \dots, 44407, 44409\}$ or $E := \{11997, 11998, \dots, 33604, 33605\}$
3. **(900, 22491, 22509)** $\Rightarrow 22509 - 900 = 147^2$, $S_{147 \times 147} := 3441123$, $T_{21609} := 22491^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 45015, 45017\}$ or $E := \{12605, 12606, \dots, 34212, 34213\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 148

This subsection brings magic squares of order 148 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(298, 22200, 22202)** $\Rightarrow 22202 - 298 = 148^2$, $S_{148 \times 148} := 3330000$, $T_{21904} := 22200^2$,
 $E := \{597, 599, \dots, 44401, 44403\}$
2. **(600, 22496, 22504)** $\Rightarrow 22504 - 600 = 148^2$, $S_{148 \times 148} := 3419392$, $T_{21904} := 22496^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 45005, 45007\}$
3. **(906, 22792, 22810)** $\Rightarrow 22810 - 906 = 148^2$, $S_{148 \times 148} := 3509968$, $T_{21904} := 22792^2$,
 $E := \{1813, 1815, \dots, 45617, 45619\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 149

This subsection brings magic squares of order 149 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(300, 22499, 22501)** $\Rightarrow 22501 - 300 = 149^2$, $S_{149 \times 149} := 3397349$, $T_{22201} := 22499^2$,
 $E := \{601, 603, \dots, 44999, 45001\}$ or $E := \{11701, 11702, \dots, 33900, 33901\}$
2. **(604, 22797, 22805)** $\Rightarrow 22805 - 604 = 149^2$, $S_{149 \times 149} := 3487941$, $T_{22201} := 22797^2$,
 $E := \{1209, 1211, \dots, 45607, 45609\}$ or $E := \{12309, 12310, \dots, 34508, 34509\}$
3. **(912, 23095, 23113)** $\Rightarrow 23113 - 912 = 149^2$, $S_{149 \times 149} := 3579725$, $T_{22201} := 23095^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 46223, 46225\}$ or $E := \{12925, 12926, \dots, 35124, 35125\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 150

This subsection brings magic squares of order 150 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(302, 22800, 22802)** $\Rightarrow 22802 - 302 = 150^2$, $S_{150 \times 150} := 3465600$, $T_{22500} := 22800^2$,
 $E := \{605, 607, \dots, 45601, 45603\}$
2. **(608, 23100, 23108)** $\Rightarrow 23108 - 608 = 150^2$, $S_{150 \times 150} := 3557400$, $T_{22500} := 23100^2$,
 $E := \{1217, 1219, \dots, 46213, 46215\}$
3. **(918, 23400, 23418)** $\Rightarrow 23418 - 918 = 150^2$, $S_{150 \times 150} := 3650400$, $T_{22500} := 23400^2$,
 $E := \{1837, 1839, \dots, 46833, 46835\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 151

This subsection brings magic squares of order 151 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(304, 23103, 23105)** $\Rightarrow 23105 - 304 = 151^2$, $S_{151 \times 151} := 3534759$, $T_{22801} := 23103^2$,
 $E := \{609, 611, \dots, 46207, 46209\}$ or $E := \{12009, 12010, \dots, 34808, 34809\}$
2. **(612, 23405, 23413)** $\Rightarrow 23413 - 612 = 151^2$, $S_{151 \times 151} := 3627775$, $T_{22801} := 23405^2$,
 $E := \{1225, 1227, \dots, 46823, 46825\}$ or $E := \{12625, 12626, \dots, 35424, 35425\}$

3. **(924, 23707, 23725)** $\Rightarrow 23725 - 924 = 151^2$, $S_{151 \times 151} := 3721999$, $T_{22801} := 23707^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 47447, 47449\}$ or $E := \{13249, 13250, \dots, 36048, 36049\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 152

This subsection brings magic squares of order 152 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(306, 23408, 23410)** $\Rightarrow 23410 - 306 = 152^2$, $S_{152 \times 152} := 3604832$, $T_{23104} := 23408^2$,
 $E := \{613, 615, \dots, 46817, 46819\}$
2. **(616, 23712, 23720)** $\Rightarrow 23720 - 616 = 152^2$, $S_{152 \times 152} := 3699072$, $T_{23104} := 23712^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 47437, 47439\}$
3. **(930, 24016, 24034)** $\Rightarrow 24034 - 930 = 152^2$, $S_{152 \times 152} := 3794528$, $T_{23104} := 24016^2$,
 $E := \{1861, 1863, \dots, 48065, 48067\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 153

This subsection brings magic squares of order 153 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(308, 23715, 23717)** $\Rightarrow 23717 - 308 = 153^2$, $S_{153 \times 153} := 3675825$, $T_{23409} := 23715^2$,
 $E := \{617, 619, \dots, 47431, 47433\}$ or $E := \{12321, 12322, \dots, 35728, 35729\}$
2. **(620, 24021, 24029)** $\Rightarrow 24029 - 620 = 153^2$, $S_{153 \times 153} := 3771297$, $T_{23409} := 24021^2$,
 $E := \{1241, 1243, \dots, 48055, 48057\}$ or $E := \{12945, 12946, \dots, 36352, 36353\}$
3. **(936, 24327, 24345)** $\Rightarrow 24345 - 936 = 153^2$, $S_{153 \times 153} := 3867993$, $T_{23409} := 24327^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 48687, 48689\}$ or $E := \{13577, 13578, \dots, 36984, 36985\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 154

This subsection brings magic squares of order 154 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(310, 24024, 24026)** $\Rightarrow 24026 - 310 = 154^2$, $S_{154 \times 154} := 3747744$, $T_{23716} := 24024^2$,
 $E := \{621, 623, \dots, 48049, 48051\}$
2. **(624, 24332, 24340)** $\Rightarrow 24340 - 624 = 154^2$, $S_{154 \times 154} := 3844456$, $T_{23716} := 24332^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 48677, 48679\}$
3. **(942, 24640, 24658)** $\Rightarrow 24658 - 942 = 154^2$, $S_{154 \times 154} := 3942400$, $T_{23716} := 24640^2$,
 $E := \{1885, 1887, \dots, 49313, 49315\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 155

This subsection brings magic squares of order 155 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(312, 24335, 24337)** $\Rightarrow 24337 - 312 = 155^2$, $S_{155 \times 155} := 3820595$, $T_{24025} := 24335^2$,
 $E := \{625, 627, \dots, 48671, 48673\}$ or $E := \{12637, 12638, \dots, 36660, 36661\}$
2. **(628, 24645, 24653)** $\Rightarrow 24653 - 628 = 155^2$, $S_{155 \times 155} := 3918555$, $T_{24025} := 24645^2$,
 $E := \{1257, 1259, \dots, 49303, 49305\}$ or $E := \{13269, 13270, \dots, 37292, 37293\}$
3. **(948, 24955, 24973)** $\Rightarrow 24973 - 948 = 155^2$, $S_{155 \times 155} := 4017755$, $T_{24025} := 24955^2$,
 $E := \{1897, 1899, \dots, 49943, 49945\}$ or $E := \{13909, 13910, \dots, 37932, 37933\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 156

This subsection brings magic squares of order 156 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(314, 24648, 24650)** $\Rightarrow 24650 - 314 = 156^2$, $S_{156 \times 156} := 3894384$, $T_{24336} := 24648^2$,
 $E := \{629, 631, \dots, 49297, 49299\}$
2. **(632, 24960, 24968)** $\Rightarrow 24968 - 632 = 156^2$, $S_{156 \times 156} := 3993600$, $T_{24336} := 24960^2$,
 $E := \{1265, 1267, \dots, 49933, 49935\}$
3. **(954, 25272, 25290)** $\Rightarrow 25290 - 954 = 156^2$, $S_{156 \times 156} := 4094064$, $T_{24336} := 25272^2$,
 $E := \{1909, 1911, \dots, 50577, 50579\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 157

This subsection brings magic squares of order 157 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(316, 24963, 24965)** $\Rightarrow 24965 - 316 = 157^2$, $S_{157 \times 157} := 3969117$, $T_{24649} := 24963^2$,
 $E := \{633, 635, \dots, 49927, 49929\}$ or $E := \{12957, 12958, \dots, 37604, 37605\}$
2. **(636, 25277, 25285)** $\Rightarrow 25285 - 636 = 157^2$, $S_{157 \times 157} := 4069597$, $T_{24649} := 25277^2$,
 $E := \{1273, 1275, \dots, 50567, 50569\}$ or $E := \{13597, 13598, \dots, 38244, 38245\}$
3. **(960, 25591, 25609)** $\Rightarrow 25609 - 960 = 157^2$, $S_{157 \times 157} := 4171333$, $T_{24649} := 25591^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 51215, 51217\}$ or $E := \{14245, 14246, \dots, 38892, 38893\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 158

This subsection brings magic squares of order 158 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(318, 25280, 25282)** $\Rightarrow 25282 - 318 = 158^2$, $S_{158 \times 158} := 4044800$, $T_{24964} := 25280^2$,
 $E := \{637, 639, \dots, 50561, 50563\}$
2. **(640, 25596, 25604)** $\Rightarrow 25604 - 640 = 158^2$, $S_{158 \times 158} := 4146552$, $T_{24964} := 25596^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 51205, 51207\}$
3. **(966, 25912, 25930)** $\Rightarrow 25930 - 966 = 158^2$, $S_{158 \times 158} := 4249568$, $T_{24964} := 25912^2$,
 $E := \{1933, 1935, \dots, 51857, 51859\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 159

This subsection brings magic squares of order 159 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(320, 25599, 25601)** $\Rightarrow 25601 - 320 = 159^2$, $S_{159 \times 159} := 4121439$, $T_{25281} := 25599^2$,
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 51199, 51201\}$ or $E := \{13281, 13282, \dots, 38560, 38561\}$
2. **(644, 25917, 25925)** $\Rightarrow 25925 - 644 = 159^2$, $S_{159 \times 159} := 4224471$, $T_{25281} := 25917^2$,
 $E := \{1289, 1291, \dots, 51847, 51849\}$ or $E := \{13929, 13930, \dots, 39208, 39209\}$
3. **(972, 26235, 26253)** $\Rightarrow 26253 - 972 = 159^2$, $S_{159 \times 159} := 4328775$, $T_{25281} := 26235^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 52503, 52505\}$ or $E := \{14585, 14586, \dots, 39864, 39865\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 160

This subsection brings magic squares of order 160 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(322, 25920, 25922)** $\Rightarrow 25922 - 322 = 160^2$, $S_{160 \times 160} := 4199040$, $T_{25600} := 25920^2$,
 $E := \{645, 647, \dots, 51841, 51843\}$
2. **(648, 26240, 26248)** $\Rightarrow 26248 - 648 = 160^2$, $S_{160 \times 160} := 4303360$, $T_{25600} := 26240^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 52493, 52495\}$
3. **(978, 26560, 26578)** $\Rightarrow 26578 - 978 = 160^2$, $S_{160 \times 160} := 4408960$, $T_{25600} := 26560^2$,
 $E := \{1957, 1959, \dots, 53153, 53155\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 161

This subsection brings magic squares of order 161 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(324, 26243, 26245)** $\Rightarrow 26245 - 324 = 161^2$, $S_{161 \times 161} := 4277609$, $T_{25921} := 26243^2$,
 $E := \{649, 651, \dots, 52487, 52489\}$ or $E := \{13609, 13610, \dots, 39528, 39529\}$
2. **(652, 26565, 26573)** $\Rightarrow 26573 - 652 = 161^2$, $S_{161 \times 161} := 4383225$, $T_{25921} := 26565^2$,
 $E := \{1305, 1307, \dots, 53143, 53145\}$ or $E := \{14265, 14266, \dots, 40184, 40185\}$

3. **(984, 26887, 26905)** $\Rightarrow 26905 - 984 = 161^2$, $S_{161 \times 161} := 4490129$, $T_{25921} := 26887^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 53807, 53809\}$ or $E := \{14929, 14930, \dots, 40848, 40849\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 162

This subsection brings magic squares of order 162 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(326, 26568, 26570)** $\Rightarrow 26570 - 326 = 162^2$, $S_{162 \times 162} := 4357152$, $T_{26244} := 26568^2$,
 $E := \{653, 655, \dots, 53137, 53139\}$
2. **(656, 26892, 26900)** $\Rightarrow 26900 - 656 = 162^2$, $S_{162 \times 162} := 4464072$, $T_{26244} := 26892^2$,
 $E := \{1313, 1315, \dots, 53797, 53799\}$
3. **(990, 27216, 27234)** $\Rightarrow 27234 - 990 = 162^2$, $S_{162 \times 162} := 4572288$, $T_{26244} := 27216^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 54465, 54467\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 163

This subsection brings magic squares of order 163 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(328, 26895, 26897)** $\Rightarrow 26897 - 328 = 163^2$, $S_{163 \times 163} := 4437675$, $T_{26569} := 26895^2$,
 $E := \{657, 659, \dots, 53791, 53793\}$ or $E := \{13941, 13942, \dots, 40508, 40509\}$
2. **(660, 27221, 27229)** $\Rightarrow 27229 - 660 = 163^2$, $S_{163 \times 163} := 4545907$, $T_{26569} := 27221^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 54455, 54457\}$ or $E := \{14605, 14606, \dots, 41172, 41173\}$
3. **(996, 27547, 27565)** $\Rightarrow 27565 - 996 = 163^2$, $S_{163 \times 163} := 4655443$, $T_{26569} := 27547^2$,
 $E := \{1993, 1995, \dots, 55127, 55129\}$ or $E := \{15277, 15278, \dots, 41844, 41845\}$

4.31 Magic Squares of Orders 164-248: Blocks of 2

• Magic Squares of Order 164

This subsection brings magic squares of order 164 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(330, 27224, 27226)** $\Rightarrow 27226 - 330 = 164^2$, $S_{164 \times 164} := 4519184$, $T_{26896} := 27224^2$,
 $E := \{661, 663, \dots, 54449, 54451\}$
2. **(664, 27552, 27560)** $\Rightarrow 27560 - 664 = 164^2$, $S_{164 \times 164} := 4628736$, $T_{26896} := 27552^2$,
 $E := \{1329, 1331, \dots, 55117, 55119\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 165

This subsection brings magic squares of order 165 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(332, 27555, 27557)** $\Rightarrow 27557 - 332 = 165^2$, $S_{165 \times 165} := 4601685$, $T_{27225} := 27555^2$,
 $E := \{665, 667, \dots, 55111, 55113\}$ or $E := \{14277, 14278, \dots, 41500, 41501\}$
2. **(668, 27885, 27893)** $\Rightarrow 27893 - 668 = 165^2$, $S_{165 \times 165} := 4712565$, $T_{27225} := 27885^2$,
 $E := \{1337, 1339, \dots, 55783, 55785\}$ or $E := \{14949, 14950, \dots, 42172, 42173\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 166

This subsection brings magic squares of order 166 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(334, 27888, 27890)** $\Rightarrow 27890 - 334 = 166^2$, $S_{166 \times 166} := 4685184$, $T_{27556} := 27888^2$,
 $E := \{669, 671, \dots, 55777, 55779\}$
2. **(672, 28220, 28228)** $\Rightarrow 28228 - 672 = 166^2$, $S_{166 \times 166} := 4797400$, $T_{27556} := 28220^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 56453, 56455\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 167

This subsection brings magic squares of order 167 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(336, 28223, 28225)** $\Rightarrow 28225 - 336 = 167^2$, $S_{167 \times 167} := 4769687$, $T_{27889} := 28223^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 56447, 56449\}$ or $E := \{14617, 14618, \dots, 42504, 42505\}$
2. **(676, 28557, 28565)** $\Rightarrow 28565 - 676 = 167^2$, $S_{167 \times 167} := 4883247$, $T_{27889} := 28557^2$,
 $E := \{1353, 1355, \dots, 57127, 57129\}$ or $E := \{15297, 15298, \dots, 43184, 43185\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 168

This subsection brings magic squares of order 168 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(338, 28560, 28562)** $\Rightarrow 28562 - 338 = 168^2$, $S_{168 \times 168} := 4855200$, $T_{28224} := 28560^2$,
 $E := \{677, 679, \dots, 57121, 57123\}$
2. **(680, 28896, 28904)** $\Rightarrow 28904 - 680 = 168^2$, $S_{168 \times 168} := 4970112$, $T_{28224} := 28896^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 57805, 57807\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 169

This subsection brings magic squares of order 169 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(340, 28899, 28901)** $\Rightarrow 28901 - 340 = 169^2$, $S_{169 \times 169} := 4941729$, $T_{28561} := 28899^2$,
 $E := \{681, 683, \dots, 57799, 57801\}$ or $E := \{14961, 14962, \dots, 43520, 43521\}$
2. **(684, 29237, 29245)** $\Rightarrow 29245 - 684 = 169^2$, $S_{169 \times 169} := 5058001$, $T_{28561} := 29237^2$,
 $E := \{1369, 1371, \dots, 58487, 58489\}$ or $E := \{15649, 15650, \dots, 44208, 44209\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 170

This subsection brings magic squares of order 170 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(342, 29240, 29242)** $\Rightarrow 29242 - 342 = 170^2$, $S_{170 \times 170} := 5029280$, $T_{28900} := 29240^2$,
 $E := \{685, 687, \dots, 58481, 58483\}$
2. **(688, 29580, 29588)** $\Rightarrow 29588 - 688 = 170^2$, $S_{170 \times 170} := 5146920$, $T_{28900} := 29580^2$,
 $E := \{1377, 1379, \dots, 59173, 59175\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 171

This subsection brings magic squares of order 171 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(344, 29583, 29585)** $\Rightarrow 29585 - 344 = 171^2$, $S_{171 \times 171} := 5117859$, $T_{29241} := 29583^2$,
 $E := \{689, 691, \dots, 59167, 59169\}$ or $E := \{15309, 15310, \dots, 44548, 44549\}$
2. **(692, 29925, 29933)** $\Rightarrow 29933 - 692 = 171^2$, $S_{171 \times 171} := 5236875$, $T_{29241} := 29925^2$,
 $E := \{1385, 1387, \dots, 59863, 59865\}$ or $E := \{16005, 16006, \dots, 45244, 45245\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 172

This subsection brings magic squares of order 172 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(346, 29928, 29930)** $\Rightarrow 29930 - 346 = 172^2$, $S_{172 \times 172} := 5207472$, $T_{29584} := 29928^2$,
 $E := \{693, 695, \dots, 59857, 59859\}$
2. **(696, 30272, 30280)** $\Rightarrow 30280 - 696 = 172^2$, $S_{172 \times 172} := 5327872$, $T_{29584} := 30272^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 60557, 60559\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 173

This subsection brings magic squares of order 173 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(348, 30275, 30277)** $\Rightarrow 30277 - 348 = 173^2$, $S_{173 \times 173} := 5298125$, $T_{29929} := 30275^2$,
 $E := \{697, 699, \dots, 60551, 60553\}$ or $E := \{15661, 15662, \dots, 45588, 45589\}$
2. **(700, 30621, 30629)** $\Rightarrow 30629 - 700 = 173^2$, $S_{173 \times 173} := 5419917$, $T_{29929} := 30621^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 61255, 61257\}$ or $E := \{16365, 16366, \dots, 46292, 46293\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 174

This subsection brings magic squares of order 174 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(350, 30624, 30626)** $\Rightarrow 30626 - 350 = 174^2$, $S_{174 \times 174} := 5389824$, $T_{30276} := 30624^2$,
 $E := \{701, 703, \dots, 61249, 61251\}$
2. **(704, 30972, 30980)** $\Rightarrow 30980 - 704 = 174^2$, $S_{174 \times 174} := 5513016$, $T_{30276} := 30972^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 61957, 61959\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 175

This subsection brings magic squares of order 175 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(352, 30975, 30977)** $\Rightarrow 30977 - 352 = 175^2$, $S_{175 \times 175} := 5482575$, $T_{30625} := 30975^2$,
 $E := \{705, 707, \dots, 61951, 61953\}$ or $E := \{16017, 16018, \dots, 46640, 46641\}$
2. **(708, 31325, 31333)** $\Rightarrow 31333 - 708 = 175^2$, $S_{175 \times 175} := 5607175$, $T_{30625} := 31325^2$,
 $E := \{1417, 1419, \dots, 62663, 62665\}$ or $E := \{16729, 16730, \dots, 47352, 47353\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 176

This subsection brings magic squares of order 176 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(354, 31328, 31330)** $\Rightarrow 31330 - 354 = 176^2$, $S_{176 \times 176} := 5576384$, $T_{30976} := 31328^2$,
 $E := \{709, 711, \dots, 62657, 62659\}$
2. **(712, 31680, 31688)** $\Rightarrow 31688 - 712 = 176^2$, $S_{176 \times 176} := 5702400$, $T_{30976} := 31680^2$,
 $E := \{1425, 1427, \dots, 63373, 63375\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 177

This subsection brings magic squares of order 177 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(356, 31683, 31685)** $\Rightarrow 31685 - 356 = 177^2$, $S_{177 \times 177} := 5671257$, $T_{31329} := 31683^2$,
 $E := \{713, 715, \dots, 63367, 63369\}$ or $E := \{16377, 16378, \dots, 47704, 47705\}$
2. **(716, 32037, 32045)** $\Rightarrow 32045 - 716 = 177^2$, $S_{177 \times 177} := 5798697$, $T_{31329} := 32037^2$,
 $E := \{1433, 1435, \dots, 64087, 64089\}$ or $E := \{17097, 17098, \dots, 48424, 48425\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 178

This subsection brings magic squares of order 178 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(358, 32040, 32042)** $\Rightarrow 32042 - 358 = 178^2$, $S_{178 \times 178} := 5767200$, $T_{31684} := 32040^2$,
 $E := \{717, 719, \dots, 64081, 64083\}$
2. **(720, 32396, 32404)** $\Rightarrow 32404 - 720 = 178^2$, $S_{178 \times 178} := 5896072$, $T_{31684} := 32396^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 64805, 64807\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 179

This subsection brings magic squares of order 179 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(360, 32399, 32401)** $\Rightarrow 32401 - 360 = 179^2$, $S_{179 \times 179} := 5864219$, $T_{32041} := 32399^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 64799, 64801\}$ or $E := \{16741, 16742, \dots, 48780, 48781\}$
2. **(724, 32757, 32765)** $\Rightarrow 32765 - 724 = 179^2$, $S_{179 \times 179} := 5994531$, $T_{32041} := 32757^2$,
 $E := \{1449, 1451, \dots, 65527, 65529\}$ or $E := \{17469, 17470, \dots, 49508, 49509\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 180

This subsection brings magic squares of order 180 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(362, 32760, 32762)** $\Rightarrow 32762 - 362 = 180^2$, $S_{180 \times 180} := 5962320$, $T_{32400} := 32760^2$,
 $E := \{725, 727, \dots, 65521, 65523\}$
2. **(728, 33120, 33128)** $\Rightarrow 33128 - 728 = 180^2$, $S_{180 \times 180} := 6094080$, $T_{32400} := 33120^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 66253, 66255\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 181

This subsection brings magic squares of order 181 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(364, 33123, 33125)** $\Rightarrow 33125 - 364 = 181^2$, $S_{181 \times 181} := 6061509$, $T_{32761} := 33123^2$,
 $E := \{729, 731, \dots, 66247, 66249\}$ or $E := \{17109, 17110, \dots, 49868, 49869\}$
2. **(732, 33485, 33493)** $\Rightarrow 33493 - 732 = 181^2$, $S_{181 \times 181} := 6194725$, $T_{32761} := 33485^2$,
 $E := \{1465, 1467, \dots, 66983, 66985\}$ or $E := \{17845, 17846, \dots, 50604, 50605\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 182

This subsection brings magic squares of order 182 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(366, 33488, 33490)** $\Rightarrow 33490 - 366 = 182^2$, $S_{182 \times 182} := 6161792$, $T_{33124} := 33488^2$,
 $E := \{733, 735, \dots, 66977, 66979\}$
2. **(736, 33852, 33860)** $\Rightarrow 33860 - 736 = 182^2$, $S_{182 \times 182} := 6296472$, $T_{33124} := 33852^2$,
 $E := \{1473, 1475, \dots, 67717, 67719\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 183

This subsection brings magic squares of order 183 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(368, 33855, 33857)** $\Rightarrow 33857 - 368 = 183^2$, $S_{183 \times 183} := 6263175$, $T_{33489} := 33855^2$,
 $E := \{737, 739, \dots, 67711, 67713\}$ or $E := \{17481, 17482, \dots, 50968, 50969\}$
2. **(740, 34221, 34229)** $\Rightarrow 34229 - 740 = 183^2$, $S_{183 \times 183} := 6399327$, $T_{33489} := 34221^2$,
 $E := \{1481, 1483, \dots, 68455, 68457\}$ or $E := \{18225, 18226, \dots, 51712, 51713\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 184

This subsection brings magic squares of order 184 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(370, 34224, 34226)** $\Rightarrow 34226 - 370 = 184^2$, $S_{184 \times 184} := 6365664$, $T_{33856} := 34224^2$,
 $E := \{741, 743, \dots, 68449, 68451\}$
2. **(744, 34592, 34600)** $\Rightarrow 34600 - 744 = 184^2$, $S_{184 \times 184} := 6503296$, $T_{33856} := 34592^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 69197, 69199\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 185

This subsection brings magic squares of order 185 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(372, 34595, 34597)** $\Rightarrow 34597 - 372 = 185^2$, $S_{185 \times 185} := 6469265$, $T_{34225} := 34595^2$,
 $E := \{745, 747, \dots, 69191, 69193\}$ or $E := \{17857, 17858, \dots, 52080, 52081\}$
2. **(748, 34965, 34973)** $\Rightarrow 34973 - 748 = 185^2$, $S_{185 \times 185} := 6608385$, $T_{34225} := 34965^2$,
 $E := \{1497, 1499, \dots, 69943, 69945\}$ or $E := \{18609, 18610, \dots, 52832, 52833\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 186

This subsection brings magic squares of order 186 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(374, 34968, 34970)** $\Rightarrow 34970 - 374 = 186^2$, $S_{186 \times 186} := 6573984$, $T_{34596} := 34968^2$,
 $E := \{749, 751, \dots, 69937, 69939\}$
2. **(752, 35340, 35348)** $\Rightarrow 35348 - 752 = 186^2$, $S_{186 \times 186} := 6714600$, $T_{34596} := 35340^2$,
 $E := \{1505, 1507, \dots, 70693, 70695\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 187

This subsection brings magic squares of order 187 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(376, 35343, 35345)** $\Rightarrow 35345 - 376 = 187^2$, $S_{187 \times 187} := 6679827$, $T_{34969} := 35343^2$,
 $E := \{753, 755, \dots, 70687, 70689\}$ or $E := \{18237, 18238, \dots, 53204, 53205\}$
2. **(756, 35717, 35725)** $\Rightarrow 35725 - 756 = 187^2$, $S_{187 \times 187} := 6821947$, $T_{34969} := 35717^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 71447, 71449\}$ or $E := \{18997, 18998, \dots, 53964, 53965\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 188

This subsection brings magic squares of order 188 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(378, 35720, 35722)** $\Rightarrow 35722 - 378 = 188^2$, $S_{188 \times 188} := 6786800$, $T_{35344} := 35720^2$,
 $E := \{757, 759, \dots, 71441, 71443\}$
2. **(760, 36096, 36104)** $\Rightarrow 36104 - 760 = 188^2$, $S_{188 \times 188} := 6930432$, $T_{35344} := 36096^2$,
 $E := \{1521, 1523, \dots, 72205, 72207\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 189

This subsection brings magic squares of order 189 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(380, 36099, 36101)** $\Rightarrow 36101 - 380 = 189^2$, $S_{189 \times 189} := 6894909$, $T_{35721} := 36099^2$,
 $E := \{761, 763, \dots, 72199, 72201\}$ or $E := \{18621, 18622, \dots, 54340, 54341\}$
2. **(764, 36477, 36485)** $\Rightarrow 36485 - 764 = 189^2$, $S_{189 \times 189} := 7040061$, $T_{35721} := 36477^2$,
 $E := \{1529, 1531, \dots, 72967, 72969\}$ or $E := \{19389, 19390, \dots, 55108, 55109\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 190

This subsection brings magic squares of order 190 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(382, 36480, 36482)** $\Rightarrow 36482 - 382 = 190^2$, $S_{190 \times 190} := 7004160$, $T_{36100} := 36480^2$,
 $E := \{765, 767, \dots, 72961, 72963\}$
2. **(768, 36860, 36868)** $\Rightarrow 36868 - 768 = 190^2$, $S_{190 \times 190} := 7150840$, $T_{36100} := 36860^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 73733, 73735\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 191

This subsection brings magic squares of order 191 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(384, 36863, 36865)** $\Rightarrow 36865 - 384 = 191^2$, $S_{191 \times 191} := 7114559$, $T_{36481} := 36863^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 73727, 73729\}$ or $E := \{19009, 19010, \dots, 55488, 55489\}$
2. **(772, 37245, 37253)** $\Rightarrow 37253 - 772 = 191^2$, $S_{191 \times 191} := 7262775$, $T_{36481} := 37245^2$,
 $E := \{1545, 1547, \dots, 74503, 74505\}$ or $E := \{19785, 19786, \dots, 56264, 56265\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 192

This subsection brings magic squares of order 192 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(386, 37248, 37250)** $\Rightarrow 37250 - 386 = 192^2$, $S_{192 \times 192} := 7226112$, $T_{36864} := 37248^2$,
 $E := \{773, 775, \dots, 74497, 74499\}$
2. **(776, 37632, 37640)** $\Rightarrow 37640 - 776 = 192^2$, $S_{192 \times 192} := 7375872$, $T_{36864} := 37632^2$,
 $E := \{1553, 1555, \dots, 75277, 75279\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 193

This subsection brings magic squares of order 193 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(388, 37635, 37637)** $\Rightarrow 37637 - 388 = 193^2$, $S_{193 \times 193} := 7338825$, $T_{37249} := 37635^2$,
 $E := \{777, 779, \dots, 75271, 75273\}$ or $E := \{19401, 19402, \dots, 56648, 56649\}$
2. **(780, 38021, 38029)** $\Rightarrow 38029 - 780 = 193^2$, $S_{193 \times 193} := 7490137$, $T_{37249} := 38021^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 76055, 76057\}$ or $E := \{20185, 20186, \dots, 57432, 57433\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 194

This subsection brings magic squares of order 194 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(390, 38024, 38026)** $\Rightarrow 38026 - 390 = 194^2$, $S_{194 \times 194} := 7452704$, $T_{37636} := 38024^2$,
 $E := \{781, 783, \dots, 76049, 76051\}$
2. **(784, 38412, 38420)** $\Rightarrow 38420 - 784 = 194^2$, $S_{194 \times 194} := 7605576$, $T_{37636} := 38412^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 76837, 76839\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 195

This subsection brings magic squares of order 195 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(392, 38415, 38417)** $\Rightarrow 38417 - 392 = 195^2$, $S_{195 \times 195} := 7567755$, $T_{38025} := 38415^2$,
 $E := \{785, 787, \dots, 76831, 76833\}$ or $E := \{19797, 19798, \dots, 57820, 57821\}$
2. **(788, 38805, 38813)** $\Rightarrow 38813 - 788 = 195^2$, $S_{195 \times 195} := 7722195$, $T_{38025} := 38805^2$,
 $E := \{1577, 1579, \dots, 77623, 77625\}$ or $E := \{20589, 20590, \dots, 58612, 58613\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 196

This subsection brings magic squares of order 196 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(394, 38808, 38810)** $\Rightarrow 38810 - 394 = 196^2$, $S_{196 \times 196} := 7683984$, $T_{38416} := 38808^2$,
 $E := \{789, 791, \dots, 77617, 77619\}$
2. **(792, 39200, 39208)** $\Rightarrow 39208 - 792 = 196^2$, $S_{196 \times 196} := 7840000$, $T_{38416} := 39200^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 78413, 78415\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 197

This subsection brings magic squares of order 197 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(396, 39203, 39205)** $\Rightarrow 39205 - 396 = 197^2$, $S_{197 \times 197} := 7801397$, $T_{38809} := 39203^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 78407, 78409\}$ or $E := \{20197, 20198, \dots, 59004, 59005\}$
2. **(796, 39597, 39605)** $\Rightarrow 39605 - 796 = 197^2$, $S_{197 \times 197} := 7958997$, $T_{38809} := 39597^2$,
 $E := \{1593, 1595, \dots, 79207, 79209\}$ or $E := \{20997, 20998, \dots, 59804, 59805\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 198

This subsection brings magic squares of order 198 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(398, 39600, 39602)** $\Rightarrow 39602 - 398 = 198^2$, $S_{198 \times 198} := 7920000$, $T_{39204} := 39600^2$,
 $E := \{797, 799, \dots, 79201, 79203\}$
2. **(800, 39996, 40004)** $\Rightarrow 40004 - 800 = 198^2$, $S_{198 \times 198} := 8079192$, $T_{39204} := 39996^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 80005, 80007\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 199

This subsection brings magic squares of order 199 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(400, 39999, 40001)** $\Rightarrow 40001 - 400 = 199^2$, $S_{199 \times 199} := 8039799$, $T_{39601} := 39999^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 79999, 80001\}$ or $E := \{20601, 20602, \dots, 60200, 60201\}$
2. **(804, 40397, 40405)** $\Rightarrow 40405 - 804 = 199^2$, $S_{199 \times 199} := 8200591$, $T_{39601} := 40397^2$,
 $E := \{1609, 1611, \dots, 80807, 80809\}$ or $E := \{21409, 21410, \dots, 61008, 61009\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 200

This subsection brings magic squares of order 200 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(402, 40400, 40402)** $\Rightarrow 40402 - 402 = 200^2$, $S_{200 \times 200} := 8160800$, $T_{40000} := 40400^2$,
 $E := \{805, 807, \dots, 80801, 80803\}$
2. **(808, 40800, 40808)** $\Rightarrow 40808 - 808 = 200^2$, $S_{200 \times 200} := 8323200$, $T_{40000} := 40800^2$,
 $E := \{1617, 1619, \dots, 81613, 81615\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 201

This subsection brings magic squares of order 201 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(404, 40803, 40805)** $\Rightarrow 40805 - 404 = 201^2$, $S_{201 \times 201} := 8283009$, $T_{40401} := 40803^2$,
 $E := \{809, 811, \dots, 81607, 81609\}$ or $E := \{21009, 21010, \dots, 61408, 61409\}$
2. **(812, 41205, 41213)** $\Rightarrow 41213 - 812 = 201^2$, $S_{201 \times 201} := 8447025$, $T_{40401} := 41205^2$,
 $E := \{1625, 1627, \dots, 82423, 82425\}$ or $E := \{21825, 21826, \dots, 62224, 62225\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 202

This subsection brings magic squares of order 202 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(406, 41208, 41210)** $\Rightarrow 41210 - 406 = 202^2$, $S_{202 \times 202} := 8406432$, $T_{40804} := 41208^2$,
 $E := \{813, 815, \dots, 82417, 82419\}$
2. **(816, 41612, 41620)** $\Rightarrow 41620 - 816 = 202^2$, $S_{202 \times 202} := 8572072$, $T_{40804} := 41612^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 83237, 83239\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 203

This subsection brings magic squares of order 203 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(408, 41615, 41617)** $\Rightarrow 41617 - 408 = 203^2$, $S_{203 \times 203} := 8531075$, $T_{41209} := 41615^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 83231, 83233\}$ or $E := \{21421, 21422, \dots, 62628, 62629\}$
2. **(820, 42021, 42029)** $\Rightarrow 42029 - 820 = 203^2$, $S_{203 \times 203} := 8698347$, $T_{41209} := 42021^2$,
 $E := \{1641, 1643, \dots, 84055, 84057\}$ or $E := \{22245, 22246, \dots, 63452, 63453\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 204

This subsection brings magic squares of order 204 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(410, 42024, 42026)** $\Rightarrow 42026 - 410 = 204^2$, $S_{204 \times 204} := 8656944$, $T_{41616} := 42024^2$,
 $E := \{821, 823, \dots, 84049, 84051\}$
2. **(824, 42432, 42440)** $\Rightarrow 42440 - 824 = 204^2$, $S_{204 \times 204} := 8825856$, $T_{41616} := 42432^2$,
 $E := \{1649, 1651, \dots, 84877, 84879\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 205

This subsection brings magic squares of order 205 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(412, 42435, 42437)** $\Rightarrow 42437 - 412 = 205^2$, $S_{205 \times 205} := 8784045$, $T_{42025} := 42435^2$,
 $E := \{825, 827, \dots, 84871, 84873\}$ or $E := \{21837, 21838, \dots, 63860, 63861\}$
2. **(828, 42845, 42853)** $\Rightarrow 42853 - 828 = 205^2$, $S_{205 \times 205} := 8954605$, $T_{42025} := 42845^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 85703, 85705\}$ or $E := \{22669, 22670, \dots, 64692, 64693\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 206

This subsection brings magic squares of order 206 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(414, 42848, 42850)** $\Rightarrow 42850 - 414 = 206^2$, $S_{206 \times 206} := 8912384$, $T_{42436} := 42848^2$,
 $E := \{829, 831, \dots, 85697, 85699\}$
2. **(832, 43260, 43268)** $\Rightarrow 43268 - 832 = 206^2$, $S_{206 \times 206} := 9084600$, $T_{42436} := 43260^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 86533, 86535\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 207

This subsection brings magic squares of order 207 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(416, 43263, 43265)** $\Rightarrow 43265 - 416 = 207^2$, $S_{207 \times 207} := 9041967$, $T_{42849} := 43263^2$,
 $E := \{833, 835, \dots, 86527, 86529\}$ or $E := \{22257, 22258, \dots, 65104, 65105\}$
2. **(836, 43677, 43685)** $\Rightarrow 43685 - 836 = 207^2$, $S_{207 \times 207} := 9215847$, $T_{42849} := 43677^2$,
 $E := \{1673, 1675, \dots, 87367, 87369\}$ or $E := \{23097, 23098, \dots, 65944, 65945\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 208

This subsection brings magic squares of order 208 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(418, 43680, 43682)** $\Rightarrow 43682 - 418 = 208^2$, $S_{208 \times 208} := 9172800$, $T_{43264} := 43680^2$,
 $E := \{837, 839, \dots, 87361, 87363\}$
2. **(840, 44096, 44104)** $\Rightarrow 44104 - 840 = 208^2$, $S_{208 \times 208} := 9348352$, $T_{43264} := 44096^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 88205, 88207\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 209

This subsection brings magic squares of order 209 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(420, 44099, 44101)** $\Rightarrow 44101 - 420 = 209^2$, $S_{209 \times 209} := 9304889$, $T_{43681} := 44099^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 88199, 88201\}$ or $E := \{22681, 22682, \dots, 66360, 66361\}$
2. **(844, 44517, 44525)** $\Rightarrow 44525 - 844 = 209^2$, $S_{209 \times 209} := 9482121$, $T_{43681} := 44517^2$,
 $E := \{1689, 1691, \dots, 89047, 89049\}$ or $E := \{23529, 23530, \dots, 67208, 67209\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 210

This subsection brings magic squares of order 210 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(422, 44520, 44522)** $\Rightarrow 44522 - 422 = 210^2$, $S_{210 \times 210} := 9438240$, $T_{44100} := 44520^2$,
 $E := \{845, 847, \dots, 89041, 89043\}$
2. **(848, 44940, 44948)** $\Rightarrow 44948 - 848 = 210^2$, $S_{210 \times 210} := 9617160$, $T_{44100} := 44940^2$,
 $E := \{1697, 1699, \dots, 89893, 89895\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 211

This subsection brings magic squares of order 211 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(424, 44943, 44945)** $\Rightarrow 44945 - 424 = 211^2$, $S_{211 \times 211} := 9572859$, $T_{44521} := 44943^2$,
 $E := \{849, 851, \dots, 89887, 89889\}$ or $E := \{23109, 23110, \dots, 67628, 67629\}$
2. **(852, 45365, 45373)** $\Rightarrow 45373 - 852 = 211^2$, $S_{211 \times 211} := 9753475$, $T_{44521} := 45365^2$,
 $E := \{1705, 1707, \dots, 90743, 90745\}$ or $E := \{23965, 23966, \dots, 68484, 68485\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 212

This subsection brings magic squares of order 212 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(426, 45368, 45370)** $\Rightarrow 45370 - 426 = 212^2$, $S_{212 \times 212} := 9708752$, $T_{44944} := 45368^2$,
 $E := \{853, 855, \dots, 90737, 90739\}$
2. **(856, 45792, 45800)** $\Rightarrow 45800 - 856 = 212^2$, $S_{212 \times 212} := 9891072$, $T_{44944} := 45792^2$,
 $E := \{1713, 1715, \dots, 91597, 91599\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 213

This subsection brings magic squares of order 213 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(428, 45795, 45797)** $\Rightarrow 45797 - 428 = 213^2$, $S_{213 \times 213} := 9845925$, $T_{45369} := 45795^2$,
 $E := \{857, 859, \dots, 91591, 91593\}$ or $E := \{23541, 23542, \dots, 68908, 68909\}$
2. **(860, 46221, 46229)** $\Rightarrow 46229 - 860 = 213^2$, $S_{213 \times 213} := 10029957$, $T_{45369} := 46221^2$,
 $E := \{1721, 1723, \dots, 92455, 92457\}$ or $E := \{24405, 24406, \dots, 69772, 69773\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 214

This subsection brings magic squares of order 214 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(430, 46224, 46226)** $\Rightarrow 46226 - 430 = 214^2$, $S_{214 \times 214} := 9984384$, $T_{45796} := 46224^2$,
 $E := \{861, 863, \dots, 92449, 92451\}$
2. **(864, 46652, 46660)** $\Rightarrow 46660 - 864 = 214^2$, $S_{214 \times 214} := 10170136$, $T_{45796} := 46652^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 93317, 93319\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 215

This subsection brings magic squares of order 215 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(432, 46655, 46657)** $\Rightarrow 46657 - 432 = 215^2$, $S_{215 \times 215} := 10124135$, $T_{46225} := 46655^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 93311, 93313\}$ or $E := \{23977, 23978, \dots, 70200, 70201\}$
2. **(868, 47085, 47093)** $\Rightarrow 47093 - 868 = 215^2$, $S_{215 \times 215} := 10311615$, $T_{46225} := 47085^2$,
 $E := \{1737, 1739, \dots, 94183, 94185\}$ or $E := \{24849, 24850, \dots, 71072, 71073\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 216

This subsection brings magic squares of order 216 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(434, 47088, 47090)** $\Rightarrow 47090 - 434 = 216^2$, $S_{216 \times 216} := 10265184$, $T_{46656} := 47088^2$,
 $E := \{869, 871, \dots, 94177, 94179\}$
2. **(872, 47520, 47528)** $\Rightarrow 47528 - 872 = 216^2$, $S_{216 \times 216} := 10454400$, $T_{46656} := 47520^2$,
 $E := \{1745, 1747, \dots, 95053, 95055\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 217

This subsection brings magic squares of order 217 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(436, 47523, 47525)** $\Rightarrow 47525 - 436 = 217^2$, $S_{217 \times 217} := 10407537$, $T_{47089} := 47523^2$,
 $E := \{873, 875, \dots, 95047, 95049\}$ or $E := \{24417, 24418, \dots, 71504, 71505\}$
2. **(876, 47957, 47965)** $\Rightarrow 47965 - 876 = 217^2$, $S_{217 \times 217} := 10598497$, $T_{47089} := 47957^2$,
 $E := \{1753, 1755, \dots, 95927, 95929\}$ or $E := \{25297, 25298, \dots, 72384, 72385\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 218

This subsection brings magic squares of order 218 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(438, 47960, 47962)** $\Rightarrow 47962 - 438 = 218^2$, $S_{218 \times 218} := 10551200$, $T_{47524} := 47960^2$,
 $E := \{877, 879, \dots, 95921, 95923\}$
2. **(880, 48396, 48404)** $\Rightarrow 48404 - 880 = 218^2$, $S_{218 \times 218} := 10743912$, $T_{47524} := 48396^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 96805, 96807\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 219

This subsection brings magic squares of order 219 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(440, 48399, 48401)** $\Rightarrow 48401 - 440 = 219^2$, $S_{219 \times 219} := 10696179$, $T_{47961} := 48399^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 96799, 96801\}$ or $E := \{24861, 24862, \dots, 72820, 72821\}$
2. **(884, 48837, 48845)** $\Rightarrow 48845 - 884 = 219^2$, $S_{219 \times 219} := 10890651$, $T_{47961} := 48837^2$,
 $E := \{1769, 1771, \dots, 97687, 97689\}$ or $E := \{25749, 25750, \dots, 73708, 73709\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 220

This subsection brings magic squares of order 220 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(442, 48840, 48842)** $\Rightarrow 48842 - 442 = 220^2$, $S_{220 \times 220} := 10842480$, $T_{48400} := 48840^2$,
 $E := \{885, 887, \dots, 97681, 97683\}$
2. **(888, 49280, 49288)** $\Rightarrow 49288 - 888 = 220^2$, $S_{220 \times 220} := 11038720$, $T_{48400} := 49280^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 98573, 98575\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 221

This subsection brings magic squares of order 221 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(444, 49283, 49285)** $\Rightarrow 49285 - 444 = 221^2$, $S_{221 \times 221} := 10990109$, $T_{48841} := 49283^2$,
 $E := \{889, 891, \dots, 98567, 98569\}$ or $E := \{25309, 25310, \dots, 74148, 74149\}$
2. **(892, 49725, 49733)** $\Rightarrow 49733 - 892 = 221^2$, $S_{221 \times 221} := 11188125$, $T_{48841} := 49725^2$,
 $E := \{1785, 1787, \dots, 99463, 99465\}$ or $E := \{26205, 26206, \dots, 75044, 75045\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 222

This subsection brings magic squares of order 222 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(446, 49728, 49730)** $\Rightarrow 49730 - 446 = 222^2$, $S_{222 \times 222} := 11139072$, $T_{49284} := 49728^2$,
 $E := \{893, 895, \dots, 99457, 99459\}$
2. **(896, 50172, 50180)** $\Rightarrow 50180 - 896 = 222^2$, $S_{222 \times 222} := 11338872$, $T_{49284} := 50172^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 100357, 100359\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 223

This subsection brings magic squares of order 223 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(448, 50175, 50177)** $\Rightarrow 50177 - 448 = 223^2$, $S_{223 \times 223} := 11289375$, $T_{49729} := 50175^2$,
 $E := \{897, 899, \dots, 100351, 100353\}$ or $E := \{25761, 25762, \dots, 75488, 75489\}$
2. **(900, 50621, 50629)** $\Rightarrow 50629 - 900 = 223^2$, $S_{223 \times 223} := 11490967$, $T_{49729} := 50621^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 101255, 101257\}$ or $E := \{26665, 26666, \dots, 76392, 76393\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 224

This subsection brings magic squares of order 224 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(450, 50624, 50626)** $\Rightarrow 50626 - 450 = 224^2$, $S_{224 \times 224} := 11441024$, $T_{50176} := 50624^2$,
 $E := \{901, 903, \dots, 101249, 101251\}$
2. **(904, 51072, 51080)** $\Rightarrow 51080 - 904 = 224^2$, $S_{224 \times 224} := 11644416$, $T_{50176} := 51072^2$,
 $E := \{1809, 1811, \dots, 102157, 102159\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 225

This subsection brings magic squares of order 225 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(452, 51075, 51077)** $\Rightarrow 51077 - 452 = 225^2$, $S_{225 \times 225} := 11594025$, $T_{50625} := 51075^2$,
 $E := \{905, 907, \dots, 102151, 102153\}$ or $E := \{26217, 26218, \dots, 76840, 76841\}$
2. **(908, 51525, 51533)** $\Rightarrow 51533 - 908 = 225^2$, $S_{225 \times 225} := 11799225$, $T_{50625} := 51525^2$,
 $E := \{1817, 1819, \dots, 103063, 103065\}$ or $E := \{27129, 27130, \dots, 77752, 77753\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 226

This subsection brings magic squares of order 226 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(454, 51528, 51530)** $\Rightarrow 51530 - 454 = 226^2$, $S_{226 \times 226} := 11748384$, $T_{51076} := 51528^2$,
 $E := \{909, 911, \dots, 103057, 103059\}$
2. **(912, 51980, 51988)** $\Rightarrow 51988 - 912 = 226^2$, $S_{226 \times 226} := 11955400$, $T_{51076} := 51980^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 103973, 103975\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 227

This subsection brings magic squares of order 227 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(456, 51983, 51985)** $\Rightarrow 51985 - 456 = 227^2$, $S_{227 \times 227} := 11904107$, $T_{51529} := 51983^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 103967, 103969\}$ or $E := \{26677, 26678, \dots, 78204, 78205\}$
2. **(916, 52437, 52445)** $\Rightarrow 52445 - 916 = 227^2$, $S_{227 \times 227} := 12112947$, $T_{51529} := 52437^2$,
 $E := \{1833, 1835, \dots, 104887, 104889\}$ or $E := \{27597, 27598, \dots, 79124, 79125\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 228

This subsection brings magic squares of order 228 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(458, 52440, 52442)** $\Rightarrow 52442 - 458 = 228^2$, $S_{228 \times 228} := 12061200$, $T_{51984} := 52440^2$,
 $E := \{917, 919, \dots, 104881, 104883\}$
2. **(920, 52896, 52904)** $\Rightarrow 52904 - 920 = 228^2$, $S_{228 \times 228} := 12271872$, $T_{51984} := 52896^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 105805, 105807\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 229

This subsection brings magic squares of order 229 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(460, 52899, 52901)** $\Rightarrow 52901 - 460 = 229^2$, $S_{229 \times 229} := 12219669$, $T_{52441} := 52899^2$,
 $E := \{921, 923, \dots, 105799, 105801\}$ or $E := \{27141, 27142, \dots, 79580, 79581\}$
2. **(924, 53357, 53365)** $\Rightarrow 53365 - 924 = 229^2$, $S_{229 \times 229} := 12432181$, $T_{52441} := 53357^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 106727, 106729\}$ or $E := \{28069, 28070, \dots, 80508, 80509\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 230

This subsection brings magic squares of order 230 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(462, 53360, 53362)** $\Rightarrow 53362 - 462 = 230^2$, $S_{230 \times 230} := 12379520$, $T_{52900} := 53360^2$,
 $E := \{925, 927, \dots, 106721, 106723\}$
2. **(928, 53820, 53828)** $\Rightarrow 53828 - 928 = 230^2$, $S_{230 \times 230} := 12593880$, $T_{52900} := 53820^2$,
 $E := \{1857, 1859, \dots, 107653, 107655\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 231

This subsection brings magic squares of order 231 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(464, 53823, 53825)** $\Rightarrow 53825 - 464 = 231^2$, $S_{231 \times 231} := 12540759$, $T_{53361} := 53823^2$,
 $E := \{929, 931, \dots, 107647, 107649\}$ or $E := \{27609, 27610, \dots, 80968, 80969\}$
2. **(932, 54285, 54293)** $\Rightarrow 54293 - 932 = 231^2$, $S_{231 \times 231} := 12756975$, $T_{53361} := 54285^2$,
 $E := \{1865, 1867, \dots, 108583, 108585\}$ or $E := \{28545, 28546, \dots, 81904, 81905\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 232

This subsection brings magic squares of order 232 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(466, 54288, 54290)** $\Rightarrow 54290 - 466 = 232^2$, $S_{232 \times 232} := 12703392$, $T_{53824} := 54288^2$,
 $E := \{933, 935, \dots, 108577, 108579\}$
2. **(936, 54752, 54760)** $\Rightarrow 54760 - 936 = 232^2$, $S_{232 \times 232} := 12921472$, $T_{53824} := 54752^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 109517, 109519\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 233

This subsection brings magic squares of order 233 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(468, 54755, 54757)** $\Rightarrow 54757 - 468 = 233^2$, $S_{233 \times 233} := 12867425$, $T_{54289} := 54755^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 109511, 109513\}$ or $E := \{28081, 28082, \dots, 82368, 82369\}$
2. **(940, 55221, 55229)** $\Rightarrow 55229 - 940 = 233^2$, $S_{233 \times 233} := 13087377$, $T_{54289} := 55221^2$,
 $E := \{1881, 1883, \dots, 110455, 110457\}$ or $E := \{29025, 29026, \dots, 83312, 83313\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 234

This subsection brings magic squares of order 234 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(470, 55224, 55226)** $\Rightarrow 55226 - 470 = 234^2$, $S_{234 \times 234} := 13032864$, $T_{54756} := 55224^2$,
 $E := \{941, 943, \dots, 110449, 110451\}$
2. **(944, 55692, 55700)** $\Rightarrow 55700 - 944 = 234^2$, $S_{234 \times 234} := 13254696$, $T_{54756} := 55692^2$,
 $E := \{1889, 1891, \dots, 111397, 111399\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 235

This subsection brings magic squares of order 235 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(472, 55695, 55697)** $\Rightarrow 55697 - 472 = 235^2$, $S_{235 \times 235} := 13199715$, $T_{55225} := 55695^2$,
 $E := \{945, 947, \dots, 111391, 111393\}$ or $E := \{28557, 28558, \dots, 83780, 83781\}$
2. **(948, 56165, 56173)** $\Rightarrow 56173 - 948 = 235^2$, $S_{235 \times 235} := 13423435$, $T_{55225} := 56165^2$,
 $E := \{1897, 1899, \dots, 112343, 112345\}$ or $E := \{29509, 29510, \dots, 84732, 84733\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 236

This subsection brings magic squares of order 236 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(474, 56168, 56170)** $\Rightarrow 56170 - 474 = 236^2$, $S_{236 \times 236} := 13367984$, $T_{55696} := 56168^2$,
 $E := \{949, 951, \dots, 112337, 112339\}$
2. **(952, 56640, 56648)** $\Rightarrow 56648 - 952 = 236^2$, $S_{236 \times 236} := 13593600$, $T_{55696} := 56640^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 113293, 113295\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 237

This subsection brings magic squares of order 237 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(476, 56643, 56645)** $\Rightarrow 56645 - 476 = 237^2$, $S_{237 \times 237} := 13537677$, $T_{56169} := 56643^2$,
 $E := \{953, 955, \dots, 113287, 113289\}$ or $E := \{29037, 29038, \dots, 85204, 85205\}$
2. **(956, 57117, 57125)** $\Rightarrow 57125 - 956 = 237^2$, $S_{237 \times 237} := 13765197$, $T_{56169} := 57117^2$,
 $E := \{1913, 1915, \dots, 114247, 114249\}$ or $E := \{29997, 29998, \dots, 86164, 86165\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 238

This subsection brings magic squares of order 238 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(478, 57120, 57122)** $\Rightarrow 57122 - 478 = 238^2$, $S_{238 \times 238} := 13708800$, $T_{56644} := 57120^2$,
 $E := \{957, 959, \dots, 114241, 114243\}$
2. **(960, 57596, 57604)** $\Rightarrow 57604 - 960 = 238^2$, $S_{238 \times 238} := 13938232$, $T_{56644} := 57596^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 115205, 115207\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 239

This subsection brings magic squares of order 239 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(480, 57599, 57601)** $\Rightarrow 57601 - 480 = 239^2$, $S_{239 \times 239} := 13881359$, $T_{57121} := 57599^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 115199, 115201\}$ or $E := \{29521, 29522, \dots, 86640, 86641\}$
2. **(964, 58077, 58085)** $\Rightarrow 58085 - 964 = 239^2$, $S_{239 \times 239} := 14112711$, $T_{57121} := 58077^2$,
 $E := \{1929, 1931, \dots, 116167, 116169\}$ or $E := \{30489, 30490, \dots, 87608, 87609\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 240

This subsection brings magic squares of order 240 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(482, 58080, 58082)** $\Rightarrow 58082 - 482 = 240^2$, $S_{240 \times 240} := 14055360$, $T_{57600} := 58080^2$,
 $E := \{965, 967, \dots, 116161, 116163\}$
2. **(968, 58560, 58568)** $\Rightarrow 58568 - 968 = 240^2$, $S_{240 \times 240} := 14288640$, $T_{57600} := 58560^2$,
 $E := \{1937, 1939, \dots, 117133, 117135\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 241

This subsection brings magic squares of order 241 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(484, 58563, 58565)** $\Rightarrow 58565 - 484 = 241^2$, $S_{241 \times 241} := 14230809$, $T_{58081} := 58563^2$,
 $E := \{969, 971, \dots, 117127, 117129\}$ or $E := \{30009, 30010, \dots, 88088, 88089\}$
2. **(972, 59045, 59053)** $\Rightarrow 59053 - 972 = 241^2$, $S_{241 \times 241} := 14466025$, $T_{58081} := 59045^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 118103, 118105\}$ or $E := \{30985, 30986, \dots, 89064, 89065\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 242

This subsection brings magic squares of order 242 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(486, 59048, 59050)** $\Rightarrow 59050 - 486 = 242^2$, $S_{242 \times 242} := 14407712$, $T_{58564} := 59048^2$,
 $E := \{973, 975, \dots, 118097, 118099\}$
2. **(976, 59532, 59540)** $\Rightarrow 59540 - 976 = 242^2$, $S_{242 \times 242} := 14644872$, $T_{58564} := 59532^2$,
 $E := \{1953, 1955, \dots, 119077, 119079\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 243

This subsection brings magic squares of order 243 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(488, 59535, 59537)** $\Rightarrow 59537 - 488 = 243^2$, $S_{243 \times 243} := 14586075$, $T_{59049} := 59535^2$,
 $E := \{977, 979, \dots, 119071, 119073\}$ or $E := \{30501, 30502, \dots, 89548, 89549\}$
2. **(980, 60021, 60029)** $\Rightarrow 60029 - 980 = 243^2$, $S_{243 \times 243} := 14825187$, $T_{59049} := 60021^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 120055, 120057\}$ or $E := \{31485, 31486, \dots, 90532, 90533\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 244

This subsection brings magic squares of order 244 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(490, 60024, 60026)** $\Rightarrow 60026 - 490 = 244^2$, $S_{244 \times 244} := 14765904$, $T_{59536} := 60024^2$,
 $E := \{981, 983, \dots, 120049, 120051\}$
2. **(984, 60512, 60520)** $\Rightarrow 60520 - 984 = 244^2$, $S_{244 \times 244} := 15006976$, $T_{59536} := 60512^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 121037, 121039\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 245

This subsection brings magic squares of order 245 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(492, 60515, 60517)** $\Rightarrow 60517 - 492 = 245^2$, $S_{245 \times 245} := 14947205$, $T_{60025} := 60515^2$,
 $E := \{985, 987, \dots, 121031, 121033\}$ or $E := \{30997, 30998, \dots, 91020, 91021\}$
2. **(988, 61005, 61013)** $\Rightarrow 61013 - 988 = 245^2$, $S_{245 \times 245} := 15190245$, $T_{60025} := 61005^2$,
 $E := \{1977, 1979, \dots, 122023, 122025\}$ or $E := \{31989, 31990, \dots, 92012, 92013\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 246

This subsection brings magic squares of order 246 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(494, 61008, 61010)** $\Rightarrow 61010 - 494 = 246^2$, $S_{246 \times 246} := 15129984$, $T_{60516} := 61008^2$,
 $E := \{989, 991, \dots, 122017, 122019\}$
2. **(992, 61500, 61508)** $\Rightarrow 61508 - 992 = 246^2$, $S_{246 \times 246} := 15375000$, $T_{60516} := 61500^2$,
 $E := \{1985, 1987, \dots, 123013, 123015\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 247

This subsection brings magic squares of order 247 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(496, 61503, 61505)** $\Rightarrow 61505 - 496 = 247^2$, $S_{247 \times 247} := 15314247$, $T_{61009} := 61503^2$,
 $E := \{993, 995, \dots, 123007, 123009\}$ or $E := \{31497, 31498, \dots, 92504, 92505\}$
2. **(996, 61997, 62005)** $\Rightarrow 62005 - 996 = 247^2$, $S_{247 \times 247} := 15561247$, $T_{61009} := 61997^2$,
 $E := \{1993, 1995, \dots, 124007, 124009\}$ or $E := \{32497, 32498, \dots, 93504, 93505\}$

• Magic Squares of Order 248

This subsection brings magic squares of order 248 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $3 \leq a \leq 1000$.

1. **(498, 62000, 62002)** $\Rightarrow 62002 - 498 = 248^2$, $S_{248 \times 248} := 15500000$, $T_{61504} := 62000^2$,
 $E := \{997, 999, \dots, 124001, 124003\}$
2. **(1000, 62496, 62504)** $\Rightarrow 62504 - 1000 = 248^2$, $S_{248 \times 248} := 15748992$, $T_{61504} := 62496^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 125005, 125007\}$

4.32 Magic Squares of Orders 249-499: Single

This subsection brings magic squares of order 249-499 generated by Pythagorean triples (a, b, c) , $500 \leq a \leq 1000$. In each case there is a single representation.

1. **(500, 62499, 62501)** $\Rightarrow 62501 - 500 = 249^2$, $S_{249 \times 249} := 15687249$, $T_{62001} := 62499^2$,
 $E := \{1001, 1003, \dots, 124999, 125001\}$ or $E := \{32001, 32002, \dots, 94000, 94001\}$
2. **(502, 63000, 63002)** $\Rightarrow 63002 - 502 = 250^2$, $S_{250 \times 250} := 15876000$, $T_{62500} := 63000^2$,
 $E := \{1005, 1007, \dots, 126001, 126003\}$
3. **(504, 63503, 63505)** $\Rightarrow 63505 - 504 = 251^2$, $S_{251 \times 251} := 16066259$, $T_{63001} := 63503^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 127007, 127009\}$ or $E := \{32509, 32510, \dots, 95508, 95509\}$
4. **(506, 64008, 64010)** $\Rightarrow 64010 - 506 = 252^2$, $S_{252 \times 252} := 16258032$, $T_{63504} := 64008^2$,
 $E := \{1013, 1015, \dots, 128017, 128019\}$
5. **(508, 64515, 64517)** $\Rightarrow 64517 - 508 = 253^2$, $S_{253 \times 253} := 16451325$, $T_{64009} := 64515^2$,
 $E := \{1017, 1019, \dots, 129031, 129033\}$ or $E := \{33021, 33022, \dots, 97028, 97029\}$
6. **(510, 65024, 65026)** $\Rightarrow 65026 - 510 = 254^2$, $S_{254 \times 254} := 16646144$, $T_{64516} := 65024^2$,
 $E := \{1021, 1023, \dots, 130049, 130051\}$
7. **(512, 65535, 65537)** $\Rightarrow 65537 - 512 = 255^2$, $S_{255 \times 255} := 16842495$, $T_{65025} := 65535^2$,
 $E := \{1025, 1027, \dots, 131071, 131073\}$ or $E := \{33537, 33538, \dots, 98560, 98561\}$
8. **(514, 66048, 66050)** $\Rightarrow 66050 - 514 = 256^2$, $S_{256 \times 256} := 17040384$, $T_{65536} := 66048^2$,
 $E := \{1029, 1031, \dots, 132097, 132099\}$
9. **(516, 66563, 66565)** $\Rightarrow 66565 - 516 = 257^2$, $S_{257 \times 257} := 17239817$, $T_{66049} := 66563^2$,
 $E := \{1033, 1035, \dots, 133127, 133129\}$ or $E := \{34057, 34058, \dots, 100104, 100105\}$
10. **(518, 67080, 67082)** $\Rightarrow 67082 - 518 = 258^2$, $S_{258 \times 258} := 17440800$, $T_{66564} := 67080^2$,
 $E := \{1037, 1039, \dots, 134161, 134163\}$
11. **(520, 67599, 67601)** $\Rightarrow 67601 - 520 = 259^2$, $S_{259 \times 259} := 17643339$, $T_{67081} := 67599^2$,
 $E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 135199, 135201\}$ or $E := \{34581, 34582, \dots, 101660, 101661\}$
12. **(522, 68120, 68122)** $\Rightarrow 68122 - 522 = 260^2$, $S_{260 \times 260} := 17847440$, $T_{67600} := 68120^2$,
 $E := \{1045, 1047, \dots, 136241, 136243\}$
13. **(524, 68643, 68645)** $\Rightarrow 68645 - 524 = 261^2$, $S_{261 \times 261} := 18053109$, $T_{68121} := 68643^2$,
 $E := \{1049, 1051, \dots, 137287, 137289\}$ or $E := \{35109, 35110, \dots, 103228, 103229\}$
14. **(526, 69168, 69170)** $\Rightarrow 69170 - 526 = 262^2$, $S_{262 \times 262} := 18260352$, $T_{68644} := 69168^2$,
 $E := \{1053, 1055, \dots, 138337, 138339\}$
15. **(528, 69695, 69697)** $\Rightarrow 69697 - 528 = 263^2$, $S_{263 \times 263} := 18469175$, $T_{69169} := 69695^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 139391, 139393\}$ or $E := \{35641, 35642, \dots, 104808, 104809\}$

16. **(530, 70224, 70226)** $\Rightarrow 70226 - 530 = 264^2$, $S_{264 \times 264} := 18679584$, $T_{69696} := 70224^2$,
 $E := \{1061, 1063, \dots, 140449, 140451\}$
17. **(532, 70755, 70757)** $\Rightarrow 70757 - 532 = 265^2$, $S_{265 \times 265} := 18891585$, $T_{70225} := 70755^2$,
 $E := \{1065, 1067, \dots, 141511, 141513\}$ or $E := \{36177, 36178, \dots, 106400, 106401\}$
18. **(534, 71288, 71290)** $\Rightarrow 71290 - 534 = 266^2$, $S_{266 \times 266} := 19105184$, $T_{70756} := 71288^2$,
 $E := \{1069, 1071, \dots, 142577, 142579\}$
19. **(536, 71823, 71825)** $\Rightarrow 71825 - 536 = 267^2$, $S_{267 \times 267} := 19320387$, $T_{71289} := 71823^2$,
 $E := \{1073, 1075, \dots, 143647, 143649\}$ or $E := \{36717, 36718, \dots, 108004, 108005\}$
20. **(538, 72360, 72362)** $\Rightarrow 72362 - 538 = 268^2$, $S_{268 \times 268} := 19537200$, $T_{71824} := 72360^2$,
 $E := \{1077, 1079, \dots, 144721, 144723\}$
21. **(540, 72899, 72901)** $\Rightarrow 72901 - 540 = 269^2$, $S_{269 \times 269} := 19755629$, $T_{72361} := 72899^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 145799, 145801\}$ or $E := \{37261, 37262, \dots, 109620, 109621\}$
22. **(542, 73440, 73442)** $\Rightarrow 73442 - 542 = 270^2$, $S_{270 \times 270} := 19975680$, $T_{72900} := 73440^2$,
 $E := \{1085, 1087, \dots, 146881, 146883\}$
23. **(544, 73983, 73985)** $\Rightarrow 73985 - 544 = 271^2$, $S_{271 \times 271} := 20197359$, $T_{73441} := 73983^2$,
 $E := \{1089, 1091, \dots, 147967, 147969\}$ or $E := \{37809, 37810, \dots, 111248, 111249\}$
24. **(546, 74528, 74530)** $\Rightarrow 74530 - 546 = 272^2$, $S_{272 \times 272} := 20420672$, $T_{73984} := 74528^2$,
 $E := \{1093, 1095, \dots, 149057, 149059\}$
25. **(548, 75075, 75077)** $\Rightarrow 75077 - 548 = 273^2$, $S_{273 \times 273} := 20645625$, $T_{74529} := 75075^2$,
 $E := \{1097, 1099, \dots, 150151, 150153\}$ or $E := \{38361, 38362, \dots, 112888, 112889\}$
26. **(550, 75624, 75626)** $\Rightarrow 75626 - 550 = 274^2$, $S_{274 \times 274} := 20872224$, $T_{75076} := 75624^2$,
 $E := \{1101, 1103, \dots, 151249, 151251\}$
27. **(552, 76175, 76177)** $\Rightarrow 76177 - 552 = 275^2$, $S_{275 \times 275} := 21100475$, $T_{75625} := 76175^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 152351, 152353\}$ or $E := \{38917, 38918, \dots, 114540, 114541\}$
28. **(554, 76728, 76730)** $\Rightarrow 76730 - 554 = 276^2$, $S_{276 \times 276} := 21330384$, $T_{76176} := 76728^2$,
 $E := \{1109, 1111, \dots, 153457, 153459\}$
29. **(556, 77283, 77285)** $\Rightarrow 77285 - 556 = 277^2$, $S_{277 \times 277} := 21561957$, $T_{76729} := 77283^2$,
 $E := \{1113, 1115, \dots, 154567, 154569\}$ or $E := \{39477, 39478, \dots, 116204, 116205\}$
30. **(558, 77840, 77842)** $\Rightarrow 77842 - 558 = 278^2$, $S_{278 \times 278} := 21795200$, $T_{77284} := 77840^2$,
 $E := \{1117, 1119, \dots, 155681, 155683\}$
31. **(560, 78399, 78401)** $\Rightarrow 78401 - 560 = 279^2$, $S_{279 \times 279} := 22030119$, $T_{77841} := 78399^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 156799, 156801\}$ or $E := \{40041, 40042, \dots, 117880, 117881\}$
32. **(562, 78960, 78962)** $\Rightarrow 78962 - 562 = 280^2$, $S_{280 \times 280} := 22266720$, $T_{78400} := 78960^2$,
 $E := \{1125, 1127, \dots, 157921, 157923\}$

33. **(564, 79523, 79525)** $\Rightarrow 79525 - 564 = 281^2$, $S_{281 \times 281} := 22505009$, $T_{78961} := 79523^2$,
 $E := \{1129, 1131, \dots, 159047, 159049\}$ or $E := \{40609, 40610, \dots, 119568, 119569\}$
34. **(566, 80088, 80090)** $\Rightarrow 80090 - 566 = 282^2$, $S_{282 \times 282} := 22744992$, $T_{79524} := 80088^2$,
 $E := \{1133, 1135, \dots, 160177, 160179\}$
35. **(568, 80655, 80657)** $\Rightarrow 80657 - 568 = 283^2$, $S_{283 \times 283} := 22986675$, $T_{80089} := 80655^2$,
 $E := \{1137, 1139, \dots, 161311, 161313\}$ or $E := \{41181, 41182, \dots, 121268, 121269\}$
36. **(570, 81224, 81226)** $\Rightarrow 81226 - 570 = 284^2$, $S_{284 \times 284} := 23230064$, $T_{80656} := 81224^2$,
 $E := \{1141, 1143, \dots, 162449, 162451\}$
37. **(572, 81795, 81797)** $\Rightarrow 81797 - 572 = 285^2$, $S_{285 \times 285} := 23475165$, $T_{81225} := 81795^2$,
 $E := \{1145, 1147, \dots, 163591, 163593\}$ or $E := \{41757, 41758, \dots, 122980, 122981\}$
38. **(574, 82368, 82370)** $\Rightarrow 82370 - 574 = 286^2$, $S_{286 \times 286} := 23721984$, $T_{81796} := 82368^2$,
 $E := \{1149, 1151, \dots, 164737, 164739\}$
39. **(576, 82943, 82945)** $\Rightarrow 82945 - 576 = 287^2$, $S_{287 \times 287} := 23970527$, $T_{82369} := 82943^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 165887, 165889\}$ or $E := \{42337, 42338, \dots, 124704, 124705\}$
40. **(578, 83520, 83522)** $\Rightarrow 83522 - 578 = 288^2$, $S_{288 \times 288} := 24220800$, $T_{82944} := 83520^2$,
 $E := \{1157, 1159, \dots, 167041, 167043\}$
41. **(580, 84099, 84101)** $\Rightarrow 84101 - 580 = 289^2$, $S_{289 \times 289} := 24472809$, $T_{83521} := 84099^2$,
 $E := \{1161, 1163, \dots, 168199, 168201\}$ or $E := \{42921, 42922, \dots, 126440, 126441\}$
42. **(582, 84680, 84682)** $\Rightarrow 84682 - 582 = 290^2$, $S_{290 \times 290} := 24726560$, $T_{84100} := 84680^2$,
 $E := \{1165, 1167, \dots, 169361, 169363\}$
43. **(584, 85263, 85265)** $\Rightarrow 85265 - 584 = 291^2$, $S_{291 \times 291} := 24982059$, $T_{84681} := 85263^2$,
 $E := \{1169, 1171, \dots, 170527, 170529\}$ or $E := \{43509, 43510, \dots, 128188, 128189\}$
44. **(586, 85848, 85850)** $\Rightarrow 85850 - 586 = 292^2$, $S_{292 \times 292} := 25239312$, $T_{85264} := 85848^2$,
 $E := \{1173, 1175, \dots, 171697, 171699\}$
45. **(588, 86435, 86437)** $\Rightarrow 86437 - 588 = 293^2$, $S_{293 \times 293} := 25498325$, $T_{85849} := 86435^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 172871, 172873\}$ or $E := \{44101, 44102, \dots, 129948, 129949\}$
46. **(590, 87024, 87026)** $\Rightarrow 87026 - 590 = 294^2$, $S_{294 \times 294} := 25759104$, $T_{86436} := 87024^2$,
 $E := \{1181, 1183, \dots, 174049, 174051\}$
47. **(592, 87615, 87617)** $\Rightarrow 87617 - 592 = 295^2$, $S_{295 \times 295} := 26021655$, $T_{87025} := 87615^2$,
 $E := \{1185, 1187, \dots, 175231, 175233\}$ or $E := \{44697, 44698, \dots, 131720, 131721\}$
48. **(594, 88208, 88210)** $\Rightarrow 88210 - 594 = 296^2$, $S_{296 \times 296} := 26285984$, $T_{87616} := 88208^2$,
 $E := \{1189, 1191, \dots, 176417, 176419\}$
49. **(596, 88803, 88805)** $\Rightarrow 88805 - 596 = 297^2$, $S_{297 \times 297} := 26552097$, $T_{88209} := 88803^2$,
 $E := \{1193, 1195, \dots, 177607, 177609\}$ or $E := \{45297, 45298, \dots, 133504, 133505\}$

50. **(598, 89400, 89402)** $\Rightarrow 89402 - 598 = 298^2$, $S_{298 \times 298} := 26820000$, $T_{88804} := 89400^2$,
 $E := \{1197, 1199, \dots, 178801, 178803\}$
51. **(600, 89999, 90001)** $\Rightarrow 90001 - 600 = 299^2$, $S_{299 \times 299} := 27089699$, $T_{89401} := 89999^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 179999, 180001\}$ or $E := \{45901, 45902, \dots, 135300, 135301\}$
52. **(602, 90600, 90602)** $\Rightarrow 90602 - 602 = 300^2$, $S_{300 \times 300} := 27361200$, $T_{90000} := 90600^2$,
 $E := \{1205, 1207, \dots, 181201, 181203\}$
53. **(604, 91203, 91205)** $\Rightarrow 91205 - 604 = 301^2$, $S_{301 \times 301} := 27634509$, $T_{90601} := 91203^2$,
 $E := \{1209, 1211, \dots, 182407, 182409\}$ or $E := \{46509, 46510, \dots, 137108, 137109\}$
54. **(606, 91808, 91810)** $\Rightarrow 91810 - 606 = 302^2$, $S_{302 \times 302} := 27909632$, $T_{91204} := 91808^2$,
 $E := \{1213, 1215, \dots, 183617, 183619\}$
55. **(608, 92415, 92417)** $\Rightarrow 92417 - 608 = 303^2$, $S_{303 \times 303} := 28186575$, $T_{91809} := 92415^2$,
 $E := \{1217, 1219, \dots, 184831, 184833\}$ or $E := \{47121, 47122, \dots, 138928, 138929\}$
56. **(610, 93024, 93026)** $\Rightarrow 93026 - 610 = 304^2$, $S_{304 \times 304} := 28465344$, $T_{92416} := 93024^2$,
 $E := \{1221, 1223, \dots, 186049, 186051\}$
57. **(612, 93635, 93637)** $\Rightarrow 93637 - 612 = 305^2$, $S_{305 \times 305} := 28745945$, $T_{93025} := 93635^2$,
 $E := \{1225, 1227, \dots, 187271, 187273\}$ or $E := \{47737, 47738, \dots, 140760, 140761\}$
58. **(614, 94248, 94250)** $\Rightarrow 94250 - 614 = 306^2$, $S_{306 \times 306} := 29028384$, $T_{93636} := 94248^2$,
 $E := \{1229, 1231, \dots, 188497, 188499\}$
59. **(616, 94863, 94865)** $\Rightarrow 94865 - 616 = 307^2$, $S_{307 \times 307} := 29312667$, $T_{94249} := 94863^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 189727, 189729\}$ or $E := \{48357, 48358, \dots, 142604, 142605\}$
60. **(618, 95480, 95482)** $\Rightarrow 95482 - 618 = 308^2$, $S_{308 \times 308} := 29598800$, $T_{94864} := 95480^2$,
 $E := \{1237, 1239, \dots, 190961, 190963\}$
61. **(620, 96099, 96101)** $\Rightarrow 96101 - 620 = 309^2$, $S_{309 \times 309} := 29886789$, $T_{95481} := 96099^2$,
 $E := \{1241, 1243, \dots, 192199, 192201\}$ or $E := \{48981, 48982, \dots, 144460, 144461\}$
62. **(622, 96720, 96722)** $\Rightarrow 96722 - 622 = 310^2$, $S_{310 \times 310} := 30176640$, $T_{96100} := 96720^2$,
 $E := \{1245, 1247, \dots, 193441, 193443\}$
63. **(624, 97343, 97345)** $\Rightarrow 97345 - 624 = 311^2$, $S_{311 \times 311} := 30468359$, $T_{96721} := 97343^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 194687, 194689\}$ or $E := \{49609, 49610, \dots, 146328, 146329\}$
64. **(626, 97968, 97970)** $\Rightarrow 97970 - 626 = 312^2$, $S_{312 \times 312} := 30761952$, $T_{97344} := 97968^2$,
 $E := \{1253, 1255, \dots, 195937, 195939\}$
65. **(628, 98595, 98597)** $\Rightarrow 98597 - 628 = 313^2$, $S_{313 \times 313} := 31057425$, $T_{97969} := 98595^2$,
 $E := \{1257, 1259, \dots, 197191, 197193\}$ or $E := \{50241, 50242, \dots, 148208, 148209\}$
66. **(630, 99224, 99226)** $\Rightarrow 99226 - 630 = 314^2$, $S_{314 \times 314} := 31354784$, $T_{98596} := 99224^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 198449, 198451\}$

67. **(632, 99855, 99857)** $\Rightarrow 99857 - 632 = 315^2$, $S_{315 \times 315} := 31654035$, $T_{99225} := 99855^2$,
 $E := \{1265, 1267, \dots, 199711, 199713\}$ or $E := \{50877, 50878, \dots, 150100, 150101\}$
68. **(634, 100488, 100490)** $\Rightarrow 100490 - 634 = 316^2$, $S_{316 \times 316} := 31955184$, $T_{99856} := 100488^2$,
 $E := \{1269, 1271, \dots, 200977, 200979\}$
69. **(636, 101123, 101125)** $\Rightarrow 101125 - 636 = 317^2$, $S_{317 \times 317} := 32258237$, $T_{100489} := 101123^2$,
 $E := \{1273, 1275, \dots, 202247, 202249\}$ or $E := \{51517, 51518, \dots, 152004, 152005\}$
70. **(638, 101760, 101762)** $\Rightarrow 101762 - 638 = 318^2$, $S_{318 \times 318} := 32563200$, $T_{101124} := 101760^2$,
 $E := \{1277, 1279, \dots, 203521, 203523\}$
71. **(640, 102399, 102401)** $\Rightarrow 102401 - 640 = 319^2$, $S_{319 \times 319} := 32870079$, $T_{101761} := 102399^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 204799, 204801\}$ or $E := \{52161, 52162, \dots, 153920, 153921\}$
72. **(642, 103040, 103042)** $\Rightarrow 103042 - 642 = 320^2$, $S_{320 \times 320} := 33178880$, $T_{102400} := 103040^2$,
 $E := \{1285, 1287, \dots, 206081, 206083\}$
73. **(644, 103683, 103685)** $\Rightarrow 103685 - 644 = 321^2$, $S_{321 \times 321} := 33489609$, $T_{103041} := 103683^2$,
 $E := \{1289, 1291, \dots, 207367, 207369\}$ or $E := \{52809, 52810, \dots, 155848, 155849\}$
74. **(646, 104328, 104330)** $\Rightarrow 104330 - 646 = 322^2$, $S_{322 \times 322} := 33802272$, $T_{103684} := 104328^2$,
 $E := \{1293, 1295, \dots, 208657, 208659\}$
75. **(648, 104975, 104977)** $\Rightarrow 104977 - 648 = 323^2$, $S_{323 \times 323} := 34116875$, $T_{104329} := 104975^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 209951, 209953\}$ or $E := \{53461, 53462, \dots, 157788, 157789\}$
76. **(650, 105624, 105626)** $\Rightarrow 105626 - 650 = 324^2$, $S_{324 \times 324} := 34433424$, $T_{104976} := 105624^2$,
 $E := \{1301, 1303, \dots, 211249, 211251\}$
77. **(652, 106275, 106277)** $\Rightarrow 106277 - 652 = 325^2$, $S_{325 \times 325} := 34751925$, $T_{105625} := 106275^2$,
 $E := \{1305, 1307, \dots, 212551, 212553\}$ or $E := \{54117, 54118, \dots, 159740, 159741\}$
78. **(654, 106928, 106930)** $\Rightarrow 106930 - 654 = 326^2$, $S_{326 \times 326} := 35072384$, $T_{106276} := 106928^2$,
 $E := \{1309, 1311, \dots, 213857, 213859\}$
79. **(656, 107583, 107585)** $\Rightarrow 107585 - 656 = 327^2$, $S_{327 \times 327} := 35394807$, $T_{106929} := 107583^2$,
 $E := \{1313, 1315, \dots, 215167, 215169\}$ or $E := \{54777, 54778, \dots, 161704, 161705\}$
80. **(658, 108240, 108242)** $\Rightarrow 108242 - 658 = 328^2$, $S_{328 \times 328} := 35719200$, $T_{107584} := 108240^2$,
 $E := \{1317, 1319, \dots, 216481, 216483\}$
81. **(660, 108899, 108901)** $\Rightarrow 108901 - 660 = 329^2$, $S_{329 \times 329} := 36045569$, $T_{108241} := 108899^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 217799, 217801\}$ or $E := \{55441, 55442, \dots, 163680, 163681\}$
82. **(662, 109560, 109562)** $\Rightarrow 109562 - 662 = 330^2$, $S_{330 \times 330} := 36373920$, $T_{108900} := 109560^2$,
 $E := \{1325, 1327, \dots, 219121, 219123\}$
83. **(664, 110223, 110225)** $\Rightarrow 110225 - 664 = 331^2$, $S_{331 \times 331} := 36704259$, $T_{109561} := 110223^2$,
 $E := \{1329, 1331, \dots, 220447, 220449\}$ or $E := \{56109, 56110, \dots, 165668, 165669\}$

84. **(666, 110888, 110890)** $\Rightarrow 110890 - 666 = 332^2$, $S_{332 \times 332} := 37036592$, $T_{110224} := 110888^2$,
 $E := \{1333, 1335, \dots, 221777, 221779\}$
85. **(668, 111555, 111557)** $\Rightarrow 111557 - 668 = 333^2$, $S_{333 \times 333} := 37370925$, $T_{110889} := 111555^2$,
 $E := \{1337, 1339, \dots, 223111, 223113\}$ or $E := \{56781, 56782, \dots, 167668, 167669\}$
86. **(670, 112224, 112226)** $\Rightarrow 112226 - 670 = 334^2$, $S_{334 \times 334} := 37707264$, $T_{111556} := 112224^2$,
 $E := \{1341, 1343, \dots, 224449, 224451\}$
87. **(672, 112895, 112897)** $\Rightarrow 112897 - 672 = 335^2$, $S_{335 \times 335} := 38045615$, $T_{112225} := 112895^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 225791, 225793\}$ or $E := \{57457, 57458, \dots, 169680, 169681\}$
88. **(674, 113568, 113570)** $\Rightarrow 113570 - 674 = 336^2$, $S_{336 \times 336} := 38385984$, $T_{112896} := 113568^2$,
 $E := \{1349, 1351, \dots, 227137, 227139\}$
89. **(676, 114243, 114245)** $\Rightarrow 114245 - 676 = 337^2$, $S_{337 \times 337} := 38728377$, $T_{113569} := 114243^2$,
 $E := \{1353, 1355, \dots, 228487, 228489\}$ or $E := \{58137, 58138, \dots, 171704, 171705\}$
90. **(678, 114920, 114922)** $\Rightarrow 114922 - 678 = 338^2$, $S_{338 \times 338} := 39072800$, $T_{114244} := 114920^2$,
 $E := \{1357, 1359, \dots, 229841, 229843\}$
91. **(680, 115599, 115601)** $\Rightarrow 115601 - 680 = 339^2$, $S_{339 \times 339} := 39419259$, $T_{114921} := 115599^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 231199, 231201\}$ or $E := \{58821, 58822, \dots, 173740, 173741\}$
92. **(682, 116280, 116282)** $\Rightarrow 116282 - 682 = 340^2$, $S_{340 \times 340} := 39767760$, $T_{115600} := 116280^2$,
 $E := \{1365, 1367, \dots, 232561, 232563\}$
93. **(684, 116963, 116965)** $\Rightarrow 116965 - 684 = 341^2$, $S_{341 \times 341} := 40118309$, $T_{116281} := 116963^2$,
 $E := \{1369, 1371, \dots, 233927, 233929\}$ or $E := \{59509, 59510, \dots, 175788, 175789\}$
94. **(686, 117648, 117650)** $\Rightarrow 117650 - 686 = 342^2$, $S_{342 \times 342} := 40470912$, $T_{116964} := 117648^2$,
 $E := \{1373, 1375, \dots, 235297, 235299\}$
95. **(688, 118335, 118337)** $\Rightarrow 118337 - 688 = 343^2$, $S_{343 \times 343} := 40825575$, $T_{117649} := 118335^2$,
 $E := \{1377, 1379, \dots, 236671, 236673\}$ or $E := \{60201, 60202, \dots, 177848, 177849\}$
96. **(690, 119024, 119026)** $\Rightarrow 119026 - 690 = 344^2$, $S_{344 \times 344} := 41182304$, $T_{118336} := 119024^2$,
 $E := \{1381, 1383, \dots, 238049, 238051\}$
97. **(692, 119715, 119717)** $\Rightarrow 119717 - 692 = 345^2$, $S_{345 \times 345} := 41541105$, $T_{119025} := 119715^2$,
 $E := \{1385, 1387, \dots, 239431, 239433\}$ or $E := \{60897, 60898, \dots, 179920, 179921\}$
98. **(694, 120408, 120410)** $\Rightarrow 120410 - 694 = 346^2$, $S_{346 \times 346} := 41901984$, $T_{119716} := 120408^2$,
 $E := \{1389, 1391, \dots, 240817, 240819\}$
99. **(696, 121103, 121105)** $\Rightarrow 121105 - 696 = 347^2$, $S_{347 \times 347} := 42264947$, $T_{120409} := 121103^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 242207, 242209\}$ or $E := \{61597, 61598, \dots, 182004, 182005\}$
100. **(698, 121800, 121802)** $\Rightarrow 121802 - 698 = 348^2$, $S_{348 \times 348} := 42630000$, $T_{121104} := 121800^2$,
 $E := \{1397, 1399, \dots, 243601, 243603\}$

101. **(700, 122499, 122501)** $\Rightarrow 122501 - 700 = 349^2$, $S_{349 \times 349} := 42997149$, $T_{121801} := 122499^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 244999, 245001\}$ or $E := \{62301, 62302, \dots, 184100, 184101\}$
102. **(702, 123200, 123202)** $\Rightarrow 123202 - 702 = 350^2$, $S_{350 \times 350} := 43366400$, $T_{122500} := 123200^2$,
 $E := \{1405, 1407, \dots, 246401, 246403\}$
103. **(704, 123903, 123905)** $\Rightarrow 123905 - 704 = 351^2$, $S_{351 \times 351} := 43737759$, $T_{123201} := 123903^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 247807, 247809\}$ or $E := \{63009, 63010, \dots, 186208, 186209\}$
104. **(706, 124608, 124610)** $\Rightarrow 124610 - 706 = 352^2$, $S_{352 \times 352} := 44111232$, $T_{123904} := 124608^2$,
 $E := \{1413, 1415, \dots, 249217, 249219\}$
105. **(708, 125315, 125317)** $\Rightarrow 125317 - 708 = 353^2$, $S_{353 \times 353} := 44486825$, $T_{124609} := 125315^2$,
 $E := \{1417, 1419, \dots, 250631, 250633\}$ or $E := \{63721, 63722, \dots, 188328, 188329\}$
106. **(710, 126024, 126026)** $\Rightarrow 126026 - 710 = 354^2$, $S_{354 \times 354} := 44864544$, $T_{125316} := 126024^2$,
 $E := \{1421, 1423, \dots, 252049, 252051\}$
107. **(712, 126735, 126737)** $\Rightarrow 126737 - 712 = 355^2$, $S_{355 \times 355} := 45244395$, $T_{126025} := 126735^2$,
 $E := \{1425, 1427, \dots, 253471, 253473\}$ or $E := \{64437, 64438, \dots, 190460, 190461\}$
108. **(714, 127448, 127450)** $\Rightarrow 127450 - 714 = 356^2$, $S_{356 \times 356} := 45626384$, $T_{126736} := 127448^2$,
 $E := \{1429, 1431, \dots, 254897, 254899\}$
109. **(716, 128163, 128165)** $\Rightarrow 128165 - 716 = 357^2$, $S_{357 \times 357} := 46010517$, $T_{127449} := 128163^2$,
 $E := \{1433, 1435, \dots, 256327, 256329\}$ or $E := \{65157, 65158, \dots, 192604, 192605\}$
110. **(718, 128880, 128882)** $\Rightarrow 128882 - 718 = 358^2$, $S_{358 \times 358} := 46396800$, $T_{128164} := 128880^2$,
 $E := \{1437, 1439, \dots, 257761, 257763\}$
111. **(720, 129599, 129601)** $\Rightarrow 129601 - 720 = 359^2$, $S_{359 \times 359} := 46785239$, $T_{128881} := 129599^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 259199, 259201\}$ or $E := \{65881, 65882, \dots, 194760, 194761\}$
112. **(722, 130320, 130322)** $\Rightarrow 130322 - 722 = 360^2$, $S_{360 \times 360} := 47175840$, $T_{129600} := 130320^2$,
 $E := \{1445, 1447, \dots, 260641, 260643\}$
113. **(724, 131043, 131045)** $\Rightarrow 131045 - 724 = 361^2$, $S_{361 \times 361} := 47568609$, $T_{130321} := 131043^2$,
 $E := \{1449, 1451, \dots, 262087, 262089\}$ or $E := \{66609, 66610, \dots, 196928, 196929\}$
114. **(726, 131768, 131770)** $\Rightarrow 131770 - 726 = 362^2$, $S_{362 \times 362} := 47963552$, $T_{131044} := 131768^2$,
 $E := \{1453, 1455, \dots, 263537, 263539\}$
115. **(728, 132495, 132497)** $\Rightarrow 132497 - 728 = 363^2$, $S_{363 \times 363} := 48360675$, $T_{131769} := 132495^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 264991, 264993\}$ or $E := \{67341, 67342, \dots, 199108, 199109\}$
116. **(730, 133224, 133226)** $\Rightarrow 133226 - 730 = 364^2$, $S_{364 \times 364} := 48759984$, $T_{132496} := 133224^2$,
 $E := \{1461, 1463, \dots, 266449, 266451\}$
117. **(732, 133955, 133957)** $\Rightarrow 133957 - 732 = 365^2$, $S_{365 \times 365} := 49161485$, $T_{133225} := 133955^2$,
 $E := \{1465, 1467, \dots, 267911, 267913\}$ or $E := \{68077, 68078, \dots, 201300, 201301\}$

118. **(734, 134688, 134690)** $\Rightarrow 134690 - 734 = 366^2$, $S_{366 \times 366} := 49565184$, $T_{133956} := 134688^2$,
 $E := \{1469, 1471, \dots, 269377, 269379\}$
119. **(736, 135423, 135425)** $\Rightarrow 135425 - 736 = 367^2$, $S_{367 \times 367} := 49971087$, $T_{134689} := 135423^2$,
 $E := \{1473, 1475, \dots, 270847, 270849\}$ or $E := \{68817, 68818, \dots, 203504, 203505\}$
120. **(738, 136160, 136162)** $\Rightarrow 136162 - 738 = 368^2$, $S_{368 \times 368} := 50379200$, $T_{135424} := 136160^2$,
 $E := \{1477, 1479, \dots, 272321, 272323\}$
121. **(740, 136899, 136901)** $\Rightarrow 136901 - 740 = 369^2$, $S_{369 \times 369} := 50789529$, $T_{136161} := 136899^2$,
 $E := \{1481, 1483, \dots, 273799, 273801\}$ or $E := \{69561, 69562, \dots, 205720, 205721\}$
122. **(742, 137640, 137642)** $\Rightarrow 137642 - 742 = 370^2$, $S_{370 \times 370} := 51202080$, $T_{136900} := 137640^2$,
 $E := \{1485, 1487, \dots, 275281, 275283\}$
123. **(744, 138383, 138385)** $\Rightarrow 138385 - 744 = 371^2$, $S_{371 \times 371} := 51616859$, $T_{137641} := 138383^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 276767, 276769\}$ or $E := \{70309, 70310, \dots, 207948, 207949\}$
124. **(746, 139128, 139130)** $\Rightarrow 139130 - 746 = 372^2$, $S_{372 \times 372} := 52033872$, $T_{138384} := 139128^2$,
 $E := \{1493, 1495, \dots, 278257, 278259\}$
125. **(748, 139875, 139877)** $\Rightarrow 139877 - 748 = 373^2$, $S_{373 \times 373} := 52453125$, $T_{139129} := 139875^2$,
 $E := \{1497, 1499, \dots, 279751, 279753\}$ or $E := \{71061, 71062, \dots, 210188, 210189\}$
126. **(750, 140624, 140626)** $\Rightarrow 140626 - 750 = 374^2$, $S_{374 \times 374} := 52874624$, $T_{139876} := 140624^2$,
 $E := \{1501, 1503, \dots, 281249, 281251\}$
127. **(752, 141375, 141377)** $\Rightarrow 141377 - 752 = 375^2$, $S_{375 \times 375} := 53298375$, $T_{140625} := 141375^2$,
 $E := \{1505, 1507, \dots, 282751, 282753\}$ or $E := \{71817, 71818, \dots, 212440, 212441\}$
128. **(754, 142128, 142130)** $\Rightarrow 142130 - 754 = 376^2$, $S_{376 \times 376} := 53724384$, $T_{141376} := 142128^2$,
 $E := \{1509, 1511, \dots, 284257, 284259\}$
129. **(756, 142883, 142885)** $\Rightarrow 142885 - 756 = 377^2$, $S_{377 \times 377} := 54152657$, $T_{142129} := 142883^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 285767, 285769\}$ or $E := \{72577, 72578, \dots, 214704, 214705\}$
130. **(758, 143640, 143642)** $\Rightarrow 143642 - 758 = 378^2$, $S_{378 \times 378} := 54583200$, $T_{142884} := 143640^2$,
 $E := \{1517, 1519, \dots, 287281, 287283\}$
131. **(760, 144399, 144401)** $\Rightarrow 144401 - 760 = 379^2$, $S_{379 \times 379} := 55016019$, $T_{143641} := 144399^2$,
 $E := \{1521, 1523, \dots, 288799, 288801\}$ or $E := \{73341, 73342, \dots, 216980, 216981\}$
132. **(762, 145160, 145162)** $\Rightarrow 145162 - 762 = 380^2$, $S_{380 \times 380} := 55451120$, $T_{144400} := 145160^2$,
 $E := \{1525, 1527, \dots, 290321, 290323\}$
133. **(764, 145923, 145925)** $\Rightarrow 145925 - 764 = 381^2$, $S_{381 \times 381} := 55888509$, $T_{145161} := 145923^2$,
 $E := \{1529, 1531, \dots, 291847, 291849\}$ or $E := \{74109, 74110, \dots, 219268, 219269\}$
134. **(766, 146688, 146690)** $\Rightarrow 146690 - 766 = 382^2$, $S_{382 \times 382} := 56328192$, $T_{145924} := 146688^2$,
 $E := \{1533, 1535, \dots, 293377, 293379\}$

135. **(768, 147455, 147457)** $\Rightarrow 147457 - 768 = 383^2$, $S_{383 \times 383} := 56770175$, $T_{146689} := 147455^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 294911, 294913\}$ or $E := \{74881, 74882, \dots, 221568, 221569\}$
136. **(770, 148224, 148226)** $\Rightarrow 148226 - 770 = 384^2$, $S_{384 \times 384} := 57214464$, $T_{147456} := 148224^2$,
 $E := \{1541, 1543, \dots, 296449, 296451\}$
137. **(772, 148995, 148997)** $\Rightarrow 148997 - 772 = 385^2$, $S_{385 \times 385} := 57661065$, $T_{148225} := 148995^2$,
 $E := \{1545, 1547, \dots, 297991, 297993\}$ or $E := \{75657, 75658, \dots, 223880, 223881\}$
138. **(774, 149768, 149770)** $\Rightarrow 149770 - 774 = 386^2$, $S_{386 \times 386} := 58109984$, $T_{148996} := 149768^2$,
 $E := \{1549, 1551, \dots, 299537, 299539\}$
139. **(776, 150543, 150545)** $\Rightarrow 150545 - 776 = 387^2$, $S_{387 \times 387} := 58561227$, $T_{149769} := 150543^2$,
 $E := \{1553, 1555, \dots, 301087, 301089\}$ or $E := \{76437, 76438, \dots, 226204, 226205\}$
140. **(778, 151320, 151322)** $\Rightarrow 151322 - 778 = 388^2$, $S_{388 \times 388} := 59014800$, $T_{150544} := 151320^2$,
 $E := \{1557, 1559, \dots, 302641, 302643\}$
141. **(780, 152099, 152101)** $\Rightarrow 152101 - 780 = 389^2$, $S_{389 \times 389} := 59470709$, $T_{151321} := 152099^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 304199, 304201\}$ or $E := \{77221, 77222, \dots, 228540, 228541\}$
142. **(782, 152880, 152882)** $\Rightarrow 152882 - 782 = 390^2$, $S_{390 \times 390} := 59928960$, $T_{152100} := 152880^2$,
 $E := \{1565, 1567, \dots, 305761, 305763\}$
143. **(784, 153663, 153665)** $\Rightarrow 153665 - 784 = 391^2$, $S_{391 \times 391} := 60389559$, $T_{152881} := 153663^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 307327, 307329\}$ or $E := \{78009, 78010, \dots, 230888, 230889\}$
144. **(786, 154448, 154450)** $\Rightarrow 154450 - 786 = 392^2$, $S_{392 \times 392} := 60852512$, $T_{153664} := 154448^2$,
 $E := \{1573, 1575, \dots, 308897, 308899\}$
145. **(788, 155235, 155237)** $\Rightarrow 155237 - 788 = 393^2$, $S_{393 \times 393} := 61317825$, $T_{154449} := 155235^2$,
 $E := \{1577, 1579, \dots, 310471, 310473\}$ or $E := \{78801, 78802, \dots, 233248, 233249\}$
146. **(790, 156024, 156026)** $\Rightarrow 156026 - 790 = 394^2$, $S_{394 \times 394} := 61785504$, $T_{155236} := 156024^2$,
 $E := \{1581, 1583, \dots, 312049, 312051\}$
147. **(792, 156815, 156817)** $\Rightarrow 156817 - 792 = 395^2$, $S_{395 \times 395} := 62255555$, $T_{156025} := 156815^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 313631, 313633\}$ or $E := \{79597, 79598, \dots, 235620, 235621\}$
148. **(794, 157608, 157610)** $\Rightarrow 157610 - 794 = 396^2$, $S_{396 \times 396} := 62727984$, $T_{156816} := 157608^2$,
 $E := \{1589, 1591, \dots, 315217, 315219\}$
149. **(796, 158403, 158405)** $\Rightarrow 158405 - 796 = 397^2$, $S_{397 \times 397} := 63202797$, $T_{157609} := 158403^2$,
 $E := \{1593, 1595, \dots, 316807, 316809\}$ or $E := \{80397, 80398, \dots, 238004, 238005\}$
150. **(798, 159200, 159202)** $\Rightarrow 159202 - 798 = 398^2$, $S_{398 \times 398} := 63680000$, $T_{158404} := 159200^2$,
 $E := \{1597, 1599, \dots, 318401, 318403\}$
151. **(800, 159999, 160001)** $\Rightarrow 160001 - 800 = 399^2$, $S_{399 \times 399} := 64159599$, $T_{159201} := 159999^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 319999, 320001\}$ or $E := \{81201, 81202, \dots, 240400, 240401\}$

152. **(802, 160800, 160802)** $\Rightarrow 160802 - 802 = 400^2$, $S_{400 \times 400} := 64641600$, $T_{160000} := 160800^2$,
 $E := \{1605, 1607, \dots, 321601, 321603\}$
153. **(804, 161603, 161605)** $\Rightarrow 161605 - 804 = 401^2$, $S_{401 \times 401} := 65126009$, $T_{160801} := 161603^2$,
 $E := \{1609, 1611, \dots, 323207, 323209\}$ or $E := \{82009, 82010, \dots, 242808, 242809\}$
154. **(806, 162408, 162410)** $\Rightarrow 162410 - 806 = 402^2$, $S_{402 \times 402} := 65612832$, $T_{161604} := 162408^2$,
 $E := \{1613, 1615, \dots, 324817, 324819\}$
155. **(808, 163215, 163217)** $\Rightarrow 163217 - 808 = 403^2$, $S_{403 \times 403} := 66102075$, $T_{162409} := 163215^2$,
 $E := \{1617, 1619, \dots, 326431, 326433\}$ or $E := \{82821, 82822, \dots, 245228, 245229\}$
156. **(810, 164024, 164026)** $\Rightarrow 164026 - 810 = 404^2$, $S_{404 \times 404} := 66593744$, $T_{163216} := 164024^2$,
 $E := \{1621, 1623, \dots, 328049, 328051\}$
157. **(812, 164835, 164837)** $\Rightarrow 164837 - 812 = 405^2$, $S_{405 \times 405} := 67087845$, $T_{164025} := 164835^2$,
 $E := \{1625, 1627, \dots, 329671, 329673\}$ or $E := \{83637, 83638, \dots, 247660, 247661\}$
158. **(814, 165648, 165650)** $\Rightarrow 165650 - 814 = 406^2$, $S_{406 \times 406} := 67584384$, $T_{164836} := 165648^2$,
 $E := \{1629, 1631, \dots, 331297, 331299\}$
159. **(816, 166463, 166465)** $\Rightarrow 166465 - 816 = 407^2$, $S_{407 \times 407} := 68083367$, $T_{165649} := 166463^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 332927, 332929\}$ or $E := \{84457, 84458, \dots, 250104, 250105\}$
160. **(818, 167280, 167282)** $\Rightarrow 167282 - 818 = 408^2$, $S_{408 \times 408} := 68584800$, $T_{166464} := 167280^2$,
 $E := \{1637, 1639, \dots, 334561, 334563\}$
161. **(820, 168099, 168101)** $\Rightarrow 168101 - 820 = 409^2$, $S_{409 \times 409} := 69088689$, $T_{167281} := 168099^2$,
 $E := \{1641, 1643, \dots, 336199, 336201\}$ or $E := \{85281, 85282, \dots, 252560, 252561\}$
162. **(822, 168920, 168922)** $\Rightarrow 168922 - 822 = 410^2$, $S_{410 \times 410} := 69595040$, $T_{168100} := 168920^2$,
 $E := \{1645, 1647, \dots, 337841, 337843\}$
163. **(824, 169743, 169745)** $\Rightarrow 169745 - 824 = 411^2$, $S_{411 \times 411} := 70103859$, $T_{168921} := 169743^2$,
 $E := \{1649, 1651, \dots, 339487, 339489\}$ or $E := \{86109, 86110, \dots, 255028, 255029\}$
164. **(826, 170568, 170570)** $\Rightarrow 170570 - 826 = 412^2$, $S_{412 \times 412} := 70615152$, $T_{169744} := 170568^2$,
 $E := \{1653, 1655, \dots, 341137, 341139\}$
165. **(828, 171395, 171397)** $\Rightarrow 171397 - 828 = 413^2$, $S_{413 \times 413} := 71128925$, $T_{170569} := 171395^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 342791, 342793\}$ or $E := \{86941, 86942, \dots, 257508, 257509\}$
166. **(830, 172224, 172226)** $\Rightarrow 172226 - 830 = 414^2$, $S_{414 \times 414} := 71645184$, $T_{171396} := 172224^2$,
 $E := \{1661, 1663, \dots, 344449, 344451\}$
167. **(832, 173055, 173057)** $\Rightarrow 173057 - 832 = 415^2$, $S_{415 \times 415} := 72163935$, $T_{172225} := 173055^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 346111, 346113\}$ or $E := \{87777, 87778, \dots, 260000, 260001\}$
168. **(834, 173888, 173890)** $\Rightarrow 173890 - 834 = 416^2$, $S_{416 \times 416} := 72685184$, $T_{173056} := 173888^2$,
 $E := \{1669, 1671, \dots, 347777, 347779\}$

169. **(836, 174723, 174725)** $\Rightarrow 174725 - 836 = 417^2$, $S_{417 \times 417} := 73208937$, $T_{173889} := 174723^2$,
 $E := \{1673, 1675, \dots, 349447, 349449\}$ or $E := \{88617, 88618, \dots, 262504, 262505\}$
170. **(838, 175560, 175562)** $\Rightarrow 175562 - 838 = 418^2$, $S_{418 \times 418} := 73735200$, $T_{174724} := 175560^2$,
 $E := \{1677, 1679, \dots, 351121, 351123\}$
171. **(840, 176399, 176401)** $\Rightarrow 176401 - 840 = 419^2$, $S_{419 \times 419} := 74263979$, $T_{175561} := 176399^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 352799, 352801\}$ or $E := \{89461, 89462, \dots, 265020, 265021\}$
172. **(842, 177240, 177242)** $\Rightarrow 177242 - 842 = 420^2$, $S_{420 \times 420} := 74795280$, $T_{176400} := 177240^2$,
 $E := \{1685, 1687, \dots, 354481, 354483\}$
173. **(844, 178083, 178085)** $\Rightarrow 178085 - 844 = 421^2$, $S_{421 \times 421} := 75329109$, $T_{177241} := 178083^2$,
 $E := \{1689, 1691, \dots, 356167, 356169\}$ or $E := \{90309, 90310, \dots, 267548, 267549\}$
174. **(846, 178928, 178930)** $\Rightarrow 178930 - 846 = 422^2$, $S_{422 \times 422} := 75865472$, $T_{178084} := 178928^2$,
 $E := \{1693, 1695, \dots, 357857, 357859\}$
175. **(848, 179775, 179777)** $\Rightarrow 179777 - 848 = 423^2$, $S_{423 \times 423} := 76404375$, $T_{178929} := 179775^2$,
 $E := \{1697, 1699, \dots, 359551, 359553\}$ or $E := \{91161, 91162, \dots, 270088, 270089\}$
176. **(850, 180624, 180626)** $\Rightarrow 180626 - 850 = 424^2$, $S_{424 \times 424} := 76945824$, $T_{179776} := 180624^2$,
 $E := \{1701, 1703, \dots, 361249, 361251\}$
177. **(852, 181475, 181477)** $\Rightarrow 181477 - 852 = 425^2$, $S_{425 \times 425} := 77489825$, $T_{180625} := 181475^2$,
 $E := \{1705, 1707, \dots, 362951, 362953\}$ or $E := \{92017, 92018, \dots, 272640, 272641\}$
178. **(854, 182328, 182330)** $\Rightarrow 182330 - 854 = 426^2$, $S_{426 \times 426} := 78036384$, $T_{181476} := 182328^2$,
 $E := \{1709, 1711, \dots, 364657, 364659\}$
179. **(856, 183183, 183185)** $\Rightarrow 183185 - 856 = 427^2$, $S_{427 \times 427} := 78585507$, $T_{182329} := 183183^2$,
 $E := \{1713, 1715, \dots, 366367, 366369\}$ or $E := \{92877, 92878, \dots, 275204, 275205\}$
180. **(858, 184040, 184042)** $\Rightarrow 184042 - 858 = 428^2$, $S_{428 \times 428} := 79137200$, $T_{183184} := 184040^2$,
 $E := \{1717, 1719, \dots, 368081, 368083\}$
181. **(860, 184899, 184901)** $\Rightarrow 184901 - 860 = 429^2$, $S_{429 \times 429} := 79691469$, $T_{184041} := 184899^2$,
 $E := \{1721, 1723, \dots, 369799, 369801\}$ or $E := \{93741, 93742, \dots, 277780, 277781\}$
182. **(862, 185760, 185762)** $\Rightarrow 185762 - 862 = 430^2$, $S_{430 \times 430} := 80248320$, $T_{184900} := 185760^2$,
 $E := \{1725, 1727, \dots, 371521, 371523\}$
183. **(864, 186623, 186625)** $\Rightarrow 186625 - 864 = 431^2$, $S_{431 \times 431} := 80807759$, $T_{185761} := 186623^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 373247, 373249\}$ or $E := \{94609, 94610, \dots, 280368, 280369\}$
184. **(866, 187488, 187490)** $\Rightarrow 187490 - 866 = 432^2$, $S_{432 \times 432} := 81369792$, $T_{186624} := 187488^2$,
 $E := \{1733, 1735, \dots, 374977, 374979\}$
185. **(868, 188355, 188357)** $\Rightarrow 188357 - 868 = 433^2$, $S_{433 \times 433} := 81934425$, $T_{187489} := 188355^2$,
 $E := \{1737, 1739, \dots, 376711, 376713\}$ or $E := \{95481, 95482, \dots, 282968, 282969\}$

186. **(870, 189224, 189226)** $\Rightarrow 189226 - 870 = 434^2$, $S_{434 \times 434} := 82501664$, $T_{188356} := 189224^2$,
 $E := \{1741, 1743, \dots, 378449, 378451\}$
187. **(872, 190095, 190097)** $\Rightarrow 190097 - 872 = 435^2$, $S_{435 \times 435} := 83071515$, $T_{189225} := 190095^2$,
 $E := \{1745, 1747, \dots, 380191, 380193\}$ or $E := \{96357, 96358, \dots, 285580, 285581\}$
188. **(874, 190968, 190970)** $\Rightarrow 190970 - 874 = 436^2$, $S_{436 \times 436} := 83643984$, $T_{190096} := 190968^2$,
 $E := \{1749, 1751, \dots, 381937, 381939\}$
189. **(876, 191843, 191845)** $\Rightarrow 191845 - 876 = 437^2$, $S_{437 \times 437} := 84219077$, $T_{190969} := 191843^2$,
 $E := \{1753, 1755, \dots, 383687, 383689\}$ or $E := \{97237, 97238, \dots, 288204, 288205\}$
190. **(878, 192720, 192722)** $\Rightarrow 192722 - 878 = 438^2$, $S_{438 \times 438} := 84796800$, $T_{191844} := 192720^2$,
 $E := \{1757, 1759, \dots, 385441, 385443\}$
191. **(880, 193599, 193601)** $\Rightarrow 193601 - 880 = 439^2$, $S_{439 \times 439} := 85377159$, $T_{192721} := 193599^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 387199, 387201\}$ or $E := \{98121, 98122, \dots, 290840, 290841\}$
192. **(882, 194480, 194482)** $\Rightarrow 194482 - 882 = 440^2$, $S_{440 \times 440} := 85960160$, $T_{193600} := 194480^2$,
 $E := \{1765, 1767, \dots, 388961, 388963\}$
193. **(884, 195363, 195365)** $\Rightarrow 195365 - 884 = 441^2$, $S_{441 \times 441} := 86545809$, $T_{194481} := 195363^2$,
 $E := \{1769, 1771, \dots, 390727, 390729\}$ or $E := \{99009, 99010, \dots, 293488, 293489\}$
194. **(886, 196248, 196250)** $\Rightarrow 196250 - 886 = 442^2$, $S_{442 \times 442} := 87134112$, $T_{195364} := 196248^2$,
 $E := \{1773, 1775, \dots, 392497, 392499\}$
195. **(888, 197135, 197137)** $\Rightarrow 197137 - 888 = 443^2$, $S_{443 \times 443} := 87725075$, $T_{196249} := 197135^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 394271, 394273\}$ or $E := \{99901, 99902, \dots, 296148, 296149\}$
196. **(890, 198024, 198026)** $\Rightarrow 198026 - 890 = 444^2$, $S_{444 \times 444} := 88318704$, $T_{197136} := 198024^2$,
 $E := \{1781, 1783, \dots, 396049, 396051\}$
197. **(892, 198915, 198917)** $\Rightarrow 198917 - 892 = 445^2$, $S_{445 \times 445} := 88915005$, $T_{198025} := 198915^2$,
 $E := \{1785, 1787, \dots, 397831, 397833\}$ or $E := \{100797, 100798, \dots, 298820, 298821\}$
198. **(894, 199808, 199810)** $\Rightarrow 199810 - 894 = 446^2$, $S_{446 \times 446} := 89513984$, $T_{198916} := 199808^2$,
 $E := \{1789, 1791, \dots, 399617, 399619\}$
199. **(896, 200703, 200705)** $\Rightarrow 200705 - 896 = 447^2$, $S_{447 \times 447} := 90115647$, $T_{199809} := 200703^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 401407, 401409\}$ or $E := \{101697, 101698, \dots, 301504, 301505\}$
200. **(898, 201600, 201602)** $\Rightarrow 201602 - 898 = 448^2$, $S_{448 \times 448} := 90720000$, $T_{200704} := 201600^2$,
 $E := \{1797, 1799, \dots, 403201, 403203\}$
201. **(900, 202499, 202501)** $\Rightarrow 202501 - 900 = 449^2$, $S_{449 \times 449} := 91327049$, $T_{201601} := 202499^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 404999, 405001\}$ or $E := \{102601, 102602, \dots, 304200, 304201\}$
202. **(902, 203400, 203402)** $\Rightarrow 203402 - 902 = 450^2$, $S_{450 \times 450} := 91936800$, $T_{202500} := 203400^2$,
 $E := \{1805, 1807, \dots, 406801, 406803\}$

203. **(904, 204303, 204305)** $\Rightarrow 204305 - 904 = 451^2$, $S_{451 \times 451} := 92549259$, $T_{203401} := 204303^2$,
 $E := \{1809, 1811, \dots, 408607, 408609\}$ or $E := \{103509, 103510, \dots, 306908, 306909\}$
204. **(906, 205208, 205210)** $\Rightarrow 205210 - 906 = 452^2$, $S_{452 \times 452} := 93164432$, $T_{204304} := 205208^2$,
 $E := \{1813, 1815, \dots, 410417, 410419\}$
205. **(908, 206115, 206117)** $\Rightarrow 206117 - 908 = 453^2$, $S_{453 \times 453} := 93782325$, $T_{205209} := 206115^2$,
 $E := \{1817, 1819, \dots, 412231, 412233\}$ or $E := \{104421, 104422, \dots, 309628, 309629\}$
206. **(910, 207024, 207026)** $\Rightarrow 207026 - 910 = 454^2$, $S_{454 \times 454} := 94402944$, $T_{206116} := 207024^2$,
 $E := \{1821, 1823, \dots, 414049, 414051\}$
207. **(912, 207935, 207937)** $\Rightarrow 207937 - 912 = 455^2$, $S_{455 \times 455} := 95026295$, $T_{207025} := 207935^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 415871, 415873\}$ or $E := \{105337, 105338, \dots, 312360, 312361\}$
208. **(914, 208848, 208850)** $\Rightarrow 208850 - 914 = 456^2$, $S_{456 \times 456} := 95652384$, $T_{207936} := 208848^2$,
 $E := \{1829, 1831, \dots, 417697, 417699\}$
209. **(916, 209763, 209765)** $\Rightarrow 209765 - 916 = 457^2$, $S_{457 \times 457} := 96281217$, $T_{208849} := 209763^2$,
 $E := \{1833, 1835, \dots, 419527, 419529\}$ or $E := \{106257, 106258, \dots, 315104, 315105\}$
210. **(918, 210680, 210682)** $\Rightarrow 210682 - 918 = 458^2$, $S_{458 \times 458} := 96912800$, $T_{209764} := 210680^2$,
 $E := \{1837, 1839, \dots, 421361, 421363\}$
211. **(920, 211599, 211601)** $\Rightarrow 211601 - 920 = 459^2$, $S_{459 \times 459} := 97547139$, $T_{210681} := 211599^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 423199, 423201\}$ or $E := \{107181, 107182, \dots, 317860, 317861\}$
212. **(922, 212520, 212522)** $\Rightarrow 212522 - 922 = 460^2$, $S_{460 \times 460} := 98184240$, $T_{211600} := 212520^2$,
 $E := \{1845, 1847, \dots, 425041, 425043\}$
213. **(924, 213443, 213445)** $\Rightarrow 213445 - 924 = 461^2$, $S_{461 \times 461} := 98824109$, $T_{212521} := 213443^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 426887, 426889\}$ or $E := \{108109, 108110, \dots, 320628, 320629\}$
214. **(926, 214368, 214370)** $\Rightarrow 214370 - 926 = 462^2$, $S_{462 \times 462} := 99466752$, $T_{213444} := 214368^2$,
 $E := \{1853, 1855, \dots, 428737, 428739\}$
215. **(928, 215295, 215297)** $\Rightarrow 215297 - 928 = 463^2$, $S_{463 \times 463} := 100112175$, $T_{214369} := 215295^2$,
 $E := \{1857, 1859, \dots, 430591, 430593\}$ or $E := \{109041, 109042, \dots, 323408, 323409\}$
216. **(930, 216224, 216226)** $\Rightarrow 216226 - 930 = 464^2$, $S_{464 \times 464} := 100760384$, $T_{215296} := 216224^2$,
 $E := \{1861, 1863, \dots, 432449, 432451\}$
217. **(932, 217155, 217157)** $\Rightarrow 217157 - 932 = 465^2$, $S_{465 \times 465} := 101411385$, $T_{216225} := 217155^2$,
 $E := \{1865, 1867, \dots, 434311, 434313\}$ or $E := \{109977, 109978, \dots, 326200, 326201\}$
218. **(934, 218088, 218090)** $\Rightarrow 218090 - 934 = 466^2$, $S_{466 \times 466} := 102065184$, $T_{217156} := 218088^2$,
 $E := \{1869, 1871, \dots, 436177, 436179\}$
219. **(936, 219023, 219025)** $\Rightarrow 219025 - 936 = 467^2$, $S_{467 \times 467} := 102721787$, $T_{218089} := 219023^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 438047, 438049\}$ or $E := \{110917, 110918, \dots, 329004, 329005\}$

220. **(938, 219960, 219962)** $\Rightarrow 219962 - 938 = 468^2$, $S_{468 \times 468} := 103381200$, $T_{219024} := 219960^2$,
 $E := \{1877, 1879, \dots, 439921, 439923\}$
221. **(940, 220899, 220901)** $\Rightarrow 220901 - 940 = 469^2$, $S_{469 \times 469} := 104043429$, $T_{219961} := 220899^2$,
 $E := \{1881, 1883, \dots, 441799, 441801\}$ or $E := \{111861, 111862, \dots, 331820, 331821\}$
222. **(942, 221840, 221842)** $\Rightarrow 221842 - 942 = 470^2$, $S_{470 \times 470} := 104708480$, $T_{220900} := 221840^2$,
 $E := \{1885, 1887, \dots, 443681, 443683\}$
223. **(944, 222783, 222785)** $\Rightarrow 222785 - 944 = 471^2$, $S_{471 \times 471} := 105376359$, $T_{221841} := 222783^2$,
 $E := \{1889, 1891, \dots, 445567, 445569\}$ or $E := \{112809, 112810, \dots, 334648, 334649\}$
224. **(946, 223728, 223730)** $\Rightarrow 223730 - 946 = 472^2$, $S_{472 \times 472} := 106047072$, $T_{222784} := 223728^2$,
 $E := \{1893, 1895, \dots, 447457, 447459\}$
225. **(948, 224675, 224677)** $\Rightarrow 224677 - 948 = 473^2$, $S_{473 \times 473} := 106720625$, $T_{223729} := 224675^2$,
 $E := \{1897, 1899, \dots, 449351, 449353\}$ or $E := \{113761, 113762, \dots, 337488, 337489\}$
226. **(950, 225624, 225626)** $\Rightarrow 225626 - 950 = 474^2$, $S_{474 \times 474} := 107397024$, $T_{224676} := 225624^2$,
 $E := \{1901, 1903, \dots, 451249, 451251\}$
227. **(952, 226575, 226577)** $\Rightarrow 226577 - 952 = 475^2$, $S_{475 \times 475} := 108076275$, $T_{225625} := 226575^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 453151, 453153\}$ or $E := \{114717, 114718, \dots, 340340, 340341\}$
228. **(954, 227528, 227530)** $\Rightarrow 227530 - 954 = 476^2$, $S_{476 \times 476} := 108758384$, $T_{226576} := 227528^2$,
 $E := \{1909, 1911, \dots, 455057, 455059\}$
229. **(956, 228483, 228485)** $\Rightarrow 228485 - 956 = 477^2$, $S_{477 \times 477} := 109443357$, $T_{227529} := 228483^2$,
 $E := \{1913, 1915, \dots, 456967, 456969\}$ or $E := \{115677, 115678, \dots, 343204, 343205\}$
230. **(958, 229440, 229442)** $\Rightarrow 229442 - 958 = 478^2$, $S_{478 \times 478} := 110131200$, $T_{228484} := 229440^2$,
 $E := \{1917, 1919, \dots, 458881, 458883\}$
231. **(960, 230399, 230401)** $\Rightarrow 230401 - 960 = 479^2$, $S_{479 \times 479} := 110821919$, $T_{229441} := 230399^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 460799, 460801\}$ or $E := \{116641, 116642, \dots, 346080, 346081\}$
232. **(962, 231360, 231362)** $\Rightarrow 231362 - 962 = 480^2$, $S_{480 \times 480} := 111515520$, $T_{230400} := 231360^2$,
 $E := \{1925, 1927, \dots, 462721, 462723\}$
233. **(964, 232323, 232325)** $\Rightarrow 232325 - 964 = 481^2$, $S_{481 \times 481} := 112212009$, $T_{231361} := 232323^2$,
 $E := \{1929, 1931, \dots, 464647, 464649\}$ or $E := \{117609, 117610, \dots, 348968, 348969\}$
234. **(966, 233288, 233290)** $\Rightarrow 233290 - 966 = 482^2$, $S_{482 \times 482} := 112911392$, $T_{232324} := 233288^2$,
 $E := \{1933, 1935, \dots, 466577, 466579\}$
235. **(968, 234255, 234257)** $\Rightarrow 234257 - 968 = 483^2$, $S_{483 \times 483} := 113613675$, $T_{233289} := 234255^2$,
 $E := \{1937, 1939, \dots, 468511, 468513\}$ or $E := \{118581, 118582, \dots, 351868, 351869\}$
236. **(970, 235224, 235226)** $\Rightarrow 235226 - 970 = 484^2$, $S_{484 \times 484} := 114318864$, $T_{234256} := 235224^2$,
 $E := \{1941, 1943, \dots, 470449, 470451\}$

237. **(972, 236195, 236197)** $\Rightarrow 236197 - 972 = 485^2$, $S_{485 \times 485} := 115026965$, $T_{235225} := 236195^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 472391, 472393\}$ or $E := \{119557, 119558, \dots, 354780, 354781\}$
238. **(974, 237168, 237170)** $\Rightarrow 237170 - 974 = 486^2$, $S_{486 \times 486} := 115737984$, $T_{236196} := 237168^2$,
 $E := \{1949, 1951, \dots, 474337, 474339\}$
239. **(976, 238143, 238145)** $\Rightarrow 238145 - 976 = 487^2$, $S_{487 \times 487} := 116451927$, $T_{237169} := 238143^2$,
 $E := \{1953, 1955, \dots, 476287, 476289\}$ or $E := \{120537, 120538, \dots, 357704, 357705\}$
240. **(978, 239120, 239122)** $\Rightarrow 239122 - 978 = 488^2$, $S_{488 \times 488} := 117168800$, $T_{238144} := 239120^2$,
 $E := \{1957, 1959, \dots, 478241, 478243\}$
241. **(980, 240099, 240101)** $\Rightarrow 240101 - 980 = 489^2$, $S_{489 \times 489} := 117888609$, $T_{239121} := 240099^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 480199, 480201\}$ or $E := \{121521, 121522, \dots, 360640, 360641\}$
242. **(982, 241080, 241082)** $\Rightarrow 241082 - 982 = 490^2$, $S_{490 \times 490} := 118611360$, $T_{240100} := 241080^2$,
 $E := \{1965, 1967, \dots, 482161, 482163\}$
243. **(984, 242063, 242065)** $\Rightarrow 242065 - 984 = 491^2$, $S_{491 \times 491} := 119337059$, $T_{241081} := 242063^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 484127, 484129\}$ or $E := \{122509, 122510, \dots, 363588, 363589\}$
244. **(986, 243048, 243050)** $\Rightarrow 243050 - 986 = 492^2$, $S_{492 \times 492} := 120065712$, $T_{242064} := 243048^2$,
 $E := \{1973, 1975, \dots, 486097, 486099\}$
245. **(988, 244035, 244037)** $\Rightarrow 244037 - 988 = 493^2$, $S_{493 \times 493} := 120797325$, $T_{243049} := 244035^2$,
 $E := \{1977, 1979, \dots, 488071, 488073\}$ or $E := \{123501, 123502, \dots, 366548, 366549\}$
246. **(990, 245024, 245026)** $\Rightarrow 245026 - 990 = 494^2$, $S_{494 \times 494} := 121531904$, $T_{244036} := 245024^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 490049, 490051\}$
247. **(992, 246015, 246017)** $\Rightarrow 246017 - 992 = 495^2$, $S_{495 \times 495} := 122269455$, $T_{245025} := 246015^2$,
 $E := \{1985, 1987, \dots, 492031, 492033\}$ or $E := \{124497, 124498, \dots, 369520, 369521\}$
248. **(994, 247008, 247010)** $\Rightarrow 247010 - 994 = 496^2$, $S_{496 \times 496} := 123009984$, $T_{246016} := 247008^2$,
 $E := \{1989, 1991, \dots, 494017, 494019\}$
249. **(996, 248003, 248005)** $\Rightarrow 248005 - 996 = 497^2$, $S_{497 \times 497} := 123753497$, $T_{247009} := 248003^2$,
 $E := \{1993, 1995, \dots, 496007, 496009\}$ or $E := \{125497, 125498, \dots, 372504, 372505\}$
250. **(998, 249000, 249002)** $\Rightarrow 249002 - 998 = 498^2$, $S_{498 \times 498} := 124500000$, $T_{248004} := 249000^2$,
 $E := \{1997, 1999, \dots, 498001, 498003\}$
251. **(1000, 249999, 250001)** $\Rightarrow 250001 - 1000 = 499^2$, $S_{499 \times 499} := 125249499$, $T_{249001} := 249999^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 499999, 500001\}$ or $E := \{126501, 126502, \dots, 375500, 375501\}$

5 Even Order Triples and Magic Squares

From above we observe that for the **Pythagorean triples** starting with even number greater than or equal to **Pythagorean triple**8, i.e., (a, b, c) , $c > b > a$, $a \geq 8$, there is at least one triple resulting in a magic square with entries sum a perfect square. Let's suppose k be a order of magic square, then $2(k + 1)$ is the even number generating a magic square with entries sum a perfect square. In this case, for the **Pythagorean triple** (a, b, c) , the $a = 2(k + 1)$. All the magic square are with **consecutive odd number entries**, but in case of even order magic square still we can have **consecutive natural number entries**. In each case, these entries are also given. See the details below:

1. **(8, 15, 17)** $\Rightarrow 17 - 8 = 3^2$, $S_{3 \times 3} := 75$, $T_9 := 15^2$,
 $E := \{17, 19, \dots, 31, 33\}$ or $E := \{21, 22, \dots, 28, 29\}$
2. **(10, 24, 26)** $\Rightarrow 26 - 10 = 4^2$, $S_{4 \times 4} := 144$, $T_{16} := 24^2$,
 $E := \{21, 23, \dots, 49, 51\}$
3. **(12, 35, 37)** $\Rightarrow 37 - 12 = 5^2$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 245$, $T_{25} := 35^2$,
 $E := \{25, 27, \dots, 71, 73\}$ or $E := \{37, 38, \dots, 60, 61\}$
4. **(14, 48, 50)** $\Rightarrow 50 - 14 = 6^2$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 384$, $T_{36} := 48^2$,
 $E := \{29, 31, \dots, 97, 99\}$
5. **(16, 63, 65)** $\Rightarrow 65 - 16 = 7^2$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 567$, $T_{49} := 63^2$,
 $E := \{33, 35, \dots, 127, 129\}$ or $E := \{57, 58, \dots, 104, 105\}$
6. **(18, 80, 82)** $\Rightarrow 82 - 18 = 8^2$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 800$, $T_{64} := 80^2$,
 $E := \{37, 39, \dots, 161, 163\}$
7. **(20, 99, 101)** $\Rightarrow 101 - 20 = 9^2$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 1089$, $T_{81} := 99^2$,
 $E := \{41, 43, \dots, 199, 201\}$ or $E := \{81, 82, \dots, 160, 161\}$
8. **(22, 120, 122)** $\Rightarrow 122 - 22 = 10^2$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 1440$, $T_{100} := 120^2$,
 $E := \{45, 47, \dots, 241, 243\}$
9. **(24, 143, 145)** $\Rightarrow 145 - 24 = 11^2$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 1859$, $T_{121} := 143^2$,
 $E := \{49, 51, \dots, 287, 289\}$ or $E := \{109, 110, \dots, 228, 229\}$
10. **(26, 168, 170)** $\Rightarrow 170 - 26 = 12^2$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 2352$, $T_{144} := 168^2$,
 $E := \{53, 55, \dots, 337, 339\}$
11. **(28, 195, 197)** $\Rightarrow 197 - 28 = 13^2$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 2925$, $T_{169} := 195^2$,
 $E := \{57, 59, \dots, 391, 393\}$ or $E := \{141, 142, \dots, 308, 309\}$
12. **(30, 224, 226)** $\Rightarrow 226 - 30 = 14^2$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 3584$, $T_{196} := 224^2$,
 $E := \{61, 63, \dots, 449, 451\}$
13. **(32, 255, 257)** $\Rightarrow 257 - 32 = 15^2$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 4335$, $T_{225} := 255^2$,
 $E := \{65, 67, \dots, 511, 513\}$ or $E := \{177, 178, \dots, 400, 401\}$

14. **(34, 288, 290)** $\Rightarrow 290 - 34 = 16^2$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 5184$, $T_{256} := 288^2$,
 $E := \{69, 71, \dots, 577, 579\}$
15. **(36, 323, 325)** $\Rightarrow 325 - 36 = 17^2$, $S_{17 \times 17} := 6137$, $T_{289} := 323^2$,
 $E := \{73, 75, \dots, 647, 649\}$ or $E := \{217, 218, \dots, 504, 505\}$
16. **(38, 360, 362)** $\Rightarrow 362 - 38 = 18^2$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 7200$, $T_{324} := 360^2$,
 $E := \{77, 79, \dots, 721, 723\}$
17. **(40, 399, 401)** $\Rightarrow 401 - 40 = 19^2$, $S_{19 \times 19} := 8379$, $T_{361} := 399^2$,
 $E := \{81, 83, \dots, 799, 801\}$ or $E := \{261, 262, \dots, 620, 621\}$
18. **(42, 440, 442)** $\Rightarrow 442 - 42 = 20^2$, $S_{20 \times 20} := 9680$, $T_{400} := 440^2$,
 $E := \{85, 87, \dots, 881, 883\}$
19. **(44, 483, 485)** $\Rightarrow 485 - 44 = 21^2$, $S_{21 \times 21} := 11109$, $T_{441} := 483^2$,
 $E := \{89, 91, \dots, 967, 969\}$ or $E := \{309, 310, \dots, 748, 749\}$
20. **(46, 528, 530)** $\Rightarrow 530 - 46 = 22^2$, $S_{22 \times 22} := 12672$, $T_{484} := 528^2$,
 $E := \{93, 95, \dots, 1057, 1059\}$
21. **(48, 575, 577)** $\Rightarrow 577 - 48 = 23^2$, $S_{23 \times 23} := 14375$, $T_{529} := 575^2$,
 $E := \{97, 99, \dots, 1151, 1153\}$ or $E := \{361, 362, \dots, 888, 889\}$
22. **(50, 624, 626)** $\Rightarrow 626 - 50 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 16224$, $T_{576} := 624^2$,
 $E := \{101, 103, \dots, 1249, 1251\}$
23. **(52, 675, 677)** $\Rightarrow 677 - 52 = 25^2$, $S_{25 \times 25} := 18225$, $T_{625} := 675^2$,
 $E := \{105, 107, \dots, 1351, 1353\}$ or $E := \{417, 418, \dots, 1040, 1041\}$
24. **(54, 728, 730)** $\Rightarrow 730 - 54 = 26^2$, $S_{26 \times 26} := 20384$, $T_{676} := 728^2$,
 $E := \{109, 111, \dots, 1457, 1459\}$
25. **(56, 783, 785)** $\Rightarrow 785 - 56 = 27^2$, $S_{27 \times 27} := 22707$, $T_{729} := 783^2$,
 $E := \{113, 115, \dots, 1567, 1569\}$ or $E := \{477, 478, \dots, 1204, 1205\}$
26. **(58, 840, 842)** $\Rightarrow 842 - 58 = 28^2$, $S_{28 \times 28} := 25200$, $T_{784} := 840^2$,
 $E := \{117, 119, \dots, 1681, 1683\}$
27. **(60, 899, 901)** $\Rightarrow 901 - 60 = 29^2$, $S_{29 \times 29} := 27869$, $T_{841} := 899^2$,
 $E := \{121, 123, \dots, 1799, 1801\}$ or $E := \{541, 542, \dots, 1380, 1381\}$
28. **(62, 960, 962)** $\Rightarrow 962 - 62 = 30^2$, $S_{30 \times 30} := 30720$, $T_{900} := 960^2$,
 $E := \{125, 127, \dots, 1921, 1923\}$
29. **(64, 1023, 1025)** $\Rightarrow 1025 - 64 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 33759$, $T_{961} := 1023^2$,
 $E := \{129, 131, \dots, 2047, 2049\}$ or $E := \{609, 610, \dots, 1568, 1569\}$
30. **(66, 1088, 1090)** $\Rightarrow 1090 - 66 = 32^2$, $S_{32 \times 32} := 36992$, $T_{1024} := 1088^2$,
 $E := \{133, 135, \dots, 2177, 2179\}$

31. **(68, 1155, 1157)** $\Rightarrow 1157 - 68 = 33^2$, $S_{33 \times 33} := 40425$, $T_{1089} := 1155^2$,
 $E := \{137, 139, \dots, 2311, 2313\}$ or $E := \{681, 682, \dots, 1768, 1769\}$
32. **(70, 1224, 1226)** $\Rightarrow 1226 - 70 = 34^2$, $S_{34 \times 34} := 44064$, $T_{1156} := 1224^2$,
 $E := \{141, 143, \dots, 2449, 2451\}$
33. **(72, 1295, 1297)** $\Rightarrow 1297 - 72 = 35^2$, $S_{35 \times 35} := 47915$, $T_{1225} := 1295^2$,
 $E := \{145, 147, \dots, 2591, 2593\}$ or $E := \{757, 758, \dots, 1980, 1981\}$
34. **(74, 1368, 1370)** $\Rightarrow 1370 - 74 = 36^2$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 51984$, $T_{1296} := 1368^2$,
 $E := \{149, 151, \dots, 2737, 2739\}$
35. **(76, 1443, 1445)** $\Rightarrow 1445 - 76 = 37^2$, $S_{37 \times 37} := 56277$, $T_{1369} := 1443^2$,
 $E := \{153, 155, \dots, 2887, 2889\}$ or $E := \{837, 838, \dots, 2204, 2205\}$
36. **(78, 1520, 1522)** $\Rightarrow 1522 - 78 = 38^2$, $S_{38 \times 38} := 60800$, $T_{1444} := 1520^2$,
 $E := \{157, 159, \dots, 3041, 3043\}$
37. **(80, 1599, 1601)** $\Rightarrow 1601 - 80 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 65559$, $T_{1521} := 1599^2$,
 $E := \{161, 163, \dots, 3199, 3201\}$ or $E := \{921, 922, \dots, 2440, 2441\}$
38. **(82, 1680, 1682)** $\Rightarrow 1682 - 82 = 40^2$, $S_{40 \times 40} := 70560$, $T_{1600} := 1680^2$,
 $E := \{165, 167, \dots, 3361, 3363\}$
39. **(84, 1763, 1765)** $\Rightarrow 1765 - 84 = 41^2$, $S_{41 \times 41} := 75809$, $T_{1681} := 1763^2$,
 $E := \{169, 171, \dots, 3527, 3529\}$ or $E := \{1009, 1010, \dots, 2688, 2689\}$
40. **(86, 1848, 1850)** $\Rightarrow 1850 - 86 = 42^2$, $S_{42 \times 42} := 81312$, $T_{1764} := 1848^2$,
 $E := \{173, 175, \dots, 3697, 3699\}$
41. **(88, 1935, 1937)** $\Rightarrow 1937 - 88 = 43^2$, $S_{43 \times 43} := 87075$, $T_{1849} := 1935^2$,
 $E := \{177, 179, \dots, 3871, 3873\}$ or $E := \{1101, 1102, \dots, 2948, 2949\}$
42. **(90, 2024, 2026)** $\Rightarrow 2026 - 90 = 44^2$, $S_{44 \times 44} := 93104$, $T_{1936} := 2024^2$,
 $E := \{181, 183, \dots, 4049, 4051\}$
43. **(92, 2115, 2117)** $\Rightarrow 2117 - 92 = 45^2$, $S_{45 \times 45} := 99405$, $T_{2025} := 2115^2$,
 $E := \{185, 187, \dots, 4231, 4233\}$ or $E := \{1197, 1198, \dots, 3220, 3221\}$
44. **(94, 2208, 2210)** $\Rightarrow 2210 - 94 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 105984$, $T_{2116} := 2208^2$,
 $E := \{189, 191, \dots, 4417, 4419\}$
45. **(96, 2303, 2305)** $\Rightarrow 2305 - 96 = 47^2$, $S_{47 \times 47} := 112847$, $T_{2209} := 2303^2$,
 $E := \{193, 195, \dots, 4607, 4609\}$ or $E := \{1297, 1298, \dots, 3504, 3505\}$
46. **(98, 2400, 2402)** $\Rightarrow 2402 - 98 = 48^2$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 120000$, $T_{2304} := 2400^2$,
 $E := \{197, 199, \dots, 4801, 4803\}$
47. **(100, 2499, 2501)** $\Rightarrow 2501 - 100 = 49^2$, $S_{49 \times 49} := 127449$, $T_{2401} := 2499^2$,
 $E := \{201, 203, \dots, 4999, 5001\}$ or $E := \{1401, 1402, \dots, 3800, 3801\}$

48. **(102, 2600, 2602)** $\Rightarrow 2602 - 102 = 50^2$, $S_{50 \times 50} := 135200$, $T_{2500} := 2600^2$,
 $E := \{205, 207, \dots, 5201, 5203\}$
49. **(104, 2703, 2705)** $\Rightarrow 2705 - 104 = 51^2$, $S_{51 \times 51} := 143259$, $T_{2601} := 2703^2$,
 $E := \{209, 211, \dots, 5407, 5409\}$ or $E := \{1509, 1510, \dots, 4108, 4109\}$
50. **(106, 2808, 2810)** $\Rightarrow 2810 - 106 = 52^2$, $S_{52 \times 52} := 151632$, $T_{2704} := 2808^2$,
 $E := \{213, 215, \dots, 5617, 5619\}$
51. **(108, 2915, 2917)** $\Rightarrow 2917 - 108 = 53^2$, $S_{53 \times 53} := 160325$, $T_{2809} := 2915^2$,
 $E := \{217, 219, \dots, 5831, 5833\}$ or $E := \{1621, 1622, \dots, 4428, 4429\}$
52. **(110, 3024, 3026)** $\Rightarrow 3026 - 110 = 54^2$, $S_{54 \times 54} := 169344$, $T_{2916} := 3024^2$,
 $E := \{221, 223, \dots, 6049, 6051\}$
53. **(112, 3135, 3137)** $\Rightarrow 3137 - 112 = 55^2$, $S_{55 \times 55} := 178695$, $T_{3025} := 3135^2$,
 $E := \{225, 227, \dots, 6271, 6273\}$ or $E := \{1737, 1738, \dots, 4760, 4761\}$
54. **(114, 3248, 3250)** $\Rightarrow 3250 - 114 = 56^2$, $S_{56 \times 56} := 188384$, $T_{3136} := 3248^2$,
 $E := \{229, 231, \dots, 6497, 6499\}$
55. **(116, 3363, 3365)** $\Rightarrow 3365 - 116 = 57^2$, $S_{57 \times 57} := 198417$, $T_{3249} := 3363^2$,
 $E := \{233, 235, \dots, 6727, 6729\}$ or $E := \{1857, 1858, \dots, 5104, 5105\}$
56. **(118, 3480, 3482)** $\Rightarrow 3482 - 118 = 58^2$, $S_{58 \times 58} := 208800$, $T_{3364} := 3480^2$,
 $E := \{237, 239, \dots, 6961, 6963\}$
57. **(120, 3599, 3601)** $\Rightarrow 3601 - 120 = 59^2$, $S_{59 \times 59} := 219539$, $T_{3481} := 3599^2$,
 $E := \{241, 243, \dots, 7199, 7201\}$ or $E := \{1981, 1982, \dots, 5460, 5461\}$
58. **(122, 3720, 3722)** $\Rightarrow 3722 - 122 = 60^2$, $S_{60 \times 60} := 230640$, $T_{3600} := 3720^2$,
 $E := \{245, 247, \dots, 7441, 7443\}$
59. **(124, 3843, 3845)** $\Rightarrow 3845 - 124 = 61^2$, $S_{61 \times 61} := 242109$, $T_{3721} := 3843^2$,
 $E := \{249, 251, \dots, 7687, 7689\}$ or $E := \{2109, 2110, \dots, 5828, 5829\}$
60. **(126, 3968, 3970)** $\Rightarrow 3970 - 126 = 62^2$, $S_{62 \times 62} := 253952$, $T_{3844} := 3968^2$,
 $E := \{253, 255, \dots, 7937, 7939\}$
61. **(128, 4095, 4097)** $\Rightarrow 4097 - 128 = 63^2$, $S_{63 \times 63} := 266175$, $T_{3969} := 4095^2$,
 $E := \{257, 259, \dots, 8191, 8193\}$ or $E := \{2241, 2242, \dots, 6208, 6209\}$
62. **(130, 4224, 4226)** $\Rightarrow 4226 - 130 = 64^2$, $S_{64 \times 64} := 278784$, $T_{4096} := 4224^2$,
 $E := \{261, 263, \dots, 8449, 8451\}$
63. **(132, 4355, 4357)** $\Rightarrow 4357 - 132 = 65^2$, $S_{65 \times 65} := 291785$, $T_{4225} := 4355^2$,
 $E := \{265, 267, \dots, 8711, 8713\}$ or $E := \{2377, 2378, \dots, 6600, 6601\}$
64. **(134, 4488, 4490)** $\Rightarrow 4490 - 134 = 66^2$, $S_{66 \times 66} := 305184$, $T_{4356} := 4488^2$,
 $E := \{269, 271, \dots, 8977, 8979\}$

65. **(136, 4623, 4625)** $\Rightarrow 4625 - 136 = 67^2$, $S_{67 \times 67} := 318987$, $T_{4489} := 4623^2$,
 $E := \{273, 275, \dots, 9247, 9249\}$ or $E := \{2517, 2518, \dots, 7004, 7005\}$
66. **(138, 4760, 4762)** $\Rightarrow 4762 - 138 = 68^2$, $S_{68 \times 68} := 333200$, $T_{4624} := 4760^2$,
 $E := \{277, 279, \dots, 9521, 9523\}$
67. **(140, 4899, 4901)** $\Rightarrow 4901 - 140 = 69^2$, $S_{69 \times 69} := 347829$, $T_{4761} := 4899^2$,
 $E := \{281, 283, \dots, 9799, 9801\}$ or $E := \{2661, 2662, \dots, 7420, 7421\}$
68. **(142, 5040, 5042)** $\Rightarrow 5042 - 142 = 70^2$, $S_{70 \times 70} := 362880$, $T_{4900} := 5040^2$,
 $E := \{285, 287, \dots, 10081, 10083\}$
69. **(144, 5183, 5185)** $\Rightarrow 5185 - 144 = 71^2$, $S_{71 \times 71} := 378359$, $T_{5041} := 5183^2$,
 $E := \{289, 291, \dots, 10367, 10369\}$ or $E := \{2809, 2810, \dots, 7848, 7849\}$
70. **(146, 5328, 5330)** $\Rightarrow 5330 - 146 = 72^2$, $S_{72 \times 72} := 394272$, $T_{5184} := 5328^2$,
 $E := \{293, 295, \dots, 10657, 10659\}$
71. **(148, 5475, 5477)** $\Rightarrow 5477 - 148 = 73^2$, $S_{73 \times 73} := 410625$, $T_{5329} := 5475^2$,
 $E := \{297, 299, \dots, 10951, 10953\}$ or $E := \{2961, 2962, \dots, 8288, 8289\}$
72. **(150, 5624, 5626)** $\Rightarrow 5626 - 150 = 74^2$, $S_{74 \times 74} := 427424$, $T_{5476} := 5624^2$,
 $E := \{301, 303, \dots, 11249, 11251\}$
73. **(152, 5775, 5777)** $\Rightarrow 5777 - 152 = 75^2$, $S_{75 \times 75} := 444675$, $T_{5625} := 5775^2$,
 $E := \{305, 307, \dots, 11551, 11553\}$ or $E := \{3117, 3118, \dots, 8740, 8741\}$
74. **(154, 5928, 5930)** $\Rightarrow 5930 - 154 = 76^2$, $S_{76 \times 76} := 462384$, $T_{5776} := 5928^2$,
 $E := \{309, 311, \dots, 11857, 11859\}$
75. **(156, 6083, 6085)** $\Rightarrow 6085 - 156 = 77^2$, $S_{77 \times 77} := 480557$, $T_{5929} := 6083^2$,
 $E := \{313, 315, \dots, 12167, 12169\}$ or $E := \{3277, 3278, \dots, 9204, 9205\}$
76. **(158, 6240, 6242)** $\Rightarrow 6242 - 158 = 78^2$, $S_{78 \times 78} := 499200$, $T_{6084} := 6240^2$,
 $E := \{317, 319, \dots, 12481, 12483\}$
77. **(160, 6399, 6401)** $\Rightarrow 6401 - 160 = 79^2$, $S_{79 \times 79} := 518319$, $T_{6241} := 6399^2$,
 $E := \{321, 323, \dots, 12799, 12801\}$ or $E := \{3441, 3442, \dots, 9680, 9681\}$
78. **(162, 6560, 6562)** $\Rightarrow 6562 - 162 = 80^2$, $S_{80 \times 80} := 537920$, $T_{6400} := 6560^2$,
 $E := \{325, 327, \dots, 13121, 13123\}$
79. **(164, 6723, 6725)** $\Rightarrow 6725 - 164 = 81^2$, $S_{81 \times 81} := 558009$, $T_{6561} := 6723^2$,
 $E := \{329, 331, \dots, 13447, 13449\}$ or $E := \{3609, 3610, \dots, 10168, 10169\}$
80. **(166, 6888, 6890)** $\Rightarrow 6890 - 166 = 82^2$, $S_{82 \times 82} := 578592$, $T_{6724} := 6888^2$,
 $E := \{333, 335, \dots, 13777, 13779\}$
81. **(168, 7055, 7057)** $\Rightarrow 7057 - 168 = 83^2$, $S_{83 \times 83} := 599675$, $T_{6889} := 7055^2$,
 $E := \{337, 339, \dots, 14111, 14113\}$ or $E := \{3781, 3782, \dots, 10668, 10669\}$

82. **(170, 7224, 7226)** $\Rightarrow 7226 - 170 = 84^2$, $S_{84 \times 84} := 621264$, $T_{7056} := 7224^2$,
 $E := \{341, 343, \dots, 14449, 14451\}$
83. **(172, 7395, 7397)** $\Rightarrow 7397 - 172 = 85^2$, $S_{85 \times 85} := 643365$, $T_{7225} := 7395^2$,
 $E := \{345, 347, \dots, 14791, 14793\}$ or $E := \{3957, 3958, \dots, 11180, 11181\}$
84. **(174, 7568, 7570)** $\Rightarrow 7570 - 174 = 86^2$, $S_{86 \times 86} := 665984$, $T_{7396} := 7568^2$,
 $E := \{349, 351, \dots, 15137, 15139\}$
85. **(176, 7743, 7745)** $\Rightarrow 7745 - 176 = 87^2$, $S_{87 \times 87} := 689127$, $T_{7569} := 7743^2$,
 $E := \{353, 355, \dots, 15487, 15489\}$ or $E := \{4137, 4138, \dots, 11704, 11705\}$
86. **(178, 7920, 7922)** $\Rightarrow 7922 - 178 = 88^2$, $S_{88 \times 88} := 712800$, $T_{7744} := 7920^2$,
 $E := \{357, 359, \dots, 15841, 15843\}$
87. **(180, 8099, 8101)** $\Rightarrow 8101 - 180 = 89^2$, $S_{89 \times 89} := 737009$, $T_{7921} := 8099^2$,
 $E := \{361, 363, \dots, 16199, 16201\}$ or $E := \{4321, 4322, \dots, 12240, 12241\}$
88. **(182, 8280, 8282)** $\Rightarrow 8282 - 182 = 90^2$, $S_{90 \times 90} := 761760$, $T_{8100} := 8280^2$,
 $E := \{365, 367, \dots, 16561, 16563\}$
89. **(184, 8463, 8465)** $\Rightarrow 8465 - 184 = 91^2$, $S_{91 \times 91} := 787059$, $T_{8281} := 8463^2$,
 $E := \{369, 371, \dots, 16927, 16929\}$ or $E := \{4509, 4510, \dots, 12788, 12789\}$
90. **(186, 8648, 8650)** $\Rightarrow 8650 - 186 = 92^2$, $S_{92 \times 92} := 812912$, $T_{8464} := 8648^2$,
 $E := \{373, 375, \dots, 17297, 17299\}$
91. **(188, 8835, 8837)** $\Rightarrow 8837 - 188 = 93^2$, $S_{93 \times 93} := 839325$, $T_{8649} := 8835^2$,
 $E := \{377, 379, \dots, 17671, 17673\}$ or $E := \{4701, 4702, \dots, 13348, 13349\}$
92. **(190, 9024, 9026)** $\Rightarrow 9026 - 190 = 94^2$, $S_{94 \times 94} := 866304$, $T_{8836} := 9024^2$,
 $E := \{381, 383, \dots, 18049, 18051\}$
93. **(192, 9215, 9217)** $\Rightarrow 9217 - 192 = 95^2$, $S_{95 \times 95} := 893855$, $T_{9025} := 9215^2$,
 $E := \{385, 387, \dots, 18431, 18433\}$ or $E := \{4897, 4898, \dots, 13920, 13921\}$
94. **(194, 9408, 9410)** $\Rightarrow 9410 - 194 = 96^2$, $S_{96 \times 96} := 921984$, $T_{9216} := 9408^2$,
 $E := \{389, 391, \dots, 18817, 18819\}$
95. **(196, 9603, 9605)** $\Rightarrow 9605 - 196 = 97^2$, $S_{97 \times 97} := 950697$, $T_{9409} := 9603^2$,
 $E := \{393, 395, \dots, 19207, 19209\}$ or $E := \{5097, 5098, \dots, 14504, 14505\}$
96. **(198, 9800, 9802)** $\Rightarrow 9802 - 198 = 98^2$, $S_{98 \times 98} := 980000$, $T_{9604} := 9800^2$,
 $E := \{397, 399, \dots, 19601, 19603\}$
97. **(200, 9999, 10001)** $\Rightarrow 10001 - 200 = 99^2$, $S_{99 \times 99} := 1009899$, $T_{9801} := 9999^2$,
 $E := \{401, 403, \dots, 19999, 20001\}$ or $E := \{5301, 5302, \dots, 15100, 15101\}$
98. **(202, 10200, 10202)** $\Rightarrow 10202 - 202 = 100^2$, $S_{100 \times 100} := 1040400$, $T_{10000} := 10200^2$,
 $E := \{405, 407, \dots, 20401, 20403\}$

99. **(204, 10403, 10405)** $\Rightarrow 10405 - 204 = 101^2$, $S_{101 \times 101} := 1071509$, $T_{10201} := 10403^2$,
 $E := \{409, 411, \dots, 20807, 20809\}$ or $E := \{5509, 5510, \dots, 15708, 15709\}$
100. **(206, 10608, 10610)** $\Rightarrow 10610 - 206 = 102^2$, $S_{102 \times 102} := 1103232$, $T_{10404} := 10608^2$,
 $E := \{413, 415, \dots, 21217, 21219\}$
101. **(208, 10815, 10817)** $\Rightarrow 10817 - 208 = 103^2$, $S_{103 \times 103} := 1135575$, $T_{10609} := 10815^2$,
 $E := \{417, 419, \dots, 21631, 21633\}$ or $E := \{5721, 5722, \dots, 16328, 16329\}$
102. **(210, 11024, 11026)** $\Rightarrow 11026 - 210 = 104^2$, $S_{104 \times 104} := 1168544$, $T_{10816} := 11024^2$,
 $E := \{421, 423, \dots, 22049, 22051\}$
103. **(212, 11235, 11237)** $\Rightarrow 11237 - 212 = 105^2$, $S_{105 \times 105} := 1202145$, $T_{11025} := 11235^2$,
 $E := \{425, 427, \dots, 22471, 22473\}$ or $E := \{5937, 5938, \dots, 16960, 16961\}$
104. **(214, 11448, 11450)** $\Rightarrow 11450 - 214 = 106^2$, $S_{106 \times 106} := 1236384$, $T_{11236} := 11448^2$,
 $E := \{429, 431, \dots, 22897, 22899\}$
105. **(216, 11663, 11665)** $\Rightarrow 11665 - 216 = 107^2$, $S_{107 \times 107} := 1271267$, $T_{11449} := 11663^2$,
 $E := \{433, 435, \dots, 23327, 23329\}$ or $E := \{6157, 6158, \dots, 17604, 17605\}$
106. **(218, 11880, 11882)** $\Rightarrow 11882 - 218 = 108^2$, $S_{108 \times 108} := 1306800$, $T_{11664} := 11880^2$,
 $E := \{437, 439, \dots, 23761, 23763\}$
107. **(220, 12099, 12101)** $\Rightarrow 12101 - 220 = 109^2$, $S_{109 \times 109} := 1342989$, $T_{11881} := 12099^2$,
 $E := \{441, 443, \dots, 24199, 24201\}$ or $E := \{6381, 6382, \dots, 18260, 18261\}$
108. **(222, 12320, 12322)** $\Rightarrow 12322 - 222 = 110^2$, $S_{110 \times 110} := 1379840$, $T_{12100} := 12320^2$,
 $E := \{445, 447, \dots, 24641, 24643\}$
109. **(224, 12543, 12545)** $\Rightarrow 12545 - 224 = 111^2$, $S_{111 \times 111} := 1417359$, $T_{12321} := 12543^2$,
 $E := \{449, 451, \dots, 25087, 25089\}$ or $E := \{6609, 6610, \dots, 18928, 18929\}$
110. **(226, 12768, 12770)** $\Rightarrow 12770 - 226 = 112^2$, $S_{112 \times 112} := 1455552$, $T_{12544} := 12768^2$,
 $E := \{453, 455, \dots, 25537, 25539\}$
111. **(228, 12995, 12997)** $\Rightarrow 12997 - 228 = 113^2$, $S_{113 \times 113} := 1494425$, $T_{12769} := 12995^2$,
 $E := \{457, 459, \dots, 25991, 25993\}$ or $E := \{6841, 6842, \dots, 19608, 19609\}$
112. **(230, 13224, 13226)** $\Rightarrow 13226 - 230 = 114^2$, $S_{114 \times 114} := 1533984$, $T_{12996} := 13224^2$,
 $E := \{461, 463, \dots, 26449, 26451\}$
113. **(232, 13455, 13457)** $\Rightarrow 13457 - 232 = 115^2$, $S_{115 \times 115} := 1574235$, $T_{13225} := 13455^2$,
 $E := \{465, 467, \dots, 26911, 26913\}$ or $E := \{7077, 7078, \dots, 20300, 20301\}$
114. **(234, 13688, 13690)** $\Rightarrow 13690 - 234 = 116^2$, $S_{116 \times 116} := 1615184$, $T_{13456} := 13688^2$,
 $E := \{469, 471, \dots, 27377, 27379\}$
115. **(236, 13923, 13925)** $\Rightarrow 13925 - 236 = 117^2$, $S_{117 \times 117} := 1656837$, $T_{13689} := 13923^2$,
 $E := \{473, 475, \dots, 27847, 27849\}$ or $E := \{7317, 7318, \dots, 21004, 21005\}$

116. **(238, 14160, 14162)** $\Rightarrow 14162 - 238 = 118^2$, $S_{118 \times 118} := 1699200$, $T_{13924} := 14160^2$,
 $E := \{477, 479, \dots, 28321, 28323\}$
117. **(240, 14399, 14401)** $\Rightarrow 14401 - 240 = 119^2$, $S_{119 \times 119} := 1742279$, $T_{14161} := 14399^2$,
 $E := \{481, 483, \dots, 28799, 28801\}$ or $E := \{7561, 7562, \dots, 21720, 21721\}$
118. **(242, 14640, 14642)** $\Rightarrow 14642 - 242 = 120^2$, $S_{120 \times 120} := 1786080$, $T_{14400} := 14640^2$,
 $E := \{485, 487, \dots, 29281, 29283\}$
119. **(244, 14883, 14885)** $\Rightarrow 14885 - 244 = 121^2$, $S_{121 \times 121} := 1830609$, $T_{14641} := 14883^2$,
 $E := \{489, 491, \dots, 29767, 29769\}$ or $E := \{7809, 7810, \dots, 22448, 22449\}$
120. **(248, 15375, 15377)** $\Rightarrow 15377 - 248 = 123^2$, $S_{123 \times 123} := 1921875$, $T_{15129} := 15375^2$,
 $E := \{497, 499, \dots, 30751, 30753\}$ or $E := \{8061, 8062, \dots, 23188, 23189\}$
121. **(250, 15624, 15626)** $\Rightarrow 15626 - 250 = 124^2$, $S_{124 \times 124} := 1968624$, $T_{15376} := 15624^2$,
 $E := \{501, 503, \dots, 31249, 31251\}$
122. **(252, 15875, 15877)** $\Rightarrow 15877 - 252 = 125^2$, $S_{125 \times 125} := 2016125$, $T_{15625} := 15875^2$,
 $E := \{505, 507, \dots, 31751, 31753\}$ or $E := \{8317, 8318, \dots, 23940, 23941\}$
123. **(254, 16128, 16130)** $\Rightarrow 16130 - 254 = 126^2$, $S_{126 \times 126} := 2064384$, $T_{15876} := 16128^2$,
 $E := \{509, 511, \dots, 32257, 32259\}$
124. **(256, 16383, 16385)** $\Rightarrow 16385 - 256 = 127^2$, $S_{127 \times 127} := 2113407$, $T_{16129} := 16383^2$,
 $E := \{513, 515, \dots, 32767, 32769\}$ or $E := \{8577, 8578, \dots, 24704, 24705\}$
125. **(258, 16640, 16642)** $\Rightarrow 16642 - 258 = 128^2$, $S_{128 \times 128} := 2163200$, $T_{16384} := 16640^2$,
 $E := \{517, 519, \dots, 33281, 33283\}$
126. **(260, 16899, 16901)** $\Rightarrow 16901 - 260 = 129^2$, $S_{129 \times 129} := 2213769$, $T_{16641} := 16899^2$,
 $E := \{521, 523, \dots, 33799, 33801\}$ or $E := \{8841, 8842, \dots, 25480, 25481\}$
127. **(262, 17160, 17162)** $\Rightarrow 17162 - 262 = 130^2$, $S_{130 \times 130} := 2265120$, $T_{16900} := 17160^2$,
 $E := \{525, 527, \dots, 34321, 34323\}$
128. **(264, 17423, 17425)** $\Rightarrow 17425 - 264 = 131^2$, $S_{131 \times 131} := 2317259$, $T_{17161} := 17423^2$,
 $E := \{529, 531, \dots, 34847, 34849\}$ or $E := \{9109, 9110, \dots, 26268, 26269\}$
129. **(266, 17688, 17690)** $\Rightarrow 17690 - 266 = 132^2$, $S_{132 \times 132} := 2370192$, $T_{17424} := 17688^2$,
 $E := \{533, 535, \dots, 35377, 35379\}$
130. **(268, 17955, 17957)** $\Rightarrow 17957 - 268 = 133^2$, $S_{133 \times 133} := 2423925$, $T_{17689} := 17955^2$,
 $E := \{537, 539, \dots, 35911, 35913\}$ or $E := \{9381, 9382, \dots, 27068, 27069\}$
131. **(270, 18224, 18226)** $\Rightarrow 18226 - 270 = 134^2$, $S_{134 \times 134} := 2478464$, $T_{17956} := 18224^2$,
 $E := \{541, 543, \dots, 36449, 36451\}$
132. **(272, 18495, 18497)** $\Rightarrow 18497 - 272 = 135^2$, $S_{135 \times 135} := 2533815$, $T_{18225} := 18495^2$,
 $E := \{545, 547, \dots, 36991, 36993\}$ or $E := \{9657, 9658, \dots, 27880, 27881\}$

133. **(274, 18768, 18770)** $\Rightarrow 18770 - 274 = 136^2$, $S_{136 \times 136} := 2589984$, $T_{18496} := 18768^2$,
 $E := \{549, 551, \dots, 37537, 37539\}$
134. **(276, 19043, 19045)** $\Rightarrow 19045 - 276 = 137^2$, $S_{137 \times 137} := 2646977$, $T_{18769} := 19043^2$,
 $E := \{553, 555, \dots, 38087, 38089\}$ or $E := \{9937, 9938, \dots, 28704, 28705\}$
135. **(278, 19320, 19322)** $\Rightarrow 19322 - 278 = 138^2$, $S_{138 \times 138} := 2704800$, $T_{19044} := 19320^2$,
 $E := \{557, 559, \dots, 38641, 38643\}$
136. **(280, 19599, 19601)** $\Rightarrow 19601 - 280 = 139^2$, $S_{139 \times 139} := 2763459$, $T_{19321} := 19599^2$,
 $E := \{561, 563, \dots, 39199, 39201\}$ or $E := \{10221, 10222, \dots, 29540, 29541\}$
137. **(282, 19880, 19882)** $\Rightarrow 19882 - 282 = 140^2$, $S_{140 \times 140} := 2822960$, $T_{19600} := 19880^2$,
 $E := \{565, 567, \dots, 39761, 39763\}$
138. **(284, 20163, 20165)** $\Rightarrow 20165 - 284 = 141^2$, $S_{141 \times 141} := 2883309$, $T_{19881} := 20163^2$,
 $E := \{569, 571, \dots, 40327, 40329\}$ or $E := \{10509, 10510, \dots, 30388, 30389\}$
139. **(286, 20448, 20450)** $\Rightarrow 20450 - 286 = 142^2$, $S_{142 \times 142} := 2944512$, $T_{20164} := 20448^2$,
 $E := \{573, 575, \dots, 40897, 40899\}$
140. **(288, 20735, 20737)** $\Rightarrow 20737 - 288 = 143^2$, $S_{143 \times 143} := 3006575$, $T_{20449} := 20735^2$,
 $E := \{577, 579, \dots, 41471, 41473\}$ or $E := \{10801, 10802, \dots, 31248, 31249\}$
141. **(290, 21024, 21026)** $\Rightarrow 21026 - 290 = 144^2$, $S_{144 \times 144} := 3069504$, $T_{20736} := 21024^2$,
 $E := \{581, 583, \dots, 42049, 42051\}$
142. **(292, 21315, 21317)** $\Rightarrow 21317 - 292 = 145^2$, $S_{145 \times 145} := 3133305$, $T_{21025} := 21315^2$,
 $E := \{585, 587, \dots, 42631, 42633\}$ or $E := \{11097, 11098, \dots, 32120, 32121\}$
143. **(294, 21608, 21610)** $\Rightarrow 21610 - 294 = 146^2$, $S_{146 \times 146} := 3197984$, $T_{21316} := 21608^2$,
 $E := \{589, 591, \dots, 43217, 43219\}$
144. **(296, 21903, 21905)** $\Rightarrow 21905 - 296 = 147^2$, $S_{147 \times 147} := 3263547$, $T_{21609} := 21903^2$,
 $E := \{593, 595, \dots, 43807, 43809\}$ or $E := \{11397, 11398, \dots, 33004, 33005\}$
145. **(298, 22200, 22202)** $\Rightarrow 22202 - 298 = 148^2$, $S_{148 \times 148} := 3330000$, $T_{21904} := 22200^2$,
 $E := \{597, 599, \dots, 44401, 44403\}$
146. **(300, 22499, 22501)** $\Rightarrow 22501 - 300 = 149^2$, $S_{149 \times 149} := 3397349$, $T_{22201} := 22499^2$,
 $E := \{601, 603, \dots, 44999, 45001\}$ or $E := \{11701, 11702, \dots, 33900, 33901\}$
147. **(302, 22800, 22802)** $\Rightarrow 22802 - 302 = 150^2$, $S_{150 \times 150} := 3465600$, $T_{22500} := 22800^2$,
 $E := \{605, 607, \dots, 45601, 45603\}$
148. **(304, 23103, 23105)** $\Rightarrow 23105 - 304 = 151^2$, $S_{151 \times 151} := 3534759$, $T_{22801} := 23103^2$,
 $E := \{609, 611, \dots, 46207, 46209\}$ or $E := \{12009, 12010, \dots, 34808, 34809\}$
149. **(306, 23408, 23410)** $\Rightarrow 23410 - 306 = 152^2$, $S_{152 \times 152} := 3604832$, $T_{23104} := 23408^2$,
 $E := \{613, 615, \dots, 46817, 46819\}$

150. **(308, 23715, 23717)** $\Rightarrow 23717 - 308 = 153^2$, $S_{153 \times 153} := 3675825$, $T_{23409} := 23715^2$,
 $E := \{617, 619, \dots, 47431, 47433\}$ or $E := \{12321, 12322, \dots, 35728, 35729\}$
151. **(310, 24024, 24026)** $\Rightarrow 24026 - 310 = 154^2$, $S_{154 \times 154} := 3747744$, $T_{23716} := 24024^2$,
 $E := \{621, 623, \dots, 48049, 48051\}$
152. **(312, 24335, 24337)** $\Rightarrow 24337 - 312 = 155^2$, $S_{155 \times 155} := 3820595$, $T_{24025} := 24335^2$,
 $E := \{625, 627, \dots, 48671, 48673\}$ or $E := \{12637, 12638, \dots, 36660, 36661\}$
153. **(314, 24648, 24650)** $\Rightarrow 24650 - 314 = 156^2$, $S_{156 \times 156} := 3894384$, $T_{24336} := 24648^2$,
 $E := \{629, 631, \dots, 49297, 49299\}$
154. **(316, 24963, 24965)** $\Rightarrow 24965 - 316 = 157^2$, $S_{157 \times 157} := 3969117$, $T_{24649} := 24963^2$,
 $E := \{633, 635, \dots, 49927, 49929\}$ or $E := \{12957, 12958, \dots, 37604, 37605\}$
155. **(318, 25280, 25282)** $\Rightarrow 25282 - 318 = 158^2$, $S_{158 \times 158} := 4044800$, $T_{24964} := 25280^2$,
 $E := \{637, 639, \dots, 50561, 50563\}$
156. **(320, 25599, 25601)** $\Rightarrow 25601 - 320 = 159^2$, $S_{159 \times 159} := 4121439$, $T_{25281} := 25599^2$,
 $E := \{641, 643, \dots, 51199, 51201\}$ or $E := \{13281, 13282, \dots, 38560, 38561\}$
157. **(322, 25920, 25922)** $\Rightarrow 25922 - 322 = 160^2$, $S_{160 \times 160} := 4199040$, $T_{25600} := 25920^2$,
 $E := \{645, 647, \dots, 51841, 51843\}$
158. **(324, 26247, 26249)** $\Rightarrow 26249 - 324 = 161^2$, $S_{161 \times 161} := 4277609$, $T_{25921} := 26247^2$,
 $E := \{649, 651, \dots, 52487, 52489\}$ or $E := \{13609, 13610, \dots, 39528, 39529\}$
159. **(326, 26568, 26570)** $\Rightarrow 26570 - 326 = 162^2$, $S_{162 \times 162} := 4357152$, $T_{26244} := 26568^2$,
 $E := \{653, 655, \dots, 53137, 53139\}$
160. **(328, 26895, 26897)** $\Rightarrow 26897 - 328 = 163^2$, $S_{163 \times 163} := 4437675$, $T_{26569} := 26895^2$,
 $E := \{657, 659, \dots, 53791, 53793\}$ or $E := \{13941, 13942, \dots, 40508, 40509\}$
161. **(330, 27224, 27226)** $\Rightarrow 27226 - 330 = 164^2$, $S_{164 \times 164} := 4519184$, $T_{26896} := 27224^2$,
 $E := \{661, 663, \dots, 54449, 54451\}$
162. **(332, 27555, 27557)** $\Rightarrow 27557 - 332 = 165^2$, $S_{165 \times 165} := 4601685$, $T_{27225} := 27555^2$,
 $E := \{665, 667, \dots, 55111, 55113\}$ or $E := \{14277, 14278, \dots, 41500, 41501\}$
163. **(334, 27888, 27890)** $\Rightarrow 27890 - 334 = 166^2$, $S_{166 \times 166} := 4685184$, $T_{27556} := 27888^2$,
 $E := \{669, 671, \dots, 55777, 55779\}$
164. **(336, 28223, 28225)** $\Rightarrow 28225 - 336 = 167^2$, $S_{167 \times 167} := 4769687$, $T_{27889} := 28223^2$,
 $E := \{673, 675, \dots, 56447, 56449\}$ or $E := \{14617, 14618, \dots, 42504, 42505\}$
165. **(338, 28560, 28562)** $\Rightarrow 28562 - 338 = 168^2$, $S_{168 \times 168} := 4855200$, $T_{28224} := 28560^2$,
 $E := \{677, 679, \dots, 57121, 57123\}$
166. **(340, 28899, 28901)** $\Rightarrow 28901 - 340 = 169^2$, $S_{169 \times 169} := 4941729$, $T_{28561} := 28899^2$,
 $E := \{681, 683, \dots, 57799, 57801\}$ or $E := \{14961, 14962, \dots, 43520, 43521\}$

167. **(342, 29240, 29242)** $\Rightarrow 29242 - 342 = 170^2$, $S_{170 \times 170} := 5029280$, $T_{28900} := 29240^2$,
 $E := \{685, 687, \dots, 58481, 58483\}$
168. **(344, 29583, 29585)** $\Rightarrow 29585 - 344 = 171^2$, $S_{171 \times 171} := 5117859$, $T_{29241} := 29583^2$,
 $E := \{689, 691, \dots, 59167, 59169\}$ or $E := \{15309, 15310, \dots, 44548, 44549\}$
169. **(346, 29928, 29930)** $\Rightarrow 29930 - 346 = 172^2$, $S_{172 \times 172} := 5207472$, $T_{29584} := 29928^2$,
 $E := \{693, 695, \dots, 59857, 59859\}$
170. **(348, 30275, 30277)** $\Rightarrow 30277 - 348 = 173^2$, $S_{173 \times 173} := 5298125$, $T_{29929} := 30275^2$,
 $E := \{697, 699, \dots, 60551, 60553\}$ or $E := \{15661, 15662, \dots, 45588, 45589\}$
171. **(350, 30624, 30626)** $\Rightarrow 30626 - 350 = 174^2$, $S_{174 \times 174} := 5389824$, $T_{30276} := 30624^2$,
 $E := \{701, 703, \dots, 61249, 61251\}$
172. **(352, 30975, 30977)** $\Rightarrow 30977 - 352 = 175^2$, $S_{175 \times 175} := 5482575$, $T_{30625} := 30975^2$,
 $E := \{705, 707, \dots, 61951, 61953\}$ or $E := \{16017, 16018, \dots, 46640, 46641\}$
173. **(354, 31328, 31330)** $\Rightarrow 31330 - 354 = 176^2$, $S_{176 \times 176} := 5576384$, $T_{30976} := 31328^2$,
 $E := \{709, 711, \dots, 62657, 62659\}$
174. **(356, 31683, 31685)** $\Rightarrow 31685 - 356 = 177^2$, $S_{177 \times 177} := 5671257$, $T_{31329} := 31683^2$,
 $E := \{713, 715, \dots, 63367, 63369\}$ or $E := \{16377, 16378, \dots, 47704, 47705\}$
175. **(358, 32040, 32042)** $\Rightarrow 32042 - 358 = 178^2$, $S_{178 \times 178} := 5767200$, $T_{31684} := 32040^2$,
 $E := \{717, 719, \dots, 64081, 64083\}$
176. **(360, 32399, 32401)** $\Rightarrow 32401 - 360 = 179^2$, $S_{179 \times 179} := 5864219$, $T_{32041} := 32399^2$,
 $E := \{721, 723, \dots, 64799, 64801\}$ or $E := \{16741, 16742, \dots, 48780, 48781\}$
177. **(362, 32760, 32762)** $\Rightarrow 32762 - 362 = 180^2$, $S_{180 \times 180} := 5962320$, $T_{32400} := 32760^2$,
 $E := \{725, 727, \dots, 65521, 65523\}$
178. **(364, 33123, 33125)** $\Rightarrow 33125 - 364 = 181^2$, $S_{181 \times 181} := 6061509$, $T_{32761} := 33123^2$,
 $E := \{729, 731, \dots, 66247, 66249\}$ or $E := \{17109, 17110, \dots, 49868, 49869\}$
179. **(366, 33488, 33490)** $\Rightarrow 33490 - 366 = 182^2$, $S_{182 \times 182} := 6161792$, $T_{33124} := 33488^2$,
 $E := \{733, 735, \dots, 66977, 66979\}$
180. **(368, 33855, 33857)** $\Rightarrow 33857 - 368 = 183^2$, $S_{183 \times 183} := 6263175$, $T_{33489} := 33855^2$,
 $E := \{737, 739, \dots, 67711, 67713\}$ or $E := \{17481, 17482, \dots, 50968, 50969\}$
181. **(370, 34224, 34226)** $\Rightarrow 34226 - 370 = 184^2$, $S_{184 \times 184} := 6365664$, $T_{33856} := 34224^2$,
 $E := \{741, 743, \dots, 68449, 68451\}$
182. **(372, 34595, 34597)** $\Rightarrow 34597 - 372 = 185^2$, $S_{185 \times 185} := 6469265$, $T_{34225} := 34595^2$,
 $E := \{745, 747, \dots, 69191, 69193\}$ or $E := \{17857, 17858, \dots, 52080, 52081\}$
183. **(374, 34968, 34970)** $\Rightarrow 34970 - 374 = 186^2$, $S_{186 \times 186} := 6573984$, $T_{34596} := 34968^2$,
 $E := \{749, 751, \dots, 69937, 69939\}$

184. **(376, 35343, 35345)** $\Rightarrow 35345 - 376 = 187^2$, $S_{187 \times 187} := 6679827$, $T_{34969} := 35343^2$,
 $E := \{753, 755, \dots, 70687, 70689\}$ or $E := \{18237, 18238, \dots, 53204, 53205\}$
185. **(378, 35720, 35722)** $\Rightarrow 35722 - 378 = 188^2$, $S_{188 \times 188} := 6786800$, $T_{35344} := 35720^2$,
 $E := \{757, 759, \dots, 71441, 71443\}$
186. **(380, 36099, 36101)** $\Rightarrow 36101 - 380 = 189^2$, $S_{189 \times 189} := 6894909$, $T_{35721} := 36099^2$,
 $E := \{761, 763, \dots, 72199, 72201\}$ or $E := \{18621, 18622, \dots, 54340, 54341\}$
187. **(382, 36480, 36482)** $\Rightarrow 36482 - 382 = 190^2$, $S_{190 \times 190} := 7004160$, $T_{36100} := 36480^2$,
 $E := \{765, 767, \dots, 72961, 72963\}$
188. **(384, 36863, 36865)** $\Rightarrow 36865 - 384 = 191^2$, $S_{191 \times 191} := 7114559$, $T_{36481} := 36863^2$,
 $E := \{769, 771, \dots, 73727, 73729\}$ or $E := \{19009, 19010, \dots, 55488, 55489\}$
189. **(386, 37248, 37250)** $\Rightarrow 37250 - 386 = 192^2$, $S_{192 \times 192} := 7226112$, $T_{36864} := 37248^2$,
 $E := \{773, 775, \dots, 74497, 74499\}$
190. **(388, 37635, 37637)** $\Rightarrow 37637 - 388 = 193^2$, $S_{193 \times 193} := 7338825$, $T_{37249} := 37635^2$,
 $E := \{777, 779, \dots, 75271, 75273\}$ or $E := \{19401, 19402, \dots, 56648, 56649\}$
191. **(390, 38024, 38026)** $\Rightarrow 38026 - 390 = 194^2$, $S_{194 \times 194} := 7452704$, $T_{37636} := 38024^2$,
 $E := \{781, 783, \dots, 76049, 76051\}$
192. **(392, 38415, 38417)** $\Rightarrow 38417 - 392 = 195^2$, $S_{195 \times 195} := 7567755$, $T_{38025} := 38415^2$,
 $E := \{785, 787, \dots, 76831, 76833\}$ or $E := \{19797, 19798, \dots, 57820, 57821\}$
193. **(394, 38808, 38810)** $\Rightarrow 38810 - 394 = 196^2$, $S_{196 \times 196} := 7683984$, $T_{38416} := 38808^2$,
 $E := \{789, 791, \dots, 77617, 77619\}$
194. **(396, 39203, 39205)** $\Rightarrow 39205 - 396 = 197^2$, $S_{197 \times 197} := 7801397$, $T_{38809} := 39203^2$,
 $E := \{793, 795, \dots, 78407, 78409\}$ or $E := \{20197, 20198, \dots, 59004, 59005\}$
195. **(398, 39600, 39602)** $\Rightarrow 39602 - 398 = 198^2$, $S_{198 \times 198} := 7920000$, $T_{39204} := 39600^2$,
 $E := \{797, 799, \dots, 79201, 79203\}$
196. **(400, 39999, 40001)** $\Rightarrow 40001 - 400 = 199^2$, $S_{199 \times 199} := 8039799$, $T_{39601} := 39999^2$,
 $E := \{801, 803, \dots, 79999, 80001\}$ or $E := \{20601, 20602, \dots, 60200, 60201\}$
197. **(402, 40400, 40402)** $\Rightarrow 40402 - 402 = 200^2$, $S_{200 \times 200} := 8160800$, $T_{40000} := 40400^2$,
 $E := \{805, 807, \dots, 80801, 80803\}$
198. **(404, 40803, 40805)** $\Rightarrow 40805 - 404 = 201^2$, $S_{201 \times 201} := 8283009$, $T_{40401} := 40803^2$,
 $E := \{809, 811, \dots, 81607, 81609\}$ or $E := \{21009, 21010, \dots, 61408, 61409\}$
199. **(406, 41208, 41210)** $\Rightarrow 41210 - 406 = 202^2$, $S_{202 \times 202} := 8406432$, $T_{40804} := 41208^2$,
 $E := \{813, 815, \dots, 82417, 82419\}$
200. **(408, 41615, 41617)** $\Rightarrow 41617 - 408 = 203^2$, $S_{203 \times 203} := 8531075$, $T_{41209} := 41615^2$,
 $E := \{817, 819, \dots, 83231, 83233\}$ or $E := \{21421, 21422, \dots, 62628, 62629\}$

201. **(410, 42024, 42026)** $\Rightarrow 42026 - 410 = 204^2$, $S_{204 \times 204} := 8656944$, $T_{41616} := 42024^2$,
 $E := \{821, 823, \dots, 84049, 84051\}$
202. **(412, 42435, 42437)** $\Rightarrow 42437 - 412 = 205^2$, $S_{205 \times 205} := 8784045$, $T_{42025} := 42435^2$,
 $E := \{825, 827, \dots, 84871, 84873\}$ or $E := \{21837, 21838, \dots, 63860, 63861\}$
203. **(414, 42848, 42850)** $\Rightarrow 42850 - 414 = 206^2$, $S_{206 \times 206} := 8912384$, $T_{42436} := 42848^2$,
 $E := \{829, 831, \dots, 85697, 85699\}$
204. **(416, 43263, 43265)** $\Rightarrow 43265 - 416 = 207^2$, $S_{207 \times 207} := 9041967$, $T_{42849} := 43263^2$,
 $E := \{833, 835, \dots, 86527, 86529\}$ or $E := \{22257, 22258, \dots, 65104, 65105\}$
205. **(418, 43680, 43682)** $\Rightarrow 43682 - 418 = 208^2$, $S_{208 \times 208} := 9172800$, $T_{43264} := 43680^2$,
 $E := \{837, 839, \dots, 87361, 87363\}$
206. **(420, 44099, 44101)** $\Rightarrow 44101 - 420 = 209^2$, $S_{209 \times 209} := 9304889$, $T_{43681} := 44099^2$,
 $E := \{841, 843, \dots, 88199, 88201\}$ or $E := \{22681, 22682, \dots, 66360, 66361\}$
207. **(422, 44520, 44522)** $\Rightarrow 44522 - 422 = 210^2$, $S_{210 \times 210} := 9438240$, $T_{44100} := 44520^2$,
 $E := \{845, 847, \dots, 89041, 89043\}$
208. **(424, 44943, 44945)** $\Rightarrow 44945 - 424 = 211^2$, $S_{211 \times 211} := 9572859$, $T_{44521} := 44943^2$,
 $E := \{849, 851, \dots, 89887, 89889\}$ or $E := \{23109, 23110, \dots, 67628, 67629\}$
209. **(426, 45368, 45370)** $\Rightarrow 45370 - 426 = 212^2$, $S_{212 \times 212} := 9708752$, $T_{44944} := 45368^2$,
 $E := \{853, 855, \dots, 90737, 90739\}$
210. **(428, 45795, 45797)** $\Rightarrow 45797 - 428 = 213^2$, $S_{213 \times 213} := 9845925$, $T_{45369} := 45795^2$,
 $E := \{857, 859, \dots, 91591, 91593\}$ or $E := \{23541, 23542, \dots, 68908, 68909\}$
211. **(430, 46224, 46226)** $\Rightarrow 46226 - 430 = 214^2$, $S_{214 \times 214} := 9984384$, $T_{45796} := 46224^2$,
 $E := \{861, 863, \dots, 92449, 92451\}$
212. **(432, 46655, 46657)** $\Rightarrow 46657 - 432 = 215^2$, $S_{215 \times 215} := 10124135$, $T_{46225} := 46655^2$,
 $E := \{865, 867, \dots, 93311, 93313\}$ or $E := \{23977, 23978, \dots, 70200, 70201\}$
213. **(434, 47088, 47090)** $\Rightarrow 47090 - 434 = 216^2$, $S_{216 \times 216} := 10265184$, $T_{46656} := 47088^2$,
 $E := \{869, 871, \dots, 94177, 94179\}$
214. **(436, 47523, 47525)** $\Rightarrow 47525 - 436 = 217^2$, $S_{217 \times 217} := 10407537$, $T_{47089} := 47523^2$,
 $E := \{873, 875, \dots, 95047, 95049\}$ or $E := \{24417, 24418, \dots, 71504, 71505\}$
215. **(438, 47960, 47962)** $\Rightarrow 47962 - 438 = 218^2$, $S_{218 \times 218} := 10551200$, $T_{47524} := 47960^2$,
 $E := \{877, 879, \dots, 95921, 95923\}$
216. **(440, 48399, 48401)** $\Rightarrow 48401 - 440 = 219^2$, $S_{219 \times 219} := 10696179$, $T_{47961} := 48399^2$,
 $E := \{881, 883, \dots, 96799, 96801\}$ or $E := \{24861, 24862, \dots, 72820, 72821\}$
217. **(442, 48840, 48842)** $\Rightarrow 48842 - 442 = 220^2$, $S_{220 \times 220} := 10842480$, $T_{48400} := 48840^2$,
 $E := \{885, 887, \dots, 97681, 97683\}$

218. **(444, 49283, 49285)** $\Rightarrow 49285 - 444 = 221^2$, $S_{221 \times 221} := 10990109$, $T_{48841} := 49283^2$,
 $E := \{889, 891, \dots, 98567, 98569\}$ or $E := \{25309, 25310, \dots, 74148, 74149\}$
219. **(446, 49728, 49730)** $\Rightarrow 49730 - 446 = 222^2$, $S_{222 \times 222} := 11139072$, $T_{49284} := 49728^2$,
 $E := \{893, 895, \dots, 99457, 99459\}$
220. **(448, 50175, 50177)** $\Rightarrow 50177 - 448 = 223^2$, $S_{223 \times 223} := 11289375$, $T_{49729} := 50175^2$,
 $E := \{897, 899, \dots, 100351, 100353\}$ or $E := \{25761, 25762, \dots, 75488, 75489\}$
221. **(450, 50624, 50626)** $\Rightarrow 50626 - 450 = 224^2$, $S_{224 \times 224} := 11441024$, $T_{50176} := 50624^2$,
 $E := \{901, 903, \dots, 101249, 101251\}$
222. **(452, 51075, 51077)** $\Rightarrow 51077 - 452 = 225^2$, $S_{225 \times 225} := 11594025$, $T_{50625} := 51075^2$,
 $E := \{905, 907, \dots, 102151, 102153\}$ or $E := \{26217, 26218, \dots, 76840, 76841\}$
223. **(454, 51528, 51530)** $\Rightarrow 51530 - 454 = 226^2$, $S_{226 \times 226} := 11748384$, $T_{51076} := 51528^2$,
 $E := \{909, 911, \dots, 103057, 103059\}$
224. **(456, 51983, 51985)** $\Rightarrow 51985 - 456 = 227^2$, $S_{227 \times 227} := 11904107$, $T_{51529} := 51983^2$,
 $E := \{913, 915, \dots, 103967, 103969\}$ or $E := \{26677, 26678, \dots, 78204, 78205\}$
225. **(458, 52440, 52442)** $\Rightarrow 52442 - 458 = 228^2$, $S_{228 \times 228} := 12061200$, $T_{51984} := 52440^2$,
 $E := \{917, 919, \dots, 104881, 104883\}$
226. **(460, 52899, 52901)** $\Rightarrow 52901 - 460 = 229^2$, $S_{229 \times 229} := 12219669$, $T_{52441} := 52899^2$,
 $E := \{921, 923, \dots, 105799, 105801\}$ or $E := \{27141, 27142, \dots, 79580, 79581\}$
227. **(462, 53360, 53362)** $\Rightarrow 53362 - 462 = 230^2$, $S_{230 \times 230} := 12379520$, $T_{52900} := 53360^2$,
 $E := \{925, 927, \dots, 106721, 106723\}$
228. **(464, 53823, 53825)** $\Rightarrow 53825 - 464 = 231^2$, $S_{231 \times 231} := 12540759$, $T_{53361} := 53823^2$,
 $E := \{929, 931, \dots, 107647, 107649\}$ or $E := \{27609, 27610, \dots, 80968, 80969\}$
229. **(466, 54288, 54290)** $\Rightarrow 54290 - 466 = 232^2$, $S_{232 \times 232} := 12703392$, $T_{53824} := 54288^2$,
 $E := \{933, 935, \dots, 108577, 108579\}$
230. **(468, 54755, 54757)** $\Rightarrow 54757 - 468 = 233^2$, $S_{233 \times 233} := 12867425$, $T_{54289} := 54755^2$,
 $E := \{937, 939, \dots, 109511, 109513\}$ or $E := \{28081, 28082, \dots, 82368, 82369\}$
231. **(470, 55224, 55226)** $\Rightarrow 55226 - 470 = 234^2$, $S_{234 \times 234} := 13032864$, $T_{54756} := 55224^2$,
 $E := \{941, 943, \dots, 110449, 110451\}$
232. **(472, 55695, 55697)** $\Rightarrow 55697 - 472 = 235^2$, $S_{235 \times 235} := 13199715$, $T_{55225} := 55695^2$,
 $E := \{945, 947, \dots, 111391, 111393\}$ or $E := \{28557, 28558, \dots, 83780, 83781\}$
233. **(474, 56168, 56170)** $\Rightarrow 56170 - 474 = 236^2$, $S_{236 \times 236} := 13367984$, $T_{55696} := 56168^2$,
 $E := \{949, 951, \dots, 112337, 112339\}$
234. **(476, 56643, 56645)** $\Rightarrow 56645 - 476 = 237^2$, $S_{237 \times 237} := 13537677$, $T_{56169} := 56643^2$,
 $E := \{953, 955, \dots, 113287, 113289\}$ or $E := \{29037, 29038, \dots, 85204, 85205\}$

235. **(478, 57120, 57122)** $\Rightarrow 57122 - 478 = 238^2$, $S_{238 \times 238} := 13708800$, $T_{56644} := 57120^2$,
 $E := \{957, 959, \dots, 114241, 114243\}$
236. **(480, 57599, 57601)** $\Rightarrow 57601 - 480 = 239^2$, $S_{239 \times 239} := 13881359$, $T_{57121} := 57599^2$,
 $E := \{961, 963, \dots, 115199, 115201\}$ or $E := \{29521, 29522, \dots, 86640, 86641\}$
237. **(482, 58080, 58082)** $\Rightarrow 58082 - 482 = 240^2$, $S_{240 \times 240} := 14055360$, $T_{57600} := 58080^2$,
 $E := \{965, 967, \dots, 116161, 116163\}$
238. **(484, 58563, 58565)** $\Rightarrow 58565 - 484 = 241^2$, $S_{241 \times 241} := 14230809$, $T_{58081} := 58563^2$,
 $E := \{969, 971, \dots, 117127, 117129\}$ or $E := \{30009, 30010, \dots, 88088, 88089\}$
239. **(486, 59048, 59050)** $\Rightarrow 59050 - 486 = 242^2$, $S_{242 \times 242} := 14407712$, $T_{58564} := 59048^2$,
 $E := \{973, 975, \dots, 118097, 118099\}$
240. **(488, 59535, 59537)** $\Rightarrow 59537 - 488 = 243^2$, $S_{243 \times 243} := 14586075$, $T_{59049} := 59535^2$,
 $E := \{977, 979, \dots, 119071, 119073\}$ or $E := \{30501, 30502, \dots, 89548, 89549\}$
241. **(490, 60024, 60026)** $\Rightarrow 60026 - 490 = 244^2$, $S_{244 \times 244} := 14765904$, $T_{59536} := 60024^2$,
 $E := \{981, 983, \dots, 120049, 120051\}$
242. **(492, 60515, 60517)** $\Rightarrow 60517 - 492 = 245^2$, $S_{245 \times 245} := 14947205$, $T_{60025} := 60515^2$,
 $E := \{985, 987, \dots, 121031, 121033\}$ or $E := \{30997, 30998, \dots, 91020, 91021\}$
243. **(494, 61008, 61010)** $\Rightarrow 61010 - 494 = 246^2$, $S_{246 \times 246} := 15129984$, $T_{60516} := 61008^2$,
 $E := \{989, 991, \dots, 122017, 122019\}$
244. **(496, 61503, 61505)** $\Rightarrow 61505 - 496 = 247^2$, $S_{247 \times 247} := 15314247$, $T_{61009} := 61503^2$,
 $E := \{993, 995, \dots, 123007, 123009\}$ or $E := \{31497, 31498, \dots, 92504, 92505\}$
245. **(498, 62000, 62002)** $\Rightarrow 62002 - 498 = 248^2$, $S_{248 \times 248} := 15500000$, $T_{61504} := 62000^2$,
 $E := \{997, 999, \dots, 124001, 124003\}$
246. **(500, 62499, 62501)** $\Rightarrow 62501 - 500 = 249^2$, $S_{249 \times 249} := 15687249$, $T_{62001} := 62499^2$,
 $E := \{1001, 1003, \dots, 124999, 125001\}$ or $E := \{32001, 32002, \dots, 94000, 94001\}$
247. **(502, 63000, 63002)** $\Rightarrow 63002 - 502 = 250^2$, $S_{250 \times 250} := 15876000$, $T_{62500} := 63000^2$,
 $E := \{1005, 1007, \dots, 126001, 126003\}$
248. **(504, 63503, 63505)** $\Rightarrow 63505 - 504 = 251^2$, $S_{251 \times 251} := 16066259$, $T_{63001} := 63503^2$,
 $E := \{1009, 1011, \dots, 127007, 127009\}$ or $E := \{32509, 32510, \dots, 95508, 95509\}$
249. **(506, 64008, 64010)** $\Rightarrow 64010 - 506 = 252^2$, $S_{252 \times 252} := 16258032$, $T_{63504} := 64008^2$,
 $E := \{1013, 1015, \dots, 128017, 128019\}$
250. **(508, 64515, 64517)** $\Rightarrow 64517 - 508 = 253^2$, $S_{253 \times 253} := 16451325$, $T_{64009} := 64515^2$,
 $E := \{1017, 1019, \dots, 129031, 129033\}$ or $E := \{33021, 33022, \dots, 97028, 97029\}$
251. **(510, 65024, 65026)** $\Rightarrow 65026 - 510 = 254^2$, $S_{254 \times 254} := 16646144$, $T_{64516} := 65024^2$,
 $E := \{1021, 1023, \dots, 130049, 130051\}$

252. **(512, 65535, 65537)** $\Rightarrow 65537 - 512 = 255^2$, $S_{255 \times 255} := 16842495$, $T_{65025} := 65535^2$,
 $E := \{1025, 1027, \dots, 131071, 131073\}$ or $E := \{33537, 33538, \dots, 98560, 98561\}$
253. **(514, 66048, 66050)** $\Rightarrow 66050 - 514 = 256^2$, $S_{256 \times 256} := 17040384$, $T_{65536} := 66048^2$,
 $E := \{1029, 1031, \dots, 132097, 132099\}$
254. **(516, 66563, 66565)** $\Rightarrow 66565 - 516 = 257^2$, $S_{257 \times 257} := 17239817$, $T_{66049} := 66563^2$,
 $E := \{1033, 1035, \dots, 133127, 133129\}$ or $E := \{34057, 34058, \dots, 100104, 100105\}$
255. **(518, 67080, 67082)** $\Rightarrow 67082 - 518 = 258^2$, $S_{258 \times 258} := 17440800$, $T_{66564} := 67080^2$,
 $E := \{1037, 1039, \dots, 134161, 134163\}$
256. **(520, 67599, 67601)** $\Rightarrow 67601 - 520 = 259^2$, $S_{259 \times 259} := 17643339$, $T_{67081} := 67599^2$,
 $E := \{1041, 1043, \dots, 135199, 135201\}$ or $E := \{34581, 34582, \dots, 101660, 101661\}$
257. **(522, 68120, 68122)** $\Rightarrow 68122 - 522 = 260^2$, $S_{260 \times 260} := 17847440$, $T_{67600} := 68120^2$,
 $E := \{1045, 1047, \dots, 136241, 136243\}$
258. **(524, 68643, 68645)** $\Rightarrow 68645 - 524 = 261^2$, $S_{261 \times 261} := 18053109$, $T_{68121} := 68643^2$,
 $E := \{1049, 1051, \dots, 137287, 137289\}$ or $E := \{35109, 35110, \dots, 103228, 103229\}$
259. **(526, 69168, 69170)** $\Rightarrow 69170 - 526 = 262^2$, $S_{262 \times 262} := 18260352$, $T_{68644} := 69168^2$,
 $E := \{1053, 1055, \dots, 138337, 138339\}$
260. **(528, 69695, 69697)** $\Rightarrow 69697 - 528 = 263^2$, $S_{263 \times 263} := 18469175$, $T_{69169} := 69695^2$,
 $E := \{1057, 1059, \dots, 139391, 139393\}$ or $E := \{35641, 35642, \dots, 104808, 104809\}$
261. **(530, 70224, 70226)** $\Rightarrow 70226 - 530 = 264^2$, $S_{264 \times 264} := 18679584$, $T_{69696} := 70224^2$,
 $E := \{1061, 1063, \dots, 140449, 140451\}$
262. **(532, 70755, 70757)** $\Rightarrow 70757 - 532 = 265^2$, $S_{265 \times 265} := 18891585$, $T_{70225} := 70755^2$,
 $E := \{1065, 1067, \dots, 141511, 141513\}$ or $E := \{36177, 36178, \dots, 106400, 106401\}$
263. **(534, 71288, 71290)** $\Rightarrow 71290 - 534 = 266^2$, $S_{266 \times 266} := 19105184$, $T_{70756} := 71288^2$,
 $E := \{1069, 1071, \dots, 142577, 142579\}$
264. **(536, 71823, 71825)** $\Rightarrow 71825 - 536 = 267^2$, $S_{267 \times 267} := 19320387$, $T_{71289} := 71823^2$,
 $E := \{1073, 1075, \dots, 143647, 143649\}$ or $E := \{36717, 36718, \dots, 108004, 108005\}$
265. **(538, 72360, 72362)** $\Rightarrow 72362 - 538 = 268^2$, $S_{268 \times 268} := 19537200$, $T_{71824} := 72360^2$,
 $E := \{1077, 1079, \dots, 144721, 144723\}$
266. **(540, 72899, 72901)** $\Rightarrow 72901 - 540 = 269^2$, $S_{269 \times 269} := 19755629$, $T_{72361} := 72899^2$,
 $E := \{1081, 1083, \dots, 145799, 145801\}$ or $E := \{37261, 37262, \dots, 109620, 109621\}$
267. **(542, 73440, 73442)** $\Rightarrow 73442 - 542 = 270^2$, $S_{270 \times 270} := 19975680$, $T_{72900} := 73440^2$,
 $E := \{1085, 1087, \dots, 146881, 146883\}$
268. **(544, 73983, 73985)** $\Rightarrow 73985 - 544 = 271^2$, $S_{271 \times 271} := 20197359$, $T_{73441} := 73983^2$,
 $E := \{1089, 1091, \dots, 147967, 147969\}$ or $E := \{37809, 37810, \dots, 111248, 111249\}$

269. **(546, 74528, 74530)** $\Rightarrow 74530 - 546 = 272^2$, $S_{272 \times 272} := 20420672$, $T_{73984} := 74528^2$,
 $E := \{1093, 1095, \dots, 149057, 149059\}$
270. **(548, 75075, 75077)** $\Rightarrow 75077 - 548 = 273^2$, $S_{273 \times 273} := 20645625$, $T_{74529} := 75075^2$,
 $E := \{1097, 1099, \dots, 150151, 150153\}$ or $E := \{38361, 38362, \dots, 112888, 112889\}$
271. **(550, 75624, 75626)** $\Rightarrow 75626 - 550 = 274^2$, $S_{274 \times 274} := 20872224$, $T_{75076} := 75624^2$,
 $E := \{1101, 1103, \dots, 151249, 151251\}$
272. **(552, 76175, 76177)** $\Rightarrow 76177 - 552 = 275^2$, $S_{275 \times 275} := 21100475$, $T_{75625} := 76175^2$,
 $E := \{1105, 1107, \dots, 152351, 152353\}$ or $E := \{38917, 38918, \dots, 114540, 114541\}$
273. **(554, 76728, 76730)** $\Rightarrow 76730 - 554 = 276^2$, $S_{276 \times 276} := 21330384$, $T_{76176} := 76728^2$,
 $E := \{1109, 1111, \dots, 153457, 153459\}$
274. **(556, 77283, 77285)** $\Rightarrow 77285 - 556 = 277^2$, $S_{277 \times 277} := 21561957$, $T_{76729} := 77283^2$,
 $E := \{1113, 1115, \dots, 154567, 154569\}$ or $E := \{39477, 39478, \dots, 116204, 116205\}$
275. **(558, 77840, 77842)** $\Rightarrow 77842 - 558 = 278^2$, $S_{278 \times 278} := 21795200$, $T_{77284} := 77840^2$,
 $E := \{1117, 1119, \dots, 155681, 155683\}$
276. **(560, 78399, 78401)** $\Rightarrow 78401 - 560 = 279^2$, $S_{279 \times 279} := 22030119$, $T_{77841} := 78399^2$,
 $E := \{1121, 1123, \dots, 156799, 156801\}$ or $E := \{40041, 40042, \dots, 117880, 117881\}$
277. **(562, 78960, 78962)** $\Rightarrow 78962 - 562 = 280^2$, $S_{280 \times 280} := 22266720$, $T_{78400} := 78960^2$,
 $E := \{1125, 1127, \dots, 157921, 157923\}$
278. **(564, 79523, 79525)** $\Rightarrow 79525 - 564 = 281^2$, $S_{281 \times 281} := 22505009$, $T_{78961} := 79523^2$,
 $E := \{1129, 1131, \dots, 159047, 159049\}$ or $E := \{40609, 40610, \dots, 119568, 119569\}$
279. **(566, 80088, 80090)** $\Rightarrow 80090 - 566 = 282^2$, $S_{282 \times 282} := 22744992$, $T_{79524} := 80088^2$,
 $E := \{1133, 1135, \dots, 160177, 160179\}$
280. **(568, 80655, 80657)** $\Rightarrow 80657 - 568 = 283^2$, $S_{283 \times 283} := 22986675$, $T_{80089} := 80655^2$,
 $E := \{1137, 1139, \dots, 161311, 161313\}$ or $E := \{41181, 41182, \dots, 121268, 121269\}$
281. **(570, 81224, 81226)** $\Rightarrow 81226 - 570 = 284^2$, $S_{284 \times 284} := 23230064$, $T_{80656} := 81224^2$,
 $E := \{1141, 1143, \dots, 162449, 162451\}$
282. **(572, 81795, 81797)** $\Rightarrow 81797 - 572 = 285^2$, $S_{285 \times 285} := 23475165$, $T_{81225} := 81795^2$,
 $E := \{1145, 1147, \dots, 163591, 163593\}$ or $E := \{41757, 41758, \dots, 122980, 122981\}$
283. **(574, 82368, 82370)** $\Rightarrow 82370 - 574 = 286^2$, $S_{286 \times 286} := 23721984$, $T_{81796} := 82368^2$,
 $E := \{1149, 1151, \dots, 164737, 164739\}$
284. **(576, 82943, 82945)** $\Rightarrow 82945 - 576 = 287^2$, $S_{287 \times 287} := 23970527$, $T_{82369} := 82943^2$,
 $E := \{1153, 1155, \dots, 165887, 165889\}$ or $E := \{42337, 42338, \dots, 124704, 124705\}$
285. **(578, 83520, 83522)** $\Rightarrow 83522 - 578 = 288^2$, $S_{288 \times 288} := 24220800$, $T_{82944} := 83520^2$,
 $E := \{1157, 1159, \dots, 167041, 167043\}$

286. **(580, 84099, 84101)** $\Rightarrow 84101 - 580 = 289^2$, $S_{289 \times 289} := 24472809$, $T_{83521} := 84099^2$,
 $E := \{1161, 1163, \dots, 168199, 168201\}$ or $E := \{42921, 42922, \dots, 126440, 126441\}$
287. **(582, 84680, 84682)** $\Rightarrow 84682 - 582 = 290^2$, $S_{290 \times 290} := 24726560$, $T_{84100} := 84680^2$,
 $E := \{1165, 1167, \dots, 169361, 169363\}$
288. **(584, 85263, 85265)** $\Rightarrow 85265 - 584 = 291^2$, $S_{291 \times 291} := 24982059$, $T_{84681} := 85263^2$,
 $E := \{1169, 1171, \dots, 170527, 170529\}$ or $E := \{43509, 43510, \dots, 128188, 128189\}$
289. **(586, 85848, 85850)** $\Rightarrow 85850 - 586 = 292^2$, $S_{292 \times 292} := 25239312$, $T_{85264} := 85848^2$,
 $E := \{1173, 1175, \dots, 171697, 171699\}$
290. **(588, 86435, 86437)** $\Rightarrow 86437 - 588 = 293^2$, $S_{293 \times 293} := 25498325$, $T_{85849} := 86435^2$,
 $E := \{1177, 1179, \dots, 172871, 172873\}$ or $E := \{44101, 44102, \dots, 129948, 129949\}$
291. **(590, 87024, 87026)** $\Rightarrow 87026 - 590 = 294^2$, $S_{294 \times 294} := 25759104$, $T_{86436} := 87024^2$,
 $E := \{1181, 1183, \dots, 174049, 174051\}$
292. **(592, 87615, 87617)** $\Rightarrow 87617 - 592 = 295^2$, $S_{295 \times 295} := 26021655$, $T_{87025} := 87615^2$,
 $E := \{1185, 1187, \dots, 175231, 175233\}$ or $E := \{44697, 44698, \dots, 131720, 131721\}$
293. **(594, 88208, 88210)** $\Rightarrow 88210 - 594 = 296^2$, $S_{296 \times 296} := 26285984$, $T_{87616} := 88208^2$,
 $E := \{1189, 1191, \dots, 176417, 176419\}$
294. **(596, 88803, 88805)** $\Rightarrow 88805 - 596 = 297^2$, $S_{297 \times 297} := 26552097$, $T_{88209} := 88803^2$,
 $E := \{1193, 1195, \dots, 177607, 177609\}$ or $E := \{45297, 45298, \dots, 133504, 133505\}$
295. **(598, 89400, 89402)** $\Rightarrow 89402 - 598 = 298^2$, $S_{298 \times 298} := 26820000$, $T_{88804} := 89400^2$,
 $E := \{1197, 1199, \dots, 178801, 178803\}$
296. **(600, 89999, 90001)** $\Rightarrow 90001 - 600 = 299^2$, $S_{299 \times 299} := 27089699$, $T_{89401} := 89999^2$,
 $E := \{1201, 1203, \dots, 179999, 180001\}$ or $E := \{45901, 45902, \dots, 135300, 135301\}$
297. **(602, 90600, 90602)** $\Rightarrow 90602 - 602 = 300^2$, $S_{300 \times 300} := 27361200$, $T_{90000} := 90600^2$,
 $E := \{1205, 1207, \dots, 181201, 181203\}$
298. **(604, 91203, 91205)** $\Rightarrow 91205 - 604 = 301^2$, $S_{301 \times 301} := 27634509$, $T_{90601} := 91203^2$,
 $E := \{1209, 1211, \dots, 182407, 182409\}$ or $E := \{46509, 46510, \dots, 137108, 137109\}$
299. **(606, 91808, 91810)** $\Rightarrow 91810 - 606 = 302^2$, $S_{302 \times 302} := 27909632$, $T_{91204} := 91808^2$,
 $E := \{1213, 1215, \dots, 183617, 183619\}$
300. **(608, 92415, 92417)** $\Rightarrow 92417 - 608 = 303^2$, $S_{303 \times 303} := 28186575$, $T_{91809} := 92415^2$,
 $E := \{1217, 1219, \dots, 184831, 184833\}$ or $E := \{47121, 47122, \dots, 138928, 138929\}$
301. **(610, 93024, 93026)** $\Rightarrow 93026 - 610 = 304^2$, $S_{304 \times 304} := 28465344$, $T_{92416} := 93024^2$,
 $E := \{1221, 1223, \dots, 186049, 186051\}$
302. **(612, 93635, 93637)** $\Rightarrow 93637 - 612 = 305^2$, $S_{305 \times 305} := 28745945$, $T_{93025} := 93635^2$,
 $E := \{1225, 1227, \dots, 187271, 187273\}$ or $E := \{47737, 47738, \dots, 140760, 140761\}$

303. **(614, 94248, 94250)** $\Rightarrow 94250 - 614 = 306^2$, $S_{306 \times 306} := 29028384$, $T_{93636} := 94248^2$,
 $E := \{1229, 1231, \dots, 188497, 188499\}$
304. **(616, 94863, 94865)** $\Rightarrow 94865 - 616 = 307^2$, $S_{307 \times 307} := 29312667$, $T_{94249} := 94863^2$,
 $E := \{1233, 1235, \dots, 189727, 189729\}$ or $E := \{48357, 48358, \dots, 142604, 142605\}$
305. **(618, 95480, 95482)** $\Rightarrow 95482 - 618 = 308^2$, $S_{308 \times 308} := 29598800$, $T_{94864} := 95480^2$,
 $E := \{1237, 1239, \dots, 190961, 190963\}$
306. **(620, 96099, 96101)** $\Rightarrow 96101 - 620 = 309^2$, $S_{309 \times 309} := 29886789$, $T_{95481} := 96099^2$,
 $E := \{1241, 1243, \dots, 192199, 192201\}$ or $E := \{48981, 48982, \dots, 144460, 144461\}$
307. **(622, 96720, 96722)** $\Rightarrow 96722 - 622 = 310^2$, $S_{310 \times 310} := 30176640$, $T_{96100} := 96720^2$,
 $E := \{1245, 1247, \dots, 193441, 193443\}$
308. **(624, 97343, 97345)** $\Rightarrow 97345 - 624 = 311^2$, $S_{311 \times 311} := 30468359$, $T_{96721} := 97343^2$,
 $E := \{1249, 1251, \dots, 194687, 194689\}$ or $E := \{49609, 49610, \dots, 146328, 146329\}$
309. **(626, 97968, 97970)** $\Rightarrow 97970 - 626 = 312^2$, $S_{312 \times 312} := 30761952$, $T_{97344} := 97968^2$,
 $E := \{1253, 1255, \dots, 195937, 195939\}$
310. **(628, 98595, 98597)** $\Rightarrow 98597 - 628 = 313^2$, $S_{313 \times 313} := 31057425$, $T_{97969} := 98595^2$,
 $E := \{1257, 1259, \dots, 197191, 197193\}$ or $E := \{50241, 50242, \dots, 148208, 148209\}$
311. **(630, 99224, 99226)** $\Rightarrow 99226 - 630 = 314^2$, $S_{314 \times 314} := 31354784$, $T_{98596} := 99224^2$,
 $E := \{1261, 1263, \dots, 198449, 198451\}$
312. **(632, 99855, 99857)** $\Rightarrow 99857 - 632 = 315^2$, $S_{315 \times 315} := 31654035$, $T_{99225} := 99855^2$,
 $E := \{1265, 1267, \dots, 199711, 199713\}$ or $E := \{50877, 50878, \dots, 150100, 150101\}$
313. **(634, 100488, 100490)** $\Rightarrow 100490 - 634 = 316^2$, $S_{316 \times 316} := 31955184$, $T_{99856} := 100488^2$,
 $E := \{1269, 1271, \dots, 200977, 200979\}$
314. **(636, 101123, 101125)** $\Rightarrow 101125 - 636 = 317^2$, $S_{317 \times 317} := 32258237$, $T_{100489} := 101123^2$,
 $E := \{1273, 1275, \dots, 202247, 202249\}$ or $E := \{51517, 51518, \dots, 152004, 152005\}$
315. **(638, 101760, 101762)** $\Rightarrow 101762 - 638 = 318^2$, $S_{318 \times 318} := 32563200$, $T_{101124} := 101760^2$,
 $E := \{1277, 1279, \dots, 203521, 203523\}$
316. **(640, 102399, 102401)** $\Rightarrow 102401 - 640 = 319^2$, $S_{319 \times 319} := 32870079$, $T_{101761} := 102399^2$,
 $E := \{1281, 1283, \dots, 204799, 204801\}$ or $E := \{52161, 52162, \dots, 153920, 153921\}$
317. **(642, 103040, 103042)** $\Rightarrow 103042 - 642 = 320^2$, $S_{320 \times 320} := 33178880$, $T_{102400} := 103040^2$,
 $E := \{1285, 1287, \dots, 206081, 206083\}$
318. **(644, 103683, 103685)** $\Rightarrow 103685 - 644 = 321^2$, $S_{321 \times 321} := 33489609$, $T_{103041} := 103683^2$,
 $E := \{1289, 1291, \dots, 207367, 207369\}$ or $E := \{52809, 52810, \dots, 155848, 155849\}$
319. **(646, 104328, 104330)** $\Rightarrow 104330 - 646 = 322^2$, $S_{322 \times 322} := 33802272$, $T_{103684} := 104328^2$,
 $E := \{1293, 1295, \dots, 208657, 208659\}$

320. **(648, 104975, 104977)** $\Rightarrow 104977 - 648 = 323^2$, $S_{323 \times 323} := 34116875$, $T_{104329} := 104975^2$,
 $E := \{1297, 1299, \dots, 209951, 209953\}$ or $E := \{53461, 53462, \dots, 157788, 157789\}$
321. **(650, 105624, 105626)** $\Rightarrow 105626 - 650 = 324^2$, $S_{324 \times 324} := 34433424$, $T_{104976} := 105624^2$,
 $E := \{1301, 1303, \dots, 211249, 211251\}$
322. **(652, 106275, 106277)** $\Rightarrow 106277 - 652 = 325^2$, $S_{325 \times 325} := 34751925$, $T_{105625} := 106275^2$,
 $E := \{1305, 1307, \dots, 212551, 212553\}$ or $E := \{54117, 54118, \dots, 159740, 159741\}$
323. **(654, 106928, 106930)** $\Rightarrow 106930 - 654 = 326^2$, $S_{326 \times 326} := 35072384$, $T_{106276} := 106928^2$,
 $E := \{1309, 1311, \dots, 213857, 213859\}$
324. **(656, 107583, 107585)** $\Rightarrow 107585 - 656 = 327^2$, $S_{327 \times 327} := 35394807$, $T_{106929} := 107583^2$,
 $E := \{1313, 1315, \dots, 215167, 215169\}$ or $E := \{54777, 54778, \dots, 161704, 161705\}$
325. **(658, 108240, 108242)** $\Rightarrow 108242 - 658 = 328^2$, $S_{328 \times 328} := 35719200$, $T_{107584} := 108240^2$,
 $E := \{1317, 1319, \dots, 216481, 216483\}$
326. **(660, 108899, 108901)** $\Rightarrow 108901 - 660 = 329^2$, $S_{329 \times 329} := 36045569$, $T_{108241} := 108899^2$,
 $E := \{1321, 1323, \dots, 217799, 217801\}$ or $E := \{55441, 55442, \dots, 163680, 163681\}$
327. **(662, 109560, 109562)** $\Rightarrow 109562 - 662 = 330^2$, $S_{330 \times 330} := 36373920$, $T_{108900} := 109560^2$,
 $E := \{1325, 1327, \dots, 219121, 219123\}$
328. **(664, 110223, 110225)** $\Rightarrow 110225 - 664 = 331^2$, $S_{331 \times 331} := 36704259$, $T_{109561} := 110223^2$,
 $E := \{1329, 1331, \dots, 220447, 220449\}$ or $E := \{56109, 56110, \dots, 165668, 165669\}$
329. **(666, 110888, 110890)** $\Rightarrow 110890 - 666 = 332^2$, $S_{332 \times 332} := 37036592$, $T_{110224} := 110888^2$,
 $E := \{1333, 1335, \dots, 221777, 221779\}$
330. **(668, 111555, 111557)** $\Rightarrow 111557 - 668 = 333^2$, $S_{333 \times 333} := 37370925$, $T_{110889} := 111555^2$,
 $E := \{1337, 1339, \dots, 223111, 223113\}$ or $E := \{56781, 56782, \dots, 167668, 167669\}$
331. **(670, 112224, 112226)** $\Rightarrow 112226 - 670 = 334^2$, $S_{334 \times 334} := 37707264$, $T_{111556} := 112224^2$,
 $E := \{1341, 1343, \dots, 224449, 224451\}$
332. **(672, 112895, 112897)** $\Rightarrow 112897 - 672 = 335^2$, $S_{335 \times 335} := 38045615$, $T_{112225} := 112895^2$,
 $E := \{1345, 1347, \dots, 225791, 225793\}$ or $E := \{57457, 57458, \dots, 169680, 169681\}$
333. **(674, 113568, 113570)** $\Rightarrow 113570 - 674 = 336^2$, $S_{336 \times 336} := 38385984$, $T_{112896} := 113568^2$,
 $E := \{1349, 1351, \dots, 227137, 227139\}$
334. **(676, 114243, 114245)** $\Rightarrow 114245 - 676 = 337^2$, $S_{337 \times 337} := 38728377$, $T_{113569} := 114243^2$,
 $E := \{1353, 1355, \dots, 228487, 228489\}$ or $E := \{58137, 58138, \dots, 171704, 171705\}$
335. **(678, 114920, 114922)** $\Rightarrow 114922 - 678 = 338^2$, $S_{338 \times 338} := 39072800$, $T_{114244} := 114920^2$,
 $E := \{1357, 1359, \dots, 229841, 229843\}$
336. **(680, 115599, 115601)** $\Rightarrow 115601 - 680 = 339^2$, $S_{339 \times 339} := 39419259$, $T_{114921} := 115599^2$,
 $E := \{1361, 1363, \dots, 231199, 231201\}$ or $E := \{58821, 58822, \dots, 173740, 173741\}$

337. **(682, 116280, 116282)** $\Rightarrow 116282 - 682 = 340^2$, $S_{340 \times 340} := 39767760$, $T_{115600} := 116280^2$,
 $E := \{1365, 1367, \dots, 232561, 232563\}$
338. **(684, 116963, 116965)** $\Rightarrow 116965 - 684 = 341^2$, $S_{341 \times 341} := 40118309$, $T_{116281} := 116963^2$,
 $E := \{1369, 1371, \dots, 233927, 233929\}$ or $E := \{59509, 59510, \dots, 175788, 175789\}$
339. **(686, 117648, 117650)** $\Rightarrow 117650 - 686 = 342^2$, $S_{342 \times 342} := 40470912$, $T_{116964} := 117648^2$,
 $E := \{1373, 1375, \dots, 235297, 235299\}$
340. **(688, 118335, 118337)** $\Rightarrow 118337 - 688 = 343^2$, $S_{343 \times 343} := 40825575$, $T_{117649} := 118335^2$,
 $E := \{1377, 1379, \dots, 236671, 236673\}$ or $E := \{60201, 60202, \dots, 177848, 177849\}$
341. **(690, 119024, 119026)** $\Rightarrow 119026 - 690 = 344^2$, $S_{344 \times 344} := 41182304$, $T_{118336} := 119024^2$,
 $E := \{1381, 1383, \dots, 238049, 238051\}$
342. **(692, 119715, 119717)** $\Rightarrow 119717 - 692 = 345^2$, $S_{345 \times 345} := 41541105$, $T_{119025} := 119715^2$,
 $E := \{1385, 1387, \dots, 239431, 239433\}$ or $E := \{60897, 60898, \dots, 179920, 179921\}$
343. **(694, 120408, 120410)** $\Rightarrow 120410 - 694 = 346^2$, $S_{346 \times 346} := 41901984$, $T_{119716} := 120408^2$,
 $E := \{1389, 1391, \dots, 240817, 240819\}$
344. **(696, 121103, 121105)** $\Rightarrow 121105 - 696 = 347^2$, $S_{347 \times 347} := 42264947$, $T_{120409} := 121103^2$,
 $E := \{1393, 1395, \dots, 242207, 242209\}$ or $E := \{61597, 61598, \dots, 182004, 182005\}$
345. **(698, 121800, 121802)** $\Rightarrow 121802 - 698 = 348^2$, $S_{348 \times 348} := 42630000$, $T_{121104} := 121800^2$,
 $E := \{1397, 1399, \dots, 243601, 243603\}$
346. **(700, 122499, 122501)** $\Rightarrow 122501 - 700 = 349^2$, $S_{349 \times 349} := 42997149$, $T_{121801} := 122499^2$,
 $E := \{1401, 1403, \dots, 244999, 245001\}$ or $E := \{62301, 62302, \dots, 184100, 184101\}$
347. **(702, 123200, 123202)** $\Rightarrow 123202 - 702 = 350^2$, $S_{350 \times 350} := 43366400$, $T_{122500} := 123200^2$,
 $E := \{1405, 1407, \dots, 246401, 246403\}$
348. **(704, 123903, 123905)** $\Rightarrow 123905 - 704 = 351^2$, $S_{351 \times 351} := 43737759$, $T_{123201} := 123903^2$,
 $E := \{1409, 1411, \dots, 247807, 247809\}$ or $E := \{63009, 63010, \dots, 186208, 186209\}$
349. **(706, 124608, 124610)** $\Rightarrow 124610 - 706 = 352^2$, $S_{352 \times 352} := 44111232$, $T_{123904} := 124608^2$,
 $E := \{1413, 1415, \dots, 249217, 249219\}$
350. **(708, 125315, 125317)** $\Rightarrow 125317 - 708 = 353^2$, $S_{353 \times 353} := 44486825$, $T_{124609} := 125315^2$,
 $E := \{1417, 1419, \dots, 250631, 250633\}$ or $E := \{63721, 63722, \dots, 188328, 188329\}$
351. **(710, 126024, 126026)** $\Rightarrow 126026 - 710 = 354^2$, $S_{354 \times 354} := 44864544$, $T_{125316} := 126024^2$,
 $E := \{1421, 1423, \dots, 252049, 252051\}$
352. **(712, 126735, 126737)** $\Rightarrow 126737 - 712 = 355^2$, $S_{355 \times 355} := 45244395$, $T_{126025} := 126735^2$,
 $E := \{1425, 1427, \dots, 253471, 253473\}$ or $E := \{64437, 64438, \dots, 190460, 190461\}$
353. **(714, 127448, 127450)** $\Rightarrow 127450 - 714 = 356^2$, $S_{356 \times 356} := 45626384$, $T_{126736} := 127448^2$,
 $E := \{1429, 1431, \dots, 254897, 254899\}$

354. **(716, 128163, 128165)** $\Rightarrow 128165 - 716 = 357^2$, $S_{357 \times 357} := 46010517$, $T_{127449} := 128163^2$,
 $E := \{1433, 1435, \dots, 256327, 256329\}$ or $E := \{65157, 65158, \dots, 192604, 192605\}$
355. **(718, 128880, 128882)** $\Rightarrow 128882 - 718 = 358^2$, $S_{358 \times 358} := 46396800$, $T_{128164} := 128880^2$,
 $E := \{1437, 1439, \dots, 257761, 257763\}$
356. **(720, 129599, 129601)** $\Rightarrow 129601 - 720 = 359^2$, $S_{359 \times 359} := 46785239$, $T_{128881} := 129599^2$,
 $E := \{1441, 1443, \dots, 259199, 259201\}$ or $E := \{65881, 65882, \dots, 194760, 194761\}$
357. **(722, 130320, 130322)** $\Rightarrow 130322 - 722 = 360^2$, $S_{360 \times 360} := 47175840$, $T_{129600} := 130320^2$,
 $E := \{1445, 1447, \dots, 260641, 260643\}$
358. **(724, 131043, 131045)** $\Rightarrow 131045 - 724 = 361^2$, $S_{361 \times 361} := 47568609$, $T_{130321} := 131043^2$,
 $E := \{1449, 1451, \dots, 262087, 262089\}$ or $E := \{66609, 66610, \dots, 196928, 196929\}$
359. **(726, 131768, 131770)** $\Rightarrow 131770 - 726 = 362^2$, $S_{362 \times 362} := 47963552$, $T_{131044} := 131768^2$,
 $E := \{1453, 1455, \dots, 263537, 263539\}$
360. **(728, 132495, 132497)** $\Rightarrow 132497 - 728 = 363^2$, $S_{363 \times 363} := 48360675$, $T_{131769} := 132495^2$,
 $E := \{1457, 1459, \dots, 264991, 264993\}$ or $E := \{67341, 67342, \dots, 199108, 199109\}$
361. **(730, 133224, 133226)** $\Rightarrow 133226 - 730 = 364^2$, $S_{364 \times 364} := 48759984$, $T_{132496} := 133224^2$,
 $E := \{1461, 1463, \dots, 266449, 266451\}$
362. **(732, 133955, 133957)** $\Rightarrow 133957 - 732 = 365^2$, $S_{365 \times 365} := 49161485$, $T_{133225} := 133955^2$,
 $E := \{1465, 1467, \dots, 267911, 267913\}$ or $E := \{68077, 68078, \dots, 201300, 201301\}$
363. **(734, 134688, 134690)** $\Rightarrow 134690 - 734 = 366^2$, $S_{366 \times 366} := 49565184$, $T_{133956} := 134688^2$,
 $E := \{1469, 1471, \dots, 269377, 269379\}$
364. **(736, 135423, 135425)** $\Rightarrow 135425 - 736 = 367^2$, $S_{367 \times 367} := 49971087$, $T_{134689} := 135423^2$,
 $E := \{1473, 1475, \dots, 270847, 270849\}$ or $E := \{68817, 68818, \dots, 203504, 203505\}$
365. **(738, 136160, 136162)** $\Rightarrow 136162 - 738 = 368^2$, $S_{368 \times 368} := 50379200$, $T_{135424} := 136160^2$,
 $E := \{1477, 1479, \dots, 272321, 272323\}$
366. **(740, 136899, 136901)** $\Rightarrow 136901 - 740 = 369^2$, $S_{369 \times 369} := 50789529$, $T_{136161} := 136899^2$,
 $E := \{1481, 1483, \dots, 273799, 273801\}$ or $E := \{69561, 69562, \dots, 205720, 205721\}$
367. **(742, 137640, 137642)** $\Rightarrow 137642 - 742 = 370^2$, $S_{370 \times 370} := 51202080$, $T_{136900} := 137640^2$,
 $E := \{1485, 1487, \dots, 275281, 275283\}$
368. **(744, 138383, 138385)** $\Rightarrow 138385 - 744 = 371^2$, $S_{371 \times 371} := 51616859$, $T_{137641} := 138383^2$,
 $E := \{1489, 1491, \dots, 276767, 276769\}$ or $E := \{70309, 70310, \dots, 207948, 207949\}$
369. **(746, 139128, 139130)** $\Rightarrow 139130 - 746 = 372^2$, $S_{372 \times 372} := 52033872$, $T_{138384} := 139128^2$,
 $E := \{1493, 1495, \dots, 278257, 278259\}$
370. **(748, 139875, 139877)** $\Rightarrow 139877 - 748 = 373^2$, $S_{373 \times 373} := 52453125$, $T_{139129} := 139875^2$,
 $E := \{1497, 1499, \dots, 279751, 279753\}$ or $E := \{71061, 71062, \dots, 210188, 210189\}$

371. **(750, 140624, 140626)** $\Rightarrow 140626 - 750 = 374^2$, $S_{374 \times 374} := 52874624$, $T_{139876} := 140624^2$,
 $E := \{1501, 1503, \dots, 281249, 281251\}$
372. **(752, 141375, 141377)** $\Rightarrow 141377 - 752 = 375^2$, $S_{375 \times 375} := 53298375$, $T_{140625} := 141375^2$,
 $E := \{1505, 1507, \dots, 282751, 282753\}$ or $E := \{71817, 71818, \dots, 212440, 212441\}$
373. **(754, 142128, 142130)** $\Rightarrow 142130 - 754 = 376^2$, $S_{376 \times 376} := 53724384$, $T_{141376} := 142128^2$,
 $E := \{1509, 1511, \dots, 284257, 284259\}$
374. **(756, 142883, 142885)** $\Rightarrow 142885 - 756 = 377^2$, $S_{377 \times 377} := 54152657$, $T_{142129} := 142883^2$,
 $E := \{1513, 1515, \dots, 285767, 285769\}$ or $E := \{72577, 72578, \dots, 214704, 214705\}$
375. **(758, 143640, 143642)** $\Rightarrow 143642 - 758 = 378^2$, $S_{378 \times 378} := 54583200$, $T_{142884} := 143640^2$,
 $E := \{1517, 1519, \dots, 287281, 287283\}$
376. **(760, 144399, 144401)** $\Rightarrow 144401 - 760 = 379^2$, $S_{379 \times 379} := 55016019$, $T_{143641} := 144399^2$,
 $E := \{1521, 1523, \dots, 288799, 288801\}$ or $E := \{73341, 73342, \dots, 216980, 216981\}$
377. **(762, 145160, 145162)** $\Rightarrow 145162 - 762 = 380^2$, $S_{380 \times 380} := 55451120$, $T_{144400} := 145160^2$,
 $E := \{1525, 1527, \dots, 290321, 290323\}$
378. **(764, 145923, 145925)** $\Rightarrow 145925 - 764 = 381^2$, $S_{381 \times 381} := 55888509$, $T_{145161} := 145923^2$,
 $E := \{1529, 1531, \dots, 291847, 291849\}$ or $E := \{74109, 74110, \dots, 219268, 219269\}$
379. **(766, 146688, 146690)** $\Rightarrow 146690 - 766 = 382^2$, $S_{382 \times 382} := 56328192$, $T_{145924} := 146688^2$,
 $E := \{1533, 1535, \dots, 293377, 293379\}$
380. **(768, 147455, 147457)** $\Rightarrow 147457 - 768 = 383^2$, $S_{383 \times 383} := 56770175$, $T_{146689} := 147455^2$,
 $E := \{1537, 1539, \dots, 294911, 294913\}$ or $E := \{74881, 74882, \dots, 221568, 221569\}$
381. **(770, 148224, 148226)** $\Rightarrow 148226 - 770 = 384^2$, $S_{384 \times 384} := 57214464$, $T_{147456} := 148224^2$,
 $E := \{1541, 1543, \dots, 296449, 296451\}$
382. **(772, 148995, 148997)** $\Rightarrow 148997 - 772 = 385^2$, $S_{385 \times 385} := 57661065$, $T_{148225} := 148995^2$,
 $E := \{1545, 1547, \dots, 297991, 297993\}$ or $E := \{75657, 75658, \dots, 223880, 223881\}$
383. **(774, 149768, 149770)** $\Rightarrow 149770 - 774 = 386^2$, $S_{386 \times 386} := 58109984$, $T_{148996} := 149768^2$,
 $E := \{1549, 1551, \dots, 299537, 299539\}$
384. **(776, 150543, 150545)** $\Rightarrow 150545 - 776 = 387^2$, $S_{387 \times 387} := 58561227$, $T_{149769} := 150543^2$,
 $E := \{1553, 1555, \dots, 301087, 301089\}$ or $E := \{76437, 76438, \dots, 226204, 226205\}$
385. **(778, 151320, 151322)** $\Rightarrow 151322 - 778 = 388^2$, $S_{388 \times 388} := 59014800$, $T_{150544} := 151320^2$,
 $E := \{1557, 1559, \dots, 302641, 302643\}$
386. **(780, 152099, 152101)** $\Rightarrow 152101 - 780 = 389^2$, $S_{389 \times 389} := 59470709$, $T_{151321} := 152099^2$,
 $E := \{1561, 1563, \dots, 304199, 304201\}$ or $E := \{77221, 77222, \dots, 228540, 228541\}$
387. **(782, 152880, 152882)** $\Rightarrow 152882 - 782 = 390^2$, $S_{390 \times 390} := 59928960$, $T_{152100} := 152880^2$,
 $E := \{1565, 1567, \dots, 305761, 305763\}$

388. **(784, 153663, 153665)** $\Rightarrow 153665 - 784 = 391^2$, $S_{391 \times 391} := 60389559$, $T_{152881} := 153663^2$,
 $E := \{1569, 1571, \dots, 307327, 307329\}$ or $E := \{78009, 78010, \dots, 230888, 230889\}$
389. **(786, 154448, 154450)** $\Rightarrow 154450 - 786 = 392^2$, $S_{392 \times 392} := 60852512$, $T_{153664} := 154448^2$,
 $E := \{1573, 1575, \dots, 308897, 308899\}$
390. **(788, 155235, 155237)** $\Rightarrow 155237 - 788 = 393^2$, $S_{393 \times 393} := 61317825$, $T_{154449} := 155235^2$,
 $E := \{1577, 1579, \dots, 310471, 310473\}$ or $E := \{78801, 78802, \dots, 233248, 233249\}$
391. **(790, 156024, 156026)** $\Rightarrow 156026 - 790 = 394^2$, $S_{394 \times 394} := 61785504$, $T_{155236} := 156024^2$,
 $E := \{1581, 1583, \dots, 312049, 312051\}$
392. **(792, 156815, 156817)** $\Rightarrow 156817 - 792 = 395^2$, $S_{395 \times 395} := 62255555$, $T_{156025} := 156815^2$,
 $E := \{1585, 1587, \dots, 313631, 313633\}$ or $E := \{79597, 79598, \dots, 235620, 235621\}$
393. **(794, 157608, 157610)** $\Rightarrow 157610 - 794 = 396^2$, $S_{396 \times 396} := 62727984$, $T_{156816} := 157608^2$,
 $E := \{1589, 1591, \dots, 315217, 315219\}$
394. **(796, 158403, 158405)** $\Rightarrow 158405 - 796 = 397^2$, $S_{397 \times 397} := 63202797$, $T_{157609} := 158403^2$,
 $E := \{1593, 1595, \dots, 316807, 316809\}$ or $E := \{80397, 80398, \dots, 238004, 238005\}$
395. **(798, 159200, 159202)** $\Rightarrow 159202 - 798 = 398^2$, $S_{398 \times 398} := 63680000$, $T_{158404} := 159200^2$,
 $E := \{1597, 1599, \dots, 318401, 318403\}$
396. **(800, 159999, 160001)** $\Rightarrow 160001 - 800 = 399^2$, $S_{399 \times 399} := 64159599$, $T_{159201} := 159999^2$,
 $E := \{1601, 1603, \dots, 319999, 320001\}$ or $E := \{81201, 81202, \dots, 240400, 240401\}$
397. **(802, 160800, 160802)** $\Rightarrow 160802 - 802 = 400^2$, $S_{400 \times 400} := 64641600$, $T_{160000} := 160800^2$,
 $E := \{1605, 1607, \dots, 321601, 321603\}$
398. **(804, 161603, 161605)** $\Rightarrow 161605 - 804 = 401^2$, $S_{401 \times 401} := 65126009$, $T_{160801} := 161603^2$,
 $E := \{1609, 1611, \dots, 323207, 323209\}$ or $E := \{82009, 82010, \dots, 242808, 242809\}$
399. **(806, 162408, 162410)** $\Rightarrow 162410 - 806 = 402^2$, $S_{402 \times 402} := 65612832$, $T_{161604} := 162408^2$,
 $E := \{1613, 1615, \dots, 324817, 324819\}$
400. **(808, 163215, 163217)** $\Rightarrow 163217 - 808 = 403^2$, $S_{403 \times 403} := 66102075$, $T_{162409} := 163215^2$,
 $E := \{1617, 1619, \dots, 326431, 326433\}$ or $E := \{82821, 82822, \dots, 245228, 245229\}$
401. **(810, 164024, 164026)** $\Rightarrow 164026 - 810 = 404^2$, $S_{404 \times 404} := 66593744$, $T_{163216} := 164024^2$,
 $E := \{1621, 1623, \dots, 328049, 328051\}$
402. **(812, 164835, 164837)** $\Rightarrow 164837 - 812 = 405^2$, $S_{405 \times 405} := 67087845$, $T_{164025} := 164835^2$,
 $E := \{1625, 1627, \dots, 329671, 329673\}$ or $E := \{83637, 83638, \dots, 247660, 247661\}$
403. **(814, 165648, 165650)** $\Rightarrow 165650 - 814 = 406^2$, $S_{406 \times 406} := 67584384$, $T_{164836} := 165648^2$,
 $E := \{1629, 1631, \dots, 331297, 331299\}$
404. **(816, 166463, 166465)** $\Rightarrow 166465 - 816 = 407^2$, $S_{407 \times 407} := 68083367$, $T_{165649} := 166463^2$,
 $E := \{1633, 1635, \dots, 332927, 332929\}$ or $E := \{84457, 84458, \dots, 250104, 250105\}$

405. **(818, 167280, 167282)** $\Rightarrow 167282 - 818 = 408^2$, $S_{408 \times 408} := 68584800$, $T_{166464} := 167280^2$,
 $E := \{1637, 1639, \dots, 334561, 334563\}$
406. **(820, 168099, 168101)** $\Rightarrow 168101 - 820 = 409^2$, $S_{409 \times 409} := 69088689$, $T_{167281} := 168099^2$,
 $E := \{1641, 1643, \dots, 336199, 336201\}$ or $E := \{85281, 85282, \dots, 252560, 252561\}$
407. **(822, 168920, 168922)** $\Rightarrow 168922 - 822 = 410^2$, $S_{410 \times 410} := 69595040$, $T_{168100} := 168920^2$,
 $E := \{1645, 1647, \dots, 337841, 337843\}$
408. **(824, 169743, 169745)** $\Rightarrow 169745 - 824 = 411^2$, $S_{411 \times 411} := 70103859$, $T_{168921} := 169743^2$,
 $E := \{1649, 1651, \dots, 339487, 339489\}$ or $E := \{86109, 86110, \dots, 255028, 255029\}$
409. **(826, 170568, 170570)** $\Rightarrow 170570 - 826 = 412^2$, $S_{412 \times 412} := 70615152$, $T_{169744} := 170568^2$,
 $E := \{1653, 1655, \dots, 341137, 341139\}$
410. **(828, 171395, 171397)** $\Rightarrow 171397 - 828 = 413^2$, $S_{413 \times 413} := 71128925$, $T_{170569} := 171395^2$,
 $E := \{1657, 1659, \dots, 342791, 342793\}$ or $E := \{86941, 86942, \dots, 257508, 257509\}$
411. **(830, 172224, 172226)** $\Rightarrow 172226 - 830 = 414^2$, $S_{414 \times 414} := 71645184$, $T_{171396} := 172224^2$,
 $E := \{1661, 1663, \dots, 344449, 344451\}$
412. **(832, 173055, 173057)** $\Rightarrow 173057 - 832 = 415^2$, $S_{415 \times 415} := 72163935$, $T_{172225} := 173055^2$,
 $E := \{1665, 1667, \dots, 346111, 346113\}$ or $E := \{87777, 87778, \dots, 260000, 260001\}$
413. **(834, 173888, 173890)** $\Rightarrow 173890 - 834 = 416^2$, $S_{416 \times 416} := 72685184$, $T_{173056} := 173888^2$,
 $E := \{1669, 1671, \dots, 347777, 347779\}$
414. **(836, 174723, 174725)** $\Rightarrow 174725 - 836 = 417^2$, $S_{417 \times 417} := 73208937$, $T_{173889} := 174723^2$,
 $E := \{1673, 1675, \dots, 349447, 349449\}$ or $E := \{88617, 88618, \dots, 262504, 262505\}$
415. **(838, 175560, 175562)** $\Rightarrow 175562 - 838 = 418^2$, $S_{418 \times 418} := 73735200$, $T_{174724} := 175560^2$,
 $E := \{1677, 1679, \dots, 351121, 351123\}$
416. **(840, 176399, 176401)** $\Rightarrow 176401 - 840 = 419^2$, $S_{419 \times 419} := 74263979$, $T_{175561} := 176399^2$,
 $E := \{1681, 1683, \dots, 352799, 352801\}$ or $E := \{89461, 89462, \dots, 265020, 265021\}$
417. **(842, 177240, 177242)** $\Rightarrow 177242 - 842 = 420^2$, $S_{420 \times 420} := 74795280$, $T_{176400} := 177240^2$,
 $E := \{1685, 1687, \dots, 354481, 354483\}$
418. **(844, 178083, 178085)** $\Rightarrow 178085 - 844 = 421^2$, $S_{421 \times 421} := 75329109$, $T_{177241} := 178083^2$,
 $E := \{1689, 1691, \dots, 356167, 356169\}$ or $E := \{90309, 90310, \dots, 267548, 267549\}$
419. **(846, 178928, 178930)** $\Rightarrow 178930 - 846 = 422^2$, $S_{422 \times 422} := 75865472$, $T_{178084} := 178928^2$,
 $E := \{1693, 1695, \dots, 357857, 357859\}$
420. **(848, 179775, 179777)** $\Rightarrow 179777 - 848 = 423^2$, $S_{423 \times 423} := 76404375$, $T_{178929} := 179775^2$,
 $E := \{1697, 1699, \dots, 359551, 359553\}$ or $E := \{91161, 91162, \dots, 270088, 270089\}$
421. **(850, 180624, 180626)** $\Rightarrow 180626 - 850 = 424^2$, $S_{424 \times 424} := 76945824$, $T_{179776} := 180624^2$,
 $E := \{1701, 1703, \dots, 361249, 361251\}$

422. **(852, 181475, 181477)** $\Rightarrow 181477 - 852 = 425^2$, $S_{425 \times 425} := 77489825$, $T_{180625} := 181475^2$,
 $E := \{1705, 1707, \dots, 362951, 362953\}$ or $E := \{92017, 92018, \dots, 272640, 272641\}$
423. **(854, 182328, 182330)** $\Rightarrow 182330 - 854 = 426^2$, $S_{426 \times 426} := 78036384$, $T_{181476} := 182328^2$,
 $E := \{1709, 1711, \dots, 364657, 364659\}$
424. **(856, 183183, 183185)** $\Rightarrow 183185 - 856 = 427^2$, $S_{427 \times 427} := 78585507$, $T_{182329} := 183183^2$,
 $E := \{1713, 1715, \dots, 366367, 366369\}$ or $E := \{92877, 92878, \dots, 275204, 275205\}$
425. **(858, 184040, 184042)** $\Rightarrow 184042 - 858 = 428^2$, $S_{428 \times 428} := 79137200$, $T_{183184} := 184040^2$,
 $E := \{1717, 1719, \dots, 368081, 368083\}$
426. **(860, 184899, 184901)** $\Rightarrow 184901 - 860 = 429^2$, $S_{429 \times 429} := 79691469$, $T_{184041} := 184899^2$,
 $E := \{1721, 1723, \dots, 369799, 369801\}$ or $E := \{93741, 93742, \dots, 277780, 277781\}$
427. **(862, 185760, 185762)** $\Rightarrow 185762 - 862 = 430^2$, $S_{430 \times 430} := 80248320$, $T_{184900} := 185760^2$,
 $E := \{1725, 1727, \dots, 371521, 371523\}$
428. **(864, 186623, 186625)** $\Rightarrow 186625 - 864 = 431^2$, $S_{431 \times 431} := 80807759$, $T_{185761} := 186623^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 373247, 373249\}$ or $E := \{94609, 94610, \dots, 280368, 280369\}$
429. **(866, 187488, 187490)** $\Rightarrow 187490 - 866 = 432^2$, $S_{432 \times 432} := 81369792$, $T_{186624} := 187488^2$,
 $E := \{1733, 1735, \dots, 374977, 374979\}$
430. **(868, 188355, 188357)** $\Rightarrow 188357 - 868 = 433^2$, $S_{433 \times 433} := 81934425$, $T_{187489} := 188355^2$,
 $E := \{1737, 1739, \dots, 376711, 376713\}$ or $E := \{95481, 95482, \dots, 282968, 282969\}$
431. **(870, 189224, 189226)** $\Rightarrow 189226 - 870 = 434^2$, $S_{434 \times 434} := 82501664$, $T_{188356} := 189224^2$,
 $E := \{1741, 1743, \dots, 378449, 378451\}$
432. **(872, 190095, 190097)** $\Rightarrow 190097 - 872 = 435^2$, $S_{435 \times 435} := 83071515$, $T_{189225} := 190095^2$,
 $E := \{1745, 1747, \dots, 380191, 380193\}$ or $E := \{96357, 96358, \dots, 285580, 285581\}$
433. **(874, 190968, 190970)** $\Rightarrow 190970 - 874 = 436^2$, $S_{436 \times 436} := 83643984$, $T_{190096} := 190968^2$,
 $E := \{1749, 1751, \dots, 381937, 381939\}$
434. **(876, 191843, 191845)** $\Rightarrow 191845 - 876 = 437^2$, $S_{437 \times 437} := 84219077$, $T_{190969} := 191843^2$,
 $E := \{1753, 1755, \dots, 383687, 383689\}$ or $E := \{97237, 97238, \dots, 288204, 288205\}$
435. **(878, 192720, 192722)** $\Rightarrow 192722 - 878 = 438^2$, $S_{438 \times 438} := 84796800$, $T_{191844} := 192720^2$,
 $E := \{1757, 1759, \dots, 385441, 385443\}$
436. **(880, 193599, 193601)** $\Rightarrow 193601 - 880 = 439^2$, $S_{439 \times 439} := 85377159$, $T_{192721} := 193599^2$,
 $E := \{1761, 1763, \dots, 387199, 387201\}$ or $E := \{98121, 98122, \dots, 290840, 290841\}$
437. **(882, 194480, 194482)** $\Rightarrow 194482 - 882 = 440^2$, $S_{440 \times 440} := 85960160$, $T_{193600} := 194480^2$,
 $E := \{1765, 1767, \dots, 388961, 388963\}$
438. **(884, 195363, 195365)** $\Rightarrow 195365 - 884 = 441^2$, $S_{441 \times 441} := 86545809$, $T_{194481} := 195363^2$,
 $E := \{1769, 1771, \dots, 390727, 390729\}$ or $E := \{99009, 99010, \dots, 293488, 293489\}$

439. **(886, 196248, 196250)** $\Rightarrow 196250 - 886 = 442^2$, $S_{442 \times 442} := 87134112$, $T_{195364} := 196248^2$,
 $E := \{1773, 1775, \dots, 392497, 392499\}$
440. **(888, 197135, 197137)** $\Rightarrow 197137 - 888 = 443^2$, $S_{443 \times 443} := 87725075$, $T_{196249} := 197135^2$,
 $E := \{1777, 1779, \dots, 394271, 394273\}$ or $E := \{99901, 99902, \dots, 296148, 296149\}$
441. **(890, 198024, 198026)** $\Rightarrow 198026 - 890 = 444^2$, $S_{444 \times 444} := 88318704$, $T_{197136} := 198024^2$,
 $E := \{1781, 1783, \dots, 396049, 396051\}$
442. **(892, 198915, 198917)** $\Rightarrow 198917 - 892 = 445^2$, $S_{445 \times 445} := 88915005$, $T_{198025} := 198915^2$,
 $E := \{1785, 1787, \dots, 397831, 397833\}$ or $E := \{100797, 100798, \dots, 298820, 298821\}$
443. **(894, 199808, 199810)** $\Rightarrow 199810 - 894 = 446^2$, $S_{446 \times 446} := 89513984$, $T_{198916} := 199808^2$,
 $E := \{1789, 1791, \dots, 399617, 399619\}$
444. **(896, 200703, 200705)** $\Rightarrow 200705 - 896 = 447^2$, $S_{447 \times 447} := 90115647$, $T_{199809} := 200703^2$,
 $E := \{1793, 1795, \dots, 401407, 401409\}$ or $E := \{101697, 101698, \dots, 301504, 301505\}$
445. **(898, 201600, 201602)** $\Rightarrow 201602 - 898 = 448^2$, $S_{448 \times 448} := 90720000$, $T_{200704} := 201600^2$,
 $E := \{1797, 1799, \dots, 403201, 403203\}$
446. **(900, 202499, 202501)** $\Rightarrow 202501 - 900 = 449^2$, $S_{449 \times 449} := 91327049$, $T_{201601} := 202499^2$,
 $E := \{1801, 1803, \dots, 404999, 405001\}$ or $E := \{102601, 102602, \dots, 304200, 304201\}$
447. **(902, 203400, 203402)** $\Rightarrow 203402 - 902 = 450^2$, $S_{450 \times 450} := 91936800$, $T_{202500} := 203400^2$,
 $E := \{1805, 1807, \dots, 406801, 406803\}$
448. **(904, 204303, 204305)** $\Rightarrow 204305 - 904 = 451^2$, $S_{451 \times 451} := 92549259$, $T_{203401} := 204303^2$,
 $E := \{1809, 1811, \dots, 408607, 408609\}$ or $E := \{103509, 103510, \dots, 306908, 306909\}$
449. **(906, 205208, 205210)** $\Rightarrow 205210 - 906 = 452^2$, $S_{452 \times 452} := 93164432$, $T_{204304} := 205208^2$,
 $E := \{1813, 1815, \dots, 410417, 410419\}$
450. **(908, 206115, 206117)** $\Rightarrow 206117 - 908 = 453^2$, $S_{453 \times 453} := 93782325$, $T_{205209} := 206115^2$,
 $E := \{1817, 1819, \dots, 412231, 412233\}$ or $E := \{104421, 104422, \dots, 309628, 309629\}$
451. **(910, 207024, 207026)** $\Rightarrow 207026 - 910 = 454^2$, $S_{454 \times 454} := 94402944$, $T_{206116} := 207024^2$,
 $E := \{1821, 1823, \dots, 414049, 414051\}$
452. **(912, 207935, 207937)** $\Rightarrow 207937 - 912 = 455^2$, $S_{455 \times 455} := 95026295$, $T_{207025} := 207935^2$,
 $E := \{1825, 1827, \dots, 415871, 415873\}$ or $E := \{105337, 105338, \dots, 312360, 312361\}$
453. **(914, 208848, 208850)** $\Rightarrow 208850 - 914 = 456^2$, $S_{456 \times 456} := 95652384$, $T_{207936} := 208848^2$,
 $E := \{1829, 1831, \dots, 417697, 417699\}$
454. **(916, 209763, 209765)** $\Rightarrow 209765 - 916 = 457^2$, $S_{457 \times 457} := 96281217$, $T_{208849} := 209763^2$,
 $E := \{1833, 1835, \dots, 419527, 419529\}$ or $E := \{106257, 106258, \dots, 315104, 315105\}$
455. **(918, 210680, 210682)** $\Rightarrow 210682 - 918 = 458^2$, $S_{458 \times 458} := 96912800$, $T_{209764} := 210680^2$,
 $E := \{1837, 1839, \dots, 421361, 421363\}$

456. **(920, 211599, 211601)** $\Rightarrow 211601 - 920 = 459^2$, $S_{459 \times 459} := 97547139$, $T_{210681} := 211599^2$,
 $E := \{1841, 1843, \dots, 423199, 423201\}$ or $E := \{107181, 107182, \dots, 317860, 317861\}$
457. **(922, 212520, 212522)** $\Rightarrow 212522 - 922 = 460^2$, $S_{460 \times 460} := 98184240$, $T_{211600} := 212520^2$,
 $E := \{1845, 1847, \dots, 425041, 425043\}$
458. **(924, 213443, 213445)** $\Rightarrow 213445 - 924 = 461^2$, $S_{461 \times 461} := 98824109$, $T_{212521} := 213443^2$,
 $E := \{1849, 1851, \dots, 426887, 426889\}$ or $E := \{108109, 108110, \dots, 320628, 320629\}$
459. **(926, 214368, 214370)** $\Rightarrow 214370 - 926 = 462^2$, $S_{462 \times 462} := 99466752$, $T_{213444} := 214368^2$,
 $E := \{1853, 1855, \dots, 428737, 428739\}$
460. **(928, 215295, 215297)** $\Rightarrow 215297 - 928 = 463^2$, $S_{463 \times 463} := 100112175$, $T_{214369} := 215295^2$,
 $E := \{1857, 1859, \dots, 430591, 430593\}$ or $E := \{109041, 109042, \dots, 323408, 323409\}$
461. **(930, 216224, 216226)** $\Rightarrow 216226 - 930 = 464^2$, $S_{464 \times 464} := 100760384$, $T_{215296} := 216224^2$,
 $E := \{1861, 1863, \dots, 432449, 432451\}$
462. **(932, 217155, 217157)** $\Rightarrow 217157 - 932 = 465^2$, $S_{465 \times 465} := 101411385$, $T_{216225} := 217155^2$,
 $E := \{1865, 1867, \dots, 434311, 434313\}$ or $E := \{109977, 109978, \dots, 326200, 326201\}$
463. **(934, 218088, 218090)** $\Rightarrow 218090 - 934 = 466^2$, $S_{466 \times 466} := 102065184$, $T_{217156} := 218088^2$,
 $E := \{1869, 1871, \dots, 436177, 436179\}$
464. **(936, 219023, 219025)** $\Rightarrow 219025 - 936 = 467^2$, $S_{467 \times 467} := 102721787$, $T_{218089} := 219023^2$,
 $E := \{1873, 1875, \dots, 438047, 438049\}$ or $E := \{110917, 110918, \dots, 329004, 329005\}$
465. **(938, 219960, 219962)** $\Rightarrow 219962 - 938 = 468^2$, $S_{468 \times 468} := 103381200$, $T_{219024} := 219960^2$,
 $E := \{1877, 1879, \dots, 439921, 439923\}$
466. **(940, 220899, 220901)** $\Rightarrow 220901 - 940 = 469^2$, $S_{469 \times 469} := 104043429$, $T_{219961} := 220899^2$,
 $E := \{1881, 1883, \dots, 441799, 441801\}$ or $E := \{111861, 111862, \dots, 331820, 331821\}$
467. **(942, 221840, 221842)** $\Rightarrow 221842 - 942 = 470^2$, $S_{470 \times 470} := 104708480$, $T_{220900} := 221840^2$,
 $E := \{1885, 1887, \dots, 443681, 443683\}$
468. **(944, 222783, 222785)** $\Rightarrow 222785 - 944 = 471^2$, $S_{471 \times 471} := 105376359$, $T_{221841} := 222783^2$,
 $E := \{1889, 1891, \dots, 445567, 445569\}$ or $E := \{112809, 112810, \dots, 334648, 334649\}$
469. **(946, 223728, 223730)** $\Rightarrow 223730 - 946 = 472^2$, $S_{472 \times 472} := 106047072$, $T_{222784} := 223728^2$,
 $E := \{1893, 1895, \dots, 447457, 447459\}$
470. **(948, 224675, 224677)** $\Rightarrow 224677 - 948 = 473^2$, $S_{473 \times 473} := 106720625$, $T_{223729} := 224675^2$,
 $E := \{1897, 1899, \dots, 449351, 449353\}$ or $E := \{113761, 113762, \dots, 337488, 337489\}$
471. **(950, 225624, 225626)** $\Rightarrow 225626 - 950 = 474^2$, $S_{474 \times 474} := 107397024$, $T_{224676} := 225624^2$,
 $E := \{1901, 1903, \dots, 451249, 451251\}$
472. **(952, 226575, 226577)** $\Rightarrow 226577 - 952 = 475^2$, $S_{475 \times 475} := 108076275$, $T_{225625} := 226575^2$,
 $E := \{1905, 1907, \dots, 453151, 453153\}$ or $E := \{114717, 114718, \dots, 340340, 340341\}$

473. **(954, 227528, 227530)** $\Rightarrow 227530 - 954 = 476^2$, $S_{476 \times 476} := 108758384$, $T_{226576} := 227528^2$,
 $E := \{1909, 1911, \dots, 455057, 455059\}$
474. **(956, 228483, 228485)** $\Rightarrow 228485 - 956 = 477^2$, $S_{477 \times 477} := 109443357$, $T_{227529} := 228483^2$,
 $E := \{1913, 1915, \dots, 456967, 456969\}$ or $E := \{115677, 115678, \dots, 343204, 343205\}$
475. **(958, 229440, 229442)** $\Rightarrow 229442 - 958 = 478^2$, $S_{478 \times 478} := 110131200$, $T_{228484} := 229440^2$,
 $E := \{1917, 1919, \dots, 458881, 458883\}$
476. **(960, 230399, 230401)** $\Rightarrow 230401 - 960 = 479^2$, $S_{479 \times 479} := 110821919$, $T_{229441} := 230399^2$,
 $E := \{1921, 1923, \dots, 460799, 460801\}$ or $E := \{116641, 116642, \dots, 346080, 346081\}$
477. **(962, 231360, 231362)** $\Rightarrow 231362 - 962 = 480^2$, $S_{480 \times 480} := 111515520$, $T_{230400} := 231360^2$,
 $E := \{1925, 1927, \dots, 462721, 462723\}$
478. **(964, 232323, 232325)** $\Rightarrow 232325 - 964 = 481^2$, $S_{481 \times 481} := 112212009$, $T_{231361} := 232323^2$,
 $E := \{1929, 1931, \dots, 464647, 464649\}$ or $E := \{117609, 117610, \dots, 348968, 348969\}$
479. **(966, 233288, 233290)** $\Rightarrow 233290 - 966 = 482^2$, $S_{482 \times 482} := 112911392$, $T_{232324} := 233288^2$,
 $E := \{1933, 1935, \dots, 466577, 466579\}$
480. **(968, 234255, 234257)** $\Rightarrow 234257 - 968 = 483^2$, $S_{483 \times 483} := 113613675$, $T_{233289} := 234255^2$,
 $E := \{1937, 1939, \dots, 468511, 468513\}$ or $E := \{118581, 118582, \dots, 351868, 351869\}$
481. **(970, 235224, 235226)** $\Rightarrow 235226 - 970 = 484^2$, $S_{484 \times 484} := 114318864$, $T_{234256} := 235224^2$,
 $E := \{1941, 1943, \dots, 470449, 470451\}$
482. **(972, 236195, 236197)** $\Rightarrow 236197 - 972 = 485^2$, $S_{485 \times 485} := 115026965$, $T_{235225} := 236195^2$,
 $E := \{1945, 1947, \dots, 472391, 472393\}$ or $E := \{119557, 119558, \dots, 354780, 354781\}$
483. **(974, 237168, 237170)** $\Rightarrow 237170 - 974 = 486^2$, $S_{486 \times 486} := 115737984$, $T_{236196} := 237168^2$,
 $E := \{1949, 1951, \dots, 474337, 474339\}$
484. **(976, 238143, 238145)** $\Rightarrow 238145 - 976 = 487^2$, $S_{487 \times 487} := 116451927$, $T_{237169} := 238143^2$,
 $E := \{1953, 1955, \dots, 476287, 476289\}$ or $E := \{120537, 120538, \dots, 357704, 357705\}$
485. **(978, 239120, 239122)** $\Rightarrow 239122 - 978 = 488^2$, $S_{488 \times 488} := 117168800$, $T_{238144} := 239120^2$,
 $E := \{1957, 1959, \dots, 478241, 478243\}$
486. **(980, 240099, 240101)** $\Rightarrow 240101 - 980 = 489^2$, $S_{489 \times 489} := 117888609$, $T_{239121} := 240099^2$,
 $E := \{1961, 1963, \dots, 480199, 480201\}$ or $E := \{121521, 121522, \dots, 360640, 360641\}$
487. **(982, 241080, 241082)** $\Rightarrow 241082 - 982 = 490^2$, $S_{490 \times 490} := 118611360$, $T_{240100} := 241080^2$,
 $E := \{1965, 1967, \dots, 482161, 482163\}$
488. **(984, 242063, 242065)** $\Rightarrow 242065 - 984 = 491^2$, $S_{491 \times 491} := 119337059$, $T_{241081} := 242063^2$,
 $E := \{1969, 1971, \dots, 484127, 484129\}$ or $E := \{122509, 122510, \dots, 363588, 363589\}$
489. **(986, 243048, 243050)** $\Rightarrow 243050 - 986 = 492^2$, $S_{492 \times 492} := 120065712$, $T_{242064} := 243048^2$,
 $E := \{1973, 1975, \dots, 486097, 486099\}$

490. **(988, 244035, 244037)** $\Rightarrow 244037 - 988 = 493^2$, $S_{493 \times 493} := 120797325$, $T_{243049} := 244035^2$,
 $E := \{1977, 1979, \dots, 488071, 488073\}$ or $E := \{123501, 123502, \dots, 366548, 366549\}$
491. **(990, 245024, 245026)** $\Rightarrow 245026 - 990 = 494^2$, $S_{494 \times 494} := 121531904$, $T_{244036} := 245024^2$,
 $E := \{1981, 1983, \dots, 490049, 490051\}$
492. **(992, 246015, 246017)** $\Rightarrow 246017 - 992 = 495^2$, $S_{495 \times 495} := 122269455$, $T_{245025} := 246015^2$,
 $E := \{1985, 1987, \dots, 492031, 492033\}$ or $E := \{124497, 124498, \dots, 369520, 369521\}$
493. **(994, 247008, 247010)** $\Rightarrow 247010 - 994 = 496^2$, $S_{496 \times 496} := 123009984$, $T_{246016} := 247008^2$,
 $E := \{1989, 1991, \dots, 494017, 494019\}$
494. **(996, 248003, 248005)** $\Rightarrow 248005 - 996 = 497^2$, $S_{497 \times 497} := 123753497$, $T_{247009} := 248003^2$,
 $E := \{1993, 1995, \dots, 496007, 496009\}$ or $E := \{125497, 125498, \dots, 372504, 372505\}$
495. **(998, 249000, 249002)** $\Rightarrow 249002 - 998 = 498^2$, $S_{498 \times 498} := 124500000$, $T_{248004} := 249000^2$,
 $E := \{1997, 1999, \dots, 498001, 498003\}$
496. **(1000, 249999, 250001)** $\Rightarrow 250001 - 1000 = 499^2$, $S_{499 \times 499} := 125249499$, $T_{249001} := 249999^2$,
 $E := \{2001, 2003, \dots, 499999, 500001\}$ or $E := \{126501, 126502, \dots, 375500, 375501\}$

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